

The Importance of Accurate Boundary Condition in Obtaining Reliable Shearing Stresses on a Torsional Finite Element Simulation

Jairo Aparecido Martins
Research & Development
DESCH North America
Cambridge, Ontario, Canada
Jairo.martins@desch.com

Estaner Claro Romão
Department of Environmental Engineering
Lorena School of Engineering, University of São Paulo
Lorena, São Paulo, Brasil
estaner23@usp.br

Received: 21 December 2021 | Accepted: 3 January 2022

Abstract- Many combustion engines and electric motors drive machines or equipment by turning a shaft and thus producing work. As a relevant part of a machine principle, torque transference deserves deep analysis regarding the techniques that determine precisely the Finite Element (FE) boundary conditions that are to be applied. This work presents a shaft loaded with a torque that causes torsion and results in shear stresses in the shaft material. In this context, when designing and calculating a shaft to transfer torque, virtual analysis like FE Analysis (FEA) must replicate the reality as accurately as possible. Indeed, slight changes in load and constraint in a virtual simulation can produce considerably different shear stresses and unrealistic results. This paper aims to demonstrate how distinct boundary conditions for the same torque transference can result in very different results when a simulation does not comply with reality. The results showed the importance of being very attentive when applying loads and constraints on a shaft under torsion while calculating it via FEA.

Keywords- torsion; numerical simulation; boundary conditions

I. INTRODUCTION

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is becoming increasingly popular among design engineers who use it as a product-design tool. Being safe and cost-efficient, the use of FEA as a product-design tool requires training, practice, and, mainly, experience, which is not present in the undergraduate curricula of mechanical engineering programs due to time constraints [1-4]. Among applications and calculations by the tool, there are many books on metallurgy and mechanics that describe many types of loads and boundary conditions to consider, torque being one among them as an important load.

Authors in [5-7] presented solid concepts and provided examples of real applications for readers. In addition, there are scientific works that calculate and analyze torque for several interesting applications. Authors in [8] developed a FEA program based on FORTRAN for analyzing working behavior and calculating torque and drag during oil extraction. The values of displacement obtained from the FEA model matched those from the analytical model. Authors in [9] presented

different methods for the calculation of torque as a function of rotation angle in an electrical machine. The results obtained by the distinct methodology were compared with the experimental data, which allowed attaining practical information concerning the advantages and limitations of each method. Authors in [10] investigated techniques for the optimal design of permanent magnet motors considering rotation. By applying the optimal design method, the authors reduced about 40% of the volume of the permanent magnet of the IPM motor and about 15% of the torque ripple. This reinforced the idea that most of the FE models should also be evaluated experimentally in order to be calibrated with reality. However, even in a virtual simulation platform, the model has to be as much realistic as possible and should utilize the most accurate and realistic boundary techniques. In this context, authors in [11] studied the simplification of the design geometry in the FEA of structural and other continuum problems and concluded that strategies for identifying possible idealizations, controlling their application, and estimating the associated errors appear to be feasible. In particular, authors in [12] assessed the mechanical properties of glass/metal joints. In his study, a Finite Element Method (FEM) was implemented to analyze the torsional shear strength test designed for glass-ceramic/steel joints aiming towards solid oxide fuel/electrolysis cell application. The authors concluded that the difference between the analytically derived nominal shear strength, and the real critical shear stress derived via simulation, reduces with decreasing fracture torque.

The boundary condition results might end up differently and some of them wrong if the simulation is not as close to reality as it could be. To the best of our knowledge, there are no papers that describe the impacts on the results on FE simulations when torque incurs on different (non-realistic) boundary conditions. Many pieces of literature and videos on media teach watchers how to run a FE simulation. However, not always the presentations are correct and precise. For instance, [13-15] described a few boundaries conditions for torque application incompatible with reality and can cause problems in the field. For this reason, this paper aims to demonstrate how distinct boundary conditions for the same

Corresponding author: Estaner Claro Romão

torque transference can result in expressively distinct results when a simulation does not comply with reality.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study used classical equations to determine the torque to utilize in the FEM as a torsion load. The shaft used on the simulations had one extreme constrained and another one receiving a torsional momentum (torque). To calculate the shearing stresses by numerical simulation, the shaft diameter was kept fixed at 10mm, and the length changed throughout the simulations. In addition, the loading region, where torque incurred, was altered in the simulations, from face to partial body, to whole body, and finally using an arm like if it were a wrench. Two opposing torques (*T*) produce a twisting load along the axis of a circular shaft, resulting in a total shear stress distribution (τ) given by (1) [16]:

$$\tau = \frac{T \cdot r}{J} \quad (1)$$

where $0 \leq r \leq R$. *r* is the distance from the center of the shaft and *R* is the outside radius, both in mm. Since the diameter of the shaft is fixed, therefore *R.T* is the applied torque (N.mm), τ the shear stress (MPa), and *J* is the moment of polar inertia (mm⁴), which is given by (2):

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \pi \cdot R^4 \quad (2)$$

Therefore combining (1) to (2) results to:

$$\tau = \frac{2 \cdot T}{\pi \cdot R^3} \text{ or } T = \frac{\tau \cdot \pi \cdot R^3}{2} \quad (3)$$

Assuming a fixed shearing stress of 100MPa as well as a fixed shaft diameter of 10mm, the torque result comes from (3) and is fixed at 19,635N.mm. It is relevant to highlight that since the purpose of the simulation is to apply 19,635N.mm as a total torque, only half of the torque was input on the shaft because the torque reaction generates the whole aimed torque. The fixed torque value was used throughout all simulations when running the FEA. In addition, each simulation had the shaft length altered progressively from 10mm to 1,000mm. For numerical simulations Autodesk F360 was utilized, considering a linear-elastic analysis and as an output the von Mises stress [18-20]. As seen in Table I, the same torque was input in four different ways. On the shaft face, along the shaft body, at a particular region, and by applying a vertical force on the arm attached to the shaft. In terms of mesh configuration, the same mesh for all simulations was utilized, which followed a maximum number of mesh refinement of 6, a convergence tolerance of 5%, a portion (40%) of elements to refine it, and an average element size of 10%.

TABLE I. BOUNDARY CONDITIONS FOR A SHAFT DIAMETER 10mm LOADED WITH A FIXED TORQUE OF 9,817.5N.mm.

Simulation boundaries	Description
	Shaft 10mm in diameter with length from 10 to 1,000mm. Simulation with constraint at back surface and torque applied on shaft face (SF).
	Shaft 10mm in diameter with length from 10 to 1,000mm. Simulation with constraint at the back surface and torque applied on shaft whole body (SWB).
	Shaft 10mm in diameter with length from 10 to 1,000mm. Simulation with constraint at the back surface and a torque applied on a body region of 15mm length (1.5 times the shaft diameter) (SPB).
	Shaft 10mm in diameter with length from 10 to 1,000mm. Simulation with constraint at the back surface and force applied on a wrench extreme (SWR).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 1 to 4 show the different equivalent stress (von Mises) in MPa for the following configurations: shaft with a torque applied at its face (SF), shaft torque body (SWB), shaft region (slip body) torque (SPB), and force with arm like a wrench (SWR). Figure 1 shows the maximum stress at the edge of the face where the torque is transmitted, and it reaches 105.1MPa for a shaft length of 60mm (SF). Figure 2 shows a von Mises stress of 89.08MPa at constraint face.

Fig. 1. Example of a shaft (10mm diameter × 60mm) simulated with a torque applied on the face (SF).

SWB differed from the SF condition, from 105.1MPa to 89.08MPa. Not only the shear stress intensity was different, but also the stress localization. Unlike SF, the maximum torque for SWB moved to the opposite side from the torque load. Figure 3 shows a change in torque from SWB to SPB. At this case, the maximum shearing stress was seen where the load was applied, and it reached 92.79MPa. When an arm was added (SWR), then a force was applied to simulate the torque. The shearing stress reached 107.5MPa and was positioned close to the shaft constraint (Figure 4). Figure 5 shows the variance of shearing stress for 10mm shaft diameter with a length changing from 10mm to 1,000mm, and affixed torque of 9,817.5N.mm applied on the shaft face (SF). For a short shaft (10mm length), the stress was significantly higher than the calculated value of 100MPa, reaching a peak of 180MPa. The diameter and length for this condition are the same and fixed at 10mm. There is a wide stress variance and up and down change for lengths from 10 to 200mm when the stress decreases and reaches a value close to the calculated value. However, after 200mm, the measured stress is unstable and has a high standard deviation as seen in Table II and Figures 9 and 10.

Fig. 2. Example of a shaft (10mm diameter × 60mm) simulated with a torque applied on the body (SWB).

Fig. 3. Example of a shaft (10mm diameter × 60mm) simulated with a torque applied on a region of the body (SPB).

Fig. 4. Example of a shaft (10mm diameter × 60mm) simulated with a force applied on arm (SWR).

Moreover, the standard deviation changes, depending on the length. It begins from 28MPa for lengths between 10mm and 100mm and reduces to 14MPa for lengths between 100mm and 300mm and it ends up with 12MPa from lengths between 300mm and 1,000mm.

Fig. 5. Shear stress with a torque applied on shaft face versus different lengths (SF).

When stress is applied to the shaft body (SWB), it reaches the highest stress level of 102MPa to a length of 10mm (Figure

6), thereafter it drops with length increment, reaching 86MPa when the length is 30mm. Soon after this point, the stress starts increasing again and it reaches 95MPa for a length maximum of 1,000mm. The standard deviation changes from 4MPa for lengths between 10mm and 100mm, then it reduces to 1MPa for lengths between 100mm and 300mm and ends up at 1MPa for lengths between 300mm and 1,000mm.

Fig. 6. Shear stress with a torque applied on shaft body versus different lengths (SWB).

When the torque is loaded on a specific and limited region of the shaft (SPB), the stress starts with a high value for a short shaft (103MPa for 10mm length), then it drops to 93MPa, thereon stresses fluctuate up and down and reach 95MPa at 1,000mm length (Figure 7). When it comes to standard deviation, it changes from 3MPa for lengths between 10mm and 100mm, then it reduces to 1MPa for lengths between 100mm and 300mm, and ends up at 1MPa for lengths between 300mm and 1,000mm. This presents a quite similar standard deviation when compared with the previous condition (SWB).

Fig. 7. Shear stress with a torque applied on shaft specific region versus different length (SPB).

A distinct behavior from previous situations is verified for a shaft that has an arm with a force-generating a torque (SWR) as shown in Figure 8. The shearing stress is pretty close to 100MPa as previously calculated analytically, but for 120mm and onwards it raises continually and moderately until 300mm when there is a steep inclination on the graph, demonstrating a mechanical instability. The standard deviation changes from 2MPa for lengths between 10mm and 100mm, then it goes up to 15MPa for lengths between 100mm and 300mm and it steeped up considerably to 89MPa for lengths between 300mm and 1,000mm. This presents the highest instability of all previous conditions. This stability comes from a lack of rigidity of the bar when it gets longer and longer until a point where the combination becomes totally mechanically unstable (uneven).

Fig. 8. Shear stress with a torque applied on shaft by a force applied on an arm (SWR).

Table II shows the partial calculations of shearing stress averages and standard deviations. It compiles variations of von Mises stress average and how data deviation occurs based on standard deviation. The shaft with a torque applied on a specific region showed the closer value to the calculated 100MPa (95MPa) and the lower standard deviation throughout all shaft lengths. In Figures 9 and 10, there is a comparison among stresses generated by torques applied on a region of a shaft body. A line at 100MPa is traced to help compare FEA to the analytical calculated value. The condition where the torque is applied on the face of the bar (Figure 9 left) shows that for short bars, the von Mises stress is higher, then it decreases constantly until the length of 1,000mm, which is 100 times the diameter of the shaft.

Therefore, this condition shows stress values that, when compared with the analytical calculation, do not seem accurate enough or reliable. When the torque is applied on the whole body (Figure 9(b)), the von Mises values are similar, and close to 90MPa for the full range of lengths with a standard value very low for short shafts as well as for longer bars. This means that the stress value is only 10% lower than the analytical calculated von Mises stress. When the torque is applied on a specific region of the bar, established as 1.5 times the shaft diameter (Figure 10(a)), the stress values were very close to the analytical calculation and varied from 95 to 96MPa.

TABLE II. DISTINCT VALUES FOR EACH CONFIGURATION

Condition	Von Mises stress (MPa) Average $10 \leq L \leq 100$	Calculated stress (τ) (MPa) StDev $10 \leq L \leq 100$	Von Mises stress (MPa) Average $100 \leq L \leq 300$	Calculated stress (τ) (MPa) StDev $100 \leq L \leq 300$	Von Mises (MPa) Average $300 \leq L \leq 1,000$	Calculated stress (τ) (MPa) StDev $300 \leq L \leq 1,000$
SF	145	28	125	14	115	12
SWB	90	4	91	1	95	1
SPB	95	3	94	1	96	1
SWR	95	2	117	15	276	89

Fig. 9. (a) Torques and standard deviation from distinct length intervals for (a) SF, (b) SWB.

This configuration represents remarkably real conditions seen on machines and equipment where an electrical motor has a coupling assembled on a specific length of the shaft. The final configuration applied a torque indirectly on the shaft by using an arm. At the extreme of the arm, the force that generates the torque was applied. At this case, the value was very close to the analytical one (100MPa analytical value versus 95MPa for simulation) for short shafts smaller than 100mm. For shafts with lengths between 100mm and 300mm the value surpassed the analytical value (117MPa versus 100MPa) and reached 276MPa, which is completely unrealistic.

The configurations were ranked comparatively with the analytical calculation. The closer value was verified at the SWR condition, to shaft length from 10 to 100mm, presenting a shear stress average of 95MPa and a standard deviation of

2MPa. The second was the SPB condition, with also 95MPa for shear stress and a standard deviation of 3MPa. The third condition was SWB, with an average of 90MPa and a standard deviation of 4MPa, and the last one was SF with an average of 145MPa and standard deviation of 28MPa, see Table II and Figures 9 and 10.

Fig. 10. Torques and standard deviation from distinct length intervals for (a) torque applied on a specific region of the shaft (SPB), (b) torque inputted on an arm like a wrench (SWR).

For shaft's lengths from 100 to 300mm, the sequence changed. The SPB condition ranked first with a von Mises Stress of 94MPa and standard deviation of 1MPa, the second was SWB with a von Mises Stress of 91MPa and standard deviation of 1MPa. SWR was the third with a von Mises Stress of 117MPa and standard deviation of 15MPa, and SF was last exhibiting a von Mises Stress of 125MPa and standard deviation of 14MPa. For longer positions (300 to 1,000mm) there was another change in positions. First was SPB with a von Mises Stress of 96MPa and standard deviation of 1MPa, then

SWB with a von Mises Stress of 95MPa and standard deviation of 1MPa. The third was SF with a von Mises Stress of 115MPa and standard deviation of 12MPa, and SWR was last with a von Mises stress of 276MPa and standard deviation of 89MPa.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper aimed to demonstrate how distinct boundary conditions for the same torque transference could result in different results when a simulation does not comply with reality. The results showed that unrealistic boundary conditions might result in unlikely shearing stresses and depending on the precision aimed, the results can lead to wrong conclusions, sometimes leading to failures. The results reinforced that realistic simulations are compulsory when working with FEA, even for a simple load as torsion. For this simulation in particular, the calculation of shearing stresses' averages and standard deviation within intervals helped to define the most appropriate way to apply a torque on a shaft with the presented dimensions. This simplification can lead to wrong conclusions on a system design and generate failure. Therefore, close attention and comparison between the simulation and reality are essential in order to produce a successful project.

To sum up, many machines and equipment have alternate ways of transferring movement by torsion. It can be by a coupling to transfer torque from an electrical motor to a system or a mechanism lever to produce a parallel actuating system. However, the real matter is that the FEA system can provide precise outputs only with precise and realistic inputs (boundary conditions).

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge the financial support by CAPES (process number 23038.000263/2022-19).

REFERENCES

- [1] P. M. Kurowski, "Teaching Finite Element Analysis For Design Engineers," in *Canadian Design Engineering Network Conference*, Toronto, Canada, Jul. 2006, pp. 203–234, <https://doi.org/10.24908/pceea.v0i0.3839>.
- [2] P. M. Kurowski, *Finite Element Analysis For Design Engineers*. Warrendale, PA, USA: SAE International, 2004.
- [3] P. Kurowski, "Chapter 3: Fundamental Concepts of Finite Element Analysis," in *Finite Element Analysis for Design Engineers*, Warrendale, PA, USA: SAE International, 2017, pp. 17–33.
- [4] I. Widiastuti and C. W. Budiyo, "Applying an Experiential Learning Cycle with the Aid of Finite Element Analysis in Engineering Education," *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, vol. 15, no. Special, pp. 97–103, Dec. 2018.
- [5] G. Dieter, *Mechanical Metallurgy*. New York, NY, USA: McGraw Hill, 1968.
- [6] T. Brown, *Mark's Calculations For Machine Design*. New York, NY, USA: McGraw-Hill, 2005.
- [7] G. E. O. Giacaglia, *Mecanica Geral*. Chicago, IL, USA: Campus, 1982.
- [8] A. Wu, G. Hareland, and M. Fazelzadeh, "Torque & Drag Analysis Using Finite Element Method," *Modern Applied Science*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 13–27, Nov. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.5539/mas.v5n6p13>.
- [9] N. Sadowski, Y. Lefevre, M. Lajoie-Mazenc, and J. Cros, "Finite element torque calculation in electrical machines while considering the movement," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 1410–1413, Mar. 1992, <https://doi.org/10.1109/20.123957>.
- [10] T. Ohnishi and N. Takahashi, "Optimal design of efficient IPM motor using finite element method," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 3537–3539, Sep. 2000, <https://doi.org/10.1109/20.908891>.
- [11] C. G. Armstrong, "Modelling requirements for finite-element analysis," *Computer-Aided Design*, vol. 26, no. 7, pp. 573–578, Jul. 1994, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-4485\(94\)90088-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-4485(94)90088-4).
- [12] M. Fakouri Hasanabadi, J. Malzbender, S. M. Groß-Barsnick, H. Abdoli, A. H. Kokabi, and M. A. Faghihi-Sani, "Finite element optimization of sample geometry for measuring the torsional shear strength of glass/metal joints," *Ceramics International*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 4857–4863, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2019.10.221>.
- [13] L. Zhixin, L. Xiaoqing, C. Xuedong, and C. Lumin, "The Study on Boundary Conditions to the Effect of Mode Analysis in FEA," *China Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 19, no. 9, pp. 0–1054, May 2008.
- [14] P. Bratley, B. L. Fox, and L. E. Schrage, *A Guide to Simulation*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 1987.
- [15] R. G. Ingalls, "Introduction to simulation," in *Winter Simulation Conference*, Phoenix, AZ, USA, Dec. 2011, pp. 1374–1388, <https://doi.org/10.1109/WSC.2011.6147858>.
- [16] T. Brown, *Mark's Calculations For Machine Design*, 1st edition. New York, NY, USA: McGraw Hill, 2005.
- [17] "Learn Fusion 360 | Fusion 360 Support, Tutorials & Videos." <https://www.autodesk.ca/en/products/fusion-360/learn-support> (accessed Mar. 17, 2022).
- [18] M. M. Teymoori and J. M. Ahangarkolaei, "A Tunable Capacitor Based on MEMS Technology for RF Applications," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 982–986, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.679>.
- [19] S. Bekkouche and M. Kadja, "Numerical Analysis of Density-Driven Reactive Flows in Hele-Shaw Cell Geometry," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5434–5440, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3349>.
- [20] E. C. Romao and L. H. P. de Assis, "Numerical Simulation of 1D Unsteady Heat Conduction-Convection in Spherical and Cylindrical Coordinates by Fourth-Order FDM," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2389–2392, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1724>.

Analysis of Leakage Inductances in Shunt Reactors: Application to High Voltage Transmission Lines

Tu Pham Minh

School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
Hanoi University of Science and Technology
Hanoi, Vietnam
tu.phamminh@hust.edu.vn

Hung Bui Duc

School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
Hanoi University of Science and Technology
Hanoi, Vietnam
hung.buiduc@hust.edu.vn

Vuong Dang Quoc

School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
Hanoi University of Science and Technology
Hanoi, Vietnam
vuong.dangquoc@hust.edu.vn

Received: 12 February 2022 | Revised: 1 March 2022 | Accepted: 16 March 2022

Abstract—Inductance is one of the main parameters directly related to the reactive powers of Shunt Reactors (SRs) in electrical systems. Thus, the definition and computation of leakage inductances and the ratio of leakage to total inductances play an extremely important role in the design and manufacturing of SRs. In this study, a finite element approach was developed to compute leakage and total inductances and define a relationship between them with different SR powers and high voltage levels. The expanded method is presented with the magnetic vector potential formulations.

Keywords—shunt reactor; leakage inductance; magnetic vector potential formulation; finite element method

I. INTRODUCTION

In long-distance high voltage transmission lines, capacitances occur between the phase voltage and earth or between phase voltages, leading to large reactive power in the electrical system [1-3]. In general, when a system operates on a full load, the reactive power is absorbed by the inductance load and lines. On the other hand, if the system works on low or no load, the voltage along lines increases, leading to overload voltage at the end of the line and affecting directly the electrical devices. Therefore, to overcome these drawbacks and maintain voltage stability in the electrical system, a Shunt Reactor (SR) is proposed to absorb the generated reactive powers [1-9]. The total inductance values, consisting of fringing and leakage inductances, are needed to compute and analyze the reactive power capacity of an SR. Fringing inductances have been recently proposed in [4, 10].

In this study, a finite element approach was developed with magnetic vector potential formulations to calculate and analyze the leakage inductances of an SR. Based on the obtained results, a relation of the shape factors of an SR, between inductance leakages and total inductance, was proposed to help

researchers and designers to select suitable leakage inductances for computing and designing.

II. MAGNETODYNAMIC PROBLEMS

A. Maxwell's Equations

A canonical magneto-dynamic problem is defined in a domain Ω , with boundary:

$$\partial\Omega = \Gamma = \Gamma_h \cup \Gamma_e$$

Maxwell's equations, considered in the frequency domain and behavior laws, are written in the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 as [11-12]:

$$\text{curl } H = J_s \quad (1-a)$$

$$\text{curl } E = -j\omega B \quad (1-b)$$

$$\text{div } B = 0 \quad (1-c)$$

$$B = \mu H \quad (2-a)$$

$$J = \sigma E \quad (2-b)$$

where H is the magnetic field (A/m), B is the magnetic flux density (T), E is the electric field (V/m), J_s is the current density (A/m²), and μ and σ are the relative permeability and electric conductivity (S/m), respectively. The Boundary Conditions (BCs) defined on Γ are expressed as [11-12]:

$$n \times H|_{\Gamma_h} = 0 \quad (3-a)$$

$$n \cdot B|_{\Gamma_e} = 0 \quad (3-b)$$

where n is the unit normal exterior to Ω , with $\Omega = \Omega_c \cup \Omega_c^c$. The domains Ω_c and Ω_c^c are the conducting and non-conducting regions, respectively. The equations (1-a) and (1-b) were solved with BCs taking into account the tangential component of H in (3-a) and the normal component of B in (3-b).

The fields H , B , E , and J are defined to satisfy Tonti's diagram [12]. This means that $H \in F_h(\text{curl}; \Omega)$, $E \in F_e(\text{curl}; \Omega)$, $J \in H(\text{div}; \Omega)$, and $B \in F_b(\text{div}; \Omega)$, where $F_h(\text{curl}; \Omega)$ and $F_e(\text{div}; \Omega)$ are function spaces containing BCs and the fields defined on Γ_h and Γ_e of the studied domain Ω .

Fig. 1. Tonti's diagram [12].

The field B in (1-c) is derived from a vector potential A such that:

$$B = \text{curl } A \quad (4)$$

Combining (4) with (1-b), leads to the definition of an electric scalar potential v such that:

$$E = -\partial_t A - \text{grad } v \quad (5)$$

B. Magnetic Vector Potential Weak Formulations

Based on the weak form of Ampere's law (1-a), the weak formulation of magnetic problems is written as [11-13]:

$$\frac{1}{\mu} \oint_{\Omega} (\text{curl } A \cdot \text{curl } t) d\Omega - \sigma \oint_{\Omega_c} (\partial_t A \cdot \text{curl } t) d\Omega_c + \sigma \oint_{\Omega_c} (\text{grad } v \cdot \text{curl } t) d\Omega_c + \int_{\Gamma} (n \times H) \cdot t d\Gamma = \oint_{\Omega_s} (J_s \cdot t) d\Omega_s, \forall t \in F_e^0(\text{curl}, \Omega) \quad (6)$$

where $F_e^0(\text{curl}, \Omega)$ is a function space defined on Ω and containing the basis functions for A and the test function t . The surface integral term $\langle n \times H, t \rangle_{\Gamma_h}$ on Γ_h in (6) accounts for the natural BCs and can be given in (3a-b). The energy density (w_t) is defined via the post-processing, i.e:

$$w_m = \frac{1}{2} \oint_{\Omega} H \cdot B d\Omega \quad (7)$$

Finally, the inductance value (L) is computed via (7), being:

$$L = \frac{2w_m}{I^2} \quad (8)$$

III. ANALYSIS OF THE PRACTICAL TEST

The practical test problem was a single-phase SR of 35MVar (500/ $\sqrt{3}$ kV and 50Hz). A simple model of this single-phase SR is presented in Figure 2. The typical parameters are given in Table I [4]. The percentage of the leakage inductance to the total can be defined as:

$$k_l \% = \frac{L_{leakage}}{L_{total}} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

where $L_{leakage}$ (H) and L_{total} (H) are the leakage and total inductances of the SR respectively. The distribution of the magnetic vector potentials due to the current following in the winding is presented in Figure 3. The percentage ratio of $L_{leakage}$ to L_{total} (k_l %) for different reactive powers and voltage levels is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 2. Model of a single-phase shunt reactor.

TABLE I. TYPICAL PARAMETERS OF THE SR

Parameters	Notations	Values
Reactive power	Q (MVar)	35
Rated voltage	U (kV)	500/ $\sqrt{3}$
Rated current	I (A)	121.24
Total inductance	L (H)	7.5788
Core dimension	D _c (mm)	701
Height of core	H _c (mm)	1793
Total air gap length	l _g (mm)	386
Turn number	N (turn)	2018

Fig. 3. Distribution of magnetic vector potentials.

Fig. 4. Ratio of $L_{leakage}$ to L_{total} (k_l %) for different voltage levels.

As can be noted, at the same voltage level, when the reactive power increases, the ratio of leakage inductance to total inductance also increases. From the obtained results, a polynomial function of the leakage inductance, power, and voltage, is expressed via the Lagrange interpolation method [14]. According to the Lagrange interpolation theory, it is possible to determine a polynomial function $P(x)$ of degree less than or equal to n satisfying the conditions $P(x_i) = y_i$, for $i = 1 \dots n+1$. The general formula is written as:

$$P(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} y_i \prod_{j \neq i} \frac{x-x_j}{x_i-x_j} \quad (10)$$

where x_i can be considered as the voltage (U), power (Q), and y_i is the ratio of the total value of leakage flux. Based on (10), the polynomial leakage inductance according to power and voltage is defined as:

$$\%L_{leakage} = f(Q, U) = (-9.913 \times 10^{-10}U^2 + 6.116 \times 10^{-7}U - 3.451 \times 10^{-4})Q^2 + (1.329 \times 10^{-7}U^2 - 8.83 \times 10^{-5}U + 9.037 \times 10^{-2})Q - (9.008 \times 10^{-7}U^2 + 3.002 \times 10^{-5}U - 8.289) \quad (11)$$

where Q (MVar) is the reactive power and U (kV) is the voltage. Polynomial (10) allows determining the percentage of leakage inductance at different reactive powers and voltage values. In addition, leakage inductance depends significantly on the winding factor (k_w) in the magnetic core's window. It is shown that k_w is the basis to determine the overall shape of the magnetic core. For each value of different reactive power and voltage, the value of $L_{leakage}$ is computed with the different value of k_w ($k_w = 4 \div 12$) for a change step of 0.2, as shown in Figure 5.

A polynomial function of the leakage inductance value at the high voltage level of 110 kV is defined as:

$$k_{l(110kV)}\% = f(k_w, Q) = (-4.753 \times 10^{-6}Q^2 + 10.61 \times 10^{-4}Q + 0.1136)k_w^2 + (1.127 \times 10^{-4}Q^2 - 2.627 \times 10^{-2}Q - 2.704)k_w + (-9.091 \times 10^{-4}Q^2 + 0.2223 \times 10^{-2}Q + 20.85) \quad (12)$$

Fig. 5. Calculation of the leakage inductance with the change of winding factor.

In the same way, the leakage inductance value at the high voltage level of 220kV is expressed as:

$$k_{l(220kV)}\% = f(k_w, Q) = (-5.069 \times 10^{-6}Q^2 + 10.3 \times 10^{-4}Q + 0.1068)k_w^2 + (1.154 \times 10^{-4}Q^2 - 2.517 \times 10^{-2}Q - 2.567)k_w + (-8.932 \times 10^{-4}Q^2 + 0.2135 \times 10^{-2}Q + 20.15) \quad (13)$$

For the extra high voltage level of 500kV, the leakage inductance is computed as:

$$k_{l(500kV)}\% = f(k_w, Q) = (-4.823 \times 10^{-6}Q^2 + 9.908 \times 10^{-4}Q + 0.1046)k_w^2 + (1.11 \times 10^{-4}Q^2 - 2.432 \times 10^{-2}Q - 2.521)k_w + (-8.535 \times 10^{-4}Q^2 + 0.2063 \times 10^{-2}Q + 19.94) \quad (14)$$

Based on the polynomial functions given in (12), (13), and (14), the percentage of leakage inductance to total inductance k_l (%) according to k_w at different reactive powers and voltage levels is shown in Figures 6-8.

Fig. 6. The value of k_l (%) flowing to k_w with different powers at 110kV.

Fig. 7. The value of k_l (%) flowing to k_w with different powers at 220kV.

Based on the results shown in Figures 6-8 and the polynomial functions of the leakage inductance according to the winding factor at different reactive powers and voltage levels, this method can be a basis for researchers, designers, and manufacturers to choose and look up leakage inductance values when calculating the design, and thus reduce the number of the needed virtual object models.

Fig. 8. The value of k_l (%) flowing to k_w with different powers at 500kV.

IV. CONCLUSION

A finite element approach was developed with the magnetic vector potential formulations. Based on the development of the formulation, the leakage and total inductance values according to the winding factor were defined at different reactive powers and voltage levels of 110kV, 220kV, and 500kV. The proposed method and the obtained results could help designers and manufacturers to make a suitable selection of the leakage inductance during the design or manufacturing of the SRs. The obtained results also show that there is a very good agreement on standardizing the type of leakage inductances in the SR.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This study was funded by the Hanoi University of Science and Technology (HUST) under grant number T2021-PC-006. The authors also gratefully acknowledge the Quy Nhon University, which provided favorable conditions for the use of the copyright-supported Ansys Electronics Desktop V19.R1.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Norouzian, "Shunt Reactors: Optimizing Transmission Voltage System," ABB Transformers and Reactors, Oct. 2016.
- [2] Z. Lubošny, J. Klucznik, and K. Dobrzyński, "The Issues of Reactive Power Compensation in High-voltage Transmission Lines," *Acta Energetica*, no. 23, pp. 102–108, Jun. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.12736/issn.2300-3022.2015210>.
- [3] A. S. Nunes, P. Kuo-Peng, and M. G. Vanti, "Air Core Reactor Analysis Based on RNM Method," presented at the Compumag 2013 - 19th International Conference on the Computation of Electromagnetic Fields, Budapest, Hungary, Jul. 2013, Art. no. 3.
- [4] T. P. Minh *et al.*, "Finite Element Modeling of Shunt Reactors Used in High Voltage Power Systems," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7411–7416, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4271>.
- [5] T. Pham Minh, H. Bui Duc, T. Tran Van, D. Dang Chi, and V. Dang Quoc, "Investigating Effects of Distance Air-Gaps on Iron-Core Shunt Reactors," in *Advances in Engineering Research and Application*, Cham, 2022, pp. 545–557, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-92574-1_57.
- [6] H. Amreiz, A. Janbey, and M. Darwish, "Emulation of Series and Shunt Reactor Compensation," in *2020 55th International Universities Power Engineering Conference (UPEC)*, Turin, Italy, Sep. 2020, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/UPEC49904.2020.9209786>.
- [7] L. M. Escibano, R. Prieto, J. A. Oliver, J. A. Cobos, and J. Uceda, "New modeling strategy for the fringing energy in magnetic components with air gap," in *APEC. Seventeenth Annual IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (Cat. No.02CH37335)*, Dallas, TX, USA, Mar. 2002, vol. 1, pp. 144–150 vol.1, <https://doi.org/10.1109/APEC.2002.989240>.
- [8] S. Grebovic, N. Oprasic, and A. Balota, "Influence of Shunt Reactor Switching on Overvoltages in 400 kV Substation," in *2020 9th Mediterranean Conference on Embedded Computing (MECO)*, Budva, Montenegro, Jun. 2020, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MECO49872.2020.9134116>.
- [9] R. P. Hutahaean and G. Sianipar, "Transient analysis of 150 kV shunt reactor at Bulukumba Substation," in *Proceedings of the 2011 International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, Bandung, Indonesia, Jul. 2011, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEEL2011.6021818>.
- [10] H. B. Duc, T. P. Minh, T. P. Anh, and V. D. Quoc, "A Novel Approach for the Modeling of Electromagnetic Forces in Air-Gap Shunt Reactors," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8223–8227, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4692>.
- [11] V. D. Quoc, "Robust Correction Procedure for Accurate Thin Shell Models via a Perturbation Technique," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5832–5836, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3615>.
- [12] V. D. Quoc, "Accurate Magnetic Shell Approximations with Magnetostatic Finite Element Formulations by a Subdomain Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 5953–5957, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3678>.
- [13] R. V. Sabariego, "The Fast Multipole Method for electromagnetic field computation," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Vigo, Vigo, Spain, 2004.
- [14] R. L. Burden, J. D. Faires, and A. M. Burden, *Numerical Analysis*. Boston, MA, USA: Cengage Learning, 2015.

Influence of Membrane Type on Some Electrical Properties of a Single Microbial Fuel Cell

Hafsa Bouzidi

LMPMP and LEES Laboratories
Faculty of Technology
Ferhat Abbas University
Setif, Algeria
hafsabouzidi@yahoo.fr

Lhadi Otmani

URMES Laboratory
Campus El Maabouda
Ferhat Abbas University
Setif, Algeria
elhadi_otmani@yahoo.fr

Rachida Doufnoune

URMES Laboratory
Campus El Maabouda
Ferhat Abbas University
Setif, Algeria
doufnoune@yahoo.fr

Larbi Zerroual

LMPMP Laboratory
Faculty of Technology
Ferhat Abbas University
Setif, Algeria
zerroual@yahoo.fr

Djafer Benachour

LMPMP Laboratory
Faculty of Technology
Ferhat Abbas University
Setif, Algeria
bendjafer@univ-setif.dz

Received: 8 February 2022 | Revised: 27 February 2022 | Accepted: 14 March 2022

Abstract—The effects of different parameters on the electric output of air-cathode microbial fuel cells were investigated in this work. The single microbial fuel cell was equipped by modifying Proton Exchange Membranes (PEM). Two membrane types were prepared: first by using the combination of Poly Vinyl Alcohol (PVA) with Polystyrene Sulfonate (PSSNa), while the second membrane was elaborated by mixing Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC) with Methyl Tri-Octyl Ammonium (MTOA) chloride. The PEMs were incorporated into the air-cathode to form a Membrane Electrode Assembly (MEA) to promote electricity generation. PVA/PSSNa and PVC-MTOA membranes were synthesized by solution casting method. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Ultraviolet (UV) Visible spectroscopy, Scanning Electronique Microscope (SEM), Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), and water Contact Angle (CA) were used as characterization techniques to explore the membrane structure and properties. The performance and the electric capacity of the microbial fuel cell in real time were operated using an external resistance of 5k Ω . Impedance and resistance capacity were determined using the polarization method. It was found that the internal resistance of the PVA/PSSNa and PVC-MTOA membranes were 50 and 350 Ω respectively. The voltage values at open circuit of the cells using PVA/PSSNa and PVC-MTOA membranes were 600mV and 150mV respectively. The values of power, current, and power density, are quite interesting. Cells with PVA/PSSNa and PVC-MTOA membranes gave values of 18.24 and 9.64mW.cm⁻² respectively.

Keywords—PVA/PSSNa; PVC-MTOA; membrane; single microbial fuel cells; renewable energy; wastewater

I. INTRODUCTION

Human sustainability is determined by deriving factors, among which energy is the most important. During the last

decade, fossil fuel commodity has seen a sharp decline because of the harmful effects of fossil fuels on the environment [1]. The problem of pollution pushes the researchers to look for new sources of energy, such as renewable energy [2]. Promising results were acquired by different renewable energy sources, such as solar, wind, tidal, geothermal, and biomass. In the last few years, the research into alternative sources of renewable energy has increased exponentially [3]. However, a new source of energy which is sustainable and environmentally stable was needed [4]. Wastewater treatment is a new energy technology and a bio-energy source [5-6]. The bio-energy process [7] involves the use of microbes to produce electricity. This technology is considered to have tremendous potential [8]. The bacteria available in a bio-convertible substrate were directly used as a catalyst to convert chemical energy to electricity in [9]. It is known that bacteria can generate electricity from organic waste sources [10]. A renewable process was used to generate energy in the form of electricity, in consistent fresh, resourceful manners, through the use of the Microbial Fuel Cells (MFCs) [11]. It was found that in MFCs, energy can be recovered from wastewater treatment, in fact from a wide range of organic compounds present in wastewater [12].

The MFCs consist of two compartments: anodic and cathodic. MFCs are composed of one anodic chamber filled with wastewater and an air cathodic chamber. The anode compartment includes domestic or industrial wastewater with sludge, and the cathode compartment is either used to remove heavy metals or for denitrification [9]. Many MFCs play an important role in producing bio-energy, such as value-added chemicals, via an easy operation, and at low maintenance cost [13]. The removal of organic constituents of wastewater leads

Corresponding author: Djafer Benachour

to the electricity production from the chemical energy stored in chemical bonds [12]. Three mechanisms to generate bioelectricity have been proposed: direct electron transport via membrane bound proteins (e.g. cytochromes), conductive nano-wires, and indirect shuttles via redox mediators (e.g. riboflavin) [14]. With regard to the source abundance, high efficiency, and convenient transportation, the most promising energy conversion devices are Proton Exchange Membranes (PEMs) [15]. PEMs are the most important factor to transport protons, and Nafion membrane has been widely used due to its high conductivity.

Recently, numerous studies have been conducted to find alternative membranes [16]. Desirable PEMs require excellent characteristics, the most important of which is high and stable proton conductivity [17]. An electron flow through the electrodes producing bioelectricity, has been demonstrated experimentally by the bacterial degradation in wastewater [18]. Microbial electricity production offers the possibility of obtaining electrical current from a wide range of soluble or dissolved organic wastes such as artificial, real, and biomass lignocellulosic wastewater [19]. The most important advantages of MFC are wastewater treatment, application of micro-organisms, energy production, and inexpensive biocatalysts [12]. Since the production of electricity in MFCs is related to wastewater treatment, it is considered as one of the most attractive energy sources [20]. MFCs are an emerging technology for simultaneous treatment of wastewater and energy recovery [21], following a similar concept to traditional fuel cells [3]. The process of MFCs was based on the generation of bioelectricity, and this method has been led by the bio-potential developed between the bacterial metabolic activity and the electron acceptor conditions, separated by a membrane [22].

The use of MFCs is one potential alternative energy source [3]. The reduction of electron acceptors, with electricity, was harvested in a circuit, by the anode which collected organics oxidized by the electrogenic microorganisms and combined with protons to cathode. The electricity generation and stability of MFCs are radically affected by the microbial communities on the electrode surface [23]. MFC operation includes several steps: first, the carbon dioxide is digested from bacteria and the released electrons are transferred to the anode. Then, electrical energy is generated via the travel of electrons from the anode in an external circuit. Finally, the electrons are taken up by oxygen and hydrogen ions to form water while they are traveling to the cathode to complete the circuit [24]. Recently, a suitable secondary stage process to fully recover the energy embedded in the metabolites and improve treatment efficiency, has been proven using MFC technology [25]. In MFC systems, the produced electrons are not directly transferred from bacteria to their electrons acceptor. The transport process is realized over other factors: cathode, anode, resistance, and membrane which transfer protons to the cathode [26-27]. When the MFCs are operated independently of an electrical device and as an integrated part of an electrical grid that controls the fuel cell output, an external resistance is used to dissipate the electrical energy [20]. The separator is an important factor that affects the design of MFCs [28], which is used to separate anode and cathode. The Cation Exchange Membrane (CEM) and PEM,

are investigated as the most important effect in the system: a membrane permits the proton passage and not the substrate, using an organic medium [29-34]. Recently, authors in [9] proposed that the factors which can lower the internal resistance in the MFC, should be optimized to obtain the highest values of voltage density and power.

Most works cited in the literature deal with the use of fuel cells in electrochemical application (batteries), at an industrial scale. In the present work, a new strategy in MFC (single chamber) has been tested using two different PEMs. Combined with a resistance, this separator was based on the order: PVA with PSSNa, and PVC, while the MTOA membrane was synthesized and characterized. The medium contained different organic products and was used as an energy source for the bacteria. Lead dioxide (PbO_2) was used as the cathode material.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

PVA with a molecular weight of 130,000 (99% hydrolyzed powder), PSSNa powder with a molecular weight of 70,000, glutaraldehyde (GLA), PVC powder with a molecular weight of 93.92g/mol, MTOA as ionic liquid with a molecular weight of 404.16g/mol, and tetrahydrofuran (THF) with a molecular weight of 72.10g/mol, which was used as a dissolving agent, were all provided by Sigma-Aldrich and were used as such without any further purification. Figure 1 shows the diagram of the experimental procedure.

Fig. 1. Experimental diagram.

A. Membrane Preparation

1) PVA-PSSNa Film Preparation

As a first step, 1.5g PVA were dissolved in deionized water and the obtained solution was stirred at 80°C until the PVA particles were completely dissolved. At the same time, the PSSNa solution was prepared by dissolving 0.6g in deionized water. The obtained mixture was further stirred at room temperature until the stabilization of the solution. As a second step, GLA was poured dropwise to the solution and then few drops of HCl solution were added. It is worth noting that a simple pouring of the mixture into a glass sheet with a uniform surface and similar thickness was realized. Finally, the thin film was dried at room temperature for a day.

2) PVC-MTOA Film Preparation

PVC powder (0.09g) and MTOA (0.21g) were dissolved in THF and stirred until complete dissolution. The obtained viscous solution was poured in a plastic mold (diameter = 2.8cm). After the evaporation of the solvent, the thin film was dried at room temperature.

3) Microbial Fuel Cell Configuration and Media Composition

The anodic single chamber is made of glass material with a volume of 250ml (SCHOTT DURAN). The chamber was filled with 200ml of wastewater taken from a water purification station (National Office of Disinfection-Sfiha, Setif, Algeria), with total sprouts, total coliforms, and fecal coliform. The electrode used in this experiment was a carbon fiber fixed in the cap of the chamber. The cathode is made of 0.6g of PbO₂ powder dissolved in 0.5ml ethanol, spread on a piece of stainless steel, left to dry in open air. The Voltage Open Circuit (VOC) was measured with a digital multi-meter. The real time voltage values were recorded with an Arduino program. The carbon fiber rod in the anodic chamber and the cathode were connected into a recorder by the Arduino Uno R3 (open-source electronics prototyping platform, Italy) and the data were registered on a computer. The medium solution was prepared using different components: NH₄Cl (1.50g/L⁻¹), KCl (0.1g/L⁻¹), Na₂HPO₄ (0.6g/L⁻¹), acetate (1.36g/L⁻¹), NaHCO₃ (2.5g/L⁻¹), CaCl₂ (0.1g/L⁻¹), and yeast extract (0.05g/L⁻¹). These components were dissolved in distilled water and the anodic chamber was filled every week.

B. Membrane Characterization

The structure of the thin films was characterized by FTIR spectroscopy, the analysis was recorded on a JASCO-IR spectrometer. The signal scans of 32 were realized in the 4000-400cm⁻¹ wavenumber range at a resolution of 4cm⁻¹. UV-visible spectroscopy was used to characterize the structure of the thin films; the scan was carried out using a Shimadzu UV-2401PC UV-visible spectrophotometer in the range of 200–800nm. The optical absorbance of the obtained membranes was recorded and the energy band gap was evaluated from the UV spectrum. The endothermic and exothermic phenomena change of the physical state of the thin films were determined using a diffraction scanning calorimetric (DSC) (Jupiter ,STA 449 F3), the scan was realized in the temperature range of 35-350°C, with a rate of 10°C/min in open air. The variation in weight loss of the membranes as a function of the temperature was examined by TGA analysis, the thermal properties were measured using a thermogravimetric analysis (TGA PERKIN-ELMER) apparatus in which the temperature range was set from 25 to 500°C, with a heating rate of 10°C/min. The surface morphology of the membranes was observed by SEM (JEOL, JSM 6510 LV) and the analysis was operated at an acceleration voltage of 30kV. Water CA measurement was used to determine the hydrophilicity or hydrophobicity character of the prepared membranes. This was done using a Ram E-hart CA goniometer/tensiometer. The surface examination was operated at room temperature and with relative humidity of 30 ± 5%. The swelling rate measurements (η) were made through membrane weight, the measurement was based on the calculation of the membrane mass in dry and hydrated state. The swelling rate is expressed as a percentage:

$$\eta = \left[\frac{mf - mi}{mi} \right] * 100 \quad (1)$$

where η is the swelling rate (%), and mf and mi are the final and initial weight of the membrane (g) respectively.

C. MFC Operation and Electrochemical Characterization

The internal resistance of the membranes was measured with the impedance spectroscopy method. The Frequency Response Analysis (FRA) in the beginning and the end (cell discharge) was inspected using a Volta-lab instrument PGSTAT302N, Metrohm Autolab B.V. The frequencies of the operation were oscillated from 1MHz to 0.01Hz with 0.05V amplitude perturbation in 5% of NaCl solution. It should be noted that the different measurement steps of impedance and real time operations were operated in NaCl and bacterial medium solutions respectively. Consequently, the same conditions of MFCs exploited in the impedance measurement were applied. However, Nyquist plot was used to determine the internal resistance of the system after applying the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy technique. Equation (2) gives the relation between the impedance system and the ionic conductivity:

$$\sigma = \frac{L}{R.A} \quad (2)$$

where σ is the ionic conductivity (S/cm⁻¹), L the thickness (cm), A the cross-section area (cm²) and R the resistance (Ω).

A Nyquist plot was used to determine the internal resistance of the system after applying the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy technique. The membranes were tested in MFCs using wastewater as substrate. A fixed resistance R_{ext} of 5k Ω was used and the result was recorded. A PEM was used in MFCs. The charge-discharge cycle with time gives the voltage as a function of current (current density) (V vs. I), and the power (power density) as a function of current density (P vs. I). The power curve was used to determine the internal resistance. It started at Open Circuit Voltage (OCV), the slope is equal to the internal resistance in the case of a linear polarization curve.

$$E_{cell} = OCV - IR_{int} \quad (3)$$

where E_{cell} , I and R_{int} are the voltage of the cell, current density, and internal resistance respectively.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Spectroscopic Characterization and Morphological Studies

1) FTIR Characterization

PVA-PSSNa was obtained from the reaction of PVA-PSSNa and GLA. The FTIR spectra confirmed the chemical structure. Figure 2 shows the FTIR spectra of PVA-PSSNa. The very wide band that appears at 3356cm⁻¹ is related to the stretching vibration of hydroxyl groups of PVA chains. The 2931cm⁻¹ band is attributed to alkanes, and ester bands are registered at 1715cm⁻¹ and 1435cm⁻¹. The symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations due to the sulfonic group are located at 1125cm⁻¹ and 1240cm⁻¹ respectively. The broad band at 1125cm⁻¹ indicates the linking of sulfonic anion with phenyl ring. Additionally, the aromatic functional groups of PSSNa

chain are located at 840cm^{-1} . In the FTIR spectra of PVC-MTOA membrane, the band located at 3673cm^{-1} is associated to a strong free alcohol related to a bond interaction between PVC and MTOA in the presence of the THF as solvent agent. The located bands at $3000\text{-}3100\text{cm}^{-1}$ present an amine deformation of the MTOA. A strong alkane C-H band is situated at 2896cm^{-1} related to the PVC. The ammonium groups are located at 2400cm^{-1} . The alkene groups are observed at 2109cm^{-1} , the band recorded at 965cm^{-1} confirmed the existence of the alkene. The appearance of a broad absorption band at 1628cm^{-1} was related to the linked N-H, the bands at 1460cm^{-1} and 1248cm^{-1} indicated the C-H and C-C bonds respectively, an alcohol group was located at 1378cm^{-1} , and chloroalkane C-Cl was located at 723cm^{-1} [35-36].

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of (a) PSSNa/PVA membrane and (b) PVC/MTOA.

2) DSC Characterization

The DSC thermograms are illustrated on Figure 3.

Fig. 3. DSC curve of (a) the blend PVA/PSSNa, (b) the blend PVC/MTOA.

As mentioned above, the mixture was stable and has good miscibility between polymers, thus no visible phase separation

between PVA and PSSNa was detected. This confirms the morphology results obtained by SEM. In addition, the thermograms revealed a single glass transition temperature (T_g) of the blend in the range of 60 to 90°C, which indicates the total miscibility of the polymers. In the DSC curve obtained on PVC/MTOA membrane, a sudden change in heat transfer at 165.5°C is noticed. This may be explained by the irregularly shaped samples, the ionic liquid being more flexible than the PVC, results in a flexible membrane compared to the PVA/PSSNa membrane. The second endothermic peak at 221°C related to the crystallization temperature (T_c) corresponds to the side reaction and decomposition of the membrane while the third peak at 245°C corresponds to the melting point temperature. At high temperature all the interactions between the chains are broken.

3) SEM Characterization

SEM images of the membranes are presented in Figure 4. A micrograph of the mixture formed by blending PVA, PSSNa, GLA, is also reported in the same Figure.

Fig. 4. (a) SEM of the PVA/PSSNa, (b) water CA of PVA/PSSNa, (c) SEM of the PVC/MTOA, and (d) water CA of PVC/MTOA.

As can be seen in Figure 4, no phase separation was observed for the prepared membranes. The PVA/PSSNa presents a good combination between the two polymers and homogenous surface. PVC/MTOA membrane exhibits a smooth and homogeneous nonporous surface too. The obtained membranes are transparent and have good clarity, implying good compatibility between the ionic liquid and the polymer. This leads to more contact area and more compatibility to form a bio-film (in which the ionic charge is produced because it is formed with the bacteria found in the medium).

4) Contact Angle and Swelling Rate Characterization

The hydrophilicity of the membranes was evaluated using the water CA technique. It can be noted that for PVA/PSSNa membrane the values varied from 35.6° to 36.9°, while for PVC/MTOA membrane, the contact angle values varied from 12.3° to 12.7°. The polymers containing sulfonic acid groups

transport protons via the vehicular mechanism, relying on the presence of water PVA/PSSNa membrane. The water adsorption of the PVC/MTOA membrane is attributed to the ionic liquid group. Table I summarizes the CA and the swelling rate values of PVA/PSSNa and PVC/MTOA membranes, it confirms the results observed in Figure 4.

TABLE I. CONTACT ANGLE AND SWELLING RATE VALUES OF PVA/PSSNa AND PVC/MTOA MEMBRANES

Membrane	Contact angle (°)	Swelling rate (%)
PVA/PSSNa	35.6-36.9	78.38
PVC/MTOA	12.3-12.7	86.07

The water absorption of the two membranes was studied by immersing the membranes in deionized solution. The weight of the membranes was measured before and after immersion. The membranes show that the water uptake was elevated due to water molecule mobility. The elevated water-uptake improves the swelling rate of PVA/PSSNa ($\eta = 78\%$) and PVC/MTOA ($\eta = 86\%$) membranes. The problem encountered is that the membranes never return to their initial states after being immersed in water. Consequently, the membranes have a good water uptake, and this will increase the proton conductivity.

5) TGA Characterization

The thermal stability of PVA/PSSNa and PVC/MTOA membranes under nitrogen atmosphere, was evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis. The TGA thermograms are presented in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. TGA curves of (a) the blend PVA/PSSNa, (b) the blend PVC/MTOA.

The thermogram shows a typical three-step degradation of PVA/PSSNa. A small weight loss was observed at about 61°C due to the evaporation of physisorbed water. The second weight loss, which occurred between 217 and 462°C, corresponds to the degradation of PVA/PSSNa. The third weight loss, above 465°C, was due to the decomposition of the backbones of the materials. The curves showed a typical two-step degradation pattern of the PVC/MTOA membrane. No obvious weight loss was observed until 250°C. The weight loss recorded between 253 and 415°C corresponds to the

degradation of PVC, whereas the second weight loss in the range 415-495°C is due to the decomposition of MTOA.

6) UV Characterization

The UV spectra of PVA/PSSNa and PVC/MTOA are presented in Figure 6. The main peaks are located at 227-193.5nm and are attributed to PVA/PSSNa and PVC/MTOA respectively, which indicates a significant interaction between polymers, while no phase separation was noticed.

Fig. 6. UV visible spectra of (a) PSSNa/PVA and (b) PVC/MTOA membranes.

B. Electrochemical Monitoring

Figure 7 shows the Nyquist plots for the supported membranes, based on PVA/PSSNa and PVC/MTOA. The values of the internal resistance and the ionic conductivity are given in Table II. The internal resistance values are 54.12 and 350Ω for PVA/PSSNa and PVC/MTOA respectively. These values confirm the high conductivity of PVA/PSSNa membrane.

TABLE II. MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MEMBRANES

Membrane	Thickness (μm)	Area (cm ²)	Internal resistance (Ω)	Ionic conductivity (S cm ⁻¹)
PVA/PSSNa	301	0.785	54.12	1.02×10^{-4}
PVC/MTOA	230	0.785	350	8.37×10^{-6}

After the discharge of the cells, it was noticed that the internal resistance was approximately 62Ω for the PVA/PSSNa membrane. Almost no difference in the internal resistance value before and after the test was detected, while in the case of PVC/MTOA membrane, the internal resistance significantly increased at the end of the test (1200Ω). This difference can be related to the membrane aging. The ionic conductivities of the PVA/PSSNa and PVC/MTOA membranes are respectively 1.02×10^{-4} and 8.37×10^{-6} S/cm. PVA/PSSNa presents higher proton conductivity compared to PVC/MTOA (see Table II).

Fig. 7. Frequency response analysis of membranes based on (a,c) PVA/PSSNa and (b,d) PVC/MTOA membranes.

TABLE III. ELECTRICAL PARAMETERS OF THE MEMBRANES

	External resistance (kΩ)	Time (weeks)	OCV (mV)	Maximum power (mW.cm ⁻²)	Maximum voltage (mV)	Maximum current density (mA.cm ⁻²)
PVA/PSSNa	5	1	604	18.24	386.02	0.14
		2	377	9.05	278.49	0.09
		3	341	6.25	239.78	0.09
		4	342	6.98	239.78	0.09
		5	300	4.98	205.38	0.08
PVC/MTOA	5	1	156	1.50	422.58	0.04
		2	156	1.55	450.54	0.04
		3	198	2.50	212.9	0.05
		4	389	9.64	212.9	0.10
		5	292	5.26	119.75	0.07

High electron transfer from the anodic chamber to the cathode leads to high current. The anode potential should be low and the cathode potential should be high in order to have a maximum fuel cell performance. The metabolic activities of the biocatalyst and the respective energy dissipation can affect the anode potential. In a biofuel cell, bacteria drain off their electrons to the anode.

Figure 8 shows the polarization curve of MFCs filled with wastewater. The two curves describe the voltage and power as functions of the current density to identify the maximum output power density of MFCs. The obtained open circuit voltage was 604mV for the PVA/PSSNa and 156mV for PVC/MTOA (Table III). Figure 9 shows the polarization curve of MFCs filled with medium. The power and the current density increased after four weeks in the case of the PVC/MTOA membrane but the voltage decreased from the first week. The maximal values were obtained in the second week of using the medium and were 9.64mw/cm² power and 0.10mA/cm² current density.

Fig. 8. Polarization curves of the MFC using different membranes (in wastewater).

Fig. 9. Polarization curves of the MFC using different membranes (using the medium).

Regarding the PVA/PSSNa membrane, the maximal values were observed during the first week and they were about 18.24mw/cm² power and 0.14mA/cm² current density. The cell decreased after that and this decrease of power generation can be related to the structure and to the effect of the internal resistance of the two membranes: the PVC/MTOA membrane is more flexible (from the mechanical point of view) and more

resistant (from the electrical point of view) than the PVA/PSSNa membrane. This difference will impact the bio-film formed, while the PVA/PSSNa will be more effective in the electricity generation. Accordingly, the electron transfer from the anodic chamber to the cathode decreases according to the bio-film forming the electrical resistances of the electrodes, the membrane internal resistance and electrolyte, the power drops due to the increasing Ohmic losses, and the electrode overpotentials to the point where no more power is produced. [37-39].

In a previous similar work [21], the authors used a PVC-based membrane, however the conductivity obtained was not as good as the one obtained in this study for the PVC/MTOA membrane. In addition, we used the CA parameter to evaluate the membrane surface capacity for matter adsorption, which, to the best of our knowledge, is reported for the first time.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, MFCs were used to directly generate electricity from the oxidation of dissolved organic matter. However, the optimization of MFCs requires more knowledge about the factors that can increase the power output such as the capacity of proton exchange system which can affect the system characteristics, particularly the internal resistance and the external resistance. The power (P) was calculated according to $P = IV$ ($I = V/R$), where I (A) is the current, V (V) is the voltage, and R (Ω) is the resistance. The prepared assisted cross-linked PVA-PSSNa membrane has a good ionic conductivity and a good miscibility and thermal stability. In addition, it exhibits high proton exchange capacity and lower internal resistance, compared to the PVC/MTOA membrane which has a high internal resistance and a long term to discharge. It has also good miscibility, a hydrophilic character, and a good thermal stability.

AUTHORSHIP CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

The results presented here are part of a Ph.D. thesis work. H. Bouzidi, as a Ph.D. student, conducted most of the experimental and characterization work. L. Otmani and R. Doufnoune prepared and provided the PVA-PSSNa membrane, L. Zerroual (thesis co-advisor) helped in the electrochemical experimental work, while D. Benachour (thesis advisor) did the editing.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Ogungbemi *et al.*, "Fuel cell membranes – Pros and cons," *Energy*, vol. 172, pp. 155–172, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2019.01.034>.
- [2] J. Liu, "China's renewable energy law and policy: A critical review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 99, pp. 212–219, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.10.007>.
- [3] A. J. Slate, K. A. Whitehead, D. A. C. Brownson, and C. E. Banks, "Microbial fuel cells: An overview of current technology," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 101, pp. 60–81, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.09.044>.
- [4] J. Chouler *et al.*, "Towards effective small scale microbial fuel cells for energy generation from urine," *Electrochimica Acta*, vol. 192, pp. 89–98, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2016.01.112>.
- [5] D. J. Batstone, T. Hulsen, C. M. Mehta, and J. Keller, "Platforms for energy and nutrient recovery from domestic wastewater: A review," *Chemosphere*, vol. 140, pp. 2–11, Dec. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.10.021>.
- [6] H.-L. Song, Y. Zhu, and J. Li, "Electron transfer mechanisms, characteristics and applications of biological cathode microbial fuel cells – A mini review," *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, vol. 12, no. 8, pp. 2236–2243, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabj.2015.01.008>.
- [7] Z. Zhang, R. Miyajima, T. Inada, D. Miyagi, and M. Tsuda, "Novel energy management method for suppressing fuel cell degradation in hydrogen and electric hybrid energy storage systems compensating renewable energy fluctuations," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 43, no. 14, pp. 6879–6886, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2018.02.124>.
- [8] D. Lal, "Microbes to Generate Electricity," *Indian Journal of Microbiology*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 120–122, Mar. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12088-012-0343-2>.
- [9] T. H. Choi *et al.*, "Electrochemical performance of microbial fuel cells based on disulfonated poly(arylene ether sulfone) membranes," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 220, pp. 269–279, Dec. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2012.07.109>.
- [10] B. E. Logan and J. M. Regan, "Electricity-producing bacterial communities in microbial fuel cells," *Trends in Microbiology*, vol. 14, no. 12, pp. 512–518, Dec. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tim.2006.10.003>.
- [11] K. Senthilkumar and M. Naveen Kumar, "Generation of bioenergy from industrial waste using microbial fuel cell technology for the sustainable future," in *Refining Biomass Residues for Sustainable Energy and Bioproducts*, R. P. Kumar, E. Gnansounou, J. K. Raman, and G. Baskar, Eds. Cambridge, MA, United States: Academic Press, 2020, pp. 183–193.
- [12] R. Tajdid Khajeh, S. Aber, and K. Nofouzi, "Efficient improvement of microbial fuel cell performance by the modification of graphite cathode via electrophoretic deposition of CuO/ZnO," *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, vol. 240, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 122208, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2019.122208>.
- [13] Y. Li, C. Cheng, S. Bai, L. Jing, Z. Zhao, and L. Liu, "The performance of Pd-rGO electro-deposited PVDF/carbon fiber cloth composite membrane in MBR/MFC coupled system," *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 365, pp. 317–324, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.02.048>.
- [14] S.-H. Chang *et al.*, "Feasibility study of surface-modified carbon cloth electrodes using atmospheric pressure plasma jets for microbial fuel cells," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 336, pp. 99–106, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2016.10.058>.
- [15] Q. Zhao *et al.*, "Effect of aminated nanocrystal cellulose on proton conductivity and dimensional stability of proton exchange membranes," *Applied Surface Science*, vol. 466, pp. 691–702, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2018.10.063>.
- [16] B. Lin *et al.*, "Protic ionic liquid/functionalized graphene oxide hybrid membranes for high temperature proton exchange membrane fuel cell applications," *Applied Surface Science*, vol. 455, pp. 295–301, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2018.05.205>.
- [17] H. Gao *et al.*, "Improving the proton conductivity of proton exchange membranes via incorporation of HPW-functionalized mesoporous silica nanospheres into SPEEK," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 43, no. 48, pp. 21940–21948, Nov. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2018.08.214>.
- [18] K. Tota-Maharaj and P. Paul, "Performance of pilot-scale microbial fuel cells treating wastewater with associated bioenergy production in the Caribbean context," *International Journal of Energy and Environmental Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 213–220, Sep. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40095-015-0169-x>.
- [19] R. Huarachi-Olivera *et al.*, "Bioelectrogenesis with microbial fuel cells (MFCs) using the microalga *Chlorella vulgaris* and bacterial communities," *Electronic Journal of Biotechnology*, vol. 31, pp. 34–43, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejbt.2017.10.013>.
- [20] A. Gonzalez del Campo, P. Canizares, J. Lobato, M. Rodrigo, and F. J. Fernandez Morales, "Effects of External Resistance on Microbial Fuel Cell's Performance," in *Environment, Energy and Climate Change II: Energies from New Resources and the Climate Change*, G. Lefebvre, E.

- Jimenez, and B. Cabanas, Eds. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2016, pp. 175–197.
- [21] M. J. Salar-Garcia, V. M. Ortiz-Martinez, A. P. de los Rios, and F. J. Hernandez-Fernandez, "A method based on impedance spectroscopy for predicting the behavior of novel ionic liquid-polymer inclusion membranes in microbial fuel cells," *Energy*, vol. 89, pp. 648–654, Sep. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2015.05.149>.
- [22] M. Rahimnejad, T. Jafary, F. Haghparast, G. Najafpour, and A. A. Ghoreyshi, "Nafion as a nanoprotion conductor in microbial fuel cells," *Turkish Journal of Engineering and Environmental Sciences*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 289–292, Feb. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.3906/muh-1006-48>.
- [23] S. Xin *et al.*, "Electricity generation and microbial community of single-chamber microbial fuel cells in response to Cu₂O nanoparticles/reduced graphene oxide as cathode catalyst," *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 380, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 122446, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.122446>.
- [24] N. S. N. Hisham *et al.*, "Microbial fuel cells using different types of wastewater for electricity generation and simultaneously removed pollutant," *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 316–325, 2013.
- [25] J. L. Varanasi, S. Roy, S. Pandit, and D. Das, "Improvement of energy recovery from cellobiose by thermophilic dark fermentative hydrogen production followed by microbial fuel cell," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 40, no. 26, pp. 8311–8321, Jul. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.04.124>.
- [26] J. Grandgirard, D. Poinsot, L. Krespi, J.-P. Nenon, and A.-M. Cortesero, "Costs of secondary parasitism in the facultative hyperparasitoid *Pachycrepoideus dubius*: does host size matter?," *Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata*, vol. 103, no. 3, pp. 239–248, 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1570-7458.2002.00982.x>.
- [27] C.-Y. Chen, T.-Y. Chen, and Y.-C. Chung, "A comparison of bioelectricity in microbial fuel cells with aerobic and anaerobic anodes," *Environmental Technology*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 286–293, Feb. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2013.826254>.
- [28] X. Zhang, S. Cheng, X. Wang, X. Huang, and B. E. Logan, "Separator Characteristics for Increasing Performance of Microbial Fuel Cells," *Environmental Science & Technology*, vol. 43, no. 21, pp. 8456–8461, Nov. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es901631p>.
- [29] B. E. Logan *et al.*, "Microbial Fuel Cells: Methodology and Technology," *Environmental Science & Technology*, vol. 40, no. 17, pp. 5181–5192, Sep. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es0605016>.
- [30] B. Zhang and J. Ni, "Enhancement of Electricity Generation and Sulfide Removal in Microbial Fuel Cells with Lead Dioxide Catalyzed Cathode," in *4th International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedical Engineering*, Chengdu, China, Jun. 2010, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICBBE.2010.5514899>.
- [31] A. S. Alghamdi, "Synthesis and Mechanical Characterization of High Density Polyethylene/Graphene Nanocomposites," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2814–2817, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1961>.
- [32] S. Chaoui, D. Smail, A. Hellati, and D. Benachour, "Effect of Starch Nanocrystals on the Properties of Low Density Polyethylene/Thermoplastic Starch Blends," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 5875–5881, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3608>.
- [33] N. el H. Belkham, D. Benachour, and A. Mehamha, "Elaboration and Physico-Chemical Characterization of the Gibbsite Li(OH)₃ Hybrid Material," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6740–6744, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3988>.
- [34] A. S. Alghamdi, "Creep Resistance of Polyethylene-based Nanocomposites," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4367–4370, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2759>.
- [35] R. M. Silverstein, G. C. Bassler, and C. T. Morrill, *Spectrometric identification of organic compounds*, 3d ed. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 1974.
- [36] S. Chaibi, D. Benachour, M. Merbah, M. Esperanza Cagiao, and F. J. Balta Calleja, "The role of crosslinking on the physical properties of gelatin based films," *Colloid and Polymer Science*, vol. 293, no. 10, pp. 2741–2752, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00396-015-3660-2>.
- [37] D. Chalal, R. Garuz, D. Benachour, J. Boucle, and B. Ratier, "Influence of an electrode self-protective architecture on the stability of inverted polymer solar cells based on P3HT:PCBM with an active area of 2cm²," *Synthetic Metals*, vol. 212, pp. 161–166, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.synthmet.2015.12.021>.
- [38] H. Satha, I. Kouadri, and D. Benachour, "Thermal, Structural and Morphological Studies of Cellulose and Cellulose Nanofibers Extracted from Bitter Watermelon of the Cucurbitaceae Family," *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, vol. 28, no. 7, pp. 1914–1920, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10924-020-01735-6>.
- [39] M. Hafani, M. A. Chemrak, M. Djennad, and D. Benachour, "Formulation and characterization of a new PET-based membrane for methane gas dehydration," *Polymer-Plastics Technology and Materials*, vol. 60, no. 15, pp. 1605–1619, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1080/25740881.2021.1912091>.

Development of an Automated Ticketing and Tracking System for the Monitoring of Surface Mine Hauling Operations

Lovely Mae Dagsa
SMART Mines Research Project
Caraga State University
Butuan City, Philippines
lmdagsa@carsu.edu.ph

Alexander T. Demetillo
SMART Mines Research Project
Caraga State University
Butuan City, Philippines
atdemetillo@carsu.edu.ph

Alfred Dennis B. Balamad
SMART Mines Research Project
Caraga State University
Butuan City, Philippines
densvanz13@gmail.com

Edgardo Ricardo B. Sajonia Jr.
SMART Mines Research Project
Caraga State University
Butuan City, Philippines
ebsajonia@carsu.edu.ph

Gerome L. Amper
SMART Mines Research Project
Caraga State University
Butuan City, Philippines
glamper@carsu.edu.ph

Marie Claire O. Virtudazo
SMART Mines Research Project
Caraga State University
Butuan City, Philippines
mcovirtudazo@carsu.edu.ph

Received: 9 February 2022 | Revised: 18 February 2022 | Accepted: 23 March 2022

Abstract—Telematics systems that integrate wireless communications and automation for equipment tracking and trip monitoring in mining operations have an advanced impact on the operational efficiency and optimization of the mine's asset inventory. In this study, a system was developed for solution in a mining area with low mobile network signal coverage and no internet service available to monitor and analyze the actual utilization executed by heavy equipment using microcontrollers with communication capabilities (GSM/GPRS, WiFi, and Bluetooth) and sensor modules for fuel monitoring and location tracking. Open-source software was utilized, such as PHP framework and MySQL, to provide a fast and real-time display of daily mine operations. The study provides an online tracking and ticketing system on mine hauling vehicles, introducing a cost-efficient, reliable, interactive platform for web-based monitoring and real-time telematics. The data acquired in real-time provide significant information which will allow innovative equipment optimization.

Keywords—telematics; microcontrollers; GSM; GPRS; WiFi; PHP; MySQL; tracking and ticketing system; web-based monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

By allowing the extraction of important information from industrial processes, the industrial revolution, which includes automation, information, and communication technology, can improve production and commercial processes. Due to the infrastructural limitations in communication, data management, storage, and information exchange, the mining industry is rather traditional and slow to change [1]. The hauling system has been a mainstay of the mining industry for many years. While machines have increased in size and scale and

automation has become an important development, there have been few innovations to the actual load and haul process [2]. Most recent efforts focused on using robotics and automation to assist the extraction and transport of minerals and ore [3]. Trip analysis in mining hauling operations can lead to a series of important analytics applications for asset managers. Analyzing trip data helps fleet managers and dispatchers understand and estimate asset utilization, route deviation, and ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival). This system is extremely crucial when making production decisions and adjustments to improve the efficiency and use of equipment. Implementing good monitoring systems plays a vital role in achieving this. Nowadays, the competitive global economy is forcing mining companies worldwide to modernize their operations through increased mechanization, automation, and monitoring [4–8].

Historically in fleet management, trips are logged manually or semi-automatically, whereas using GPS-based data to infer trips provides an automated approach to trip management and analysis [9–11]. This system alleviates the labor of manual recording and avoids the possibility of unauthorized or misreported trips, and improves the accuracy of actual trip data. One of the most common asset tracking technologies is an embedded GPS receiver and other sensors to track a movable asset such as a trailer, which connects with a central data server via satellite or cellular communications. Every telematics communication typically contains location data, vehicle identity information, timestamps, and an event code [12].

Monitoring systems implemented in various fields utilize different technologies like unmanned vehicles, GSM, IoT, and WSN to retrieve information from the monitored equipment or area [13–17, 21–22]. However, in mining area settings where

mobile network connection and internet coverage are difficult to acquire, it is necessary to implement a one-of-a-kind data transfer system. This study developed such a system to solve the transmission problem and to monitor and analyze the actual utilization executed by the mining company's heavy equipment, by using microcontrollers with wireless communication capabilities (GSM/GPRS, WiFi, and Bluetooth) and sensor modules for fuel monitoring and location tracking. Open-source software, such as PHP framework and MySQL database, was utilized to provide a fast and real-time display of daily mine operations. The study provides an online tracking and ticketing system of mine hauling vehicles, introducing a cost-efficient, reliable, and interactive platform for web-based monitoring and real-time telematics [18–20]. This system is specially tailored for the mining industry and their environmental conditions. Measures are made in order to accommodate areas with low mobile network and internet coverage. Unlike other tracking systems [23-27], this tracker module is integrated in the mining industry process, and the data it sends include some mining hauling operation parameters. This helps smoothen out their operations in terms of equipment monitoring and management. Table I shows the differences of the proposed method and the current process used by this project's partner mining company.

TABLE I. PROPOSED SYSTEM VS CURRENT COMPANY OPERATIONS

Parameter	Proposed method	Status quo
Vehicle status	Check status/location instantly	Check status at the end of day, no location tracking
Checker transaction	Wireless transmission, automatic data transfer to server	Paper transactions, Data is manually encoded to the server at the end of day
Data summary	View data in the web anytime of the day	View data in Excel after they are manually encoded after shift (end of day)

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE/METHODOLOGY AND FLOWCHART

Figure 1 indicates the system overview of the study. The details of the system components are shown in Figure 2 and are analyzed below.

Fig. 1. System overview.

- Loading Station: In this station, the Dump Truck (DT) is being loaded with ore in the mine yard. The installed

tracker module in the DT is started. DT location and fuel status are always periodically sent to the cloud every 30s for the whole duration of the trip. This module uses GSM/GPRS communication to send all the data acquired by the DT module to the cloud. If a mobile network signal is not available, the tracker module can save all the acquired data and send them when it acquires a signal later on the trip.

- Checker Station: After ore loading, the equipment, specifically the dump truck, passes through a checker station. There, checker personnel create a trip ticket or Delivery Receipt (MDR) to track the ore's trip. Trip Ticket data are sent back to the DT module to the cloud since checker stations don't have mobile network signals or internet connections. The DT module will send the MDR information once it acquires a mobile network signal later on the trip.
- Receiver Station: In this station, the equipment, specifically the DT, arrives at the stockyard where the ore is expected to be delivered. Receiving personnel send the destination information to the DT module. The DT module then sends it to the cloud. This process completes one trip data and can be viewed on a web application.

Fig. 2. System architecture and flow.

III. HARDWARE, SOFTWARE, AND SYSTEM INTEGRATION

A. Hardware Design

The tracker module design for this system used methods slightly different from the existing technologies [10-13]. This tracker module sends the location and status of the monitored vehicle and carries essential operations' data generated during the trip. Table II shows the comparison of the proposed system with the existing tracker modules [23-27]. The proposed system includes fuel monitoring and integration to smartphones in order to add additional information like vehicle status and driver info. Also, the proposed system is specially tailored for

mining industry conditions in the Philippines, where mobile network coverage is very low. Also, this tracker module is integrated in the mining industry process, and the data it sends include some mining hauling operation parameters.

Fig. 3. Tracker module.

TABLE II. PROPOSED TRACKER VS EXISTING TRACKER MODULES

Parameters	Proposed	Existing tracker modules
GSM/GPRS transmission	Existing	Existing
GPS module	Existing	Existing
Smartphone integration	Existing	None
SD card backup	Existing	Existing
Fuel monitoring	Existing	None
Web integration	Existing	Existing

Two interconnected ESP32 modules with SIM800L, a fuel sensor, and a Micro SD module make up the primary tracker module. A processor unit, short-range wireless communication technology (WiFi and Bluetooth), and a cellular network unit make up the ESP32 module (SIM800L). The two ESP32 modules are connected in a serial communication protocol. The first ESP32 module will receive the external data from other modules such as the checker module, weighbridge, and receiver modules through wireless communication and then send them to the second ESP32 module through serial communication. The second ESP32 module, which is equipped with the SIM800L(GSM/GPRS) module, will send the received data to the cloud. The tracker module is also equipped with a fuel sensor port, which receives the fuel level data of the vehicle. The system also has three indicator LEDs that help the user identify the device's working status. The first LED is the Power LED, which lights up when the system is turned on and has performed all needed initializations, the second is the Bluetooth LED, which lights up when the module is connected to an external device, and the third is the receive data indicator, which lights up when external data are received.

Three switches were also installed in the module. The first switch is the Main Switch, which is responsible for turning the device 'on' and 'off', the second switch is the reset which can be used to reset the device when restarts are needed, and the third is the toggle switch which is used to tell the device to receive external data. An SD card module can also be found in the system. It serves as a temporary data storage device while the data are not yet sent to the server. The data on the SD card are erased once a transmission confirmation is received. If the transmission is not successful, the SD card retains the data until

the module acquires signal to resend them. The SD card is not manually erased since it will not be full from the stored data. A Li-ion battery was used as the system's power supply, which was also partnered with a charging module that controls the system's charging and discharging and protects the battery from overvoltage and undervoltage situations. The modules will be tapped directly into the vehicle's internal power supply. The batteries in this case will act as backup every time the vehicle is turned off, so the tracking may continue. When the vehicle is turned on again, the batteries are automatically recharged. With the battery's capacity of 13.3Wh, and 1.3W average power consumption of the tracker, the battery can last up to 10hrs, until the vehicle is needed to be turned on again to charge it. Since the vehicles are used daily in day and night shifts, there is only little time that the battery is being used, only during transition of drivers and maintenance after shift. A shock-proof rubber was also used in the enclosure to protect the modules from possible external vibrations. The dimensions of this module are 10cm×7cm×4cm.

Fig. 4. Checker module.

The checker module consists of two interconnected ESP32 modules with SIM800L and a micro SD module. The two ESP32 modules are connected in a serial communication protocol. The first ESP32 module will receive the data from an external device with a user interface to create the trip ticket through Bluetooth communication and then send it to the second ESP32 module through serial communication. The checker application has the interface for the checker personnel to enter additional information for the trip (e.g. source of material, destination, shift, department, ore composition, etc.). The app has the ability to check the authenticity of the user checking the current trip. The checker personnel are registered in a database, and the checker app is being synced into that database in order to get the list of the valid personnel. The app then checks the person who is logged-in in the app if he/she is in the list before he/she can proceed with the transactions. The second ESP32 module transmits the received data to the tracker module through WiFi communication. The system has two indicator LEDs that help the user identify the device's working status. The first is the power LED which lights up when the system is turned on and has performed all needed initializations and the second is the Bluetooth LED, which lights up when the module is connected to an external device. Two switches are also installed in the module. The first is the main switch, which is responsible for turning the device 'on' and 'off' and the

second switch is the reset which can be used to reset the device. An SD card module is also installed. This system serves as temporary data storage while the data are not yet forwarded to the tracker module. Like the tracker module, the data on the SD card are also being erased once a transmission confirmation is received to avoid data overflow. A Li-ion battery was used as the system's power supply, which was also partnered with a charging module that controls the system's charging and discharging and protects the battery from overvoltage and undervoltage. The checker station is expected to also have a stand-alone solar station to accommodate the module's charging. Like the tracker module, a shock-proof rubber was also used in the enclosure to protect the modules from external vibrations. The dimensions of this module are 10cm×7cm×4cm.

B. Software

- Arduino IDE 1.8: An open-source software platform used to write programs, while programs can be uploaded directly to the board. This IDE is compatible with ESP32 microcontroller chips and is used to compile and upload programs to an onboard microcontroller unit in the system.
- PHP 7.2 and MySQL 5.5: The system utilized open-source software such as PHP scripting language towards the web development of the study and MySQL database to display the data acquired by the modules during operations.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The full system was tested for 10 days straight, and the testing gathered over 4300 lines of raw data. The system enabled quick tracking/monitoring of the equipment used during hauling operations. The biggest benefit from the system was the easy access in monitoring by the management, which allowed them to have production data in their operations in contradiction to their old methods. In their old method, they were only able to check their production data at the end of the day, which limits them to make adjustments in their operations mid-day. Being able to monitor data so close to real time helped them improve efficiency and optimize their operations.

Fig. 5. System testing.

This system also reduced paper usage, which is responsible for a good amount of their budget. Implementing this system would provide savings to the company in terms of operation cost in the long run. Figure 5 shows the tracker module interacting with the developed android app, which provides the necessary data needed for monitoring. The tracker module sends parameters like the equipment ID, operator ID, department, MDR, status, location, speed, and fuel level and the sensor sends the data. The location sent by the tracker was validated by comparing the values to the readings of Garmin Oregon 750 during field testing. The raw data were received by a web server (Figure 6), which displays the data in tabular form for easy reviewing. The web server also processes the data and translates the latitude and longitude data into actual map locations (Figure 7).

#	DT RFID	OP RFID	DEPARTMENT	MDR	STATUS	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude	Speed	Fuel (l)	Sensor Time
1	244F28-45D4-3C	2980282	PRODUCTION GENERAL	2022 CHC-55461	INSPECTION	8.95541	125.58033	111.72	0.07	60.00	2022-01-01 07:05:40:32
2	244F28-45D4-3C	2980282	PRODUCTION GENERAL	2022 CHC-55461	INSPECTION	8.95527	125.58756	81.8	0.4	59.98	2022-01-01 07:06:02:27
3	244F28-45D4-3C	2980282	PRODUCTION GENERAL	2022 CHC-55461	INSPECTION	8.95522	125.58742	126.06	1.17	59.98	2022-01-01 07:06:03:57
4	244F28-45D4-3C	2980282	PRODUCTION GENERAL	2022 CHC-55461	INSPECTION	8.95952	125.58652	71.15	0.19	59.83	2022-01-01 07:06:07:27
5	244F28-45D4-3C	2980282	PRODUCTION GENERAL	2022 CHC-55461	INSPECTION	8.96044	125.5999	46.71	2.37	59.72	2022-01-01 07:06:08:27
6	244F28-45D4-3C	2980282	PRODUCTION GENERAL	2022 CHC-55461	INSPECTION	8.96045	125.59987	236.61	1.85	59.72	2022-01-01 07:06:09:57
7	244F28-45D4-3C	2980282	PRODUCTION GENERAL	2022 CHC-55461	INSPECTION	8.95972	125.60122	98.12	11.62	59.84	2022-01-01 07:06:18:57

Fig. 6. Monitoring data display on the web.

Fig. 7. Map showing actual track traversed by the equipment.

Fig. 8. Checker app sending data to the checker module.

Figure 8 shows the checker app interacting with the checker module. The checker app and module together send the MDR data to the tracker module consisting of parameters like shift

schedule, activity, ore type, source, destination, distance traveled, fuel consumed, and other mining operation-related parameters. The MDR data are being recorded on the server (Figure 9) and can be tracked if the trips are already completed or still on pending status. The reliability assessment of the data transmission aspect of this research was done by comparing the raw data logs shown in Figure 10 and 11 received from the modules to the data being displayed in the server. The data sent by the modules were sampled periodically and compared to the current display on the Web.

ID	MDR	Type	Date	Shift	Charging	Activity	Status	On Type	UC On Type	N/A	%A	%B	Source	Destination	Stopage ID
SAMPLE	SM		03-Jan-2022			ORE TRANS	---	---	---	---	1.03%	18.02%	MA-2	ST4	ST4
2022-MB-3308	SM		15-Jan-2022			BARGELOADING	---	---	---	---	1.80%	24.50%	MA-2	PL-2	PL-2
2022-MB-7462	SM		15-Jan-2022			ORE MINING	---	---	---	---	2.10%	23.80%	MA-2	PL-2	PL-2
2022-MB-6787	SM		15-Jan-2022			BENEFICATING	---	---	---	---	2.80%	21.40%	MA-2	ST5-3	ST5-3
2022-MB-2070	SM		11-Jan-2022			CRUSHING	---	---	---	---	2.40%	24.20%	MA-2	ST4-4	ST4-4
2022-MB-6308	SM		17-Jan-2022			WASTE MINE	---	---	---	---	2.80%	22.20%	MA-2	ST1-2	ST1-2

Fig. 9. Tabular display of the checker data (trip tickets) on the Web.

```
11:53:22.804 -> AppData: 24:6F:28:46:D4:3C62021-51-09e11:51:56e1ST6ORE MINING&LIM&LF&MA-1&STY-3&PIT1&618132&YES&YES&T7
11:53:22.804 -> Mac_Adv:24:6F:28:46:D4:3C62021-51-09e11:51:56e1ST6ORE MINING&LIM&LF&MA-1&STY-3&PIT1&618132&YES&YES&T7
11:53:22.851 -> Writing file: ./Checker.txt
11:53:22.898 -> File written
```

Fig. 10. Sample raw data logs from the checker module.

```
11:54:44.263 -> Fuel Level = info
11:54:44.263 -> dt_rfid=4C8DA17&op_rfid=9CA94E18&lat=W/A&lng=W/A&speed=W/A&elevation=W/A&current_time=2021-11-09 11:54
11:54:44.404 -> ./File_httpDetail.txt
11:54:44.404 -> Writing file: ./File_httpDetail.txt
11:54:48.153 -> File written
```

Fig. 11. Sample raw data logs from the tracker module

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this research, an automated ticketing and tracking system for mining industry applications was developed. The system was able to monitor pieces of equipment even in areas with low mobile network coverage and no available internet connection. Based on the results, the system showed a big contribution in making the daily operations of mining industries more efficient by providing real-time monitoring and ticketing tools that can be used in process decision- and adjustment- making during operations. The system was able to improve the company's data transfer, from the End-of-Day status to real-time. It was also able to provide faster ticket issuance, improve the safety of the personnel since the operations are done wirelessly, and save on the cost of paper used on the tickets. Eventually, using this automation system will lead to more efficient daily operations, thus potentially increasing the overall output and profitability of the company.

Therefore, the proponents highly recommend this project to the mining industries in the Philippines, which are still using manual ticketing systems and no equipment monitoring, especially those located in low mobile network coverage areas. However, the required personnel responsible for the maintenance and operation for its sustainability in a full-time basis are needed to be trained. Moreover, for future work, the researchers recommend looking for a cheaper alternative in data sending technology since GSM load is relatively expensive in the Philippines.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors wish to acknowledge the support and funding of the Department of Science and Technology - Philippine Council for Industry, Energy, and Emerging Technology Research and Development (DOST-PCIEERD). This project is under the Collaborative R&D to Leverage Philippine Economy (CRADLE) - Science for Change Program (S4CP). Data were obtained through an actual experiment at the mining site of Cagdianao Mining Corporation (CMC).

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Aziz, O. Schelen, and U. Bodin, "A Study on Industrial IoT for the Mining Industry: Synthesized Architecture and Open Research Directions," *IoT*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 529–550, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.3390/iot1020029>.
- [2] I. A. O. Aguayo, M. Nehring, and G. M. W. Ullah, "Optimising Productivity and Safety of the Open Pit Loading and Haulage System with a Surge Loader," *Mining*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 167–179, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/mining1020011>.
- [3] P. G. Dempsey, L. M. Kocher, M. F. Nasarwanji, J. P. Pollard, and A. E. Whitson, "Emerging Ergonomics Issues and Opportunities in Mining," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 15, no. 11, Nov. 2018, Art. no. 2449, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15112449>.
- [4] O. Pasch and S. Uludag, "Optimization of the load-and-haul operation at an opencast colliery," *Journal of the Southern African Institute of Mining and Metallurgy*, vol. 118, no. 5, pp. 449–456, May 2018, <https://doi.org/10.17159/2411-9717/2018/v118n5a1>.
- [5] D. R. Singh and A. K. Mishra, "Review of IT enabled technologies in Indian mining industry for improved productivity amp; safety," in *3rd International Conference on Recent Advances in Information Technology*, Dhanbad, India, Mar. 2016, pp. 613–618, <https://doi.org/10.1109/RAIT.2016.7507969>.
- [6] Q. Cao, B. Bouqata, P. D. Mackenzie, D. Messier, and J. J. Salvo, "A grid-based clustering method for mining frequent trips from large-scale, event-based telematics datasets," in *International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics*, San Antonio, TX, USA, Oct. 2009, pp. 2996–3001, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSMC.2009.5345924>.
- [7] B. Jakkula, G. Mandela, and M. S. Chivukula, "Improvement of overall equipment performance of underground mining machines- a case study," *Advances in Modelling and Analysis A*, vol. 79, no. 1, pp. 6–11, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.18280/mmc>.
- [8] L.-S. Weng, C.-L. Lin, and H.-H. Chang, "Development of a real-time mine auxiliary monitoring system using RF wireless sensor networks," in *13th International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work in Design*, Santiago, Chile, Apr. 2009, pp. 680–685, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSCWD.2009.4968137>.
- [9] M. N. Ramadan, M. A. Al-Khedher, and S. A. Al-Kheder, "Intelligent Anti-Theft and Tracking System for Automobiles," *International Journal of Machine Learning and Computing*, pp. 83–88, 2012, <https://doi.org/10.7763/IJMLC.2012.V2.94>.
- [10] M. Saidani, B. Yannou, Y. Leroy, and F. Cluzel, "Heavy vehicles on the road towards the circular economy: Analysis and comparison with the automotive industry," *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, vol. 135, pp. 108–122, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.06.017>.
- [11] A. Atkins, L. Zhang, and H. Yu, "Applications of RFID and mobile technology in tracking of equipment for maintenance in the mining industry," in *Underground Coal Operators' Conference*, Staffordshire, UK, Feb. 2010, pp. 350–358.
- [12] Q. Cao, P. D. Mackenzie, and J. J. Salvo, "Mining trips from telematics dataset for value-added logistics applications in asset tracking systems," in *International Conference on Service Operations, Logistics and Informatics*, Chicago, IL, USA, Jul. 2009, pp. 135–139, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SOLI.2009.5203918>.

- [13] R. Parasuraman, T. B. Sheridan, and C. D. Wickens, "A model for types and levels of human interaction with automation," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics - Part A: Systems and Humans*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 286–297, Feb. 2000, <https://doi.org/10.1109/3468.844354>.
- [14] D. K. Ahangaran, A. B. Yasrebi, A. Wetherelt, and P. Foster, "Real-time dispatching modelling for trucks with different capacities in open pit mines," *Archives of Mining Sciences*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 39–52, Oct. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10267-012-0003-8>.
- [15] M. Farahpoor and E. Sabouri, "Robust telematics health monitoring and dispatching management system based on IoT and M2M Technologies," *PeerJ*, vol. 4, pp. 1–9, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.7287/peerj.preprints.27087v1>.
- [16] A. Johari *et al.*, "Tank Water Level Monitoring System using GSM Network," *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 1114–1120, 2011.
- [17] D. K. Yadav, P. Mishra, and S. K. Das, "Study of real-time miner tracking using wireless sensor area network," in *International Conference on Microwave, Optical and Communication Engineering*, Bhubaneswar, India, Dec. 2015, pp. 330–333, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMOCE.2015.7489759>.
- [18] R. Cuasito and C. Namoco, "Trends in Industrial Automation and Academic Initiatives in the Philippines: Assessment and Analysis of Mechatronics-Enabling Technologies, Skill Set Demands, and Academic Relevance," *International Journal of Automation Technology*, vol. 6, pp. 757–764, Nov. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.20965/ijat.2012.p0757>.
- [19] A. T. Demetillo and E. B. Taboada, "Real-Time Water Quality Monitoring For Small Aquatic Area Using Unmanned Surface Vehicle," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 3959–3964, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2661>.
- [20] A. T. Demetillo, R. Y. Capangpangan, M. C. Bonotan, J. P. B. Lagare, and E. B. Taboada, "Real-time detection of cyanide in surface water and its automated data acquisition and dissemination system," *Nature Environment and Pollution Technology: An International Quarterly Scientific Journal*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 395–402, 2020.
- [21] S. Zafar, G. Miraj, R. Baloch, D. Murtaza, and K. Arshad, "An IoT Based Real-Time Environmental Monitoring System Using Arduino and Cloud Service," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3238–3242, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2144>.
- [22] K. Gorenekli and Y. Becerikli, "Development of Electronic Water Meter Based on Wireless Network and RF," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 3905–3908, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2556>.
- [23] L. Wheeler, R. Podoloff, M. Vosseller, E. Chen, and B. Marcus, "Location tracking system," WO2008085555A3, Nov. 06, 2008.
- [24] Q. Huang, X. Chen, and J. Nie, "GPS and GSM mixed positioning control device," CN203773057U, Aug. 13, 2014.
- [25] M. Zlojutro, "Vehicle tracking and monitoring system," US7701363B1, Apr. 20, 2010.
- [26] R. Wagner, V. Lee, and R. Phillips, "Gps tracking system and method employing public portal publishing location data," US20130104035A1, Apr. 25, 2013.
- [27] V. Callegari, "GPS receiver comprising a data link via GPRS and/or UMTS," EP2023155A1, Feb. 11, 2009.

Realistic Determination of Live Loads on Various Reinforced Concrete Structures

Zuhairuddin Soomro

Department of Civil Engineering
Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering,
Science & Technology
Larkano Campus, Pakistan
zuhairuddin@quest.edu.pk

Salim Khoso

Department of Civil Engineering
Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering,
Science & Technology
Larkano Campus, Pakistan
enr.salimkhoso@gmail.com

Tariq Ali

Department of Civil Engineering
The Islamia University of
Bahawalpur
Bahawalpur, Pakistan
tariqdehraj@gmail.com

Suhail Ahmed Abbasi

Department of Civil Engineering
Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering,
Science & Technology
Larkano Campus, Pakistan
abbasi.suhail2009@gmail.com

Abdul Aziz Ansari

Department of Civil Engineering
Faculty of Engineering, Science,
Technology and Management
Ziauddin University
Karachi, Sindh, Pakistan
aziz.ansari@zu.edu.pk

Muhammad Tayyab Naqash

Department of Civil Engineering
Faculty of Engineering
Islamic University of Madinah
Saudi Arabia
enr.tayyabnaqash@gmail.com

Received: 27 January 2022 | Revised: 8 February 2022 and 20 February 2022 | Accepted: 21 February 2022

Abstract-This paper presents various case studies of examined and calculated live loads on reinforced concrete structures. These case studies accumulated information and data of existing structures about their design live loads and acquired detailed drawings showing the reinforcement in their floor slab sections. The actual occupancy loads that act on the floor slabs were assessed, and the ultimate loads that an individual slab section should be able to support were calculated using the methods recommended by ACI, CP-114, CP-110, and the yield line theory. A reinforced concrete slab panel was also tested to check the validity of the theoretically predicted ultimate loads. The results were compared to find a safety margin and, if necessary, recommend lower live load outlines for cost reduction. The case studies showed that there is sufficient margin to reduce design live loads on the floor slabs of residential buildings, especially in multistory apartment blocks. Moreover, it was found that the live loads, especially on residential buildings, could be decreased to two-thirds of the code values without risking floor overloading.

Keywords-structures; loads; economy; case study; occupancy; slab; reinforcement

I. INTRODUCTION

Generally, loads are classified as dead loads, live loads, including people, supplies, and machines, environmental loads, including rains and snow loads, lateral loads, such as wind and blasts, dynamic loads due to earthquakes, upward loads, such as those due to water, earth pressure, waves, and ice, and loads induced by temperature and shrinkage [1]. Among these, dead loads can be determined with a high degree of certainty. Snow and rain loads are very rare in Pakistan. The wind has a pronounced impact on tall buildings having more than 10-15 stories and has little significance in public or common

residential buildings [2, 3]. Using the maximum possible values given by the standards for the loads increases construction costs [4, 5]. For these reasons, probabilistic considerations are used to determine design loads. Moreover, the design values of live loads are very rarely reached during the life spans of many structures [6, 7]. The load values are usually based on recommendations of foreign standards, which are very conservative compared to the actual live loads on floor slabs in Pakistan. Therefore, more realistic live loads should be determined for the design of the structures. Assuming that a typical person weighs 68kg and occupies a space of 0.37m², it has a live load of about 185kg/m². People can be overloaded to produce a maximum load of 610kg/m². However, such occupancy in a large area is very unlikely. Another factor that also affects the decision regarding the intensity of live loads is that the probability of achieving the full design live loads on an entire floor decreases as its area increases. To incorporate this fact, building codes suggest live load reductions. One common way to achieve this is to reduce live load values for areas larger than 14m² at a rate of 0.08% per m² up to a reduction of 60% [8, 9], but this reduction does not apply to public assembly buildings. Certain types of live loads may produce dynamic effects. However, more commonly, these are not considered explicitly, since a complete analysis would be excessively time-consuming [10, 11]. The live loads are conservative enough to account for increased stresses caused by the structure's vibration [12-15].

II. PRESENT INVESTIGATION

A combined effect of both load enhancement and the safety factors of the materials allows a structure to withstand the imposed loads, which could vary even several times more than

the loads for which it was intended [16]. The safety factor ensures that a reasonable margin exists between the maximum operating load of the component and its load capacity. It has been common practice to introduce idealization, approximation, and larger bending moments based on conventional methods to design structures for a long time, increasing safety margins. Although incidental overload can occur, the question arises of whether it can be possible to accommodate such massive loads to exhaust all the strength of the floor [17]. A reliability analysis exhibits an almost infinite load on a slab in monolithic connections with the structural members for its complete collapse. As an example, on the eve of the cricket World Cup celebration, it was observed that a balcony of a house having dimensions of 1×5 m was jam-packed with almost 30 people. The people were weighing 2040 kg approximately, which is equivalent to 458 kg/m^2 . From the technical details of the slabs, the ultimate load-carrying capacity was calculated to be about $3,806 \text{ kg/m}^2$. Nevertheless, this is one case of the overloadings that must be considered while proposing a realistic value of live loads. For this reason, the ACI code recommended a live load of 488 kg/m^2 for balconies and a minimum of 293 kg/m^2 when the area of the balcony of a residential building does not exceed 9 m^2 [18, 19].

This study examined a wide variety of existing Reinforced Cement Concrete (RCC) buildings in different towns and cities of the Sindh province in Pakistan, including primary and secondary schools, urban and rural hospitals, mosques, residential villas, luxurious apartments, and multistory shopping centers and malls. Technical data of buildings in terms of slab thickness, size, spacing, and arrangement of reinforcement bars were obtained, and the intensity of live loads acting on these slabs was assessed. The ultimate live loads were calculated by employing the methods recommended by ACI [17], CP-114 [18], CP-110 [19], and yield line theory. A yield value of 275 MPa was adopted for steel. Wherever the principles of Limit State Design were applied, the partial safety factors for loads were presumed to be equal to unity. The bending moment factors for the calculations were selected from the respective design standards' tables wherever appropriate. A wide variety of chosen case studies are presented in the following sections [23-25].

A. Multistory Building

This building was under construction during the investigation. The structural frame with floor slabs was already complete while dividing masonry walls were being erected. There was a large stack of bricks on the first-floor slab, soaked with water. The stack was approximately 1.5 m in height and consisted of about 1000 bricks weighing about 3,450 kg. The room's total area was 12.25 m^2 (3.5×3.5 m). Adding the weight of 6 workers and 2 visitors, which is about 545 kg, the total imposed load on the floor area was equal to 326 kg/m^2 . This is much higher than the design live-load of 145 kg/m^2 . However, from technical data, the slab was reinforced with main bars of 13 mm diameter placed at 150 mm c/c and distribution bars of 10 mm diameter placed at 230 mm c/c. The minimum standard load-carrying capacity, shown in Table I, was $1,693 \text{ kg/m}^2$, which is 5.3 times more than the actual imposed load. Thus, there is a possibility of reducing the design live-load without

risking the stability and durability of the structure. It is expected that the actual occupancy loads of this flat, under normal circumstances, would not be more than the Villa's [26-27].

B. Residential Villa

The residential Villa was a double-story building that was assessed to have a total live load of 455 kg, including all items of daily use, on a total floor area of 21 m^2 . This can be compared with the lowest live load of 1450 kg/m^2 calculated based on the elastic theory method and the recommendations of CP-114. This building had a considerable inherent margin of safety. Even in occasional overload due to visitors on a festivity, the load will never touch the ultimate mark of 1665 kg/m^2 calculated based on CP-110. Therefore, there is enough margin to reduce the design live loads by reducing reinforcing steel and cost without sacrificing safety.

C. Vocational Training Center

This building was a women's vocational training center with large halls occupied by professionals and trainees who sew, knit, embroider, and create patterns on clothing while many visitors were also wandering around. During peak hours, in the afternoon, the center was estimated to be jam-packed, and there would be approximately one person per 0.4 m^2 of the corridor area. This would mean that the live loads of people would be about 183 kg/m^2 , which is not constant but is probably the maximum that could be reached. Allowing 4.5 kgs per person as the weight of personal belongings, the average live load is approximately 195 kg/m^2 . This may be compared with the minimum estimated live load of 757 kg/m^2 from yield line theory. Therefore, there is a lot of room for live load reduction. Within the shops (3×9 m), the occupancy loads of workers, sewing machines, and other items were estimated at 41.5 kg/m^2 , which is much less than the design live load of 293 kg/m^2 recommended by the British standard.

D. Community Marriage Hall

This building was examined on a weekend night during a marriage. People were sitting on the floor, which was covered with a thick carpet. The number of persons sitting on the floor was counted and calculated approximately one per 0.3 m^2 of the floor area. This load was too high and probably the maximum that could be accommodated within that space. Therefore, the live load per m^2 of the persons was approximately 210 kg/m^2 . Adding the additional loads of moveable items, approximately at 24 kg/m^2 , the total live load becomes 234 kg/m^2 . This can be compared with the minimum standard estimated live load of 713 kg/m^2 based on the yield line theory. It seems that there is also a substantial margin of safety in this case, and therefore, the live load could be reduced to some extent.

E. Primary School Building

This is a standard design adopted by the Education Works Department for the construction of primary schools in various towns and villages of the Sindh province. The original plan consists of only the ground floor with a provision of a first floor when it becomes essential. The classrooms were 5×6 m wide, with a central beam that divided the floor slab into two panels of 3×5 m. On the floor, the load would be that of

children and benches. The benches and the average weight of the children were supposed to be around 32kg. The benches were arranged in two rows, each bench being 2m long. Six children were sitting on each bench. However, 69 students were sitting in the classroom during the investigation. In front, there was a table weighing about 18kg and a chair for the instructor. It was estimated that the weight of each bench was approximately 27kg. Therefore, the total live load on the floor was 2,817kg. The maximum live load using the recommendations of CP-114 was calculated to 1,400kg/m², which can be compared with the actual live load of 98kg/m². The highest ultimate standard load was 2,918kg/m². So again, the margin of safety and, therefore, room for reduction in design live loads is sufficient.

F. Library Building

Libraries are a common feature of cities and an integral part of almost all educational institutions, including high schools, colleges, and universities. This study examined the library building in Moro city. The highest standard ultimate load was 3,270kg/m² for CP-110, while the minimum was found for CP-114 and could be taken as a safe load that the slab was capable of carrying without the stresses exceeding their permitted values. The steel almirahs in the library were placed side by side beside the walls, almost touching the ceiling. Books are heavy items and therefore their load is also considerable, but as they are placed beside the wall along the periphery of the room, their load induces a relatively small bending moment. The loads of furniture and persons divided by the floor area were estimated at less than 58kg/m². However, considering a specific weight of books at 244kg/m² and the total number of books accommodated per panel of the slab, it was found that the uniformly distributed load due to books would be 234kg/m². Therefore, the total actual live load was 292kg/m².

G. Boys Hostel

The work drawings of the Quaid-e-Awam University College of Engineering, Science & Technology Larkana Hostel and the utilized steel during the construction of the slab were used to calculate the loads. Although the hostel rooms were designed to accommodate three students each, four students were living in each room. There were 4 beds, 4 chairs, and 2 study tables. Assuming 4 visitors and 45kg for each boy's personal belongings, including books, clothes, etc., the total live load on the floor slab would be equal to 980kg. This can be compared with the lowest standard ultimate live load of 2,152kg/m² calculated based on CP-114. The difference between actual and standard loads is so high that it can be undoubtedly deduced that the design live loads could have been reduced to decrease the cost of construction. During the games, a large number of students gather in the corridor to watch the match, standing along the periphery. The number of students was estimated to be one per 0.5m² of the corridor area. In that case, the live load would be in the range of 122kg/m². This is much less than the load-carrying capacity of the slabs and reasonably less than the design live load.

H. Shopping Center

This shopping center is a double-story building in the heart of Larkana city. As the number of visitors seems quite

considerable, the live load should not be less than 150kg/m² on the corridor, taking into account one person per 0.5m² and 2.5kg of personal belongings, and 60kg/m² in the shops. Thus, the live load prescribed for such public buildings is almost twice the design imposed. The standard live load carrying capacity of the floor slab was found to be between 483kg/m² and 1327kg/m².

I. Shopping Mall

This building is located in Hyderabad city. It consists of a basement, a ground floor, and five upper floors. It is a typical example of public buildings with a highly uncertain live load. The loads in stores and corridors were calculated separately, and depending on the heavier items placed in the stores and the extensive mobility of people in the corridors, it was inferred that the loads would not be less than in the previous case of the shopping center. However, as the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th floors were residential apartments, their slabs were reinforced with the same diameter bars and spacing as those of the lower slabs. They were also reinforced with 13mm diameter bars at 150mm c/c with alternate bars bent up. The distribution bars had a 10mm diameter at 200mm c/c. For the residential floors, the margin is quite significant because the calculated live loads are as high as 2,098kg/m².

J. University Corridor

This corridor consists of closely spaced columns 2.7m c/c, a relatively smaller width of 3.5m as clear span as compared to the total corridor length of 22m. The corridor was designed for a total load of 975kg/m², including the dead load and the live load of 490kg/m². The design was accomplished following the elastic theory method. At any given time, it was observed that the number of persons passing never exceeds a single group of 5 or 6 people on a single panel. However, there is the possibility of large groups of students passing through the corridor occasionally. Assuming that the corridor would be jam-packed with an average of one person per 0.4m², the live load would be equal to 183kg/m², which is only 15% of the ultimate strength of 1,170kg/m² given by CP-110. Therefore, there is an enormous scope of reduction.

K. Community Mosque

A multistory mosque was visited on a Friday when most of the people gather to pray. Although many people were sitting closely, people were found sitting sparsely on the first floor. However, it was observed that during prayer, each person requires a strip of 0.5m width and 1.5m length on average, having an area of approximately 0.75m². Therefore, the average live load is equal to 102.5kg/m². During the sermon, people do not sit in proper rows but gather together randomly, and the load in such a case was estimated at 234kg/m², at the rate of one person per 0.3m². This is approximately 12% of the maximum ultimate load of 1,908kg/m² imposed by CP-110.

L. Public Hospital

The uncertainty on the maximum intensity of live loads and the fluctuation of the occupancy load from point to point and time to time is large. However, in private rooms, the load intensity was not found to be much greater than in standard residential bedrooms. However, in casualty and general wards,

the live loads due to visitors and other persons, including staff, other accompanied persons, and those waiting for their turn, are quite high. The maximum standard ultimate load, in this case, was specified as $2,465\text{kg/m}^2$ by the yield line theory, while the

minimum standard ultimate live load was 937kg/m^2 using CP-114. The maximum intensity of the actual load was estimated at 145kg/m^2 for casualties and 39kg/m^2 for private rooms. Therefore, a reduction of the design live load is possible.

TABLE I. ULTIMATE LIVE LOADS FOR THE FLOOR SLABS OF THE STUDIED BUILDINGS

	Case Study	CP-114	CP-110	ACI	Yield line	Assessed load	Code value	Code
		kg/m^2	kg/m^2	kg/m^2	kg/m^2	kg/m^2	kg/m^2	
1	Multistory building	1693	3748	3123	3016	364	147	B
2	Residential villa	1450	1665	1498	1566	22	147	B
3	Vocational training center	864	2157	1581	757	234	390	B
4	Community marriage hall	1161	2435	2415	713	234	488	B
5	Primary school building	1400	2206	2669	2918	98	292	B
6	Library	1742	3270	3050	2723	292	60 reading room 150 stack room 80 corridor	A A A
7	Boys hostel	2152	3428	3953	3621	49	195	B
8	Shopping center	483	1327	1161	1142	210	390	B
9	Shopping mall	1020	2098	1801	1483	151	390	B
10	University corridor	3118	5719	5372	3240	183	390	A
11	Community mosque	844	1908	1630	1327	337	0	B
12	Public hospital	937	2128	1835	2465	185	195	B

III. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

A square RCC slab panel in a monolithic connection with an edge beam on all four sides with an effective span equal to 600mm and an overall thickness of 50mm was tested by applying a point load at its center. The slab was reinforced with a 3mm diameter wire, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The Reinforcement cage.

Fig. 2. Testing arrangement of the model.

Finite element software was used to analyze and design the model, employing a 4-nodded rectangular plate bending element with 3 degrees of freedom at each node. The design flexural load was maintained at 10kN. The punching shear strength of the slab and its ultimate flexural strength based on the actual material properties were determined in the laboratory. Figure 2 shows the testing arrangement of the mode. The calculated live load carrying capacity based on flexure and punching shear was compared with the experimental ultimate load. The behavior of the model was studied in terms of load-displacement history, crack pattern, strain in concrete, mode of failure, and ultimate load [19, 20].

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

From the case studies and the experimental results obtained, it can be deduced that the live loads adopted for the design of floor slabs are only a small amount of the total load-carrying capacity of the slab, computed based on the strength of concrete, the ratio of reinforcement steel, and boundary conditions. Therefore, there is enough margin to reduce the design live loads and consequently the steel ratio and thus to reduce the cost of materials. However, it was also observed that there are not only live loads but standard requirements for a minimum ratio of reinforcing steel, including distribution steel and partial safety factors, that cause the increase in the moment of resistance of the floor slabs. Thus there is not only the occupancy loads but there are several other aspects as well that must also be studied before concluding, such as creep of concrete, corrosion of steel, temperature stresses, occasional fires, probability of unforeseen drastic overloading, shock loading, lateral loading, redistribution of stresses between concrete and steel and consequently shifting of the neutral axis, quality of workmanship, use of standard materials, human errors during construction, and unexpected behavior of soil beneath the foundation. By examining only the load-carrying capacity and the live loads, it can be asserted that live loads, particularly on residential buildings, could be reduced to the 2/3 of standard values without risking floor overloading. During this investigation, it was observed that in all cases the

slabs were designed and reinforcement was provided based on empirical values of bending moment coefficients, enhancing the load-carrying capacity of the slab un-proportionately. More economical sections could be reached if moment fields are predicted with the help of finite element analysis. This explains how the ultimate live loads in all case studies are far higher than the design code value of occupancy loads [20].

V. SUGGESTIONS

The scope of this study could be extended to a broader range of public buildings in metropolitan cities, such as Karachi and Lahore in Pakistan or any other part of the world. A systematic investigation should be carried out on the floor areas where heavy concentrated loads of equipment and machinery are expected. It is also imperative to investigate the matter more objectively and study the long-term effects on the stability and durability of buildings if the reinforcement is reduced based on reduced design live loads. Furthermore, no matter how rare, there is always a possibility of strong wind currents during a storm, which might cause over-stressing of the slab, which would then act as coupling media to resist the overturning effect of the lateral wind forces. This is where the additional moment of resistance due to higher design live loads would provide an extra margin of safety against failure. Other sources of uncertainty, such as steel corrosion, concrete cover splitting, temperature stresses due to occasional exposure to fire, unexpected behavior of the soil beneath the foundation, and human errors during construction, should also be investigated.

VI. CONCLUSION

The presented case studies showed that there is sufficient margin to reduce the design live loads on the floor slabs of residential buildings, particularly in multistory apartment blocks, reducing their construction cost. By considering the load-carrying capacity and occupancy loads, it can be affirmed that live loads, especially on residential buildings, could be decreased to two-thirds of the code values without risking floor overloading. Experimentally, the actual strength of the RCC slabs was several times higher than the design loads and the ultimate loads proposed by the standards. Therefore, there is enough margin to reduce construction cost by reducing the amount of reinforcement, providing that serviceability limits and code provisions regarding minimum reinforcing and distribution steel are not disregarded.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was carried out in the Structures Laboratory of Civil Engineering Department, Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering Science & Technology (QUEST), Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan. The authors express their appreciation to the university authorities for providing the facilities and funds for this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Memon, A. A. Ansari, and B. A. Memon, "A Review of Intensity of Live Loads on RCC Floor Slabs," *Mehran University Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 15–25, 1996.
- [2] M. Memon and A. A. Ansari, "A Study of Occupancy Loads in Residential and Public Buildings in Pakistan," *A Study of Occupancy Loads in Residential and Public Buildings in Pakistan*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 145–150, 1998.
- [3] M. T. Naqash, K. Mahmood, and S. Khoso, "An Overview on the Seismic Design of Braced Frames," *American Journal of Civil Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 41–47, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajce.20140202.15>.
- [4] S. Khoso, J. Raad, and A. Parvin, "Experimental Investigation on the Properties of Recycled Concrete Using Hybrid Fibers," *Open Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 09, no. 02, Apr. 2019, Art. no. 91812, <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojcm.2019.92009>.
- [5] S. A. Mangi *et al.*, "A Review on Potential use of Coal Bottom Ash as a Supplementary Cementing Material in Sustainable Concrete Construction," *International Journal of Integrated Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 9, 2018.
- [6] S. A. Mangi, M. H. W. Ibrahim, S. H. Khahro, N. Jamaluddin, and S. Shahidan, "Development of Supplementary Cementitious Materials: A Systematic Review," *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, vol. 29, no. 9, pp. 4682–4691, 2020.
- [7] Y. Almoosi and N. Oukaili, "The Response of a Highly Skewed Steel I-Girder Bridge with Different Cross-Frame Connections," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7349–7357, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4137>.
- [8] M. T. Naqash, G. D. Matteis, and A. D. Luca, "Seismic design of steel moment resisting frames-European versus American practice," *NED University Journal of Engineering Research*, Oct. 2012.
- [9] A. H. Bhutto, G. S. Bhurgri, S. Zardari, M. A. Zardari, B. A. Memon, and M. M. Babar, "Settlement Response of a Multi-Story Building," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6220–6223, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3757>.
- [10] A. Soltani, S. Khoso, M. A. Keerio, and A. Formisano, "Assessment of Physical and Mechanical Properties of Concrete Produced from Various Portland Cement Brands," *Open Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 9, no. 4, Sep. 2019, Art. no. 95273, <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojcm.2019.94020>.
- [11] M. H. Naqash, M. H. Aburamadan, O. Harireche, A. AlKassem, and Q. U. Farooq, "The Potential of Wind Energy and Design Implications on Wind Farms in Saudi Arabia," *International Journal of Renewable Energy Development*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 839–856, 2021.
- [12] S. Khoso, M. A. Keerio, and A. A. Ansari, "Effects of Rice Husk Ash and Recycled Aggregates on Mechanical Properties of Concrete," *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 1832–1835, Mar. 2017.
- [13] M. Jovanović and G. Radoičić, "A Human Crowd Effect Modelled by the Discrete-Time Fourier Series," *Facta Universitatis, Series: Working and Living Environmental Protection*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 139–148, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.22190/FUWLEP1702139J>.
- [14] M. Naqash, "Study on the Fundamental Period of Vibration of Steel Moment Resisting Frames," *International Journal of Advanced Structures and Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 2319–2324, Jan. 2014.
- [15] M. Oad, A. H. Buller, B. A. Memon, and N. A. Memon, "Impact of Long-Term Loading on Reinforced Concrete Beams Made with Partial Replacement of Coarse Aggregates with Recycled Aggregates from Old Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3818–3821, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2498>.
- [16] S. Khoso, K. J. Shahzaib, A. A. Aziz, and K. Z. Hussain, "Experimental investigation on the properties of cement concrete partially replaced by silica fume and fly ash," *Journal of Applied Engineering Science*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 345–350, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.5937/jaes14-11116>.
- [17] S. Khoso, F. Wagan, J. Khan, N. Bhatti, and A. Ansari, "Qualitative analysis of baked clay bricks available in Larkana region, Pakistan," *Architecture Civil Engineering Environment*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 41–50, 2014.
- [18] M. T. Naqash, Q. U. Farooq, and O. Harireche, "Seismic Evaluation of Steel Moment Resisting Frames (MRFs)—Supported by Loose Granular Soil," *Open Journal of Earthquake Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, Mar. 2019, Art. no. 91464, <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojer.2019.82003>.

- [19] S. A. A. Shah, M. A. A. Gul, T. Naqash, Z. Khan, and M. Rizwan, "Effects of Fiber Reinforcements on the Strength of Shotcrete," *Civil Engineering and Architecture*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 176–183, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.13189/cea.2021.090115>.
- [20] American Concrete Institute (ACI), Building code requirements for structural concrete (ACI 318-14): an ACI standard and commentary on building code requirements for structural concrete (ACI 318R-14). Farmington Hills, MI, USA: American Concrete Institute, ACI, 2014.
- [21] "Structural Codes of Practice. CP 114 : The Structural Use of Reinforced Concrete in Buildings," British Standards Institute, CP 114, 1965.
- [22] "Structural Codes of Practice. CP 110:1:1972 for the structural use of concrete. Part 1: Design, materials and workmanship," British Standards Institute, CP 110:1:1972, 1972.
- [23] M. T. Naqash and A. Alluqmani, "Codal Requirements Using Capacity Design Philosophy, and Their Applications in the Design of Steel Structures in Seismic Zones," *Open Journal of Earthquake Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 88–107, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojer.2018.72006>.
- [24] M. T. Naqash, "Codal Comparisons for the Seismic Resistance of Steel Moment Resisting Frames (MRF). Part A: Codes Approach," *International Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 254–263, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.ijcem.20170606.04>.
- [25] M. Umar, S. A. A. Shah, K. Shahzada, M. T. Naqash, and W. Ali, "Assessment of Seismic Capacity for Reinforced Concrete Frames with Perforated Unreinforced Brick Masonry Infill Wall," *Civil Engineering Journal*, vol. 6, no. 12, pp. 2397–2415, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-2020-03091625>.
- [26] M. Mumtaz, J. Mendoza, A. S. Vosoughi, A. S. Unger, and V. K. Goel, "A Comparative Biomechanical Analysis of Various Rod Configurations Following Anterior Column Realignment and Pedicle Subtraction Osteotomy," *Neurospine*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 587–596, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.14245/ns.2142450.225>.
- [27] M. T. Naqash, "Pushover Response of Multi Degree of Freedom Steel Frames," *Civil Engineering Journal*, vol. 6, pp. 86–97, Dec. 2020, [https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-2020-SP\(EMCE\)-08](https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-2020-SP(EMCE)-08).

Optimization of Load Ranking and Load Shedding in a Power System Using the Improved AHP Algorithm

Trong Nghia Le

Electrical and Electronics Department
HCMC University of Technology and Education
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
trongnghia@hcmute.edu.vn

Minh Vu Nguyen Hoang

Urban Engineering Department
HCMC University of Architecture
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
vu.nguyenhoangminh@uah.edu.vn

Thai An Nguyen

Electrical and Electronics Department
Cao Thang Technical College
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
nguyenthaian@caothang.edu.vn

Trieu Tan Phung

Electrical and Electronics Department
Cao Thang Technical College
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
phungtrieutan@caothang.edu.vn

Buu Dao Phan

Electrical and Electronics Department
HCMC University of Technology and Education
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
2180602@student.hcmute.edu.vn

Received: 21 February 2022 | Revised: 12 March 2022 | Accepted: 20 March 2022

Abstract-This paper proposes a method of load ranking and load shedding in a power system based on the calculation of the priority weighting continuity of the power supply of loads and the improved AHP algorithm. The proposed method applies the theories of covariance between objects, correlation, and fuzzy preference to develop a fuzzy preference correlation matrix based on the percentage of Vital Load, Semi Vital Load, and Non-Vital Load at each load bus. This matrix replaces the judgment matrix of the traditional AHP algorithm to form the criteria layers and scheme layers of the problem. The priority weighting continuity of the power supply of loads is continuously calculated and updated according to the load profile and is used to distribute the load shedding power to each load bus. This distribution optimizes the objective function and maximizes the load benefits, thereby minimizing the damages due to load shedding. The traditional AHP method and the proposed method are applied to the IEEE 30 bus system and the result comparison demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed method.

Keywords-optimal load shedding; load ranking; AHP; improved AHP; correlation

I. INTRODUCTION

Load shedding often occurs in order to optimize the operation, in a case of emergency, or due to power shortage of the power system. There are many studies interested in the problem of load shedding in a power system [1-3], however, to the best of our knowledge, the economic loss of load shedding has not yet been taken into account. To ensure the initiative in

planned load break or optimal load shedding without unduly affecting the interests of customers and electricity suppliers in the competitive electricity market, the loads of the system are required to be classified and ranked according to priorities in the power supply continuity.

There are many studies on load classification and ranking [4, 5]. A microgrid system constantly evaluates and prioritizes the loads in the system to propose load management strategies to control the power generation dispatch of the power sources in the system. In [6], loads are classified into three types and are considered as schedulable variables based on their characteristics and importance. Thereby, the microgrid optimization reduces the operating costs of the system. The methods used to classify loads in the power system suggest the use of ISODATA algorithm to classify customers based on information supplied by the customers and load profile [7]. In [8], the authors propose a model of load classification according to a five-stage process developed on the summary and analysis of studies on load classification in a smart grid environment. A classification method based on fuzzy c-means (FCM) is presented. In [9], the authors show how to extract Characteristic Attributes of the Frequency Domain (CAFDs) and use these CAFDs to form a hierarchy of load profiles that can be used as system framework for load classification of customers.

The ranking of load shedding is applied quite commonly. In [10], the authors propose load shedding based on the AHP

Corresponding author: Trong Nghia Le

method to stabilize the voltage of the power system. Thus, a simple and flexible load shedding model can be developed. This method is based on the assessment of experts from different backgrounds, so it is subjective. In [11], a method for load shedding based on priority demand is proposed with a combination of wind power. Higher priority loads are connected to a wind power source that protects them from shedding under emergency conditions. This is done by real-time monitoring of the power system accompanied by shedding of lower priority loads. In [12], the authors propose the development of a load shedding strategy based on load priority. Thereby, loads with high priority demand will be connected to an emergency power source and at the same time, loads with lower priority demand will be shed.

In this paper, a method of load ranking and shedding in the system based on the improved AHP algorithm to calculate the power supply priority weighting of loads is proposed. This calculation is consistent with the actual load classification, allowing the system operator to be proactive in planned load shedding or load shedding due to system failure. In addition, this method eliminates the expert factor in traditional AHP calculation and incorporates economic conditions. The load shedding strategy of the proposed method is objective, helping to reduce the shedding power and to minimize the damage to the system and the customers while it optimizes the objective function and load benefits.

II. PRIORITY RANKING OF POWER SUPPLY CONTINUITY LOADS BASED ON THE IMPROVED AHP ALGORITHM

Priority ranking of loads in the power system is important in ensuring the reliability of the power supply for the loads that are considered important and are highly ranked in the system. The loads in the power system are classified in three types by their priority level: type 1 (Vital load or priority load type 1), type 2 (Semi-Vital load or priority load type 2), and type 3 (Non-Vital load or priority load type 3) [13, 14]. Type 1 load is a type of load that is continuously power supplied, and in case of power failure, it will cause extremely serious consequences. This type of load includes mines, hospitals, loads of steelworks, blast furnaces, etc. In addition, it also disrupts order and affects international politics, such as loads of embassies, public cultural works, etc. Type 2 load is a type of load that, if the power is lost, will cause economic losses such as production shortage, increase of by-products, waste of work, etc. Type 3 load is a type of load that allows power outage, which are civil works, welfare works, and residential areas. In the grid diagrams, the load buses usually have high capacity. The case of feeder lines including only one priority load type is quite rare. These loads will be actually collected and from there the percentage of each type of loads on those feeder lines will be summarized. From the power percentages of these loads, an improved AHP method based on statistical math, Pearson correlation math, and Spearman correlation will be applied to calculate the optimal weights of each respective load bus. From this result, we can rank priority loads that need to be power supplied uninterruptedly and the load power that needs to be shed at each bus when there are many priority loads.

The improved AHP method applied in this paper is a combination of the traditional AHP method and fuzzy

preference relation theory. Based on the percentage of priority load types at each load bus, the theory of variance and covariance is applied to calculate the quantitative value and develop a judgment matrix according to the pairs of load type criteria: Type 1 load, type 2 load, and type 3 load of the criteria layer. From this judgment matrix, the weights of each load type in the criteria layer are determined. The value of variance between elements of each type of load of each criterion is used to develop a fuzzy preference correlation matrix. This matrix is used to replace the judgment matrix of the scheme layer to calculate the weights of the loads of each type. The weights of the criteria layer and the scheme layer are combined to get the power supply continuity priority weighting of each load. The process of calculating the power supply continuity priority weighting and distributing load shedding power of the proposed method is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The process of calculating the power supply continuity priority weighting and distributing load shedding power.

The process of calculating the priority weighting continuity of power supply includes the following steps:

- Develop a hierarchical model of the AHP algorithm, in which the criteria layer includes the load types and the scheme layer includes loads in the power system. The hierarchical model of the AHP algorithm to calculate the power supply continuity priority weighting of loads is presented in Figure 2.
- Calculate the weights of the criteria layer.
- Calculate the weights of the scheme layer.
- Calculate the combined weights.

Details of the process of calculating the weights of the criteria layer and the scheme layer are presented below.

Fig. 2. The hierarchical model of the improved AHP algorithm to calculate the power supply continuity priority weighting of the loads.

A. Calculating the Weights of the Criteria Layer

The criteria layer of the model of the calculation of the power supply continuity priority weighting represents the load types in the system. The percentages of the load types of each load show the importance of those loads. The process of calculating the weights of the criteria layer is shown in Figure 1 and is in accordance with the following steps:

1) Step 1: Set up the Covariance Matrix between the Criteria

The covariance of the criteria is calculated to form the covariance matrix. The criteria of this problem are the load types (Vital Load, Semi Vital Load, Non-Vital Load) in the power system. The covariance matrix of the criteria ε_i and ε_j is expressed as ε_{ij} [15]. The model of the steps of calculating the criteria weights is shown in Figure 2. The covariance matrix between the criteria has the following form:

$$\varepsilon = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} & \varepsilon_{12} & \cdots & \varepsilon_{1n} \\ \varepsilon_{21} & \varepsilon_{22} & \cdots & \varepsilon_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \varepsilon_{n1} & \varepsilon_{n2} & \cdots & \varepsilon_{nn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where the main diagonal elements are calculated using the variance of the criterion data:

$$\varepsilon_{ii} = \sigma^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \quad (2)$$

and the remaining elements are calculated using the covariance between the criteria. When the covariance between the two criteria is negative, its absolute value will be taken and the values of these elements are symmetric to each other through the main diagonal.

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \varepsilon_{ji} = |Cov(X, Y)| = \left| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i,j=1}^n (x_i - \mu_x)(y_j - \mu_y) \right| \quad (3)$$

2) Step 2: Set up the Relative Covariance Matrix

The relative covariance matrix β is obtained by transforming the covariance matrix ε , dividing each covariance column ε_{ij} by the covariance ε_{ii} . The advantage of this transformation is that a matrix whose main diagonal factor is 1 will be gotten. The obtained matrix has the following form:

$$\beta = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \beta_{12} & \cdots & \beta_{1n} \\ \beta_{21} & 1 & \cdots & \beta_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \beta_{n1} & \beta_{n2} & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

3) Step 3: Set up the Correlation Matrix between the Criteria

The correlation matrix α shows the relation between the criteria. The elements in the correlation matrix are called relation coefficients and have the form of (5) [16]. These values are obtained from the values of the elements of the matrix β .

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{\beta_{ij}}{\sqrt{\beta_{ij} \times \beta_{ji}}}, \quad \beta_{ji} = \frac{1}{\beta_{ij}} \quad (5)$$

From (5), the correlation matrix between the criteria has the form of (6):

$$\alpha = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \alpha_{12} & \cdots & \alpha_{1n} \\ \alpha_{21} & 1 & \cdots & \alpha_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \alpha_{n1} & \alpha_{n2} & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

4) Step 4: Calculate the Weights of the Criteria Layer

After having the correlation matrix α , the root method will be used to calculate the weights of criteria layer [17].

$$A_{(i)} = \prod_{j=1}^n \alpha_{ij} \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (7)$$

$$W_{(i)}^* = \sqrt[n]{A_{(i)}} \quad (8)$$

$W_{(i)}^*$ will be normalized and the results of the weights of the criteria are calculated by:

$$W_{C(i)} = \frac{W_{(i)}^*}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_{(i)}^*} \quad (9)$$

5) Step 5: Check the Consistency of the Correlation Matrix

The consistency of the correlation matrix will be checked by calculating the Consistency Ratio (CR) [17]. A correlation matrix will be called the most consistent matrix when $CR < 0.1$. CR is calculated by:

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \quad (10)$$

with:

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \quad (11)$$

where λ_{max} is the maximal eigenvalue of the correlation matrix and is determined by:

$$\lambda_{\max} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(\alpha W)_{(i)}}{nW_{(i)}}, j=1, \dots, n \quad (12)$$

where $(\alpha W)_i$ represents the i^{th} component of the vector αW in the correlation matrix α .

B. Calculate the Weights of the Scheme Layer

The scheme layer of the model represents the relationship between loads in the same criterion. Subjectivity in decision making is a problem that needs to be minimized, and fuzzy preference theory is applied to solve this problem [15-16]. The process of calculating the weights of the scheme layer is shown in Figure 1 and is described below.

1) Step 1: Calculate the Variance

V_i is the variance between attributes of $n-1$ objects in a criterion, excluding the i^{th} object. The variance between attributes in the entire set of criteria is used to calculate the elements of the fuzzy preference relation matrix. V_i is calculated according to:

$$V_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{n-1} (x_j - \bar{x})^2}{n-1} \text{ with } j \neq i \quad (13)$$

where x_j is the value of the j^{th} object in a criterion, \bar{x} is the corresponding sample mean of the criterion, and n is the size of the sample of the criterion.

2) Step 2: Develop the Fuzzy Preference Matrix

The P_{ij} elements in the fuzzy preference matrix P are determined based on the variance of the object attribute, which is calculated by (14) and (15):

$$p_{ij} = \frac{V_i}{V_i + V_j} \quad (14)$$

$$p_{ji} = 1 - p_{ij} \quad (15)$$

where $i, j \in [1, n]$, the higher the P_{ij} value, the greater the priority for the i^{th} object. The diagonal elements have a value of 0.5. Based on the calculation of variance, the fuzzy preference matrix is easier to be calculated and the result is unique and certain. The fuzzy preference matrix P has the form of (16):

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 & p_{12} & \dots & p_{1n} \\ p_{21} & 0.5 & \dots & p_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ p_{n1} & p_{n2} & \dots & 0.5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

3) Step 3: Develop the Fuzzy Preference Relation Consistency Matrix

The weights of the scheme layer will be calculated based on the consistency matrix \bar{P} , which is used to replace the pairwise comparison matrix between the attributes of a criterion and the

attributes of another criterion. The elements of the consistency matrix \bar{P} are established based on (17):

$$(\bar{P}_{ik})_{n \times n} = \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n (p_{ij} + p_{ik}) - 0.5 \right)_{n \times n} \quad (17)$$

The value of the element of the consistency matrix \bar{P} represents the level of importance between the schemes. If $\bar{p}_{ij} > 0.5$, x_i will be more important than x_j , if $\bar{p}_{ij} < 0.5$, then x_j is more important than x_i , and if $\bar{p}_{ij} = 0.5$, x_i is as important as x_j . According to the above calculation, the main diagonal of the consistency matrix will be 0.5.

4) Step 4: Calculate the Weights of the Scheme Layer

The weights of the scheme layer are calculated based on the pros and cons of the scheme. The values of this level use the values of the elements in the consistency matrix \bar{P} . Equation (18) is applied to calculate them:

$$r_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & x_i > x_j \\ 0.5 & x_i = x_j \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where r_{ij} is the priority index in the comparison between the scheme x_i and the scheme x_j . The priority index R_i of the scheme x_i in the set of scheme X is calculated by:

$$R_i = \sum_{j=1}^n r_{ij} \quad (19)$$

The weights of the scheme layer $W_{P(j)}$ are calculated based on the priority indexes R_i for the scheme x_i in the set of scheme X and are determined by:

$$W_{P(j)} = \frac{R_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n R_i} \quad j \in [1, n] \quad (20)$$

Based on this weight calculation method, it is possible to determine the weights of the scheme layer by solving the fuzzy preference consistency of the relation of alternatives of the matrix P .

C. Calculate the Combined Weights

Based on the calculation results of the weights of the criteria layer and the scheme layer, the aggregate priority weight of the power supply continuity $W_{L,ij}$ of each L_i is calculated by (21):

$$W_{L,ij} = \sum_{i,j=1}^n W_{C(i)} \times W_{P(j)} \quad i, j \in [1, n] \quad (21)$$

The shedding power at the buses is calculated according to:

$$P_{Shed,L_i,t_k} = K_{Shed,L_i,t_k} \cdot P_{Shed,t_k} = \frac{K_{i,t_k}}{\sum_{i=1}^n K_{i,t_k}} \cdot P_{Shed,t_k} \quad (22)$$

where P_{Shed,L_i,t_k} is the shedding power of the i^{th} load bus (MW), at the k^{th} time stage (with $k=1 \div 6$), P_{Shed,t_k} is the total load shedding power of the system (MW) at the k^{th} time stage, K_{Shed,L_i,t_k} is the load shedding weight of the i^{th} load bus at the k^{th} time stage, and $P_{L_i,k}$ is the load power L_i at the k^{th} time stage. K_{i,t_k} is calculated by:

$$K_{i,t_k} = \frac{W_{L_{ij}} \cdot P_{L_i,k}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{W_{L_{ij}}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n P_{L_i,k}} \quad (23)$$

The distribution of shedding power to the load buses must satisfy the following constraints: First, the smaller the priority weight of the power supply continuity of the load bus, the greater the shedding power and vice versa. In this regard, it should be noted that it is not possible to shed the entire power of the low-priority load buses as to ensure background or base loads and high-priority loads (Vital loads) at these load buses. Second, the shedding power at the load buses P_{Shed,L_i,t_k} is not allowed to be greater than the power of the load bus at the k^{th} time stage, $P_{Shed,L_i,t_k} < P_{L_i,k}$.

III. OBJECTIVE FUNCTION - BENEFIT FUNCTION

The objective function for load shedding using the traditional AHP method is [17]:

$$H_i = \sum_{i=1}^n W_{L_{ij}} \cdot v_{ij} \cdot x_{ik} \quad (24)$$

where x_{ik} is the decision variable (equals to 0 or 1) on load bus i at the k^{th} time stage [17], v_{ij} is the independent load value (or cost) in a specific load bus i at the k^{th} time stage (\$/kW or \$/MW), and $W_{L_{ij}}$ is the aggregate priority weight of the power supply continuity. $W_{L_{ij}}$, v_{ij} are definite numbers, so the H_i function will reach its maximum value when all x_{ik} are equal to 1. Decision variable x_{ij} equals to 1 if the load demand is satisfied, otherwise it is equal to 0.

In this paper, we propose a method to calculate the objective and benefit functions for load shedding using the improved AHP method presented in equations (25) and (26):

$$H_i = \sum_{i=1}^n W_{L_{ij}} \cdot v_{ij} \cdot (1 - K_{Shed,L_i,t_k}) \quad (25)$$

$$Benefit = \sum_{i=1}^n v_{ij} \cdot (P_{L_i,k} - P_{Shed,L_i,t_k}) \quad (26)$$

IV. CASE STUDY AND SIMULATION RESULTS

The IEEE 30 bus system is used for calculations according to the proposed method. The parameters of the system, the capacity of the generators, and the daily load data, including the independent load value/cost at each load site are listed in [17]. Suppose generator G1 is out of service. The total source power is only 225.0MW. This results in limited power supply at some time stages. The total system generation resources P_G and load demands P_L can be seen in [17]. The results of collecting information about power and power percentage of Vital Load, Semi Vital Load, and Non-Vital Load at each load bus are presented in Table I. Implementing the steps of the improved AHP algorithm to determine the priority weights of the load buses in the system, serves as the basis for load shedding. The loads with low priority factors will be prioritized for shedding in order to minimize the damage caused by power outages.

TABLE I. PERCENTAGE LOAD TYPES OF THE SYSTEM LOAD BUSES

Load L_i	Load name	Vital Load (%)	Semi Vital Load (%)	Non-Vital Load (%)	Variance V_i of L_i in		
					Vital Load criteria	Semi Vital Load criteria	Non-Vital Load criteria
L_1	PD ₂	0.124	0.342	0.534	0.0047	0.0011	0.0024
L_2	PD ₃	0.127	0.346	0.527	0.0047	0.0011	0.0024
L_3	PD ₄	0.131	0.332	0.537	0.0048	0.0011	0.0024
L_4	PD ₆	0.132	0.348	0.52	0.0048	0.0011	0.0025
L_5	PD ₇	0.133	0.328	0.539	0.0048	0.0011	0.0024
L_6	PD ₈	0.134	0.338	0.528	0.0048	0.0011	0.0024
L_7	PD ₁₀	0.135	0.344	0.521	0.0048	0.0011	0.0025
L_8	PD ₁₂	0.138	0.324	0.538	0.0048	0.0011	0.0024
L_9	PD ₁₄	0.136	0.326	0.538	0.0048	0.0011	0.0024
L_{10}	PD ₁₅	0.137	0.313	0.55	0.0048	0.0011	0.0023
L_{11}	PD ₁₆	0.242	0.289	0.469	0.0050	0.0011	0.0025
L_{12}	PD ₁₇	0.246	0.268	0.486	0.0049	0.0011	0.0025
L_{13}	PD ₁₈	0.25	0.256	0.494	0.0049	0.0010	0.0025
L_{14}	PD ₁₉	0.252	0.274	0.474	0.0049	0.0011	0.0025
L_{15}	PD ₂₀	0.258	0.254	0.488	0.0049	0.0010	0.0025
L_{16}	PD ₂₁	0.267	0.282	0.451	0.0048	0.0011	0.0024
L_{17}	PD ₂₃	0.276	0.258	0.466	0.0048	0.0010	0.0025
L_{18}	PD ₂₄	0.279	0.292	0.429	0.0047	0.0011	0.0023
L_{19}	PD ₂₆	0.291	0.276	0.433	0.0046	0.0011	0.0023
L_{20}	PD ₂₉	0.294	0.28	0.426	0.0046	0.0011	0.0023
L_{21}	PD ₃₀	0.298	0.342	0.36	0.0046	0.0011	0.0016

From the percentages of Vital Load, Semi Vital Load, and Non-Vital Load at the load buses in the system, the theory of Section II is applied to calculate the weights of each criteria layer. The matrices ϵ, β, α are calculated by (1), (4), and (6) and are presented as follows:

$$\epsilon = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0048 & 0.0018 & 0.0030 \\ 0.0018 & 0.0011 & 0.0007 \\ 0.0030 & 0.0007 & 0.0024 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\beta = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0000 & 1.6026 & 1.2756 \\ 0.3649 & 1.0000 & 0.2756 \\ 0.6351 & 0.6026 & 1.0000 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\alpha = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0000 & 2.0957 & 1.4172 \\ 0.4772 & 1.0000 & 0.6762 \\ 0.7056 & 1.4788 & 1.0000 \end{bmatrix}$$

From the correlation matrix between the criteria α and by applying (7), (8), and (9) we get the weights of the criteria layer. The results are presented in Table II.

TABLE II. EQUIVALENT PARAMETERS OF WIND POWER PLANT

	Vital Load	Semi Vital Load	Non-Vital Load
$W_{C(i)}$	0.4581	0.2186	0.3233

Applying (12) results to $\lambda_{max} = 3$, and by (11) and (10) we get calculate $CI=0$ and $CR=0$. This shows the high consistency of the correlation matrix. After calculating the weights of the criteria layer, the theory to calculate the weights of the scheme layer is applied. Applying (13) in combination with the data of the percentage of the load type, we get the variances of the characteristics which are shown in Table I. The elements in the fuzzy preference relation matrix P and the fuzzy preference consistency matrix \bar{P} are calculated by (14), (15) and (17). Applying (18) and (19) allows us to calculate the priority index r_{ij} of the scheme layers. The results are presented in Table III.

TABLE III. PRIORITY INDEX R_i OF THE SCHEMES IN THE P MATRICES AND WEIGHTS OF THE SCHEME LAYER

Load L_i	R_i of \bar{P}_1	R_i of \bar{P}_2	R_i of \bar{P}_3	$W_{P(i)}$ of Vital Load	$W_{P(i)}$ of Semi Vital Load	$W_{P(i)}$ of Non-Vital Load
L_1	3.5	8.5	9.5	0.0159	0.0385	0.0431
L_2	4.5	4.5	12.5	0.0204	0.0204	0.0567
L_3	6.5	10.5	9.5	0.0295	0.0476	0.0431
L_4	8.5	3.5	14.5	0.0385	0.0159	0.0658
L_5	9.5	15.5	5.5	0.0431	0.0703	0.0249
L_6	10.5	10.5	10.5	0.0476	0.0476	0.0476
L_7	11.5	6.5	13.5	0.0522	0.0295	0.0612
L_8	14.5	17.5	7	0.0658	0.0794	0.0317
L_9	12.5	16.5	7	0.0567	0.0748	0.0317
L_{10}	13.5	20.5	3.5	0.0612	0.0930	0.0159
L_{11}	20.5	18.5	16.5	0.0930	0.0839	0.0748
L_{12}	19.5	6.5	18.5	0.0884	0.0295	0.0839
L_{13}	18.5	1.5	19.5	0.0839	0.0068	0.0884
L_{14}	17.5	10.5	17.5	0.0794	0.0476	0.0794
L_{15}	16.5	0.5	20.5	0.0748	0.0023	0.0930
L_{16}	15.5	14.5	10.5	0.0703	0.0658	0.0476
L_{17}	7.5	2.5	15.5	0.0340	0.0113	0.0703
L_{18}	5.5	19.5	2.5	0.0249	0.0884	0.0113
L_{19}	2.5	11.5	4.5	0.0113	0.0522	0.0204
L_{20}	1.5	13.5	1.5	0.0068	0.0612	0.0068
L_{21}	0.5	7.5	0.5	0.0023	0.0340	0.0023
$\sum_{i=1}^n R_i$	220.5	220.5	220.5			

The weights of the scheme layer are calculated based on the priority index R_i . Applying (20) calculates the weights of the scheme layer. The results are presented in Table III. The hierarchical model showing the results of the weights of the criteria layer and the scheme layer is presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Weights of the criteria and the scheme layers in the IEEE 30 bus system hierarchy.

After obtaining the weights of the criteria layer (Table II) and the weights of the scheme layer (Table III), we apply (21) to calculate the power supply continuity aggregate priority weights of the load buses. The results of calculating and load ranking are presented in Table IV. Based on the load ranking results the higher $W_{L,ij}$ the load has, the more important it is and the later its order for load shedding is. The more heavily weighted the load, the smaller the power shedding ratio and vice versa.

Equation (22) is applied to calculate the power shedding distribution at the load buses. The values of the objective function H_i and the Benefit function are calculated by (25) and (26). The results are presented in Table IV. The comparison results between the AHP and the improved AHP methods are presented in Table V. The comparison results show that the

improved AHP approach is truly optimal. It not only has maximal load benefits and reduces the total load shedding, but also considers the percentages of Vital Load, Semi Vital Load, and Non-Vital Load of the load buses. For example, the improved AHP method has the total load shedding power increased from 10.48% to 69.54% corresponding to time stages of t_2 - t_6 . Meanwhile, the objective function of the improved AHP method increases from 48.81% to 52.67% and the load benefits also increase from 229\$ to 1466\$. That shows that the improved AHP method is better than the AHP method.

V. DISCUSSION

In the improved AHP method, the correlation matrix α replaces the pairwise judgment matrix of the traditional AHP method. The elements of the correlation matrix are inversely symmetric across the main diagonal line, just like in the judgment matrix of the traditional AHP method. However, for the improved AHP method, these values are derived from

statistical and correlation mathematical processing based on the input as a percentage of the priority load types at each load bus. Therefore, this matrix is objective and reliable. Meanwhile, in the traditional AHP method, these values are obtained from the subjective opinions of experts. When implementing load shedding in the traditional AHP method, the entire loads are shed [17]. This is difficult to do in practice because base loads or very important loads must be maintained. Meanwhile, the improved AHP method, based on the percentages of Vital Load, Semi Vital Load, and Non-Vital Load as the basis for the application of statistical and correlation math based on the AHP algorithm hierarchical model to calculate power supply continuity weights, is feasible and practical. Therefore, if the data collection system of system parameters can satisfy the continuity, this method will be very effective. It ensures less load shedding power while ensuring a higher objective function and higher load benefits compared to the traditional AHP method.

TABLE IV. POWER SUPPLY CONTINUITY PRIORITY WEIGHTS AND LOAD BUS RANKING

Load L_i	Power supply continuity priority weight of load buses ($W_{L,i,j}$)	Rank	V_{ij} (\$/kW)	P_{Shed,L_i,t_1} at t_1 0.00h – 4.00h (MW)	P_{Shed,L_i,t_2} at t_2 4.01h – 8.00h (MW)	P_{Shed,L_i,t_3} at t_3 8.01h – 12.00h (MW)	P_{Shed,L_i,t_4} at t_4 12.01h – 16.00h (MW)	P_{Shed,L_i,t_5} at t_5 16.01h – 20.00h (MW)	P_{Shed,L_i,t_6} at t_6 20.01h – 24.00h (MW)
L_1	0.029626441	18	300	0	3.003446	5.828059	3.726798	3.003446	0.209771
L_2	0.032136639	17	300	0	0.344511	0.668509	0.450038	0.344511	0.024062
L_3	0.037842291	15	300	0	0.825931	1.640064	1.101938	0.825931	0.059031
L_4	0.042388041	13	280	0	9.112701	17.68281	11.3498	9.112701	0.636461
L_5	0.043168144	12	280	0	2.165763	4.202572	2.823654	2.165763	0.151264
L_6	0.047619048	11	300	0	2.583331	5.012845	3.249887	2.583331	0.180428
L_7	0.050129246	10	300	0	0.474435	0.92062	0.618553	0.474435	0.033136
L_8	0.057738432	7	280	0	0.795413	1.543465	1.037034	0.795413	0.055554
L_9	0.05259167	9	280	0	0.483408	0.938034	0.630253	0.483408	0.033763
L_{10}	0.053503791	8	245	0	0.628447	1.219475	0.81935	0.628447	0.043893
L_{11}	0.085123456	1	220	0	0.1686	0.327162	0.220146	0.1686	0.011776
L_{12}	0.074080937	2	280	0	0.498168	0.966673	0.649495	0.498168	0.034794
L_{13}	0.068512253	4	220	0	0.187533	0.371643	0.249702	0.187533	0.013377
L_{14}	0.072425184	3	245	0	0.544156	1.043705	0.70164	0.544156	0.037566
L_{15}	0.064831551	5	280	0	0.139148	0.27001	0.181416	0.139148	0.009719
L_{16}	0.061973073	6	280	0	1.157909	2.246874	1.510099	1.157909	0.080872
L_{17}	0.040785013	14	220	0	0.315025	0.6243	0.419459	0.315025	0.022471
L_{18}	0.034424924	16	220	0	1.036301	2.010898	1.351913	1.036301	0.072379
L_{19}	0.023192711	19	300	0	0.618808	1.200771	0.807996	0.618808	0.04322
L_{20}	0.018699685	20	220	0	0.52628	1.021223	0.686147	0.52628	0.036757
L_{21}	0.00920747	21	245	0	4.720686	9.160291	6.15468	4.720686	0.329708
Total	1.00			0	30.33	58.9	38.74	30.33	2.12

TABLE V. SUMMARY AND COMPARISON OF AHP AND IMPROVED AHP (iAHP) LOAD SHEDDING METHODS FOR THE IEEE 30-BUS SYSTEM

Methods	AHP	iAHP	AHP	iAHP	AHP	iAHP	AHP	iAHP	AHP	iAHP	AHP	iAHP
Time stage	t_1	t_1	t_2	t_2	t_3	t_3	t_4	t_4	t_5	t_5	t_6	t_6
Max. system generation (MW)	225.0	225.0	225.0	225.0	225.0	225.0	225.0	225.0	225.0	225.0	225.0	225.0
System demands (MW)	198.69	198.69	255.33	255.33	283.9	283.9	263.74	263.74	255.33	255.33	227.12	227.12
Committed loads (MW)	198.69	198.69	213.8	225.0	218.1	225.0	219.93	225.0	213.8	225.0	220.16	225.0
Total load shedding (MW)	0.0	0.0	41.53	30.33	65.80	58.9	43.81	38.74	41.53	30.33	6.96	2.12
H_i	130.87	254.2	123.87	254.2	120.32	254.2	123.87	254.2	123.87	254.2	130.10	254.2
Benefit ($\times 10^3$)\$	55058	55058	60979	62445	62306	62535	62717	62425	60979	62445	61406	62356

In addition, in this paper, we propose (25) to compare the value of H_i function with (24). From there, the advantages of the proposed load shedding distribution method can be seen more clearly. In (24), the entire load at bus i at the k^{th} time stage is cut ($x_{ik} = 0$) and does not consider the ratio of Vital, Semi-Vital, and Non Vital loads. However, in (25), we do not cut the entire load i , we only cut a part of the load i based on the K_{Shed, L_i, t_k} weight. K_{Shed, L_i, t_k} has been calculated by (22) – (23).

VI. CONCLUSION

The calculation of the power supply continuity priority weighting of each load bus by applying the theory of covariance and forming the criteria and scheme layers was conducted in this paper. The calculation of the power supply continuity priority weighting of each load bus by applying the theory of covariance and forming the criteria and scheme layers of the problem avoids the un-objectiveness of experts' opinions and gets consistent results, thus overcoming the disadvantages of the traditional AHP method. Besides, it supports the ranking of the load buses and distributes the shedding power in the power system in a more optimized way. The objective function and the benefits are better than those of the traditional AHP method.

The results of load bus prioritization can serve to set the priority of power cut of load shedding relays or planned power cuts in case of long-term power shortage or load shedding in emergency situations. In further work, more consideration should be given to the continuous variation over time of the percentage of each load type and possible combinations of constraints: the cost of power failure, the cost of fines for power failure, and the load cost for a more optimal distribution of load shedding.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work belongs to the project grant No: T2021-46TD funded by Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology and Education, Vietnam.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. T. H. Nhung, T. T. Phung, H. M. V. Nguyen, T. N. Le, T. A. Nguyen, and T. D. Vo, "Load Shedding in Microgrids with Dual Neural Networks and AHP Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8090–8095, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4652>.
- [2] M. A. Zdiri, A. S. Alshammari, A. A. Alzamil, M. B. Ammar, and H. H. Abdallah, "Optimal Shedding Against Voltage Collapse Based on Genetic Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7695–7701, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4448>.
- [3] T. Le and B. L. N. Phung, "Load Shedding in Microgrids with Consideration of Voltage Quality Improvement," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6680–6686, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3931>.
- [4] B. Moran, "Microgrid load management and control strategies," in *2016 IEEE/PES Transmission and Distribution Conference and Exposition (T D)*, Dallas, TX, USA, Feb. 2016, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDC.2016.7520025>.
- [5] W. Shi, X. Xie, C.-C. Chu, and R. Gadh, "A distributed optimal energy management strategy for microgrids," in *2014 IEEE International Conference on Smart Grid Communications (SmartGridComm)*, Venice, Italy, Aug. 2014, pp. 200–205, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SmartGridComm.2014.7007646>.
- [6] Z. Zhang, J. Wang, and X. Cao, "An energy management method of island microgrid based on load classification and scheduling," *Dianli Xitong Zidonghua/Automation of Electric Power Systems*, vol. 39, no. 15, pp. 17–23 and 109, Aug. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.7500/AEPS20140114001>.
- [7] A. Mutanen, M. Ruska, S. Repo, and P. Jarventausta, "Customer Classification and Load Profiling Method for Distribution Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 1755–1763, Jul. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRD.2011.2142198>.
- [8] K. Zhou, S. Yang, and C. Shen, "A review of electric load classification in smart grid environment," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 24, pp. 103–110, Aug. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2013.03.023>.
- [9] S. Zhong and K.-S. Tam, "Hierarchical Classification of Load Profiles Based on Their Characteristic Attributes in Frequency Domain," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 2434–2441, Sep. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2014.2362492>.
- [10] L. Ye, J. Sun, T. Zhou, J. Zhang, W. Sun, and H. Xi, "A practical under-voltage load shedding strategy for regional power grid considering multiple operating modes," *Energy Reports*, vol. 7, pp. 175–182, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2021.02.004>.
- [11] Y. F. Hassan, Y. G. Rashid, and F. M. Tuaimah, "Demand Priority in a Power System With Wind Power Contribution Load Shedding Scheme Based," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 25, no. 11, pp. 92–110, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.31026/j.eng.2019.11.08>.
- [12] Y. F. Hassan and F. M. Tuaimah, "Reduction Strategy for Electrical Loads Based on Demand Priority in Power System," *Recent Patents on Engineering*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 388–395, <https://doi.org/10.2174/1872212114999200407104350>.
- [13] *Regulations on electrical equipment*. Vietnam: Ministry of Industry and Trade, 2006.
- [14] C. Wang, H. Yu, L. Chai, H. Liu, and B. Zhu, "Emergency Load Shedding Strategy for Microgrids Based on Dueling Deep Q-Learning," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 19707–19715, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3055401>.
- [15] Z. Deng and J. Wang, "Multi-Sensor Data Fusion Based on Improved Analytic Hierarchy Process," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 9875–9895, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2964729>.
- [16] L.-W. Lee, "Group decision making with incomplete fuzzy preference relations based on the additive consistency and the order consistency," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 39, no. 14, pp. 11666–11676, Oct. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2012.04.043>.
- [17] J. Zhu, "Optimal Load Shedding," in *Optimization of Power System Operation*, IEEE, 2015, pp. 437–482, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118887004.ch11>.

The Effect of Water-Binder Ratio and RHA on the Mechanical Performance of Sustainable Concrete

Salim Khoso

Department of Civil Engineering
Quaid-e-Awam University of
Engineering, Science & Technology
Larkano Campus, Pakistan
enr.salimkhoso@gmail.com

Suhail Ahmed Abbasi

Department of Civil Engineering
Quaid-e-Awam University of
Engineering, Science & Technology
Larkano Campus, Pakistan
abbasi.suhail2009@gmail.com

Tariq Ali

Department of Civil Engineering
The Islamia University of
Bahawalpur
Pakistan
tariqdehraj@gmail.com

Zuhairuddin Soomro

Department of Civil Engineering
Quaid-e-Awam University of
Engineering, Science & Technology
Larkano Campus, Pakistan
zuhairuddin@quest.edu.pk

Muhammad Tayyab Naqash

Department of Civil Engineering
Faculty of Engineering
Islamic University in Madinah
Saudi Arabia
enr.tayyabnaqash@gmail.com

Abdul Aziz Ansari

Department of Civil Engineering,
Faculty of Engineering, Science,
Technology and Management
Ziauddin University
Karachi, Sindh, Pakistan
aziz.ansari@zu.edu.pk

Received: 30 January 2022 | Revised: 16 February 2022 | Accepted: 22 February 2022

Abstract-Nowadays, the utilization of industrial energy, as well as construction waste, is of high concern. The current paper describes a study of the mechanical properties of cement concrete mixes utilizing Rice Husk Ash (RHA) as a cement substitute. The use of such industrial and agricultural by-products has been the focus of waste reduction for economic, environmental, and technical reasons. In this research, the compressive and split tensile strength of concrete was studied through a 15% substitution of cement with RHA with 0.40, 0.45, and 0.50 water-binder ratios. It has been found that the addition of RHA significantly improves the mechanical properties of concrete for the used water-binder ratios. The ultimate strength in both compressive and tensile strength was observed at a water-binder ratio of 0.50. It has also been observed that as the water to cement ratio increased, higher gains in concrete's compressive and tensile strength were obtained for all curing periods

Keywords-rice husk ash; water-binder ratio; slump; compressive strength; tensile strength

I. INTRODUCTION

Cement concrete is considered one of the most important building materials and is extensively used in a variety of structures. This material however, also has a significant carbon footprint, as its production accounts for nearly 7% of total greenhouse gas emissions [1]. Efforts have been made to use industrial waste materials in concrete as cement replacements in order to reduce carbon emissions. Utilizing waste in the construction industry helps reducing the disposal problem. During the last few years, many researchers have recognized that the use of pozzolanic materials like Sugarcane Bagasse Ash (SCBA), silica fume, Fly Ash (FA), and RHA, not only improves the characteristics of concrete, but also it provides

low-cost construction options [2, 28]. Global production of rice equals nearly 700 million tons per year, and this value is increasing as the consumption of rice is increasing. Table I gives the list of the countries leading the rice growth around the world and the potential production of husk and ash. The use of RHA as a partial cement substitute will provide cheaper materials for low-cost construction. RHA is very rich in silica, however, the silica content depends on the type of rice husk, the burning method, and the combustion period [3]. The utilization of global rice between 2014 and 2015 was estimated to hit 700 million tons [4, 5]. In Pakistan, rice husk is being used as a food additive, and sometimes the by-product of rice husk is used in kilns as fuel. The rice husk used as fuel in kilns and other places generates huge amounts of RHA with no useful application. It is commonly discarded and dumped in open areas taking up a lot of space and causing environmental pollution. This waste has been used as cement replacement to minimize its impact on the environment [6, 7]. RHA can produce pozzolanic activity at temperatures around 400°C, and, due to the contained water, the amorphous silica present in RHA can also take part in the reaction with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ to produce C-S-H gel [8, 9, 29]. The addition of RHA in concrete has reached significant importance as it is considered environmentally safe and more durable for infrastructural development [10, 11, 30]. It has been found that using RHA in concrete increases compressive and tensile strength [12, 13, 31], reduces permeability [14] and chemical attacks [15], has minimal effects of Alkali-Silica Reactivity (ASR) [16], reduces the shrinkage due to particle packing, leads to the formation of denser concrete with improved workability [17], reduces heat transfer to the walls of various structures [18], and diminishes the need of superplasticizers [19, 20].

Corresponding author: Salim Khoso

www.etasr.com

Khoso et al.: The Effect of Water-Binder Ratio and RHA on the Mechanical Performance of ...

The aim of this study is to use RHA in concrete and observe its impact on the water-binder ratio, while minimizing its effect on the environment by using it as a cement replacement material.

TABLE I. RHA IN THE TOP 20 COUNTRIES REGARDING RICE PRODUCTION [4-5]

Country	Rice production (tons)	% of total rice production	Produced husk (20% of total) (tons)	Potential ash production (18% of husk) (tons)
China	204,350,000	29.26	40,870,000	7,356,600
India	152,660,000	21.86	30,532,000	5,495,760
Indonesia	69,554,048	9.96	13,910,810	2,503,946
Bangladesh	39,000,000	5.59	7,800,000	1,404,000
Viet-Nam	43,709,000	6.26	8,741,800	1,573,524
Thailand	37,080,000	5.31	7,416,000	1,334,880
Burma	33,200,000	4.75	6,640,000	1,195,200
Philippines	18,500,000	2.65	3,700,000	666,000
Brazil	11,500,000	1.65	2,300,000	414,000
Japan	10,700,400	1.53	2,140,080	385,214
USA	10,606,000	1.52	2,121,200	381,816
Korea	7,509,000	1.08	1,501,800	270,324
Pakistan	5,800,000	0.83	1,160,000	208,800
Egypt	5,700,000	0.82	1,140,000	205,200
Nepal	4,750,000	0.68	950,000	171,000
Cambodia	4,099,016	0.59	819,803	147,565
Nigeria	3,000,000	0.43	600,000	108,000
Sri Lanka	2,710,000	0.39	542,000	97,560
Colombia	2,400,440	0.34	480,088	86,416
Laos	2,350,000	0.34	470,000	84,600
Rest of the world	29,118,000	4.17	5,823,600	1,048,248
Total (world)	698,295,904	100	139,659,181	25,138,653

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

The materials utilized in this study consist of cement, fine aggregates, coarse aggregates, and potable water. Elephant brand cement was purchased from a local distributor of materials and was used as a binder in all samples. The cement was purchased after checking the date of manufacture, and no cement older than 20 days was used. The fine aggregates used was clean natural hill sand, free from clay and other impurities, having passed through a 4.75mm sieve. The coarse aggregates, with a maximum size of 19mm, were washed and dried before use. RHA was collected from locally available brick kilns in the vicinity of Larkana, Sindh, Pakistan. It is generally the waste material left over after the baking of bricks in kilns. The RHA used in this experimental work was free from other ingredients and passed through a 325-sieve. Drinking water with a pH value of 7.3 was used [21, 22].

B. Methodology

Concrete samples with RHA as supplementary cementitious material with a mix proportion of 1:2:4 were prepared. Three different water to cement (w/c) ratios of 0.40, 0.45, 0.50 were used in the samples. For the RHA-modified concrete mixtures, the cement was substituted with 15% RHA (by weight). Three mixtures of plain concrete and three mixtures of RHA concrete were prepared. For each mixture 30 cubes, and for each age 5

cubes (90 cubes in total), each measuring 150mm×150mm×150mm were fabricated. Three different curing ages, namely 7, 14, and 28 days were considered. Similarly, for each mixture (30 cylinders) and for each age (5 cylinders), cylinders of 150mm diameter and 300mm height were fabricated in order to check the tensile strength of both concretes with regard to the same curing ages. The concrete samples were fabricated and removed from the molds after one day and were placed in a water tank for the curing periods [23-25].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Workability

Slump cone test was carried out for all the prepared concrete mixes to check their workability. The results are presented in Table II. It can be observed that using RHA in concrete causes minimal changes and has a minor effect on workability. However, a reduction in workability was observed due to the higher water absorption due to the presence of RHA in concrete [26, 27].

B. Compression Test

1) Results of Plain and RHA Concrete at 0.40 w/c Ratio

The results of the compressive strength test of the cubes for both plain and the RHA concrete with 15% cement substituted with RHA at 7, 14, and 28 days using 0.40 w/c ratio are given in Table III and Figure 1.

TABLE II. SLUMP CONE TEST RESULTS

Batch	w/c ratio	Mix proportion	Slump of plain cement concrete (mm)	Slump of RHA concrete (mm)
1	0.40	1:2:4	85	81
2	0.45	1:2:4	92	87
3	0.50	1:2:4	96	91

Fig. 1. Comparison of the compression test results of plain and RHA mixed concrete at 0.40 w/c ratio.

TABLE III. COMPRESSION TEST RESULTS, 0.40 W/C RATIO

Curing days	Compression test results of plain concrete (MPa)	Compression test results of RHA concrete (MPa)	Increase in compressive strength of RHA over plain concrete (%)
7	22.57	23.09	2.30
14	28.08	28.76	2.42
28	33.99	34.61	1.82

It can be observed that the compressive strength of the specimens made with RHA concrete is higher than the strength of plain concrete at all ages (7, 14, and 28 days) when using the 0.40 w/c ratio. The maximum compressive strength of the RHA concrete at the age of 14 days is 2.42% higher than the plain cement concrete.

2) Results of Plain and RHA Concrete at 0.45 w/c Ratio

The results of the compressive strength test of the cubes of plain concrete using 15% replacement of cement with RHA at 7, 14, and 28 days when using 0.45 w/c ratio are given in Table IV and in Figure 2.

TABLE IV. COMPRESSION TEST RESULTS, 0.45W/C RATIO

Curing days	Compression test results of plain concrete (MPa)	Compression test results of RHA concrete (MPa)	Increase in compressive strength of RHA over plain concrete (%)
7	20.33	21.55	6.00
14	25.88	27.19	5.06
28	30.62	32.05	4.67

Fig. 2. Comparison of the compression test results of plain and RHA mixed concrete at 0.45 w/c ratio.

It can be seen that the specimens made with RHA have more compressive strength when compared to the control concrete samples at all curing ages. The maximum compression test of RHA concrete at 7 days curing period is 6% more than the control concrete specimens!

3) Results of Plain and RHA Concrete at 0.50 w/c Ratio

The results of the compression test of the plain concrete and the RHA concrete using 15% replacement of cement with RHA at 7, 14, and 28 days using 0.50 w/c ratio are given in Table V and Figure 3.

TABLE V. COMPRESSION TEST RESULTS, 0.50 W/C RATIO

Curing days	Compression test results of plain concrete (MPa)	Compression test results of RHA concrete (MPa)	Increase in compressive strength of RHA over plain concrete (%)
7 Days	17.41	19.25	10.57
14 Days	21.99	23.96	8.96
28 Days	27.22	30.75	12.97

Fig. 3. Comparison of the compression test results of plain and RHA mixed concrete at 0.50 w/c ratio.

The results of the compression test of plain concrete cubes and those with 15% replacement of cement with RHA at 7, 14, and 28 days using 0.50 w/c ratio show a gain in strength for the mixed samples. The maximum compression test result of RHA concrete was achieved at 28 days, and is 12.97% more than the plain cement concrete.

C. Tensile Strength Test

1) Results of Plain and RHA Concrete at 0.40 w/c Ratio

Table VI and Figure 4 show the results of the tensile strength test of the cylinders for control concrete and for RHA concrete using 15% replacement of cement with RHA at 7, 14, and 28 days using 0.40 w/c ratio. It can be observed that RHA concrete has more tensile strength than the control concrete. The maximum tensile strength of RHA mixed concrete is observed at 7 days and is 8.07% more than the plain concrete's.

TABLE VI. TENSILE TEST RESULTS, 0.40 W/C RATIO

Curing days	Tensile strength of plain concrete (MPa)	Tensile strength of RHA concrete (MPa)	Increase in tensile strength of RHA over plain concrete (%)
7	2.23	2.41	8.072
14	2.79	2.99	7.168
28	3.38	3.59	6.213

Fig. 4. Comparison of the tensile test results of plain and RHA mixed concrete at 0.40 w/c ratio.

2) Results of Plain and RHA Concrete at 0.45 w/c Ratio

The results of the tensile strength test of the cylinders made from plain concrete using 15% replacement of cement with RHA at 7, 14, and 28 days and 0.45 w/c ratio are given in Table VII and Figure 5. The results at 7, 14, and 28 days show that RHA possesses more strength than the control concrete. Higher tensile strength results were obtained at all curing periods for the RHA concrete specimens. The maximum tensile strength of the RHA concrete at 14 days is 11.88% more than the plain concrete's.

TABLE VII. TENSILE TEST RESULTS, 0.45 W/C RATIO

Curing days	Tensile strength of plain concrete (MPa)	Tensile strength of RHA concrete (MPa)	Increase in tensile strength of RHA over plain concrete (%)
7	2.09	2.33	11.48
14	2.61	2.92	11.88
28	3.03	3.32	9.57

Fig. 5. Comparison of the tensile test results of plain and RHA mixed concrete at 0.45 w/c ratio.

3) Results of Plain and RHA Concrete at 0.50 w/c Ratio

The results of the tensile strength test of the cylinders of plain concrete and those made of RHA concrete using 15% replacement of cement with RHA at 7, 14, and 28 days with 0.50 w/c ratio are given in Table VIII and Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the tensile test results of plain and RHA mixed concrete at 0.50 w/c ratio.

The results show that the tensile strength of RHA concrete is higher than that of control concrete for all curing periods. The maximum tensile strength of RHA concrete was obtained at 28 days curing period, and is 14.87% more than the control concrete specimens'.

TABLE VIII. TENSILE TEST RESULTS, 0.50 W/C RATIO

Curing days	Tensile strength of plain concrete (MPa)	Tensile strength of RHA concrete (MPa)	Increase in tensile strength of RHA over plain concrete (%)
7	1.75	1.99	13.71
14	2.21	2.51	13.57
28	2.69	3.09	14.87

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study has mainly focused on the inherent mechanical properties, which include compressive and tensile strength, of RHA concrete at different curing periods and various w/c ratios. The results revealed that replacing cement with 15% of RHA improved the mechanical properties for curing periods of 7, 14, and 28 days. From the findings, it could be concluded that:

- The maximum compression test results of concrete specimens made with RHA and with 0.40, 0.45, and 0.50 w/c ratios resulted to 2.42%, 6%, and 12.97% more strength than those obtained using control concrete specimens respectively.
- The maximum increase in compressive strength was achieved when cement was replaced with 15% RHA for 0.50 w/c ratio at 28 days curing period and was 14.87%.
- The increase in the tensile strength of concrete specimens fabricated with RHA concrete with 0.40, 0.45, and 0.50 w/c ratios was 8.07%, 11.88%, and 14.87% respectively.
- The maximum increase in tensile strength when using 15% RHA cement was observed at 0.50 w/c ratio at 28 days, which was 12.97% more than that of plain concrete.
- Cement concrete made with RHA has the property to not only enhance the strength of cement concrete but also to save construction material cost, ultimately making these new structures more economical than the traditional ones.

Furthermore, the use of RHA shown an increase in the strength of concrete at 15% RHA replacement. It has also been observed that as the w/c ratio is increased, higher gains in compressive and tensile strength of concrete were obtained at all curing periods.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors are grateful to the Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering, Science and Technology, Campus Larkano for providing the required facilities for this research work.

REFERENCES

[1] P. Raikwar and V. Tare, "Study of Concrete Properties Using Rice Husk Ash and Marble Powder," *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering*, vol. 4, no. 8, pp. 680-688, Aug. 2014.

- [2] N. G. Amrutha, N. Mattur, and S. Rajeeva, "Chloride-ion impermeability of self-compacting high-volume fly ash concrete mixes," *International Journal of Civil & Environmental Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 29–35, Jan. 2011.
- [3] A. M. Fadzil, M. J. Megat Azmi, A. B. Badrol Hisyam, M. A. Khairun Azizi, "Engineering Properties of Ternary Blended Cement Containing Rice Husk Ash and Fly Ash as Partial Cement Replacement Materials", ICCBT A, vol. 10, pp. 125–134, 2008.
- [4] N. Bouzoubaâ and B. Fournier, "Concrete incorporating rice-husk ash: compressive strength and chloride-ion penetrability." Materials Technology Laboratory, CANMET, Department of Natural Resources, Canada, 2001.
- [5] O. Wallach, "Visualizing the World's Biggest Rice Producers," *Visual Capitalist*, Feb. 23, 2022. <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/worlds-biggest-rice-producers/> (accessed Mar. 25, 2022).
- [6] P. N. P. Chandrasekhar and J. Majeed, "Effect of calcination temperature and heating rate on the optical properties and reactivity of rice husk ash," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 41, no. 23, pp. 7926–7933, Dec. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-006-0859-0>.
- [7] A. N. Givi, S. A. Rashid, F. N. A. Aziz, and M. A. M. Salleh, "Contribution of Rice Husk Ash to the Properties of Mortar and Concrete: A Review," *Journal of American Science*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 157–165, 2010.
- [8] G. R. de Sensale, "Strength development of concrete with rice-husk ash," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 158–160, Feb. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2005.09.005>.
- [9] K. Ganesan, K. Rajagopal, and K. Thangavel, "Rice husk ash blended cement: Assessment of optimal level of replacement for strength and permeability properties of concrete," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 22, no. 8, pp. 1675–1683, Aug. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2007.06.011>.
- [10] P. Chindaprasirt, P. Kanchanda, A. Sathonsaowaphak, and H. T. Cao, "Sulfate resistance of blended cements containing fly ash and rice husk ash," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 1356–1361, Jun. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2005.10.005>.
- [11] N. P. Hasparyk, P. J. M. Monteiro, and H. Carasek, "Effect of Silica Fume and Rice Husk Ash on Alkali-Silica Reaction," *Materials Journal*, vol. 97, no. 4, pp. 486–492, Jul. 2000, <https://doi.org/10.14359/7416>.
- [12] G. Habeeb and M. Fayyadh, "Rice Husk Ash Concrete: the Effect of RHA Average Particle Size on Mechanical Properties and Drying Shrinkage," *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 1616–1622, Jul. 2009.
- [13] C. Lertsatitthanakorn, S. Athajariyakul, and S. Soponronnarit, "Technoeconomical evaluation of a rice husk ash (RHA) based sand-cement block for reducing solar conduction heat gain to a building," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 364–369, Jan. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2007.11.017>.
- [14] V. Sata, C. Jaturapitakkul, and K. Kiattikomol, "Influence of pozzolan from various by-product materials on mechanical properties of high-strength concrete," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 21, no. 7, pp. 1589–1598, Jul. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2005.09.011>.
- [15] S. Khoso, F. Wagan, J. Khan, N. Bhatti, and A. Ansari, "Qualitative analysis of baked clay bricks available in Larkana region, Pakistan," *Architecture Civil Engineering Environment*, no. Vol. 7, 2, pp. 41–50, 2014.
- [16] M. T. Naqash, K. Mahmood, and S. Khoso, "An overview on the seismic design of braced frames," *American Journal of Civil Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 41–47, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajce.20140202.15>.
- [17] S. Khoso, A. Ansari, and F. Wagan, "Investigative construction of buildings using baked clay post-reinforced beam panels," *Architecture Civil Engineering Environment*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 57–66, 2014.
- [18] A. A. Ansari, S. A. Mangi, S. Khoso, K. Lal Khatri, and G. S. Solangi, "Latest Developments in the Structural Material Consisting of Reinforced Baked Clay," in *7th International Civil Engineering Congress*, Karachi, Pakistan, Jun. 2015, pp. 35–43.
- [19] S. Khoso, H. F. Wagan, H. A. Tunio, and A. A. Ansari, "An overview on emerging water scarcity in Pakistan, its causes, impacts and remedial measures," *Journal of Applied Engineering Science*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 35–44, 2015, <https://doi.org/10.5937/jaes13-6445>.
- [20] S. Khoso, A. A. Ansari, J. S. Khan, and F. H. Wagan, "Experimental Study on Recycled Concrete using Dismantled Road Aggregate and Baggase Ash," in *7th International International Civil Engineering Congress*, Karachi, Pakistan, Jun. 2015, pp. 54–61.
- [21] S. Khoso, J. Raad, and A. Parvin, "Experimental Investigation on the Properties of Recycled Concrete Using Hybrid Fibers," *Open Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 9, no. 2, Apr. 2019, Art. no. 183, <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojcm.2019.92009>.
- [22] A. Soltani, S. Khoso, M. A. Keerio, and A. Formisano, "Assessment of Physical and Mechanical Properties of Concrete Produced from Various Portland Cement Brands," *Open Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 9, no. 4, Sep. 2019, Art. no. 327, <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojcm.2019.94020>.
- [23] S. Khoso, A. A. Ansari, and D. Bangwar, "Effects of Rice Husk Ash and Recycled Aggregates on Mechanical Properties of Concrete," *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, vol. 8, pp. 1832–1835, Mar. 2017.
- [24] S. Khoso, K. J. Shahzaib, A. A. Aziz, and K. Z. Hussain, "Experimental investigation on the properties of cement concrete partially replaced by silica fume and fly ash," *Journal of Applied Engineering Science*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 345–350, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.5937/jaes14-11116>.
- [25] M. Mumtaz, J. Mendoza, A. S. Vosoughi, A. S. Unger, and V. K. Goel, "A Comparative Biomechanical Analysis of Various Rod Configurations Following Anterior Column Realignment and Pedicle Subtraction Osteotomy," *Neurospine*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 587–596, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.14245/ns.2142450.225>.
- [26] B. H. Abu Bakar, R. Putrajaya, and H. Abdulaziz, "Malaysian Rice Husk Ash – Improving The Durability And Corrosion Resistance of Concrete: Pre-Review," *Concrete Research Letters*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 6–13, 2010.
- [27] P. J. Ramadhansyah *et al.*, "Strength and Porosity of Porous Concrete Pavement Containing Nano Black Rice Husk Ash," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 712, no. 1, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 012037, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/712/1/012037>.
- [28] A. Saand, T. Ali, M. A. Keerio, and D. K. Bangwar, "Experimental Study on the Use of Rice Husk Ash as Partial Cement Replacement in Aerated Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4534–4537, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2903>.
- [29] N. Bheel, A. W. Abro, I. A. Shar, A. A. Dayo, S. Shaikh, and Z. H. Shaikh, "Use of Rice Husk Ash as Cementitious Material in Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4209–4212, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2746>.
- [30] Z. A. Tunio, F. U. R. Abro, T. Ali, A. S. Buller, and M. A. Abbasi, "Influence of Coarse Aggregate Gradation on the Mechanical Properties of Concrete, Part I: No-Fines Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4612–4615, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3046>.
- [31] A. S. Buller, Z. A. Tunio, F. U. R. Abro, T. Ali, and K. A. Jamali, "Influence of Coarse Aggregate Gradation on the Mechanical Properties of Concrete, Part II: No-Fines Vs. Ordinary Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4623–4626, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3021>.

Sentiment Analysis of Public Tweets Towards the Emergence of SARS-CoV-2 Omicron Variant: A Social Media Analytics Framework

Mohammad Mahyoob

Department of Languages and Translation
Faculty of Science & Arts at Al-Ola
Taibah University
Madinah, Saudi Arabia
mqassem@taibahu.edu.sa

Jeehaan Algaraady

Department of English
Taiz University
Yemen
jihhan.amu@gmail.com

Musaad Alrahaili

Department of Languages and Translation
Faculty of Arts & Humanities
Taibah University
Madinah, Saudi Arabia
mrahaili@taibahu.edu.sa

Abdulaziz Ablwi

Department of Computer Science
Applied College
Taibah University
Madinah, Saudi Arabia
ablwi@taibahu.edu.sa

Received: 22 February 2022 | Revised: 16 March 2022 | Accepted: 25 March 2022

Abstract-While different variants of COVID-19 dramatically affected the lives of millions of people across the globe, a new version of COVID-19, "SARS-CoV-2 Omicron," emerged. This paper analyzes the public attitude and sentiment towards the emergence of the SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant on Twitter. The proposed approach relies on the text analytics of Twitter data considering tweets, retweets, and hashtags' main themes, the pandemic restriction, the efficacy of covid-19 vaccines, transmissible variants, and the surge of infection. A total of 18,737 tweets were pulled via Twitter Application Programming Interface (API) from December 3, 2021, to December 26, 2021, using the SentiStrength software that employs a lexicon of sentiment terms and a set of linguistic rules. The analysis was conducted to distinguish and codify subjective content and estimate the strength of positive and negative sentiment with an average of 95% confidence intervals based upon emotion strength scales of 1-5. It is found that negativity was dominated after the outbreak of Omicron and scored 31.01% for weak, 16.32% for moderate, 5.36% for strong, and 0.35% for very strong sentiment strength. In contrast, positivity decreased gradually and scored 16.48% for weak, 11.19% for moderate, 0.80% for strong, 0.04% for very strong sentiment strength. Identifying the public emotional status would help the concerned authorities to provide appropriate strategies and communications to relieve public worries towards pandemics.

Keywords-sentiment analysis; social media; SARS-CoV-2 Omicron; Twitter; text analytics; data mining

I. INTRODUCTION

With the emergence of social media, using machine and deep learning for sentiment analysis attract many researchers

because it is scalable to process and analyze big data. Machine Learning (ML) algorithms learn the hidden patterns of the data and can predict the class labels of unknown samples. Thus, ML is widely applied in sentiment analysis to predict public sentiments [1, 2].

COVID-19 emerged as an infectious disease that created a global crisis that dramatically affected the world in different sectors like education [3], health, economy, etc. Amidst the crisis of coronavirus, new mutations of COVID-19 emerged, such as the Beta, Delta, and Omicron variants [4], spreading panic and fear in people. The SARS-CoV-2 omicron variant was first detected in South Africa on November 24, 2021, and has spread to more than 57 countries [5].

The impact of the SARS-CoV-2 virus is still a source of concern globally. Many countries announced an acceleration of booster jab rollouts, and the people fear that the variant may destabilize the efficacy of COVID-19 vaccines. Many countries sealed their borders to foreign visitors. Measuring the public's sentiments and opinions towards the Omicron version is important, not only to give us a clear picture of their sentiments, but also to explain whether the public attitude and awareness towards this variant are affected by their earlier experiences with COVID-19. In addition, this evaluation would provide the policymakers with the actual public sentiments and enable them to evaluate their earlier proposed strategies, recommendations, and effectiveness messages and modify them according to the current condition. The disseminated information on the COVID-19 pandemic gave birth to various mental and psychological concerns for social media users [6].

Corresponding author: Mohammad Mahyoob

www.etasr.com

Mahyoob et al.: Sentiment Analysis of Public Tweets Towards the Emergence of SARS-CoV-2 Omicron ...

The impact of the Omicron pandemic may affect the public in the same way and return the earlier scenario of the COVID-19 pandemic. In the beginning, people in different countries were more worried than before, as the early indication is that Omicron is more transmissible than other COVID-19 variants, and there is a devastating consequence in its infection rate [7]. In addition, it is more capable than Delta of preventing the immune defense of both the vaccinated and the previously infected people. The public's concerns were highly raised after the World Health Organization (WHO) reports about the Omicron rapid outbreak. People and health officials started sharing and expressing their opinions, emotions, clarifications, and recommendations on social media and social networking sites. The main concern of social media analytics is to collect data using various methods, processes and understand, summarize, and visualize the output [8].

Social media surveillance can systematically monitor public emotions and reactions to epidemical events in real-time [9]. These expressions comprise rich and open data for researchers, especially for survey and classification studies such as sentiment analysis or opinion mining. Sentiment analysis processes and identifies the data of certain domains through natural language processing. Sentiment analysis using social media plays a crucial role in various fields such as social development, people's awareness, economic development [10-12]. Indeed, many studies applied ML, and Deep Learning (DL) methods and algorithms to explore and investigate the public's sentiments on social media platforms towards the outbreak of COVID-19 and its emerging variants [13-15]. However, no recent studies have detected public sentiments towards the emergence of the omicron variant. Only a few articles and reports such as [16, 17] investigate Omicron's situation as it emerged recently. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to reveal and explore the public feelings and views towards the SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant worldwide through the sentiment analysis of social media, mainly Twitter. The social media analytics SentiStrength software and Voyant-tools were utilized to analyze the data. This study gives us a clear picture of the public's sentiment towards this pandemic which would help the authorities provide appropriate information to relax and ease the public's panic. Moreover, it helps the government address future health emergencies, including transmittable diseases, and provide better healthcare.

II. RELATED WORK

This study aims to explore and mine the public's opinion and find out the percentage of the positivity and negativity toward the new Covid-19 Omicron variant. As the new variant emerged on November 24, 2021, a few articles and reports are investigating Omicron's situation. Authors in [18] commented on the Omicron variant's implications for transmission, cure, and diagnosis. Their recommendation is to continue in the cautions of wearing masks, social distancing, vaccination, etc. Authors in [19] studied the potential prediction of the Omicron variant and provided some recommendations which can be used to protect people from the Omicron virus. Authors in [20] studied the detection of public opinion about the effectiveness of vaccination during the Omicron variant outbreak. The data

were collected from YouTube comments of English news channels. They classified the comments into positive, negative, and neutral using Vader and TextBlob tools. They applied the SVM algorithm to analyze the data. The results scored 63% accuracy in TextBlob and 70% with Vader. Authors in [16] studied the previous Covid-19 vaccines' efficacy against the SARS-CoV-2 omicron variant. The study concluded that there is no or limited protection against the symptoms of the Omicron variant by using some previous cures used for the other Covid-19 variants [17]. Many studies investigated the public sentiment since the COVID-19 emergence. Authors in [21] conducted a study about the outbreak of COVID-19 in Italy. The interest of the research was to predict the disease evolution in the country. The authors collected their data from the official channels declaring the number of infected people in different Italian provinces. The model of the spatio-temporal distribution of COVID-19 was used. An endemic-epidemic multivariate time-series mixed-effects generalized model has been used for counting to understand the spatio-temporal diffusion of the disease. The study results were divided into three phases. The first was related to the outbreak of COVID-19 over time. The second was devoted to the transmittance of the disease among the people of the same district. And the third was concerned with the spatial neighborhood and the main reasons for the contagion effect. They also found that strict control measures in some districts effectively limit contagion and disease outbreaks. A considerable amount of the literature has been published on the public's attitudes towards the COVID-19 pandemic. To the best of our knowledge, no previous study has investigated the reaction of the people to the new variant of the pandemic in social media, especially Twitter, and this is the gap this study aims to fill.

III. METHOD AND DATA ACQUISITION

This section presents the construction of the harvested data and the proposed method. The tweets were collected by searching keywords submitted as seeds to Twitter via its API, likely about COVID-19 Omicron variant from December 4, 2021, to December 26, 2021, using the social media analytics SentiStrength software [22]. The quoted queries were "Omicron", "COVID-19 variant Omicron", "sars-cov-2", "COVID-19". The data were filtered out for cleaning and removing the duplicates, getting 18,737 posts generated by 15,388 post authors (2400 female, 3759 male, 12578 unknown) distributed across countries (56.9% None, 23.1% USA, 14.7% UK, 9.0% Australia, 7.1% Canada). The 'tweets' data table comprise 'id', 'date', 'tweet', 'URL', 'username', 'outlinks', 'likeCount', 'retweetCount', 'replyCount', and 'quoteCount'. After collecting the data, we extracted, analyzed, and visualized them using a combination of tools: SentiStrength, Mozdeh, and Voyant-tools (free, web-based text analytics tools). We analyzed to distinguish and codify subjective content and estimate the strength of positive and negative sentiment in the data that employs a lexicon of sentiment terms and a set of linguistic rules (e.g. for idioms, negation, and booster words). Figure 1 displays the model of the study.

SentiStrength's lexicon is a manually curated list of over 3,000 terms and term stems, each annotated with a positive or negative sentiment strength. The training data of the

SentiStrength library were used to compute the polarity of the word class of the harvested data. The strength range of positive sentiments varies from 1 to 5, where 1 means not positive and 5 means extremely or very strong positive. At the same time, the strength range of negative sentiment is from -1 to -5, where -1 means not negative, and -5 means extremely or strong negative. Any tweet with [-1, 1] score was considered to not show any sentiment, so it was categorized as neutral sentiment. SentiStrength was chosen for accuracy approaching human-level, and its dual system lets negative sentiments be investigated independently from positive sentiments, something that is essential for the research goal [22, 24]. The Voyant-tools were employed to visualize some data.

Fig. 1. The model of the study.

IV. RESULTS

A. Sentiment Strength and Trends

Figure 2 illustrates the time-series graph of the collected tweets. Figure 2(a) displays the overall trends and spikes of the tweets about the Omicron variant. Intuitively, the general direction gives us helpful background information about topic interest and the period when the Twitter users discuss it. It shows a gradual increase in the overall trend. The highest number of tweets were posted at the beginning of the second week of December 2021, mainly on 8th, with 6087 posted tweets. This spike is followed by a steady lower level of activity and an increase in the trend in the fourth week of December. Figure 2(b) represents the average post sentiment from 1 to 5, and the most down green line represents the proportion of subjective texts. The thick black line is the average negative sentiment strength, and the thick red line is the average positive sentiment strength. The thinner grey and pink lines are the same but just for the subjective texts (i.e. positive, or negative sentiment > 1). The sentiment data is bucketed into a minimum of 20 data points for smoothing. It is noted that the two sentiment polarities are close, with an apparent increase in negative sentiment during the peak.

Fig. 2. Time series graph for the proportion of (a) tweet volume and (b) sentiment containing the word Omicron.

Figure 3 shows the sparkline graph, representing the mentioned terms' distribution with linear data segments. It indicates the sudden increase in the volume of the tweets. Z-score is a normalized value for the terms' raw frequency compared to the other term frequencies in the same document.

Term	Relative ↓	Z-Score	Trend
omicron*	20,346	3,602.925	
covid*	16,223	2,872.925	
variant*	7,843	1,388.925	
vaccine*	2,287	404.925	
booster*	937	165.925	
symptoms*	508	69.925	
transmissible	175	30.925	
omicronvariant	158	27.925	

Fig. 3. The sparkline graph of the data.

Fig. 4. Tweets sentiment strength.

The sentiment strength scores of the posted tweets during the Omicron spread are illustrated in Figure 4. It is indicated that most public sentiments were neutral, as most of the posted tweets scored 1, which means no positive or negative sentiments were expressed because zeros were not used. Positivity decreased for the weak, moderate, strong, and very strong sentiment strength scores. At the same time, negativity increased gradually and became dominant, which means people started to show significant concerns about the Omicron variant. Figure 5 shows the significant decrease of positive sentiments to 0.04%, which is very positive after a few days of the outbreak. In contrast, negative sentiment was dominated and scored 0.35% for very negative.

Fig. 5. Sentiment analysis.

B. Tweet Trends and Spikes

Figure 6 illustrates the trends and spikes of Omicron-related tweets in countries like the UK, USA, KSA, India, Canada, Australia, Germany, and China. It is noted that the curves show an increase in the number of tweets during Dec 2021, almost from 4th to 25th December 2021, except in KSA (Kingdom of Saudi Arabia). This reflects the people's high interest in Omicron due to their previous experience with COVID-19. There are millions of expatriates who live in Saudi Arabia. Their native language isn't Arabic, and they use English on social media platforms. English is the first or second language in all other selected countries. Interestingly, in China, the posts on Omicron increased and covered a more comprehensive range of time during the study period. This reflects the high Chinese interest in Omicron due to their experience with COVID-19. Millions in China are using Twitter and they tweet and retweet using the English language. In contrast, KSA shows less interest in the Omicron variant. The bubble chart cross shows the classification of the texts for positive and negative sentiment across different countries and how positivity and negativity are associated with each other. The positive and negative sentiment scores are presented in the bubbles. As shown in Figure 7, the sentiment in the listed countries is very negative with a score of 5, while there is no very positive sentiment with a score of 5 except the USA. It is found that in KSA, public sentiment was almost neutral, and no significant concerns were monitored. This may prove the positive effect of vaccination on physical and mental health [25]. Due to the considerable role of the Saudi government in encountering the COVID-19 outbreak, the positive and neutral sentiment is highly noticed.

Fig. 6. Distribution of Omicron-related tweets across countries.

C. Top Frequent Terms and Hashtags

Table I represents the top frequent terms, including the hashtags associated with the specified sentiment range. It illustrates the occurrence of the word "Omicron" and all other related words more often in tweets containing Omicron. The pMatch rate displays the proportion of Omicron tweets, including the term Omicron 336.4%, variant 142.9%, vaccine 75%, etc. The list of the most frequent words related to the SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant is ranked according to the match and order of importance. Words that occur most often in the text match the search and filters compared to the remaining texts, and they are listed according to their statistical

significance. The chi-square value represents the association between the listed term and searches with filters. The percentage of texts that don't match the search but contain the word, the most frequent words, and their statistical significance can also be seen.

statistically significant, since the confidence intervals are (1.8712, 1.9541). The score of the first phase is (1.8139, 1.8517) and the difference is statistically significant between the two groups. It is reasonably straightforward and statistical evident that people tend to tweet more negatively after the outbreak of the Omicron variant reached at least 57 countries.

Fig. 7. Bubble chart for sentiment analysis.

Table II shows the overall sentiment average alongside 95% confidence intervals in the first phase from 3rd to 10th December 2021 and the second phase from 11th to 25th December 2021. For the positive sentiment of the first set, the average is higher, and the difference is statistically significant since the confidence intervals are (1.3963, 1.4255). The second set score is (1.3527, 1.4193), there is no overlapping between the two data sets. People tended to tweet more positively at the beginning of the Omicron variant emergence. The second phase is higher for the negative sentiment, and the difference is

TABLE I. MOST FREQUENT WORDS AND THEIR STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE

Word	NoMatch	Matches	Chisq
omicron	336.40%	9236	135151.6
variant	142.90%	3945	19398.1
vaccine	75.00%	2051	8350.8
new	61.20%	1682	6509.6
Pfizer	52.70%	1443	5533
#omicron	51.20%	1401	5340.4
covid-19	48.10%	1322	4951.8
delta	28.10%	773	2754.3
#covid19	19.70%	540	1901.3
protection	19.60%	536	1886.4
spread	19.40%	534	1860.8
Africa	16.30%	447	1559.6
sars-cov-2	17.30%	507	1491.1
health	15.80%	435	1488.8
infection	14.40%	396	1374.5
coronavirus	11.70%	325	1092.8
pandemic	11.60%	322	1073.3
symptom	9.00%	247	843.1
confirmed	9.00%	250	835.9
fear	6.10%	169	570.2
patient	5.90%	162	545.9
dangerous	3.30%	91	301
illness	3.30%	90	297.6
#coronavirus	2.70%	74	242.8
pcr	2.50%	68	222.3
contagious	2.10%	58	188.2
infectious	2.20%	62	193.3
#delta	2.20%	60	195
#sars_cov_2	0.50%	14	39

TABLE II. OVERALL AVERAGE OF SENTIMENT ALONGSIDE 95% CONFIDENCE

	First phase	Second phase
Pos	1.4109 (1.3963, 1.4255)	1.3860 (1.3527, 1.4193)
Neg	1.8328 (1.8139, 1.8517)	1.9126 (1.8712, 1.9541)
Av pos - Av neg:	-0.4219	-0.5266

Figure 8 displays the fetched concordance entries and the repeated phrase forms which can be found in the text. The number of branches is shown on both sides of the keyword (Omicron), and the context is retrieved as it is shown along with branches. Most of the keywords (word association, contextualization, concordance, etc.) in the tweets are about Covid-19 variant Omicron, healthcare, vaccines, symptoms, etc.

V. DISCUSSION

The current content-analyzing of tweets, retweets, and hashtags on Twitter study is one of the first systematic studies identifying and testing the public's attitude towards the Omicron variant. The study explores the emotion of Twitter users at the early stage of the variant emergence during December 2021. The results revealed that the spike of interest

in omicron variants worldwide was detected at the beginning of the second week of December 2021, as many cases have been detected in this period. Many countries set restrictive measures to control the outbreak of Omicron and minimize its subsequent effects as this variant is highly transmissible even among fully vaccinated people [26]. The results indicate that the polarized tweets concerning the new variant are inevitable as they started with negative and increased to very negative after 10 days of the Omicron variant outbreak.

The results also exemplify a significantly higher negative share of tweets at the end of the month compared to the beginning. That is due to people's potential worry of the surge of infection, transmissible variant, the efficacy of covid-19

vaccines, etc. that corroborates the findings of [27]. It is noted that the z-score of the term "Omicron" is 3,602.925 and is the highest frequent term used by social media users in their tweets and comments, compared with other related words such as "vaccine," which scored 404.925. These scores indicate that the social media users believe that the Omicron variant may expose their life and health to risk. The sentiment analysis conducted in this study clarifies the emotion of the lay audience and how the pandemic negatively influences their language and thoughts towards the new variant of COVID-19. This conclusion is consistent with [28, 29]. Indeed, the analysis exposes that the public's emotions can contribute to relaxing their worries and concerns by the authorities and to an intense polarization of health care on social media.

Fig. 8. The concordance entries of the data.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The purpose of the current study was to understand Twitter users' views and sentiments towards the emergence of the SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant. The analysis conducted in this study has shown the emotion of the lay audience and how the pandemic negatively influences their language and thoughts towards the new variant of COVID-19. The study reveals a worldwide increase in the overall trend and a high spike in public interest and publications about the omicron variant on Twitter in the second week of December 2021. This variant is highly transmissible even among fully vaccinated individuals.

Many cases have been detected during this period, forcing many countries to set restrictive measures to control the outbreak and minimize its subsequent effects. It is found that the polarized tweets concerning the Omicron variant are inevitable as they started with negative and increased to very negative after 10 days.

The results also exemplify a significantly higher negative share of tweets at the end of the month compared to the beginning. That is due to people's potential worry of the surge of infection, transmissible variant, the efficacy of vaccines, etc. Sentiment analysis can contribute to an intense polarization of

health care on social media. This study gives us a clear picture of the global public's sentiment towards this pandemic which would help authorities to provide timely information to relax and ease the public's concerns. Moreover, it helps the governments address future health crises involving infectious diseases earlier. This study has many limitations. First, the data were collected from one social media platform (Twitter) considering only English tweets. As an extension of the work, it would be interesting to investigate and assess the effect of the new variant of COVID-19 on peoples' emotions and attitudes in other social network platforms and different languages.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This study received funding from the Scientific Research at Taibah University, KSA, under Taibah University's Initiative for Coronavirus Research, Grant Scheme [HUM-9].

REFERENCES

- [1] M. S. Neethu and R. Rajasree, "Sentiment analysis in twitter using machine learning techniques," in *Fourth International Conference on Computing, Communications and Networking Technologies*, Tiruchengode, India, Jul. 2013, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCNT.2013.6726818>.
- [2] P. Baid, A. Gupta, and N. Chaplot, "Sentiment Analysis of Movie Reviews using Machine Learning Techniques," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 179, no. 7, pp. 45–49, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.5120/ijca2017916005>.
- [3] M. Mahyoob, "Online Learning Effectiveness During the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Case Study of Saudi Universities," *International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Education*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 1–14, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJICTE.20211001.0a7>.
- [4] X. He, W. Hong, X. Pan, G. Lu, and X. Wei, "SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant: Characteristics and prevention," *MedComm*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 838–845, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mco2.110>.
- [5] "GISAID - hCov19 Variants." <https://www.gisaid.org/hcov19-variants/> (accessed Mar. 28, 2022).
- [6] A. D. Dubey, *Twitter Sentiment Analysis during COVID19 Outbreak*. Jaipur, India: Jaipuria Institute of Management, 2020.
- [7] N. A. Khan, H. Al-Thani, and A. El-Menyar, "The emergence of new SARS-CoV-2 variant (Omicron) and increasing calls for COVID-19 vaccine boosters-The debate continues," *Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*, vol. 45, 2022, Art. no. 102246, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmaid.2021.102246>.
- [8] W. Fan and M. D. Gordon, "The power of social media analytics," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 57, no. 6, pp. 74–81, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2602574>.
- [9] Fornacciarì, M. Mordonini, and M. Tomaiuolo, *Social Network and Sentiment Analysis on Twitter: Towards a Combined Approach*. Parma, Italy: University of Parma, 2015.
- [10] M. Madhukar and S. Verma, "Hybrid Semantic Analysis of Tweets: A Case Study of Tweets on Girl-Child in India," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 2014–2016, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1246>.
- [11] U. P. Gurav and S. Kotrappa, "Sentiment Aware Stock Price Forecasting using an SA-RNN-LBL Learning Model," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6356–6361, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3805>.
- [12] I. A. Kandhro, S. Z. Jumani, F. Ali, Z. U. Shaikh, M. A. Arain, and A. A. Shaikh, "Performance Analysis of Hyperparameters on a Sentiment Analysis Model," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 6016–6020, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3549>.
- [13] H. Yin, S. Yang, and J. Li, "Detecting Topic and Sentiment Dynamics Due to COVID-19 Pandemic Using Social Media," in *16th International Conference on Advanced Data Mining and Applications*, Foshan, China, Dec. 2020, pp. 610–623, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-65390-3_46.
- [14] Md. S. Satu *et al.*, "TClustVID: A novel machine learning classification model to investigate topics and sentiment in COVID-19 tweets," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 226, Aug. 2021, Art. no. 107126, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2021.107126>.
- [15] K. Chakraborty, S. Bhatia, S. Bhattacharyya, J. Platos, R. Bag, and A. E. Hassanien, "Sentiment Analysis of COVID-19 tweets by Deep Learning Classifiers—A study to show how popularity is affecting accuracy in social media," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 97, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 106754, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2020.106754>.
- [16] N. Andrews *et al.*, "Effectiveness of COVID-19 vaccines against the Omicron (B.1.1.529) variant of concern." medRxiv, pp. 1–16, Dec. 14, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.14.21267615>.
- [17] N. Intiaz Khan, T. Mahmud, and M. Nazrul Islam, "COVID-19 and black fungus: Analysis of the public perceptions through machine learning," *Engineering Reports*, 2021, Art. no. e12475, <https://doi.org/10.1002/eng2.12475>.
- [18] S. Rao and M. Singh, "The Newly Detected B.1.1.529 (Omicron) Variant of SARS-CoV-2 With Multiple Mutations," *DHR Proceedings*, vol. 1, pp. 7–10, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.47488/dhrp.v1i55.35>.
- [19] P. T. Damavandi, "The Omicron variant and potential predictions of secondary infections," Nov. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/urt6e>.
- [20] M. G. T. Akbar and D. B. Srisulistiwati, "Analisa Sentimen Efektifitas Vaksin terhadap Varian COVID 19 Omicron Berbasis Leksikon," *Journal of Information and Information Security*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 251–258, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.31599/jiforty.v2i2.898>.
- [21] D. Giuliani, M. M. Dickson, G. Espa, and F. Santi, "Modelling and predicting the spatio-temporal spread of COVID-19 in Italy," *BMC Infectious Diseases*, vol. 20, no. 1, Sep. 2020, Art. no. 700, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-020-05415-7>.
- [22] *SentiStrength*. <http://sentistrength.wlv.ac.uk/>.
- [23] M. Thelwall and A. Mas-Bleda, "YouTube science channel video presenters and comments: female friendly or vestiges of sexism?," *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, vol. 70, no. 1, pp. 28–46, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-09-2017-0204>.
- [24] M. Thelwall, K. Buckley, G. Paltoglou, D. Cai, and A. Kappas, "Sentiment strength detection in short informal text," *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, vol. 61, no. 12, pp. 2544–2558, 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.21416>.
- [25] J. Algaraady and M. Mahyoob, "Public Sentiment Analysis in Social Media on the SARS-CoV-2 Vaccination Using VADER Lexicon Polarity," *Humanities and Educational Sciences Journal*, no. 22, pp. 591–609, Mar. 2022.
- [26] L. T. Brandal *et al.*, "Outbreak caused by the SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant in Norway, November to December 2021," *Eurosurveillance*, vol. 26, no. 50, Dec. 2021, Art. no. 2101147, <https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2021.26.50.2101147>.
- [27] X. Liu *et al.*, "Public mental health problems during COVID-19 pandemic: a large-scale meta-analysis of the evidence," *Translational Psychiatry*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 1–10, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41398-021-01501-9>.
- [28] Y. Yang, W. Li, Q. Zhang, L. Zhang, T. Cheung, and Y.-T. Xiang, "Mental health services for older adults in China during the COVID-19 outbreak," *The Lancet Psychiatry*, vol. 7, no. 4, Apr. 2020, Art. no. e19, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(20\)30079-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(20)30079-1).
- [29] Z. Su, D. McDonnell, J. Ahmad, A. Cheshmehzangi, and Y.-T. Xiang, "Mind the 'worry fatigue' amid Omicron scares," *Brain, Behavior, and Immunity*, vol. 101, pp. 60–61, Mar. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2021.12.023>.

The Iconic Language in Reading and Interpretation of the Cognitive Map

The Case Study of Individual Rural Housing Lemzara, Setif

Assia Omari

Mediterranean Architecture Research Laboratory
Department of Architecture
Ferhat Abbas Setif University 1
Setif, Algeria
assia.omari@univ-setif.dz

Monia Bousnina

Mediterranean Architecture Research Laboratory
Department of Architecture
Ferhat Abbas Setif University 1
Setif, Algeria
mounia.bousnina@univ-setif.dz

Received: 26 February 2022 | Revised: 20 March 2022 | Accepted: 22 March 2022

Abstract- The graphic representation of the "vision" of the land planner in identifying rural communities entails several cognitive mechanisms. This first step of establishing a basic degree of environmental awareness is critical. The assignment requires the capacity to embody a complex visual world and convey it graphically in a simple and illustrated manner. This article examines an intervention in a rural agglomeration's space. It is a set of ordered functions endowed with meaning. The article aims to scientifically explain the process of creating a participatory habitat and investigate the experience of the occupants by developing a scientific language with graphomotor capabilities around the concepts of vision, space, and representations. The method used is the collection and interpretation of twelve cognitive maps created by the designer and residents of Douar Lemzara, Setif, Algeria. The concepts and models of cognitive mapping point to the conclusion that the cognitive map is an effective method for reading the environment's actual information. Cognitive map analysis enables a better understanding of the most prominent physical characteristics of urban areas. Based on the analysis of respondents' cognitive maps, it is recommended to prioritize the treatment of Algeria's urban environment and engage residents in land use and planning. This opportunity to investigate and approach cognitive representations of space represents a novel mode of investigation and enrichment of the toolkits of various stakeholders in space, as well as an opportunity to improve inhabitants' experience.

Keywords- vision; rural; mind map; inhabitant experience; cognitive mechanism; representation

I. INTRODUCTION

The cognitive map has been defined as a collection of mental representations and ideas that are constructed in order to visualize and process data. Mental maps and mind maps are used interchangeably. They are tools that enable strategists to transcend the limitations of short-term memory and analyze information over extended periods of time [1]. Authors in [2] elaborated the explanation of cognitive maps: Cognitive maps are mental representations of the world in which we live. Human cognitive maps examine how individuals define their personal experiences and views, which determines their decision to live in and continue to live in certain locations [3].

In the same vein, authors in [4] have elaborated that the role of images in a metropolis's environment is meditative. A global image language establishes connections between the residents of new types of cities, as well as between words and physical elements. Authors in [5] have advocated for the use of mental maps by architects and planners to gain a better understanding of the considerations that must be made before beginning to visualize a successful public space. They have further elaborated that the effectiveness of cognitive mapping will be determined by the users' involuntary association with the space. The positioning of blocks, the structure's significance, the degree to which it is used, the user interface, and natural factors all contribute to cognitive mapping. Authors in [6] conducted a study in cognitive maps as correspondence associated with specific locations or spatial images that people have of their physical environment and that primarily influence spatial behavior. People's cognitive maps of a location form as a result of regular interactions with the neighborhood [3]. The experiences will result in the formation of memories and the development of conscious representations. Each representation, experience, and memory is unique and specific to each individual in a variety of settings and circumstances [7].

The investigation of the encoded mental maps focuses on the cognitive representations of the rural agglomeration space. The cognitive representations of space are examined in their functional and social dimensions [8]. The experience of the constructor of the mental map of the physical location lends the map a metaphorical significance. Thus, the mental map transforms into a cognitive map [9]. This step is critical for architects since it establishes the site's identity where environmental data are gathered, and post-sketch analysis is conducted. This is a challenging phase to analyze throughout the project design process, which the current study attempts to clarify via the development of an analytical grid. Authors in [10] proposed to begin by reexamining the urban framework of the Algerian cities and their evolution in response to the changing trade circumstances imposed by globalization, rather than just the metropolitan area. Similarly, studies have been conducted to illustrate how visualization and simulation approaches might aid planners in maintaining urban areas [11].

Corresponding author: Assia Omari

www.etasr.com

Omari & Bousnina: The Iconic Language in Reading and Interpretation of the Cognitive Map

In this regard, the current study examines the methodology of using cognitive maps as an effective planning tool. The current research attempts to uncover information about the users' relationships with their surroundings via iconic language. Specifically, it investigates the effect of affectivity and memory on the identification and orientation of locations and the mobility and imageability of belonging contexts.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Context of the Study

Algerian public authorities sought to bring constructions into compliance, striking a balance between the interests of the residents and their demands for housing and the public interest in urban planning on economic, social, cultural, environmental, and aesthetic aspects [12]. Accordingly, in 2000, the Ministry of Housing and Spatial Planning launched a program of "500 aided rural housing units" in the Wilaya of Setif, as a part of a process of "aid to the stone" recommended by Algeria's housing policy (1 million aided social housing units). This initiative was designed for residents of rural agglomerations on the upper plateaus. One of these regions is the state of Setif, which concretized a significant portion of the program by analyzing a sample of 150/500 rural housing units.

The mental maps developed collaboratively by the operational actors, i.e. the urban subdivision's technical service, prospective buyers, and the architect in charge of the operation all contribute to making the position of each land base geographically recognizable and fully apparent. One hundred and fifty mental maps have replaced many site designs in the construction permit files. The corpus of the research was utilized to create a unique (personalized) scenario plan for each construction permit graphic file. The replacement of the project's scenario plan for the term and subsequently for the mental map legitimized the application for a construction permit and enabled the commencement of the complex process of "dwelling" as an existential position. This resulted in the automatic acquisition of a slew of rights, including financial assistance, access to the property, development of premises via various connections (gas, water, electricity, sanitation), and structuring of neighborhood facilities (schools, health care rooms, mosques, and administrative offices), among others, depending on the size and scope of the actions established. In situ, the real-size operation ensures new information in an environment, resulting in modifications in environmental knowledge [13]. This quantifiable knowledge is concerned with the collective memory of incidental information encountered along simulated routes and represented by cognitive maps [14]. The measures of knowledge are concerned with the accuracy of the route maps, the memory of scene displacement encountered along the simulated routes, the frames of reference or spatial references, and the coherences of these representations [15]. This operation aims to create innovative hypotheses about suburban and rural agglomerations on the outskirts of Setif. By providing access to everyday requirements, public transportation contributes significantly to maintaining and boosting urban wellbeing [16]. Hence, the bus shelters were examined more closely: their visibility, their usage, their usefulness, and their environmental

importance were determined through the decoding and deciphering of a representation of the area in question [9]. Additionally, this inquiry conjures the growth of individualism and the disintegration of a social framework as a result of the territory's expanding urbanization. The whole process is formalized and agreed upon in advance within the same group via the introduction of new forms of employment based on allocation in place of the family domain as a symbol of progress and modernity. This research opportunity necessitates a close examination of its substratum's social morphology and way of thinking via observation of its development and a real-time survey of its active region [17].

B. Mental Maps as a Planning Tool

The use of field experiences in the professions responsible for urban morphology has nowadays become more than necessary. The focus is on maximizing the project's effect, not only of the project itself but also of the actions and procedures that resulted in it. Consequently, tracing a collection of buildings is straightforward: All that is required is field surveys, rights-of-way mapping, or a topographic survey. However, comprehending the synergy of these buildings in terms of neighborhood unity, socio-spatial organization, or any behavior is quite different. This means that the architect or planner uses the location map or site plan to demonstrate the apparent spatial phenomena of location and the unseen features that underpin these visible spatial phenomena in structure and process. Thus, cognitive mapping develops into a field for identifying the unseen mental map, which serves as a decision-support tool [15]. This analytical technique is based on a detailed understanding of the visual components of the mental maps that are the simpler to read, perceive, learn, and comprehend. It is primarily concerned with the shape and logic of the connections between its components. Second, it delves into the logic and organizational mechanisms of the habitat in rural agglomerations by examining the residential space's physical configurations and social representations.

C. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to re-examine the questioning of orientation, followed by the taking of position and reconstruction of the inhabitant's reference markers in space, specifically, to understand how its cognitive representations are constructed through the query. As a result, the paper discusses how these sites were physically represented and how the urban subdivision's technician identified the establishment plates for rural residences.

D. The Sample of the Study

The following criteria were used to choose representative samples: The peri-urban region was chosen because the eastern portion of Setif is experiencing significant changes in terms of expansion and urban growth. These changes entailed the assistance for housing development programs, the new city of Ouled Saber, and rural housing. The density of the mental maps located in the same place is another factor for selecting this setting. Moreover, the location of the study has a unique geographical position in respect to the pairs Setif - Constantine and Setif - Batna. This is reflected in the mobility and growth polarity of the region in regard to road networks and mobility.

TABLE I. ENCODING OF 12 MENTAL MAPS OF LAMZARA CITY (OFFICE OF ARCHITECTURE "CARRÉ D'ART", 2002)

code	01/C3	02/C3	03/C3	04/C3
Mental map				
code	05/C3	06/C3	07/C3	08/C3
Mental map				
code	09/C3	10/C3	11/C3	12/C3
Mental map				

To develop the 150 files for rural housing purchase, building licenses were required. The project owners in many administrative districts (Daira of Guedjel, Ouled Saber, and Setif) requested that the engineering offices (project managers) create requests in both graphic and textual form in order to generate the administrative file required to get the building permit. The decree of the building permit is critical in releasing the first tranche of financial assistance for the realization of the projects. This study opportunity was critical for the researchers since it allowed them to create meaningful syntheses of such operational experiences. The designers and residents collaborated to create scenario plans, which revealed previously unnoticed spatial features. These constructions disclose living areas that are unique to natural surroundings, as opposed to urban ones, while current urban planning tools such as the Regional Spatial Planning Scheme and the Master Plan

of Land Use and Urbanism analyze the situation of these rural agglomerations solely in terms of excess land reserves for city production or flows and economic exchanges.

Twelve mental maps are used in this context to address how the people of these rural agglomerations' living spaces are socio-spatially organized, and how the projection and localization of their future habitat facilitate access to their territory's "mental map" in terms of representation and social organization [6].

E. Objectives

The purpose of this strategy is to elicit common qualities among the mental maps gathered, as well as those that are unique to each person and those that form groupings. Additionally, the following questions are tackled:

- Is it required to build cognitive maps of a certain social group before developing development plans for the rural agglomerations in question?
- Can the mind map be used as a planning tool at the meta-design phase of development plans?

The collection of 150 location graphics depicts skewed spatial maps of numerous rural villages. The fundamental objective is to determine the approximate location of evolving housing cells and to provide information about the spatial distribution of localized content [15]. This stage pertains to the research's mechanical component. It elucidates the fundamental properties of the spatialized experience by providing an explanation for phenomenological cognitive mapping study. For architects and urban planners, the map as an exploration and communication tool facilitates a better understanding of the space under consideration, "the agglomeration," and its conceptual meaning. As a result, it is necessary to assume responsibility for future expectations of occupants about the design and spatial development of their living surroundings.

F. Data Collection

The data collection phase has undergone several stages: The temporal encoding of the pre-project phase between 2000 and 2001 entailed the establishment of the cognitive maps. Afterwards, from 2002 to 2003, the phase of submitting requests for building permits was formed of textual components and traditional documents, which include the scenario plan, the mass plan, numerous section plans, the elevations, and the details of execution. The data were collected from the architecture company "Carré d'Art's" written and digital archives between 2000-2005, the Cadastre of Setif, the Regional Spatial Planning Scheme and the Master Plan of Land Use. Then, 35 mechta and douar locations were selected as representative samples of rural villages. Twelve mental maps were collected and used as the primary tool for analysis and classification (Table I).

III. METHODS OF ANALYSIS

A. Classification of Mental Maps according to Rob Kitchin

Before analyzing the corpus of the study, it was necessary to conduct a classification of the corpus by relevance to the research issue: the geographical location of the agglomeration according to common or particular criteria. This categorization follows the logic of exploration and decoding, rather than just validating the accuracy of localization. In accordance, the current research deployed the approach of typological categorization of Rob Kitchin [18]. This method enabled the treatment and categorization of the corpus's numerous spatial representations according to their appearance and functional aspects. This classification technique analyzes and categorizes the various spatial representations found in the research corpus based on their apparent shapes. Kitchin suggested the following classification of mental maps:

- The fundamental method (free drawings without constraints).
- The conventional method (focusing on specific aspects of an environment and the representation of certain elements).
- The framed method (by proposing a background map or imposing a scale).
- The transverse method (representing the evolution of the stages of successive representations).
- The method of visual language.
- The overlapping technique: verbal and pictorial information.

B. Rob Kitchin Technique

Using Kitchin's technique, the mental maps were grouped according to the most effective and direct manner of easily locating intervention spots [18]. The traditional approach is focused on the unique characteristics of an area, and the depiction of certain features since the mind map incorporates both verbal and pictorial information (the cross technique). By combining the sensory input from the surroundings, the creator of each mind map created an ideal course of travel-oriented toward a goal or objective from a starting point. These data are filtered, consolidated, and sometimes forecasted. This structure is, in reality, a spatial encoding [14]. Therefore, the identified and evaluated mental maps are functional representations of the geographical space. They are constructed by geographical experiences on two levels, one functional and one social [8]. It appears that these mental maps are primarily envisioned as information constructs. Each map is a unique and single creation [19], created immediately in response to the specific location of the displacement and indirectly via a tailored translation of ambient spatial information.

C. Study of the Shape of the Mental Maps

1) Classification of the Cognitive Maps and the Encoding of Space

Various strategies have been deployed to read the mental maps to uncover cognitive representations of space, to decipher the hand drawings (mental maps of situations) in their iconographic forms and to arrive at a recognizable and collective level of scientific reading and interpretation through the analysis of shared and disparate features and the iconic message created by each of the analyzed maps.

a) The Technique of Rothwell

This approach allows the competency of the map designer to articulate his or her depiction of the place inside the metropolitan region to be evaluated [20]. The purpose is to orient oneself in sparse space using a spatial reference and to find and position the plot of the project land in respect to property boundaries and permanent landmarks to optimize the itinerary. This approach infuses the drawing with the dimension of mastery of spatial size and proportions.

b) The Technique of Canter

This is a technique that provides information about the shape and nature of spatial structures when selecting the land for the realization of a project by moving to the site with the future buyer and establishing the exact location of the project and determining the parcel's metric dimensions. By incorporating four cognitive tasks, this technique explains and

categorizes the phases of elaboration and generation of spatial mental maps [21]:

- Spatial orientation by the designation of geographic north.
- The reduction of a large-scale extended space to the size of a white A4 sheet of paper.
- The implementation of geometrical projections according to their organizational logic and the identification of components according to their perceptual appearance rank.
- The portrayal of the mental picture's constituents symbolically and customarily.

c) *The Technique of Byrne*

This approach is founded on the premise that the outcome of the graphic output is contingent upon the designer's starting point for completing the work at hand and the desired outcome. Additionally, the skills of the designer to project himself into geographical space and his mastery of measurement, scale, and plane geometry were considered.

d) *Downs and Stea Technique*

As an analytical tool, it entails creating a correlation between the drawing (the freehand sketch) and the spatial representation: the result of the internalization of environmental information, its codifications, and externalizations [16]. This operation aims to communicate information about the project's location and status to the responder and interviewer by presenting technical expertise via standard visual language.

e) *Cross Reading through the Different Techniques*

The application and intersection of all of these methodologies resulted in cross-reading of the various maps of the Lamzara area. This reading was carried out in order to extract as much useful information as possible from the majority of the representations to determine the common characteristics of this rural agglomeration. It is an activity for the expectations of a population while predicting its living environment. The purpose is to create an analytical grid that enables the maps to be classified and sub-groups using common criteria derived from the various research approaches outlined above and to determine the iconic message included within each mind map (Table II).

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. *The Structure and the Nature of the Link between the Mental Maps*

According to Table III, about 80% of mental maps are on a territorial scale: (between Batna, Setif, and Ras -el -maa) (N°01C3/03C3/04C3/05C3/06C3/07C3/08C3/09C3/09C3/10C3/11C3), while 20% are on a more local scale: (Guedjel centre, R'mada, and Ras -el-ma (02C3 and 12C3).

This demonstrates the critical nature of the regional size of the agglomeration. This territorial inscription is explained by the gravitational and boundary location of the agglomeration concerning the very active vehicle flow along the National Road (NR) 75. This road axis becomes a structuring axis and a

major reference for the entire population of Lamzara, especially if the dwellings are located near this flow, implying the significance of the shape of the building, distance, course geometry, orientation, morphology, and time of exposure concerning the mobility and displacements in this environment [7]. This latter is constructed according to a perceptual logic, which results in the perception mechanism along a route. The quality of the connection is determined by this logic [14]. It is characterized by the existence or absence of relationships between closed and open geometric shapes and the rest of the natural world. Thus, the legibility of the environment contributes to the accessibility and location of goals through a clear view and route across a loosely constructed framework. This clarity results from the inherent simplicity of interactions and the nature of the connections between the built and unbuilt areas.

B. *Spatial and Social Representations*

The examined mental maps exhibit several typologies. They are classified according to the routes and geometrical structure of spatial representations and the functional quality of the connections that constitute social representations. The aim of the cognitive maps is to represent beliefs about the relationship between concepts [13]. In contrast, the analysis of the mental maps (Table II) reveals the presence of an iconic message that facilitates the location of intervention sites and provides information about the degree of mastery of knowledge about the perceived physical environment and its associated social behavioral practices.

The resultant picture of the Lamzara agglomeration is a fluid region with a high level of daily mobility inside the territorial geographical unit. The latter is traversed by NR 75, which facilitates heavy road traffic which, due to its regularity, divides the area into two entities: Lamzara - East and Lamzara - West.

The repeated appearance of schools, mosques, and bus stops in all mental maps indicates the presence of a cognitive-behavioral routine [22], which is detected using an indirect technique that calculates the frequency of appearance of elements associated with the target (the housing project) in the study corpus. The social practice of neighborhood equipment contributes to the intelligibility of the agglomeration.

It has been observed that the route diagram evolves in response to "directed navigation" [16], with the ultimate objective of sketching a clear ideal path for the location of the project.

The examination of the graphic criteria found in a sample of Lamzara's rural settlements, namely orientation, lines, surfaces, shapes and symbols and their linkages has revealed the significance of each graphic criterion category to its analogical spatial counterpart. Each mental map is composed of graphic elements that form the basis for the construction of meaning by their configuration and disposition. The presence of similar meanings in the bulk of the Lamzara sample is due to the environment itself but to the representations of the social group that developed them just by encompassing a shared culture and environment over a certain period [23].

TABLE II. STRUCTURING OF THE ICONIC MESSAGE OF THE MENTAL MAPS OF THE LAMZARA AGGLOMERATION

Reading the shape of the mental maps using the cross method					
Spatial unit: Lemzara agglomeration C3	Category of graphic criteria				Iconic message, Downs and Stea index: - Environment not known. - Known environment, but not mastered - Known and mastered environment
	Orientation, Rothwell and Canter index: Geographic North in the direction of the sheet A4 and the writing.	Spatial scale ratio by Rothwell and Byrne index: Local /territorial/ communal /inter- wilaya in relation to the A4 sheet	Symbols and transcriptions, Canter's index: Line, curve, polygon, surface, signs, words, toponyms, the path.	Byrne's index : (the link or junction) perceptual logic according to the target: focal, direct, indirect, hierarchical.	
Map 01C3	Arrow to the right	From Batna to Setif centre /A4 Inter-wilaya	6 lines 7 polygons 9 words	Indirect Hierarchical	Known environment, but not mastered
Map 02C3	Arrow to the right	Center of Guedjel and R'mada/A4 Inter -communale	2 lines 15 polygons 6 curves 16 words	Direct	Known environment, but not mastered
Map 03C3	Arrow to the left	From Setif centre to Batna/A4 Inter-wilaya	6 lines 6 curves 9 polygons 1 ovoid surfaces	Indirect Hierarchical	Known environment, but not mastered
Map 04C3	Arrow to the right	From Setif centre to Batna/A4 Inter-wilaya	2 lines 1 curve 6 polygons 1 cross	Direct	Known environment, but not mastered
Map 05C3	Arrow to the right	From Batna to Setif centre /A4 Inter-wilaya	8 lines 5 polygons 1 circle	Direct	Known environment, but not mastered
Map 06C3	Arrow to the right	From Batna to Setif centre /A4 Inter-wilaya	8 lines 2 curves 9 polygons 1 cross	Indirect	Known and mastered environment
Map 07C3	Arrow to the right	From Setif centre to Batna/A4 Inter-wilaya	2 lines 1 Surface 6 polygons	No junction registered	Known and mastered environment
Map 08C3	Arrow to the left	From Setif centre to Batna/A4 Inter-wilaya	7 lines Multi curve 4 polygons	Indirect Hierarchical	Known environment, but not mastered
Map 09C3	Arrow to the right	From Setif centre to Batna/A4 Inter-wilaya	7 lines Multi curve 4 polygons	Indirect Hierarchical	Known environment, but not mastered
Map 10C3	Arrow upwards	From Setif centre to Batna/A4 Inter-wilaya	2 lines 5 polygons	No junction registered	Known environment, but not mastered
MAP 11C3	Arrow to the right	From Batna to Setif centre /A4 Inter-wilaya bipolar	19 lines 2 curves 9 polygons	Direct	Known and mastered environment
Map 12C3	Arrow to the left	Multipolar : Batna /Setif /Ras el maa	8 lines 1 cross 5 polygons	Direct	Known and mastered environment
Significance	NR 75 is an axis of geographical orientation and divides the agglomeration into right and left parts, and gives importance to residential mobility	The importance of territorial registration of the agglomeration is due to its gravitational position in relation to the NR 75.	The morphology of the urban fabric is easily apprehended due to the clarity of the visibility of the spatial referents of the perceived environment.	The legibility and intelligibility of the space participates in the accessibility and the location of the targets following the clarity of vision and path through the loose built framework. This clarity is due to the simplicity of the relations and the nature of the legible links between the built and the unbuilt environment.	The representation of the Lamzara agglomeration is strongly known and mildly mastered due to the presence of a simple and explicit structural logic. This controlled environmental knowledge is reflected in the majority of the cognitive maps.

TABLE III. SYNTHESIS OF THE READING OF THE MENTAL MAPS

	Rothwell and Canter index			Rothwell and Byrne index		Symbols and transcriptions, Canter's index		Byrne's index			Iconic message, Downs and Stea index		
	Left	Right	Upward	Local	Territorial	Closed built	Open, not built	Direct link	Indirect link	No junction	Known and mastered	Known and not mastered	Not known and not mastered
Synthesis of the 12 mental maps of Lamzara	2	9	1	02	10	25%	75%	06	04	02	04	08	00

TABLE IV. INFORMATION CONSTRUCTION AND PRODUCTION OF MEANING

Maps	Iconic message	Spatial representation	Social representation
01C3/02C3/03C3/ 04C3//05C3/08C3/ 09C3/10C3	Known and mastered environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The legibility of the paths is materialized by the presence of geometric links between the closed structures (polygons and spots) and the open structures (points and lines). -The links in the majority of the maps are direct, indirect or combined (hierarchical, in the form of loops, branches, ramified). -The maps in this case become illustrated maps thus rich in information. They become cognitive maps. -The existence of several levels of construction in the same map reflects the graphic ability of the constructor or draftsman to elucidate a complex environmental reality in a simple and understandable iconic message. 	<p>The representation of the Lamzara agglomeration is strongly mastered as a result of the presence of a simple and explicit structural logic. This mastered environmental knowledge is reflected in the majority of the cognitive maps (85%).</p> <p>The inhabitants of Lamzara consider the NR 75 as a major spatial reference and give it socio-economic importance because this axis raises the rank of this small village to that of a structured and compact village agglomeration by the introduction of the semi-detached along the NR 75 axis. This situation introduces the notion of street in a rural environment with sparse morphology.</p> <p>-The proximity of the NR 75 is for the agglomeration of Lamzara a lever and gives potentiality for future development.</p>
11C3/12C3/07C3	Known and not mastered environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ambiguity of pathways: absence of links between closed and open structures. -They are deduced maps or simple constructions by linking to one or two spatial referents at most, making a total abstraction of the rest of the environment. -They are generally maps of clear and recognizable geographical location. 	<p>The consideration of a smaller scale and the disparity with the rest of the agglomeration is mainly due to the clarity of the situation and its location by the majority of residents and visitors of Lamzara.</p>

C. Examination of the Morphic Structure of the Mental Map

1) Techniques Used to Study the Morphic Structure

The morphic structure analysis approach was utilized in the context of a Ph.D. dissertation and offered the identification of a typology of place morphic structures via the reading of developing representative cognitive maps [24]. This analytical method is a necessary basis to comprehend the logic and structure of the complete system portrayed and examined.

2) Morphic Structures of Mental Maps

This categorization aims to denote the various morphic structures inside the researched agglomeration using Lamzara's 12 maps. The cognitive maps are provided as typological structures. Table V identifies two prominent morphological structures: Structure resembling an itinerary and structure resembling axiality. This demonstrates the focus of the designers on mobility and spatial navigation inside the Lamzara agglomeration region. Throughout the diagram's creation and examination, the 12 mental maps interact with their environment.

The findings indicate the presence of two prominent morphological patterns in the form of routes and axiality. As observed, 80% of the analyzed maps are sequential, indicating

the agglomeration's importance for mobility. They establish causation between the NR 75 and the project by using the locative verbs find oneself, locate oneself, and position oneself in connection to the NR 75. The quality and quantity of features in the mental maps are also very informative in terms of transferring information on the morphic arrangement and structure of the various paths. Consider the following behavioral routine [21]: The map 06C3 informs of an alternate route for the target's localization in order to minimize the error factor and accessibility time. The map implicitly implies the person who constructed it and the person who transmitted the information in the route to be borrowed, which is a matter of behavioral routines.

As a result, it may be concluded that each diagram or mind map formed linkages between the designer's memories, the environment's facts, and the conducted interviews with the occupants.

D. Coherence Measures for Spatial Representations

The correspondence approach entails retracing the routes, finding reference points, assessing the physical legibility of space (the quality of the forms), and presenting them with a novel experience. This may be accomplished in situ via the researchers' comments or photos or through the use of an aerial

snapshot of the location (as is the case in this study). The purpose of this approach is to highlight the distinction between perception and representation of measurable geometric space and assess the degree of similarity between the mental map and geographic reality. The approach enabled the assertion of the

constructor of the cognitive map's degree of expertise and his capacity to embody and visually portray the experienced world at a reduced size. This approach allows the precise assessment of the degree of similarity between the picture viewed and perceived with the associated mental map.

TABLE V. TYPOLOGIES OF THE STRUCTURES OF THE SPATIAL REPRESENTATION AND CONFIGURATION OF COGNITIVE MORPHIC STRUCTURES OF LEMZARA [24]

			Configuration of morphic structures [24]								
			S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9
			Structure in the form of a route	Structure in the form of axiality	Structure in the form of a cross	Structure in the form of a double crossing	Structure in the combined form of centrality and axiality	Structure as a sequential plan	Structure in the form of topological centrality	Structure in the form of a spot	Structure as a fragment
			Sequential maps				Spatiale maps				
Typology of spatial categories			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Map name											
05C3	12C3	07C3	XXX	XXX							
03C3	02C3	09C3	XX							X	
11C3	04C3	08C3	XXX	XXX							
01C3	06C3	10C3	X					XX			
			12	9	6	/	/	/	2	/	1

Fig. 1. Application of the technique of [25] in the calculation of spatial regression-map 02/C3: (a) Digital mind map: Superimposition of the digitized mental map on a grid representing a spatial unit, (b) Aerial view (Google maps): Overlay of the Geographic Image G on a grid representing a spatial unit, (c) The superposition of A on B perception by correspondences, (d) The spatial regression percentage rate of accuracy: By triangulation, the degree of similarity between the geographical reality and the mental representation is close to 70% of the general criteria.

The approach in [25] entails superimposing the scaled planar representations on the same reference frame, with a minimum of 3 reference points. This approach was applied on a

small sample (1 map), since most of the assessed maps are sequential maps showing the agglomeration's relevance for movement (Figure 1). This map will be used as a starting point for analysis to simulate constructing a cognitive location model in rural areas. The purpose of this analysis is to develop a cognitive reading tool for spatial regressions and to calculate the rates of accuracy for correspondences in terms of closeness or distance between cognitive distances.

The processing of the cognitive picture enabled the quantification of the variations between the two locations for each constituent while also emphasizing the individual variances. Consequently, it is possible to differentiate between distortion and coherence in the cognitive image, which is unavoidably wrong beforehand. Spatial distortion, therefore, indicates abnormalities in the cognitive representations of space that are inaccurate. This is why freehand sketching techniques and concurrent consideration of the direction and distance between parts are of paramount importance.

V. DISCUSSION

Various evaluations of cognitive maps using different techniques reveal that their schematic consistency is saturated with particular knowledge and data. The analysis and collection of mental representations through schematic data connected with items and their physical reality counterparts provides a valuable tool to access valuable information. These data cannot function independently of their socio-spatial environments because each of them emits one or more iconic messages. The purpose of the iconic messages in this study is to develop a grid for deciphering and analyzing spatial representations by starting with the individuals' graphic productions or mental maps. Consequently, the data creation process enables the establishment of a conducive environment for initiating the design process. This relates to the conceptual idea phase for architects and to the stage of gathering and organizing data that enables the development of a scenario, including the stretching

or tightening of urbanistic logic for urban planners. The phase of data creation is critical for interpreting and comprehending the underlying structures of mental maps. This stage entails drawing paths for the tool's successful engagement in architecture, urbanism, and territorial planning at the appropriate scale. The purpose is to create new methods to search for design tools at various architectural, urban, and even territorial sizes that are vision-based and allow for the establishment of linkages between environmental data, the designer's memory, and the client's needs.

VI. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this research is to examine the mental map as a tool for efficient urban planning. Individuals design their own maps using this approach, based on a series of questions on orientation, lines, surfaces, forms, and symbols. The cognitive representations of space are examined in their functional and social dimensions. In accordance, the current research deployed the approach of typological categorization of [18]. This strategy allowed for the treatment and classification of the various spatial representations of the corpus on the basis of their appearance and function. Four different methods for examining and classifying mental maps were utilized to analyze and interpret these maps. Additionally, the morphic structure of the mental representations was deployed to comprehend the logic and structure of the complete portrayed and examined system. Additionally, the coherence structure of the mental maps was examined to emphasize the distinction between perception and representation of quantifiable geometric space and allowed the assessment of the degree of resemblance between the mental map and the geographic reality. To increase the collective representation of space, the most frequently used technique is freehand drawing or graphic production of a vision of a physical environment saturated with social significance synthesized on external support, typically a white A4 sheet of paper. The advantage of this technique is that it is adaptable and usable in a variety of contexts. The mental map transmits a structured message and is necessary for architectural projection and urban planning. However, the accuracy of the physical information is secondary to its cognitive capacity, which reflects other structures in the interpretation of socio-spatial representations beyond physical reality.

This study attempted to elevate the image and its associated iconic language. The cognitive picture of space representation in rural and sparse settings is primarily a decision support tool for spatial concerns, such as housing programming and planning. As a result, it is greatly influenced by the interaction of the individual with the environment, and it serves as a valuable indication of this relationship throughout the inhabitant's experiences with the rural housing program's implementation.

Throughout the research, various strategies were used to elicit patterns of cognition and orientation in the geographical environment of the individual in connection to his group of belonging and his residential trajectory. This has allowed for an understanding of the integration process of the individual (beneficiary) and his role in establishing his own space within his constrained social group and geographical and territorial

surroundings. This is true from the procedural step of site selection through the reconfiguration of what was originally offered as an evolving template for rural-dwelling units.

This experience allowed a deeper understanding of the environmental knowledge and its configurations by collecting a diverse range of data that allows the simultaneous collection of physical components and social representations. It was discovered that the names and rankings assigned to this information throughout the map's development and their spatial relationships affect the overall spatial structure that creates them. Environmental information has been supported, including physical visibility of the environment, subjective accessibility to locations, cognitive hurdles, activity and daily mobility, location choices, residential strategies, and perceived suburban polarity. At the same time, it externalizes social representations, allowing the social legibility of the studied environment, the affective appropriation of places and physical elements, and social relationships within the space. In this situation, the map takes on the role of an exploratory research tool.

It can be used to assess the impact of integrating the same rural housing prototype through a variety of different configurations of interior and exterior land bases within pre-existing urbanisable perimeters on its current and future morphological evolution and within its anchorage location and immediate environment.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors are grateful to the Mediterranean Architecture Research Laboratory for their contribution in the current research.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Sammut-Bonnici and J. McGee, "Cognitive Map," in *Wiley Encyclopedia of Management*, New York, NY, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2015, pp. 1–3.
- [2] R. Artigiani, V. Csanyi, A. Combs, and E. Laszlo, *Changing visions: Human cognitive maps: Past, present, and future*. Westport, CT, USA: Praeger, 1996.
- [3] P. Gould and R. White, *Mental Maps*. London, UK: Routledge, 2012.
- [4] B. Jasz, "Mental map of the city: elements of visual argumentation and creativity in modern city planning," *Creativity Studies*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 284–293, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.3846/cs.2018.6901>.
- [5] R. Chopra and G. D. Mahapatra, "Cognitive Mapping In Spaces For Public Use," *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*, vol. 7, no. 9, pp. 138–142, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.15623/ijret.2018.0709020>.
- [6] A. Rapoport, *Human Aspects of Urban Form: Towards a Man—Environment Approach to Urban Form and Design*. Amsterdam, Netherlands: Elsevier, 2016.
- [7] K. Lynch, *The Image of the City*. Cambridge, MA, USA: MIT Press, 1964.
- [8] R. M. Downs and D. Stea, *Maps in minds: reflections on cognitive mapping*. New York, NY, USA: Harper & Row, 1977.
- [9] L. Chauvin, "Modeles de cartes cognitives etendues aux notions de contexte et d'échelle," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Angers, Angers, France, 2010.
- [10] M. Gherbi, "Problematic of Environment Protection in Algerian Cities," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 18, pp. 265–275, Jan. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2012.05.038>.

- [11] F. T. Benaissa and B. Khalfallah, "Industrial Activity Land Suitability Assessment Using Delphi and AHP to Control Land Consumption": The Case Study of Bordj Bouarreridj, Algeria," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7738–7744, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4362>.
- [12] E. Benkhaled, M. Mili, and F. Oudina, "Illegal Construction Imposed by the Private Lands in Peripheral Urban Areas of M'sila, Algeria," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8188–8192, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4703>.
- [13] D. Appleyard, "Styles and Methods of Structuring a City," *Environment and Behavior*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 100–117, Jun. 1970, <https://doi.org/10.1177/001391657000200106>.
- [14] T. Ramadier, "Rapport au quartier, representation de l'espace et mobilite quotidienne: le cas d'un quartier peripherique de Quebec-ville," *Espaces et societes*, vol. 108, no. 1, pp. 111–132, 2002.
- [15] C. Cauvin, F. Escobar, and A. Serradj, *Thematic Cartography, Cartography and the Impact of the Quantitative Revolution*. New York, NY, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2013.
- [16] A. Jawed, M. A. H. Talpur, I. A. Chandio, and P. N. Mahesar, "Impacts of In-Accessible and Poor Public Transportation System on Urban Environment: Evidence from Hyderabad, Pakistan," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 3896–3899, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2482>.
- [17] A.-P. Lagopoulos, "L'image mentale de l'agglomeration," *Communications*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 55–78, 1977, <https://doi.org/10.3406/comm.1977.1409>.
- [18] R. Kitchin, "Collecting and analysing cognitive mapping data," in *Cognitive Mapping*, London, UK: Routledge, 2000, pp. 9–23.
- [19] S. J. Milgram and D. Jodelet, "Psychological maps of Paris," in *Environmental psychology: people and their physical settings*, H. Proshansky, N. Ittelson, and L. G. Rivlin, Eds. New York, NY, USA: Holt, Rinehart and Winston, 1976.
- [20] D. C. Rothwell, "Cognitive mapping of the home environment," Ph.D. dissertation, University of British Columbia, British Columbia, Canada, 1974.
- [21] D. Canter, *The psychology of place*. New York, NY, USA: St. Martin's Press, 1977.
- [22] M. Boulahbal, "Les territoires individuels de la mobilité: Proposition d'une méthode de représentation et premiers résultats," *Recherche, Transports, Sécurité*, no. 57, pp. 36–52, 1997.
- [23] F. Michel, "L'imaginaire patrimonial et le projet d'urbanisme. Perspective cognitive sur l'agir spatial," in *L'imaginaire géographique. Perspectives, pratiques et devenirs*, M. Bédard, J. P. Augustin, and R. Desnoilles, Eds. Quebec, Canada: Presses de l'Université du Québec, 2012, pp. 193–224.
- [24] M. Madani Bousnina, "Contribution a une approche sensitive de la ville : les referents spatiaux perceptifs mnemoniques," Ph.D. dissertation, The University Ferhat Abbas of Setif, Setif, Algeria, 2018.
- [25] L. Bridel and C. Delapierre, "Sud-ouest lausannois: banlieue et modeles culturels," *Bulletin de la Societe Neuchateloise de Geographie*, vol. 27, pp. 85–213, 1982.
- [26] A. Byrne, *Perception and conceptual content*. Cambridge, MA, USA: MIT Press, 2005.

Development of an Alumni Databank: The Case of Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology

Emmanuel Carlos Navarro
College of Information and Communications Technology
Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology
Cabanatuan, Philippines
emmanuel.navarro@neust.edu.ph

Received: 6 January 2022 | Revised: 19 February 2022 | Accepted: 27 February 2022

Abstract- The Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology is the third oldest University in Nueva Ecija province. As the year progresses, the University keeps producing thousands of graduates during each academic year. An average of 4,737 individuals graduated from different programs during the past five years. The University is obligated by the Commission on Higher Education to collect up-to-date data and information through the CHECK system. Unfortunately, the office of alumni affairs and placement, which is in charge to collect and manage the graduates' information, does not have an automated alumni database system. This paper presents the development of an alumni databank. The online database record management system for alumni considerably benefits the University's Alumni Affairs and Placement Office, particularly in tracing its graduates and managing graduates' profile information. It can manage alumni profiles, notify graduates of job advertisements, and is capable of generating statistical reports with data analytics. Security measures were also employed to protect against any potential system breach and unauthorized use.

Keywords- alumni databank; electronic collection; analytics; higher education institution

I. INTRODUCTION

The Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST) is the third oldest school in the province of Nueva Ecija. Its academic mandate started in June 1908 in San Isidro, Nueva Ecija. Through the years, its name changed as more course offerings were introduced along with the increase of enrollees. It started providing vocational expertise as Wright Institute (1908-1928). In 1929, it was named Nueva Ecija Trade School (1929-1953) offering secondary education, then Central Luzon School of Arts and Trades (1953-1964), in 1964, it was promulgated as Central Luzon Polytechnic College (1964-1998) specializing in engineering courses, and in 1998 it started to be named Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology [1]. The University produces thousands of graduates each academic year. A yearly average of 4,737 individuals graduated from different programs in the past five years [2]. The University's graduates are deployed in various industries, promoting the University and allowing it to attract more students and maintain its competitiveness.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) mandates that Higher Education Institutions, either private, local, or state Universities, to submit data/information [3, 4]. With this development, the University regularly collects and manages records of its graduates. Data collection is a fundamental step to take in each research study [5]. According to authors in [6], databases for alumni are vital to every learning institution. They emphasize the school's needs in collecting data and information to communicate, verify, archive, and research the alumni. Many studies show that most colleges and universities, either private or public, must have a management tool to protect, maintain, and record their data. Hence, Graduate Tracer Studies (GTS) are commonly becoming a regular practice worldwide [7]. Doing this data/information collection helps the University monitor the graduates' placement, their specific skill sets, and the industry qualifications requirements.

NEUST regularly conducts tracer studies to follow-up on its graduates. The CHED per se has a Knowledge Management Division which is composed of three sections: Information Management, Knowledge Resource, and System Integration. Each section's primary purpose is to formulate, coordinate, and implement policies and guidelines related to higher education data collection, processing, and data banking through the Higher Education Management Information System (HEMIS) in all CHED offices and higher education institutions through the integration of CHED Electronic Collection and Knowledge System (CHECKS) [8]. Authors in [9], conducted a tracer study of Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) graduates. They extracted BSIT graduates' data with personal information from the registrar's office of the campus using Google Forms [10]. After getting the list, the link <https://tinyurl.com/bsit-tracer16-18> was disseminated to the CICT NEUSTSIC closed group. The authors in [11] undertook a survey with the help of some students and other faculty members of the College of Business Administration and Accountancy of their Academic Institution. Various means of data gathering were utilized, such as email and facebook messaging. The same instruments were used in the tracer study conducted in NEUST Atate Campus with a total of 118 graduates, 65 of which were BSITs (27 graduates of the year 2018 and 38 graduates of the year 2019), 24 were BSBA (Batch 2018), and 29 were BSEntres (Batch 2019) [12].

Corresponding author: Emmanuel C. Navarro

In NEUST, the Alumni Affairs and Placement Office does not maintain an automated alumni database system to keep relevant data of the University graduates. Instead, they still collect, process and file alumni data manually, which is tedious. The difficulty of Alumni Affairs and Placement Office starts when the graduates receive their diploma and other vital records from the University. Obtaining data from them becomes more challenging due to the lack of communication, changes of personal information, and lack of pertinent linkage to them. Thus, it takes some time to generate timely and reliable reports. To address these concerns, the development of an NEUST-SIC alumni databank is timely and relevant to the needs of the University. The developed Alumni Databank intends to establish a network between the graduates and the Alumni Affairs and Placement Office. The provision of analytics allows the information to be processed quickly, enables clarity of communication, and focuses on further analysis [13]. The printable reports are inclusive of graduates' total number and employability and are filtered according to gender and course. The Alumni Databank is deemed necessary to know and assess the graduates' present status [14] and for the University to have an alumni record repository.

II. OBJECTIVES

The greatest assets of any academic institution are the product of its labor, the alumni. For this reason, the objective of this study is to develop the NUEST-San Isidro Campus Alumni Databank, with the function to collect graduates' information that will help track their updated information as professionals and present a way to connect them to the University after graduation. Furthermore, this study aims to design an online database record of alumni, that is able to notify graduates for job advertisements, post future University activities, and capable of report generation with data analytics. It also adheres to demand technology that provides various services for storage and data availability from any place and at any time [15].

III. METHODOLOGY

This study used development research, a powerful method in the development of instructional technology. According to [16], the systematic review of designing, developing, and evaluating instructional programs, processes, and products must meet internal consistency and effectiveness criteria. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was applied. Authors in [17] define the TAM as an information technology framework for understanding users' adoption and use of emerging technologies, particularly in the workplace environment. If a user perceives a technology as easy to use and perceives it as useful to his needs, chances are he will accept it [18].

Fig. 1. TAM.

TAM is an information system theory used to look at technology at work, which deals with user acceptability behavior. According to [19], the perceived usefulness defines the degree to which a person believes that the system's use will improve his performance. However, perceived ease of use refers to the degree to which a person believes that the system's service will be effortless. Authors in [20] stated that Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) impact a person's state of mind toward utilizing a specific tool. The TAM models' primary goal is to determine the dominant use to accept or not to accept new systems, technology, instruments, or devices. It intends to utilize by controlling the individual's personality toward using a specific means.

IV. ALUMNI DATABANK DESIGN AND LIMITATIONS DURING THE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

The NEUST San Isidro Campus Alumni Databank was developed for only the NEUST San Isidro Campus. The data were gathered through online interviews conducted with the campus alumni coordinator. Further references were taken from the mandates of the CHED relevant to the graduate tracer studies, which were taken online. System Development Life Cycle (SDLC) was used in the development process. According to [21], a conceptual model includes policies and procedures for developing or altering systems throughout their cycle. Authors in [22] determined that SDLC is a mechanism used to produce deliverable systems and a vital instrument that aids in effective and efficient information systems. Authors in [23] explained that the lifecycle of an information system passes through various phases, starting with its conception down to the stage when it is no longer available for use. Figure 2 depicts the typical development phases followed systematically with tasks such as planning, analysis, design, implementation, and maintenance required to accomplish new or modified information systems.

Fig. 2. Information system life cycle.

The development starts with the planning phase where the researcher understands the problem and identifies and lays down possible threats and project constraints that may hinder the integration. In addition to that, a Gantt chart was created to monitor the progress of the project. The context diagram, drawn in Figure 3, defines and identifies the extreme boundaries and course of information of the entire system.

Fig. 3. Context diagram.

Fig. 4. Level 1 representation of the DFD processes.

The analysis phase included the detailed examination of collected data and user needs. In this way, processes can be tailored to fit any desired process [24]. This study dissected the collected data in multiple analyses to solve issues and come up with accurate and appropriate findings. Authors in [25] stated that one of the prerequisites for each computer system is the assurance of data integrity. By this process, the system will make sure that no changes are made in the database while in operation. This study follows three comprehensive stages of data analysis motivated by [26] which breaks down that data analysis covers everything from reading the source method of data collection to the creation and visualization of the extracted data. The evaluation was first. This stage helps determine and characterize the information of collected data to provide an outcome to achieve a goal. Secondly, the cleaning stages classified the information belonging to its entities. This eliminates duplications, irrelevant data, white spaces, and not valuable records. The output of this process is data integrity. Lastly, the summarizing stage assures that the collected data are reliable and rich in information, which is the basis for formulating data-driven decisions.

The design phase included designing the application, the database, and the user interface. This stage shows the way the system was conceptualized and ensures that the requirements have been met. Several software engineering diagrams were

made to recognize users' roles and the workflow processes of the developed system. Figure 4 illustrates the technical drawing showing how the developed Alumni Databank system worked.

The implementation phase started with coding and a series of tests to evaluate the system's functionality and usability. Lastly, the integration of the developed system into its new environment was conducted. Features of the developed system are limited only to graduates' online registration, posting of job fairs, and NEUST alumni-related activities, and organization job hiring. The alumni coordinator of the said campus is the one who will maintain and manage the Alumni Databank system. The use-case diagram in Figure 5 shows the distinct function and role of the user to the developed system. In this case, it describes the system's capability and how a particular user will utilize it.

Fig. 5. Use-case diagram.

A. Database Modeling

The representation of database modeling in information systems is a conceptual way to describe the data structure, which is required in database management. In this way, the data collection will be easy to organize, manage, maintain, protect, and provide access to as a computerized database. There are a lot of structure diagrams in designing a database. One of the most frequently used and applied in this study in illustrating the relationships of different entities to each other within the system is the Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) (Figure 6). The presented database schema identifies the relationships and attributes in each entity, e.g. users related to alumni, works, and education belong to the same class. In this case, the values recorded to alumni, works, and education are also recorded to the users. The values from the users are all recorded to the alumni, works, and education. The primary purpose of the ERD of the Alumni Databank is to visualize the physical database which is helpful in identifying mistakes and design flaws that allow necessary adjustments. Data entries have to be performed by the end-users who are the alumni and the Alumni personnel.

B. Security

The developed Alumni Databank incorporates protective measures and protocols to protect the information and limit the

possibility of data breach. To ensure the integrity and security of the system, the Alumni Databank has a user maintenance that allows two kinds of accounts that can be used to access the system. The "Admin Account," is the alumni coordinator, has complete control and responsibility for managing the system, and uses all the available functionalities, and the "End-user Account" with limited access and designated for the university graduates. Authentication features were used as the first line of protection. Only users with authorized username and password can access it. Also, the system administrator may check all the registered users which will serve as a countercheck for bogus accounts.

Fig. 6. An example ERD used in the development of the Alumni Databank.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Alumni Databank system was developed in order to help the Alumni Affairs and Placement Office of NEUST to

collect data and locate the graduate's whereabouts and have updated information about them. Figure 7 presents the system's architecture design. An internet connection is required to facilitate communication between the alumni and the developed Alumni Databank [27]. The front-end of the system was developed using HTML5 for the web structures, CSS3 for design, and JavaScript for the system's functional behavior. JQuery was also used for a more graphical representation of tables. Bootstrap 4.1.3, an open-source front-end toolkit, was used to make the web application responsive [28] and Fontawesome Webfont icons provided the visual icons. Using these front-end utilities, the Alumni Databank system was developed. Back-end development refers to the server-side of an application [29], which means users cannot see how the back-end works. However, this code integrates the system between its database to the browser. To make this integration possible, PHP 7.3.4-2 [30] was used. MariaDB Ver 15.1 Distrib 10.3.23 was used for defining the database structure along with MySQL Workbench and Sublime Text3 for coding.

Fig. 7. Web application architecture of the Alumni Databank.

Tracking graduate whereabouts is significant for Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). Moreso, the integration of industry 4.0 in the education system impacts strategic leadership [31] and transforms data-driven operations. The Alumni Databank is designed to keep the graduate's records of NEUST - San Isidro Campus and of the University as a whole. Figures 8 and 9 show the reports through a bar chart, the graduates per year and per course. The assigned campus alumni coordinator will have access to maintain and manage the system, while only administrators and coordinators have full access to the Alumni Databank. The end-users' privileges include creating and updating their profiles and browsing posted job advertisements and announcements.

Figure 10 displays the announcement module wherein the administrators and coordinators can manage the creation of job advertisements and University-related activity announcements. Only the administrator and the system developer can access the system database backup, access the graduate's lists and information, generate reports, and have the privilege to modify the system if there will be any change request.

Fig. 8. Graduate reports per year.

Fig. 9. Graduate reports per course.

Fig. 10. Job advertisement, University related activity announcement page.

The developed Alumni Databank establishes a network between the graduates and the Alumni Affairs and Placement Office. It considerably benefited the Office, particularly in tracing its graduates and managing their profiled information. With the existing system of graduates tracing, the office staff in charge encounters difficulties in merely looking for them via social media platforms, not to mention the limited data

available. Some graduates who are not active in social media or whose profile is different from their actual names are not tracked at all. Thus, the preparation of needed reports takes a lot of time and is prone for being incomplete, and is less reliable. This system would make it easier to prepare the documentation required by the CHED by establishing a standard communication gateway with graduates to collect their information after graduation. Compared to the manual system, obtaining data from them is no longer tedious since graduates themselves may update their personal information like contact numbers, address, and pertinent linkage to them can be acquired, tasks which were previously difficult to perform. The needed reports can easily be generated, printed or downloaded in PDF format by authorized system users. Data analytics was also integrated for a visual presentation of reports which have been more useful as compared to traditional reports created with the manual system.

VI. CONCLUSION

The repository of alumni record management for NEUST San Isidro Campus, was developed with the following functionalities: online registration, posting job opportunities offered by the University and other job advertisements from partner agencies. Reports with analytics were provided inclusive of generation of graduates statistics, employability and graduates aggregated according to their gender. The developed system was able to produce printable reports of alumni records with some data analytics. For further improvement in the future, the following recommendations are hereby given:

- Integration of the Alumni Databank system to the University system for full utilization in the NEUST - San Isidro Campus.
- Considering the said system implementation as a benchmark in aligning the inputs and processes of the NEUST, the said system can also be utilized in other Colleges/Campuses.
- The University Management of Information System (MIS) may integrate the Alumni Databank system to the University Portal for deployment.
- The Alumni Affairs and Placement Office director, the Vice President for Academic Affairs, the Vice President for Research, Extension and Training office, and all Alumni Coordinator per Colleges/Campuses in cooperation of the Deans and Directors may provide a set of guidelines regarding the system use prior to implementation.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Historical Background," *Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology*, Jun. 07, 2020. <https://neust.edu.ph/historical-background/> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).
- [2] "2020 Higher Education Facts and Figures," *CHED*. <https://ched.gov.ph/2020-higher-education-facts-and-figures/> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).
- [3] "2012 CHED Memorandum Orders," *CHED*. <https://ched.gov.ph/2012-ched-memorandum-orders/> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).
- [4] "2014 CHED Memorandum Orders," *CHED*. <https://ched.gov.ph/2014-ched-memorandum-orders/> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).

- [5] "How to Collect Data for Research Project," Sep. 16, 2021. <https://papersowl.com/blog/how-to-collect-data-for-research> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).
- [6] J. Etcuban and D. Durano, "Development of an Alumni Database for a University," *IAMURE International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. 12, pp. 109–128, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.7718/iamure.v12i1.953>.
- [7] E. O. Badiru and M. Wahome, "Conducting Graduate Tracer Studies for Quality Assurance in East African Universities: A Focus on Graduate Students Voices on Quality Culture," *Journal of Education and Practice*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 174–181, 2016.
- [8] "Knowledge Management Division," *CHED*. <https://ched.gov.ph/ched/official-organization-structure/office-planning-research-knowledge-management-oprkm/knowledge-management-division/> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).
- [9] J. C. Mina, E. J. G. Reyes, and R. F. Salas, "A Tracer Study of Bachelor of Science in Information Technology(BSIT) Graduates of Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST), San Isidro Campus," *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 1337–1344, 2020.
- [10] "Google Forms: Free Online Form Creator." <https://www.google.com/forms/about/> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).
- [11] R. Calma and M. Clarin, "A Tracer Study of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) Graduates of an Academic Institution from 2016 to 2018," May 2020. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341342842_A_Tracer_Study_of_the_Bachelor_of_Science_in_Business_Administration_BSBA_Graduates_of_an_Academic_Institution_from_2016_to_2018/references.
- [12] R. P. Corpuz, "Tracer Study of Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology Graduates (Atate Campus)," *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 434–440, 2020.
- [13] "Graphical Analysis | Continuous Improvement Toolkit." <https://citoolkit.com/articles/graphical-analysis/> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).
- [14] B. C. Lunar, "Employment Status of the Graduates of De La Salle Lipa's Certificate in Medical Transcription Program: A Tracer Survey and an Assessment," *International Journal of Advanced Engineering, Management and Science*, vol. 2, no. 6, Art. no. 239528, Jun. 2016.
- [15] M. F. Hyder, S. Tooba, and Waseemullah, "Performance Evaluation of RSA-based Secure Cloud Storage Protocol using OpenStack," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7321–7325, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4220>.
- [16] R. C. Richey, *Developmental Research: The Definition and Scope*. Washington, DC, USA: ERIC, 1994.
- [17] J. D. Portz *et al.*, "Using the Technology Acceptance Model to Explore User Experience, Intent to Use, and Use Behavior of a Patient Portal Among Older Adults With Multiple Chronic Conditions: Descriptive Qualitative Study," *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, vol. 21, no. 4, Apr. 2019, Art. no. e11604, <https://doi.org/10.2196/11604>.
- [18] Q. Ma and L. Liu, "The Technology Acceptance Model: A Meta-Analysis of Empirical Findings," *Journal of Organizational and End User Computing*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 59–72, Jan. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.4018/joeuc.2004010104>.
- [19] F. D. Davis, "Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology," *MIS Quarterly*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 319–340, 1989, <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>.
- [20] A. L. S. Hoong, L. S. Thi, and M. H. Lin, "Affective Technology Acceptance Model: Extending Technology Acceptance Model with Positive and Negative Affect," in *Knowledge Management Strategies and Applications*, London, UK: IntechOpen, 2017, pp. 147–165.
- [21] "SDLC Tutorial." <https://www.tutorialspoint.com/sdlc/index.htm> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).
- [22] F. Yakubu, B. I. Ahmad, O. M. Omowumi, and M. A. Mngohol, "Process and Database Modelling of a University Bursary System: A Perspective of Cash Office," *International Journal of Computer Science Issues*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 555–560, 2011.
- [23] S. Cohen, D. Dori, and U. de Haan, "A Software System Development Life Cycle Model for Improved Stakeholders' Communication and Collaboration," *International Journal of Computers Communications & Control*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 20–41, Mar. 2010.
- [24] A. Jones, "ISO 12207 Software life cycle processes — fit for purpose?," *Software Quality Journal*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 243–253, Dec. 1996, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00209183>.
- [25] M. Widera, J. Wrobel, A. Widera, and A. Matonia, "A method of ensuring data integrity in a data stream management system," *Journal of Medical Informatics & Technologies*, vol. 8, pp. 141–148, 2004.
- [26] "The Three Stages of Data Analysis: Evaluating Raw Data — Methodspace." <https://www.methodspace.com/blog/three-stages-data-analysis-evaluating-raw-data> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).
- [27] M. C. Lam, M. Ayob, J. Y. Lee, N. Abdullah, F. A. Hamzah, and S. S. M. Zahir, "Mobile-based Hospital Bed Management with Near Field Communication Technology : A Case Study," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5706–5712, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3527>.
- [28] M. Jacob and T. Otto, "Bootstrap V.5.0." <https://getbootstrap.com/docs/5.0/getting-started/introduction/> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).
- [29] "Front End Development vs Back End Development: Where to Start?," *Course Report*. <https://www.coursereport.com/blog/front-end-development-vs-back-end-development-where-to-start> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).
- [30] "PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor." <https://www.php.net/> (accessed Mar. 29, 2022).
- [31] M. F. Mubarak, F. A. Shaikh, M. Mubarik, K. A. Samo, and S. Mastoi, "The impact of digital transformation on business performance: a study of Pakistani SMEs," *Engineering Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 5056–5061, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3201>.

Application of Fminsearch Optimization to Minimize Total Maintenance Cost with the Aim of Reducing Environmental Degradation

Yasmina Bella

LAS Laboratory

Electrical Engineering Department

Ferhat Abbas Sétif University 1

Setif, Algeria

b_yasmina2014@univ-setif.dz

Kezzab Fatima Zohra

DACHR Electrical Engineering Department

Ferhat Abbas Sétif University 1

Setif, Algeria

fatimazohra.kezzab@univ-setif.dz

Received: 7 March 2022 | Revised: 24 March 2022 | Accepted: 28 March 2022

Abstract-This study examined a production system under deterioration and its impact on the degradation of the environment. The environment degrades as the production system reaches a certain level of deterioration. To reduce environmental degradation, the system's deterioration is monitored through scheduled inspections, after which preventive or corrective actions are taken. To achieve the optimum inspection dates that minimize the average total cost per time unit, the Fminsearch algorithm was applied to calculate the optimal inspection dates for two cases of sequential inspection: periodic and aperiodic. To validate the performance of the proposed Fminsearch algorithm, simulation results were compared with the Nelder-Mead method. The comparison results showed the superiority of the Fminsearch algorithm in optimizing inspection maintenance dates to reduce the environmental degradation ratio.

Keywords-environment degradation; fminsearch algorithm optimization; maintenance; Nelder-Mead; production system

I. INTRODUCTION

Environmental protection is described by international standards to which manufacturers must comply. The degradation of industrial systems can impact the environment in many ways. For example, the process of meeting energy demands raises concerns about energy sustainability and environmental protection, in conjunction with the market and regulatory requirements [1, 2]. Many environmental taxes have been imposed in recent decades all over the world. In the United States, the use of pollution prevention activities has increased significantly in the last two decades. The Pollution Prevention (P2) program is considered one of the main ways to reduce pollution [3, 4]. To ensure the efficient operation of an industrial system and meet the requirements of the environmental protection standards, inspection and maintenance activities are carried out. Inspection aids in controlling the degradation process of a production system and collecting crucial data on its reliability to determine the maintenance measures to be taken. Since the difficulties faced in maintenance inspections are attracting a lot of attention in

the industry, many inspection strategies have been developed. In [5], the optimal inspection dates and treats for the sequential inspection strategy were calculated, while a similar model was used in [6]. In [7], the same model was proposed with the estimate of the delay of the inspections, integrating the penalty cost in the mathematical model. The optimal inspection period and the maintenance threshold of system degradation were calculated in [8, 9]. A mathematical model was developed in [10] for the overall cost, including the production cost along with the maintenance action cost.

This study analyzed an inspection strategy that covers the environmental impact of the degradation of a production system. This strategy decreases degradation through maintenance actions to reduce environmental impact [11-13]. The system under consideration is submissive to continuous growing degradation. In this system, failure is detected only when it occurs, while the level of degradation of the system is only known after periodic or aperiodic sequential inspections. After checking the level of degradation when it exceeds a threshold, preventive actions are planned after a fixed timeframe, while corrective actions are carried out immediately after a system failure [14]. The main task was to minimize environmental degradation by decreasing the overall maintenance cost. The total cost is made up of the cost of corrective and preventive operations and inspection actions and the cost of penalties due to the environmental impact of system degradation. The main contribution of this study is the resolving of the optimization problem based on the Fminsearch algorithm. This algorithm is a direct search method to reduce non-linear functions [15-17].

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEM

A. Notations

The following notations are used:

- C_{cm} : The average cost of corrective maintenance.
- C_{ed} : The average cost per time unit of severe environmental degradation.

Corresponding author: Yasmina Bella

- C_{ins} : The average cost of an inspection.
- C_{pm} : The average cost of preventive maintenance.
- TF_p : The timeframe to perform preventive maintenance.
- T_{th} : A random elapsed time from when the system degradation began until it reaches the threshold.
- t : Variable of T_{th} on the time axis.
- f_d : The probability density function of T_{th} .
- X : A random elapsed time from instant t until failure (lifetime of the system after exceeding the threshold).
- x : Variable of X , from the instant t .
- g_d, G_d : probability density and distribution function of X respectively.
- N_{ins} : A random number of examinations during a cycle.
- $\varphi^*(\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_i)$: The vector of examination dates.
- T_{rd} : A random time of excessive environmental degradation.
- T_{cy} : A random cycle time measured between two consecutive maintenance actions: preventive or corrective.
- P_{cm} : Probability that the cycle will end with corrective maintenance action.
- P_{pm} : Probability that the cycle will end with preventive maintenance action.
- C_{tot} : The total cost incurred by maintenance and examination operations and by environmental degradation during a cycle.

B. Assumptions

This study was based on the following assumptions:

- After each inspection, two types of action are likely: to leave it as it is or perform preventive maintenance.
- Corrective maintenance is performed immediately after a system failure.
- The inspection actions are assumed to be perfect, i.e. the inspection reveals the actual level of the system's degradation without error.
- Corrective and preventive maintenance actions are meant to be perfect.
- The durations of inspection and maintenance actions are negligible.
- System degradation leads to environmental degradation.
- The system only fails if its degradation level exceeds the alarm threshold. Such a failure is supposed to be detected automatically (self-declared failure case).
- The system works as it should after corrective or preventive maintenance actions.

- The costs C_{cm}, C_{pm}, C_{ins} and C_{ed} , with the timeframe TF_p as well as the densities f_d and g_d are kept in the system's database.
- Preventive maintenance action is scheduled after a timeframe TF_p , if the inspection reveals that the level of degradation has exceeded the alarm threshold, as seen in Figure 1. Any inspections in this interval are canceled. As an example: in the interval $[\varphi_4, \varphi_4 + TF_p]$, the inspections are canceled.

Fig. 1. Evolution of system degradation and distribution of examinations over time.

III. THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF MAINTENANCE COST

This section presents the mathematical model of the average total cost per time unit Q of maintenance. Q is defined as the ratio between the average global cost $E(C_{tot})$ and the average cycle time $E(T_{cy})$ [18]:

$$Q = E(C_{tot}) / E(T_{cy}) \quad (1)$$

This cost includes the cost of preventive and corrective actions, the inspection cost, and the penalty cost. In the case of corrective action, the average cost is $(C_{cm} \times P_{cm})$, while the expression $(C_{pm} \times P_{pm})$ indicates the average cost in the case of preventive maintenance. $E(N_{ins})$ is defined as the average number of inspections during the time cycle, and their average cost is given by $C_{ins} \times E(N_{ins})$. $E(T_{ed})$ is the average time of the critical environmental degradation and the expression $C_{ed} \times E(T_{ed})$ corresponds to the penalty cost due to severe environmental degradation. The following formula illustrates the average cost:

$$E(C_{tot}) = (C_{cm} \times P_{cm}) + (C_{pm} \times P_{pm}) + (C_{ins} \times E(N_{ins})) + (C_{ed} \times E(T_{ed})) \quad (2)$$

This formula uses the proposals developed in [4, 18]. The probability P_{cm} that a time cycle will end with corrective actions is given by:

$$P_{cm} = \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\varphi_{i-1}}^{\varphi_i} G_d(\varphi_i + TF_p - t) f_d(t) dt \quad (3)$$

The probability that corresponds to the case where the time cycle ends with preventive action is given by:

$$P_{pm} = 1 - P_{cm} \quad (4)$$

The average number $E(N_{ins})$ of examinations during a time cycle is given by:

$$E(N_{ins}) = \sum_{i=1}^n i \left(\int_0^{\varphi_{i+1}} G_d(\varphi_{i+1} - t) f_d(t) dt \times \int_0^{\varphi_i} G_d(\varphi_i - t) f_d(t) dt \right) \quad (5)$$

The average time $E(T_{rd})$ of excessive environmental degradation through a time cycle is given by:

$$E(T_{rd}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\varphi_{i-1}}^{\varphi_i} \left(\int_0^{\varphi_i+TF_p-t} [1 - G_d(x)] dx \right) f_d(t) dt \quad (6)$$

The expression of the numerator of the function presented by (1) is concluded from (2) - (6) as:

$$E(C_{tot}) = ((P_{cm} - P_{pm}) \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\varphi_{i-1}}^{\varphi_i} G_d(\varphi_i + TF_p - t) f_d(t) dt + P_{pm} + C_{ins} \sum_{i=1}^n i \left(\int_0^{\varphi_{i+1}} G(\varphi_{i+1} - t) f_d(t) dt \int_0^{\varphi_i} G(\varphi_i - t) f_d(t) dt \right) + C_{ed} \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\varphi_{i-1}}^{\varphi_i} \left(\int_0^{\varphi_i+TF_p-t} [1 - G_d(x)] dx \right) f_d(t) dt \quad (7)$$

The denominator of (1) is given by:

$$E(T_{cy}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\varphi_{i-1}}^{\varphi_i} \left(t + \int_0^{\varphi_i+TF_p-t} [1 - G_d(x)] dx \right) f_d(t) dt \quad (8)$$

From (7) and (8), the general expression of the mathematical model of the average total cost per time unit of the maintenance function defined by (1) is deduced as:

$$Q(\varphi_i) = \frac{\left((P_{cm} - P_{pm}) \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\varphi_{i-1}}^{\varphi_i} G_d(\varphi_i + TF_p - t) f_d(t) dt + P_{pm} + C_{ins} \sum_{i=1}^n i \left(\int_0^{\varphi_{i+1}} G(\varphi_{i+1} - t) f_d(t) dt \int_0^{\varphi_i} G(\varphi_i - t) f_d(t) dt \right) + C_{ed} \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\varphi_{i-1}}^{\varphi_i} \left(\int_0^{\varphi_i+TF_p-t} [1 - G_d(x)] dx \right) f_d(t) dt \right)}{\sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\varphi_{i-1}}^{\varphi_i} \left(t + \int_0^{\varphi_i+TF_p-t} [1 - G_d(x)] dx \right) f_d(t) dt} \quad (9)$$

The minimum value of the average total cost per time unit $\min Q(\varphi)$ is considered an objective function. The Fminsearch optimization was applied to calculate the optimal inspections vector to reduce the environmental degradation ratio and minimize the maintenance cost value $Q(\varphi)$.

IV. OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE

A periodic and an aperiodic sequential examination plan were applied to solve the problem without any constraint on the examination periods. In the aperiodic plan, the interval between examinations is independent. This problem is a multidimensional nonlinear problem [19]. The mathematical model exposed in Section III was exploited to solve this problem. The objective was to find the optimal examination dates which minimize the average total cost per time unit $Q(\varphi_i)$ given by (9). The Fminsearch algorithm was used to find the minimum of an unconstrained multivariable function using a derivative-free method. This algorithm has been used repeatedly to resolve nonlinear functions and is well known for its robustness and ease of implementation [14].

A. Analytical Procedure

The flowchart shown in Figure 2 corresponds to the analytical approach and was developed to determine the optimal sequential examination dates that minimize the average global cost per time unit. At first, the input data: $f_d, g_d, C_{cm}, C_{pm}, C_{ed}, C_{ins}$ and TF_p are given. Afterward, the Fminsearch algorithm is applied to calculate the optimal vector of examination dates $(\varphi^*(\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_n))$. Then, the iteration number is tested: If the inequality $n > N$ is unattained, n increases. If it was attained, iterations stop. Finally, the solution vector of examination dates φ_i that match up to the minimum value $Q(\varphi_i)$ is selected.

```

Begin
% inputs
f_d : % the probability density function of T_{th}
g_d : % the probability density function of X
C_{cm} : % the average cost of corrective maintenance
C_{pm} : % the average cost of preventive maintenance
C_{ed} : % the average cost of environmental degradation
C_{ins} : % the average cost of examination (inspection)
TF_p : % timeframe to perform preventive maintenance
N : % iteration number
i = 1;
While i ≤ N;
    fun = Q(φ_i); /* function cost*/
    (φ_i^*, valQ(φ_i^*)) = fminsearch(fun, φ_i); % optimize the maintenance function cost
End while
valQ(φ^*)_{min} = min(valQ(φ_1^*), valQ(φ_2^*), valQ(φ_N^*)); % optimal value of function cost
sol(φ^*) = φ^*; % solution of optimal examination vector
End.
    
```

Fig. 2. Pseudo code of the Fminsearch algorithm.

Two techniques were proposed to calculate the optimal inspection dates of the production system: periodic and aperiodic sequential inspection. The results of the Fminsearch algorithm were compared to the Nelder-Mead optimization method [18, 20].

B. Numerical Applications

The above procedure was used to estimate the optimal examination dates. The input data were provided: probability densities f_d and g_d , the costs $C_{cm}, C_{pm}, C_{ed}, C_{ins}$ and time flow TF_p . Time was expressed in time units, while cost was expressed in monetary units. λ is the ratio between the mean time $E(T_{rd})$ of severe environmental degradation and the average time $E(T_{cy})$ of the time cycle:

$$\lambda = \frac{E(T_{rd})}{E(T_{cy})} \quad (10)$$

Therefore:

$$\lambda = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\varphi_{i-1}}^{\varphi_i} \left(\int_0^{\varphi_i+TF_p-t} [1 - G_d(x)] dx \right) f_d(t) dt}{\sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\varphi_{i-1}}^{\varphi_i} \left(t + \int_0^{\varphi_i+TF_p-t} [1 - G_d(x)] dx \right) f_d(t) dt} \quad (11)$$

1) Periodic Sequential Examination

In this case, inspection is performed periodically. The inspection period $\Delta\varphi$ is defined as:

$$\Delta\varphi = (\varphi_i) - (\varphi_{i-1}) = Cte, \quad i = 1, 2 \dots n \quad (12)$$

The probability densities f_d and g_d correlate jointly to the random variables T_{cy} and X . The probability density f_d is given by:

$$f_d(\tau) = \frac{1}{\sigma f \sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\tau - \mu f}{\sigma f} \right)^2} \quad (13)$$

with $\mu f = 1100$ and $\sigma f = 150$. The probability density g_d is given by:

$$g_d(\tau) = \frac{1}{\sigma g \sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\tau - \mu g}{\sigma g} \right)^2} \quad (14)$$

with $\mu g = 130$ and $\sigma g = 40$. The average costs are fixed as $C_{cm} = 16108, C_{pm} = 988,$ and $C_{ins} = 150.$ C_{ed} and TF_p are introduced as parameters.

a) Application 1:

To examine the impact of cost C_{ed} over the cost $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ and the ratio λ , the analytical Fminsearch algorithm was implemented in Matlab. The delay TF_p was considered negligible, so the preventive operations are executed immediately. The cost $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ and the ratio λ are presented in Table I.

TABLE I. THE IMPACT OF COST C_{ed} OVER $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ AND RATIO λ WITH $TF_p = 0$, IN THE CASE OF A PERIODIC INSPECTION STRATEGY

C_{ed}	$\Delta\varphi^*$	$E(N_{ins})$	$E(T_{rd})$	C_{tot}	$E(T_{cy})$	$Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$	λ [%]
0	22	3.48	15.02	987.36	726	1.36	2.07
10	19	2.01	8.50	985.53	541.5	1.82	1.57
20	18	2.20	5.97	986.58	486	2.03	1.23
30	15	3.54	3.51	985.50	337.5	2.92	1.04
40	13	2.12	2.53	986.11	253.5	3.89	1.00
50	12	1.62	1.96	987.12	216	4.57	0.91

As shown in Table I, when C_{ed} increases, λ decreases, reducing the rate of environmental degradation. $E(T_{ed})$ decreases by increasing the penalty cost C_{ed} , therefore the rate of environmental deterioration decreases. Figure 3 presents the variation of $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ as a function of C_{ed} . The results obtained by the Fminsearch algorithm show a decrease in the value of $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$. This value varies from 55.11% to 2.76% compared to the Nelder-Mead method.

Fig. 3. Influence of penalty cost C_{ed} over $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ in the case of a periodic examination strategy.

Fig. 4. Impact of penalty cost C_{ed} on the ratio λ , in the case of periodic examination strategy.

Figure 4 shows the variations of λ . The Fminsearch algorithm gives lower values that vary from 46.37% to 67.38%

compared to the Nelder-Mead, for an increasing value of C_{ed} . On the other hand, the ratio λ decreases by increasing the penalty cost, i.e. the degradation of the system as well as that of the environment are reduced.

b) Application 2

The penalty cost C_{ed} was fixed at 20 monetary units to study the impact of the duration TF_p over $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ and λ . Table II shows the optimal period between inspections $\Delta\varphi^*$ for different values of the parameter TF_p , by applying the Fminsearch algorithm. From Table II, it is noted that for $TF_p = 0$, λ and $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ have a minimal value of 1.20% and 1.64, respectively. Therefore, preventive operations should be carried out as soon as possible, i.e. the delay TF_p , should be minimal. Figure 5 presents the variation of the optimal value of the cost $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ as a function of TF_p . The Fminsearch algorithm gives better cost optimization for low values of TF_p , (up to 56.50%).

TABLE II. THE IMPACT OF TF_p OVER $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ AND λ WITH $C_{ed} = 20$, IN THE CASE OF A PERIODIC EXAMINATION STRATEGY.

TF_p	$\Delta\varphi^*$	$E(N_{ins})$	$E(T_{rd})$	C_{tot}	$E(T_{cy})$	$Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$	λ [%]
0	20	2.41	7.2	984	600	1.64	1.20
10	17	1.35	8.97	984.04	433.5	2.27	2.07
20	14	2.75	9.73	987.84	294	3.36	3.31
30	13	2.12	10.74	981.04	253.5	3.89	4.24
40	11	1.23	8.67	987.36	181.5	5.44	4.78
50	10	2.44	6.19	797.04	121.5	6.58	5.10

Fig. 5. Impact of timeframe TF_p over $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$, in the case of periodic examination strategy.

Fig. 6. Influence of timeframe TF_p over λ , in the case of a periodic inspection sequential strategy.

Figure 6 shows that the ratio λ increases with the lengthening of the time to carry out preventive operations. The Fminsearch algorithm gives an improved λ compared to the Nelder-Mead method.

2) *Aperiodic Sequential Examination*

The probability densities f_d and g_d correspond to the random variables T_{th} and X , respectively. It is assumed that each of the two densities follows the Weibull law whose scale parameter is expressed in time units, while the form parameter has no unit. The probability density f_d is given by:

$$f_d(t) = \left(\frac{\beta_f}{\alpha_f}\right) \left(\frac{t}{\alpha_f}\right)^{\beta_f-1} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\alpha_f}\right)^{\beta_f}} \quad (15)$$

where the scale parameter is $\alpha_f = 1164$ and the shape parameter is $\beta_f = 8.7$. The probability density g_d of the random time X elapsed from the instant t until the occurrence of the failure is given by:

$$g_d(x) = \left(\frac{\beta_g}{\alpha_g}\right) \left(\frac{x}{\alpha_g}\right)^{\beta_g-1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha_g}\right)^{\beta_g}} \quad (16)$$

where the scale parameter is $\alpha_g = 144$ and the form parameter is $\beta_g = 3.6$. The average costs are respectively fixed as $C_{cm} = 6180$, $C_{pm} = 4170$, and $C_{ins} = 492$, while C_{ed} and TF_p are introduced as parameters.

a) *Application 3:*

The effect of C_{ed} on $Q(\varphi^*)$ and λ was examined using the Fminsearch algorithm, when TF_p is fixed at zero, i.e. when preventive maintenance actions are not delayed. Table III shows the optimal Q for each value of the optimal vector φ^* . When $C_{ed} = 0$, $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ has a minimum and λ has a maximum value of 3.23 and 3%, respectively. According to Table III, the increase in the C_{ed} penalty cost induces an increase in the number of inspections. These additional inspections are necessary to detect, as quickly as possible, the exceeding of the degradation threshold to reduce the resulting cost, i.e. the reduction of $(C_{ed} \times E(T_{rd}))$.

TABLE III. THE IMPACT OF PENALTY COST C_{ed} OVER $Q(\varphi^*)$ AND λ , IN CASE OF A PERIODIC SEQUENTIAL INSPECTION STRATEGY

C_{ed}	φ^*	$Q(\varphi^*)$	$\lambda\%$
0	1.33, 5.99, 48.59	3.23	3.00
10	2.18, 6.15, 10.32, 12.96, 54.21	3.48	2.67
20	2.50, 5.89, 9.40, 15.04, 62.60	3.93	2.40
30	1.32, 4.58, 8.74, 9.24, 23.99, 62.49	4.94	2.22
40	1.32, 3.36, 8.74, 10.24, 24.03, 62.50	5.95	2.20
50	1.40, 4.58, 8.60, 9.80, 25.30, 61.49	6.96	2.17

Figure 7 shows the variation of the optimal value of the average total cost per time unit $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ according to the penalty cost C_{ed} . The evolution of $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ is directly proportional to the C_{ed} cost. The obtained results show that Fminsearch gives a better optimization of the cost $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ compared to the Nelder-Mead algorithm, as there is a decrease in the value of $Q(\Delta\varphi^*)$ up to 30.08%. The variation of the rate of degradation λ as a function of C_{ed} is presented in Figure 8. The evolution of the ratio λ is inversely proportional to C_{ed} , which implies that excessive environmental degradation is

reduced. Figure 8 confirms the superiority of the Fminsearch algorithm compared to the Nelder-Mead in minimizing the degradation ratio. The Fminsearch algorithm has a maximum reduction of 60.05% compared to the Nelder-Mead at $C_{ed} = 0$

Fig. 7. Influence of the penalty cost C_{ed} on $Q(\varphi^*)$ in the case of an aperiodic sequential inspection strategy.

Fig. 8. Influence of the penalty cost C_{ed} on degradation rate λ in case of an aperiodic sequential inspection strategy.

b) *Application 4:*

To evaluate the impact of TF_p over $Q(\varphi^*)$ and λ , the cost C_{ed} was set to 30 currency units, while several values are assigned to the duration TF_p . Table IV shows the average total cost per time unit $Q(\varphi^*)$ with the corresponding ratio λ for each vector φ^* .

TABLE IV. INFLUENCE OF THE DURATION F_p OVER $Q(\varphi^*)$ AND λ IN CASE OF AN APERIODIC SEQUENTIAL EXAMINATION STRATEGY

TF_p	φ^*	$Q(\varphi^*)$	$\lambda\%$
0	2.27, 3.73, 6.41, 7.79, 10.48, 63.39	4.00	2.59
10	4.23, 6.35, 7.56, 19.00, 59.88	5.24	3.53
20	3.43, 5.68, 21.51, 60.97	6.30	4.31
30	3.70, 5.76, 19.18, 56.98	7.32	5.14
40	1.28, 8.37, 54.14	8.38	5.92
50	1.24, 8.79, 55.29	9.36	6.26

According to Table IV, in the case where the duration TF_p is set to zero, the ratio λ is minimal and equal to 2.59%, and the optimal value of the average total cost per time unit $Q(\varphi^*)$ is 4.00. Figure 9 shows the optimal value of the average total cost per time unit $Q(\varphi^*)$ concerning TF_p . The Fminsearch

algorithm gives a better optimization of the cost, up to 53.04%, for low values of TF_p . Figure 10 shows the degradation rate λ as a function of TF_p . The Fminsearch algorithm improves the λ up to 53.99% compared to the Nelder-Mead algorithm.

Fig. 9. Influence of the duration TF_p over $Q(\phi^*)$ in the case of an aperiodic sequential inspection strategy.

Fig. 10. Influence of the duration TF_p on λ in the case of an aperiodic sequential inspection strategy.

V. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to maintain a production system whose declining performance causes environmental degradation by applying the Fminsearch algorithm to optimize periodic and aperiodic inspection maintenance dates. This method improved the impact of the environmental degradation cost C_{ed} and the duration TF_p on the total average maintenance cost and the ratio of environmental degradation. Moreover, the results of this method were compared to those of the Nelder-Mead method. The simulation results showed the superior performance of the Fminsearch algorithm in the optimization of inspection maintenance dates to reduce the ratio of environmental degradation.

Future work could examine the modification of certain assumptions, such as the duration of inspections and maintenance actions. These hypotheses could enable the study of the production system availability. Other optimization methods such as metaheuristics or simulation methods could be applied, while the industrial production could be described with real data.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. M. Kumar and N. A. Singh, "Environmental Economic Dispatch with the use of Particle Swarm Optimization Technique based on Space Reduction Strategy," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4605–4611, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2969>.
- [2] K. Siderakis, D. Pylarinos, E. Thalassinakis, I. Vitellas, and E. Pyrgioti, "Pollution Maintenance Techniques in Coastal High Voltage Installations," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–7, Feb. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.6>.
- [3] L. T. M. Bui and S. Kapon, "The impact of voluntary programs on polluting behavior: Evidence from pollution prevention programs and toxic releases," *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, vol. 64, no. 1, pp. 31–44, Jul. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2012.01.002>.
- [4] D. R. Harrington, "Two-stage adoption of different types of pollution prevention (P2) activities," *Resource and Energy Economics*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 349–373, Sep. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reseneeco.2012.02.002>.
- [5] Y. S. Sherif and M. L. Smith, "Optimal maintenance models for systems subject to failure—A Review," *Naval Research Logistics Quarterly*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 47–74, 1981, <https://doi.org/10.1002/nav.3800280104>.
- [6] L. A. Cox Jr. and Y. Qiu, "Optimal inspection and repair of renewable coherent systems with independent components and constant failure rates," *Naval Research Logistics (NRL)*, vol. 41, no. 6, pp. 771–788, 1994, [https://doi.org/10.1002/1520-6750\(199410\)41:6<771::AID-NAV3220410607>3.0.CO;2-0](https://doi.org/10.1002/1520-6750(199410)41:6<771::AID-NAV3220410607>3.0.CO;2-0).
- [7] A. Chelbi and D. Ait-Kadi, "An optimal inspection strategy for randomly failing equipment," *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, vol. 63, no. 2, pp. 127–131, Feb. 1999, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0951-8320\(98\)00031-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0951-8320(98)00031-3).
- [8] B. Castanier, C. Béranger, and A. Grall, "A sequential condition-based repair/replacement policy with non-periodic inspections for a system subject to continuous wear," *Applied Stochastic Models in Business and Industry*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 327–347, 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1002/asmb.493>.
- [9] A. Mancuso, M. Compare, A. Salo, and E. Zio, "Optimal Prognostics and Health Management-driven inspection and maintenance strategies for industrial systems," *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, vol. 210, Jun. 2021, Art. no. 107536, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2021.107536>.
- [10] M. Sharifi and S. Taghipour, "Optimal production and maintenance scheduling for a degrading multi-failure modes single-machine production environment," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 106, Jul. 2021, Art. no. 107312, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2021.107312>.
- [11] W. Fauriat and E. Zio, "Optimization of an aperiodic sequential inspection and condition-based maintenance policy driven by value of information," *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, vol. 204, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 107133, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2020.107133>.
- [12] M. L. Neves, L. P. Santiago, and C. A. Maia, "A condition-based maintenance policy and input parameters estimation for deteriorating systems under periodic inspection," *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, vol. 61, no. 3, pp. 503–511, Oct. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2011.04.005>.
- [13] O. A. Adebimpe, V. Oladokun, and O. E. Charles-Owaba, "Preventive Maintenance Interval Prediction: a Spare Parts Inventory Cost and Lost Earning Based Model," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 811–817, Jun. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.565>.
- [14] N. Rezg, S. Dellagi, and A. Khatib, "Joint Optimization Service and Maintenance Policies under Environmental Constraints," in *Joint Optimization of Maintenance and Production Policies*, London, UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2014, pp. 105–130.
- [15] L. M. Rios and N. V. Sahinidis, "Derivative-free optimization: a review of algorithms and comparison of software implementations," *Journal of Global Optimization*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 1247–1293, Jul. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10898-012-9951-y>.

-
- [16] S. Lavania and D. Nagaria, "Fminsearch Optimization Based Model Order Reduction," in *2016 Second International Conference on Computational Intelligence Communication Technology (CICT)*, Ghaziabad, India, Oct. 2016, pp. 568–571, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CICT.2016.118>.
- [17] L. Wu and Q. Zhou, "Adaptive sequential predictive maintenance policy with nonperiodic inspection for hard failures," *Quality and Reliability Engineering International*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 1173–1185, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1002/qre.2788>.
- [18] H. Chouikhi, "Optimisation des stratégies de maintenance verte pour les systèmes de production," Ph.D. dissertation, Université de Lorraine, Lorraine, France, 2012.
- [19] S. Khouni and K. E. Hemsas, "Nonlinear System Identification using Uncoupled State Multi-model Approach: Application to the PCB Soldering System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5221–5227, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3247>.
- [20] H. Chouikhi, A. Khatab, and N. Rezg, "A condition-based maintenance policy for a production system under excessive environmental degradation," *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 727–737, Aug. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10845-012-0715-9>.

A Study of the Impact of Iron Content on the Thermal Response of the sPP/Fe Composites

Abdulaal Z. Al-Khazaal

Department of Chemical and Material Engineering
Northern Border University
Arar, Saudi Arabia
abdulaal.alkhazaal@nbu.edu.sa

Naveed Ahmad

Department of Chemical and Material Engineering
Northern Border University
Arar, Saudi Arabia
naveed.ahmad@nbu.edu.sa

Received: 6 March 2022 | Revised: 24 March 2022 | Accepted: 29 March 2022

Abstract—A set of syndiotactic polypropylene/iron (sPP/Fe) composite samples were manufactured with the extrusion technique to study the impact of iron content on the thermal behavior of sPP/Fe composites in the melt phase. The dosage of iron contents varied from 0 to 8%. Melting point (T_m), crystallization temperature (T_c), and thermal degradation temperature (T_d) were measured by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and Thermal Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) for each composite sample. Thermal temperatures (T_m , T_c , and T_d) increased with increasing the iron contents due to the enhancement of the strength and thermal stability of the sample. This investigation is a validated fact that fillers (iron) alter both the macroscopic and microscopic properties of the polymer composites.

Keywords—thermal properties; DSC; TGA; polymer composites; thermal degradation temperature

I. INTRODUCTION

Polymer composites have become one of the most important manufactured materials and can be industrialized by the incorporation of filler (natural or synthetic) into the polymer to improve its targeted properties [1-5]. Polymer composites with different types of fillers and combinations are widely used with improved mechanical, thermal, barrier and fire resistant properties for different applications [6-8]. However, the end desired microstructure and macrostructure properties of polymer composites are greatly dependent on the nature, amount, geometry and interfacial interactions of the components [9]. The thermal properties are highly dependent and sensitive to microstructure properties of polymer and polymer composites [10-14]. Therefore, the relationship of the thermal response and microstructure properties is an excellent key in both the process and quality control to realize and develop new materials with the desired properties. Thermal properties can be used in the understanding of molecular structure and the link with both microstructure and macrostructure properties [6, 7, 15-18]. Some of the recent scientific advances in the iron/polymer and its properties are mentioned below.

Authors in [19] investigated the thermal properties including thermal conductivity, thermal diffusivity, and

specific heat of metal (copper, zinc, iron, and bronze) powder-filled high-density polyethylene composites experimentally in the range of filler content 0-24%. They found a region of low particle content (0-16%), where the particles are embedded homogeneously in the polymer matrix and do not interact with each other. Fillers at higher content regions, tend to accumulate and conductive chains result in a quiche enhancement in thermal conductivity. Authors in [20] studied the thermo-mechanical properties of polymer/metal composites. The Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) was used as a matrix and copper and iron particles as fillers. The effect of metal powder was studied to confirm the effects of metal particles on the thermo-mechanical properties of the composites, such as tensile strength and thermal conductivity. It was found that the tensile strength of the composites decreases with increasing loading of the metal particles, while the thermal conductivity of the metal/polymer composite filament was found to improve by increasing metal content. More recently, authors in [21] examined the electrical and thermal conductivity of the ternary epoxy composites (CMs) with two-component fillers, multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNT)/TiO₂, and MWCNT/carbonyl iron (Fe). Both electrical and thermal properties were found sensitive to both fillers. However, MWCNT/TiO₂ or MWCNT/Fe into epoxy supports smaller changes in thermal conductivity as compared to the two-phase MWCNT/epoxy composites.

To the best of our knowledge, the understanding of the thermal properties of syndiotactic polypropylene/Iron (sPP/Fe) has not been established by now. Thus, in the present work, sPP/Fe composites with different iron dosages were investigated to study the influence of iron content on the thermal properties of the composites, including melting point temperature (T_m), crystallization temperature (T_c), and thermal degradation temperature (T_d).

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Experimental Work

1) Materials

Polymer composites were prepared using Syndiotactic polypropylene (sPP) and iron (Fe) with content variety as a

Corresponding author: Abdulaal Z. Al-Khazaal

filler. Zhongwei Industrial Co. Ltd supplied the polymer with 60% degree of syndiotacticity, and Sigma Aldrich provided the iron in powder form. Five samples were prepared with Fe content varying from 0 to 8% with a step size of 2%.

2) Preparation of Polymer Composites

The extrusion technique was used to formulate a set of sPP/Fe composites with different percentages of Fe as shown in Table I. For each sample, at first the required amount of Fe was dried in an oven at 75°C for 24 hours, and then it was accurately weighed. After that, when the extruder reached 250°C, both polypropylene and the required amount of iron entered the extruder for mixing to prepare the composite samples. The size of the prepared polymer-iron composite sample was mechanically reduced to suitable size before completely dried. Then, a film of the composite sample was prepared by compression molding at 170°C and 7Psi pressure for the duration of 1 hour using Hot Press.

B. Analytical Work

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and Thermal Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) were conducted to investigate the influence of iron content on the thermal behavior of the sPP/Fe composites.

1) Differential Scanning Calorimetry

The melting temperature (T_m) of all samples was determined by DSC using non-isothermal crystallization tests. Two main cycles (heating and cooling) were used in this technique. In the heating cycle, the sample having a weight of 4mg was heated up to 200°C at a constant heating rate of 10°C/min. After the melting point peak was obtained, the sample was kept under this annealing process for 5 minutes in order to eliminate the crystallinity and remove thermal history. During the cooling cycle, the DSC temperature was decreased up to -130°C with a cooling rate of -10°C/min. Therefore, the peaks of crystallinity and glassy behavior of the composites were observed. Evaluations were made using the instrument software TA-60 to estimate the melting temperature (T_m) and crystallization temperature (T_c) of all the samples.

2) Thermal Gravimetric Analysis

Thermal degradation temperature (T_d) shows the maximum temperature at which a polymer is useful. In this investigation, the thermal degradation temperature of all composites was measured using TGA. This analysis was conducted by observing the drop in the mass of the composite sample. In the beginning of the analysis, the sample was weighed, and then loaded to the equipment and heated up to 600°C. During the heating process, the polymer started to burn at a certain temperature where the fall in the mass of samples was observed. The obtained results were analyzed with TA-60 for each sample.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table I expresses the thermal information of all polymer composites extracted from DSC and TGA. The number shown in the sample ID represents the percentage of sPP and Fe in each composite sample.

TABLE I. THERMAL TEMPERATURES OF THE COMPOSITE SAMPLES

Sample ID	Fe %	T_c (°C)	T_m (°C)	T_d (°C)
PP-Fe-(100-0)	0	113.96	146.72	360
PP-Fe-(98-02)	2	114.79	147.86	380
PP-Fe-(96-04)	4	115.76	148.62	395
PP-Fe-(94-06)	6	116.51	149.71	405
PP-Fe-(92-08)	8	117.69	150.62	418

A. The Effect of Iron Content on Crystallization Temperature

DSC determines the heat flow as a function of temperature, which is directly related to the latent heat of crystallization. In DSC measurements, the temperature at the peak of the endothermic heat flow represents the crystallization temperature of the composite sample. Fig. 1. Figure 1 illustrates the experimental results of DSC related to the crystallization temperature of each sample. Figure 2 shows the relation between the crystallization temperatures of a set of composite samples with different Fe content. It was found that the increase in Fe content increases the crystallization temperature and hence the crystallinity of the composites due to the increase of the crystalline phase.

Fig. 1. DSC results (T_c) of all composite samples.

Fig. 2. Relationship between iron content and crystallization temperature.

B. The Effect of Iron Content on Melting Point Temperature

The melting point of all the samples was determined from the peak of DSC as displayed in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. DSC results of all samples showing the melting point peak.

The influence of Fe content on the melting point of the composites was noted. The melting point was found to increase with the increase in the Fe content as illustrated in Figure 4. This can be related to the fact that an increase in the Fe content increases the adhesive properties of the composites and more energy is required to break the bonds of monomers. In other words, an increase in Fe content increases the latent heat of fusion of the composite samples.

Fig. 4. Relationship between the Fe content and the melting point of all composite samples.

C. The Effect of Iron Content on Thermal Degradation Temperature

The T_d of sPP/Fe was measured by TGA. Figure 5 displays that T_d changes with the Fe content of sPP/Fe composites. T_d is noted from the dropping point of the mass of the sample (the point at which the mass of the composites starts to drop). This is the maximum point of thermal tolerance of the sample. At this point, irreversible changes occur in the sample. We noted two drops in the mass of sPP/Fe samples. The first drop occurred at relatively low temperature due to the removal of moisture content from the sample. The second drop occurred at higher temperature, which shows the drop in the mass of the sample.

The relationship between thermal degradation temperature and Fe content is presented in Figure 6. The thermal degradation temperature increases when Fe content increases. The thermal degradation can be related to the fact that Fe content enhances the thermal stability of the sPP/Fe

composites. T_d shows the maximum temperature at which a polymer is useful. At higher temperatures, the components of the long chain of the polymer can disrupt (chain scission) and interact with one another (cross-link), thus altering the properties of the polymer.

Fig. 5. TGA results of the composite samples.

Fig. 6. Relationship of Fe content and degradation temperature.

In the light of the above findings, it is clear that Fe as filler alters the thermal properties of sPP/FE composites. The same result was found in [17]. The authors found that rheological and thermal properties like melting point vary with varying filler content. To the best of our knowledge, the thermal properties of sPP/FE composites have not yet been studied.

IV. CONCLUSION

Thermal properties including melting point, crystallization, and thermal degradation temperatures are used as a tool to predict not only thermal stability, but also other microstructure properties and polymer chain dimensions which affects overall polymer chain dynamics. The iron content alters the thermal properties of the polymer composites and hence the polymer chain dimensions. The experimental results established that thermal measurements performed on sPP/Fe composites of different iron contents show that melting point, crystallization temperature and thermal degradation temperature significantly depend on the iron loading. In other words, crystallization, melting point, and thermal degradation temperature increase with increase in the iron dosage due to the consequently

increased crystallinity, increased latent heat of fusion, and increased the thermal stability respectively.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was funded by the Deanship of Scientific Research at Northern Border University through the Fast-track Research Funding Program (ENG-2018-3-9-F-7595).

REFERENCES

- [1] D. J. Arriola, E. M. Carnahan, P. D. Hustad, R. L. Kuhlman, and T. T. Wenzel, "Catalytic Production of Olefin Block Copolymers via Chain Shuttling Polymerization," *Science*, vol. 312, no. 5774, pp. 714–719, May 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1125268>.
- [2] V. C. Gibson, "Shuttling Polyolefins to a New Materials Dimension," *Science*, vol. 312, no. 5774, pp. 703–704, May 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1127258>.
- [3] A. S. Alghamdi, "Synthesis and Mechanical Characterization of High Density Polyethylene/Graphene Nanocomposites," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2814–2817, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1961>.
- [4] N. Ahmad, E. Fouad, and F. Ahmad, "Effect of Shear Flow on Crystallization of Syndiotactic Polypropylene/Clay Composites," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3108–3112, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2079>.
- [5] N. Ahmad, F. Ahmad, and I. Alenezi, "Influence of Starch Content on the Thermal and Viscoelastic Properties of Syndiotactic Polypropylene/Starch Composites," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7228–7232, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4161>.
- [6] Y. Xiang, Z. Peng, and D. Chen, "A new polymer/clay nano-composite hydrogel with improved response rate and tensile mechanical properties," *European Polymer Journal*, vol. 42, no. 9, pp. 2125–2132, Sep. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2006.04.003>.
- [7] M. Sarkar, K. Dana, S. Ghatak, and A. Banerjee, "Polypropylene-clay composite prepared from Indian bentonite," *Bulletin of Materials Science*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 23–28, Feb. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12034-008-0005-5>.
- [8] A. Ghanbari, M.-C. Heuzey, P. J. Carreau, and M.-T. Ton-That, "Morphological and rheological properties of PET/clay nanocomposites," *Rheologica Acta*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 59–74, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00397-012-0667-1>.
- [9] G. Jatav, R. Mukhopadhyay, and N. De, "Characterization of Swelling Behaviour of Nanoclay Composite," *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 5, May 2013.
- [10] J. M. Carella, W. W. Graessley, and L. J. Fetters, "Effects of chain microstructure on the viscoelastic properties of linear polymer melts: polybutadienes and hydrogenated polybutadienes," *Macromolecules*, vol. 17, no. 12, pp. 2775–2786, Dec. 1984, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ma00142a059>.
- [11] L. J. Fetters, D. J. Lohse, D. Richter, T. A. Witten, and A. Zirkel, "Connection between Polymer Molecular Weight, Density, Chain Dimensions, and Melt Viscoelastic Properties," *Macromolecules*, vol. 27, no. 17, pp. 4639–4647, Aug. 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ma00095a001>.
- [12] G. H. Fredrickson, "The theory of polymer dynamics," *Current Opinion in Solid State and Materials Science*, vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 812–816, Dec. 1996, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-0286\(96\)80106-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-0286(96)80106-9).
- [13] A. Eckstein *et al.*, "Determination of Plateau Moduli and Entanglement Molecular Weights of Isotactic, Syndiotactic, and Atactic Polypropylenes Synthesized with Metallocene Catalysts," *Macromolecules*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 1335–1340, Jan. 1998, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ma971270d>.
- [14] S. Bagheri-Kazemabad *et al.*, "Morphology, rheology and mechanical properties of polypropylene/ethylene-octene copolymer/clay nanocomposites: Effects of the compatibilizer," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 72, no. 14, pp. 1697–1704, Sep. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2012.06.007>.
- [15] C. Liu, J. He, E. van Ruymbeke, R. Keunings, and C. Bailly, "Evaluation of different methods for the determination of the plateau modulus and the entanglement molecular weight," *Polymer*, vol. 47, no. 13, pp. 4461–4479, Jun. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2006.04.054>.
- [16] J. D. Ferry, *Viscoelastic Properties of Polymers, 3rd Edition*, 3rd ed. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 1980.
- [17] N. Ahmad and E. Fouad, "Influence of Clay Contents on Rheology of Syndiotactic Polypropylene/Clay Composites," *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 1537–1543, 2017.
- [18] N. Ahmad, R. Di Girolamo, F. Auriemma, C. De Rosa, and N. Grizzuti, "Relations between Stereoregularity and Melt Viscoelasticity of Syndiotactic Polypropylene," *Macromolecules*, vol. 46, no. 19, pp. 7940–7946, Oct. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ma401469a>.
- [19] N. M. Sofian, M. Rusu, R. Neagu, and E. Neagu, "Metal Powder-Filled Polyethylene Composites. V. Thermal Properties," *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 20–33, Jan. 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1106/9N6K-VKH1-MHYX-FBC4>.
- [20] S. Hwang, E. I. Reyes, K. Moon, R. C. Rumpf, and N. S. Kim, "Thermo-mechanical Characterization of Metal/Polymer Composite Filaments and Printing Parameter Study for Fused Deposition Modeling in the 3D Printing Process," *Journal of Electronic Materials*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 771–777, Mar. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11664-014-3425-6>.
- [21] T. A. Len, L. L. Vovchenko, O. V. Turkov, O. V. Lozitsky, and L. Y. Matzui, "Electrical and thermal properties of epoxy composites filled with carbon nanotubes and inorganic particles," *Molecular Crystals and Liquid Crystals*, vol. 717, no. 1, pp. 109–120, Mar. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15421406.2020.1860536>.

Modeling and Simulation of a UV Water Treatment System Fed by a GPV Source Using the Bond Graph Approach

Riahi Said

UR-LAPER, Faculty of Sciences of Tunis
University of Tunis El Manar
Tunis, Tunisia
riahi.said@fst.utm.tn

Naoufel Zitouni

UR-LAPER, Faculty of Sciences of Tunis
University of Tunis El Manar
Tunis, Tunisia
naoufel_zitouni@yahoo.fr

Viorel Minzu

Control and Electrical Engineering Department
Dunarea de Jos University
Galati, Romania
Viorel.Minzu@ugal.ro

Abdelkader Mami

UR-LAPER, Faculty of Sciences of Tunis
University of Tunis El Manar
Tunis, Tunisia
abdelkader.mami@fst.utm

Received: 15 February 2022 | Revised: 4 March 2022 | Accepted: 5 March 2022

Abstract-This work presents a simulation model for a UV water treatment system, powered by a photovoltaic generator, which relates the current consumed by the lamp to the UV flux and water quality. The overall system also includes electronic converters, electronic ballast (RLC resonant circuit), a UV lamp (UV irradiation source), and a centrifugal pump. To optimize the power transfer from the PV generator to the ballast and the UV lamp, a Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) device is used. The overall water treatment system presents a complex model due to its hybrid components. The bond graph tool with a multidisciplinary vocation allows precisely, by its graphic nature, using a unified language, to explicitly display the nature of the power exchanges in the system and facilitate its control. This tool is a solution for non-linear systems that guarantees and facilitates their modeling without difficulties.

Keywords-bondgraph; UV water treatment system; complex model; photovoltaic generator; centrifugal pump; simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Several water resources may be untreated and therefore they can be factors of transmission of diseases. The reuse of wastewater after an adequate treatment by UV radiation, presents a very good solution to solve the problems related to water pollution and constitutes a potential water resource. The majority of the existing UV disinfection systems use low pressure mercury arc lamps as a source of UV radiation that generates short waves in the region of 253,7nm [1-3]. The discharge lamp is placed in a reactor and is surrounded by a quartz tube immersed in a chamber in which the fluid is circulated. It is powered by an energy source such as a photovoltaic generator via an electronic ballast composed of an inverter, a transformer and a resonant circuit (RLC) [4, 5]. A

centrifugal motor pump as shown in Figure 1 ensures the circulation of water between the two tanks. The physico-chemical parameters (pH, temperature, etc.), the applied UV dose, the exposure time, as well as the number and type of microorganisms, are factors that can influence the final water quality. Many studies have been developed to improve water treatment systems despite their complexity, especially of the UV lamp model [6-8].

The aim of this study was to build a simulation model for all the components of the complex UV water treatment system shown in Figure 2. The bond graph approach is a modeling tool that facilitates the links between the different physical domains (mechanical, hydraulic, electrical) that represent the overall system. A photovoltaic (PV) generator model is presented in the first section along with the MPPT control in order to adapt the PV source and the load with a simulation result.

Fig. 1. Structure of the overall UV water treatment system powered by a PV panel.

Corresponding author: Abdelkader Mami

Fig.2. Representation of the energy exchanges in the system with different physical fields.

II. MODELING OF THE PV SOURCE BY THE BOND GRAPH APPROACH

A. The PV Generator Model

In order to power UV water disinfection systems with solar energy in a simple and inexhaustible way, we need to use PV generators. PV panels are characterized by the non-linearity of their output which is influenced by environmental factors (temperature and irradiation). The PV model used has two resistors in series and in shunt as shown in the equivalent electrical diagram in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Equivalent electrical circuit of a single diode PV generator.

The simplified equation of the PV current is:

$$I_{pv} = I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{q \times (V + I \times R_s)}{n \times K \times N_s \times T}\right) - 1 \right] - I_{sh} \quad (1)$$

where I_{pv} is the the output current, I_0 the diode inverse saturation current, and R_s the series resistor. K is the Boltzmann's constant, q is the electronic charge, n is the ideal diode factor ($1 < n < 2$) for a unique junction, and T is the functioning temperature. The current through the shunt resistor is given by:

$$I_{sh} = (V_{pv} + I_{pv} \times R_s) / R_{sh} \quad (2)$$

The photocurrent generated by the cell depends on the ambient temperature (T) and the solar irradiation (G) and is represented by:

$$I_{ph} = I_{sc} + K_I \cdot (T - 298) \cdot G / 1000 \quad (3)$$

B. Bond Graph Model of the Photovoltaic Generator

A simplified model that does not take into account the losses was adopted. This model is called mono-diode coupled to a starting capacitor that is placed in parallel with the

photovoltaic generator. The added capacitance represents the capacitance of the PN junction and it depends on the voltage V_d .

Fig. 4. Electrical diagram of the PV generator with starting capacity.

The bond graph model for the equivalent circuit is presented in Figure 5. It contains an element of capacitance, and the element noted as R_D is the resistance of the diode. It contains the non-linear characteristic. This allowed us to replace the generator by a modulated flux source S_f which plays the role of the modulating signal representing the photovoltaic current I_{ph} . This model was simulated by the software 20-sim [6, 9-11].

Fig. 5. Bond graph of the PV model.

To simulate the characteristics of the photovoltaic panel $I=f(V)$ and $P=f(V)$ [18-19], we use the BG model shown in Figure 5. In this simulation, the receiver is an initially discharged capacitor. The simulation results are represented in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Simulation of the characteristic curves of the PV system.

III. CONVERTERS USED

Static converters are mainly made up of semiconductor components that work in switching mode (thyristors, power

transistors, etc.). In our UV system, the converters are placed as follows: a first chopper booster is inserted between the UV lamp and the PV generator, a second chopper devolver is inserted between the motor pump and the PV panel, and a single-phase inverter generates a square voltage.

A. Dynamic Boost Converter

As the name suggests, this type of static converter amplifies the output voltage relative to the input voltage. In electronic structure, a boost chopper generally has a switch controlled on opening and closing (transistor, IGBT) and a diode [14, 15].

Fig. 7. Boost converter: (a) equivalent model, (b) its bond graph model.

B. Dynamic Buck Converter

The static converter (DC/DC) used, is most frequently used as a devolving converter, its basic schematic is that of Figure 8. A buck converter converts a DC voltage into another DC voltage of lower value [11, 16-18].

Fig. 8. Buck converter: (a) equivalent model, (b) its bond graph model.

C. Single Inverter

The resonant circuit (electronic ballast) requires a square voltage, which is obtained with an inverter, which is a static converter that converts electrical energy from DC to AC. It allows obtaining an alternating voltage adjustable in frequency and in RMS value, thus using an appropriate control sequence.

Fig. 9. Equivalent electrical diagram of a single-phase inverter.

D. Bond Graph MPPT: Perturbation and Observation Algorithm

The Perturbation and Observation (P&O) method is a widely used approach in MPPT research, because it is a simple iterative method. It can track the Maximum Power Point (MPP) even during sudden changes in irradiance and temperature [2, 9, 11, 17, 20]. Using the P&O algorithm, a link graph MPPT model was developed (Figures 11-12).

Fig. 10. Bond graph model of a single inverter.

Fig. 11. Adaptation model of an MPPT converter with a PV panel by bond graph.

Fig. 12. Simulation of the P&O control algorithm for different illuminations.

IV. BOND GRAPH MODELING OF THE ELECTRONIC BALLAST AND THE UV LAMP

The electronic power supply (electronic ballast) of a UV lamp can be broken down into three parts: The DC/AC converter, which is described above, the transformer, and the resonant circuit.

A. The Resonant Circuit (Electronic Ballast)

A discharge lamp needs sufficient voltage to light up. This lamp uses an electronic ballast capable of creating a high frequency voltage and an increase in the voltage value on the UV lamp for a short time. This overvoltage is obtained by a resonant circuit (RLC). The voltage delivered by the DC/AC converter, feeds a transformer to a resonant system formed by a resistor Rr in series with an inductance Lr and two capacitors Cr1 and Cr2 (Figure 13) The receiver is a discharge lamp (UV) which is compared to an infinite impedance before start-up and to a low value impedance after start-up [4, 5]. The corresponding bong-raph model is shown in Figure 14.

Fig. 13. Equivalent electrical diagram of a UV lamp power supply.

Fig. 14. Bond-graph model of the irradiation system.

B. The UV lamp

The UV water treatment system consists of a high pressure lamp placed vertically in a quartz sheath to be thermally isolated from the water. This lamp is assembled in a closed reactor. The water circulates in thin layers in the vicinity of the lamp because the UV rays are rapidly absorbed by the water. The disinfection efficiency obtained varies between 90% and 99.99%, depending on the duration of exposure of the water to radiation and the characteristics of the water to be treated. Certain electrical circuits generated by electronic ballasts are required to start the discharge lamp, to regulate the lamp cycle, and to control the electrical current.

Fig. 15. Schema of the UV reactor.

There are several models based on the current-voltage characteristics of the high-frequency discharge when trying to find a function that describes the relationship between current, voltage, and power consumed by the lamp. The UV lamp has a complicated model, it is in conjunction with an electronic ballast as described in (1):

$$U_e(t) = R_{Ballast}i(t) + L_{Ballast} \frac{di(t)}{dt} + U_{Lamp}(t) \quad (1)$$

The universal lamp model is defined by:

$$U_{Lamp}(t) = \frac{I_{Lamp}(t)}{G(t)} \quad (2)$$

The literature describes the conductance of a discharge lamp by a first-order differential equation, named G-model [1, 21, 22], which is presented as follows:

$$\frac{dG}{dt} = a_2 i^2 - \sum b_n G^n \quad (3)$$

where the coefficients a_2 and b_n can be determined experimentally from the voltage-current characteristics or by physical evaluation. The physical evaluation is possible when n is equal to 2 or 3. In this case, the coefficients have a physical meaning:

$$\frac{dG}{dt} = a_2 i^2 - b_2 G^2(t) - b_1 G(t) \quad (4)$$

The determination of the parameters a_2 , b_1 , and b_2 is done using an identification approach. According to (4), we developed the bond graph model of the UV lamp. Figure 16 exhibits the established model of the UV lamp.

Fig. 16. Bond graph model of the UV lamp.

V. BOND-GRAPH MODELING OF THE HYDRAULIC SYSTEM

The hydraulic system is a very important part of the water treatment system. It consists of a direct current motor connected to a centrifugal pump.

A. Modeling of the DC motor

The water treatment system has a motor pump to draw contaminated water from the inlet tank as shown in Figure 17. The motor pump subsystem must be able to control the flow rate of the contaminated water, which will determine the UV exposure time. Equation (5) expresses the latter:

$$t_{exposure} = V / Q \quad (5)$$

The values V and Q are the volume of the reactor and the flow rate of water respectively. The variation of Q determines the possibility to control the exposure time and consequently the UV dose received by the water [6, 10, 11, 23].

The dynamics of the engine [5, 10], are described by:

$$U_a = R_a I_a + L_a \frac{dI_a}{dt} + K_b \omega \quad (6)$$

$$C_m = J_m \frac{dw}{dt} + Fw + C_r \quad (7)$$

The DC motor is modeled in bond-graph by inertial elements I:La and resistive elements R:ra, representing respectively the inductance and the resistance of the armature. A gyrator models the transfer of energy from the electrical part to the mechanical part K_b ($E_a = K_b w$). The mechanical losses are modeled in bond graph by an inductive element I:J and a resistive element R:f which indicate respectively the coefficients of inertia and viscous friction of the DC machine. The DC motor drives a centrifugal pump characterized by a rotor shaft Γ proportional to the square of speed w ($\Gamma = K_T w^2$). Figure 18 presents the bond graph model of a DC motor.

Fig. 17. Schematic representation of the location of a DC motor in the UV water treatment system.

Fig. 18. Bond graph model of a DC motor.

B. Modeling of the Centrifugal Pump

The water disinfection operation consists of water circulating through a UV reactor. Once the pump is running, the rotation of the impeller produces pressure and a speed that determines the flow of the fluid in the hydraulic system [5, 10, 14]. The theoretical head H_e developed by a centrifugal pump is given by:

$$H_e = \frac{w^2 r_2^2}{2g} \quad (8)$$

The pressure developed by the wheel is directly proportional to the angular velocity w . The shaft speed is proportional to the flow rate Q . The developed pressure and the transmitted torque have the following expressions:

$$P_e = \rho g H_e = \frac{\rho r_2^2 w^2}{2} \quad (9)$$

$$T_e = \frac{\rho r_2^2 w}{2} Q \quad (10)$$

The relationship between the pressure supplied by the pump and the rotation speed, can be modeled in bond-graph by a modulated gyrator element, MGY. The latter transforms the mechanical flow (speed) into hydraulic force (pressure). The pressure losses in the pump are due to the friction between the liquid threads and against the walls of the machine:

$$T_{fp} = f_{mp} w \quad (11)$$

This friction is modeled in bond-graph by a resistive element R:f_{mp} and the moment of inertia of the rotating parts of the pump has the following expression:

$$T_{ip} = J_{pt} \frac{dw}{dt} \quad (12)$$

This moment of inertia is modeled in bond-graph by an inertial element I:J_{pt}. The pressure losses in the hydraulic circuit are due to the friction of the flow lines against the walls of the machine. They are modeled by a resistive element R:f_{cd}. The height difference between the two tanks is modeled by a negative force source:

$$Se = -\delta g H_e \quad (13)$$

The associated bond graph model of the centrifugal pump is shown in Figure 20.

Fig. 19. Synoptic diagram of a centrifugal pump.

Fig. 20. Bond graph model of the centrifugal pump.

For a stationary regime (constant speed), the characteristic of the theoretical head of a pure centrifugal pump in vacuum (isolated from the hydraulic network) can be seen in Figure 21.

Fig. 21. $H_c(Q)$ simulation characteristic of a centrifugal pump.

VI. GLOBAL MODEL OF A WATER TREATMENT SYSTEM BY BOND GRAPH

After having modeled the different elements of the water treatment system and simulated the obtained models, we can deduce the global model (BG) by combining the different models obtained, which is presented in Figure 22.

Fig. 22. Global model of the global UV water treatment unit

VII. SIMULATION RESULTS

The UV water treatment system consists of a closed cylindrical stainless steel reactor with an annular cross-section, 70cm in length, 6cm in internal diameter and 2L of useful volume. It is equipped with a single low-pressure mercury discharge lamp with the following characteristics: power 70W, nominal current 0.65A, length 400mm, diameter 15mm, placed in the axis of the irradiation room and protected by a clean quartz sleeve. The lamp is powered by an electronic ballast consisting of a single-phase inverter with transistors producing 25-100kHz at its output and a resonant circuit to realize the ignition of the lamp. The disinfection system is also equipped with a motor pump for the suction of contaminated water, a pump to draw contaminated water from the inlet tank, a flow control valve to obtain different flow rates, and a filter to improve the transmittance of the contaminated water. The treated water in this system could be recycled through a recirculation circuit that could allow multiple passes through the irradiation chamber.

According to the global model simulation, we obtained the following results: Figure 23 shows the output voltage of the single-phase inverter, which converts DC voltage to AC voltage to power the ballast and UV lamp, as they require AC

voltage. The voltage and current curves of the UV lamp (discharge lamp) are shown in Figures 24 and 25 with the following values: the voltage is approximately 150V and the current 1.42A. The parameters of the UV lamp and the electronic ballast are: $a_2=93.33$, $b_2=582036.5$, $b_f=994.7$, $R=0.9\Omega$, $C=2.8\mu F$, $L=0.16mA$. Figure 26 describes the evolution of the conductivity G of the UV lamp.

Fig. 23. Simulation of the output voltage of the inverter.

Fig. 24. The voltage of the UV lamp.

Fig. 25. The current of the UV lamp.

Fig. 26. The conductivity of the UV lamp.

Due to the negative impedance of discharge lamps and the complexity of the analysis, it is difficult to obtain models for the discharge lamps due to their negative impedance and the

complexity of the physical phenomena that occur inside the discharge tube. Discharge lamps can be operated at different frequencies with electronic ballasts. These different operating conditions can affect the behavior of the lamp. Generally, the non-linear I - V characteristic of the discharge lamps changes with frequency. Figure 27 represents the evolution of the non-linear obtained I - V characteristic after these simulations.

Fig. 27. I - V characteristic curve of the UV lamp.

The simulation of the continuous motor pump was performed using the buck converter. The motor voltage U_a is 24V. Figure 28 shows the evolution of the induced current, the motor torque, the rotation speed and the water flow. One can see a normal evolution of the four parameters.

Fig. 28. Evolution of the motor pump's parameters.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes link graph models for each subsystem of a UV water treatment unit. The different elements were connected to produce a dynamic model, which was used as the basis for building the simulation model. Using the 20-Sim software, a general simulation model was proposed. The series of simulations performed proved that the models were realistic and produced useful data. The link graph approach facilitates the connections between the different components of the overall model given the complexity of this unit. Future work could use this global model to determine the optimal parameters for all subsystems under given circumstances. The performance index could be the quality of water disinfection.

REFERENCES

[1] M. Tlili, "Conductivity Polynomial Model Parameters identification based on Particle Swarm Optimization," *Journal of Control Engineering and Applied Informatics*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 58–65, Dec. 2013.

[2] B. Mounaouer and H. Abdennaceur, "Disinfection of Water by UV Irradiation-Modeling and Improvement," *Current Biotechnology*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 199–206, 2012, <http://doi.org/10.2174/2211550111201030199>.

[3] A. A. Paidalwar and I. P. Khedkar, "Overview of Water Disinfection by UV Technology -A Review," *International Journal of Science Technology & Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 9, pp. 213–219, Mar. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30976.25608>.

[4] M. Ben Said, M. Ben Mustapha, and A. Hassen, "The impact of power supply frequency of a low pressure UV lamp on bacterial viability and activities," *Desalination and Water Treatment*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 1075–1081, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19443994.2013.860627>.

[5] N. Zitouni, R. Andoulsi, A. Sellami, A. Mami, and A. Hassen, "A new Bond Graph Model of a Water Disinfection System Based on UV Lamp Feed by Photovoltaic Source: Simulation and Experimental Results," *Journal of Automation & Systems Engineering*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 79–95, 2011.

[6] V. Minzu, S. Riahi, and E. Rusu, "Optimal Control of an Ultraviolet Water Disinfection System," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 6, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 2638, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11062638>.

[7] S. Sharma and A. Bhattacharya, "Drinking water contamination and treatment techniques," *Applied Water Science*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1043–1067, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-016-0455-7>.

[8] M. C. Collivignarelli, A. Abbà, I. Benigna, S. Sorlini, and V. Torretta, "Overview of the Main Disinfection Processes for Wastewater and Drinking Water Treatment Plants," *Sustainability*, vol. 10, no. 1, Jan. 2018, Art. no. 86, <https://doi.org/10.3390/sul0010086>.

[9] N. Zitouni, B. Khiari, R. Andoulsi, A. Sellami, A. Mami, and A. Hassen, "Modelling and non linear control of a photovoltaic system with storage batteries: A bond graph approach," *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 105–114, Jun. 2011.

[10] M. Turki, J. Belhadj, and X. Roboam, "Bond Graph modelling and analysis of an autonomous Reverse Osmosis desalination process fed by a hybrid system (photovoltaic-wind)," presented at the Electrimacs 2008, the 9th International Conference on Modeling and Simulation of Electric Machines, Converters and Systems, Quebec, Canada, Jan. 2008.

[11] R. Andoulsi, A. Mami, G. Dauphin-Tanguy, and M. Annabi, "Modelling and simulation by bond graph technique of a DC motor fed from a photovoltaic source via MPPT boost converter," in *Conference of Particle Accelerator (CSSC'99)*, New York, NY, USA, 1987, pp. 4181–4187.

[12] X. H. Nguyen and M. P. Nguyen, "Mathematical modeling of photovoltaic cell/module/arrays with tags in Matlab/Simulink," *Environmental Systems Research*, vol. 4, no. 1, Dec. 2015, Art. no. 24, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40068-015-0047-9>.

[13] J. Hahm, J. Baek, H. Kang, H. Lee, and M. Park, "Matlab-Based Modeling and Simulations to Study the Performance of Different MPPT Techniques Used for Photovoltaic Systems under Partially Shaded Conditions," *International Journal of Photoenergy*, vol. 2015, Jan. 2015, Art. no. e979267, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/979267>.

[14] N. E. Benchouia, H. A. Elias, L. Khochemane, and B. Mahmah, "Bond graph modeling approach development for fuel cell PEMFC systems," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 39, no. 27, pp. 15224–15231, Sep. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2014.05.034>.

[15] Z. R. Labidi, H. Schulte, and A. Mami, "A Systematic Controller Design for a Photovoltaic Generator with Boost Converter Using Integral State Feedback Control," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 4030–4036, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2687>.

[16] Z. R. Labidi, H. Schulte, and A. Mami, "A Model-Based Approach of DC-DC Converters Dedicated to Controller Design Applications for Photovoltaic Generators," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4371–4376, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2829>.

[17] M. Y. Allani, D. Mezghani, F. Tadeo, and A. Mami, "FPGA Implementation of a Robust MPPT of a Photovoltaic System Using a Fuzzy Logic Controller Based on Incremental and Conductance Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4322–4328, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2771>.

- [18] D. Mezghanni, R. Andoulsi, A. Mami, and G. Dauphin-Tanguy, "Bond graph modelling of a photovoltaic system feeding an induction motor-pump," *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory*, vol. 15, no. 10, pp. 1224–1238, Nov. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpat.2007.08.003>.
- [19] Z. Massaq, G. Chbirik, A. Abounada, A. Brahmi, and M. Ramzi, "Control of Photovoltaic Water Pumping System Employing Non-Linear Predictive Control and Fuzzy Logic Control," *International Review on Modelling and Simulations (IREMOS)*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 373–382, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.15866/iremos.v13i6.18615>.
- [20] S. D. Al-Majidi, M. F. Abbod, and H. S. Al-Raweshidy, "A novel maximum power point tracking technique based on fuzzy logic for photovoltaic systems," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 43, no. 31, pp. 14158–14171, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2018.06.002>.
- [21] M. H. Sellami, A. Hassen, and M. S. Sifaoui, "Modelling of UV radiation field inside a photoreactor designed for wastewater disinfection Experimental validation," *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, vol. 78, no. 3, pp. 269–287, May 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4073\(02\)00216-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4073(02)00216-9).
- [22] P. R. Herrick, "Mathematical Models for High-Intensity Discharge Lamps," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. IA-16, no. 5, pp. 648–654, Sep. 1980, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIA.1980.4503847>.
- [23] K. Ouelhazi, A. Ben Chaabene, A. Sellami, and A. Hassen, "Multivariable model of an ultraviolet water disinfection system," *Desalination and Water Treatment*, vol. 67, pp. 89–96, 2017.

An Improved Auto Categorical PSO with ML for Heart Disease Prediction

Animesh Kumar Dubey

Department of Computer Science and Engineering
JK LakshmiPat University
Jaipur, India
animeshdubey@jklu.edu.in

Amit Kumar Sinhal

Department of Computer Science and Engineering
JK LakshmiPat University
Jaipur, India
amit.sinhal@jklu.edu.in

Richa Sharma

Department of Science and Liberal Arts
JK LakshmiPat University
Jaipur, India
richasharma@jklu.edu.in

Received: 17 February 2022 | Revised: 4 March 2022 | Accepted: 27 March 2022

Abstract—Cardiovascular or heart diseases consist a global major health concern. Cardiovascular diseases have the highest mortality rate worldwide, and the death rate increases with age, but an accurate prognosis at an early stage may increase the chances of surviving. In this paper, a combined approach, based on Machine Learning (ML) with an optimization method for the prediction of heart diseases is proposed. For this, the Improved Auto Categorical Particle Swarm Optimization (IACPSO) method was utilized to pick an optimum set of features, while ML methods were used for data categorization. Three heart disease datasets were taken from the UCI ML library for testing: Cleveland, Statlog, and Hungarian. The proposed model was assessed for different performance parameters. The results indicated that, with 98% accuracy, Logistic Regression (LR) and Support Vector Machine by Grid Search (SVMGS) performed better for the Statlog, SVMGS outperformed on the Cleveland, while the LR, Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and SVMGS performed better with 97% accuracy on the Hungarian dataset. The outcomes were improved by 3 to 33% in terms of performance parameters when ML was applied with IACPSO.

Keywords—SVMGS; IACPSO; KNN; LR

I. INTRODUCTION

Globally, many people suffer from heart diseases [1]. In 1990, there were 24 million fatalities related to heart disease in the United States, by 2010 that number had risen to 38 million, a 59% increase [2]. According to current forecasts, India will have the world's highest prevalence of cardiovascular diseases and will soon overtake the rest of the world [3]. Heart disorders are responsible for almost 4 million fatalities in Europe and 1.9 million deaths in the EU [4]. In Africa, heart diseases are the leading cause of death among persons over the age of 35 [5]. Massive quantities of data on heart illnesses are collected from hospitals all around the world, which can be used manually to

quantify disease rates. However, the data so far have not been efficiently translated to correlate with disease risk and symptoms [6]. Cardiovascular disorder is accompanied by common symptoms of chest tightness, loss of body strength, and swollen legs [7]. Health history examination, clinical test reports, and associated symptoms are usually used by the doctors for diagnosis. But the obtained results by this method are not always accurate, whereas they are costly and difficult to computationally analyze [8]. Researchers have tried to come up with an efficient technique to detect heart diseases since the current diagnostic approaches for heart disease are not very effective in identifying the early stages [9]. It has been reported from different methodological approaches that a combination of ML and optimization methods may be effective in predicting early-stages of heart diseases [10]. Appropriate data are needed for training and testing in ML predictive models. We can increase the performance of ML algorithms by optimal dataset balancing for training and testing [11].

Feature selection is capable of reducing dimensionality, increasing efficiency, and enhancing classification accuracy [12-14]. The data comprising several dimensions may create trouble in feature selection. According to [15-18], classification and clustering methods of ML were proven to be more effective in terms of accuracy rates. Several feature selection evaluation metrics were investigated in [19], to improve the computational efficiency of ML algorithms as well as to discuss the unexpected problems of feature selection. Various data mining and combinations of data mining with optimization algorithms have been proposed as a means of detecting heart diseases. Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) was applied to select an effective subset from a large training set with improved accuracy in [20]. In [21], a combination of optimization and data mining was proposed, based on Glowworm Swarm Optimization (GSO) with k-means to improve the accuracy of image classification. For omics data

Corresponding author: Animesh Kumar Dubey

classification, a Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)-based model was developed in [22] and claimed good accuracy. In [23], a hybrid structure, based on PSO and grid search was proposed to predict heart diseases with 95.95% accuracy. Authors in [24], suggested a combined approach of PSO with Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The highest accuracy, 98%, was achieved by PSO with CNN. In [25], the performance of swarm optimization algorithms Artificial Bee Colony (ABC), PSO, and ACO to an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) was studied, and PSO was determined to be the most effective. A Hybrid Genetic Algorithm (HGA) with k-means was implemented in [26] for classifying and predicting heart diseases with 94.06% accuracy. In [27], ANNs with PCA and PSO were used to predict cardiac diseases, with an accuracy of 98%. In [28], PSO algorithm was proposed for dimension reduction, and several classification methods were used to diagnose heart diseases. Utilizing the dataset from the UCI library, Naïve Bayes (NB), Decision Tree (DT), and k-Nearest Neighbour (KNN) models were applied in [29] to predict heart diseases. In [30], PSO with feedforward backpropagation ANN were implemented to diagnose heart diseases, and achieved 91.94% accuracy. NB with a Genetic Algorithm (GA) were used to eliminate unnecessary information in [31] achieving high accuracy. To deal with the issues related to overfitting and underfitting, as well as selecting attributes, a deep ANN was implemented in [32], and the achieved precision was 93.33%. Similarly, Random Search Algorithm (RSA) for feature selection and Random Forest (RF) for classification were used in [33]. Several DT-based methods along with PSO were used in [34], to identify heart disease occurrence and the highest precision was obtained using a bagged tree with PSO. SVM with a multiclass approach of ML was applied in [35], to detect apple fruit diseases. In [36], crow search with deep learning method were used for the prediction of Parkinson's disease with 96% accuracy. For the detection of various plant diseases, ML algorithms were used in [37]. Various unsupervised learning and optimization methods were used in [38-40] for the prediction of heart diseases.

Most researchers used supervised and unsupervised ML methods and swarm intelligence-based optimization methods such as ACO, GSO, PSO, etc., in conjunction with ML. But their approaches were not stable in handling real-time situations. Hence, there is a need for an automated approach, which can generate the optimal solution based on the current situation. The present research work proposes a combined approach, including ML algorithms with optimization to predict heart diseases. ML methods, such as Logistic Regression (LR), DT, SVM, SVM by Grid Search (SVMGS), RF, KNN, and NB, are used, and the Improved Auto Categorical PSO (IACPSO) method is applied for selecting an optimized set of features. The major objectives of this research are:

- For PSO, to create an automated approach to the selection of the optimal value of control parameters at each iteration.
- To analyze the impact of ML algorithms on different performance parameters in the prediction of cardiovascular diseases.

- To evaluate the combined impact of ML algorithms with optimization for heart disease prediction.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Three heart disease datasets were taken from the UCI ML library for testing: Cleveland, Statlog, and Hungarian [41]. The datasets consist of a total of 76 attributes, but only 14 relevant attributes including the attributes preferred in most published experiments [42]. Predicted trait values were represented by A and P indicating the absence and presence of heart disease respectively. ML algorithms such as LR [43, 44], DT [45, 46], RF [47], KNN [48], SVM [49, 50], and NB [45, 48], were used for prediction and analysis. IACPSO was used to select an optimal set of features.

A. IACPSO

PSO is a search-based stochastic optimization technique based on population. The particles, which are potential solutions in PSO, follow the current optimum particles through the problem space [51]. The performance of PSO depends on three control parameters which are the inertial weight (w), the acceleration coefficients (C_1 and C_2), and random numbers (R_1 and R_2) [52]. The inertial weight is used for maintaining the effect of convergence and diversity. A large value of w indicates better global exploration, while a small value works on exploitation. Unbalanced values containing the parameters can hurt the results, such that if we take low values for C_1 , it tends to acquire a smooth particle trajectory and abrupt movements. Similarly, if C_1 is much greater than C_2 , it tends to excessive wander and cause premature convergence [53]. Large inertial weight tends to global search ability and small inertial weight leads to increase in local search power. By dynamic changing w , the acceleration coefficients, efficiently explore the search space [52]. Therefore, in the proposed IACPSO, the control parameters are updated automatically based on the number of particles as well as balancing them at each iteration. The Steps included in IACPSO are given below:

Step I: Initialize the Particle size ($P_0, P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n$) in the D-dimensional space.

Step II: Initialize the velocity $V_x^d(0)$, where $x \in \{P_0, P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n\}$, $d \in \{0, 1, \dots, D\}$. Calculate the velocity of a particle at the m th iteration by using (1):

$$V_x^d(m) = wV_x^d(m-1) + \emptyset_1(L_x(m) - P_x^d(m-1)) + \emptyset_2(G(m) - P_x^d(m-1)) \quad (1)$$

where w is the inertial weight, $\emptyset_1 = R_1C_1$ (local accelerations), $\emptyset_2 = R_2C_2$ (global accelerations), C_1 and C_2 are the acceleration coefficient, and R_1 and R_2 are random numbers. P_x^d is the position of the particles, $L_x(m)$ and $G(m)$ are the local and global best positions. For each iteration, control parameter values have been chosen automatically on the basis of the number of swarm particles (n), which are given in (2-5). For the value of \emptyset_1 and \emptyset_2 , generate the $n/8$ random number between 0 to 2 for the selection of C_1 and C_2 .

$$C_1 = \{C_1^1, C_1^2, C_1^3, \dots, C_1^{\frac{P_n}{8}} \text{ where } 0 \leq C_1 \leq 2\} \quad (2)$$

$$C_2 = \{C_2^1, C_2^2, C_2^3, \dots, C_2^{\frac{P_n}{8}} \text{ where } 0 \leq C_2 \leq 2\} \quad (3)$$

$$\emptyset_1 = \sum_{n=1}^{\frac{P_n}{8}} C_1 \cdot R_1 \quad (4)$$

$$\emptyset_2 = \sum_{n=1}^{\frac{P_n}{8}} C_2 \cdot R_2 \quad (5)$$

Then, as per (6), divide the value of \emptyset_1 and \emptyset_2 into three categories: Low (L), Mid (M), and High (H).

$$\emptyset_1, \emptyset_2 = \begin{cases} L, & \text{if } (0 \leq C_1, C_2 \leq 0.8) \\ M, & \text{else if } (0.9 \leq C_1, C_2 \leq 1.2) \\ H, & \text{else } (1.3 \leq C_1, C_2 \leq 2) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Similarly, for the value of w , select three values between 0.4 and 0.9 and categorize those into L , M and H , in which L is close to 0.4, M is nearer to the mean of the other two values, and H is close to 0.9. For each iteration select the value of w as per the following conditions:

- (i) If $(\emptyset_1 \ \& \ \emptyset_2 \in L)$ then consider $w = H$ (value)
- (ii) If $(\emptyset_1 \ \& \ \emptyset_2 \in M)$ then consider $w = M$ (value)
- (iii) If $(\emptyset_1 \ \& \ \emptyset_2 \in H)$ then consider $w = L$ (value)

So, the updated velocity at each iteration is:

$$V_x^d(m) = w(L, W, H)V_x^d(m-1) + \sum_{n=1}^{\frac{P_n}{8}} C_1 \cdot R_1 (L_x(m) - P_x^d(m-1)) + \sum_{n=1}^{\frac{P_n}{8}} C_2 \cdot R_2 (G(m) - P_x^d(m-1)) \quad (7)$$

Step III: Calculate position of the particles, given in (8):

$$P_x^d(m) = P_x^d(m-1) + V_x^d(m) \quad (8)$$

By using (8), we get $n/8$ number of positions for each particle, then we proceed to step IV.

Step IV: Calculate the current fitness function $\forall(P)$. Based on the $n/8$ position of particles, calculate the fitness function, given in (9) and (10), and choose the best one based on Minimization or Maximization.

$$L_x(m) = P_x(m_L) : \forall(P_x(m_L)) = \frac{\min}{\max_{0 \leq k \leq m}} \forall(P_x(k)) \quad (9)$$

$$G(m) = L_{xb}(m) : \forall(L_{xb}(m)) = \min/\max_{0 \leq x \leq n} \forall(L_x(m)) \quad (10)$$

Step V: On the basis of the fitness value, update $L_x(m)$ and $G(m)$.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Figure 1 shows the flow chart of the suggested methodology. Cleveland, Statlog, and Hungarian datasets of heart diseases were considered for the evaluation of the proposed approach. Experiments were run using an x64-based processor with Windows 10 OS and an Intel (R) Core (TM) i5-7200 CPU @ 2.50GHz. The analysis and visual presentation were done using Python and Java7. The experimental results and analysis on heart diseases datasets, based on ML algorithms like LR, SVM, DT, SVMGS, RF, NB, and KNN and the IACPSO optimization method are reported.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the proposed methodology.

A. Result Analysis Based on ML Algorithms

We assessed the effectiveness of the ML models by using parameters such as accuracy (AC), precision (PR), Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), sensitivity (SV), and F-score (FS) [11]. Table I presents the AC, PR, SV, FS, and MCC values, where PR, SV, and FS were either A or P. Here, 25% of the data were used for testing and the rest for training. For KNN, the considered values of k were 11, 17, and 15 for Cleveland, Statlog, and Hungarian datasets respectively. According to the comparative analysis shown in Figure 2, SVMGS outperformed the other methods in all aspects and achieved accuracy of 89% for Cleveland and Hungarian datasets, while for Statlog dataset, NB and LR showed better accuracy of 91%.

Fig. 2. Comparative analysis of ML algorithms in terms of AC, average PR, and average SV.

B. Result Analysis Based on IACPSO with ML Methods

IACPSO was used for feature selection. The selection of features depend upon their ranks, their values are either 0 or 1, with 0 representing the rejection of a feature and 1 representing its selection. The number of features represents the solution size for each data set. For the optimization process, the selected features along with the performance of the classifier were taken into account. The fitness function was

$$\alpha C(E) + \beta (|SF|/|TF|) \quad (11)$$

where $C(E)$ is the misclassification rate, $|SF|$ shows the number of the selected features, $|TF|$ represents the total features in the data set, and α belongs to $[1, 0]$, $\beta = (1 - \alpha)$. The value of α and β were taken from [54, 55]. For experimentation, the parameters values are: population size=12, number of iterations=100, dimension=7, $w=0.4$ to 0.9 and $C1$ and $C2=0$ to 2 .

TABLE I. EVALUATION RESULTS BASED ON THE PERFORMANCE PARAMETERS OF THE ML METHODS

Classification methods		LR	DT	RF	SVM	SVMGS	KNN	NB	
Cleveland dataset	AC		0.87	0.82	0.87	0.87	0.89	0.76	0.87
	PR	A	0.86	0.76	0.89	0.86	0.89	0.77	0.84
		P	0.88	0.89	0.85	0.88	0.88	0.74	0.90
	SV	A	0.86	0.90	0.83	0.86	0.86	0.69	0.90
		P	0.88	0.75	0.91	0.88	0.91	0.81	0.84
	FS	A	0.86	0.83	0.86	0.86	0.88	0.73	0.87
		P	0.88	0.81	0.88	0.88	0.89	0.78	0.87
MCC		0.74	0.65	0.71	0.74	0.77	0.51	0.74	
Statlog dataset	AC		0.91	0.83	0.89	0.87	0.89	0.76	0.91
	PR	A	0.89	0.82	0.86	0.88	0.85	0.81	0.89
		P	0.94	0.88	0.94	0.85	1.00	0.68	0.94
	SV	A	0.97	0.94	0.97	0.91	1.00	0.79	0.97
		P	0.81	0.67	0.76	0.81	0.71	0.71	0.81
	FS	A	0.93	0.87	0.91	0.90	0.92	0.80	0.93
		P	0.87	0.76	0.84	0.83	0.83	0.70	0.87
MCC		0.81	0.65	0.61	0.73	0.78	0.50	0.81	
Hungarian dataset	AC		0.88	0.82	0.86	0.87	0.89	0.77	0.88
	PR	A	0.87	0.77	0.88	0.85	0.90	0.77	0.85
		P	0.88	0.88	0.85	0.89	0.87	0.75	0.91
	SV	A	0.87	0.89	0.82	0.85	0.86	0.70	0.91
		P	0.88	0.75	0.90	0.89	0.91	0.82	0.85
	FS	A	0.87	0.83	0.85	0.85	0.88	0.74	0.88
		P	0.88	0.81	0.88	0.89	0.89	0.78	0.87
MCC		0.77	0.65	0.69	0.74	0.77	0.53	0.76	

TABLE II. ACCURACY OBTAINED BASED ON ML METHODS WITH IACPSO

ML methods with IACPSO		LR+IAC PSO	DT+IA CPSO	RF+IA CPSO	SVM+IACP SO	SVMGS+IAC PSO	KNN+IACPS O	NB+IAC PSO	
Cleveland	AC		0.96	0.92	0.97	0.97	0.98	0.92	0.92
	PR	A	0.97	0.90	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.92	0.93
		P	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.96	0.95	0.91	0.92
	SV	A	0.97	0.96	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.90	0.94
		P	0.96	0.91	0.98	0.98	0.96	0.91	0.90
	FS	A	0.98	0.95	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.90	0.90
		P	0.95	0.90	0.95	0.95	0.96	0.94	0.91
MCC		0.89	0.83	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.84	0.83	
Statlog	AC		0.98	0.93	0.97	0.97	0.98	0.92	0.94
	PR	A	0.99	0.94	0.97	0.97	0.98	0.91	0.91
		P	0.98	0.97	0.98	0.98	1.00	0.93	0.98
	SV	A	0.99	0.98	0.98	0.98	1.00	0.92	0.98
		P	0.95	0.90	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.93	0.87
	FS	A	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.91	0.94
		P	0.99	0.94	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.88	0.90
MCC		0.95	0.83	0.89	0.89	0.90	0.81	0.85	
Hungarian	AC		0.97	0.93	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.91	0.92
	PR	A	0.96	0.91	0.96	0.96	0.98	0.90	0.91
		P	0.99	0.94	0.99	0.99	0.95	0.91	0.93
	SV	A	0.98	0.94	0.96	0.96	1.00	0.91	0.94
		P	0.97	0.92	0.99	0.99	0.94	0.90	0.90
	FS	A	0.99	0.93	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.89	0.91
		P	0.96	0.93	0.97	0.97	0.95	0.89	0.91
MCC		0.92	0.82	0.88	0.88	0.90	0.80	0.82	

The percentage of data based on misclassification rates (shown in Figure 3) were considered for the experiment. Based on the IACPSO, only 7 of the 14 features were chosen for testing, which were thalassemia, chest pain, number of major vessels, ST anxiety exercise-induced relative to rest, exercise-induced angina, maximal heart rate achieved, and exercise-induced angina. Table II presents the AC, PR, SV, FS, and MCC values, based on the combined performance of ML methods and IACPSO. With 98% accuracy, SVMGS

outperformed the other methods in the Cleveland dataset. SVMGS and LR with 98% accuracy outscored RF, DT, KNN, NB, and SVM on the Statlog dataset. LR, RF, SVM, and SVMGS with a 97% accuracy outperformed KNN, NB and DT on the Hungarian dataset. For Cleveland, with an optimal set of features, the highest MCC was achieved by SVMGS, SVM, and RF, while LR did better in terms of MCC in Statlog and Hungarian. Figure 4 compares the ML algorithms with IACPSO results based on AC, average PR, and SV. For the

Cleveland dataset, LR, RF, SVM, and SVMGS performed better in terms of average PR, RF and SVM in terms of average SV. LR and SVMGS achieved the highest average PR of 99%, whereas the highest average SV was achieved by RF, SVM, and SVMGS for the Statlog dataset. Regarding the Hungarian dataset, LR, RF, and SVM, with 98% of average PR and SV, performed better than DT, SVMGS, KNN, and NB. With 97%, LR, RF, SVM, and SVMGS outperformed in terms of AC.

Fig. 3. Comparison of the misclassification rates of ML algorithms.

IV. DISCUSSION

The performance of ML algorithms with and without optimization was examined in this paper. An optimization algorithm (IACPSO) was used for the selection of features to improve accuracy in less time, using the optimum value of the acceleration coefficients in each iteration. In addition, these values were also linked to the graded inertial load, to balance exploration and exploitation. Table III compares the results, based on ML techniques with and without optimization. Figure 5 shows the improvement rates of performance parameters when combined approach (ML algorithms + IACPSO) were used. Outcomes were improved by 3 to 33% in terms of performance parameters when ML was applied with IACPSO. As per Table III and Figure 5, the major findings were as follows:

- When LR was applied separately, the achieved AC was 87% (Cleveland), 91% (Statlog), and 88% (Hungarian) but in the combined methodology of LR with IACPSO, the AC

increased by 9% for Cleveland and Hungarian and 7% for Statlog.

- When the DT was applied separately, AC was 82% for Cleveland and Hungarian, and 83% for Statlog, but in the combined methodology of DT with the IACPSO, the AC increased by 10% for Cleveland and Statlog and 11% for Hungarian.
- In the case of RF with IACPSO, AC was 10%, 8%, and 11% higher for Cleveland, Statlog, and Hungarian than for separately applied RF.
- For SVM, the obtained AC with the IACPSO in Cleveland, Statlog and Hungarian was 97%, which was 10% higher than when using only SVM. There was an increase in AC of 1% in Cleveland and Statlog when IACPSO was used with SVMGS.
- For KNN with IACPSO, an increase of 16% in AC occurred for Cleveland and Statlog. A large difference was found in the improvement percentage in the value of MCC, being 33% in Cleveland, 31% in Statlog, and 27% in Hungarian.
- For NB, improvement after IACPSO was 3 to 5% in terms of AC, PR, SV, and FS.

For all the aspects of performance used in the current research, ML methods with IACPSO were proven to be superior. ML algorithms were used for the classification and IACPSO method was applied for the selection of effective features. This type of combined approach gave better models for the early prediction of cardiovascular diseases.

Fig. 4. Comparison of ML methods with IACPSO in terms of AC, average PR, and average SV.

TABLE III. RESULT COMPARISON OF ML METHODS WITH AND WITHOUT IACPSO

Datasets	Cleveland					Statlog					Hungarian				
	AC	PR	SV	FS	MCC	AC	PR	SV	FS	MCC	AC	PR	SV	FS	MCC
LR	87	87	87	87	74	91	92	89	90	81	88	88	88	88	77
LR+IACPSO	96	97	97	97	89	98	99	97	99	95	97	98	98	98	92
DT	82	83	83	82	65	83	85	81	82	65	82	83	82	82	65
DT+IACPSO	92	93	94	93	83	93	96	94	96	83	93	93	94	93	92
RF	87	87	87	87	71	89	90	87	88	61	86	87	86	87	69
RF+IACPSO	97	97	98	97	90	97	98	98	98	89	97	98	98	98	88
SVM	87	87	87	87	74	87	87	86	87	73	87	87	87	87	74
SVM+IACPSO	97	97	98	97	90	97	98	98	98	89	97	98	98	98	88
SVMGS	89	89	89	89	77	89	93	86	88	78	89	89	89	89	77
SVMGS+IACPSO	98	97	96	97	90	98	99	98	97	90	97	97	97	97	90
KNN	76	76	75	76	51	76	73	75	75	50	77	76	76	76	53
KNN+IACPSO	92	92	91	92	84	92	92	93	90	81	91	91	91	89	80
NB	87	87	87	87	74	91	92	89	90	81	88	88	88	88	76
NB+IACPSO	92	93	92	91	83	94	95	94	92	85	92	92	92	91	82

Fig. 5. Improved performance rates of ML algorithms due to IACPSO.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a combined approach, based on ML algorithms and optimization is proposed to predict heart diseases at an early stage using the history of the patients. ML algorithms, such as DT, LR, SVM, SVMGS, NB, KNN, and RF were used and IACPSO was used for optimization. In IACPSO, the optimum value of control parameters was used, which helped in proper exploration and exploitation. In each iteration, $P_n/8$ number of solutions was generated in terms of local and global best, according to the objective function. The best solution was used for the next iteration. The proposed approach was investigated on Cleveland, Statlog, and Hungarian datasets and the evaluation was performed based on AC, PR, SV, FS, and MCC. The ML algorithms were compared and assessed with and without optimization, and it was found that the former were superior in all parameters. The proposed ML approach with an optimized set of features helped in predicting cardiovascular diseases and yielded better predictive results. In the future, this work can be repeated with more parameters, with real or primary datasets and various other threshold mechanisms towards the use of attributes in detecting different diseases.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. L. Bui, T. B. Horwich, and G. C. Fonarow, "Epidemiology and risk profile of heart failure," *Nature Reviews Cardiology*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 30–41, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrcardio.2010.165>.
- [2] D. Prabhakaran, P. Jeemon, and A. Roy, "Cardiovascular Diseases in India," *Circulation*, vol. 133, no. 16, pp. 1605–1620, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.114.008729>.
- [3] "Alarming Statistics from India - Neo CarDiabCare Heartlicare..." <http://neocardiacare.com/alarming-statistics-india.htm> (accessed Mar. 31, 2022).
- [4] E. Wilkins *et al.*, *European Cardiovascular Disease Statistics*. Brussels, Belgium: European Heart Network, 2017.
- [5] H. Ouyang, "Africa's Top Health Challenge: Cardiovascular Disease," *The Atlantic*, Oct. 30, 2014.
- [6] H. Kahramanli and N. Allahverdi, "Mining Classification Rules for Liver Disorders," *International Journal of Mathematics and Computers in Simulation*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 9–19, 2009.
- [7] M. Durairaj and N. Ramasamy, "A comparison of the perceptive approaches for preprocessing the data set for predicting fertility success rate," *International Journal of Control Theory and Applications*, vol. 9, no. 27, pp. 255–260, Jan. 2016.
- [8] A. Tsanas, M. A. Little, P. E. McSharry, and L. O. Ramig, "Nonlinear speech analysis algorithms mapped to a standard metric achieve clinically useful quantification of average Parkinson's disease symptom severity," *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, vol. 8, no. 59, pp. 842–855, Jun. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2010.0456>.
- [9] L. A. Allen *et al.*, "Decision Making in Advanced Heart Failure," *Circulation*, vol. 125, no. 15, pp. 1928–1952, Apr. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIR.0b013e31824f2173>.
- [10] A. K. Dubey and K. Choudhary, "A systematic review and analysis of the heart disease prediction methodology," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Research*, vol. 8, no. 38, pp. 240–256, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.19101/IJACR.2018.837025>.
- [11] A. K. Dubey, K. Choudhary, and R. Sharma, "Predicting Heart Disease Based on Influential Features with Machine Learning," *Intelligent Automation & Soft Computing*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 229–243, 2021, <https://www.techscience.com/iase/v30n3/44095>.
- [12] J. Chen, H. Huang, S. Tian, and Y. Qu, "Feature selection for text classification with Naïve Bayes," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 36, no. 3, Part 1, pp. 5432–5435, Apr. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2008.06.054>.
- [13] Y. Li, T. Li, and H. Liu, "Recent advances in feature selection and its applications," *Knowledge and Information Systems*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 551–577, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10115-017-1059-8>.
- [14] J. Li and H. Liu, "Challenges of Feature Selection for Big Data Analytics," *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 9–15, Nov. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MIS.2017.38>.
- [15] S. Bharti and S. N. Singh, "Analytical study of heart disease prediction comparing with different algorithms," in *International Conference on Computing, Communication & Automation*, Greater Noida, India, Dec. 2015, pp. 78–82, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCA.2015.7148347>.
- [16] S. Tahzeeb and S. Hasan, "A Neural Network-Based Multi-Label Classifier for Protein Function Prediction," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 7974–7981, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4597>.
- [17] K. Aldriwish, "A Deep Learning Approach for Malware and Software Piracy Threat Detection," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7757–7762, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4412>.
- [18] H. Alalawi, M. Alsuwat, and H. Alhakami, "A Survey of the Application of Artificial Intelligence on COVID-19 Diagnosis and Prediction," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7824–7835, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4503>.
- [19] J. Cai, J. Luo, S. Wang, and S. Yang, "Feature selection in machine learning: A new perspective," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 300, pp. 70–79, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2017.11.077>.
- [20] S. Sharma and K. M. Buddhiraju, "A Novel Ant Colony Optimization Based Training Subset Selection Algorithm for Hyperspectral Image Classification," in *International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, Valencia, Spain, Jul. 2018, pp. 5748–5751, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS.2018.8519217>.
- [21] J. Senthilnath, S. N. Omkar, V. Mani, N. Tejovanth, P. G. Diwakar, and A. Shenoy B., "Multi-spectral satellite image classification using Glowworm Swarm Optimization," in *International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, Jul. 2011, pp. 47–50, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS.2011.6048894>.
- [22] Z. Xu and J. Yang, "Model selection based on particle swarm optimization for omics data classification," in *5th International Conference on Mechanical, Control and Computer Engineering*, Harbin, China, Dec. 2020, pp. 1338–1341, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMCE51767.2020.00293>.
- [23] L. Demidova and I. Klyueva, "Data classification based on the hybrid versions of the particle swarm optimization algorithm," in *7th Mediterranean Conference on Embedded Computing*, Budva,

- Montenegro, Jun. 2018, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MECO.2018.8406069>.
- [24] Z. Lu, "Enhanced Accuracy Enabled by Particle Swarm Optimization in Classification Application," in *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Computer Engineering*, Beijing, China, Oct. 2020, pp. 146–149, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAICE51518.2020.00034>.
- [25] P. Bhavani Shankar and Y. Divya Vani, "Conceptual Glimpse of Genetic Algorithms in the Detection of Heart Diseases," in *International Conference on Advances in Electrical, Computing, Communication and Sustainable Technologies*, Bhubaneswar, India, Feb. 2021, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAECT49130.2021.9392604>.
- [26] Md. T. Islam, S. R. Rafa, and Md. G. Kibria, "Early Prediction of Heart Disease Using PCA and Hybrid Genetic Algorithm with k-Means," in *23rd International Conference on Computer and Information Technology*, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Dec. 2020, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCIIT51783.2020.9392655>.
- [27] A. T. Saputra, B. Prindo Sugiharto Putro, W. A. Saputra, and M. Muljono, "Optimization Neural Network With PCA And PSO On Heart Disease Classification," in *International Seminar on Application for Technology of Information and Communication*, Semarang, Indonesia, Sep. 2020, pp. 191–195, <https://doi.org/10.1109/iSemantic50169.2020.9234276>.
- [28] S. K. Prabhakar, H. Rajaguru, and S.-W. Lee, "Metaheuristic-Based Dimensionality Reduction and Classification Analysis of PPG Signals for Interpreting Cardiovascular Disease," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 165181–165206, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2950220>.
- [29] S. Hendra Wijaya, G. Timur Pamungkas, M. Burhanis Sulthan, and Muljono, "Improving Classifier Performance Using Particle Swarm Optimization on Heart Disease Detection," in *International Seminar on Application for Technology of Information and Communication*, Semarang, Indonesia, Sep. 2018, pp. 603–608, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISEMANTIC.2018.8549722>.
- [30] M. G. Feshki and O. S. Shijani, "Improving the heart disease diagnosis by evolutionary algorithm of PSO and Feed Forward Neural Network," in *Artificial Intelligence and Robotics*, Qazvin, Iran, Apr. 2016, pp. 48–53, <https://doi.org/10.1109/RIOS.2016.7529489>.
- [31] M. A. Jabbar, B. L. Deekshatulu, and P. Chandra, "Computational intelligence technique for early diagnosis of heart disease," in *International Conference on Engineering and Technology*, Coimbatore, India, Mar. 2015, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICETECH.2015.7275001>.
- [32] L. Ali, A. Rahman, A. Khan, M. Zhou, A. Javeed, and J. A. Khan, "An Automated Diagnostic System for Heart Disease Prediction Based on χ^2 Statistical Model and Optimally Configured Deep Neural Network," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 34938–34945, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2904800>.
- [33] A. Javeed, S. Zhou, L. Yongjian, I. Qasim, A. Noor, and R. Nour, "An Intelligent Learning System Based on Random Search Algorithm and Optimized Random Forest Model for Improved Heart Disease Detection," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 180235–180243, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2952107>.
- [34] I. Yekkala, S. Dixit, and M. A. Jabbar, "Prediction of heart disease using ensemble learning and Particle Swarm Optimization," in *International Conference On Smart Technologies For Smart Nation*, Bengaluru, India, Aug. 2017, pp. 691–698, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SmartTechCon.2017.8358460>.
- [35] S. Chakraborty, S. Paul, and Md. Rahat-uz-Zaman, "Prediction of Apple Leaf Diseases Using Multiclass Support Vector Machine," in *2nd International Conference on Robotics, Electrical and Signal Processing Techniques*, DHAKA, Bangladesh, Jan. 2021, pp. 147–151, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICREST51555.2021.9331132>.
- [36] M. Masud et al., "CROWD: Crow Search and Deep Learning based Feature Extractor for Classification of Parkinson's Disease," *ACM Transactions on Internet Technology*, vol. 21, no. 3, Mar. 2021, Art. no. 77, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3418500>.
- [37] M. Kumar, A. Kumar, and V. S. Palaparthi, "Soil Sensors-Based Prediction System for Plant Diseases Using Exploratory Data Analysis and Machine Learning," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 21, no. 16, pp. 17455–17468, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2020.3046295>.
- [38] A. Dubey, U. Gupta, and S. Jain, "Medical Data Clustering and Classification Using TLBO and Machine Learning Algorithms," *Computers, Materials and Continua*, vol. 70, no. 3, pp. 4523–4543, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.32604/cmc.2022.021148>.
- [39] A. K. Dubey, U. Gupta, and S. Jain, "Computational Measure of Cancer Using Data Mining and Optimization," in *International Conference on Sustainable Communication Networks and Application*, Erode, India, Jul. 2019, pp. 626–632, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-34515-0_65.
- [40] J. V. Rosy and S. B. R. Kumar, "Optimized encryption based elliptical curve Diffie-Hellman approach for secure heart disease prediction," *International Journal of Advanced Technology and Engineering Exploration*, vol. 8, no. 83, pp. 1367–1382, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.19101/IJATEE.2021.874436>.
- [41] "UCI Machine Learning Repository." <http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/index.php> (accessed Mar. 31, 2022).
- [42] J. Nahar, T. Imam, K. S. Tickle, and Y.-P. P. Chen, "Association rule mining to detect factors which contribute to heart disease in males and females," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 1086–1093, Mar. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2012.08.028>.
- [43] S. Sperandei, "Understanding logistic regression analysis," *Biochemia Medica*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 12–18, Feb. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.11613/BM.2014.003>.
- [44] J. C. Stoltzfus, "Logistic Regression: A Brief Primer," *Academic Emergency Medicine*, vol. 18, no. 10, pp. 1099–1104, 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1553-2712.2011.01185.x>.
- [45] X. Wu et al., "Top 10 algorithms in data mining," *Knowledge and Information Systems*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 1–37, Jan. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10115-007-0114-2>.
- [46] P. C. Austin, J. V. Tu, J. E. Ho, D. Levy, and D. S. Lee, "Using methods from the data-mining and machine-learning literature for disease classification and prediction: a case study examining classification of heart failure subtypes," *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, vol. 66, no. 4, pp. 398–407, Apr. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2012.11.008>.
- [47] L. Yang, *Distance Metric Learning: A Comprehensive Survey*. Michigan, MI, USA: Michigan State University, 2006.
- [48] C. M. Bishop, *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2006.
- [49] S.-W. Lin, K.-C. Ying, S.-C. Chen, and Z.-J. Lee, "Particle swarm optimization for parameter determination and feature selection of support vector machines," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 1817–1824, Nov. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2007.08.088>.
- [50] J. F. Easton, C. R. Stephens, and M. Angelova, "Risk factors and prediction of very short term versus short/intermediate term post-stroke mortality: A data mining approach," *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, vol. 54, pp. 199–210, Nov. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2014.09.003>.
- [51] J. Kennedy and R. Eberhart, "Particle swarm optimization," in *International Conference on Neural Networks*, Perth, WA, Australia, Dec. 1995, vol. 4, pp. 1942–1948, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICNN.1995.488968>.
- [52] W. Y. Dong and R. R. Zhang, "Order-3 stability analysis of particle swarm optimization," *Information Sciences*, vol. 503, pp. 508–520, Nov. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2019.07.020>.
- [53] M. R. Bonyadi and Z. Michalewicz, "Analysis of Stability, Local Convergence, and Transformation Sensitivity of a Variant of the Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 370–385, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2015.2460753>.
- [54] S. Ahmed, M. Mafarja, H. Faris, and I. Aljarah, "Feature Selection Using Salp Swarm Algorithm with Chaos," in *2nd International Conference on Intelligent Systems, Metaheuristics & Swarm Intelligence*, Phuket, Thailand, Mar. 2018, pp. 65–69.
- [55] E. Emary, H. M. Zawbaa, and A. E. Hassanien, "Binary grey wolf optimization approaches for feature selection," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 172, pp. 371–381, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2015.06.083>.

Numerical Simulation of a One-Dimensional Non-Linear Wave Equation

Adalberto Gomes da Silva Júnior

Department of Basic Science and Environmental
Engineering School at Lorena, University of São Paulo
São Paulo, Brasil
adalbertogomes.eq@usp.br

Jairo Aparecido Martins

Research & Development
DESCH North America
Cambridge, Ontario, Canada
Jairo.martins@desch.com

Estaner Claro Romão

Department of Basic Science and Environmental
Engineering School at Lorena, University of São Paulo
São Paulo, Brasil
estaner23@usp.br

Received: 15 March 2022 | Revised: 24 March 2022 | Accepted: 27 March 2022

Abstract—In this paper, numerical simulations via regressive and central finite differences of different orders were produced using Fortran code and a one-dimensional non-linear wave equation was solved. The errors obtained during simulations, when using different refinements, were listed and compared in order to determine the validity of the simulation, which demonstrates that the proposed formulation presents satisfactory results.

Keywords—finite difference method; wave equation; numerical simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to better understand phenomena in physics, engineering, and even mathematics, it is often necessary to apply mathematical modeling, which most of the times requires solving Partial Differential Equations (PDEs). Due to the high complexity of these models, an analytical solution is infeasible, requiring the use of numerical methods. Among many methods available, the most friendly, accessible, and accurate, and therefore used for multiple purposes in engineering, is the method of finite differences [1-7]. It relies in a substitution of partial derivatives at a point by its incremental reasons. Moreover, it is important to highlight that numerical simulations involving equations which guide transference of energy usually have their values matching with the analytical solution. Authors in [8] for instance, analyzed the temperatures inside a concrete dam by using an explicit method, where a transition between stationary to transient regime could be detected. Another example is described in [9], when using finite differences at sixth order, applied in an equation of convection-diffusion-reaction an implicit method, obtained low absolute errors, most of them diffusive when using more refined meshes. By using the same approximation order, authors in [10] obtained deviations of 10^{-14} in problems which considered reaction-diffusion equations in singly disturbed

systems. Many other papers have demonstrated success when using the difference finite method for the solution of problems of transport phenomena such as [11-14], however, we did not find in the open access bibliography other works that compare explicit methods in the solution of the equation proposed in this work.

Since many papers have described high precision on outputs when covering transport phenomena via finite difference methods, this paper applied this method to simulate a one-dimensional non-linear wave equation, while also checking whether this method is valid for this application. In addition, the maximum error obtained with a discrete mesh was evaluated and demonstrated the accuracy of the proposed method.

II. METHOD OF FINITE DIFFERENCES

One of the most common methods to solve PDEs is the finite difference method, which consists of an approximation of differences by incremental reasons that utilizes expansions from Taylor's series. Furthermore, a finite differences method can be classified as regressive, progressive, or central.

Assume that y is a function, i a point which belongs to a mesh and Δx an incremental reason between two points: x_{i-1} and x_i , both included in the mesh. A regressive finite difference makes use of values of a function in i and of $i-1$ to calculate a variation rate at the point. A progressive finite difference uses i and $i+1$ and finally it is also possible to know an approximate value of a differential by applying central differences, which applies values such as: $i+1$ and $i-1$ [15]. The three described equations are:

- Regressive Finite Differences:

$$\left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)_i = \frac{y_i - y_{i-1}}{\Delta x} + O(\Delta x) \quad (1)$$

- Progressive Finite Differences:

$$\left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)_i = \frac{y_{i+1}-y_i}{\Delta x} + O(\Delta x) \quad (2)$$

- Central Finite Differences:

$$\left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)_i = \frac{y_{i+1}-y_{i-1}}{2\Delta x} + O(\Delta x^2) \quad (3)$$

III. MODEL EQUATION AND FORMULATIONS

An equation of one-dimensional non-linear wave, obeying the continuity and Euler’s principles, was used in the simulations. It is important to highlight that functions such as $f(x, t)$ and $g(x, t)$ were applied in order to allow an easier way to build a precise solution when processing computational tests.

The equations of the one-dimensional non-linear wave are:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} + \rho \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = f(x, t) \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{a^2}{\rho} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} = g(x, t) \quad (5)$$

Note that (4) and (5) are only a reduction of the motion and continuity equation (Navier Stokes Equations).

For the formulations below, the explicit method is employed, which allows calculating variables u and ρ at point x_i in a mesh, by using data from previous steps. This procedure allowed considering independent equations and guaranteed a quicker computerized solution when comparing with the implicit method, which implies a linear system of algebraic equations [16].

A. Formulation I: Regressive Finite Difference

In (4):

$$\frac{\rho_i^n - \rho_i^{n-1}}{\Delta t} + u_i^{n-1} \left(\frac{\rho_i^{n-1} - \rho_{i-1}^{n-1}}{\Delta x}\right) + \rho_i^{n-1} \left(\frac{u_i^{n-1} - u_{i-1}^{n-1}}{\Delta x}\right) = f_i(x, t) \quad (6)$$

$$\rho_i^n = \left[f_i(x, t) - \rho_i^{n-1} \left(\frac{u_i^{n-1} - u_{i-1}^{n-1}}{\Delta x}\right) - u_i^{n-1} \left(\frac{\rho_i^{n-1} - \rho_{i-1}^{n-1}}{\Delta x}\right) + \rho_i^{n-1} \right] \Delta t \quad (7)$$

and in (5) :

$$\frac{u_i^n - u_i^{n-1}}{\Delta t} + u_i^{n-1} \left(\frac{u_i^{n-1} - u_{i-1}^{n-1}}{\Delta x}\right) + \frac{a^2}{\rho_i^{n-1}} \left(\frac{\rho_i^{n-1} - \rho_{i-1}^{n-1}}{\Delta x}\right) = g_i(x, t) \quad (8)$$

$$u_i^n = \left[g_i(x, t) + \frac{u_i^{n-1}}{\Delta t} - u_i^{n-1} \left(\frac{u_i^{n-1} - u_{i-1}^{n-1}}{\Delta x}\right) + \frac{a^2}{\Delta x} \left(\frac{\rho_i^{n-1}}{\rho_i^{n-1}} - 1\right) \right] \Delta t \quad (9)$$

B. Formulation II: Central Finite Difference

In Equation (4):

$$\frac{\rho_i^n - \rho_i^{n-1}}{\Delta t} + u_i^{n-1} \left(\frac{\rho_{i+1}^{n-1} - \rho_{i-1}^{n-1}}{2\Delta x}\right) + \rho_i^{n-1} \left(\frac{u_{i+1}^{n-1} - u_{i-1}^{n-1}}{2\Delta x}\right) = f_i(x, t) \quad (10)$$

$$\rho_i^n = \left[f_i(x, t) - u_i^{n-1} \left(\frac{\rho_{i+1}^{n-1} - \rho_{i-1}^{n-1}}{2\Delta x}\right) - \rho_i^{n-1} \left(\frac{u_{i+1}^{n-1} - u_{i-1}^{n-1}}{2\Delta x}\right) + \rho_i^{n-1} \right] \Delta t \quad (11)$$

and in (5):

$$\frac{u_i^n - u_i^{n-1}}{\Delta t} + u_i^{n-1} \left(\frac{u_{i+1}^{n-1} - u_{i-1}^{n-1}}{2\Delta x}\right) + \frac{a^2}{\rho_i^{n-1}} \left(\frac{\rho_{i+1}^{n-1} - \rho_{i-1}^{n-1}}{2\Delta x}\right) = g_i(x, t) \quad (12)$$

$$u_i^n = \left[g_i(x, t) + \frac{u_i^{n-1}}{\Delta t} - u_i^{n-1} \left(\frac{u_{i+1}^{n-1} - u_{i-1}^{n-1}}{2\Delta x}\right) - \frac{a^2}{\rho_i^{n-1}} \left(\frac{\rho_{i+1}^{n-1} - \rho_{i-1}^{n-1}}{2\Delta x}\right) \right] \Delta t \quad (13)$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The formulations presented above were processed with Fortran programming language. By computational code was possible to obtain results for values of u (speed) and ρ (specific mass) for both the conducted tests, i.e. with regressive finite differences and central finite differences. Furthermore, in order to make the test simpler, sound speed was assumed as $a = 1$ and the size of spatial and time domains as 0.2. Meanwhile, for the numerical tests the following equations were adopted for u and ρ :

$$u(x, t) = \text{sen}(x + t) \quad (14)$$

$$\rho(x, t) = \text{cos}(x + t) \quad (15)$$

As a result, (4) and (5) were written as:

$$f(x, t) = \text{cos}(2x + 2t) - \text{sen}(x + t) \quad (16)$$

$$g(x, t) = \text{cos}(x + t) + \text{sen}(x + t)\text{cos}(x + t) + \frac{a^2}{\text{cos}(x+t)} (-\text{sen}(x + t)) \quad (17)$$

Notice that, the previous equation is valid if: $x + t \neq \frac{\pi}{2}$.

For both numerical simulations, the values of MaxU and Maxρ were calculated, which represent the highest error incurred when comparing the calculated value, by finite differences, and the real value (the exact solution) from equations which contain all the points in the discrete mesh. Some of data for maximum errors were very high and they were considered as divergent. Further, for finite differences there were only a few values of MaxU and Maxρ that were not divergent (see Tables I and II). In addition, there was an homogeneous trend of divergences among the meshes worked along the tests.

A notable feature verified for central finite differences was the lower values for MaxU and Maxρ for smaller increments of time, while for higher spatial increments values of MaxU and Maxρ showed divergent values, see Tables III and IV.

TABLE I. MAXIMUM ERROR FOR FUNCTION $u(x, t)$ USING REGRESSIVE FINITE DIFFERENCES

Δt	Δx						
	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.001	0.0001	0.00001	0.000001
0.2	1.56E+00	5.76E-01	div	4.99E+00	1.03E+01	6.68E+00	div
0.1	div	9.51E-01	div	div	9.88E+00	1.07E+01	div
0.05	div	div	div	div	div	div	div
0.02	div	div	div	div	div	div	div
0.01	div	div	div	div	div	div	div
0.005	div	div	div	div	div	div	div

TABLE II. MAXIMUM ERROR FOR FUNCTION $\rho(x, t)$ USING REGRESSIVE FINITE DIFFERENCES

Δt	Δx						
	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.001	0.0001	0.00001	0.000001
0.2	9.85E-02	5.94E-02	div	2.01E-01	2.50E-01	2.23E-01	div
0.1	div	1.17E-01	div	div	3.88E-01	3.92E-01	div
0.05	div	div	div	div	div	div	div
0.02	div	div	div	div	div	div	div
0.01	div	div	div	div	div	div	div
0.005	div	div	div	div	div	div	div

TABLE III. MAXIMUM ERROR FOR FUNCTION $u(x, t)$ USING CENTRAL FINITE DIFFERENCES

Δt	Δx						
	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.001	0.0001	0.00001	0.000001
0.2	2.24E-01	2.02E-02	9.25E-03	8.74E-04	1.06E-04	3.82E-05	4.24E-05
0.1	4.22E+01	1.31E-01	5.99E-02	5.63E-03	5.62E-04	5.86E-05	8.74E-06
0.05	div	7.02E-01	1.63E-01	1.46E-02	1.43E-03	1.41E-04	1.20E-05
0.02	div	div	div	4.77E-02	4.50E-03	4.48E-04	4.44E-05
0.01	div	div	div	1.55E-01	8.88E-03	8.72E-04	8.70E-05
0.005	div	div	div	div	1.86E-02	1.77E-03	1.77E-04

TABLE IV. MAXIMUM ERROR FOR FUNCTION $\rho(x, t)$ USING CENTRAL FINITE DIFFERENCES

Δt	Δx						
	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.001	0.0001	0.00001	0.000001
0.2	2.68E-01	5.02E-02	2.44E-02	2.40E-03	2.63E-04	5.00E-05	3.87E-05
0.1	9.60E+01	4.58E-02	1.68E-02	1.34E-03	1.36E-04	2.50E-05	1.39E-05
0.05	div	4.36E-01	8.20E-02	3.48E-03	3.19E-04	3.16E-05	5.79E-06
0.02	div	div	div	1.01E-02	7.30E-04	7.07E-05	7.04E-06
0.01	div	div	div	1.31E-01	1.62E-03	1.49E-04	1.48E-05
0.005	div	div	div	div	4.18E-03	3.18E-04	3.10E-05

V. CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained with both numerical simulations allow inferring about the validity of finite difference methods to analyze one-dimensional non-linear wave equations. For regressive differences, the values of MaxU and Max ρ for many simulations showed divergence, most likely due to the truncation error, very common for cases where Taylor series are utilized. For central finite differences, very small values of MaxU and Max ρ , close to 10^{-3} , appeared during the simulations with spatial meshes as well as during the time dependent simulations with refined meshes. These values could be driven by choosing Δt within the range of stability requirements.

In conclusion, the finite differences methods are valid to solve the one-dimensional non-linear wave equation but they are spatially restricted and time dependent, with few increments and finite differences with higher orders.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge the financial support by CAPES (process number 23038.000263/2022-19).

REFERENCES

- [1] E. C. Romao and L. H. P. de Assis, "Numerical Simulation of 1D Unsteady Heat Conduction-Convection in Spherical and Cylindrical Coordinates by Fourth-Order FDM," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2389–2392, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1724>.
- [2] L. Saidi, S. Mekroussi, S. Kherris, D. Zebbar, and B. Mébarki, "A Numerical Investigation of the Free Flow in a Square Porous Cavity with Non-Uniform Heating on the Lower Wall," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 7982–7987, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4604>.
- [3] S. Bekkouche and M. Kadja, "Numerical Analysis of Density-Driven Reactive Flows in Hele-Shaw Cell Geometry," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5434–5440, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3349>.
- [4] M. D. de Campos, E. Claro Romão, and L. F. M. de Moura, "A finite-difference method of high-order accuracy for the solution of transient nonlinear diffusive-convective problem in three dimensions," *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, vol. 3, pp. 43–50, Jul. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2014.03.001>.
- [5] M. Campos and E. Romão, "A High-Order Finite-Difference Scheme with a Linearization Technique for Solving of Three-Dimensional Burgers Equation," *Computer Modeling in Engineering and Sciences*, vol. 103, no. 3, pp. 139–154, Dec. 2014.
- [6] Y. Ge, Z. F. Tian, and J. Zhang, "An exponential high-order compact ADI method for 3D unsteady convection-diffusion problems," *Numerical Methods for Partial Differential Equations*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 186–205, 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1002/num.21705>.
- [7] Y. Ge, F. Zhao, and J. Wei, "A High Order Compact ADI Method for Solving 3D Unsteady Convection Diffusion Problems," *Applied and Computational Mathematics*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–10, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.acm.20180701.11>.
- [8] N. Coelho, M. Vasconcelos, and L. Pedroso, "Estudo de Diferenças Finitas para a Equação de Calor em Barragens de Concreto," in *Proceedings of the XXXVI Iberian Latin-American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, Nov. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.1828.9045>.
- [9] E. C. Romao, J. C. Z. Aguiar, and M. D. de Campos, "Central difference method of $O(\Delta x^6)$ in solution of the CDR equation with variable coefficients and Robin condition," *International Journal of Applied Mathematics*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 139–153, Jan. 2012.
- [10] F. W. Gelu, G. F. Duressa, and T. A. Bullo, "Sixth-order compact finite difference method for singularly perturbed 1D reaction diffusion

- problems," *Journal of Taibah University for Science*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 302–308, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtusci.2015.12.010>.
- [11] M. M. Cruz, M. D. Campos, J. A. Martins, and E. C. Romão, "An Efficient Technique of Linearization towards Fourth Order Finite Differences for Numerical Solution of the 1D Burgers Equation," *Defect and Diffusion Forum*, vol. 348, pp. 285–290, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/DDF.348.285>.
- [12] O. A. Neves, E. C. Romão, J. B. C. Silva, and L. F. M. de Moura, "Numerical Simulation of Convection-Diffusion Problems by the Control-Volume-Based Finite-Element Method," *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part A: Applications*, vol. 57, no. 10, pp. 730–748, May 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10407781003800672>.
- [13] L. Zhang, L. Wang, and X. Ding, "Exact finite-difference scheme and nonstandard finite-difference scheme for coupled Burgers equation," *Advances in Difference Equations*, vol. 2014, no. 1, May 2014, Art. no. 122, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1687-1847-2014-122>.
- [14] H. Zhu, H. Shu, and M. Ding, "Numerical solutions of two-dimensional Burgers' equations by discrete Adomian decomposition method," *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 840–848, Aug. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.camwa.2010.05.031>.
- [15] S. C. Chapra and R. P. Canale, *Métodos Numéricos para Engenharia*, 5th ed. Sao Paolo, Brazil: Mcgraw-Hill, 2008.
- [16] A. D. O. Fortuna, *Técnicas Computacionais Para Dinâmica dos Fluidos. Conceitos Básicos e Aplicações*, 2nd ed. Sao Paolo, Brazil: EDUSP, 2020.

A Combined Chaotic System for Speech Encryption

Salah Mokhnache
EBT Department
University Ferhat Abbas Setif 1
Setif, Algeria
mokhnachesalah@yahoo.fr

Mohamed El Hossine Daachi
ETA Laboratory, Electronics Department
Mohamed El Bachir El Ibrahimi University
Bordj Bou Arréridj, Algeria
mohamed.daachi@univ-bba.dz

Tewfik Bekkouche
ETA Laboratory, Electro-mechanics Department
Mohamed El Bachir El Ibrahimi University
Bordj Bou Arréridj, Algeria
bekkou66@hotmail.com

Nacira Diffellah
ETA Laboratory, Electronics Department
Mohamed El Bachir El Ibrahimi University
Bordj Bou Arréridj, Algeria
diffellahn@gmail.com

Received: 13 March 2022 | Revised: 26 March 2022 | Accepted: 29 March 2022

Abstract-This paper presents a speech encryption scheme by performing a combination of modified chaotic maps inspired by classic logistic and cubic maps. The main idea was to enhance the performance of classical chaotic maps by extending the range of the chaotic parameter. The resulted combining map was applied to a speech encryption scheme by using the confusion and diffusion architecture. The evaluation results showed a good performance regarding the chaotic behaviors such as initial value, control parameter, Lyapunov exponent, and bifurcation diagram. Simulations and computer evaluations with security analysis showed that the proposed chaotic system exhibits excellent performance in speech encryption against various attacks. The results obtained demonstrated the efficiency of the proposed scheme compared to an existing valuable method for static and differential cryptographic attacks.

Keywords- speech encryption; chaos; modified chaotic maps

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of technologies and means of communication puts in danger data transfers and confidential information in communication networks. As much information is transmitted over these networks in the form of verbal communications, the protection of voice communications pushes toward the search for new security techniques. Cryptographic techniques are used to improve security by converting speech into an unintelligible form to an unauthorized person [1-3]. Speech signal encryption has emerged as one of the most widely used techniques to ensure the security of verbal transmissions. Various standards and protocols involving cryptography have been proposed to deal with information security issues, such as speech encryption algorithms like the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), Data Encryption Standard (DES), Triple Data Encryption Standard (3DES), and the RSA algorithm [4-5].

Each standard encryption technique has its advantages and disadvantages, but the distribution of encryption keys remains unresolved by these cryptographic techniques. Chaotic

cryptography appears as a good alternative to resolve this situation, as it offers great sensitivity and a large space of encryption keys. The appearance of chaotic cryptography [6], which defines a particular state of a nonlinear dynamic system whose behavior is never repeated, very sensitive to initial conditions, and unpredictable in the long term, gave new life to speech encryption systems [7-8] by applying chaotic maps of one, two, or three-dimensions [9,10]. Despite the success of chaotic map-based methods, they remain vulnerable to the narrow range of control parameters and the sensitivity of secret keys. Several algorithms combining chaotic maps have been proposed to expand the range of control parameters and reinforce the sensitivity of secret keys [11-12]. In this perspective, enhanced chaotic maps inspired by classic chaotic ones, such as Logistic and Cubic maps, were proposed in [13]. This approach introduced the composition of each sequence with the exponential function and then applied the arithmetic modulo to unity. The resulting new chaotic sequences were applied in a speech encryption scheme, jointly in the confusion and diffusion phases.

This study examines a speech encryption scheme by combining Logistic and Cubic maps. The performance of the chaotic sequences of Logistic and Cubic maps and their combination was examined, concerning the sensitivity of the initial value, bifurcation diagram, and Lyapunov exponent [14]. Moreover, the proposed method was simulated and experimental results were obtained concerning the estimation of different evaluation metrics. Furthermore, the behavior facing brute force attacks was also discussed by comparing the proposed with an existing valuable method.

II. THE PROPOSED ENHANCED CHAOTIC SYSTEM

The combination of chaotic maps into a non-linear combination of two different chaotic maps can be represented as a single chaotic one by the expression:

$$x_{n+1} = A_{FG} = (F(a, x_n) + G(b, x_n)) \bmod 1 \quad (1)$$

Corresponding author: Salah Mokhnache

where $F(a, x_n)$ and $G(b, x_n)$ are two 1-D chaotic maps with parameters a and b , and n is the iteration number [15]. The proposed combination of chaotic systems is based on Logistic and Cubic maps, defined as follows:

A. Logistic Map

The Logistic map is one of the famed chaotic functions that have been studied for cryptography applications. The logistic function is expressed as :

$$x_{n+1} = r \cdot x_n \cdot (1 - x_n) \quad (2)$$

where x_n takes values in the $[0, 1]$ interval and the parameter r is a positive constant taking values up to 4. Its value determines and explores the behavior of the logistic map. From $r = 3.57$, the iterations become chaotic.

B. Cubic Map

The Cubic map is another shape of the most commonly used chaotic maps to generate chaotic sequences. It is one of the most used maps in cryptographic applications. This map is formally defined by:

$$x_{n+1} = r \cdot x_n \cdot (1 - x_n^2) \quad (3)$$

where r is its parameter and x_n is a system variable whose value is $(0, 1) \forall i \geq 0$. This method shows chaotic dynamics for $2.3 < r < 2.6$.

C. Combined Chaotic Map

The proposed chaotic system is a combination of Logistic and Cubic maps by introducing the composition of each sequence with the exponential function and then applying the arithmetic modulo to unity. The subtraction between logistic and cubic maps gives a new chaotic system, expressed as:

$$x_{n+1} = r \cdot e^{2x_n} \cdot (e^{x_n} - 1) \text{ mod } 1 \quad (4)$$

D. Lyapunov Exponent

The study of the stability of a dynamic system uses the plot of the Lyapunov exponent, which allows locating the stable and the chaotic zones to quantify the stability or the instability of its movements. When the Lyapunov exponent has a positive value, it describes a chaotic zone and the system will be unstable. The performance of the dynamic system is related to the quantized values of the exponent. When the quantized value is large, the chaotic performance will be better. As shown in Figure 1(d), the Lyapunov exponents of the logistic map are negative when $r < 3.57$. For the Cubic map, the Lyapunov exponent values are less than zero when $r < 2.3$. This means that the systems governed by these two maps do not exhibit any chaotic behavior below these values. Figure 2 shows the plot of the Lyapunov exponent of the proposed chaotic map. Unlike the Logistic and the Cubic sequences, the combined presents a positive value of the Lyapunov exponent over the entire interval of the control parameter. This shows the improvement of the proposed system's performance by the expanse of the range of the chaotic parameters.

Fig. 1. Bifurcation diagrams for (a) Logistic and (b) Cubic maps – Lyapunov exponents for (c) Logistic and (d) Cubic (d) maps.

E. Bifurcation

Changes in the parameters of linear dynamical systems cause quantitative changes but do not modify the behavior of the system. In nonlinear dynamic systems, a small variation of certain parameters, called control parameters, can under well-defined conditions cause a complete change in the system's behavior at equilibrium. These are transitions of dynamic

systems into chaotic states, also called bifurcations. The bifurcation diagram is one of the tools to locate the zones of the chaotic behavior of a dynamic system, and according to Figures 1(a), (b), which present the bifurcation diagrams of the Logistic and the Cubic maps, it is noted that the chaotic ranges of both maps are limited. Figure 1(a) shows that the chaotic range of the Logistic sequence is limited in the [3.57, 4.0] interval and that the control parameter r under this range cannot have chaotic behaviors. The Cubic sequence has a limited chaotic range between [2.3, 2.6]. The bifurcation diagram of the proposed combination in Figure 2(b) shows a very wide chaotic range with an invariant uniform distribution over the entire definition interval of the control parameter.

Fig. 2. (a) Bifurcation diagram and (b) Lyapunov exponent of the proposed chaotic map.

F. Sensitivity of Initial Conditions

Chaotic systems are extremely sensitive to disturbances. This fact was illustrated by the butterfly effect, popularized by Edward Lorenz [16]. A chaotic dynamical system is unpredictable and sensitive to initial conditions. Thus, two trajectories of initially neighboring phases deviate more quickly from each other, regardless of their initial proximity. The impact of the sensitivity to the initial conditions can be highlighted by a simulation by assigning two very close initial conditions to the proposed combined system. At first, the two systems evolve similarly, but soon their behavior becomes different, as shown in Figure 3 for two close initial conditions $x_{01} = 0.58$ and $x_{01} = 0.58 + 10^{-16}$.

Fig. 3. Evolution of the proposed combined map for two very close initial conditions $x_{01} = 0.58$ (blue) and $x_{01} = 0.58 + 10^{-16}$ (red).

III. THE PROPOSED VOICE ENCRYPTION SCHEME

This section presents the proposed encryption scheme and the details of its algorithm based on the combined model of the two chaotic maps and following its temporal evolution which reveals a purely chaotic behavior.

A. Encryption Process

The encryption process is illustrated in Figure 4 and consists of the following steps:

- Step 1: Reading or recording the original speech signal.
- Step 2: Generation of a chaotic vector using the combined chaotic system based on Logistic and Cubic maps with an initial condition x_{01} and a control parameter r_{01} .
- Step 3: Arrange the chaotic vector in descending order to form a permutation vector.
- Step 4: Scramble the speech signal using the permutation vector for random changing the positions of the segments of the speech signal according to the generated chaotic vector.
- Step 5: For the diffusion phase, another chaotic vector is generated based on the same combination of Logistic and Cubic maps, with other parameters, initial condition x_{02} and control parameter r_{02} , to increase the sensitivity of the secret key and multiply the elements of this vector by 255.
- Step 6: Execute the XOR operation bit by bit between the generated chaotic and the permuted vector.
- Step 7: Obtain and extract the output encrypted speech.

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the proposed encrypted voice scheme.

B. Decryption Process

After the acquisition or loading of the encrypted signal, the operation takes the same path as the encryption process, but in a reverse way.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

MATLAB R2014 was used to perform the simulations. Various tests were performed to demonstrate the performance and security of the proposed system, such as waveform, spectrogram analysis, SNR, and correlation tests. Speech signals having an 8kHz sampling frequency with 8 bits per sample were used as test files. The improved chaotic map parameters were: $x_{01} = 0.41$, $x_{02} = 0.51$, $r_{01} = 40.31$, and $r_{02} = 50.31$.

A. Waveform and Spectrogram

A visual examination of descriptive acoustic analysis of speech can be performed in two ways: the waveform in the time domain and the energy distribution in the time-frequency plane. The prototype of the energy representation is the spectrogram. As shown in Figures 5 and 6, the waveform and spectrogram of the encrypted signal were uniformly distributed and very different from those of the original signals. The intelligibility was destroyed, and the original signal became completely unintelligible.

B. Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR)

The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) metric is an efficient estimator to measure the intelligibility of a speech signal [17-19], and it is defined as the average of the SNR values of short segments of the output signal as:

$$SNR = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_s} x^2(i)}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_s} (x(i)-y(i))^2} \quad (5)$$

where $x(i)$ is the original speech, $y(i)$ is the decrypted speech signal, and N_s is the number of samples. As SNR decreases, the higher is the quality of the encrypted signal.

C. Correlation Analysis

The correlation coefficient is an effective metric to measure encryption quality. The correlation coefficients for original signals are close to 1, which shows that the samples are strongly correlated, while for encrypted signals the correlation coefficients are close to 0, as there is no correlation between the original and the encrypted signal. This confirms the quality of the encryption process since there is no similarity between the original and the encrypted signals. The correlation coefficient is given by [19]:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{cov(x,y)}{(\sqrt{var(x)}\sqrt{var(y)})} \quad (6)$$

$$cov(x,y) = \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} (x(i) - E(x))(y(i) - E(y)) \quad (7)$$

$$E(x) = \frac{1}{N_s} \quad (8)$$

$$var(x) = \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{i=0}^{N_s} (x(i) - E(x))^2 \quad (9)$$

where N_s is the number of speech samples involved in the calculations, $cov(x,y)$ is the covariance, $E(x)$ is the expected

value of x , and $var(x)$ is the variance. The correlation and the SNR analysis results are illustrated in Table I. The values of the correlation coefficient r_{xy} between the original and the encrypted signals were very low, and the same remark is noted for the values of the SNR metric, indicating that the encrypted signal is highly noisy. During the decryption phase, the correlation coefficients between the original and corresponding decrypted speech reveal values equal to unity, which confirms the strong resemblance between the signals. However, the measurements of the SNR coefficients are high positive, which indicates a very good quality of the recovered speech signals.

TABLE I. QUALITY OF ENCRYPTED AND DECRYPTED VOICE SIGNALS

Speech files	SNR (in dB)		r_{xy}
	Encrypted/Decrypted	Encrypted/Decrypted	
Signal 1.wav	-10.4925/39.2841	0.0032/1	
Signal 2.wav	-11.3701/45.1425	0.0012/1	
Signal 3.wav	-11.8293/39.8948	-0.0002537/1	
Signal 4.wav	-16.3239/40.6553	-0.0002593/1	
Signal 5.wav	-14.3535/43.1726	-0.0052/1	

Fig. 5. Waveform plot of: (a) original voice, (b) encrypted voice, and (c) decrypted voice.

Fig. 6. Spectrogram plot of (a) original voice, (b) encrypted voice, and (c) decrypted voice.

D. Key Space Analysis

In general, the accepted keyspace of an encryption algorithm must be larger than 2^{100} to thwart brute-force attacks. The proposed system has two keys with initial conditions and control parameters (x_{01} , x_{02} , r_{01} , and r_{02}). The proposed system has 10^{16} precision for both initial conditions and 10^{14} for both control parameters. So the total keyspace is $10^{16 \times 2} \times 10^{14 \times 2} \cong 2^{180}$. This confirms that the proposed approach is highly efficient against brute-force attacks.

E. Key Sensitivity Analysis

A reliable speech signal encryption approach must be sensitive to the slightest change in the secret key, i.e. changing a single value in the secret key must produce a completely different encrypted signal. Keys for encryption (x_{01} , r_{01}) and decryption (x_{02} , r_{02}) were examined to demonstrate the sensitivity of the proposed approach. The results shown in Figure 7 indicate that if the sender's keys are identical to the receiver's, the decrypted signal is identical to the original, but if a minor change in the parameters occurs, the decrypted image in each case is still completely unknown, although the change made in the parameters is very small.

Fig. 7. Decrypted speech signal with a little change in parameters. (a) Identical parameters, (b) $x_{02} = x_{02} + 10^{-15}$, (c) $r_{02} = r_{02} + 10^{-14}$ (d) $x_{01} = x_{01} + 10^{-16}$, (e) $r_{01} = r_{01} + 10^{-14}$.

V. COMPARATIVE STUDY

Table II presents the results of the proposed method, showing very acceptable values of correlation and the SNR coefficients, in the encryption and decryption phase compared to the method described in [19]. The correlation coefficients between the original and the decrypted signal are close to 1 for the proposed method, which shows that the samples are strongly correlated, while the correlation coefficients for the encrypted signals are close to zero. The SNR coefficients between the original and the encrypted signal for the proposed method are much reduced compared to [19], showing the improved quality of the encrypted signal. The SNR coefficients between the original and the decrypted signal show very satisfactory values, close to 45.1425dB, therefore better than those found in [19]. These results show the improved performance of the proposed compared to an existing valuable method, showing unintelligible encrypted signals and highly intelligible decrypted signals.

TABLE II. RESULTS OF COMPARISON WITH [19]

Speech files	Proposed method		[19]	
	SNR (in dB)	r_{xy}	SNR(in dB)	r_{xy}
	Encrypted/Decrypted	Encrypted/Decrypted	Decrypted	Encrypted/Decrypted
Signal 1.wav	-10.4925/ 39.2841	0.0032/1	33.7464	0.0233/ 0.999
Signal 2.wav	-11.3701/ 45.1425	0.0012/1	32.5781	0.0384/ 0.999
Signal 3.wav	-11.8293/ 39.8948	-0.0002537/1	33.0569	0.0157/1
Signal 4.wav	-16.3239/ 40.6553	-0.0002593/1	34.7112	0.0119/1
Signal 5.wav	-14.3535/ 43.1726	-0.0052/1		

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a new chaotic system that combines two classical maps, the Logistic and the Cubic, for speech signal encryption. The obtained combined sequence presents a positive value of the Lyapunov exponent over the entire definition interval of the control parameter, improving the performance of the proposed system by expanding the range of the chaotic parameters. The bifurcation diagram of the new combination shows a very wide chaotic range with an invariant uniform distribution without windowing over the entire definition interval of the control parameter. The parameters of the chaotic map were the secret key of the proposed encryption scheme, which is basically structured from the confusion and diffusion architecture. Objective and subjective analyses, such as visual examination of the waveform in the time domain and spectrograms, as well as statistical analysis, were performed to prove the security of the proposed encryption approach. Performance analysis confirmed that the proposed combined system is highly secure.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. NajimAlSaad and E. Hato, "A Speech Encryption based on Chaotic Maps," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 93, no. 4, pp. 19–28, May 2014, <https://doi.org/10.5120/16203-5488>.
- [2] M. O. Al-Dwairi, A. Y. Hendi, and Z. A. AlQadi, "An Efficient and Highly Secure Technique to Encrypt and Decrypt Color Images," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4165–4168, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2525>.
- [3] R. J. Rasras, Z. A. AlQadi, and M. R. A. Sara, "A Methodology Based on Steganography and Cryptography to Protect Highly Secure Messages," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3681–3684, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2380>.
- [4] H. O. Alanazi, B. B. Zaidan, A. A. Zaidan, H. A. Jalab, M. Shabbir, and Y. Al-Nabhani, "New Comparative Study Between DES, 3DES and AES within Nine Factors," *Journal of Computing*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 152–157, Mar. 2010.
- [5] P. Patil, P. Narayankar, Narayan D.G., and Meena S.M., "A Comprehensive Evaluation of Cryptographic Algorithms: DES, 3DES, AES, RSA and Blowfish," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 78, pp. 617–624, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2016.02.108>.
- [6] R. Matthews, "On the Derivation of a 'Chaotic' Encryption Algorithm," *Cryptologia*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 29–42, Jan. 1989, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0161-118991863745>.
- [7] Y. Hu and R. Tian, "Image Encryption and Decryption Based on Chaotic Algorithm," *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, vol. 8, no. 9, pp. 1814–1825, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.4236/jamp.2020.89136>.
- [8] J. Fridrich, "Symmetric Ciphers Based on Two-Dimensional Chaotic Maps," *International Journal of Bifurcation and Chaos*, vol. 08, no. 06, pp. 1259–1284, Jun. 1998, <https://doi.org/10.1142/S021812749800098X>.
- [9] X. Wang and Q. Yu, "A block encryption algorithm based on dynamic sequences of multiple chaotic systems," *Communications in Nonlinear Science and Numerical Simulation*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 574–581, Feb. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cnsns.2007.10.011>.
- [10] B. Flaeh and M. Dhiaa, "Multi-Levels Image Encryption Technique based on Multiple Chaotic Maps and Dynamic Matrix," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 151, no. 3, pp. 1–5, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.5120/ijca2016911693>.
- [11] E. Hato and D. Shihab, "Lorenz and Rossler Chaotic System for Speech Signal Encryption," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 128, no. 11, pp. 25–33, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.5120/ijca2015906670>.
- [12] A. Elsharkawi, R. M. El-Sagheer, H. Akah, and H. Taha, "A Novel Image Stream Cipher Based On Dynamic Substitution," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 1195–1199, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.729>.
- [13] M. Boumaraf and F. Merazka, "Partial and full speech encryption schemes based on 1D chaotic maps for AMR-WB codec," in *2018 2nd International Conference on Natural Language and Speech Processing (ICNLSP)*, Algiers, Algeria, Apr. 2018, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICNLSP.2018.8374388>.
- [14] C. Pak and L. Huang, "A new color image encryption using combination of the 1D chaotic map," *Signal Processing*, vol. 138, pp. 129–137, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sigpro.2017.03.011>.
- [15] S. Gokavarapu and S. V. Kumari, "A Novel Encryption Using One Dimensional Chaotic Maps," in *Emerging ICT for Bridging the Future - Proceedings of the 49th Annual Convention of the Computer Society of India (CSI) Volume 1*, 2015, pp. 193–203, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-13728-5_22.
- [16] E. N. Lorenz, "Deterministic Nonperiodic Flow," *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 130–141, Mar. 1963, [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1963\)020<0130:DNF>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1963)020<0130:DNF>2.0.CO;2).
- [17] P. Sathiyamurthi and S. Ramakrishnan, "Speech encryption algorithm using FFT and 3D-Lorenz-logistic chaotic map," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 79, no. 25, pp. 17817–17835, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-020-08729-5>.
- [18] I.-I. B. Ltd, "Speech Encryption Technique using S - box based on Multi Chaotic Maps," *TEM Journal*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1429–1434, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.18421/TEM103-54>.
- [19] P. Sathiyamurthi and S. Ramakrishnan, "Speech encryption using chaotic shift keying for secured speech communication," *EURASIP Journal on Audio, Speech, and Music Processing*, vol. 2017, no. 1, Sep. 2017, Art. no. 20, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13636-017-0118-0>.

Statistical Modeling of Time Headway on Urban Roads: A Case Study in Baghdad

Mohammed Alhamdany
Department of Civil Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
m.abdulrazzaq1901m@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Amjad Hamad Khalil Albayati
Department of Civil Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
a.khalil@uobaghdad.edu.iq

Received: 2 March 2022 | Revised: 22 March 2022 | Accepted: 1 April 2022

Abstract—Time headway is an important feature of traffic engineering, determined by measuring the time elapsed between successive vehicles crossing a point on the road. This paper proposes a time headway modeling of urban roads for each lane of selected sites based on headway distribution. The study was carried out in the capital of Baghdad, Iraq, choosing the Mohamed Al-Qassim and Qanat Al-Jaish highways to collect field headway data. Data were obtained using image processing and Python for video analysis. Each road consisted of six lanes divided into three lanes in each direction. The three lanes were studied in the forward movement of both highways. Seven flow rates were considered for the headway data to evaluate the flow state of each lane. The EasyFit 5.5 software was used to select an appropriate headway distribution for each flow rate, using a method depending on the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for each lane. The results demonstrated that the proper model per lane was different. The selected distributions were used to develop a model through nonparametric regression using Theil's slope estimator method.

Keywords—time headway; headway distribution; urban road; headway model; flow rate; traffic volume

I. INTRODUCTION

Traffic modeling is a fundamental tool in solving traffic engineering problems. Traffic simulation depends on modeling of time headway because it represents important characteristics in microscopic flow theory. The temporal distance between two successive vehicles is known as time headway [1]. It is the time difference between the arrival of a leading vehicle and the following vehicle to a reference point. Time headway depends on the flow rate of vehicles. A short time headway represents a high flow rate. This property are critical for roadway system planning, analysis, design, and operation [2]. Time headways can be used in various traffic evaluations such as safety, capacity, and service level [3]. The minimum of time headway is obtained when traffic flow reaches its maximum. To increase route capacity and reduce vehicle delays, traffic engineers can employ detailed modeling and assessment of vehicle headway distribution. A statistical model of time headway is essential for theoretical and simulation-based traffic modeling. In addition, headway distributions are used in digital simulations that

mimic multi-lane and highway traffic [4]. Traffic volume, the proportion of big or heavy vehicles in the traffic, lane position, road layout, time, and weather affect the time headway distribution of vehicles and their appropriate models [5]. Lane distribution and speed are affected by lateral clearance on the roadsides [6]. Data are collected and analyzed using advanced technologies, such as image processing techniques, due to their effectiveness compared to sensor and loop detector methods [7].

Several studies examined the modeling of time headway distribution. A study on the effect of lane position on time lane distributions at high levels of traffic flow was presented in [8]. Based on headway distribution analysis, this study assessed driving behavior in several highway lanes in Isfahan, Iran. The results demonstrated that the fit model for the passing lane was distinct from the middle lane, due to drivers' behavior. Numerous drivers adopted unsafe headways through car-following conditions in the passing lane, demonstrating the high risk ability of the driver population, which led to considerable distances in capacities and statistical distribution models of two lanes. The proper model for the passing lane was the shifted lognormal while for the middle was the shifted gamma. A traffic detector based on a laser beam sensor was used to model a suburban artery in South Korea [9]. The observed data were divided into five flow states. The test rejected the randomness for a flow rate of 5-9veh/m. Hence, theoretical modeling was performed for the remaining flow rates 10-14, 15-19, 20-24, and 25-29veh/m. The goodness of fit tests, examined using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) method, revealed that the best fits were the Johnson SB model for a flow rate of 10-14veh/m and the Johnson SU for the remaining three flows. The log-logistic model was the second-best fit for flow rates of 20-24 and 25-29veh/m. The progression of time under high flow conditions was studied on the Palestinian arterial street in Baghdad using two different periods for data collection [10]. The quality of fit was evaluated using the nonparametric chi-square test to determine the suitability of the logistic distribution of empirical data for the time headway distribution. The logistic probability distribution function described the time headway at the congested Palestine street for

Corresponding author: Mohammed Alhamdany

scale parameters ranging from 1.5 to 0.85. The differences in time headway distributions were studied in [11] for four flow levels, 0-600, 600-1200, 1200-1800, and 1800-2400PCU/h, for different two-lane and four-lane roads in Assam using the traffic volume data collected by cameras on four-lane roads. The Burr and Log-Pearson distributions were found to be suitable for 600-1200PCU/h, while the lognormal and log-logistic distributions fit the headway for traffic flows above 1200PCU/h. In [12], the mathematical distribution of vehicle headway was analyzed for freeway and arterial roads in Riyadh city, Saudi Arabia, evaluating low-volume traffic conditions. The findings demonstrated that the shifted exponential and the gamma distributions appeared to fit data on freeways and arterials, respectively. The time headway distributions of vehicles traveling on the urban expressway in Bangkok, Thailand, were examined in [1], using exponential, lognormal, and generalized extreme value GEV distributions. This study showed that the GEV distribution could describe more than 90% of the empirical distributions on most lanes and sections of an expressway. On the other hand, the exponential was the less practical distribution, as it only described the experimental distributions during ultra-low traffic conditions.

II. DATA COLLECTION

Field data were collected at two sites, as shown in Figures 1 and 2. The first site was the Mohamed Al-Qassim Highway, a 20km-long major arterial expressway, while the second was the Qanat Al-Jaish Highway, a 22km-long major arterial expressway in Baghdad. The camera was mounted on the footbridges at approximately 10m height from the road surface to monitor traffic flow.

Fig. 1. Site No.1 Mohamed Al-Qassim Highway.

Fig. 2. Site No.2 Qanat Al-Jaish Highway.

Table I shows the camera coordinates. The selected sections consisted of six main lanes, three lanes in each direction, termed left or lane one, middle or lane two, and right or lane three. The study section was distant from ramps, loops, and horizontal or vertical curves. Data were collected during daytime, under ideal weather and good visual conditions. Data were selected to include different levels of traffic flow and the stop-and-go situation was neglected. Traffic data for site one were collected for 21 hours over three days: 3, 4, and 5/5/2021. Two hours of the second day, 1:00 PM and 2:00 PM, were excluded due to the stop-and-go condition of the vehicles. Data for site two were collected for 18 hours over three days: 22, 23, and 24/2/2021.

TABLE I. CAMERA COORDINATES

Camera	Location coordinates	
	N	E
Site one	33° 18' 44.87"	44° 27' 03.30"
Site two	33° 19' 58.94"	44° 27' 52.95"

The spot speed of vehicles passing each site was measured using a Bushnell 101911 speed gun. The speed gun was set to measure the speed in km/h and pointed in the direction of the moving vehicle. This speed gun transmits signals to moving objects and can capture a vehicle moving faster than 16km/h [13]. The average speed was determined for an interval of 15min. Therefore, the sample size of speed data of 100veh/h/ln was randomly selected from each lane. Figure 3 shows the direction and equipment used to record the data. The video clips were analyzed using Python to extract the real data, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 3. The layout of the video cameras and speed gun on the site.

Fig. 4. Data extraction from video recording using Python.

The data were compared for their accuracy. The extracted data included the number of vehicles, vehicle classification, and time headway for each lane. Figures 5 and 6 depict the traffic volume observed during the study.

Fig. 5. Traffic volume of site 1 (Mohammed Al-Qassim Highway).

Fig. 6. Traffic volume of site 2 (Qanat Al-Jaish Highway).

Seven flow rates were used to represent each lane's different flow state conditions and provide accurate headway data. Tables II and III illustrate a few characteristics of the time headways average speed, defined by the spot speed for each flow rate.

TABLE II. COLLECTED DATA FOR SITE 1

Position	Rate of flow v/h/ln	Average speed (km/h)	Sample size	Av. headway (s)	Max headway (s)	Min headway (s)	Heavy vehicles (%)
Left lane: Lane 1	937	91	937	3.84	44.74	0.37	15
	1291	91.03	1291	2.788	19.65	0.33	10
	1366	91.01	1358	2.636	21.63	0.27	10
	1493	90.62	1485	2.411	17.38	0.23	16
	1679	90.23	1675	2.143	17.4	0.2	9
	1812	89.282	1808	1.986	20.353	0.166	24
	2015	87.609	1997	1.786	14.65	0.23	13
Middle lane: Lane 2	903	83.53	902	3.988	26.33	0.3	37
	1029	82.566	1024	3.497	21.57	0.2	29
	1142	81.658	1137	3.152	20.17	0.2	19
	1278	80.987	1278	2.816	13.31	0.23	20
	1384	79.918	1359	2.6	16.28	0.17	31
	1445	78.212	1433	2.491	15.58	0.2	29
	1575	72.762	1574	2.286	13.01	0.27	31
Right lane: Lane 3	311	76.26	311	11.566	59.85	1.07	30
	418	74.1	415	8.61	42.67	0.7	12
	423	72.21	421	8.515	37.84	0.73	21
	475	70	475	7.574	41.7	1	35
	500	68.525	498	7.201	62.1	0.4	27
	581	66.21	580	6.192	35.56	0.3	20
	684	64.041	675	5.262	46.01	0.3	19

TABLE III. COLLECTED DATA FOR SITE 2

Position	Rate of flow v/h/ln	Average speed (km/h)	Sample size	Av. headway (s)	Max headway (s)	Min headway (s)	Heavy vehicles (%)
Lane 1	985	91.158	983	3.655	22.12	0.2333	35
	1286	89.285	1280	2.799	28.43	0.2	18
	1568	87.677	1562	2.295	15.55	0.3	29
	1757	86.773	1745	2.049	17.38	0.27	21
	1935	85.732	1926	1.86	14.18	0.3	25
	2106	83.846	2103	1.709	12.71	0.2	30
	2345	82.333	2345	1.535	10.61	0.2	28
Lane 2	841	83.325	840	4.278	29.23	0.33	31
	932	82.187	926	3.862	25.92	0.4	37
	1090	80.562	1081	3.303	16.82	0.4	26
	1131	80.1	1128	3.182	21.65	0.23	18
	1271	78.762	1270	2.831	19.92	0.33	38
	1393	77.337	1392	2.583	14.48	0.27	19
	1490	74.975	1484	2.415	19.48	0.23	31
Lane 3	461	66.287	454	7.804	41.84	0.67	34
	515	65.45	514	6.991	31.73	0.5	18
	593	64.512	588	6.072	38.2	0.2	11
	612	63.61	610	5.883	32.93	0.64	21
	735	61.337	735	4.895	38.5	0.37	32
	843	60.187	842	4.272	33.06	0.4	20
	950	58.95	949	3.787	28.13	0.5	14

Fig. 7. Measurement of time headway.

The flow rate was calculated using:

$$flow\ rate = \frac{3600}{h_{avg}} \quad (1)$$

where h_{avg} is the average headway in a lane.

Time headway was defined as the time between bumper to bumper of successive vehicle arrivals at a reference point or line on the lane playback screen. This time was simultaneously calculated for multiple lanes, as shown in Figure 7.

III. AUTOMATIC VEHICLE AND CLASSIFICATION METHOD

Data were extracted from videos using Python and image-processing technologies to analyze vehicle counting, vehicle classifications, and time headway for each lane. Python and the OpenCV library were used to count the vehicles. The PyCharm IDE was used to develop the code, and Prettify was used to display it. Additionally, the NumPy, CV2, and CSV libraries were also used. The developed method combined grayscale and threshold algorithms to improve the quality and accuracy of vehicle detection. A dilate filter was used to track the position of each vehicle and categorize the detected vehicles into distinct classes, which were then tallied individually for each lane to offer helpful information for traffic flow analysis. The method's flowchart is depicted in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Flowchart of the processing algorithm.

The count of vehicles was executed when the contour areas touched the Region Of Interest (ROI). The ROI was formed by drawing three imaginary lines diagonally across the road, connecting the two ends representing the three lanes [14]. When the front bumper of the vehicle touched this imaginary line, the value of the counter increased, indicating that the object's movement was observed. An imaginary was drawn diagonally by connecting two ROI points. The virtual detector was used for the classification. This method consisted of a rectangle box, considering the ROI, and the vehicles within that box were identified based on their dimensions, i.e., width and height [15].

TABLE IV. RESULTS OF AUTOMATIC AND MANUAL COUNTING

Site No.	Time	Date	Automated method (using Python)				Manual method			
			Lane 1	Lane 2	Lane 3	Total	Lane 1	Lane 2	Lane 3	Total
Two	8:00 a.m.	24/02/2021	1579	1123	575	3277	1518	1269	619	3406
Two	2:00 p.m.	24/02/2021	2345	1392	865	4602	2351	1437	865	4653
Two	7:00 a.m.	23/02/2021	983	840	514	2337	976	874	534	2368
Two	11:00 a.m.	23/02/2021	1991	1277	748	4016	1879	1348	801	4028
Two	3:00 p.m.	22/02/2021	1729	1155	566	3450	1694	1224	600	3518
One	7:00 a.m.	03/05/2021	937	902	550	2389	931	918	552	2401
One	8:00 a.m.	03/05/2021	1358	1024	362	2744	1358	1077	358	2793
One	4:00 p.m.	04/05/2021	1797	1104	415	3316	1778	1127	419	3324
One	10:00 a.m.	05/05/2021	1808	1278	421	3507	1845	1302	447	3594
One	2:00 p.m.	05/05/2021	1752	1387	475	3614	1832	1443	463	3738

Fig. 9. The fit distribution obtained using the EasyFit v5.5 software.

The colors were specified to track the object using a histogram-oriented technique. In this method, the contour properties, such as solidity and contour area, were extracted and compared with the assumed values to determine whether the vehicle is a passenger or a heavy vehicle. The contours represent the connected pixels in an image. The contours of the foreground objects were detected after performing background subtraction. The video was binarized into frames to obtain the foreground. The Open CV method was used for the process of

thresholding black and white images. The Open CV algorithm operates in the form of thresholding, as it considers the frame into two levels, i.e. background and foreground. Additionally, a binary threshold was used for the segmentation of a vehicle. The vehicle counting results were obtained and compared using manual and automated methods, and it was observed that the latter method provided accurate results quickly, as shown in Table IV.

IV. METHOD

The EasyFit v5.5 software examined the collected data to select an appropriate distribution model, as shown in Figure 9. The distributions for each flow are shown in Table V. The analysis was carried out by evaluating the goodness of fit in the K-S test. It used the maximum likelihood method for the estimation parameters of fit distributions [16]. The K-S test is commonly used to detect whether two datasets are significantly different or not by calculating the probability of similarity between the two distributions [17]. Since the K-S tests are nonparametric and do not require prior assumptions based on distribution, they were applied to the observed data for distribution fitting. In this study, five distributions were used, where most of them were previously used for time headway modeling of highways and freeways: Pearson 6 [18], inverse Gaussian [19], generalized Pareto [20], Dagum [21], and generalized gamma.

TABLE V. EQUATIONS AND PARAMETERS FOR DISTRIBUTIONS

Distribution	Equation	Parameters
Pearson 6	$f(x) = \frac{\left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^{\alpha_1-1}}{\beta B(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \left(1 + \frac{x}{\beta}\right)^{\alpha_1+\alpha_2}}$	α_1 , shape parameter >0 α_2 , shape parameter >0 β , scale parameter >0
Inverse Gaussian	$f(x) = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{2\pi(x-\gamma)^3}} \exp\left(-\frac{\lambda(x-\gamma-\mu)^2}{2\mu^2(x-\gamma)}\right)$	λ , continuous parameter >0 μ , continuous parameter >0 γ , continuous location parameter >0
Generalized Pareto	$f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(1 + k \frac{(x-\mu)^{-1-\frac{1}{k}}}{\sigma}\right), k \neq 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-\mu)}{\sigma}\right), k = 0 \end{cases}$	k , shape parameter >0 σ , scale parameter >0 μ , location parameter
Dagum	$f(x) = \frac{\alpha k \left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^{\alpha k-1}}{\beta \left(1 + \left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^{\alpha}\right)^{k+1}}$	k , shape parameter >0 α , shape parameter >0 β , scale parameter >0
Generalized Gamma	$f(x) = \frac{k(x-y)^{k\alpha-1}}{\beta^{k\alpha} \Gamma(\alpha)} \times \exp(-((x-y)/\beta)^k)$	k , shape parameter >0 α , shape parameter >0 γ , location parameter

The following process was used to determine the appropriate time headway distribution model per lane:

- The goodness of fit of the distribution of total headways collected from the lane was examined per lane.
- The goodness of fit of the distribution of the headways occurring for every flow scope (veh/h/ln) was evaluated for each lane. The flow scopes are presented in Tables II and III.
- The acceptable models were identified for each lane using the above two steps.

- A standardized model was selected using the Theil's slope estimator method for the flow ranges for each lane.

The parameters of time headway distribution models were estimated based on the previous steps.

V. RESULTS

The appropriate distribution for the time headway modeling was determined by the K-S test for each flow scope, and the results are shown in Tables VI and VII. The goodness of fit of the models was tested with a 5% level of significance. The hypotheses for each test were: The compatibility of the headway distribution with the fitted model is rejected ($h=1$) or not ($h=0$). The model parameters were estimated through the headway data for each test, as shown in Tables VIII and IX. Each flow rate's parameter estimation was performed using the conventional Maximum Likelihood Estimate (MLE). The MLE method was used because it is an unbiased estimator [22]. The results showed that the flow scope in the left lane of site 1 followed Pearson type 6 distribution, where the p-value of flow rates 937, 1291, 1366, 1493, and 2015v/h/ln was greater than 0.05. However, the flow rates of 1679 and 1812veh/h/ln were less than 0.05, but greater than 0.02. The middle lane results demonstrated that the flow scope followed the inverse Gaussian distribution. The results of the right lane showed that the flow scope followed the generalized Pareto distribution. The left lane in site two followed the Dagum distribution with a p-value greater than 0.05, except for the flow rate of 985veh/h/ln with a p-value less than 0.05 but greater than 0.02. The middle and right lanes showed that the flow scope followed the generalized gamma distribution.

The p-value, rank, decision to reject or accept the distribution for each flow, and rank value to determine if the distribution is most compatible with the data were calculated. These results were used to determine the appropriate distribution for each flow rate. The estimation of parameters for each lane was performed using the Theil slope estimator method in MATLAB. The parameters of the simple linear regression model were determined using the estimated parameters for each flow rate. A t-test was performed to compare the regression coefficients with the null hypothesis, as shown in Tables X and XI. Theil's slope estimator method was used for the parameters of the linear regression model because it is simple to perform in the case of small sample sizes [23]. Subsequently, the mean flow rate (F) function, the β_0 denoting the constant and β_1 denoting the slope in the model were calculated.

TABLE VI. K-S TEST DISTRIBUTION OF HEADWAY FOR SITE 1

Lane 1				Lane 2				Lane 3			
Pearson 6 distribution				Inverse Gaussian distribution				Generalized Pareto distribution			
Flow rate	p-value	Rank	Reject	Flow rate	p-value	Rank	Reject	Flow rate	p-value	Rank	Reject
937	0.32	11	No	903	0.67	4	No	311	0.86	2	No
1291	0.104	3	No	1029	0.86	3	No	418	0.93	3	No
1366	0.23	2	No	1142	0.303	4	No	423	0.99	1	No
1493	0.14	1	No	1278	0.52	3	No	475	0.91	2	No
1679	0.041	2	Yes	1384	0.17	4	No	500	0.64	9	No
1812	0.048	7	Yes	1445	0.2	2	No	581	0.83	2	No
2015	0.102	6	No	1575	0.5	6	No	684	0.8	7	No

TABLE VII. K-S TEST DISTRIBUTION OF HEADWAY FOR SITE 2

Lane 1				Lane 2				Lane 3			
Dagum distribution				Generalized gamma fistribution				Generalized gamma distribution			
Flow rate	p-value	Rank	Reject	Flow rate	p-value	Rank	Reject	Flow rate	p-value	Rank	Reject
985	0.042	13	Yes	841	0.99	1	No	461	0.91	4	No
1286	0.086	6	No	932	0.58	4	No	515	0.51	2	No
1568	0.13	9	No	1090	0.93	2	No	593	0.97	5	No
1757	0.34	1	No	1131	0.67	2	No	612	0.77	7	No
1935	0.37	1	No	1271	0.74	4	No	735	0.87	1	No
2106	0.13	1	No	1393	0.37	6	No	843	0.96	3	No
2345	0.13	3	No	1490	0.28	10	No	950	0.25	5	No

(Note: No=not rejected, Yes=rejected)

TABLE VIII. ESTIMATED PARAMETERS FOR FITTED DISTRIBUTION MODELS – SITE 1

No.	Lane 1 Pearson 6 distribution	Lane 2 Inverse Gaussian distribution	Lane 3 Generalized Pareto distribution
1	$\alpha_1=10.102, \alpha_2=2.0324, b=0.4249$	$\lambda=7.125, \mu=4.251, \gamma=-0.262$	$k=0.041, \sigma=10.187, \mu=0.936$
2	$\alpha_1=19.641, \alpha_2=2.0443, b=0.1622$	$\lambda=6.218, \mu=3.793, \gamma=-0.296$	$k=-0.0187, \sigma=7.945, \mu=0.8104$
3	$\alpha_1=12.681, \alpha_2=2.3164, b=0.2888$	$\lambda=6.256, \mu=3.405, \gamma=-0.253$	$k=0.0311, \sigma=7.3578, \mu=0.9213$
4	$\alpha_1=19.9, \alpha_2=2.4289, b=0.18102$	$\lambda=5.971, \mu=3.053, \gamma=-0.236$	$k=0.0116, \sigma=6.655, \mu=0.84031$
5	$\alpha_1=8.3206, \alpha_2=2.8309, b=0.4846$	$\lambda=5.885, \mu=2.815, \gamma=-0.214$	$k=0.1318, \sigma=5.412, \mu=0.9672$
6	$\alpha_1=10.021, \alpha_2=2.8365, b=0.3710$	$\lambda=4.079, \mu=2.517, \gamma=-0.043$	$k=0.02808, \sigma=5.409, \mu=0.6263$
7	$\alpha_1=17.498, \alpha_2=3.2427, b=0.2309$	$\lambda=4.682, \mu=2.369, \gamma=-0.082$	$k=0.0722, \sigma=4.3503, \mu=0.5739$

TABLE IX. ESTIMATED PARAMETERS FOR FITTED DISTRIBUTION MODELS – SITE 2

No.	Lane 1 Dagum distribution	Lane 2 Generalized gamma distribution	Lane 3 Generalized Gamma distribution
1	$\kappa=4.3043, \alpha=1.468, \beta=0.688$	$k=0.5002, \alpha=5.256, \beta=0.1224, \gamma=0.2544$	$k=0.743, \alpha=1.651, \beta=1.659, \gamma=0.212$
2	$\kappa=2.0897, \alpha=1.731, \beta=1.062$	$k=0.662, \alpha=2.951, \beta=0.607, \gamma=0.368$	$k=0.881, \alpha=1.335, \beta=1.715, \gamma=0.285$
3	$\kappa=2.536, \alpha=1.810, \beta=0.831$	$k=0.784, \alpha=2.007, \beta=1.115, \gamma=0.3748$	$k=0.899, \alpha=1.429, \beta=1.804, \gamma=0.293$
4	$\kappa=2.045, \alpha=2.161, \beta=0.994$	$k=0.681, \alpha=2.922, \beta=0.560, \gamma=0.179$	$k=0.601, \alpha=0.934, \beta=1.393, \gamma=0.135$
5	$\kappa=1.4229, \alpha=2.5797, \beta=1.2363$	$k=0.441, \alpha=6.710, \beta=0.0278, \gamma=0.2823$	$k=0.98068, \alpha=1.27683, \beta=1.7327, \gamma=0.36667$
6	$\kappa=1.660, \alpha=2.685, \beta=1.08$	$k=0.48265, \alpha=5.679, \beta=0.05310, \gamma=0.216$	$k=0.956, \alpha=1.709, \beta=1.713, \gamma=0.3323$
7	$\kappa=1.036, \alpha=2.403, \beta=1.158$	$k=0.425, \alpha=9.150, \beta=0.0103, \gamma=0.173$	$k=1.029, \alpha=1.7431, \beta=1.824, \gamma=0.464$

Each estimated parameter corresponded to a mean flow rate (F). Then, the parameters could be calculated as functions of the mean flow rate in each lane. For the first site (Mohammed Al-Qassim Highway):

- The parameters of the Pearson Type 6 distribution model for the left lane (Lane 1) were:

$$a_1 = -3.461 + 0.012 \times F \quad (2)$$

$$a_2 = 1.283 + 0.001 \times F \quad (3)$$

$$\beta = 0.805 - 0.0004 \times F \quad (4)$$

- The parameters of the inverse Gaussian distribution model for the middle lane (Lane 2) were:

$$\lambda = 9.212 - 0.003 \times F \quad (5)$$

$$\mu = 7.289 - 0.003 \times F \quad (6)$$

$$\gamma = -0.347 + 0.0001 \times F \quad (7)$$

- The parameters of the generalized Pareto distribution model for the right lane (Lane 3) were:

$$k = 0.085 - 0.00013 \times F \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma = 17.146 - 0.022085 \times F \quad (9)$$

$$\mu = 1.0483 - 0.00036 \times F \quad (10)$$

For the second site (Qanat Al-Jaish highway):

- The parameters of the Dagum distribution model for the left lane (Lane 1) were:

$$k = 6.8958 - 0.00276 \times F \quad (11)$$

$$\alpha = 0.594 + 0.00088 \times F \quad (12)$$

$$\beta = 0.406 - 0.0003 \times F \quad (13)$$

- The parameters of the generalized gamma distribution model for the middle lane (Lane 2) were:

$$k = -0.106 + 0.0007 \times F \quad (13)$$

$$\alpha = 11.155 - 0.007 \times F \quad (14)$$

$$\beta = -2.109 + 0.0023 \times F \quad (15)$$

$$\gamma = 0.37 - 0.0001 \times F \quad (16)$$

- The parameters of the generalized gamma distribution model for the right lane (Lane 3) were:

$$k = 0.5924 + 0.0005 \times F \quad (17)$$

$$\alpha = 0.9451 + 0.0008 \times F \quad (18)$$

$$\beta = 1.2574 + 0.0009 \times F \quad (19)$$

$$\gamma = 0.1333 + 0.00028 \times F \quad (20)$$

Given the parameters of each model, the headway distributions can be obtained for different flow rates in each lane. At peak traffic flow hours, the maximum observed flow rate at which vehicles can reasonably pass site one was 2015veh/h/ln in the left lane. This demonstrates that the lane's

true capacity is approximately this amount. In the middle and right lanes, the corresponding values were about 1575 and 684veh/h/ln, respectively. For site two, the maximum observed flow rates were 2345, 1490, and 950veh/h/ln in the left, middle, and right lanes respectively. The distinct behavioral pattern of drivers in the left lane, as well as their tendency to tailgate at high speeds, resulted in a disparity in lane capacity and safety. The flow rates and statistical criteria such as mean, median, and standard deviation values were calculated based on the selected models to better evaluate the reasons for the different models chosen per lane, and they were compared with the observed data, as shown in Table XII.

TABLE X. ESTIMATION OF PARAMETERS USING NONPARAMETRIC REGRESSION FOR EACH LANE - SITE 1

Position	Parameters	$\hat{\beta}0$	$\hat{\beta}1$	t-test	p-value	R ²	Parameter estimation
Lane 1	α_1	-3.461	0.012	4.455	0.01	0.972	14.4215
	α_2	1.283	0.001	9.2	0.001	0.953	2.4931
	β	0.805	-0.0004	4.619	0.0095	0.655	0.2331
Lane 2	λ	9.212	-0.00258	7.9616	0.002	0.941	5.9747
	μ	7.2894	-0.003314	45.091	1.20E-05	0.978	3.1436
	γ	-0.347	0.0001	2.119	0.009	0.687	0.3471
Lane 3	k	0.085	-0.00013	2.654	0.038	0.412	0.0176
	σ	17.146	-0.022085	15.29	0.0003	0.971	6.4441
	μ	1.0483	-0.000359	2.5336	0.0125	0.59	0.8739

As seen in Table XII, the convergence of the results for the flow values for each lane amongst the model and the real indicates the model's strength. At the same flows, the mean value of headways in the left lane is less than the middle, which is less than the right. The median value of headways in the left lane is lower than the median value in the middle, which is less than the right. This indicates that the mean and median relationship is directly proportional to each lane. This also shows that the driver's behavior is different in each lane, even when the flows are the same in different lanes.

TABLE XI. ESTIMATION OF PARAMETERS USING NONPARAMETRIC REGRESSION FOR EACH LANE - SITE 2

Position	Parameters	$\hat{\beta}0$	$\hat{\beta}1$	t-test	p-value	R ²	Parameter estimation
Lane 1	k	6.8958	-0.00276	11.97	0.0006	0.911	2.1705
	α	0.594	0.00088	12.342	0.0005	0.986	2.1129
	β	0.406	0.0003	6.372	0.003	0.891	2.1129
Lane 2	k	-0.106	0.0007	4.169	0.012	0.59	0.709
	α	11.155	-0.007	2.9	3.10E-02	0.377	2.991
	β	-2.109	0.0023	4.818	9.00E-03	0.412	0.6378
Lane 3	γ	0.37	-0.0001	2.637	0.038	0.776	0.241
	k	0.5924	0.0005	8.3357	0.0018	0.963	0.8859
	α	0.9451	0.0008	5.1	0.0073	0.95	1.4091
Lane 3	β	1.2574	0.0009	5.0689	0.0074	0.919	1.7522
	γ	0.1333	0.00028	6.1401	0.0043	0.937	0.2934

TABLE XII. COMPARISON OF CHARACTERISTICS OF HEADWAYS FOR THE SAME LANE

Site No.	Lane No.	Flow rate (v/h/ln)		Mean (sec)		Median (sec)		Std. deviation (sec)	
		Real	Model	Real	Model	Real	Model	Real	Model
1	1	1432	1591	2.514	2.363	1.714	1.504	2.5	3.11
	2	1210	1261	2.974	2.855	2.29	2.17	2.328	2.284
	3	459	484	7.846	7.438	5.504	5.423	2.414	2.6
2	1	1587	1608	2.268	2.239	1.62	1.518	2.01	2.83
	2	1122	1125	3.207	3.199	2.428	2.403	2.641	2.691
	3	635	641	5.671	5.62	4.085	3.907	2.3786	2.593

VI. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the characteristics of the time headway modeling for each lane on two urban highways in Baghdad. The field observations used video recordings and simulations of the two sites exhibited different statistical distributions of time headways for varying flow level ranges under mixed traffic conditions. Five probability distributions were considered for investigating the time headways. Furthermore, the fitted models were different for different lanes depending on the driver's behavior while selecting the lane and their movement within it. The results are summarized as follows:

- 39 hours of traffic data were collected and the ratio of heavy vehicles ranged from 9% to 38% of total flow.
- According to the field observations, the results indicate that Mohamed Al-Qassim Highway's minimum and maximum time headways were 0.166 and 59.85sec, respectively. The Qanat Al-Jaish Highway had a minimum time headway of 0.2sec and a maximum of 41.84sec. Compared to other countries, such as the USA, it is very difficult to follow a

vehicle safely with a time headway of fewer than 2sec [24]. In Germany, the recommended minimum distance headway is half the speedometer, which means that a car traveling at 80km/h should maintain a distance of at least 40m. In Sweden, the National Road Administration recommends time headway of 3sec in rural areas. Police uses a critical time headway of 1sec as an orientation to impose fines [25]. This reflects the behavior of drivers on Iraqi roads. This is a traffic violation that may lead to traffic accidents while these violations increase with traffic volume.

- The comparison between automated vehicle counting and the manual method showed accuracy results of 96% for total flow and 88-97% for each lane. These results, along with the less time to extract the data, show the effectiveness of the automated method.
- Several statistical models were selected using EasyFit, and the parameters for each flow rate were estimated using MLE. The K-S test was used to examine the goodness of fit tests. The parameters for each model in a lane were estimated using Theil's slope estimator method. By getting

the parameters of each model, headway distributions for different flow rates per lane can be obtained.

- In the case of the Mohammed Al-Qassim highway, the left lane had a mean flow rate of 1432veh/h/ln for the observed data and 1591v/h/ln for the modeled data using Pearson's Type 6 distribution, showing a 6% error. The middle lane had a mean flow rate of 1210veh/h/ln for the observed data and 1261veh/h/ln for the modeled data using an inverse Gaussian distribution, having a 4% error. The right lane had a mean flow rate of 459veh/h/ln for the observed data and 484veh/h/ln for the modeled data using a generalized Pareto distribution with a 5% error.
- In the case of the Qanat Al-Jaish highway, the left lane had a mean flow rate of 1587veh/h/ln for the observed data and 1608vrh/h/ln for the modeled data using the Dagum distribution, giving an error of 1.3 %. The middle lane had a mean flow rate of 1122veh/h/ln for the observed data and 1125veh/h/ln for the modeled data using a generalized gamma distribution, with an error of 0.3 %. The right lane had a mean flow rate of 635veh/h/ln for the observed data and 620veh/h/ln for the modeled data using a generalized gamma distribution, giving an error of 2.4 %.

These results show that the driver's behavior is different in each lane, even at the same flows in other lanes.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Panichpapiboon, "Time-Headway Distributions on an Expressway: Case of Bangkok," *Journal of Transportation Engineering*, vol. 141, no. 1, Jan. 2015, Art. no. 05014007, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)TE.1943-5436.0000731](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)TE.1943-5436.0000731).
- [2] S. A. Arhin, A. Gatiba, M. Anderson, B. Manandhar, and M. Ribbisso, "Acceptable Wait Time Models at Transit Bus Stops," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4574–4580, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2966>.
- [3] G. J. Qasim, A. K. Jameel, A. M. Abdulwahab, and A. S. Rajaa, "Estimating a congested road capacity – headway relationship of a multi-lane highway in an urban area based on lane position," *Periodicals of Engineering and Natural Sciences (PEN)*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 1263–1279, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.21533/pen.v8i3.1449>.
- [4] H. T. Zwahlen, E. Oner, and K. R. Suravaram, "Approximated Headway Distributions of Free-Flowing Traffic on Ohio Freeways for Work Zone Traffic Simulations," *Transportation Research Record*, vol. 1999, no. 1, pp. 131–140, Jan. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.3141/1999-14>.
- [5] S. Das, G. Mahapatra, A. K. Maurya, and A. Minhans, "An empirical study of vehicle time headways for different roadway facilities," presented at the 3rd Conference of Transportation Research Group of India (3rd CTRG), Kolkata, India, Dec. 2015.
- [6] N. Hazim, L. Shbeeb, and Z. A. Salem, "Impact of Roadside Fixed Objects in Traffic Conditions," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5428–5433, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3226>.
- [7] M. U. Farooq, A. Ahmed, S. M. Khan, and M. B. Nawaz, "Estimation of Traffic Occupancy using Image Segmentation," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7291–7295, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4218>.
- [8] S. M. Abtahi, M. Tamannaeei, and H. Haghshenash, "Analysis and modeling time headway distributions under heavy traffic flow conditions in the urban highways: case of Isfahan," *Transport*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 375–382, Dec. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.3846/16484142.2011.635694>.
- [9] J. Jang, C. Park, B. Kim, and N. Choi, "Modeling of Time Headway Distribution on Suburban Arterial: Case Study from South Korea," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 16, pp. 240–247, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.04.446>.
- [10] Z. A. Alkaissi, "Analytical Study of Headway Time Distribution on Congested Arterial: A Case Study Palestine Road in Baghdad City," in *Sustainable Solutions for Railways and Transportation Engineering*, Cham, 2019, pp. 85–97, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-01911-2_8.
- [11] S. Das, A. K. Maurya, "Time Headway Analysis for Four-Lane and Two-Lane Roads," *Transportation in Developing Economies*, vol. 3, no. 1, Apr. 2017, Art. no. 9, doi: 10.1007/s40890-017-0039-8.
- [12] A. S. Al-Ghandi, "Modeling vehicle headways for low traffic flows on urban freeways and arterial roadways," in *Transactions on the Built Environment*, vol. 41, WIT Press, 1999, pp. 321–341.
- [13] H. M. Al-Mosawe, D. Alobaydi, and A. Albayati, "Development of Traffic Noise Prediction Model in an Educational Urban Area," *Civil Engineering Journal*, vol. 4, no. 11, pp. 2588–2595, Nov. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-03091183>.
- [14] N. J. Uke and R. C. Thool, "Moving Vehicle Detection for Measuring Traffic Count Using OpenCV," *Journal of Automation and Control Engineering*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 349–352, Dec. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.12720/joace.1.4.349-352>.
- [15] E. R. Khansari, M. Tabibi, and F. M. Nejad, "Studying Non-coaxiality in Non-lane-based Car-following Behavior," *Civil Engineering Journal*, vol. 4, no. 12, pp. 2840–2852, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-03091202>.
- [16] Y. V. Navandar, A. Dhamaniya, and D. A. Patel, "Headway distribution for manually operated tollbooths in India in mixed traffic conditions," *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers - Transport*, vol. 173, no. 1, pp. 30–38, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1680/jtran.17.00138>.
- [17] E. Oner, "Approximated headway distributions for non-signalized and signalized freeway entrance ramps," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 20, pp. 381–389, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.08.044>.
- [18] R. Riccardo and G. Massimiliano, "An Empirical Analysis of Vehicle Time Headways on Rural Two-lane Two-way Roads," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 54, pp. 865–874, Oct. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.802>.
- [19] A. Shoaeb, S. El-Badawy, S. Shawly, and U. E. Shahdah, "Time headway distributions for two-lane two-way roads: case study from Dakahlia Governorate, Egypt," *Innovative Infrastructure Solutions*, vol. 6, no. 3, Jul. 2021, Art. no. 165, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41062-021-00531-y>.
- [20] S. K. Dubey, B. Ponnu, and S. S. Arkatkar, "Time Gap Modeling under Mixed Traffic Condition: A Statistical Analysis," *Journal of Transportation Systems Engineering and Information Technology*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 72–84, Dec. 2012, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1570-6672\(11\)60233-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1570-6672(11)60233-X).
- [21] S. Dey, B. Al-Zahrani, and S. Basloom, "Dagum Distribution: Properties and Different Methods of Estimation," *International Journal of Statistics and Probability*, vol. 6, no. 2, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijsp.v6n2p74>.
- [22] G. Zhang, Y. Wang, H. Wei, and Y. Chen, "Examining Headway Distribution Models with Urban Freeway Loop Event Data," *Transportation Research Record*, vol. 1999, no. 1, pp. 141–149, Jan. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.3141/1999-15>.
- [23] O. Adil, "Using nonparametric Theil's estimator to estimate parameters of a simple linear regression model in the case of small samples," Dec. 2019.
- [24] T. Ako and I. T. Yusuf, "Time Headway and Vehicle Speed Studies of a Road Section in Ilorin, Nigeria," *USEP: Journal of Research Information in Civil Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1031–1041, 2016.
- [25] R. S. Shirazinejad and S. Dissanayake, "Speed Characteristics in Relation to Speed Limit Increase and Its Influence on Driver's Speed Selection Behavior," *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 4, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 1369, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12041369>.

A Power Line Lightning Protection Method for Television and Radio Stations

Quang Trung Le

Engineering and Technology Department
Lilama 2 International Technology College
Dong Nai, Vietnam
qtrungttc2@gmail.com

Huy Anh Quyen

Electrical and Electronics Department
HCMC University of Technology and Education
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
anhqh@hcmute.edu.vn

Trong Nghia Le

Electrical and Electronics Department
HCMC University of Technology and Education
Ho Chi Minh city, Vietnam
trongnghia@hcmute.edu.vn

Trieu Tan Phung

Electrical and Electronics Department
Cao Thang Technical College
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
phungtrieutan@caothang.edu.vn

Hong Hau Pham

Engineering and Technology Department
Lilama 2 International Technology College
Dong Nai, Vietnam
hauph.ute@gmail.com

Received: 13 January 2022 | Revised: 25 March 2022 | Accepted: 1 April 2022

Abstract—The existing research on lightning protection focuses on risk assessment or equipment selection. There has not been any thorough research about lightning protection including risk assessment for a building in order to identify the risks when selecting lightning protection equipment according to technical requirements and cost optimization. The objective of the current paper is to propose a new risk computational method of damages by lightning for a Television and Radio Station (TRS). The new computational method consists of nine steps for identifying two risk indices, human life loss (R_1) and service loss (R_2). If the value of R_1 is higher than the regulatory limit value R_{T1} and the value of R_2 is higher than the regulatory limit value R_{T2} , the damage risks due to lightning are very serious. Therefore, the TRS is necessary to select lightning protection solutions to reduce these risks. In addition, the paper proposes a six-step procedure for selecting and testing surge protective devices. The proposed calculations are then applied to a real TRS in Vietnam, and some testing results are simulated in Matlab-Simulink.

Keywords—risk of damage by lightning; Lightning Protection System (LPS); Surge Protection Measures (SPM); Television and Radio Station (TRS)

I. INTRODUCTION

Power system development can cause many problems. The issue of maintaining and stabilizing the power system when there is a problem is always a topic of interest [1, 2]. There have been many studies regarding the assessment of the risk of damages by lightning to buildings [3, 5-7] and the guidelines

for selecting and installing lightning protection equipment [4, 8, 9]. Based on the above, we propose an overall protection method for surge protective devices on power lines connected to the TRS including risk assessment, equipment selection, and installation for reducing the risks of damages caused by lightning. This overall method is proposed for applying Surge Protective Devices (SPDs) on power lines for a TRS in Vietnam. Based on the computation of the damage values of the TRS, the paper provides a solution for selecting SPDs suitable to the characteristics of the TRS. This research focuses on the risk values about the human life loss (R_1) and service loss (R_2). When these two indices are higher than the regulatory limit values, TRS must be installed with SPDs to reduce the risk of damage by lightning. Besides, the estimation of lightning protection level is performed by simulations in Matlab/Simulink. With the simulation results, it is possible to select the SPDs that satisfy with the real requirements of the TRS with a reasonable investment funding.

II. A NEW COMPUTATION METHOD FOR SELECTING LIGHTNING SURGE PROTECTIVE DEVICES ON POWER LINES

A. The Procedure for Assessing Risk Values for the TRS

This section proposes a new computational method for identifying risk values R_1 and R_2 for a TRS. The method includes nine steps as shown in Figure 1.

Corresponding author: Trieu Tan Phung

Fig. 1. Procedure for assessing the risk values for the TRS.

- Step 1: Determine the parameters of the TRS encompassing height, length, width; height of antenna tower, degree of shielding by the structures around, density of lightning, measures of fire protection, installation method, and length of the power and service lines directly connected to the TRS, and the current lightning protection equipment.
- Step 2: Compute the risk components by the lightning strikes direct and indirect to the TRS. Then, identify risk values R_1 and R_2 .
- Step 3: Collate risk values of the R_1 and R_2 with the R_{T1} and R_{T2} (regulatory limit values R_{T1} and R_{T2} are referenced to IEC 62305-2 [5]). If these risk values are bigger than R_{T1} and R_{T2} , move to the step 4.
- Step 4: Check if the TRS has been installed with Lightning Protection System (LPS) or not. If the TRS has not been installed with LPS, transfer to step 6. If the TRS has been installed with LPS, transfer to Step 5.
- Step 5: Check if the TRS has been installed with Surge Protection Measures (SPM) on the power lines or not. If the TRS has been installed with LPS and SPM but the risk values of the R_1 and R_2 are still higher than R_{T1} and R_{T2} risk values, go to Step 8. If the TRS has not been installed with SPM, go to Step 7.
- Step 6: Select a suitable LPS for installation and go to Step 9.
- Step 7: Select a suitable SPM equipment on the power line for reducing the risk values and go to Step 9.

- Step 8: Select additional SPM equipment and go to Step 9.
- Step 9: Recompute R_1 and R_2 and go back to Step 3.

TABLE I. RECOMMEND MAXIMUM LIGHTNING CURRENT

	Exposure level		
	Low	Medium	High
Environment of building	The building is located in an urban/suburban area.	The building is located in plain.	The building is located in areas where there is high lightning risk by the surrounding environment (pylons or mountainous regions, trees, wet areas, ponds, etc.)
Recommended maximum lightning current (kA)	20	40	65

B. The Procedure for Testing and Installing SPDs

Based the calculated values of R_1 and R_2 , the procedure for selecting and testing SPDs is implemented in 6 steps, shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Procedure for testing and installing SPDs.

- Step 1: Relying on the single-line diagram of power lines connected to the TRS, build a model of the electrical network in Matlab/Simulink including surge currents.
- Step 2: Choose the SPDs for installing on the power lines.
- Step 3: Identify the locations for installing the SPDs on the power lines for Essential Main Switchboard (EMSB) and Main Switchboard (MSB).

- Step 4: Simulate for checking the withstanding of the SPDs on the power lines with wave impulse 8/20µs.
- Step 5: Check the protection voltage value (UP). The UP has to satisfy the requirements in (1) for electrical equipment [9] and in (2) for electronic devices [6]. If these requirements are not satisfied, the procedure goes back to Step 2. If these requirements are satisfied, go to Step 6.

$$U_p \leq (1200 + U_n) \quad (1)$$

$$U_p \leq 1.5U_n \quad (2)$$

- Step 6: The TRS is protected.

III. COMPUTATION FOR A REAL TRS

A. Characteristics of the Real TRS

The studied TRS was built by reinforced concrete in an area with the lightning flash density of 13.7 strikes/km²/year without nearby higher buildings. The distance from the antenna tower to the station is 4m, and the height of the antenna tower is 55m. The length of the power lines connected to the station is 550m, and the telecom line is 960m. LPS is already installed, and the telecom lines are designed with SPM. However, the power lines are not protected by SPM. The TRS needs to calculate the R₁ and R₂ and then select for the SPD to be installed on the power lines

B. Assessing the Damage Risk due to Lightning for the Studied TRS

The followed steps of the proposed method are:

- Step 1: Define the parameters of the TRS.
- Step 2: Compute the risk values of R₁ and R₂. The results are shown in Table III.
- Step 3: The risk value R₂ is higher than the regulatory limit RT2 [5].
- Step 4: Class I LPS is installed in the TRS.
- Step 5: The TRS is not yet installed with SPM on power lines.
- Step 7: Select SPD with LPS class II.
- Step 9: Recomputation of the risk values after installing the SPD. The results are shown in Table IV.

After the SPD installation, the R₁ and R₂ risk values were less than the regulatory limit values [5]. Therefore, the TRS is protected and the risk of damages by lightning is limited. In addition, the effective protection of SPD on the power lines is implemented below.

C. Implementing the Selection and Testing the Protection Level of SPD on the Power Lines

The followed steps of the proposed method are:

- Step 1: Based on the single-line diagram of the power lines connected to the TRS and the electric devices used in the TRS, the distribution network model is built in the Matlab as shown in Figure 3.

TABLE II. TRS PARAMETERS

Parameter	Notation	Value	
Density of ground flash (flashes/km ² /year)	N _g	13.7	
Structure dimensions (m)	L×W×H	12×8×10	
Height of antenna tower t (m)	H _{antenn}	55	
Location factor	C _D	1	
Measures for protection	p _B	0.02	
Coordinated SPDs	P _{EB}	0.01	
Shield at external structure boundary	K _{S1}	1	
Type of floor	r _f	10 ⁻³	
Probability of a dangerous discharge based on structure type	P _s	0.2	
Probability that lightning will cause a shock to animal or human being outside the structure due to touch and step voltage	P _h	0.01	
Measures of protection	P _{TA}	10 ⁻²	
Protection against touch voltages	P _{TU}	10 ⁻²	
Risk of fire	r _f	10 ⁻³	
Fire protection	r _p	0.2	
Shield at internal structure boundary	K _{S2}	1	
Hazard	H _Z	2	
Loss of human life	Due to touch and step voltage	L _T	10 ⁻²
	Due to physical damage	L _F	10 ⁻²
	Due to failure of the internal system	L _O	-
Loss of service	Due to physical damage	L _F	10 ⁻²
	Due to failure of the internal system	L _O	10 ⁻²

TABLE III. RISK VALUES BEFORE SPD INSTALLING

Computed risk values	Regulatory limit risk values	Comparison
R ₁ =4.69×10 ⁻⁶	R _{T1} =10 ⁻³	R ₁ < R _{T1}
R ₂ =0.034	R _{T2} =10 ⁻³	R ₂ > R _{T2}

TABLE IV. RISK VALUES AFTER SPD INSTALLATION

Computed risk values	Regulatory limit risk values	Comparison
R ₁ =7.753×10 ⁻⁸	R _{T1} =10 ⁻⁵	R ₁ < R _{T1}
R ₂ =0.00022	R _{T2} =10 ⁻³	R ₂ < R _{T2}

- Step 2: The SPD class I is selected to be installed at the Essential Main Switchboard (EMSB) with 275V rated voltage and 40kA rated current. Besides, SPD class II is chosen to be installed at the AC Main Switch Board (MSB) with 275V rated voltage and 25kA rated current.
- Step 3: Define the location for installing SPD on the power lines at EMSB and MSB.
- Step 4: Simulate and test the withstanding capacity of the SPD on power lines and the protection voltage of the load. The location of TRS has a lightning density of 13.7 strikes/km²/year, a surge current of 8/20µs and 40kA which is considered before installing the SPD. The protection voltages at the loads are presented in Table V, and their waveforms are presented in Figures 4-5.
- Step 5: From the results (Table V), there are some critical points. The protection voltage value across the AC load is 385.000V and across the DC load is 458V. These voltage values are higher than the tolerable voltage values of 1430V and 72V respectively. These tolerable voltage values are calculated using (1) and (2) with the nominal voltage of the system being 230V for AC load and 48V for DC load. Therefore, TRS needs to install SPD for protecting the electronic devices against the surges on the power lines.

- Step 2: Select the SPD of class I with rated voltage of 275V and rated current of 40kA for installation at the EMSB, the SPD of class II with rated voltage of 275V and rated current of 25kA for installation at the MSB.
- Step 3: The selected SPDs are installed on the power lines at the EMSB and MSB, and their models are added in the simulation network.
- Step 4: Simulate for SPD class I with waveform of 8/20 μ s, surge current of 40kA and SPD class II with waveform of 8/20 μ s, surge current of 25kA. The simulation result with AC load is shown in Table VI and with DC load in Table VII.

Fig. 3. Model of the distribution network in Matlab-Simulink.

TABLE V. SIMULATION RESULTS OF THE PROTECTION VOLTAGE AT LOADS WITHOUT SPD INSTALLED

Amplitude of rated current 8/20 μ s (kA)	Peak of protection voltage across the AC load (V)	Peak of protection voltage across the DC load (V)
40	386.000	459

TABLE VI. PROTECTION VOLTAGE VALUES AT THE AC LOAD AFTER SPD INSTALLATION AT THE EMSB AND MSB

Surge current 8/20 μ s (kA)	Voltage tolerance (%)	SPD class I			SPD class II		
		Rated voltage (V)	Rated current (kA)	Protection voltage across the load (V)	Rated voltage (V)	Rated current (kA)	Protection voltage across the load (V)
40	10	275	40	1779	275	25	1118

Fig. 4. Waveform of protection voltage across the AC load when SPD is not installed.

Fig. 5. Waveform Protection voltage across DC load after SPD installation.

The conclusion after the simulation results with AC load about the protection capacity of SPDs is that the TRS needs to select and install SPD class I with surge current 40kA and SPD class II with surge current 25kA.

After installing the SPD class I, the protection voltage across the DC load is 64V. This voltage value is lower than the limit of 72V. Therefore, the TRS needs to select and install SPD class I with surge current of 40kA.

- Step 5: The final solution is installed with SPD class I with rated voltage of 275V and rated current of 40kA and SPD class II with rated voltage of 275V and rated current of 25kA.
- Step 6: The structure is fully protected from surges on the power line.

Fig. 6. Waveform of the protection voltage across the AC load after the installation of class I and II SPDs.

TABLE VII. PROTECTION VOLTAGE VALUES AT THE DC LOAD AFTER INSTALLING SPDS AT THE EMSB

Rated voltage of SPD class I	Rated current (kA)	Voltage tolerance (%)	Surge current 8/20 μ s (kA)	Protection voltage across the load (V)
275	40	10	40	64

Fig. 7. Waveform of protection voltage across the DC load after the SPD installation.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a new computation method for protecting from lightning propagation on the power lines of a TRS. It involves nine steps for calculating the risk values of human life loss (R1) and service loss (R2) and six steps for selecting and testing the protection level of SPD on the power lines. The effectiveness of this method is tested on a real TRS in Vietnam.

REFERENCES

[1] G. Shahgholian and A. Fattollahi, "Improving Power System Stability Using Transfer Function: A Comparative Analysis," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 1946–1952, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1341>.

[2] D. V. Ngo, K. V. Pham, D. D. Le, K. H. Le, and K. V. Huynh, "Assessing Power System Stability Following Load Changes and Considering Uncertainty," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2758–2763, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1892>.

[3] Z. Janklovics, "The Place And Role Of Power Supply In The Overvoltage Protection And Risk Assessment Of Damages To Telecommunication Sites Due To Lightning Discharges," in *The Second International Telecommunications Energy Special Conference*, Budapest, Hungary, Apr. 1997, pp. 439–446, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TELESC.1997.655748>.

[4] *EN 62305-2:2012 - Protection against lightning - Part 2: Risk management*. SIST, 2012.

[5] *AS / NZS 1768:2007 Lightning Protection - Western Australia*. Western Australia: Department of Mines, Industry Regulation and Safety, 2017.

[6] *Risk assessment of damages to Television and Radio Station due to lightning discharges*. ITU, 1997.

[7] *NFPA 780: Standard for the Installation of Lightning Protection Systems*. Quincy, MA, USA: NFPA, 2020.

[8] *IEC 61643-21-2012 Performance requirements and testing methods, 1.1*. IEC, 2018.

[9] A. Khodadadi, M. H. Nazari, and S. H. Hosseini, "Designing an Optimal Lightning Protection Scheme for Substations Using Shielding Wires," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1595–1599, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1175>.

Load-Frequency Control of Three-Area Interconnected Power Systems with Renewable Energy Sources Using Novel PSO~PID-Like Fuzzy Logic Controllers

Diem-Vuong Doan
Faculty of Control and Automation
Electric Power University
Hanoi, Vietnam
vuongdd@epu.edu.vn

Khoat Nguyen
Faculty of Control and Automation
Electric Power University
Hanoi, Vietnam
nkn.research@gmail.com, khoatnn@epu.edu.vn

Quang-Vinh Thai
Institute of Information Technology
Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology
Hanoi, Vietnam
tqvinh@ioit.ac.vn

Received: 16 March 2022 | Revised: 30 March 2022 | Accepted: 4 April 2022

Abstract—Modern era power systems may include not only traditional primary energy sources like hydro or thermal energy, but also a variety of Renewable Energy (RE) sources such as solar and/or wind power. This leads to the complexity of the electrical networks related to their design and construction as well as system stability and control issues. Considered to be one of the most crucial control issues, Load Frequency Control (LFC), must be continuously improved in order to ensure the control goals. For an interconnected power system, the control purposes are to maintain the net frequency at nominal value, e.g. 50 or 60Hz as well as to ensure that tie-line power flows are stable at scheduled values. This work proposes a novel LFC strategy applying Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) ~ PID – like fuzzy logic-based controllers. PSO is one of the most effective optimization techniques. It is used to optimally determine four scaling factors for each LFC proposed in this study. A three-area power network consisting of a hydraulic station, a non-reheat plant, and a reheat unit along with RE sources such as wind and solar power are taken into consideration. The control performance of the proposed control strategy is compared to those of existing controllers, i.e. Genetic Algorithm (GA), Bacteria Foraging Optimization Algorithm (BFOA), Fractional Order-PID (FPID), and fuzzy logic-based PI controllers for the same interconnected power grid model with various case studies of load changes along with nonlinearities and different RE source conditions. Simulation results implemented in MATLAB/Simulink demonstrate the feasibility and applicability of the proposed control strategy.

Keywords—Load-Frequency Control (LFC); PSO~PID – like fuzzy logic controller; PID controller; RE sources; nonlinearities

Corresponding author: Khoat Nguyen

I. INTRODUCTION

The complexity and vastness of an interconnected power grid with hundreds of parameters needing to be managed have increased the difficulty of network control and stability. It is a fact that one of the most important control problems in power systems is controlling the generation capacity of plants. In [1], the authors proposed an effective integration between an artificial neural network model and a PD-like fuzzy logic inference system to control the frequency in six areas. A controller fuzzy-like PID was designed in [2] to stabilize frequency in an interconnected power system with nonlinearities and uncertainties. Controlling the output power of generating sub-stations such that transient difference in frequency of each region and power source variation between interconnected areas remains within the specified limits and ensuring zero-steady state error is called Load Frequency Control (LFC) [3–4]. The purpose of the authors in [5] is to present LFC using a GA-based robust controller in a multi-area interconnected power system with governor uncertainties. In [6], a robust H^∞ control technique for an islanded micro-grid in the presence of sudden changes in load conditions was proposed. In [7], the authors proposed the optimal sliding control method H^∞ load frequency (SMLFC) for power systems with time delay. A fractional order fuzzy PID is used to stabilize the frequency of the four areas in [8].

Smart grid is becoming an important issue at present and future power system network configuration [9]. New modern grids provide detailed information about the grid in real-time,

fast analysis of errors, and the ability to connect a large number of RE sources to the electrical system [10]. The rapid development of industry and business has caused a significant shortage of energy available in circumstances of excessive use of fossil fuels [11]. Security of sourcing concerns and environmental concerns invested in low-carbon power generation technology consist one of the priorities in the energy program of many countries [12, 13] Therefore, RE generation is a viable option that will not only meet the growing energy needs, but will also protect the environment [14]. The RE source integration poses additional uncertainties and challenges for power systems, since RE sources are discontinuous and their locations are geographically dispersed [15]. Penetration of different RE sources in modern power systems that are interconnected can greatly reduce the inertia of the system. When switching RE sources powering multi-area electrical systems using converters/inverters, such power electronic interfaces will reduce the total inertia of the system and the voltage/frequency stability. Therefore, a sufficient reduction of inertia will be a major limitation of grid connected RE sources. By increasing the penetration of the existing RE sources, the inertia of the interconnected power system may not be sufficient, creating dynamical problems for the stability of the system voltage and frequency, and cause negative effects on the stability/resiliency of the power system [16, 17]. If massive wind generation is faltered due to error, it may harm the power system's operation and lead to load frequency control issues [18]. An interconnected power system with additional RE sources is a practical need in modern life, but it reduces the inertia of the system and increases the frequency oscillations of the regions and at the same time increases the power fluctuations on power transmission lines. These include devices with nonlinear system components such as GDB (Governor Dead Band), GRC (Generation Rate Constraint), time delay in the system, changes of parameters of the electrical equipment, and varying operating loading conditions.

In traditional PID controllers, the controller parameters may not be updated when the system encounters the above problems. Therefore, a PSO~PID - like fuzzy logic – based controller is proposed in this paper to solve the LFC problem. The response results of the system are compared with the results of GA-tuned PI (GA PI) [19], BFOA PI [19], FPID [20], and fuzzy logic based – PI [21] controllers.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF INTERCONNECTED POWER SYSTEMS

The interconnected power system with high RE sources used in this study can be seen in [22]. The studied system comprises 3 areas that are interconnected by likely short transmission lines, called tie-lines. Each interconnected power system consists of several single areas. A single area usually includes a governor, a turbine, a load, and a generator. These elements are connected to be the core of a power plant.

A. Speed Governor

Governors are units used in power systems to sense the frequency bias caused by the load change and cancel it by varying the inputs of the turbines. A governor can be mathematically modeled as:

$$\Delta P_g(s) = \frac{1}{1 + sT_g} (\Delta P_c(s) - \frac{1}{R} f(s)) \quad (1)$$

where R is a speed regulation of the governor and T_g is the time constant of the speed of the governor.

B. Turbine Types

A turbine unit in power systems is used to transform the natural energy, such as the energy from steam or water, into mechanical energy that is supplied to the generator. There are three kinds of commonly used turbines: non-reheat, reheat, and hydraulic turbines, all of which can be modeled by transfer functions.

1) Non – Reheat Turbine

Non-reheat turbines are first-order units. A time delay, denoted by T_{ch} , occurs when switching the valve and turbine torque is produced. The transfer function for the non-reheat turbine is represented as:

$$G_t(s) = \frac{P_t(s)}{P_g(s)} = \frac{1}{1 + sT_{ch}} \quad (2)$$

2) Reheat Turbine

Reheat turbines are modeled as second-order units, since they have different stages. The transfer function of these turbines is:

$$G_t(s) = \frac{P_t(s)}{P_g(s)} = \frac{F_{hp}T_{rh}s + 1}{T_{ch}T_{rh}s^2 + (T_{ch} + T_{rh})s + 1} \quad (3)$$

where T_{rh} and F_{hp} are low pressure reheat time constant and high pressure stage respectively.

3) Hydraulic Turbine

Hydraulic turbines are non-minimum phase units due to the water inertia. In the hydraulic turbine, the water pressure response is opposite to the gate position change at first and recovers after the transient response. Thus, the transfer function of the hydraulic turbine can be described as:

$$G_t(s) = \frac{P_t(s)}{P_g(s)} = \frac{(-T_w s + 1)}{(0.5T_w s + 1)} \quad (4)$$

For stability concern, a transient droop compensation part in the governor is needed for the hydraulic turbine. The transfer function of the transient droop compensation part is given by:

$$G(s) = \frac{(T_r s + 1)}{(T_r \frac{R_i}{R^3} s + 1)} \quad (5)$$

where T_r , T_w and R_i are the reset time of the hydraulic unit and water star time and reset time respectively.

C. Wind Turbine (RE Source)

The wind turbine [23] consists of a turbine-generator shaft mechanism, which is used to convert the rotor rotation into electrical energy. Equation (6) represents the mechanical output of the wind turbine:

$$P_{WT} = \frac{1}{2} \rho A C_p (\lambda, \beta) V_w^3 \quad (6)$$

where λ , ρ , V_w , C_p are tip speed ratio, air density factor (Kg/cu.m), wind speed (m/s), and power coefficient respectively.

For small signal stability of the system, the rate of change of wind power output given in (7) has been considered for assessing the stability of the proposed systems.

$$\Delta P_{WT} = \begin{cases} 0, & V_w < V_{cut-in} \\ 0, & V_w > V_{cut-out} \\ 0, & V_{rated} \leq V_w \leq V_{cut-out} \\ [0.007872V_w^5 & \text{else} \\ -0.23015V_w^4 \\ +1.3256V_w^3 + 11.061V_w^2 \\ -102.2V_w + 2.33]\Delta V_w \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The first-order transfer function model of the wind turbine is:

$$\frac{\Delta P_{wtg}(s)}{\Delta P_{wt}(s)} = \frac{1}{T_{wts}s+1} \quad (8)$$

D. Solar Power (RE Source)

The transfer function model of Solar power [24] is:

$$\frac{\Delta P_{spv}(s)}{\Delta P_{sp}(s)} = \frac{1}{T_{spv}s+1} \quad (9)$$

E. Generator - Load

A generator unit in power systems converts the mechanical power received from the turbine into electrical power. For LFC, we focus on the rotor speed output (frequency of the power systems) of the generator instead of the energy transformation. Since electrical power is hard to store in large amounts, balance has to be maintained between the generated power and the load demand. The mathematical model of generator – load is:

$$\Delta F(s) = \frac{1}{Ms+D} (\Delta P_l(s) - \Delta P_d(s)) \quad (10)$$

where M is the inertia constant of the generator and D is the load damping constant. Figure 1 shows a block diagram of a three-area interconnected power system with RE sources and GDB along with GRC established in Matlab/Simulink.

The control objectives of the LFC in multi-area interconnected power systems are mainly to control the frequency variation, and tie-line power deviation in the areas towards zero while the system has many nonlinear elements, varying operating load conditions, and different loads in RE sources.

Fig. 1. A three-area interconnected power system model with RE sources, GDB, and GRC.

III. DESIGN OF THE PSO~PID FUZZY LOGIC CONTROLLER

PSO~PID - like fuzzy logic – based controllers are applied in each of the three areas. The structure of the proposed controller is shown in Figure 2. The error inputs to the controllers are the respective Area Control Errors (ACE_i) as shown in the following equations:

$$e_1(t) = ACE_1 = B_1\Delta f_1 + \Delta P_{tie} \quad (11)$$

$$e_2(t) = ACE_2 = B_2\Delta f_2 + \Delta P_{tie} \quad (12)$$

$$e_3(t) = ACE_3 = B_3\Delta f_3 + \Delta P_{tie} \quad (13)$$

Fig. 2. The proposed structure of the fuzzy – PID controller

The PID-like fuzzy logic controller has two inputs: error $E(t)$ and derivative of error $DE(t)$. The output of the fuzzy controller u is the control input which must be taken to the governor. Each PID-like fuzzy logic controller designed with ACE , ΔACE as inputs and u as output has membership functions as illustrated in Figures 3 and 4. The fuzzy logic rules are presented in Table I.

Fig. 3. Membership functions of ACE and ΔACE .

Fig. 4. Membership functions of u .

TABLE I. THE FUZZY RULES

		NB	NS	Z	PS	PB
ACE	NB	NB	NB	NB	NS	Z
	NS	NB	NB	NS	Z	PS
	Z	NS	NS	Z	PB	PB
	PS	NS	Z	PS	PB	PB
	PB	Z	PB	PS	PB	PS

In the design of a modern heuristic optimization based controller, the objective function is first defined based on the desired specifications and constraints. Performance criteria usually considered in the control design are the Integral of Time multiplied Absolute Error (ITAE), the Integral of Squared Error (ISE), the Integral of Time multiplied Squared Error (ITSE), and the Integral of Absolute Error (IAE). In this paper, ISE is used as the objective function to optimize K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4 in the PSO - PID - like fuzzy logic – based controller. The optimization technique uses the IATE objective function which is depicted in (14):

$$J = IATE = \int_0^{t_{sim}} \left(|\Delta f_1| + |\Delta f_2| + |\Delta f_3| + \sum_{i,k=1}^3 |\Delta P_{tie\ i,k}| \right) dt \quad (i \neq k) \quad (14)$$

where $\Delta f_1, \Delta f_2,$ and Δf_3 are the system frequency deviations, ΔP_{tie} is the incremental change in tie-line power and t_{sim} is the time range of simulation.

Fig. 5. A typical flowchart of the PSO algorithm.

The objective is to minimize the function J during changing conditions of the operating load with RE sources and GDB and GRC nonlinearities. Applying the objective function in (14), an effective optimization method can be used. In this study, the PSO [25] technique is chosen. PSO is a biological-inspired optimization mechanism. The computational optimization method mimics the activity of finding food of a flock of birds or fish. A typical flowchart of the PSO algorithm is illustrated in Figure 5. In this study, the PSO mechanism is executed with the parameter values indicated in Table II. N , c_1 , c_2 , and w are the population size, two acceleration coefficients, and the inertia weight factor of the PSO respectively. With these parameters, the PSO is able to optimally determine all scaling factors for the PID-like fuzzy logic controllers. Case studies of applying this optimization technique are presented below.

TABLE II. PSO PARAMETER VALUES

Parameter	N	c_1	c_2	w
Value	80	3	2.5	0.8

IV. CASE STUDIES

According to the control idea presented above, the PSO algorithm is employed to find the optimal coefficients K_1 , K_2 , K_3 , K_4 for the PID-based fuzzy logic controller based on the IATE objective function indicated in (14). After executing the PSO, the optimal coefficients given in Table III were obtained. The proposed controller is compared with GA PI [19], BFOA-PI [19], FPID [20], and Fuzzy PI [21] to verify its quality and feasibility. Five different case studies regarding load changes embedded in the 3 areas were considered (Table IV). In each simulation scenario of the load variations, the pulse loads in RE sources also affect the power network (Table IV). The obtained simulation results are shown in Figures 6-10 and Table V.

TABLE III. OPTIMAL FUZZY LOGIC-PID PARAMETERS USING PSO

Coefficient	K_1	K_2	K_3	K_4
Value	800.91	154.46	624.09	709.43

TABLE IV. SIMULATION CASE STUDIES

Case studies	Step load (pu)	Random load (pu)	Pulse load in RE sources (pu)
Case 1	$\Delta P_{d1} = \Delta P_{d2} = \Delta P_{d3} = 0.03$		$\Delta P_{spv} = \Delta P_{wts} = 0.03$
Case 2	$\Delta P_{d1} = \Delta P_{d2} = \Delta P_{d3} = 0.05$		$\Delta P_{spv} = \Delta P_{wts} = 0.03$
Case 3	$\Delta P_{d1} = \Delta P_{d2} = \Delta P_{d3} = 0.05$		$\Delta P_{spv} = \Delta P_{wts} = 0.05$
Case 4		$\Delta P_{d1} = \Delta P_{d2} = 0.05$ $\Delta P_{d3} = 0.05$	$\Delta P_{spv} = \Delta P_{wts} = 0.05$
Case 5		$\Delta P_{d1} = \Delta P_{d2} = 0.08$ $\Delta P_{d3} = 0.08$	$\Delta P_{spv} = \Delta P_{wts} = 0.05$

Fig. 6. Dynamic responses (case 1) in the three areas (a) Δf_1 , (b) Δf_2 , (c) Δf_3 .

TABLE V. IATE OBJECTIVES OF THE CONSIDERED CONTROLLERS

Techniques/parameters	ITAE (pu)	Peak time (s)		
		Δf_1	Δf_2	Δf_3
FPID [19]	68.02	55.25	55.04	59.13
GA PI [8]	67.55	61.16	60.59	60.62
BFOA PI [8]	69.60	60.13	60.34	60.16
Fuzzy PI [20]	62.09	60.88	60.09	60.34
Proposed	53.17	1.32	1.062	0.71

It can obviously be seen that the proposed PID-like fuzzy logic controller exhibits better control performance than the other controllers [19-21]. Major control indexes, such as overshoots and settling times, resulting from the proposed controller outperform the four existing controllers.

Fig. 7. Dynamic responses (case 2) in the three areas (a) Δf_1 , (b) Δf_2 , (c) Δf_3 .

The simulation results shown in Figures 6-10 illustrate that the output response of the frequency deviations in the three areas has settling times of about 20 to 30s, the overshoot is very low and frequency oscillation does not exist when using the proposed controller, proving its optimality. It is clear that when different types of load disturbances exist in the system, the undesirable effects will be minimized under the active capability of the proposed controller. In addition, from Table V, the minimum ITAE value is obtained with the proposed controller (ITAE = 53.17). Consequently, much better system performance in terms of minimum peak times in frequency deviations is achieved. It is extremely significant for the control of an interconnected power system with a huge number of electric equipment operating based strongly on the net

frequency. The shorter the peak times of the frequency deviation are, the better the obtained control quality of the power network can be. These illustrations demonstrate the applicability of the proposed fuzzy logic control strategy, which outperforms the other controllers in the LFC of an interconnected electric power grid, especially when considering uncertainties, nonlinearities, and RE sources.

Fig. 8. Dynamic responses (case 3) in the three areas (a) Δf_1 , (b) Δf_2 , (c) Δf_3 .

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, a novel PSO~PID-like fuzzy logic – based load-frequency control strategy has been proposed for a three – area interconnected power system with various RE sources and GRC and GDB nonlinearities. Such an electric power grid with

embedded various RE sources is highly complicated with different kinds of turbines used for generating stations as well as nonlinear parameters, making the control extremely challenging. It was also demonstrated from the numerical simulation results that the proposed PID-like fuzzy logic LFC controllers applying the PSO technique are completely able to solve the LFC problem, outperforming existing solutions.

practical power networks. In this aspect, the effectiveness of the studied intelligent LFC controllers will come to reality.

Fig. 9. Dynamic responses (case 4) in the three areas (a) Δf_1 , (b) Δf_2 , (c) Δf_3 .

Major control indexes of the proposed system, such as overshoot and settling time, obtained from the proposed LFC strategy were good enough, verifying this control scheme to be feasible and applicable.

Future work raised from this study will concentrate on step-by-step application of the theoretical control methodology to

Fig. 10. Dynamic responses (case 5) in the three areas (a) Δf_1 , (b) Δf_2 , (c) Δf_3 .

APPENDIX

PARAMETERS OF THE THREE AREAS [19]

Area with non-reheat turbine	Value	Area with reheat turbine	Value	Area with hydraulic turbine	Value
M_1 (p.u.s)	10	M_2 (p.u.s)	10	T_w (s)	1
D_1 (p.u./Hz)	1	D_2 (p.u./Hz)	1	T_R (s)	5
T_{ch1} (s)	0.3	T_{ch2} (s)	0.3	F_{hp}	0.3
T_{gl} (s)	0.1	T_{g2} (s)	0.2	T_{rh} (s)	7
R_1 (Hz/p.u.)	0.05	R_2 (Hz/p.u.)	0.05	T_{spv} (s)	1.8
B_1 (p.u./Hz)	21	B_2 (p.u./Hz)	21	T_{ms} (s)	1.5
T_1 (p.u./rad.)	22.6	T_2 (p.u./rad.)	22.6		

REFERENCES

- [1] T.-M.-P. Dao, Y. Wang, and N.-K. Nguyen, "Novel Hybrid Load-Frequency Controller Applying Artificial Intelligence Techniques Integrated with Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage Devices for an Interconnected Electric Power Grid," *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 41, no. 9, pp. 3309–3320, Sep. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-015-1850-3>.
- [2] D. V. Doan, K. Nguyen, and Q. V. Thai, "A Novel Fuzzy Logic Based Load Frequency Control for Multi-Area Interconnected Power Systems," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7522–7529, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4320>.
- [3] A. M. Kassem, "Neural predictive controller of a two-area load frequency control for interconnected power system," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 49–58, Sep. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2010.09.006>.
- [4] U. K. Rout, R. K. Sahu, and S. Panda, "Design and analysis of differential evolution algorithm based automatic generation control for interconnected power system," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 409–421, Sep. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2012.10.010>.
- [5] K. Soleimani and J. Mazloum, "Designing a GA-Based Robust Controller For Load Frequency Control (LFC)," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2633–2639, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1592>.
- [6] E. Pathan, A. A. Bakar, S. A. Zulkifli, M. H. Khan, H. Arshad, and M. Asad, "A Robust Frequency Controller based on Linear Matrix Inequality for a Parallel Islanded Microgrid," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6264–6269, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3769>.
- [7] Y. Sun, Y. Wang, Z. Wei, G. Sun, and X. Wu, "Robust H_∞ load frequency control of multi-area power system with time delay: a sliding mode control approach," *IEEE/CAA Journal of Automatica Sinica*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 610–617, Nov. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JAS.2017.7510649>.
- [8] R. Mohammadikia and M. Aliasghary, "A fractional order fuzzy PID for load frequency control of four-area interconnected power system using biogeography-based optimization," *International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems*, vol. 29, no. 2, 2019, Art. no. e2735, <https://doi.org/10.1002/etep.2735>.
- [9] S. Guner and A. Ozdemir, "Turkish Power System: From conventional past to smart future," in *2nd IEEE PES International Conference and Exhibition on Innovative Smart Grid Technologies*, Manchester, UK, Dec. 2011, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISGTEurope.2011.6162724>.
- [10] J. Dudiak and M. Kolcun, "Integration of renewable energy sources to the power system," in *14th International Conference on Environment and Electrical Engineering*, Krakow, Poland, Dec. 2014, pp. 148–151, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EEEIC.2014.6835854>.
- [11] L. Wang, Y.-F. Lin, and S.-C. Ke, "Stability analysis of an offshore wind farm connected to Taiwan power system using DlgSILENT," in *OCEANS 2014 - TAIPEI*, Taipei, Taiwan, Apr. 2014, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/OCEANS-TAIPEI.2014.6964538>.
- [12] L. F. Ochoa and D. H. Wilson, "Angle constraint active management of distribution networks with wind power," in *IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference Europe*, Gothenburg, Sweden, Oct. 2010, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISGTEUROPE.2010.5638966>.
- [13] A. Abdel-Majeed, R. Viereck, F. Oechsle, M. Braun, and S. Tenbohlen, "Effects of Distributed Generators from Renewable Energy on the Protection System in Distribution Networks," in *46th International Universities' Power Engineering Conference*, Soest, Germany, Sep. 2011, pp. 1–6.
- [14] R. W. Mosobi, T. Chichi, and S. Gao, "Modeling and power quality analysis of integrated renewable energy system," in *Eighteenth National Power Systems Conference*, Guwahati, India, Dec. 2014, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/NPSC.2014.7103806>.
- [15] J. Hossain and A. Mahmud, *Renewable Energy Integration: Challenges and Solutions*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2014.
- [16] H. Bevrani, M. Watanabe, and Y. Mitani, *Power System Monitoring and Control*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2014.
- [17] S. Kufeoglu and M. Lehtonen, "Macroeconomic Assessment of Voltage Sags," *Sustainability*, vol. 8, no. 12, Dec. 2016, Art. no. 1304, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8121304>.
- [18] K. Arora, A. Kumar, V. K. Kamboj, D. Prashar, B. Shrestha, and G. P. Joshi, "Impact of Renewable Energy Sources into Multi Area Multi-Source Load Frequency Control of Interrelated Power System," *Mathematics*, vol. 9, no. 2, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 186, <https://doi.org/10.3390/math9020186>.
- [19] E. S. Ali and S. M. Abd-Elazim, "Bacteria foraging optimization algorithm based load frequency controller for interconnected power system," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 633–638, Mar. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2010.12.022>.
- [20] S. A. Taher, M. Hajiakbari Fini, and S. Falahati Aliabadi, "Fractional order PID controller design for LFC in electric power systems using imperialist competitive algorithm," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 121–135, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2013.07.006>.
- [21] "Load frequency control." <https://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/31514-load-frequency-control> (accessed Apr. 05, 2022).
- [22] T. Kerdphol, F. S. Rahman, and Y. Mitani, "Virtual Inertia Control Application to Enhance Frequency Stability of Interconnected Power Systems with High Renewable Energy Penetration," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 4, Apr. 2018, Art. no. 981, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11040981>.
- [23] A. Kumar and N. V. Srikanth, "Teaching-Learning Optimization Based Adaptive Fuzzy Logic Controller for Frequency Control in an Autonomous Microgrid," *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1942–1949, Dec. 2017.
- [24] A. Annamraju and S. Nandiraju, "Robust Frequency Control in an Autonomous Microgrid: A Two-Stage Adaptive Fuzzy Approach," *Electric Power Components and Systems*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 83–94, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15325008.2018.1432723>.
- [25] D.-T. Nguyen, N.-K. Nguyen, H.-L. Le, and V.-T. Nguyen, "Designing PSO-Based PI-type Fuzzy Logic Controllers: A Typical Application to Load-Frequency Control Strategy of an Interconnected Hydropower System," in *3rd International Conference on Automation, Control and Robots*, Prague, Czech Republic, Jul. 2019, pp. 61–66, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3365265.3365278>.

The Optimal High Heating Value of the Torrefied Coconut Shells

Randell U. Espina
School of Engineering and Architecture
Ateneo de Davao University
Davao City, Philippines
ruespina@addu.edu.ph

Renyl B. Barroca
School of Engineering and Architecture
Ateneo de Davao University
Davao City, Philippines
rbbarroca@addu.edu.ph

Michael Lochinvar S. Abundo
Nanyang Technological University
Singapore
mlsabundo@gmail.com

Received: 21 March 2022 | Revised: 31 March 2022 | Accepted: 4 April 2022

Abstract- Coconut is a biomass resource that is abundant in tropical countries. In 2020, the Philippines planted 347 million coconut trees that produced 14.7 million tons of coconuts. The coconut shells (endocarp) are considered a waste material, which comprise 15.18% of each fruit and account for 2.2 million tons. The calorific value of raw coconut shells is 30.79MJ/kg. When torrefied at 275°C for 30 minutes holding time, the calorific value reached the optimal of 34.37MJ/kg, representing an increase of 11.64%. The mass yield (My) was 90.10% and the energy density was 111.64%, resulting in an energy yield of 100.59%.

Keywords- coconut; shells; torrefaction; downdraft; gasifier; gasification; gas synthesis

I. INTRODUCTION

Herbaceous and woody biomasses are used as feedstocks for biomass power plants to produce electricity. Biomass has the potential to replace fossil fuels as a way of fuel-switching to protect the environment [1]. The Philippines, with a total forest land of 15,805,325 hectares [2], is home to various naturally grown trees, such as the Industrial Tree Plantation Species (ITPS) like the *paraserianthes falcata* [3], coconut, and agricultural products, like bananas, abaca, corn, rice, sugarcane, pineapple, and many others [4, 5]. In 2020, the Philippines produced 820 thousand cubic meters of logs [2] and 66.30 million tons (MT) of various agricultural products and *falcata*. Rice contributed by 19.29 MT, corn by 8.12 MT, sugarcane by 24.40 MT, and coconut by 14.49 MT [5].

The coconut tree, which is considered a woody biomass, grows throughout the humid areas of the tropics. Each tree can have an average of 70 nuts and a maximum of 150 nuts every year, and the shell of each fruit accounts for 15.18% of its mass [6]. In 2020, 14.49 MT of coconut fruits were harvested [4, 5] thus producing about 2.20 MT of coconut shells. These coconut shells are also used as activated carbon furniture. They are typically used for cooking briquettes, either as coconut choir

with high flexural strength [7] or other biomass feedstock. Coconut trees are widely grown and owned by big companies, individuals, or villagers. There are various methods of changing the thermochemical properties of coconut shells like torrefaction, carbonization, pyrolysis, and combustion [8]. Torrefaction is a burning or combusting process where the raw biomass is heated up at a modest temperature from 200°C to 300°C to dry it or convert it to a coal-like material which eventually improves its properties as a biofuel [9]. Moreover, exposing the materials to a moderately high temperature at an expanded holding time enhances their calorific value [10].

Biomass Gasification Power System (BGPS), is a known and efficient biomass power technology [8]. Biomass gasification is claimed to produce fewer greenhouse gases since it recaptures carbon dioxide and reuses other hazardous gases [8, 11]. The energy conversion efficiency of any biomass power technology depends mainly on the characteristics of the biomass feedstock, especially on its calorific value or High Heating Value (HHV) [8, 12]. HHV can be quantified through proximate analysis where the moisture content (%MC), the volatile matter (%VM), the ash content (ASH), and the fixed carbon (%FC) are measured or with the use of a bomb calorimeter. The calorific value can also be calculated through ultimate analysis using the assessed carbon (C), hydrogen (H), nitrogen (N), oxygen (O), and sulfur (S).

Torrefied Coconut Shells (TCS) are not extensively studied for energy production. In [10], the TCS's HHV increased from 18.94MJ/kg to 31.23MJ/kg at 250°C, with 30 minutes of holding time, and a size of 15mm×15mm. This indicates that the torrefaction procedure increased the HHV of coconut shells by 64.89%. Also, authors in [13] showed that the HHV of torrefied coconut leaves improved significantly from 17.95MJ/kg (air-dried) to 27.78MJ/kg (torrefied at 295°C), a 54.76% increase. However, despite the demonstrated improved properties of the TCS, the energy density, mass yield, and

energy yield of the biomass gasification power system utilizing TCS as biomass feedstock is not yet well supported.

To determine if there is an improvement to the calorific value of the coconut shells that are torrefied, the study performed torrefaction to improve the coconut shells' thermochemical properties. Torrefaction is heating without air using a temperature from 200°C to 300°C, while pyrolysis uses heating temperature above 300°C without the presence of air [8, 14, 15]. The study torrefied the coconut shells using an electric furnace/oven and set the temperatures at 200°C, 225°C, 250°C, 275°C, and 300°C, and holding times of 10, 20, and 30 minutes. Before torrefaction, the coconut shells were ground at an average size of 25mm×25mm.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study used an experimental research design where the calorific value or HHV of the TCS was determined using proximate and ultimate analyses. The HHV using proximate analysis was compared to the HHV using ultimate analysis. Figure 1 shows the experimental setup of the torrefaction of the coconut shells. A series of experiments and tests was conducted to determine the impact of torrefaction on the coconut shells' mass yield, energy density, and energy yield when exposed to varying temperatures and residence time. Ensuring the integrity of the experimental results, the samples were sent to the Davao Analytical Laboratory for elemental analysis.

Using a crusher, 15kg of raw coconut shells were ground at approximately 25mm×25mm (see Figure 2). The selected ground coconut shells weighing 1,000 ±0.5%g were placed in a pan for heating at an electric furnace. For each test, the furnace was set to 200°C, 225°C, 250°C, 275°C, and 300°C, for cooking or holding time of 10, 20, and 30min for every temperature setting.

Fig. 1. Torrefaction experimental setup.

Fig. 2. Torrefied coconut shells.

After heating, the TCS weighing 500±0.5%g were placed in cellophane and were sealed (Figure 3). For elemental analysis,

16 samples were sent to the Davao Analytical Laboratory, an accredited analytical lab in Davao City, Philippines. The analytical test results for 1 raw and 15 torrefied shells were considered. The resulting %MC, %VM, %FC, %ASH, and S were used in determining the high heating values and applied in assessing H, C, N, and O.

Fig. 3. Sealed torrefied coconut shells.

III. RESULT ANALYSIS

A. Proximate Analysis Results

The proximate analysis determines the %MC, %ASH, %VM, and %FC of any biomass feedstock [8]. The Davao Analytical Laboratory uses the ASTM D1762-84 Standard Test Method for Chemical Analysis of biomasses to determine %MC, %ASH, %VM, and %FC [16] and gravimetry to determine the S content of TCS. HHV is the amount of heat released per unit mass of any fuel. To find the calorific value or the HHV, the equation:

$$HHV = 354.3 \times \%FC + 170.8 \times \%VM \quad (1)$$

introduced in [17] was used. The result falls not more than 2% relatively to the measured heating values of any biomass feedstock using the bomb calorimeter. Additionally, the calculation can be cross-checked using [18, 19]:

$$HHV = 0.1846 \times \%VM + 0.3525 \times \%FC \quad (2)$$

Table I displays the proximate analyses of the 16 samples, including the HHV. It can be seen that the coconut shells with the lowest HHV are the Raw Coconut Shells (RCS).

TABLE I. PROXIMATE ANALYSIS

Type, Temp (°C), Time (min)	%MC	%ASH	%VM	%FC	HHV (MJ/kg)
BCS 0, 0	11.90	0.88	0.63	86.60	30.790
TCS 200, 10	7.40	0.06	3.40	89.10	32.150
TCS 200, 20	6.80	0.54	3.30	89.30	32.200
TCS 200, 30	6.60	1.70	2.40	89.30	32.050
TCS 225, 10	7.60	0.76	3.10	88.50	31.890
TCS 225, 20	6.50	1.50	6.30	86.70	31.790
TCS225, 30	7.20	0.44	6.20	86.20	31.600
TCS 250, 10	8.00	0.97	5.00	86.00	31.320
TCS 250, 20	4.80	0.43	6.40	88.40	32.410
TCS 250, 30	3.60	1.80	9.90	84.70	31.700
TCS 275, 10	7.50	0.10	6.30	86.10	31.580
TCS 275, 20	5.00	0.20	4.40	90.40	32.780
TCS 275, 30	2.00	0.60	0.66	96.70	34.370
TCS 300, 10	4.70	0.95	2.00	92.40	33.080
TCS 300, 20	2.40	2.80	8.20	86.60	32.080
TCS 300, 30	1.10	0.81	14.20	83.90	32.150

As shown in Figure 4, the optimal HHV is at the temperature of 275°C for holding time of 30min, where the magnitude reached 34.37MJ/kg. At 300°C and holding time of 10min, HHV reduced to 33.08MJ/kg, or by 3.75%. Relatively

to the RCS, the increase was about 11.63%. In [10], the HHV increased by 51.65% when the coconut shells were torrefied at 250°C for a holding time of 15min. Several studies claim that the torrefaction process improves the HHV of biomass feedstock [20].

Fig. 4. HHV of coconut shells.

Figure 5 compares the HHV of coconut shells torrefied at various temperature levels and holding times. At a temperature of 275°C and holding time of 30min, the maximum HHV of 34.37MJ/kg was achieved.

Fig. 5. Torrefied coconut shells proximate analysis.

B. Ultimate Analysis Results

The ultimate analysis determines Carbon (%C), Hydrogen (%H), Nitrogen (%N), Sulfur (%S), and Oxygen (%O) [21]. HHV can be measured using the bomb calorimeter or can be calculated using various correlational equations. In the proximate analysis, the value of HHV was determined with an equation using %VM and %FC. For ultimate analysis, the equation [22, 23]:

$$HHV = 0.341 \times \%C + 1.322 \times \%H + 0.0686 \times \%S - 0.12 \times \%O + \% \times N - 0.0153 \times \%ASH \quad (3)$$

was used. This equation differs from that of [17], since it uses the results of the ultimate analysis parameters and %ASH from the proximate analysis. Note that the calorific value of the biomass is highly dependent on %C and %H.

The Davao Analytical Laboratory and other Chemical Analytical Laboratories do not offer ultimate analysis services, hence correlation equations were used. To determine the %C, the equation espoused by [24, 25] was used:

$$\%C = 2.1877 \times HHV + 5.9068 \quad (4)$$

For the determination of the %H, the equation supported by [19] was used:

$$\%H = 0.059 \times \%FC + 0.060 \times \%VM + 0.010 \times \%ASH \quad (5)$$

The equation introduced in [26] can be used also to determine %H:

$$\%H = ((3.55 \times \%C - 232) \times \%C - HHV + 131 \times \%N + 20600) / (2230 - 51.2 \times \%C) \text{ kJ/kg} \quad (6)$$

Regarding the %N determination, the equation introduced in [27] was used:

$$\%N = 2.6116 \times HHV - 1.1092 \times \%C + 6.3884 \times \%S \quad (7)$$

Though these equations may introduce a minute deviation to the measured values, they are widely used in biomass elemental analyses [19, 20].

Table II lists the ultimate analysis and the HHVs for the RCS and TCS. Temperature and residence time affect the calorific value of the biomass [28]. At 275°C and holding time of 30min, the HHV of the TCS increased to 34.37MJ/kg. Moreover, syngas is highly dependent on H₂ and CO content [28].

TABLE II. COCONUT SHELLS ULTIMATE ANALYSIS

Type, Temp (°C), Time (min)	C (%)	H (%)	N (%)	S (%)	O (%)	HHV _{ULT} (MJ/kg)	HHV _{PROX} (MJ/kg)
BCS 0, 0	73.3	5.2	0.8	0.3	19.7	30.18	30.79
TCS 200, 10	76.2	5.5	0.5	0.2	17.6	31.60	32.15
TCS 200, 20	76.4	5.5	0.6	0.2	16.8	31.88	32.20
TCS 200, 30	76.0	5.4	0.7	0.2	15.9	31.90	32.05
TCS 225, 10	75.7	5.4	0.4	0.2	17.6	31.29	31.89
TCS 225, 20	75.5	5.5	0.9	0.2	16.4	31.90	31.79
TCS 225, 30	75.0	5.5	0.9	0.3	17.9	31.56	31.60
TCS 250, 10	74.4	5.4	0.7	0.2	18.3	30.95	31.32
TCS 250, 20	76.8	5.6	0.9	0.2	16.0	32.61	32.41
TCS 250, 30	75.3	5.6	0.8	0.2	16.3	31.89	31.70
TCS 275, 10	75.0	5.5	0.8	0.2	16.8	30.84	31.58
TCS 275, 20	77.6	5.6	1.0	0.2	13.8	32.51	32.78
TCS 275, 30	81.1	5.8	1.3	0.2	9.8	35.00	34.37
TCS 300, 10	78.3	5.6	1.0	0.2	13.1	32.85	33.08
TCS 300, 20	76.1	5.6	0.9	0.2	15.4	31.98	32.08
TCS 300, 30	76.2	5.8	0.9	0.2	15.1	32.48	32.15

Milne's [27] equation was used for ultimate analysis, while the Cordero's [17] for proximate analysis. Figure 6 shows the graphs and the variation of the HHV using the Milne's equation:

$$HHV = 0.341 \times \%C + 1.322 \times \%H + 0.0686 \times \%S - 0.12 \times \%O + \% \times N - 0.0153 \times \%ASH \quad (8)$$

and provides identical value with:

$$HHV = 354.3 \times \%FC + 170.8 \times \%VM \quad (9)$$

introduced in [17]. Note that the optimal HHV for the two equations is at 275°C and 30min. The mean difference on the HHV using the two equations is only ±0.52% or the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was 0.3388.

Fig. 6. HHV ultimate vs. HHV proximate.

C. Mass Yields, Energy Densities, and Energy Yields

With the HHV known, Mass yield (M_Y), Energy Density (ED), and Energy yield (E_Y %) can be determined. M_Y gauges the amount of the torrefaction process. It provides the portion of the mass retained in the biomass after torrefaction [21]. It is the mass produced as a result of the processing of the biomass and is expressed as the ratio between the mass of the torrefied biomass (M_{torr}) to the mass of the raw biomass (M_{raw}) or $(M_{torr}/M_{raw}) \times 100\%$. ED is the amount or quantity of energy stored in a given biomass, which is expressed mathematically as the proportion between the HHV of the torrefied biomass (HHV_{torr}) to the HHV of the raw biomass (HHV_{raw}) or (HHV_{torr}/HHV_{raw}) [8]. E_Y is the quantity of energy essentially collected from the biomass. It is expressed as the product of the ED and the M_Y or $M_Y \times (HHV_{torr}/HHV_{raw}) \times 100\%$. Though torrefaction causes some losses, it makes biomass to be utilized effectively, especially in energy systems. This loss in energy can be quantified by the E_Y [30]. Table III shows the coconut shells' M_Y , ED, and E_Y . On average, each sample weighed $500 \pm 0.5\%$. After torrefaction, the weight of each sample was reduced by an average of 6.27% and the average moisture content was 5.82%.

Figure 7 shows the graphical presentations of M_Y , ED, and E_Y . As the temperature and holding time increase, the M_Y , the ratio between the mass of the TCS and the mass of the RCS, reduce. This is true, since the mass of the TCS becomes lower than the mass of the RCS as the exposure to a high temperature is lengthened. The process also reduces the %MC. Moreover, the ratio between the TCS and the RCS HHV increases while the M_Y decreases. This increase in the ED is a proof that the calorific value of the coconut shells increases at a reduced moisture content of the biomass.

TABLE III. MASS YIELD, ENERGY DENSITY, AND ENERGY YIELD

Type, Temp (°C), Time (min)	Mass (torr) (g)	Mass (dry) (g)	HHV (MJ/kg)	M_Y (%)	ED (%)	E_Y (%)
BCS 0, 0	500.0	440.5	30.8			
TCS 200, 10	477.5	442.2	32.2	95.5	104.4	99.7
TCS 200, 20	474.5	442.2	32.2	94.9	104.6	99.3
TCS 200, 30	473.5	442.3	32.1	94.7	104.1	98.6
TCS 225, 10	478.5	442.1	31.9	95.7	103.6	99.1
TCS 225, 20	473.0	442.3	31.8	94.6	103.3	97.7
TCS225. 30	476.5	442.2	31.6	95.3	102.6	97.8
TCS 250, 10	480.5	442.1	31.3	96.1	101.7	97.8
TCS 250, 20	464.5	442.2	32.4	92.9	105.3	97.8
TCS 250, 30	458.5	442.0	31.7	91.7	103.0	94.4
TCS 275, 10	478.0	442.2	31.6	95.6	102.6	98.1
TCS 275, 20	465.5	442.2	32.8	93.1	106.5	99.1
TCS 275, 30	450.5	441.5	34.4	90.1	111.6	100.6
TCS 300, 10	464.0	442.2	33.1	92.8	107.4	99.7
TCS 300, 20	452.5	441.6	32.1	90.5	104.2	94.3
TCS 300, 30	446.0	441.1	32.2	89.2	104.4	93.1
Average	469.6	441.9	32.1	93.5	104.6	97.8
Std. Dev.	11.3	0.3	0.8	2.3	2.5	2.2

The product of the M_Y and the ED or the ratio between the products of the mass and HHV of the TCS and RCS is the E_Y . Ideally, the value of the E_Y should be greater than 1 (100%). At a temperature of 275°C and resident time of 30min, the E_Y reached 100.59%. This indicates that the torrefaction process improved the value of biomass.

Fig. 7. Mass yield, energy density, and energy yield.

D. Summary

1) Proximate and Ultimate Analysis

Forest and agricultural resources can be used to produce electricity. One of the available resources is the coconut shell, made at 2.2 MT per year in the Philippines [4, 5, 31]. Its HHV was investigated for the possible use of coconut shells to produce electricity. To improve the HHV of any biomass resource, torrefaction (200°C to 300°C) is a good choice [20]. Coconut shells were torrefied at 200, 225, 250, 275, and 300°C with residence times of 10, 20, and 30min. TCS were sent to an accredited analytical laboratory for proximate analysis. They determined %MC, %VM, %ASH, and %FC using the standard test method for chemical analysis of wood charcoal and other biomasses [8, 16]. The sulfur content (%S) was analyzed using gravimetric analysis. Using (9) [17], the HHV_{prox} of 15

torrefied shells, including the RCS, were determined. The optimal HHV of 34.37MJ/kg was found for shells torrefied at 275°C for 30min. For the ultimate analysis wherein %C, %H, %N, %S, and %O [21], various known equations were used. Though these equations introduced minor deviations to the measured values, they are widely used in the elemental analyses of biomass and other feedstocks [19, 20]. Table IV lists the equations used in solving the HHV using ultimate analytical elements.

TABLE IV. ULTIMATE ANALYSIS EQUATIONS

Element	Equation	Reference
%C	(4)	[24, 25]
%H	(5)	[19]
%N	(7)	[27]
%S	Laboratory test results	Gravimetric
%ASH	Laboratory test results	ASTM D1762-84
%O	$\%O = 100\% - \%C - \%H - \%N - \%S - \%ASH$	[32]

The HHV_{ulti} (ultimate analysis) was found using (3) [22, 23]. Comparing the HHV_{prox} and HHV_{ulti}, the MAE was ± 0.3388 .

2) Mass Yield, Energy Density, and Energy Yield

On average, the M_y , the ratio between the HHV_{torr} and the HHV_{raw}, was 93.51%, this is what remains in TCS after torrefaction [21]. The higher the temperature and the residence time, the higher the reduction in mass hence reducing the M_y . ED, i.e. the ratio between the HHV_{torr} and the HHV_{raw}, is 104.61%. Higher ratio would mean that the TCS had increased their HHV by an immense amount. E_y , i.e. the product of the M_y and the ED, was 97.83%. This is the amount of energy that can be potentially collected from the TCS. At the temperature of 275°C and residence time of 30min, the M_y was 90.10%, and the ED was 111.64% resulting in an E_y of 100.59%.

IV. CONCLUSION

Biomass is a non-fossilized, biodegradable organic substance that can be utilized to supplement other renewable energy technologies and replace fossil fuels. Coconut is woody biomass that grows in abundance in the tropics and is a good alternative energy resource. Ground coconut shells (25mm×25mm) were torrefied to increase their HHV. At 275°C and 30min residence time, the optimal HHV of 34.37MJ/kg was achieved. This suggests an HHV 11.63% higher than the RCS's HHV of 30.79MJ/kg. This result supports the findings of [10, 13]. The computed calorific value or HHV can be determined with high certainty utilizing a combination of laboratory analyses using established test procedures for chemical analysis and correlative equations developed and extensively used. Since the TCS achieved optimal HHV, they reached an E_y of 100.59%. E_y is the product of the M_y at 90.10% and the ED at 111.64%.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported financially by the Ateneo de Davao University, the Office of the President, and the University Research Council. This project is a part of the Biomass Gasification Power System program of the School of Engineering and Architecture of the Ateneo de Davao University.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Naim and T. Mahara, "Fuel Substitution for Energy Saving: A Case Study of Foundry Plant," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3439–3444, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2298>.
- [2] "Philippine Forestry Statistics." <https://forestry.denr.gov.ph/index.php/statistics/philippines-forestry-statistics> (accessed Apr. 05, 2022).
- [3] Forest Management Bureau, "Philippine Forestry Statistics," Department of Environment Natural Resources, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://forestry.denr.gov.ph/index.php/statistics/philippines-forestry-statistics>. [Accessed 7 November 2021].
- [4] "Coconut Statistics." <https://pca.gov.ph/index.php/resources/coconut-statistics> (accessed Apr. 05, 2022).
- [5] "Philippine Statistics Authority | Republic of the Philippines." <https://psa.gov.ph/> (accessed Apr. 05, 2022).
- [6] J. E. G. Van Dam, "Coir processing technologies. Improvement of drying, softening, bleaching and dyeing coir fibre/yarn and printing coir floor coverings," FAO/CFC, Rome, Italy, 2002.
- [7] R. Mudiyo and S. Sudarno, "The Influence of Coconut Fiber on the Compressive and Flexural Strength of Paving Blocks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4702–4705, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3008>.
- [8] P. Basu, *Biomass Gasification and Pyrolysis: Practical Design and Theory*. Burlington, MA, USA: Academic Press, 2010.
- [9] M. Wilk and A. Magdziarz, "Hydrothermal carbonization, torrefaction and slow pyrolysis of *Miscanthus giganteus*," *Energy*, vol. 140, pp. 1292–1304, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.03.031>.
- [10] A. Irawan, L. U. S., and M. D. I. P., "Effect of torrefaction process on the coconut shell energy content for solid fuel," *AIP Conference Proceedings*, vol. 1826, no. 1, Mar. 2017, Art. no. 020010, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4979226>.
- [11] B. V. Babu, "Biomass pyrolysis: a state-of-the-art review," *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining*, vol. 2, no. 5, pp. 393–414, 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.92>.
- [12] A. Bhavanam and R. C. Sastry, "Biomass Gasification processes in downdraft fixed bed reactors: a review," *International Journal of Chemical Engineering and Applications*, vol. 2, no. 6, pp. 425–433, 2011.
- [13] L. D. B. Pestano and W. I. Jose, "Production of Solid Fuel by Torrefaction Using Coconut Leaves as Renewable Biomass," *International Journal of Renewable Energy Development*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 187–197, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.14710/ijred.5.3.187-197>.
- [14] W.-H. Chen and P.-C. Kuo, "A study on torrefaction of various biomass materials and its impact on lignocellulosic structure simulated by a thermogravimetry," *Energy*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 2580–2586, Jun. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2010.02.054>.
- [15] E. Dahlquist, *Technologies for Converting Biomass to Useful Energy: Combustion, Gasification, Pyrolysis, Torrefaction and Fermentation*. Boca Raton, FL, USA: CRC Press, 2013.
- [16] *ASTM D1762-84(2021), Standard Test Method for Chemical Analysis of Wood Charcoal*. West Conshohocken, PA, USA: ASTM International, 2021.
- [17] T. Cordero, F. Marquez, J. Rodriguez-Mirasol, and J. J. Rodriguez, "Predicting heating values of lignocellulosics and carbonaceous materials from proximate analysis," *Fuel*, vol. 80, no. 11, pp. 1567–1571, Sep. 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-2361\(01\)00034-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-2361(01)00034-5).
- [18] S. D. Menon, K. Sampath, and S. S. Kaarthik, "Feasibility studies of coconut shells biomass for downdraft gasification," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 44, pp. 3133–3137, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.02.813>.
- [19] M. Hasan, Y. Haseli, and E. Karadogan, "Correlations to Predict Elemental Compositions and Heating Value of Torrefied Biomass," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 9, Sep. 2018, Art. no. 2443, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11092443>.
- [20] D. R. Nhuchhen and M. T. Afzal, "HHV Predicting Correlations for Torrefied Biomass Using Proximate and Ultimate Analyses,"

- Bioengineering*, vol. 4, no. 1, Mar. 2017, Art. no. 7, <https://doi.org/10.3390/bioengineering4010007>.
- [21] P. Basu, "Torrefaction," in *Biomass Gasification, Pyrolysis and Torrefaction*, Second Edition., San Diego, CA, USA: Academic Press, pp. 87–145.
- [22] T. A. Mamvura and G. Danha, "Biomass torrefaction as an emerging technology to aid in energy production," *Heliyon*, vol. 6, no. 3, Mar. 2020, Art. no. e03531, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e03531>.
- [23] T. Milne, A. H. Brennan, and B. H. Glenn, *Sourcebook of Methods of Analysis for Biomass and Biomass Conversion Processes*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 1990.
- [24] D. L. Klass, *Biomass for Renewable Energy, Fuels, and Chemicals*. San Diego, CA, USA: Academic Press, 1998.
- [25] T. R. Brown and R. C. Brown, *Biorenewable Resources: Engineering New Products from Agriculture*, 2nd ed. Chichester, West Sussex, UK: Wiley-Blackwell, 2014.
- [26] A. Friedl, E. Padouvas, H. Rotter, and K. Varmuza, "Prediction of heating values of biomass fuel from elemental composition," *Analytica Chimica Acta*, vol. 544, no. 1, pp. 191–198, Jul. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2005.01.041>.
- [27] A. Ozyuguran, A. Akturk, and S. Yaman, "Optimal use of condensed parameters of ultimate analysis to predict the calorific value of biomass," *Fuel*, vol. 214, pp. 640–646, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2017.10.082>.
- [28] R. P. Bates and K. Dolle, "Syngas Use in Internal Combustion Engines - A Review," *Advances in Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, 2017, Art. no. 32896.
- [29] T. A. Milne and R. J. Evans, *Biomass Gasifier "Tars": Their Nature, Formation, and Conversion*. Golden, CO, United States: National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 1998.
- [30] P. Basu, *Combustion and Gasification in Fluidized Beds*. Boca Raton, FL, USA: CRC Press, 2006.
- [31] S. A. Bellow, J. O. Agunsoye, J. A. Adebisi, F. O. Kolawole, and S. B. Hassan, "Physical properties of coconut shell nanoparticles," *Kathmandu University Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 63–79, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.3126/kuset.v12i1.21566>.
- [32] S. H. Solangi, A. Q. Jakhrani, K. C. Mukwana, A. R. Jatoi, and M. R. Luhur, "Investigation of Quantity, Quality and Energy Content of Indigenous Sugarcane Trash in Naoshehro Feroze District, Sindh," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3609–3613, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2411>.

Supply Chain Management of Infrastructure Projects in Iraq

Dunya Sabah Jarallah
Civil Engineering Department
College of Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
d.jarallah1101@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Ahmed Mohammed Raof Mahjoob
Civil Engineering Department
College of Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
ahmed.mahjoob@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Received: 11 March 2022 | Revised: 27 March 2022 | Accepted: 28 March 2022

Abstract-Infrastructure projects take a long time, are complex, multidisciplinary, use different materials and products, and have high risk. These characteristics affect the process of supplying materials. The current paper studies the ability to improve the supply chain process and decrease its cost by identifying the factors that affect it. These factors are used as variables in the mathematical model, which is working under uncertain conditions when the consumption rate of materials is not constant. The information used in this model is obtained from Building Information Modeling (BIM) and Geographical Information System (GIS) techniques and the genetic algorithm is utilized to determine the optimal supplier and the quantities of supplies for different materials. The case study used in this research is a concrete bridge. The obtained results show that the cost can decrease by about 28.2% by changing the supplier and the quantity of supplies.

Keywords-Infrastructure projects; supply chain; BIM; GIS

I. INTRODUCTION

Supply chain is crucial for the successful completion of a construction project. Construction supply chains are complex networks with various relationships of resources and product/service logistics, information, and money flows. Furthermore, construction project planning and execution involve numerous participants from various organizations, necessitating intensive communication efforts to complete the project efficiently. A lack of adequate supply management in any construction project leads to cost and time overruns, claims, disputes, and low productivity, all of which can lead to project failure [1-4]. Infrastructure is the backbone of the economy and a necessary input to every economic output. It is critical to a nation's prosperity and the public's health and welfare. Infrastructure's condition has a cascading impact on a nation's economy, impacting business productivity, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment, personal income, and international competitiveness [5]. Governments invest huge amounts of capital in infrastructure projects, and programs. Due to their complexity, large-scale, long duration, high investment, and longitudinal site conditions, infrastructure projects are exposed to higher risks than traditional construction projects [6, 7].

In infrastructure, poor coordination and supply chain management directly impact productivity and performance. Due to the amount of information generated during the life cycle of projects and participants, they need precise regulations. New technologies are transforming the infrastructure design and construction industry. BIM technology provides for the continuous sharing of a digital model that can manage the whole life cycle of a building project. Recent research defines BIM in many ways. BIM is a product or an intelligent digital representation of a collection of structured data which defines a building project. It is a collaborative approach that improves project quality and efficiency by using open standards for information interchange. Another definition of BIM is that it is a facility management tool that provides a trustworthy, verifiable, transparent, and long-lasting knowledge base that can be used to run the facility throughout its life cycle. BIM provides several benefits in the construction industry, such as increased productivity and efficiency, faster production and detailing, better support for automating operations, and less internal coordination errors. The use of BIM effectively integrates the design and construction processes, resulting in better work quality, lower costs and faster project completion [8-12].

The I-BIM (Infrastructure Building Information Modeling), [13-17] is an essential management information system for digital infrastructure processes. It is one of the most modern techniques used in the Architecture, Construction, and Engineering (ACE) sector [18, 19]. It monitors construction activities and manages construction supply chains [20, 21]. In addition to the I-BIM technique, GIS is considered one of the most important techniques in the supply chain. GIS is a framework designed to collect, store, manage, and analyze geographic or spatial data. GIS allows the representation of geospatial data for efficient collection, storage, sharing, and management. The general-purpose geodetic information system can work on the regular PCs, PDAs, and on portable PCs and PDAs, and even the versatile handhelds [22]. The integration of these techniques, will improve the performance of infrastructure [23-32].

II. METHODOLOGY

This paper aims to optimize the use of BIM and GIS in supply chain management for infrastructure projects.

A. Determining the Factors that Affect Infrastructure Project Supply Chain Management

The identified factors emerged from interviews with engineers working in infrastructure projects. The questions and answers are listed in Table I.

TABLE I. INTERVIEWS QUESTIONS AND ANSWERS

Question	Answer
Are the engineers responsible for the purchase process?	No, the contractor is responsible.
Is there a planning process for managing the supply chain before starting the projects?	No, the suppliers are identified according to the price and distance.
Are there some techniques or methods used in management?	No
When the supply process occurs, are there connections between the design and supply process?	Yes, it depends on the design element to supply the materials.
Are there criteria for selecting suppliers except from price?	Price and distance.
How are the import deals conducted?	Before the start of the project.
Are there any material tracking processes?	Yes, the quantity of materials is checked when the storage level becomes zero.
What is the way of the movement of the material on the site? What factors affect the level of inventory on-site?	Not uniform, depends on the work performance.
How do the circumstances surrounding the projects affect the supply process?	They lead to delay the process and stop the projects
Are all quantities of materials supplied at one time?	Depending on the quantity of materials. If the quantity is huge, it will be divided.
Does the time of activity affect the supply process?	Yes, but it did not take in the process.

From Table I, the emerging factors that have important effects are:

- The number of supplies describes the timing of the materials.
- Nature of materials: various types of materials characterize the infrastructure projects. Structural, mechanical, and electrical materials are used. The traditional methods deal with different types of materials in the same way, so we will show how the nature of materials can affect the process of supply chain management while focusing on structural materials.
- Performance in the site of projects: The performance of projects is a factor that cannot be easily calculated and is affected by many other factors. The supply chain affects it directly because the consumption rate of materials will change depending on the performance percentage.
- Deficiency in tracking the projects and incomplete information: infrastructure projects are big, generating huge information. Tracking this information is complicated and leads to incomplete information transfer to the other participants.

- Design changes and absence of coordination.
- Collaboration and obligation between suppliers and the entity responsible for the project.
- Time of activity.

B. Selecting Proper Techniques

The technique most used in supply chain management is GIS, but with the development in the construction industry, BIM has also become popular due to its ability to model and generate information. Both techniques have particular use in the supply chain (Figure 1), but using these techniques individually will not return a benefit, so integration between them is required.

Fig. 1. BIM and GIS benefits in supply chain management.

C. Identifying Control Parameters on the Supply Chain

The most critical control parameter on the supply chain process is cost. The supply chain process includes the following types of cost:

- The cost of ordering, which is connected to the preparation of a supplier's order, including the cost of placing the order and other associated expenses.
- The delivery cost of transporting the materials from the manufacturer to the retailer supplier to the warehouse and then to the project site or from the retailer supplier to the warehouse and then to the project site.
- Purchase cost and holding cost, which are the costs of keeping the materials in the warehouse, the level of inventory of materials in the site, the time of activity, the delivery capacity and performance, and the consumption rate. These main factors generate the mathematical model.

D. Generating the Mathematical Model

The mathematical model improves the supply chain management of infrastructure projects by decreasing the supply cost. The model in [20] is used in the manufacturing industry, and modified in construction projects. It is subject to the following assumptions:

- The total material quantity is known.
- The planning horizon is long.
- There is no lead time or the lead time is constant.

- Consumption rate is not constant, but varies with performance. The performance can be low, medium, or high. Accordingly, the relationship between consumption rate and performance, can be also low, medium, or high. This relationship between performance and consumption will directly affect the inventory level in the site and warehouse, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Material movement when the consumption rate (a) is constant and (b) varies.

The mathematical model is described in (1)-(4):

$$C_o = R * N \quad (1)$$

where C_o is the ordering cost, R the ordering cost rate, and N is the optimal number of deliveries and orders.

$$C_D = N * DD * D_f \quad (2)$$

where C_D represents the delivery cost, DD is the delivery distance from supplier to the site of project, and D_f is the delivery fee per km for each material.

$$C_M = Q * P \quad (3)$$

where C_M is the material cost, Q the quantity of the material, and P the unit price for the material.

$$C_h = \int_0^t Q / N e^{t} dt * C_I \quad (4)$$

where C_h is the holding cost, t the duration of activity (time), and C_I is the inventory cost rate, which is proportional to the inventory level.

The final mathematical model will be:

$$\text{Minimize } Z = C_o + C_D + C_M + C_h \quad (5)$$

subject to:

$$Q/N \leq I \quad Q/N \leq C \quad I \geq CR$$

where C is the capacity of deliveries of each supplier, I is the level of material on site inventory, and CR is the consumption

rate of the materials in site. The first condition means that the quantity of the supply divided by the number of suppliers must be less than the level of product in the site, while the second condition means that the quantity of the supply divided by the number of supplies must be less than the capacity of the supplier in order to avoid supply shortage. The third condition means that the level of the product in the site must be less than the consumption rate in order to avoid work halt.

III. CASE STUDY

Al-Mufraq Bridge is a concrete key infrastructure project in Diyala region. Any change in plans, project halt, difference in cost, change of orders, etc. will not affect only this project, but will cause problems to the people that live in this region. Information regarding this project can be seen in Table II. The project modeling in Revit software can be seen in Figure 3.

TABLE II. AL MUFRAQ BRIDGE INFORMATION

Name	Al-Mufraq Bridge
Location	West of Diyala
Coordinates	33.74222, 44.61383
Project start	2011
Project end	22/4/2014
Project cost	\$17032145 million
Description	The main bridge body length is 450m long and 31m wide, with 4 lobes 150m long and 7m wide. Main and right roads are approximately 2km. The number of piles is 304.
Obstacles	The biggest problem was that the bridge roads were located within private property, so one of the road works was stopped. The works also stopped for days due to the delayed delivery of supply materials.

Fig. 3. (a) Piles, (b) girder, (c) column, (d) the bridge.

TABLE III. INFORMATION ABOUT PILE ELEMENTS FROM BIM-GIS

BIM information				GIS information			User information		
Q (number)	P (\$)	t (months)	I (number)	S (supplier)	D _r (\$/Km)	DD (Km)	R (\$)	CI (\$)	C (number)
304	2500	152	50	S1	1.2	577	30	0.3	2000
	2333			S2	2.5	67	35		750
	2667			S3	2.3	72	30		750
	2667			S4	3.7	182	32		1000
	2333			S5	3.1	215	30		2000
CR	15 piles per month								

Fig. 4. Relationship between Z and N for different pile suppliers by using GA.

TABLE IV. COST OF PILES FOR VARIOUS SUPPLIERS

S	N	Z (\$)
S1	23	794140
S2	44	727310
S3	45	828530
S4	23	844500
S5	24	742750

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The piles are some of the most important elements in the bridge. The piles are responsible for a large part of the cost of the project, so they are used to test the final mathematical model. The information about the bridge is taken from BIM. The information about the location of the project and the suppliers is taken from GIS, as illustrated in Table III. The mathematical model was solved by using the GA in Matlab. The results are illustrated in Table IV and Figure 4. The results show that supplier S2 has the least Z value with N equal to 44

deliveries. This means that the piles should be supplied 44 times to the site to decrease the entire cost and then compare it with the real cost of piles in projects which is 1013333\$. The saving in cost will be 286023\$. The second material considered is the girder (Table V). Its information will be the input for the final mathematical model, which was solved by using the GA in Matlab. The results are illustrated in Table VI and Figure 5.

TABLE V. INFORMATION ABOUT GIRDERS FROM BIM-GIS

Q (M.L)	6616.222				
P (\$)	400	450	450	420	435
S	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
t (months)	2				
I (M.L)	900				
D _r (\$/Km)	1.2	2.5	2.3	3.7	3.1
DD (Km)	577	67	72	182	215
R (\$)	30	35	30	32	30
CI (\$)	0.42				
C	36000	30600	34200	36000	28800
CR	800 M.L per Month				

TABLE VI. COST OF GIRDERS FOR VARIOUS SUPPLIERS

S	N	Z (\$)
S1	8	2654500
S2	9	2981100
S3	9	2981000
S4	9	2787100
S5	8	2885800

The results show that the supplier S1 has the least cost with N=8, which means that the process of supply girders will be conducted 8 times during the construction in order to decrease the whole cost of supply. When it is compared with the real cost (2940000\$), the savings in cost will be 285500\$.

Fig. 5. Relationship between Z and N for different girder suppliers by using GA.

V. CONCLUSION

This study sought the ability to improve the material supply process for infrastructure projects by decreasing the supply cost through selecting the optimal supplier and the optimal number of deliveries. The factors that have effect on the process were identified and were the considered variables of the

mathematical model. BIM and GIS were used to obtain needed information such as quantity, timeline, costs (BIM), and the locations of the project and possible suppliers along with the distance between the suppliers and the projects site (GIS). The mathematical model was solved with the GA. It was found that the supply process is not connected just with the cost of materials or with the distance, but there are other factors that

should be taken into consideration, such as the time of activity, consumption rate, type of materials, design details, and correct information about the project. The traditional methods can't cover the supply process in infrastructure projects and the need to use more modern techniques, such as BIM, GIS, and artificial intelligent is evident.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. RezaHoseini, S. Noori, and S. F. Ghannadpour, "Integrated scheduling of suppliers and multi-project activities for green construction supply chains under uncertainty," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 122, Feb. 2021, Art. no. 103485, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103485>.
- [2] X. Wei, V. Prybutok, and B. Sauter, "Review of supply chain management within project management," *Project Leadership and Society*, vol. 2, Dec. 2021, Art. no. 100013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plas.2021.100013>.
- [3] P. L. Le, W. Elmughrabi, T. M. Dao, and A. Chabaane, "Decision-making in construction logistics and supply chain management: Evolution and future directions," in *7th International Conference on Information Systems, Logistics and Supply Chain*, Lyon, France, Jul. 2018, pp. 646–655.
- [4] Q. Li and A. Liu, "Big Data Driven Supply Chain Management," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 81, pp. 1089–1094, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2019.03.258>.
- [5] *The 2017 Infrastructure Report Card*. Reston, VA, USA: ASCE, 2017.
- [6] J. M. Andric, A.-M. Mahamadu, J. Wang, P. X. W. Zou, and R. Zhong, "The cost performance and causes of overruns in infrastructure development projects in Asia," *Journal of Civil Engineering and Management*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 203–214, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.3846/jcem.2019.8646>.
- [7] K. T. Liew, W. W. Low, K. S. Wong, and S. Y. Wong, "Review: Risk assessment of infrastructure projects on project cost," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 495, Mar. 2019, Art. no. 012088, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/495/1/012088>.
- [8] C. M. Eastman, C. Eastman, P. Teicholz, R. Sacks, and K. Liston, *BIM Handbook: A Guide to Building Information Modeling for Owners, Managers, Designers, Engineers and Contractors*, 2nd ed. New Jersey, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2011.
- [9] *BIM Guide 01 - BIM Overview*. Washington DC, USA: GSA, 2007.
- [10] *National Building Information Modeling Standard Version 1.0-Part 1 Overview, Principles, and Methodologies*. Washington DC, USA: NIBS, 2007.
- [11] C. Eastman, G. Lee, and R. Sacks, "Development of a Knowledge-Rich CAD System for the North American Precast Concrete Industry," in *Annual Conference of the Association for Computer Aided Design In Architecture*, Indianapolis, IN, USA, Oct. 2003, pp. 207–215.
- [12] R. Sacks, B. Dave, L. Koskela, and R. Owen, "Analysis Framework for the Interaction Between Lean Construction and Building Information Modelling," in *17th Annual Conference of the International Group for Lean Construction*, Taipei, Taiwan, Jul. 2009.
- [13] V. Vignali, E. M. Acerra, C. Lantieri, F. Di Vincenzo, G. Piacentini, and S. Pancaldi, "Building information Modelling (BIM) application for an existing road infrastructure," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 128, Aug. 2021, Art. no. 103752, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2021.103752>.
- [14] I. A. Bhatti, A. H. Abdullah, S. Nagapan, N. B. Bhatti, S. Sohu, and A. A. Jhatial, "Implementation of Building Information Modeling (BIM) in Pakistan Construction Industry," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3199–3202, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2145>.
- [15] W. A. Hatem, A. M. Abd, and N. N. Abbas, "Motivation Factors for Adopting Building Information Modeling (BIM) in Iraq," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2668–2672, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1860>.
- [16] T. W. Alvarenga, E. N. da Silva, and L. C. B. de B. Mello, "BIM and Lean Construction: The Evolution Obstacle in the Brazilian Civil Construction Industry," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 1904–1908, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1278>.
- [17] S. Sohu, A. A. Jhatial, K. Ullah, M. T. Lakhari, and J. Shahzaib, "Determining the Critical Success Factors for Highway Construction Projects in Pakistan," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2685–2688, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1866>.
- [18] S. Kubba, "Building Information Modeling (BIM)," in *Handbook of Green Building Design and Construction*, 2nd ed., Oxford, UK: Butterworth-Heinemann, 2017, pp. 227–256.
- [19] A. Baldrich Arago, J. Roig Hernando, F. J. Llovera Saez, and J. Coll Bertran, "Quantity surveying and BIM 5D. Its implementation and analysis based on a case study approach in Spain," *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 44, Dec. 2021, Art. no. 103234, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2021.103234>.
- [20] Y. Deng, V. J. L. Gan, M. Das, J. C. P. Cheng, and C. Anumba, "Integrating 4D BIM and GIS for Construction Supply Chain Management," *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, vol. 145, no. 4, Apr. 2019, Art. no. 04019016, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CO.1943-7862.0001633](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0001633).
- [21] J. Irizarry, E. P. Karan, and F. Jalaei, "Integrating BIM and GIS to improve the visual monitoring of construction supply chain management," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 31, pp. 241–254, May 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2012.12.005>.
- [22] N. Moretti, C. Ellul, F. Re Cecconi, N. Papapiesios, and M. C. Dejacco, "GeoBIM for built environment condition assessment supporting asset management decision making," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 130, Oct. 2021, Art. no. 103859, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2021.103859>.
- [23] R. Abdalla, *Introduction to Geospatial Information and Communication Technology (GeoICT)*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2016.
- [24] Y. Yang *et al.*, "BIM-GIS-DCEs enabled vulnerability assessment of interdependent infrastructures – A case of stormwater drainage-building-road transport Nexus in urban flooding," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 125, May 2021, Art. no. 103626, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2021.103626>.
- [25] M. Marzouk and A. Othman, "Planning utility infrastructure requirements for smart cities using the integration between BIM and GIS," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 57, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 102120, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2020.102120>.
- [26] F. D'Amico, A. Calvi, E. Schiattarella, M. D. Prete, and V. Veraldi, "BIM And GIS Data Integration: A Novel Approach Of Technical/Environmental Decision-Making Process In Transport Infrastructure Design," *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 45, pp. 803–810, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2020.02.090>.
- [27] J. Zhu and P. Wu, "BIM/GIS data integration from the perspective of information flow," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 136, Apr. 2022, Art. no. 104166, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2022.104166>.
- [28] Y. Hong, A. W. A. Hammad, and A. A. Nezhad, "Optimising the implementation of BIM: A 2-stage stochastic programming approach," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 136, Apr. 2022, Art. no. 104170, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2022.104170>.
- [29] A. Z. Sampaio, "Project management in office: BIM implementation," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 196, pp. 840–847, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.12.083>.
- [30] A. Matejov and J. Sestakova, "The Experiences with utilization of BIM in railway infrastructure in Slovak Republic and Czech Republic," *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 55, pp. 1139–1146, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2021.07.084>.
- [31] M. A. van Eldik, F. Vahdatikhaki, J. M. O. dos Santos, M. Visser, and A. Doree, "BIM-based environmental impact assessment for infrastructure design projects," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 120, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 103379, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103379>.
- [32] A. Justo, M. Soilan, A. Sanchez-Rodriguez, and B. Riveiro, "Scan-to-BIM for the infrastructure domain: Generation of IFC-compliant models of road infrastructure assets and semantics using 3D point cloud data," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 127, Jul. 2021, Art. no. 103703, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2021.103703>.

Detecting Mineral Resources and Suggesting a Physical Concentration Flowsheet for Economic Minerals at the Northern Border Region of Saudi Arabia

Mohamed I. Moustafa
Engineering College
Northern Border University
Arar, Saudi Arabia
ismail2251962@yahoo.com

Mohammed A. Tashkandi
Engineering College
Northern Border University
Arar, Saudi Arabia
mohammd.tashkandi@nbu.edu.sa

Anas M. El-Sherif
Engineering College
Northern Border University
Arar, Saudi Arabia
anas.alshareef2@nbu.edu.sa

Received: 8 March 2022 | Revised: 28 March 2022 | Accepted: 5 April 2022

Abstract-There is a limited number of studies on sand deposit resources of Saudi Arabia, which cover nearly the one-third of the area of the country, whereas most of these studies deal with the environmental rather than the mineralogical or mining aspects. In this paper, and in the effort to detect the mineral resources of the Northern Border Region, the surficial Wadi sediments along the Ar'ar-Sakaka road are studied. The deposits of several Wadies (Al Aqra, Shibban al Hanzaliyat, and Arar) are mixed. The sediments of the collected samples are investigated to determine definite areas characterized by a relatively higher content of heavy minerals and a relatively lower content of carbonate minerals that are also friable enough to be investigated by some of the available physical concentration techniques. A large quantity of the surficial deposits, weighing 4.69 tons was collected from the stretch at the investigated area which is 3km long and 1.5km wide. Evaluation of the heavy minerals content, their types, and their ability for concentration and separation, was conducted. A suggested physical concentration flowsheet was concluded for concentrating and separating the contained economic minerals. The average heavy mineral content is 1.55 wt% and the identified economic minerals are magnetite, ilmenite, hematite, goethite, zircon, rutile, anatase, monazite, and xenotime. The other contained heavy minerals include monoclinic pyroxenes (diopside, and augite), monoclinic amphibole (winchite), and muscovite mica. Dolomite and calcite carbonate are also contained. The concluding results ensure that magnetite, zircon, TiO₂ minerals, and monazite are mineable for separation in individual mineral concentrates. Most of the detected economic minerals are recorded in the area for the first time. Monazite, xenotime, and zircon are responsible for some recorded radioactivity in the area.

Keywords-wet gravity concentration; high intensity magnetic separation; heavy liquid separation; X-ray diffraction; scanning electron microscope

I. INTRODUCTION

The sedimentary cover of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia contains many resources of economic importance such as phosphorous and aluminum. The Precambrian rocks of Saudi Arabia are highly dissected by dry valleys that are filled by a wide variety of stream sediments. A thorough survey of the relevant literature indicates that there are no published studies on the economics of stream deposits in Saudi Arabia except for construction materials [1]. Transported (allochthonous) sediments of economic interest are usually referred to by geologist as placer deposits. The fluvial process (river transport) is effective in liberating and transporting gold as well as many heavy minerals and may concentrate them to economic grade [2-4]. Wadi Arar is one of several main Wadies in the Northern Border Region of Saudi Arabia [5]. The mineralogical investigation of the surficial sediments of Wadi Arar reflects the occurrence of some important economic minerals of iron and titanium. In fact, most of friable sand sediments, either placer beach sand, placer sand dunes, stream or wadi sediments, are sources of various economic minerals.

It is important to detect the mineral resources of the Northern Border Region, which is a wide area of almost 112,000km². The investigation will start by covering the deposits along the area located to the right of the high way between Arar and Sakaka. At the end of this area, the deposits

of several Wadies (Al Aqra, Shiban al Hanzaliyat and Arar Wadies) are met and mixed. Therefore, relatively larger amounts of sediments are noticed in the area. However, the amount of materials transported from each Wadi may depend on several variables such as the flow type and the sediment load [6]. Hence, the occurrence of various heavy minerals is expected and some of them may be of economic interest. The determination of the types and contents of the associated economic minerals of these deposits and their mineability for some physical concentration techniques are the main subject of the current study.

II. STUDIED AREA AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

A. The Studied Area

The studied area consists of friable sediments, mainly sand, carbonates, and silt. It is located to the right along the high way between Arar and Sakaka, 12km from Arar, Northern Border Region, until 10km before Talat Ammar, Al Gouf Region, a distance of about 40km. Twenty two samples were taken from the top surficial meter of the deposits along a perpendicular profile, in a distance of 250m to the right of the high way. One sample was taken for each two successive kilometers. Also, about 4.69 tons of the surficial friable sediments were collected from the area located 14km before Talaat Ammar and extending towards Sakaka. The area is about 3km along the high way and has a width of 1.5km to the right of the road (Figure 1). The average depth of the taken sediments ranges between 20 and 30cm.

Fig. 1. The Northern Border Region and the location of the studied area, at the right of the road from Arar to Talaat Ammar.

B. Sampling Techniques

Several techniques and instruments were used in the mineralogical investigation and the physical concentration of the collected samples. They include the following:

- An oven for drying.
- Screening using a 2mm and/or 500 μ size aperture screen to remove trash and/or large sediment fragments.
- A Jones riffle splitter to obtain representative samples of various weights.

- A mechanical shaker and a set of standard sieves, with size apertures of 50, 3, 2, 1, 0.5, 0.25, 0.125, 0.063, and 0.045mm, at a definite adjustment of operating conditions to study the size distribution of the collected samples.
- Heavy liquid separation technique using bromoform (with 2.89gm/cm³ density), separating funnels, glass funnels, fast filtration papers, glass rods, holders, and acetone.
- A binocular microscope for investigating the mineral components of the various samples and also for counting the detected heavy mineral grains.
- The Outotec laboratory high intensity induced roll magnetic separator, Model: MIH (13) 111-5 PHYSEP-INC USA for the differentiation of the different heavy and economic minerals into magnetic and non-magnetic mineral fractions. The separator is adjusted at definite parameters of operating conditions: air gab, feeding rate, rotor speed, and definite splitter position adjustment between the two obtained magnetic and non-magnetic fractions, using definite ampere values.
- A half-size shaking table to investigate the wet gravity concentration of the various economic and heavy minerals at a definite adjustment of operating conditions of feeding rate, feeding pulp density, washing water, and stroke frequency. The recommended deck side slope is in the range of 8-12mm/m and the stroke length is 16mm.
- X-Ray Diffraction (XRD): Philips X-ray generator (PW 3710/31) with automatic sample changer (PW 1775, 21 position) using scintillation counter, Cu-target tube and Ni filter at 40kV and 30mA was used. This instrument is connected with a computer system using the X40 diffraction program and ASTM cards for mineral identification.
- The Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope (ESEM): Highly purified picked mineral grains representing the different heavy minerals were examined by a Philips ESEM model XL 30 equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray unit (EDX). ESEM and EDX analyses were used to investigate the morphological and chemical characteristics of the examined mineral grains.

III. THE IMPORTANCE OF TITANIUM AND ZIRCONIUM MINERALS

Ilmenite is mainly used for the manufacture of titanium dioxide white pigment which is the whitest of all white pigments known today. This pigment is more stable, being entirely unaffected by acids or alkalis that dissolve and destroy other whites. It has the good ability to maintain its visual appearance for a considerable period of time and is stable up to 1800°C. Rutile is mainly used in the manufacture of arc-welding electrodes, and for the production of titanium dioxide electrodes and is used as a coating material in ship-building and other structural steel for which there is a growing demand [7].

Titanium forms extremely hard metallic compounds with carbon, silicon, nitrogen, and boron. These are used as tips for cutting tools and in abrasive stones and wheels. Titanium

dioxide is used as an opacifier in porcelain enamels on steel sheet for refrigerators, sanitaryware, etc. Ceramic titanates are used in the electric industry. Ilmenite and rutile are now extensively used in the paint industry as well as in rubber, plastic, paper, textile, and ceramic industries [8-9].

The three principal zircon-based industries are refractories, foundries, and ceramics. Zircon sand is used in molds and shall cores, while it is becoming important to the foundry market. Due to its chemical inertness, good heat conductivity, high specific gravity, low expansion, good resistance to abrasion, high melting point, and size stability upon heating up to 1,750°C, zircon is an outstanding refractory mineral. Another traditional usage is in the ceramic industry, where the finely milled material is applied to glazes and its high refractive index is utilized to good effect for pacification purposes [10].

Zirconium offers excellent corrosion resistance and, consequently, is widely used in chemical process equipment, reactor vessels, and aerospace engineering. In particular, in the nuclear industry, zirconium in the form of zircaloy has yet to find a competitor as a cladding and structural material in water-cooled, pressurized, and boiling water type nuclear reactors [9].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Treatment of the Collected Samples

For each of the 22 collected samples, the used mineralogical analysis procedure program was:

- Drying of the collected individual samples at 110°C for 1h.
- Screening with a 2mm aperture screen to remove the oversize wt% (Table I).
- Each sample was split to obtain a relatively smaller representative sample of suitable weight.
- Using the relatively smaller representative sample, the slime wt% content was determined using the decantation method. The decantation was repeated several times until the decanted water became clear from any suspended particles. The residue of sediments was dried and weighed. The wt% of slime content was calculated (Table I).
- Each deslimed original sample was subjected to a process of wet gravity concentration to obtain a bulk first tabled concentrate containing most of the contained economic minerals and a considerable portion of other heavy minerals. The grade of the obtained bulk concentrate was low while the recovery for most of the individual economic minerals is very high. The obtained individual tabled concentrates of the treated 22 samples range between 5.6 and 22 wt% (Table I).
- Screening process with a 500 μ size aperture screen was carried out for each individual bulk tabled concentrate to remove some of the oversized calcareous fragments which can affect the feeding rate during the magnetic separation. The wt% of the obtained oversize fraction was calculated (Table I).
- For each obtained undersize fraction (-500 μ), the process of magnetic separation was carried out using successive

current values of 0.05, 0.6, and 1.5A. The weight % for each obtained fraction was calculated (Table I).

- For each obtained individual non-magnetic fraction at 1.5A, wet gravity concentration process was carried out to obtain a second tabled concentrate for each sample. This fraction would contain most of zircon and TiO₂ minerals (rutile and anatase).
- For each obtained second tabled concentrate, the process of heavy liquid separation using bromoform (2.89g/cm³) was carried out.
- Mineral identification and counting: each of the obtained bromoform heavy liquid fractions was investigated under the microscope. A definite representative number of grains, ranging between 750 and 1,000, for each individual heavy fraction were detected and counted (Table I). The grain size of the mineral grains must be considered during the microscopic counting. The weight percent of each mineral in every fraction was calculated using the equation of [11].

Due to the investigation of several samples in Wadi Arar [5], it is known that magnetite is the essential economic mineral in the area, while ilmenite and goethite are considered minor ones. So, it is better to depend on the contents of magnetite, zircon, and rutile in evaluating the investigated samples. Hence, both the obtained magnetic fractions, at 0.05A which contains most of the magnetite content, and the non-magnetic fraction at 1.5A which contains most of zircon and rutile contents, can be used to choose the most suitable sediment region for carrying out the physical concentration experiments. However, both the other two magnetic fractions obtained at 0.6 and 1.5A are composed mainly of pyroxenes, amphiboles, and minor ilmenite, goethite and monazite. Then, the region at the end of the investigated area is considered to be the relatively more enriched with economic minerals (Table I). It also contains a relatively lower content of the calcareous fragments and the most friable sediment grains. This is why the relatively larger bulk sample was collected from this region.

B. The Physical Concentration of the Bulk Large Sample

For the collected larger sample of 4.69 tons, the following steps were carried out:

1) Determination of the +2 mm Oversize Fraction

A representative sample of 2kg was taken from the collected bulk raw sediments. Screening was carried out for the sample using an aperture screen of 2mm. The trash oversize fraction was calculated as 1.93 wt%.

2) Determination of the Grain Size Distribution

A considerable representative sample was taken from the obtained undersize fraction (-2mm) and was treated using the mechanical shaker and a set of sieves with screen aperture sizes of 1, 0.5, 0.25, 0.125, and 0.075mm. Taking into consideration the obtained +2mm oversize fraction into calculation, the various grain size classes are given in Table II.

TABLE I. DIFFERENT MINERALOGICAL TREATMENTS AND COMPONENTS OF THE INVESTIGATED COLLECTED RAW SAMPLES. M=MAGNETIC AND NM=NONMAGNETIC FRACTIONS, FR=FRACTION AND CONC.=CONCENTRATE

Sample	+2mm %	Slime %	First tabled tailing %	First tabled conc. %	Distribution of the magnetic fractions of the first tabled concentrate %					Distribution of the various obtained tabled fractions of the 1.5A nonmagnetic Fr %		Original heavy Frs	Original mineral composition contents of the heavy fractions, %			
					+500 μ	0.05Am	0.6Am	1.5Am	1.5Am	Second tabled tailing	Second tabled conc.		Zircon	Rutile	Pyroxenes	Carbonates
1	7.7	2.1	68.2	22	5.46	0.41	1.15	1.59	13.39	11.10	2.3	0.103	0.046	0.026	0.025	0.006
2	23.9	5.8	60.4	9.9	2.82	0.08	0.66	1.07	5.26	3.94	1.3	0.057	0.027	0.012	0.014	0.004
3	15.1	1.7	72.5	10.7	3.90	0.24	0.37	0.46	5.73	4.57	1.2	0.049	0.023	0.010	0.010	0.005
4	8.5	2	79.2	10.3	3.22	0.32	0.48	0.49	5.80	4.39	1.4	0.064	0.032	0.013	0.015	0.004
5	15.3	0.9	76.3	7.5	1.95	0.39	0.51	0.41	4.25	3.71	0.5	0.016	0.006	0.003	0.004	0.003
6	13.5	1.7	76.8	8	1.74	0.20	0.32	0.44	5.29	4.16	1.1	0.032	0.015	0.007	0.006	0.004
7	32	1.3	54.8	11.9	5.09	0.18	0.35	0.53	5.75	4.53	1.2	0.053	0.023	0.011	0.016	0.003
8	2.3	1.8	82.9	13	2.27	0.39	0.63	0.50	9.21	6.95	2.3	0.097	0.048	0.029	0.014	0.006
9	19.6	1.5	70.9	8	2.54	0.29	0.44	0.42	4.31	3.54	0.8	0.021	0.011	0.004	0.003	0.002
10	8.5	1.4	81.6	8.5	2.24	0.36	0.51	0.49	4.90	3.63	1.3	0.036	0.017	0.008	0.009	0.003
11	4.5	0.7	82.1	12.7	3.58	0.30	0.49	0.62	7.71	5.78	1.9	0.064	0.023	0.011	0.022	0.008
12	3.7	1.4	81.9	13	2.56	0.40	0.59	0.68	8.78	6.64	2.1	0.069	0.035	0.018	0.014	0.003
13	8.2	1.6	78.2	12	1.58	0.33	0.56	0.61	8.91	6.56	2.4	0.071	0.035	0.014	0.015	0.006
14	10.3	1.2	76.6	11.9	3.10	0.45	0.79	0.77	6.78	5.36	1.4	0.053	0.028	0.010	0.011	0.003
15	5.6	1.9	81	11.5	3.08	0.38	0.59	0.51	6.95	5.04	1.9	0.117	0.052	0.024	0.033	0.007
16	1.8	2.2	87.5	8.5	2.18	0.33	0.46	0.43	5.11	4.14	1.0	0.078	0.035	0.016	0.023	0.004
17	2.6	1.8	84.9	10.7	2.38	0.33	0.55	0.55	6.91	5.01	1.9	0.136	0.061	0.027	0.036	0.012
18	0.8	1.5	84	13.7	2.47	0.70	1.19	0.96	8.38	6.54	1.8	0.143	0.071	0.019	0.043	0.010
19	0	1.8	90.3	7.9	1.82	0.35	0.61	0.55	4.56	3.65	0.9	0.100	0.055	0.020	0.017	0.007
20	5.1	1.9	82.1	10.9	2.16	0.40	0.65	0.60	7.09	5.80	1.3	0.085	0.045	0.018	0.017	0.005
21	0.1	1.6	92.7	5.6	1.82	0.20	0.29	0.28	3.00	2.50	0.5	0.044	0.021	0.009	0.011	0.003
22	11.2	1.7	78.4	8.7	2.19	0.25	0.46	0.41	5.39	4.54	0.8	0.079	0.040	0.016	0.016	0.008

3) Determination of Slime Content

A relatively smaller representative sample was taken from the obtained under-size fraction (-2mm) to determine the slime content (-63 μ) of the investigated raw sediments. The process of decantation was carried out for the sample. The residue of sediments was dried and weighed. The calculated slime content is 2 wt% (Figure 2).

TABLE II. VARIOUS GRAIN SIZE CLASSES OF THE STUDIED RAW SEDIMENTS

Items	Grain size classes, mm	Distribution of grain size of raw sediments, wt%
1	+2	1.93
2	+1	0.34
3	+0.5	3.79
4	+0.25	34.81
5	+0.125	39.80
6	+0.075	14.68
7	-0.075	4.65
Total %		100

4) Heavy Mineral Separation with Bromoform Heavy Liquid

Several relatively smaller representative samples were taken from the obtained deslimed fraction. The process of heavy liquid separation using bromoform was carried out for 3 of these representative samples. Their weight ranged between 30 and 38g. The heavy mineral content was determined by

taking the average of the individually obtained heavy bromoform fractions. The determined heavy mineral content of the investigated original raw sediments is 1.55 wt%.

5) Wet Gravity Concentration

A representative technological sample weighing 1290kg was taken from the bulk collected raw sediments (Figure 3(1)) of the area under investigation. The undersize sediment fraction (-2mm sized grains) was subjected to a rougher wet gravity concentration using the shaking table. Several circuits of wet gravity concentration by shaking table were carried out (Figure 2).

a) Rougher Wet Gravity Concentration

Several authors explained the operation principles of shaking tables [12-15]. Several representative raw sand samples were treated individually at different feeding rates, feed pulp densities, and washing water. Each time, a definite sample weight of about 100kg was dried using sunlight and screened using a 2mm aperture screen to remove the oversize fraction (+2mm), and was then subjected to a rougher stage of wet gravity concentration by shaking table (Figure 3(2)). The feeding rate ranged between 80 and 140kg, the feed pulp density ranged between 10 and 19 wt% while the used washing water ranged between 1.4 and 3.2l/m.

Fig. 2. A simplified flowsheet showing the different treatment stages of the studied sediments to obtain the various economic mineral concentrate fractions.

The following parameters represent the concluded optimum adjustment of operating conditions: feeding rate 100kg/h, feeding pulp density 14 wt%, washing water 2.2l/min, stroke length 12mm, and stroke frequency 300rpm, while suitable longitudinal and side slope values were used. The obtained rougher tabled concentrate (C1) weighs 136.79kg and contains 8.15 wt% heavy minerals (HM). The middling (M1) weighs 197.32kg and contains 2.85 HM. The tailings (T1) weighs 955.9kg, and contains 0.4 wt% HM (Table III). These three obtained tabled fractions represent 10.6, 15.3, and 74.1 wt% of the original raw sediments respectively. The obtained rougher tailings were discarded (Figure 2).

For a treated sample with feeding rate of 115kg/h, feed pulp density of 19 wt% and washing water of 1.4 l/min, the obtained tabled tailing (T1a) represents 78 wt% of the treated feed and contains 1 wt% heavy minerals. For another treated sample, with 140kg/h feeding rate, 11 wt% feed pulp density, and 3.1 l/min washing water, the obtained tailings (T1b) represent 81 wt% of the treated feed but contain 0.67 wt% HM. It is obvious that both the used feeding but rates and feed pulp densities are very

important in the recovery of the HM inside the tabled concentrate and lowering their loss in the tabled tailing fraction.

b) Cleaner Wet Gravity Concentration

The three shaking table parameters: feeding rate, feed pulp density, and washing water were recorded to obtain the suitable adjustment of operating conditions. The feeding rate ranged between 40 and 50kg/h, the feed pulp density ranged between 6-10 wt%, and the washing water between 1.65 and 2.75 l/min. Using several adjustments of the operating conditions, C1 and C2 were mixed and treated on several batches by shaking table (Figure 3(3)), and finally three fractions were obtained. The final obtained tabled concentrate C3 weighs 33.87kg and contains 30.44 wt% HM. The final obtained tabled middling M3 weighs 48.8kg and contains 4.66 wt% HM. The final obtained tabled tailings (T3) weighs 77.53 wt%, and contains 1.25 wt% HM Table III. These three fractions represent 21.14, 30.46, and 48.4 wt% of the treated feed respectively. On using the most effective adjustment of operating conditions as 50kg/h

feeding rate, 7.5 wt% feed pulp density, and 2.5 l/min washing water, the obtained tabled tailing (T3a) represents 71 wt% of the treated feed and contains 0.75 wt% of heavy minerals.

Fig. 3. The various treated fractions using the wet gravity concentration by shaking table and the different obtained magnetic and nonmagnetic fractions: (1) the collected raw sand, (2) the rougher tabling of raw sand, (3) the cleaner tabling of the obtained two tabled concentrates, (4) the scavenger tabling of the obtained tabled middling (M1), (5) the scavenger tabling of the obtained two tabled middlings (M1 and M2), (6) the tabling of the non magnetic fraction containing zircon and rutile, (7) the obtained nonmagnetic fraction at 1.5A, (8) the obtained magnetic fraction at 0.05A, (9) the obtained magnetic fraction at 0.3A, (10) the obtained magnetic fraction at 0.6A, and (11) the obtained magnetic fraction at 1.5A.

TABLE III. OBTAINED TABLED FRACTIONS WITH THEIR SYMBOLS, WEIGHTS, HEAVY BROMOFORM FRACTIONS, AND CORRESPONDING ORIGINAL CONTENTS

Item	Depared fraction	Heavy content, %	Original heavy content, %
1	Deslimed raw sediments	1.61	1.55
2	Rougher concentrate	8.15	0.84
3	Rougher middling	2.85	0.43
4	Rougher tailings	0.40	0.29
5	Scavenger concentrate	10.00	0.18
6	Scavenger middling	3.43	0.08
7	Scavenger tailings	1.51	0.16
8	Cleaner concentrate	30.44	0.80
9	Cleaner middling	4.66	0.18
10	Cleaner tailings	1.25	0.075
11	Concentrate of M2+M3	15.13	0.102
12	Tailings of M2+M3	2.83	0.154
13	Concentrate of T2+T3	10.24	0.046
14	Tailings of T2+T3	1.18	0.197
15	Non-magnetic fraction of back magnetic separation	6.09	0.089
16	Tabled non-magnetic tailings	0.96	0.021
17	Tabled non-magnetic zircon and rutile concentrate fraction	30.00	0.08
18	Bulk magnetic fraction of back magnetic separation	70.00	0.81

It was noticed that some of the relatively larger composite grains of grain sizes smaller than 2mm and larger than 0.6mm were increased and were collected within the tabled concentrate (C3). These composite grains were most probably composed of calcareous and sand materials. They were noticed with C1 and C2 but with relatively lower contents. Screening using an aperture screen of 0.6mm was carried out for the obtained C3 concentrate. An oversize (+0.6mm) fraction weighing 4.06kg was obtained (Figure 2). However, these composite grains are not too hard and can be effectively diminished in size using one or two stages of attritioning process at the top of the flowsheet of Figure 2. In this case, the process of the non-economic screening stage using a 0.6mm aperture screen can be neglected.

c) Scavenger Wet Gravity Concentration

The obtained tabled rougher middling (M1) was treated with the shaking table (Figure 3(4)), and 3 tabled fractions were obtained. The tabled concentrate (C2) weighs 23.41kg and contains 10 wt% HM, the tabled middling (M2) weighs 29.98kg and contains 3.43 wt% HM, and the tabled tailings (T2) weighs 143.93kg and contains 1.51 wt% HM (Table III). These three obtained fractions represent 11.86, 15.19, and 72.94 wt% of the treated rougher middling respectively. The parameters of the shaking table were: 75kg/h feeding rate, 13 wt% feed pulp density, 2.1 l/min and washing water.

d) Wet Gravity Concentration of the Obtained Middling and Tailings fractions

Both M2 and M3 middling fractions were mixed and treated by the shaking table (Figure 3(5)) to obtain two fractions: the tabled concentrate (CM2M3) and the tabled tailings (TM2M3). The used shaking table parameters are: 60kg/h feeding rate, 10 wt% feed pulp density, and 1.6 l/min washing water. Also, both T2 and T3 tailings fractions were mixed and treated by the shaking table to obtain two fractions: the tabled concentrate (CT2T3) and the tabled tailings (TT2T3). The used shaking table parameters are: 100kg/h feeding rate, 12 wt% feed pulp density, and 2.2 l/min washing water.

e) Magnetic Separation and Fractionation

To obtain most of the magnetic economic minerals, the process of magnetic separation is suggested due to the scarcity of water in the region. More than 25 wt% of the weight of the obtained final concentrates C3, CM2M3 and CT2T3 are magnetic minerals. Most operating conditions for magnetic separators are explained in [16-17] in order to obtain the most magnetic minerals in only one magnetic fraction of a relatively smaller weight and using only one stage of dry magnetic separation. More efficient wet high intensity magnetic separation can be carried out only for such obtained small magnetic fractions, at various successive current values.

The used operating conditions for the first dry magnetic separation and the fractionated dry magnetic separation are: 10kg/h feeding rate, 140rpm magnetic drum speed, 2mm air gap, and 2A current for the first magnetic separation and are 0.05, 0.3, 0.6 and 1.5 for the successive four current values for the second magnetic separation circuit (Figure 2).

f) *Cleaning Wet Gravity Concentration of Zircon and Rutile Minerals Fraction*

A bulk non-magnetic fraction is obtained by mixing the nonmagnetic fraction obtained from the C3 tabled concentrate at 2A with the non-magnetic fraction of the magnetic separation at 2A of the mixed CM2M3 and CT2T3 tabled fractions in addition to the obtained non-magnetic fraction at 1.5A due to the magnetic separation of the obtained bulk magnetic fraction (Figure 2). Finally, the obtained bulk non-magnetic fraction weighs 31.42kg and contains 4.08 wt% HM (Table III). Most magnetite and goethite were separated and contained in the obtained magnetic fractions. The majority of zircon and rutile mineral grains were contained in the obtained non-magnetic fraction at 1.5A. The specific gravity of zircon mineral grains is 4.6 and that of rutile is 4.2, while most of the associated gangue mineral grains have specific gravities ranging between 3.4 and 2.65. Then, a circuit of wet gravity concentration using shaking tables (Figure 3(6)) was carried out for the aforementioned bulk non-magnetic fraction. Two tabled fractions were obtained, the tabled concentrate, weighing 3.37kg and containing 30 wt% HM and the tabled tailings, weighing 28.05kg and containing 0.96 wt% HM

(Table III). The obtained tabled middlings are recycled with the treated feed. The used shaking table parameters are feeding rate of 40kg/hour, feed pulp density of 5 wt%, and washing water of 2.75 l/min. The mineral composition of the heavy bromoform fractions of the different obtained tabled fractions in addition to the deslimed original raw sand sample are given in Table IV. Using the same stages of concentration and separation of the flowsheet of Figure 2, another sample of 3400kg of the investigated sediments was treated and finally 49.73kg were obtained as bulk magnetic fraction. Due to the back magnetic separation at 2A, two non-magnetic fractions were obtained at 2 and 1.5A weighing 152.43kg and 7.52kg respectively. The bulk magnetic fraction (49.73kg) was treated through four successive stages of magnetic separation at four different successive current values: 0.05, 0.3, 0.6, and 1.5A. The non-magnetic fraction of the magnetic separation stage at 0.05A is considered the feed of the second magnetic separation stage at 0.3A. The nonmagnetic fraction of the last separation stage is the feed of the third magnetic separation stage at 0.6A where the obtained nonmagnetic fraction is the feed of the final four magnetic separation stage at 1.5A.

TABLE IV. HEAVY AND ECONOMIC MINERAL CONTENTS OF THE OBTAINED VARIOUS TABLED FRACTIONS WITH THEIR CORRESPONDING CONTENTS OF THE HEAVY BROMOFORM FRACTION (H Br FR) WEIGHT PERCENTAGES

Fractions	Heavy fractions %.	Mineral components of heavy fractions %								
		Carbonates	Pyroxenes	Goethite	Ilmenite	Rutile	Zircon	Monazite	Magnetite	Quartz
T1	0.40	1.41	86.49	12.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
T1a	1.00	3.10	71.00	6.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	19.5	0.00
T1b	0.67	1.40	91.90	6.70	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
T2	1.51	1.82	91.30	4.07	0.00	1.74	1.09	0.00	0.00	0.00
T3	1.25	0.78	92.70	3.72	0.00	3.45	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
T3a	0.75	1.90	94.2	3.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
T4	0.96	1.38	93.11	4.02	0.00	1.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
M1	2.85	1.64	86.83	3.24	3.83	1.30	1.53	0.00	1.66	0.00
M2	3.43	0.98	91.52	4.89	0.55	0.98	1.08	0.00	0.00	0.00
M3	4.66	0.41	90.04	5.96	0.46	1.03	1.58	0.51	0.00	0.00
CM2M3	15.13	0.60	78.50	13.10	1.30	2.50	3.30	0.70	0.00	0.00
TM2M3	2.83	0.60	98.40	0.70	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.10	0.00	0.00
CT2T3	10.20	1.40	77.30	11.30	0.00	5.00	4.30	0.80	0.00	0.00
TT2T3	1.20	1.50	94.80	2.30	0.00	1.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
C1	8.15	0.816	35.651	11.531	13.69	3.10	7.50	3.03	24.68	0.00
C2	10.00	1.688	80.870	1.80	8.62	1.09	2.18	0.00	3.76	0.00
C3 nm	6.09	1.01	13.32	0.00	0.00	23.29	62.38	0.00	0.00	0.00
Deslimed raw sand	1.61	1.150	59.054	9.371	8.46	2.03	4.48	1.64	13.82	0.00
Light Br. Fr. of raw sand		8.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	91.50

Finally, another four successive magnetic fractions were obtained: at 0.05A, weighing 12.67kg, at 0.3A, weighing 7.58kg, at 0.6A, weighing 12.86kg, and at 1.5A, weighing 9.10kg. The obtained non-magnetic fraction at 1.5A weighs 7.52kg. The final obtained non-magnetic fraction at 1.5A was mixed with the non-magnetic fraction at 2A and a bulk non-magnetic fraction of 159.95kg was obtained and was subjected to wet gravity concentration using the available half-size shaking table. The final tabled zircon and rutile fractions weighing 7.67kg and containing 35 wt% zircon and rutile were obtained.

Each obtained magnetic fraction was mixed with the corresponding obtained one of the treated 1290kg sample (see the flowsheet in Figure 2) along with the two obtained zircon and rutile fractions of the two treated samples, weighing 1290

and 3400kg, and the following obtained five concentrate fractions were obtained: The tabled zircon and rutile fraction, weighing 11.04kg (Figure 3(7)), the magnetic fraction at 0.05A, weighing 17.04kg (Figure 3(8)), the magnetic fraction at 0.3A, weighing 9.58kg (Figure 3(9)), the magnetic fraction at 0.6A, weighing 16.89kg (Figure 3(10)), and the magnetic fraction at 1.5A, weighing 11.59kg (Figure 3(11)).

C. *The Mineralogical Investigation*

Most of the detected heavy and economic minerals are concentrated in relatively finer grain sizes. Almost all of them are present in the undersize fraction of a screen with an aperture of 0.5mm. Most previous studies ensured that heavy minerals are highly concentrated in the relatively finer grain size classes [18-19].

Fig. 4. XRD patterns of the different separated fractions: (1) ferromagnetic fraction separated at 0.05A, (2) magnetic fraction separated at 0.3A, (3) magnetic fraction separated at 0.6A, (4) magnetic fraction separated at 1.5A, (5) heavy bromoform fraction obtained from the separated tabled nonmagnetic fraction at 1.5A. m=magnetite, i=ilmenite, h=hematite, mo=monazite, g=goethite, q=quartz, d=diopside, fd=ferrian diopside, a=augite, do=dolomite, w=winchite, c=calcite, ch=chlorite, z=zircon, r=rutile, and an=anatase.

It was noticed that a considerable portion of quartz grains, present particularly in the finer grain sizes, are stained with reddish to pink materials in addition to the presence of inclusions of opaque inclusions. Therefore, the quartz grains are met in most obtained magnetic fractions, either at 0.05, 0.6, or 1.5A. The heavy silicate minerals are relatively coarser than most economic minerals grains. The grains are subrounded,

rounded to well rounded, elongated more than spherical with highly pitted surfaces. Many of their grains are locked or stained with magnetite fragments or inclusions. They have different color shades of dark green, green, brown, yellowish to opaque. According to the XRD identification, their majority are monoclinic pyroxenes of augite and diopside in addition to minor winchite (monoclinic amphiboles). Most of the magnetite grains are iron black and have a chain structure which is characteristic for the ferromagnetic grains of high magnetic susceptibilities. Most of the grains have relatively finer grain sizes, they are angular to subangular or subrounded and spherical. Many of the grains have cubic octahedron crystals. Several grains are stained or locked with small parts of silicate minerals, most probably ferrian diopside. The identified XRD pattern of a sample of the obtained 0.05A magnetic fraction is given in Figure 4(1). The presence of ilmenite and hematite in subordinate contents is noticed. The essential line of ferrian diopside is also given in the pattern. The identified mineral patterns of magnetite, ilmenite, and hematite are in accordance with the ASTM Cards 86-1355, 89-2811, and 13-0534 respectively. It seems that individual ferriilmenite grains or ilmenite exsolved intergrowth with magnetite are present, in addition to the martitization of some magnetite grains. It was noticed that for most of the obtained magnetic fractions of various different samples of the same studied area, the same mineral can be identified by more than one ASTM cards. For example, magnetite can be identified with the ASTM cards No. 86-1355, 086-1340, 75-1609, or 19-629. This may reflect the diversity of magnetite grains with respect to the source area, grain mineral chemistry, exsolution, inclusions or also the types of associated minerals in the identified sample. The EDX analysis of an area of a sample from the obtained magnetite fraction at 0.05A is shown in Figure 5(1). Both K and Al are related to the presence of minor muscovite in the ferromagnetic fraction.

Fig. 5. EDX chemical analyses of the different obtained economic minerals: (1) an area chemical analysis of the ferromagnetic fraction separated at 0.05A, (2) a spot chemical analysis of a hematite grain separated at 0.3A, (3) a spot chemical analysis of an ilmenite grain separated at 0.3A, (4) a spot chemical analysis of a most probably chromspinell grain separated at 0.3A.

The detected ilmenite grains are angular to subangular of grey color with bluish tints. The XRD pattern of a sample of the obtained magnetic fraction at 0.3A is shown in Figure 4(2). The fraction is composed mainly of quartz, diopside, augite, ilmenite, and hematite, in accordance with the ASTM Cards 89-8936, 082-0460, 24-0203, 003-0781, and 013-0534. Minor portions of winchite, chlorite, and kaolinite are also noticed in the pattern. The EDX analyses of a hematite and ilmenite individual grains in the obtained fraction are shown in Figure 5(2)-(3). The EDX analysis of one of the detected grains identified under the binocular microscope as pyroxene, gives the chemical analysis of most probably Cr-spinel (Figure 5(4)).

In the obtained magnetic fraction at 0.6A, monazite and goethite are detected. Most of monazite grains are rounded to well rounded, of yellowish to pale yellowish color and have relatively finer grain sizes. The XRD pattern of the fraction reflects its composition of quartz, diopside, goethite, and monazite (Figure 4(3)), in accordance with the ASTM cards 79-1906, 71-1494, 17-0536, and 11-556. The EDX analysis of two individual grains, one for monazite and one for xenotime are shown in Figure 6(1)-(2). In fact, the second grain was thought to be monazite or magnetic zircon. It is well rounded elongated, colorless with pale yellowish tint color. The chemical analysis of the first monazite grain reflects the composition of rare earth elements, essentially Ce, La, Nd, Pr, Sm, and Gd, phosphate in addition to Ca, Th, and U silicates. Also, Fe, Al, Mg and K are recorded.

Fig. 6. EDX chemical analyses of the different obtained economic minerals: (1) spot chemical analysis of a monazite grain separated at 0.3A, (2) spot chemical analysis of a xenotime grain separated at 0.3A, (3) spot chemical analysis of a zircon grain separated as nonmagnetic at 1.5A, and (4) spot chemical analysis of a rutile grain separated as non-magnetic at 1.5A.

It is known that Th and U are incorporated by two exchange mechanisms in monazite and xenotime [20-27]: The brabantite exchange: $(Th, U)^{4+} Ca^{2+} = 2REE^{3+}$ and the huttonite exchange: $(Th, U)^{4+} Si^{4+} = REE^{3+} P^{5+}$. It is obvious that the detected monazite is not homogeneous but contains exsolved

intergrown with both huttonite and brabantite. The chemical analysis of xenotime reflects the composition of Y, P and some heavy rare earths: Er and Yb. Due to the presence of these radioactive minerals, the Water Quality Index (WQI) and the Irrigation Water Quality (IWQ) of the groundwater in the area can help us determine the quality and drinkability of this water [28-29]. The XRD pattern of a representative sample of the magnetic fraction obtained at 1.5A gives the mineral composition of ferrian diopside, quartz, goethite, dolomite and winchite (Figure 4(4)). These minerals are in accordance with the ASTM cards 83-0102, 78-2315, 08-0097, 34-0517, and 020-1390. The goethite grains are minor in the fraction, and have brownish, reddish, yellowish to grayish opaque color.

The XRD pattern of the heavy bromoform fraction of the tabled non-magnetic fraction at 1.5A reflects the composition of zircon, rutile, anatase in addition to diopside and calcite (Figure 4(5)), in accordance with the ASTM Cards 81-0588, 72, 1148, 02-0387, 75-1092, and 5-586. The EDX analysis of two individual grains, one for zircon and the one for rutile are shown in Figure 6(3)-(4). The majority of zircon grains are prismatic, elongated, and spherical. The grains are mainly colorless with a considerable number stained with pink material. The majority of rutile grains have black, brown, red to dark-red colors. The grains are mainly elongated subangular to subrounded in shapes. Several grains are very fine acicular prismatic. The detected anatase grains are bluish in color, relatively coarser than rutile.

Virtually, it is the first time such a study is applied to the fraiible sediments of the Northern Border Region for economic mineral identification and their mineability of concentration and separation. The presence of zircon and rutile was ensured in addition to the other iron-bearing minerals. The suggested separation flowsheet of the different recorded economic minerals will be a guide for their industrial exploitation. In fact, there are no previous similar works, neither for economic mineral identification nor for their separation, except that of [5] for economic mineral identification of one of the Wadies extended in the present area where the concluded content of total economic minerals was very low and most of the studied sediment locations were inside the Arar city. Also, not all the recorded minerals in the present study were detected in [5].

V. CONCLUSIONS

The detected heavy and economic minerals were recorded for the first time in the studied area. Most of the recorded heavy minerals are totally concentrated in relatively fine grain sizes, finer than 500μ . On the other hand, the majority of the detected economic minerals have grain sizes finer than 250μ . The calculated original heavy mineral content equals to 1.55 wt%. The majority of heavy minerals are monoclinic pyroxene, mainly augite and diopside, in addition to minor monoclinic amphibole, mainly winchite. The identified economic minerals are magnetite (Fe_3O_4), ilmenite ($FeTiO_3$), goethite ($FeOOH$), zircon ($ZrSiO_4$), rutile (TiO_2), anatase (TiO_2), monazite [$(Ce, La, Nd)PO_4$], and xenotime (YPO_4). The detected monazite is not homogeneous, it contains exsolved intergrowths of huttonite and brabantite in addition to several other light rare earth elements. The detected xenotime contains the heavy rare earth elements Er and Yb. Hematite (Fe_2O_3) is also recorded

but it may be composite with the martite magnetite or with the ferriilmeneite. The calculated original grades of the detected economic minerals are 0.21 wt% magnetite, 0.15 wt% goethite, 0.13 wt% ilmenite, 0.07 wt% zircon, 0.03 wt% rutile, and 0.025 wt% monazite. Anatase is included within rutile content while xenotime is included within monazite content.

Most of these economic minerals can be easily concentrated and separated in acceptable grades and recoveries. The magnetite can be obtained inside an individual magnetic ferromagnetic fraction using the available dry magnetic separator. On using a wet low intensity magnetic separator, the grade of the obtained concentrate can be increased through one or two stages of separation. Most of zircon and rutile mineral content is obtained in an individual non-magnetic fraction. The associated minerals have specific gravities ranging between 3.4 and 2.65. Both these two economic mineral concentrates can be easily upgraded using the wet gravity concentration by spirals and then subjected to a circuit of the high tension electrostatic separation, where finally rutile is obtained as conductor while zircon is obtained as non-conductor.

Most of the contained ilmenite is obtained in a definite magnetic fraction associated with pyroxenes, amphiboles, and quartz. Then, using both of the wet gravity concentration and/or rare earth roll magnetic separation, ilmenite can be obtained in an individual concentrate.

Goethite and monazite are obtained inside a magnetic fraction by a relatively greater magnetic field. They are associated with pyroxenes and quartz. Then, using wet gravity concentration and electrostatic separation, goethite can be obtained as conductor while monazite is obtained as non-conductor.

As a final conclusion, the presence of zircon, monazite, and xenotime in association with the iron-containing minerals in addition to the major quartz mineral grains, which are stained/coated with iron oxides may lead to the absorption of some radioactive elements on the grain surfaces of the associated minerals. If these three radioactive minerals are represented in relatively higher percentages in some locations, care must be taken in using the most upper surficial deposits in building or agriculture.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to acknowledge the approval and the support of this research study by the grant No. IF_2020_4448 from the Deanship of Scientific Research in Northern Border University (N.B.U.), Arar, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. M. Al-Safarjalani, *Placer gold deposits in the Hofuf Formation The Eastern Province of Saudi Arabia*. Al-Ahsa, Saudi Arabia: King Faisal University, 2004.
- [2] S. D. Bussey, P. M. Taufen, B. J. Suchomei, and M. Ward, "Soil and stream sediment geochemical dispersion over the Bell Springs deposit, Hog Ranch Mine, Washoe County, Nevada," *Journal of Geochemical Exploration*, vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 217–234, Apr. 1993, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0375-6742\(93\)90067-V](https://doi.org/10.1016/0375-6742(93)90067-V).
- [3] J. B. Seeley and T. J. Senden, "Alluvial gold in Kalimantan, Indonesia: A colloidal origin?," *Journal of Geochemical Exploration*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 457–478, Mar. 1994, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0375-6742\(94\)90036-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0375-6742(94)90036-1).
- [4] J. V. Tingley and S. B. Castor, "Stream sediment exploration for gold and silver in Nevada — application of an old prospecting method using modern analytical techniques," *Journal of Geochemical Exploration*, vol. 66, no. 1, pp. 1–16, Jul. 1999, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0375-6742\(99\)00013-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0375-6742(99)00013-8).
- [5] M. I. Moustafa, M. I. A. Shariah, and M. S. Aljuhani, "Mineralogical Investigation of Economic Minerals Content in Wadi Arar, Northern Border Region, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia," *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, vol. 10, no. 36, pp. 1–29, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.17485/ijst/2017/v10i36/167747>.
- [6] A. A. Mahessar *et al.*, "Sediment Transport Dynamics in the Upper Nara Canal Off-taking from Sukkur Barrage of Indus River," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6563–6569, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3924>.
- [7] R. K. Sinha, *Industrial Minerals*. New Delhi, India: Oxford & IBH, 1982.
- [8] M. I. Moustafa, "Investigations of some physical properties of zircon and rutile to prepare high purity mineral concentrates from black sand deposits, Rosetta, Egypt," M.S. thesis, Mansoura University, Mansoura, Egypt, 1995.
- [9] N. P. H. Padmanabhan, T. Sreenivas, and N. K. Rao, "Processing of Ores of Titanium, Zirconium, Hafnium, Niobium, Tantalum, Molybdenum, Rhenium, and Tungsten: International Trends and the Indian Scene," *High Temperature Materials and Processes*, vol. 9, no. 2–4, pp. 217–248, Jul. 1990, <https://doi.org/10.1515/HTMP.1990.9.2-4.217>.
- [10] V. S. Bashir, "Zircon sand and its application in ceramic industry," *Saket Industrial Digest*, vol. 2, no. 6, pp. 23–28, 1996.
- [11] N. M. Strakhov, G. I. Bushinskii, and L. V. Pustovalov, *Metody Izocheniya Ocadochnykh Porod, Tom I (Methods of Studying Sedimentary Rocks)*. Moscow, Russia: Gosgeotekhnizdat, 1957.
- [12] B. A. Wills, "Gravity Concentration Part 1," *Mining Magazine*, pp. 325–332, Oct. 1984.
- [13] R. O. Burt, *Gravity concentration technology*. Netherlands, Amsterdam: Elsevier, 1984.
- [14] B. A. Wills, *Mineral Processing Technology*, 5th ed. Oxford, UK: Pergamon Press, 1992.
- [15] M. Dieye, M. M. Thiam, A. Geneyton, and M. Gueye, "Monazite Recovery by Magnetic and Gravity Separation of Medium Grade Zircon Concentrate from Senegalese Heavy Mineral Sands Deposit," *Journal of Minerals and Materials Characterization and Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 590–608, Nov. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.4236/jmmce.2021.96038>.
- [16] N. M. Hammoud, "Physical and chemical properties of some Egyptian beach economic minerals in relation to their concentration problems," Ph.D. dissertation, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt, 1973.
- [17] M. I. Moustafa, "Mineralogy and beneficiation of some economic minerals in the Egyptian black sands," Ph.D. dissertation, Mansoura University, Mansoura, Egypt, 1999.
- [18] M. A. M. Alghamdi and A. A. E. Hegazy, "Physical Properties of Soil Sediment in Wadiarar, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia," *International Journal of Civil Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 5, pp. 1–8, 2013.
- [19] M. I. Moustafa, "Remarks on the physical, mineralogical features and amenability of the northern coast of Egypt," *Egyptian Mineralogist*, vol. 12, pp. 29–49, 2000.
- [20] C. M. Gramaccioli and T. V. Segalstad, "A uranium- and thorium-rich monazite from a South-Alpine pegmatite at Piona, Italy," *American Mineralogist*, vol. 63, no. 7–8, pp. 757–761, Aug. 1978.
- [21] G. Franz, G. Andrehs, and D. Rhede, "Crystal chemistry of monazite and xenotime from Saxothuringian-Moldanubian metapelites, NE Bavaria, Germany," *European Journal of Mineralogy*, vol. 8, pp. 1097–1118, Oct. 1996, <https://doi.org/10.1127/ejm/8/5/1097>.
- [22] B. van Emden, M. R. Thorner, J. Graham, and F. J. Lincoln, "The incorporation of actinides in monazite and xenotime from Placer deposits in Western Australia," *Canadian Mineralogist*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 95–104, 1997.
- [23] H.-J. Forster, "The chemical composition of REE-Y-Th-U-rich accessory minerals in peraluminous granites of the Erzgebirge-

- Fichtelgebirge region, Germany, Part I: The monazite-(Ce)-brabantite solid solution series," *American Mineralogist*, vol. 83, no. 3–4, pp. 259–272, Mar. 1998, <https://doi.org/10.2138/am-1998-3-409>.
- [24] H.-J. Foerster, "The chemical composition of REE-Y-Th-U-rich accessory minerals in peraluminous granites of the Erzgebirge-Fichtelgebirge region, Germany; Part II, Xenotime," *American Mineralogist*, vol. 83, no. 11-12_Part_1, pp. 1302–1315, Dec. 1998, <https://doi.org/10.2138/am-1998-11-1219>.
- [25] D. Rose, "Brabantite. Ca Th (PO₄)₂, a new mineral of the monazite group," *Neues Jahrbuch für Mineralogie*, vol. 6, pp. 247–257, 1980.
- [26] A.-M. Seydoux-Guillaume, R. Wirth, W. Heinrich, and J.-M. Montel, "Experimental determination of Thorium partitioning between monazite and xenotime using analytical electron microscopy and X-ray diffraction Rietveld analysis," *European Journal of Mineralogy*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 869–878, Sep. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1127/0935-1221/2002/0014-0869>.
- [27] M. I. Moustafa, "Chemistry and Origin of Enigmatic Monazite and Chevkinite/Perrierite in the Egyptian Black Beach Sand," *Resource Geology*, vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 271–287, 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-3928.2010.00132.x>.
- [28] K. Praveen and L. B. Roy, "Assessment of Groundwater Quality Using Water Quality Indices: A Case Study of Paliganj Distributary, Bihar, India," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8199–8203, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4696>.
- [29] N. Kumar, A. A. Mahessar, S. A. Memon, K. Ansari, and A. L. Qureshi, "Impact Assessment of Groundwater Quality using WQI and Geospatial tools: A Case Study of Islamkot, Tharparkar, Pakistan," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5288–5294, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3289>.

Fusion Machine Learning Strategies for Multi-modal Sensor-based Hand Gesture Recognition

Huong-Giang Doan
Control and Automation Faculty
Electric Power University
Hanoi, Vietnam
giangdt@epu.edu.vn

Ngoc-Trung Nguyen
Control and Automation Faculty
Electric Power University
Hanoi, Vietnam
trungnn@epu.edu.vn

Received: 14 March 2022 | Revised: 26 March 2022 | Accepted: 1 April 2022

Abstract—Hand gesture recognition has attracted the attention of many scientists, because of its high applicability in fields such as sign language expression and human machine interaction. Many approaches have been deployed to detect and recognize hand gestures, like wearable devices, image information, and/or a combination of sensors and computer vision. However, the method of using wearable sensors brings much higher accuracy and is less affected by occlusion, lighting conditions, and complex background. Existing solutions separately utilize sensor information and/or only use sensor information processing and decision-making algorithms over conventional threshold comparison algorithms and do not analyze data or utilize machine learning algorithms. In this paper, a multi-modal solution is proposed that combines information for measuring the curvature of the fingers and sensors for measuring angular velocity and acceleration. The provided information from the sensors is normalized and analyzed and various fusion strategies are used. Then, the most suitable algorithm for these sensor-based multiple modalities is proposed. The proposed system also analyzes the differences between gestures and actions that are almost similar but in fact, they are just normal moving gestures.

Keywords—hand glove; acceleration sensor; hand gesture recognition; flex sensor; human-machine interaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Hand gestures are one of the most natural ways of interaction between people (e.g. sign language [1-6, 24]) or Human Computer Interaction–HCI [7-9]. Conveying messages in sign language through hand gestures has attracted the attention of many researchers and technology developers. As a consequence, many hand gesture recognition approaches have been proposed, such as using the change of radar waves when the user changes the state of the hand [10-11, 25], utilizing image information [12-14], or sensors physically attached to the hand [15-17]. The radar-based method [10] is easy and convenient for end-users because of independent equipment but it is dramatically affected by environmental noises and the number of antennas [27]. There are many moving objects in the normal environment that can also cause changes in feedback waves such as movement of other people, or other body parts. For the image-based approach [12], hand gesture recognition systems often face many challenges such as high time cost for

hand detection and hand recognition, effects of illumination, occlusion, complex background conditions, etc. The hand mounted sensor-based method [15], although limited due to device dependence that has much higher accuracy compared to other methods and especially it face to many criteria when the actual control system requires high accuracy. Thus, this solution is preferred in many special cases.

Hand-mounted sensors were applied to measure the change in the hand shapes and hand movements that were quite efficient because of their accuracy and real-time response. Many solutions have been proposed, such as the electronic gloves [17-18]. These gloves have integrated flex sensors, mounted on the fingers, to collect the hand's curvature changing. However, this solution only measures the change in the flexure of the fingers, but it cannot obtain the movement of the hand. In [19-20], the authors proposed a method to attach the sensors on the hand for receiving velocity and angular acceleration. This method achieves the alternation of hand movement, but it is not possible to obtain the changes of hand shapes. In [21-23], the authors combined both curvature and velocity sensors, but the classification of hand gesture categories was performed by the conventional comparison structures with simple instruction sets of microcontrollers (e.g. ARV, 8051 with compare and check condition instructions), without evaluation or survey changing of parameters of sensors or machine learning algorithms. Quantitative evaluations were not implemented to compare the defined activities with normal human activities.

In this paper, a new solution is proposed, one that combines both hand shape and hand movement sensors with various fusion strategies of features. The obtained results have success rates of up to 99.87% for the stable hand gesture dataset and 97.59% when both mobile and immobile hand gesture datasets are considered. These results are higher than the 97.4% and 86.3% for seen and unseen users of 12 gestures in [28] that fed the data of finger's curvatures to a convolution neural network. There are no published hand gesture datasets based on mounted sensors and the published ones do not provide both hand's curvatures and position at the same time. So, in this research, we collected two new hand gesture databases, one with stationary hand and one with moving hand.

Fig. 1. Proposed framework for hand gesture recognition.

The data flows will be fed into classifiers with various fusion strategies of machine learning techniques to find the most optimal and suitable classification solution.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

Our proposed framework for hand gesture recognition is illustrated in Figure 1. In this research, multiple modalities of hand ($l \in [1, L], L = 3$ corresponding to $l \in [A, G, F]$) are captured by two streams:

- Finger’s curvature: five flex sensors are used to present the curvature variation of fingers.
- Hand’s motion tracking and angle: sensor MPU6050 is integrated by 3-axis MEMS of gyroscope and 3-axis MEMS of accelerometer.

All features are processed and synchronized by an MCU (Microcontroller Unit) and are transferred to a PC. Finally, various classification strategies were used, either single or multi-modalities. The cascade steps in our proposed framework will be presented in detail at the following Sections.

A. Hardware Design for Multiple features of the Hand Glove

The detailed hardware design of the electronic glove is illustrated in Figure 2. Five flex sensors are permanently mounted along the fingers of the glove to collect the curvature based on the change of the corresponding resistance value. The resistors' data are preprocessed to convert into voltage value before conversion from analog to digital with a 10-bit ADC (Analog to Digital Converter) resolution, corresponding to a range of values from 0 to 1023. The values of flex sensors from the thumb to the little finger are denoted by F_1 to F_5 ($(F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4, F_5)/F(1,2,3,4,5)$) corresponding to the curvature data of the five fingers. At the same time, the values of the 3-axis MEMS gyroscope and 3-axis MEMS accelerometer of the MPU6050 sensor were collected. The resolution of ADCs is 16 bits with a range from 0 to 65535, denoted by $(A_x, A_y, A_z)/A(x, y, z)$ and $(G_x, G_y, G_z)/G(x, y, z)$. After the MCU collects the two data streams (flex sensors and

MPU sensor) at the same time, all data are packaged and sent to the PC via the USB port according to the UART standard.

Fig. 2. Hardware design of the hand glove.

In addition, each time, the information of the hand gesture is transferred by a feature vector which is composed by eleven elements in total: $A(x, y, z)$, $G(x, y, z)$, and $F(1,2,3,4,5)$, respectively. This feature is presented in detail in (1) and will be utilized in various strategies in detail in the next section:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{Ges} &= [F_G^1, F_G^2, \dots, F_G^M], (M = 11) \\
 &= [A(x, y, z); G(x, y, z); F(1,2,3,4,5)] \quad (1) \\
 &= [A_x, A_y, A_z, G_x, G_y, G_z, F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4, F_5]
 \end{aligned}$$

B. Hand Gesture Dataset

In this paper, twelve hand postures are used, as illustrated in Figure 3. Each hand gesture is captured when the end-user is immobile or in movement. In practice, the system will recognize the hand gestures at any time and any place, i.e. hand morphologies during normal human activities that could have similar characteristics to the previously defined dataset. In addition, the feature of hand shape is only based on the curvature of the fingers that are collected by the five flex sensors. It is apparent that the accelerometer sensors and velocity sensors provide useful information about the movement and the direction of the hand’s movement.

Fig. 3. The twelve hand postures of our dataset.

Figure 4 illustrates hand tracking with three accelerator parameters $A(x, y, z)$ and three velocity features $G(x, y, z)$ of four hand gestures in two cases: (1) the end-user raises the hand in front of his/her body and performs a gesture (blue, white, violet and grey colors in Figure 4) and (2) the end-user implements the same hand shape but hand and body are moving (green, yellow, red and orange colors in Figure 4). It is clear that feature $A(x, y, z)$ or feature $G(x, y, z)$ of the same hand gesture represent the hand's movement. It could effectively separate between immobile hand mobility hands while they do not have meaning for stable gestures.

Fig. 4. (a) $A(x, y, z)$ and $G(x, y, z)$ elements of the same hand gesture.

In practice, the users are usually immobile when they want to control the device and often put their hands in front of their body. Meanwhile, the end-user's hand shapes exist at both stable and moving situations. Therefore, we collected 12 gestures as shown in Figure 3 when the hand is in front of the user's face, when the hand is immobile and during normal movement. Each category will be separately labeled by Ges_k^1 (gesture of class k , hand is frontal of body and stable) and Ges_k^2 (gesture of class k , hand is at any position and movement). We divided the data into two datasets named HandGlove1 and HandGlove2. HandGlove1 is composed by $[Ges_k^1](k \in [1, K], K = 12)$ and HandGlove2 by $[Ges_k^1; Ges_k^2](k \in [1, K], K = 12)$. This means that HandGlove2 dataset has a duplicated number of categories up to $K = 24$ classes. Each gesture was collected three times and each time consists of about 200 samples. A total of 15 adults ($User_j(j \in [1, E], E = 15)$), including 7 females and 8 males were invited to collect our dataset at different days and at various times of the day. These databases were normalized and classifiers were used.

C. Data Processing

As described above, the data collected from the flex sensors are denoted by $F(1,2,3,4,5)$ and have a value range of 0 to 1023. The data from the MPU6050 sensors include $A(x, y, z)$ and $G(x, y, z)$ have a range of values from 0 to 65535. A sensor component has a different value range and 11

components must be processed to obtain the same range. Each characteristic component F_{Ges}^i of the 12 gestures $[Ges_k^1]$ and/or $[Ges_k^1; Ges_k^2](k \in [1, K], K = 12)$ of 15 collectors ($User_j(j \in [1, E], E = 15)$) is normalized. Firstly, the maximum value $F_{Ges_{max}}^i$ and the smallest value $F_{Ges_{min}}^i$ can be determined:

$$F_{Ges_{max}}^i = \text{Max}(F_{Ges}^i \text{ of all } (Ges_k; User_j)) (k \in [1, K]); (j \in [1, E]) \quad (2)$$

$$F_{Ges_{min}}^i = \text{Min}(F_{Ges}^i \text{ of all } (Ges_k; User_j)) (k \in [1, K]); (j \in [1, E]) \quad (3)$$

Each component $F_{G_{nor}}^i$ will be recalculated as (4):

$$F_{Ges_{nor}}^i = \frac{F_{Ges}^i - F_{Ges_{min}}^i}{F_{Ges_{max}}^i - F_{Ges_{min}}^i} \quad (4)$$

As a result, the feature vector could be presented by: $F_{Ges} = [F_{Ges_{nor}}^1, F_{Ges_{nor}}^2, \dots, F_{Ges_{nor}}^{11}]$. Figure 6 illustrates the t-SNE (Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding) for all the 12 gestures. Figure 6(a) uses $[F_{Ges_{nor}}^7; \dots, F_{Ges_{nor}}^{11}]$ elements, Figure 6(b) utilizes $[F_{Ges_{nor}}^4; \dots, F_{Ges_{nor}}^{11}]$, and Figure 6(c) utilizes $[F_{Ges_{nor}}^1; \dots, F_{Ges_{nor}}^{11}]$. This Figure shows that, if only using the curvature feature from the flex sensors, the data distribution of the gestures is not segregated than using combinations of the motion features. The composition of 6 motion features enables gesture types to be separated into more distinct spatial domains. This result is only qualitative but not quantitative. These normalized features will be put into classifiers with single patterns and combined features as described in Section III.D.

D. Hand Gesture Classification

Multi-modal data stream is presented above with $F, A,$ and G which are combined using different fusion techniques. In this research, three fusion techniques are investigated: late fusion, early fusion, and Multiple Kernel Learning (MKL) [2]. In the following, we will briefly survey these methods that are utilized in the classification block of Figure 1.

1) Early Fusion

For early fusion, all normalized feature vectors of the 3 modalities are concatenated into a final feature vector as presented in (5):

$$F_f = [F_{G_{nor}}^1, F_{G_{nor}}^2, \dots, F_{G_{nor}}^M] \quad (5)$$

Then, the feature vector F_f is used as an input of a final multiple SVM classifier to predict the hand gesture label.

2) Late Fusion

For late fusion, each modality is used with multiple SVM classifiers C_{SVM}^l with $l \in [1, L](L = 3)$. The outputs of the classification step are the score vectors $S^l = [s_1^l, s_2^l, \dots, s_k^l]$. Next, the maximum operator for these score vectors S^l is applied to obtain the final score vector as presented in (6):

$$S = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_k] = \frac{s_1^1 + s_1^2 + s_1^3}{3} = [\frac{s_1^1 + s_1^2 + s_1^3}{3}, \frac{s_2^1 + s_2^2 + s_2^3}{3}, \dots, \frac{s_k^1 + s_k^2 + s_k^3}{3}] \quad (6)$$

Then, the final decision is obtained as illustrated in (7):

$$\text{gesture label} = \text{argmax}_{k \in [1, K]}(s_k) \quad (7)$$

3) Multiple Kernel Learning

MKL is an algorithm that combines a set of base kernels that could represent different similarity measures of different sources of data. As a result, each feature vector from the l^{th} ($l \in [1, L]$) modality utilizes a kernel function to compute the corresponding kernel matrix as shown in (8):

$$Kernel_K^v = similarity[(F_{Ges}^A, F_{Ges}^G), (F_{Ges}^A, F_{Ges}^F), (F_{Ges}^F, F_{Ges}^G)] \quad (8)$$

where $v \in [1, V], (V = 3)$. Then, kernel matrices $Kernel_K^v$ are used to combine for Kernel factor as presented in (9):

$$Kernel = func_{\mu}(\{Kernel_K^v\}_{v=1}^V | \mu) \quad (9)$$

where $func$ denotes the function form. The combination coefficient μ sees that the values are bound to the predefined rules or are optimized by the learning process of MKL [1, 2]. In this research, EasyMKL [1] with a binary margin maximization MKL algorithm is chosen which uses the convex summation function. The coefficients μ are restricted to be non-negative and sum to 1. A final kernel machine classifier will decide the label based on the combined kernel matrix $Kernel$ by a SVM classifier.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this paper, two datasets (HandGlove1 and HandGlove2) were utilized. The "leave-one-subject-out cross-validation" protocol is followed [3]. This means that, we took samples from one subject for testing and samples from the remaining subjects for training. Then we compute the average accuracy of every experiment.

A. Single Modality for Hand Gesture Recognition

In this section, we used HandGlove1 dataset in separating the following data types: Five components are the finger curvature sensors $F(1,2,3,4,5)$, 3 components measure the angle of the hand $A(x,y,z)$, and 3 components show the angular velocity $G(x,y,z)$. Each type is firstly normalized. It is then put into the SVM classifier. The classification results on each modality are presented in Table I. Table I shows that the finger's curvatures of the hand gesture dataset (Figure 3) obtained the highest recognition result (92.15%) while $A(x,y,z)$ cue has the lowest at only 36.48%. Although the result of the $G(x,y,z)$ modality is higher than the cue modality, but it still is ineffective for the defined dataset with 42.76%. This result shows that each data type gives low results, not suitable to control in practice.

TABLE I. SINGLE MODALITY FOR HAND GESTURE RECOGNITION ACCURACY (%) WITH SVM CLASSIFIER

Modality	Accuracy (%)
$A(x,y,z)$	36.48
$G(x,y,z)$	42.76
$F(1,2,3,4,5)$	92.15

B. Hand Gesture Recognition on Various Fusion Strategies

In this part, we will investigate different strategies (early fusion, late fusion, and MKL) on the three streams. Evaluations are conducted on HandGlove1 dataset. The results are shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Hand gesture recognition on various fusion strategies.

Fig. 6. T-SNE of 12 gestures with various modalities.

Figure 5 shows that:

- KML obtains the highest accuracy at 94.58%, 90.18%, 97.31%, and 99.87% with combination of A and F , A and G , G and G , and $A+G+F$ respectively. The late fusion method reached the lowest accuracies on all data combinations (around 75% and the smallest at 46.17% for $A+G$ modality). We can see that early fusion is quite simple while its results are lower than KML's. The late fusion method requires many classifiers but its accuracy is far smaller than KML's. Therefore, the KML solution will be utilized in the rest of the testing.
- Combinations of the 3 modalities are the highest on all classifiers and account for 97.69%, 86.02% and 99.87% for early fusion, late fusion, and KML respectively. These results can be explained through Figure 6 that shows the distribution of data using the t-SNE method [26]. When G is used, the hand gesture classes distribute in the overlap domains. When F and A are combined as shown in Figure

6(b) or F and G as illustrated in Figure 6(c) the distribution of the categories has improved but the separation is not clear enough. In Figure 6(d), A , G , and F are utilized and the data distribution domains of the 12 hand gestures are completely separated.

- Association of the three modalities accounts for slightly higher results in HandGlove1 dataset because the gestures in this dataset have negligible displacement. The hand rotations are almost the same and the hand is raised in front of the body. However, the system is trained by HandGlove1 dataset, and then this trained model is deployed in real application. As a result, the online system has many mistakes. To see the effectiveness of A and G modalities, we will be evaluated in the below Section IV.C.

C. Distinction between Command Action and Normal Gestures

In this section, the KML fusion strategy will be used for testing on the HandGlove2 dataset. All gestures belonging to the group Ges_k^2 are labeled with labels from 13 to 24. The recognition accuracy is considered only with gestures with labels from 1 to 12. These gestures are defined and expected to be correctly recognized by the system. The user raises his/her hand in front of the face and the state of the hand is stationary. Only the hand shape changes according to the specified gesture means. In this test, a combination of different modalities will be used, such as: A and F , G and F , and A , G , and F . The evaluation results are shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Efficient of modalities combination for hand gesture recognition accuracy (%) in a real environment.

In HandGlove1 dataset, the recognition results of the ways of combining data have not a big gap from 92.15% to 99.87%. Hand gestures are distinguished with other hand postures. In addition, end-user's hand and body are immobile so that the curvature of the fingers could provide enough cues of hand shapes in this dataset, so, the recognition results are quite good. However, in HandGlove2 database, the recognition accuracy is low when the 5 flex sensors are utilized. This is because of for the same changing shapes, i.e. the same five F elements, one of them moves like normal hand movement (different A and G elements). Gestures 1 to 12 have the same hand shape with corresponding gestures 13 to 24 (Figure 8). Therefore, using only the curvatures of the fingers does not give enough information to distinguish between a control operation and a normal operation as shown in Figure 8. For example, gesture 1

(red color) and gesture 13 (slow brown color) in Figure 8 have the same hand shape but hand gesture 1 is immobile while gesture 13 is in movement. Distributions of these gestures overlap in Figure 8(a), but are reparative in Figure 8(b). Thus, there is a big gap between single modal (56.72% with F) and multi-modal (97.59% with A , G , and F) in the second row of Figure 7.

In HandGlove2 dataset, combining F and A or F and G showed a significant improvement in accuracy, increasing up to 33% and 36% respectively (Figure 7). Especially, the coherency of the 3 components (A , G , and F) obtained the highest recognition accuracy, which was increased up to 97.59% in this dataset. The proposed framework could apparently distinguish between the 12 hand gestures in both immobile and mobile states. The efficiency of the system dramatically increased and practical applications can now be deployed.

Fig. 8. T-sne of 24 gestures with various modalities.

IV. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This paper presents a comparative analysis of recent fusion strategies for static hand gesture recognition on three modalities of an electronics hand glove. Among the evaluated fusion strategies (late fusion, early fusion, and KML), KML performed better, achieving the highest recognition accuracy. The evaluation results on two datasets show great interest in combining multi-modalities (5 curvature fingers from flex sensors, 3-axis gyroscope and 3-axis accelerometer from MPU6050 sensor) to increase accuracy. In most cases, multimodal KML models can achieve an accuracy rate above 97%. This performance is remarkable and promises a feasible solution for deploying gesture-based applications in practice. Finally, it was found that there is a notable gap in recognition accuracy between the same hand shapes but different normal hand movements. The last remark opens up new research directions that require further investigation on data combination with image information, using deep convolutional neural networks, and online learning. Once these bottlenecks are resolved, the development of a gesture-based interface in practical applications is straightforward.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research was funded by the Electric Power University (EPU) under the grant project titled "Research on multi-modal and multi-view hand gesture recognition combinative utilizing sensors and images".

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Aioli, G. Da San Martino, and A. Sperduti, "A Kernel Method for the Optimization of the Margin Distribution," in *Artificial Neural Networks - ICANN 2008*, Berlin, Heidelberg, Germany, 2008, pp. 305–314, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-87536-9_32.
- [2] T.-H. Tran, H.-N. Tran, and H.-G. Doan, "Dynamic Hand Gesture Recognition from Multi-modal Streams Using Deep Neural Network," in *Multi-disciplinary Trends in Artificial Intelligence*, 2019, pp. 156–167, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33709-4_14.
- [3] Dang-Manh Truong was with Hanoi University of Science Technology, Vietnam, D.-M. Truong, H.-G. Doan, T.-H. Tran, H. Vu, and T.-L. Le, "Robustness Analysis of 3D Convolutional Neural Network for Human Hand Gesture Recognition," *International Journal of Machine Learning and Computing*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 135–142, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.18178/ijmlc.2019.9.2.777>.
- [4] P. Das, T. Ahmed, and Md. F. Ali, "Static Hand Gesture Recognition for American Sign Language using Deep Convolutional Neural Network," in *2020 IEEE Region 10 Symposium (TENSYP)*, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Jun. 2020, pp. 1762–1765, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TENSYP50017.2020.9230772>.
- [5] J. Zamora-Mora and M. Chacón-Rivas, "Real-Time Hand Detection using Convolutional Neural Networks for Costa Rican Sign Language Recognition," in *2019 International Conference on Inclusive Technologies and Education (CONTIE)*, San Jose del Cabo, Mexico, Jul. 2019, pp. 180–1806, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CONTIE49246.2019.00042>.
- [6] N. Sarhan and S. Frintrop, "Transfer Learning For Videos: From Action Recognition To Sign Language Recognition," in *2020 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, Jul. 2020, pp. 1811–1815, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIP40778.2020.9191289>.
- [7] S. Veluchamy, L. R. Karlmarx, and J. J. Sudha, "Vision based gesturally controllable human computer interaction system," in *2015 International Conference on Smart Technologies and Management for Computing, Communication, Controls, Energy and Materials (ICSTM)*, Avadi, India, Feb. 2015, pp. 8–15, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSTM.2015.7225383>.
- [8] H.-G. Doan, H. Vu, T.-H. Tran, and E. Castelli, "Improvements of RGB-D hand posture recognition using a user-guide scheme," in *2015 IEEE 7th International Conference on Cybernetics and Intelligent Systems (CIS) and IEEE Conference on Robotics, Automation and Mechatronics (RAM)*, Siem Reap, Cambodia, Jul. 2015, pp. 24–29, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCIS.2015.7274542>.
- [9] S. Lee, K. Park, J. Lee, and K. Kim, "User Study of VR Basic Controller and Data Glove as Hand Gesture Inputs in VR Games," in *2017 International Symposium on Ubiquitous Virtual Reality (ISUVR)*, Nara, Japan, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISUVR.2017.16>.
- [10] N. E. A. Rashid, Y. A. I. M. Nor, K. K. M. Sharif, Z. I. Khan, and N. A. Zakaria, "Hand Gesture Recognition using Continuous Wave (CW) Radar based on Hybrid PCA-KNN," in *2021 IEEE Symposium on Wireless Technology Applications (ISWTA)*, Shah Alam, Malaysia, Dec. 2021, pp. 88–92, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISWTA52208.2021.9587404>.
- [11] G. Zhang, S. Lan, K. Zhang, and L. Ye, "Temporal-Range-Doppler Features Interpretation and Recognition of Hand Gestures Using mmW FMCW Radar Sensors," in *2020 14th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, Copenhagen, Denmark, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.23919/EuCAP48036.2020.9135694>.
- [12] P. Molchanov, X. Yang, S. Gupta, K. Kim, S. Tyree, and J. Kautz, "Online Detection and Classification of Dynamic Hand Gestures with Recurrent 3D Convolutional Neural Networks," in *2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, Jun. 2016, pp. 4207–4215, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2016.456>.
- [13] J. J. Raval and R. Gajjar, "Real-time Sign Language Recognition using Computer Vision," in *2021 3rd International Conference on Signal Processing and Communication (ICSPC)*, Coimbatore, India, Feb. 2021, pp. 542–546, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSPC51351.2021.9451709>.
- [14] J. Fink, B. Frénay, L. Meurant, and A. Cleve, "LSFB-CONT and LSFB-ISOL: Two New Datasets for Vision-Based Sign Language Recognition," in *2021 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, Shenzhen, China, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IJCNN52387.2021.9534336>.
- [15] X. Chu, J. Liu, and S. Shimamoto, "A Sensor-Based Hand Gesture Recognition System for Japanese Sign Language," in *2021 IEEE 3rd Global Conference on Life Sciences and Technologies (LifeTech)*, Nara, Japan, Mar. 2021, pp. 311–312, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LifeTech52111.2021.9391981>.
- [16] K. Liu, C. Chen, R. Jafari, and N. Kehtarnavaz, "Multi-HMM classification for hand gesture recognition using two differing modality sensors," in *2014 IEEE Dallas Circuits and Systems Conference (DCAS)*, Richardson, TX, USA, Jul. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/DCAS.2014.6965338>.
- [17] S. Zhu, A. Stuttaford-Fowler, A. Fahmy, C. Li, and J. Sieng, "Development of a Low-cost Data Glove using Flex Sensors for the Robot Hand Teleoperation," in *2021 3rd International Symposium on Robotics Intelligent Manufacturing (ISRIMT)*, Changzhou, China, Sep. 2021, pp. 47–51, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISRIMT53730.2021.9596972>.
- [18] A. K. Panda, R. Chakravarty, and S. Moulik, "Hand Gesture Recognition using Flex Sensor and Machine Learning Algorithms," in *2020 IEEE-EMBS Conference on Biomedical Engineering and Sciences (IECBES)*, Langkawi Island, Malaysia, Mar. 2021, pp. 449–453, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IECBES48179.2021.9398789>.
- [19] S. S. Kumar, R. Gatti, S. K. N. Kumar, N. Nataraja, R. P. Prasad, and T. Sarala, "Glove Based Deaf-Dumb Sign Language Interpreter," in *2021 International Conference on Recent Trends on Electronics, Information, Communication Technology (RTEICT)*, Bangalore, India, Dec. 2021, pp. 947–950, <https://doi.org/10.1109/RTEICT52294.2021.9573990>.
- [20] Z. Zou, Q. Wu, Y. Zhang, and K. Wen, "Design of Smart Car Control System for Gesture Recognition Based on Arduino," in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics and Computer Engineering (ICCECE)*, Guangzhou, China, Jan. 2021, pp. 695–699, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCECE51280.2021.9342137>.
- [21] X. Chen et al., "A Wearable Hand Rehabilitation System With Soft Gloves," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 943–952, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2020.3010369>.
- [22] S. Mugala, P. Jjagwe, and J. Aasiimwe, "Glove Based Sign Interpreter for Medical Emergencies," in *2019 IST-Africa Week Conference (IST-Africa)*, Nairobi, Kenya, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.23919/ISTAfrICA.2019.8764816>.
- [23] P. Telluri, S. Manam, S. Somarouthu, J. M. Oli, and C. Ramesh, "Low cost flex powered gesture detection system and its applications," in *2020 Second International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA)*, Coimbatore, India, Jul. 2020, pp. 1128–1131, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIRCA48905.2020.9182833>.
- [24] H. V. T. Chi, D. L. Anh, N. L. Thanh, and D. Dinh, "English-Vietnamese Cross-Lingual Paraphrase Identification Using MT-DNN," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7598–7604, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4300>.
- [25] N. T. T. Vu, N. P. Tran, and N. H. Nguyen, "Recurrent Neural Network-based Path Planning for an Excavator Arm under Varying Environment," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7088–7093, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4125>.
- [26] M. Wattenberg, F. Viégas, and I. Johnson, "How to Use t-SNE Effectively," *Distill*, vol. 1, no. 10, Oct. 2016, Art. no. e2, <https://doi.org/10.23915/distill.00002>.
- [27] A. A. Alzamil, "Assessment of Uplink Massive MIMO in Scattering Environment," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6290–6293, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3743>.
- [28] O. Luzanin and M. Plancak, "Hand gesture recognition using low-budget data glove and cluster-trained probabilistic neural network," *Assembly Automation*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 94–105, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1108/AA-03-2013-020>.

Performance Analysis of a Hybrid Microgrid with Energy Management

Mohamed Arbi Khelifi

Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Islamic University of Madinah, Saudi Arabia and SIME Laboratory, ENSIT, University of Tunis, Tunisia
mohamedarbi.khelifi@issatm.rnu.tn

Abdulrahman AlKassem

Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Islamic University of Madinah Saudi Arabia
rahman.alkasem@gmail.com

Azzedine Draou

Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Islamic University of Madinah, Saudi Arabia
adraou@yahoo.com

Received: 28 February 2022 | Revised: 28 March 2022 | Accepted: 4 April 2022

Abstract-In a hybrid microgrid system, various renewable energy resources may be integrated and modeled on-site, in such a way as to provide an optimal, consistent, and sustainable energy production at a cost-effective rate throughout the year. In this paper, a microgrid prototype consisting of a wind turbine and a photovoltaic (PV) panel is modeled and thoroughly investigated through various changes in inputs. The long-term goal of this work in IUM is to develop a concise and complete microgrid system model that can be used to simulate and fully understand its behavior and operation. The proposed model including power sources, power electronic converters, and load has been modeled in MATLAB/Simulink.

Keywords-PV microgrid; grid modeling; microgrid; wind turbine; battery

I. INTRODUCTION

During the recent years, there was a huge demand of energy from vital sectors such as the manufacturing industry, the transportation system, and general construction industry which indicated a steady growth in economic development. However, this energy is related to environment concerns because the use of fossil fuel and coal for the generation of electricity generation emits greenhouse gases (GHG). Thus, numerous stake holders aim the developing countries to use clean and green energy with financial support [1-2]. With the steady increase in global population, the demand for energy has increased dramatically and this has led to a high pressure on actual energy infrastructures to generate power above their nominal capacity. The development of electric power generation methods to make the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia a logistical center connecting three continents and thus enhance sustainable economic growth and competitiveness, while achieving convergence between all services to meet the Kingdom's needs by raising the level of protection, rationalizing energy, and improving the quality of operations and performance for providing effective services to all

Corresponding author: Mohamed Arbi Khelifi

beneficiaries, is in line with Saudi Vision 2030 [3-5]. Power generation projects are among the most important projects that the governments seek to present to their citizens to develop cities, provide basic services to the society and raise the state's economy by owning an integrated power generation system [6-8].

To extend the national grid for rural areas and remote places, a high price has to be spent for building such large power networks. This has prompted decision makers to look for alternatives energy resources such as renewable energy in local levels [9-12]. To address the challenge of this global developmental crisis, numerous meetings have been conducted between government and private stakeholders without much success bearing in mind that the population will be without any access to electricity [13-14].

The use of the alternative renewable sources such as hybrid microgrid systems is a way of achieving this objective. This will allow the generation of eco-friendly electricity in remote areas by suppressing the effect of climate change. Recently, and as a short term solution to this energy crisis, hybrid microgrids have been thoroughly used as an alternative for the generation and distribution of renewable energy in remote locations [15-18].

A Microgrid system is usually composed of distributed energy resources like photovoltaic panels, wind turbines, fuel cells, or micro turbines that may be connected to the distribution network at a medium voltage. Microgrids can also work off the main grid to meet customer needs, improve reliability, lower emissions, and improve power quality at a reduced price. The optimal use of hybrid microgrids assets as an alternative to the main grid extension has allowed for electricity generation at a reduced overall price [19-20].

In this paper, energy management with specific aspects related to remote localities is proposed, powered solely by

renewable resources where the grid extension is not plausible. These solutions can be applied for isolated water pumping, irrigation, household applications, etc. In the future, with the development of more efficient technologies, the proposed solutions will be of great interest for telecommunications applications and hydrogen storage. Recently many research works have been published on the field of modeling and simulation of isolated hybrid systems [21-24]. In this paper, we mainly focus on the study of strategies for the energy management in a hybrid microgrid. Three different energy management strategies are considered: Photovoltaic system, wind turbine, and batteries. The major contribution of this paper is the presentation of a simulation model of a hybrid microgrid energy system made up of PV panels, wind turbine, and battery for storage. This paper provides the overall description of the proposed methodology of the management strategy of the system. The effectiveness of the proposed hybrid microgrid energy system is confirmed through the simulation under several situations such as variation in power demand.

II. HYBRID AC/DC MICROGRID

Microgrids are effective systems for managing dispersed resources like small-scale distributed generators and renewable energy resources. The microgrid structure allows for more efficient operation which could lead to lower emissions and fewer power outages. Microgrids can be made up of a complicated mix of AC and DC sources, as well as AC and DC loads, and power electronic interfaces. The benefits of both AC and DC microgrids are combined in a single network architecture with hybrid AC/DC microgrids. By permitting seamless connection to numerous AC and DC sources and loads, it decreases the losses associated with multiple conversions from DC to AC and vice versa. It may also be linked to the national grid or used as a stand-alone power source. When connected to the utility grid, the AC and DC microgrids receive energy from it to balance between load demand and supply, resulting in a acceptable power balance with the grid. When there is an excess of power in the AC and DC microgrids, the power will flow to the utility grid. On the contrary, when there is a shortage of power in the AC and DC microgrids, power is returned back to the AC and DC microgrids by the utility grid. Usually, the Energy Storage Systems (ESSs) are used primarily to compensate any shortage of energy since the generating units are supposed to provide the majority of the energy consumed in the system. Thus, the AC and DC microgrids will deliver energy with a steady bus voltage and reduced harmonics to the utility grid. The main converter in the microgrid will minimize any unbalance occurring from the loads and when the output of the DC sources exceeds the output of the DC loads, the converter acts as an inverter, transferring power from DC to AC.

III. MODELING OF THE MICROGRID

A. PV Array with MPPT

Usually, the sun is considered as a potential source of energy as it is consistent and clean, as opposed to other types of energy that contaminate the atmosphere and the environment, such as coal, oil, and oil derivatives. A PV cell is usually

considered as a current source in parallel with a diode as shown in Figure 1. With the increase of intensity of sun light, current is produced by the PV cell [18].

Fig. 1. Electrical model of a solar cell.

Ideal case:

$$I_{pv} = I_{cc} \frac{E}{E_r} + k_{isc} (T - T_r) \frac{E}{E_r} - I_s \left[\exp\left(\frac{V_{pv}}{V_T}\right) - 1 \right] \quad (1)$$

Real case:

$$I_{pv} = I_{cc} \frac{E}{E_r} + k_{isc} (T - T_r) \frac{E}{E_r} - I_s \left[\exp\left(\frac{V_{pv} + R_s I_{pv}}{V_T}\right) - 1 \right] - \left(\frac{V_{pv} + R_s I_{pv}}{R_{sh}}\right) \quad (2)$$

We use the model of (1) and (2) [18], due to the difficulty of estimating the PV system's behavior. We may be able to determine the panel's I-U and P-U properties using this approach. It may also allow us to adjust the voltage, current, and power while changing the number of cells in series and parallel in the panels. The modeling of a panel composed of N_s modules in series and N_p modules in parallel is given. The diode current I_p is obtained by [18]:

$$I_p = N_p \left[I_{ph} - I_0 \left(\exp\left(\frac{\frac{V_p}{N_s} + \frac{R_s I_p}{N_p}}{V_T}\right) - 1 \right) - \frac{N_p V_p}{N_s R_{sh}} - \frac{R_s I_p}{R_{sh}} \right] \quad (3)$$

Figure 2 shows the I-V characteristics of the panel as defined for this application at various ambient temperatures and a constant irradiation of 1000W/m². It can be seen that when the temperature rises, the power produced by the PV panel decreases. Temperature fluctuations have little effect on the short circuit current. Figure 3 depicts the PV panel's I-V characteristics at constant temperature of 25°C and various irradiation values. The higher the degree of solar irradiation, the more power the PV generates. As a result, any change in the irradiance level will alter the short circuit current value proportionately.

Fig. 2. I-V characteristics at different temperature and constant irradiance of 1000W/m².

Fig. 3. I-V Characteristics of PV at constant temperature of 25°C and different irradiances.

B. Wind Turbine Modeling

Wind energy conversion is the world's fastest-growing source of new electric generation, and it is likely to stay that way for a long time in future. It is more appealing than other sources because of its extended lifespan, emission-free operation, and low cost. These turbines supplement the use of other electric power sources by delivering the most cost-effective solution in a variety of situations. Figure 4 shows the steady state features of the wind turbine as modeled by its variable pitch. In the first input, the per unit of the generator base speed is taken and the synchronous speed is modeled as the base speed of a synchronous or asynchronous generator. The second and third inputs are the blade pitch angle and the wind speed in m/s. The base speed of the permanent-magnet generator may be considered as the speed for nominal voltage generation and no load application. The rest parameters, such as the drive train's stiffness, will be taken as infinite whereas

the turbine's friction factor and inertia will be combined with those of the generator. The following equation calculates the turbine's output power [16]:

$$P_m = C_p(\lambda, \beta) \frac{\rho A}{2} V_{wind}^3 \quad (4)$$

We can use numerical integration using the trapezoidal rule to determine the total amount of electrical energy produced by the panel [16]:

$$E = \int_{sunrise}^{sunset} P(t)dt \sim \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \frac{1}{2} (P_i + P_{i+1}) \Delta t \quad (5)$$

For a constant step size we can calculate the energy production as [16]:

$$E = \int_{sunrise}^{sunset} P(t)dt \sim \left(\frac{1}{2} P_1 + \frac{1}{2} P_N + \sum_{i=2}^{N-1} P_i \right) \Delta t \quad (6)$$

Figure 4 depicts the Simulink mathematical model of a wind turbine. The generator speed of the nominal generator speed, the pitch angle in degrees, and the wind speed in m/s are used as the three inputs. The output is the torque applied to the generator shaft which can be obtained by dividing the rotational speed by the wind speed to get the tip speed ratio in pu value.

Fig. 4. Simulink mathematical model of the wind turbine.

Fig. 5. Turbine power characteristics with wind as parameter.

Figure 5 shows a series of mechanical power curves versus wind speed changes. It can be seen that average wind speed of 3.81m/s is obtained as the base wind speed. Moreover, we have obtained the maximum power as 0.73 pu ($k_p = 0.73$) at base wind speed, and the maximum rotational speed is 1.2 pu at base rotational speed.

C. Battery Operating to Support the PV System

Storage energy is used in this simulation to help the PV system fulfill the load power requirements. Because the battery active power reference (P_A) will be led by (7), it might be considered the foundation of a stand-alone system. The battery will not only be used to supply its energy to help the PV system (P_{PV}) meet the needs of the load's demand (P). It will also store the energy generated by the PV system when it exceeds the power demand of the load [17].

$$P_A = P_{PV} - P_L \quad (7)$$

Figure 6 illustrates the Simulink model of the battery and in Figure 7 we can notice the presence of three regions related to the flow characteristics of the battery. In the first region and during the charging of the battery, an exponential drop in voltage occurs. The area corresponding to the available charge in the battery before the drop of the voltage below its nominal voltage is depicted in the second region. The third region corresponds to the discharge cycle of the battery as the voltage drops. This drop depends on the type of the battery. Moreover, the battery will recharge if the current becomes negative.

Fig. 6. Battery model.

Fig. 7. Charge and discharge characteristics of the battery.

As can be seen in Figure 7, the value is not always zero because of the existence of power losses (inductors and equivalent resistances) which are not supported by the battery.

IV. THE PROPOSED POWER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (PMS)

In this paper three different management strategies are compared. The main objective of this current study presented in this paper is to propose three different energy management strategies that can satisfy the following criteria:

- guarantee the electrical energy required by the user,
- manage efficiently the resources, and
- minimize the excess energy.

The management strategy will define the autonomous control of the power sharing scheme with the local load demand. It will also guarantee the reliability operation of the generating units' production.

The PMS aims to ensure power balancing among generating units as well as load management during power outages, with vital and critical loads being prioritized. This is important to prevent the DC bus voltage from collapsing due to the microgrid being overloaded and to keep the circulating currents to a minimum. The sub-units are related to the DC bus at which the output is reversed. Moreover, the PMS is designed to provide power that has a larger renewable fraction, and can adjust all of the electric parameters supplied by the inverters based on the energy demand. However, the PMS will not rely on communication protocols of the producing units to increase the network's overall efficiency. The PMS algorithm, which is used to determine the best network configuration for the PV-Wind-Battery category, employs a cycle charging and load following dispatch strategy. The network's operational cycle is described below.

A. Energy Management A ($P_{PV} + P_W < P_{load}$)

Due to the changing nature of the renewable sources caused by seasonal climate variations, the energy produced by these sources is either insufficient or unavailable in this stage. The energy stored in the battery will be used to supply power to the local community, provided that the battery storage is within the operation's minimal SOC. The system will remain in this condition until the restoration of power or until the battery's capacity falls under 25%.

B. Energy Management B ($P_{PV} + P_W > P_{load}$)

The required load demand energy to the local community will rely mainly on the renewable sources and any excess of power will automatically be stored in the battery bank. The battery is in a charging state at this point.

C. Energy Management C ($P_{Load} < SOC_{min}$)

When the battery's SOC falls below the minimum permitted limit of 25% and renewable energy is unavailable, the system's operation is taken over by the diesel generator. The generator is offered as a backup to avoid the system from completely collapsing if the renewable energy sources are unavailable for an extended period of time. No discharge from the battery will

occur in this case since any extra power will be stored in the battery bank.

D. Discussion

When the combined power of the PV panel and the wind turbine exceeds the load requirements, the excess electricity will be stored in the battery. If, on the contrary, this power is insufficient to satisfy the load requirement, the battery will begin to discharge its stored energy to service the load. If the battery runs out of the stored energy, and electricity from the PV and wind turbine system is not available, the generator kicks in, providing the needed power to service the load with an excess as charge in the battery system.

V. CONCLUSION

A thorough evaluation of the mostly often utilized techniques in the literature for AC and DC microgrids was conducted in this paper in order to discover strategies that can be applied in hybrid microgrids. The main functions that a management plan should provide have been gathered, and a classification of the mostly studied hierarchical controls has been developed. The effectiveness of a hybrid microgrid for utilizing distributed renewable energy while meeting local load demand has also been discussed. Microgrid modeling and operation modes were also analyzed and presented. The microgrid serves as a vital link between dispersed generation and renewable energy. The approaches for power management are depicted. When opposed to a standard grid, the nature of the microgrid is irregular and intermittent.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors extend their appreciation to the Deputyship for Research & Innovation, Ministry of Education, Saudi Arabia for funding this research work through the project number (20/10).

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Muchande and S. Thale, "Hierarchical Control of a Low Voltage DC Microgrid with Coordinated Power Management Strategies," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8045–8052, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4625>.
- [2] L. T. H. Nhung, T. T. Phung, H. M. V. Nguyen, T. N. Le, T. A. Nguyen, and T. D. Vo, "Load Shedding in Microgrids with Dual Neural Networks and AHP Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8090–8095, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4652>.
- [3] A. A. Bakar *et al.*, "Decentralized Virtual Impedance-based Circulating Current Suppression Control for Islanded Microgrids," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6734–6739, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3895>.
- [4] T. Le and B. L. N. Phung, "Load Shedding in Microgrids with Consideration of Voltage Quality Improvement," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6680–6686, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3931>.
- [5] L. B. Raju and K. S. Rao, "Evaluation of Passive Islanding Detection Methods for Line to Ground Unsymmetrical Fault in Three Phase Microgrid Systems: Microgrid Islanding Detection Method," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7591–7597, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4310>.
- [6] S. Zamanian, S. Sadi, R. Ghaffarpour, and A. Mahdavian, "Inverter-based microgrid dynamic stability analysis considering inventory of dynamic and static load models," *Journal of Intelligent Procedures in Electrical Technology*, vol. 11, no. 44, pp. 91–109, Feb. 2021.
- [7] B. Keyvani-Boroujeni, G. Shahgholian, and B. Fani, "A Distributed Secondary Control Approach for Inverter-Dominated Microgrids With Application to Avoiding Bifurcation-Triggered Instabilities," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3361–3371, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JESTPE.2020.2974756>.
- [8] A. Chandra, G. K. Singh, and V. Pant, "Protection techniques for DC microgrid- A review," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 187, Oct. 2020, Art. no. 106439, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epr.2020.106439>.
- [9] A. Bani-Ahmed, M. Rashidi, and A. Nasiri, "Decentralised resilient autonomous control architecture for dynamic microgrids," *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, vol. 13, no. 11, pp. 2182–2189, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-gtd.2018.5816>.
- [10] O. Bassey, K. L. Butler-Purry, and B. Chen, "Dynamic Modeling of Sequential Service Restoration in Islanded Single Master Microgrids," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 202–214, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2019.2929268>.
- [11] H. Bevrani, B. Françoise, and T. Ise, *Microgrid Dynamics and Control*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2017.
- [12] S. Bracco and F. Delfino, "A mathematical model for the dynamic simulation of low size cogeneration gas turbines within smart microgrids," *Energy*, vol. 119, pp. 710–723, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2016.11.033>.
- [13] Y. Du, X. Lu, J. Wang, and S. Lukic, "Distributed Secondary Control Strategy for Microgrid Operation with Dynamic Boundaries," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 5269–5282, Sep. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSG.2018.2879793>.
- [14] P. Ferraro, E. Crisostomi, R. Shorten, and F. Milano, "Stochastic Frequency Control of Grid-Connected Microgrids," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 5704–5713, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2018.2821370>.
- [15] M. A. Hassan, "Dynamic Stability of an Autonomous Microgrid Considering Active Load Impact With a New Dedicated Synchronization Scheme," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 4994–5005, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2018.2798160>.
- [16] M. Juneja, S. K. Nagar, and S. R. Mohanty, "ABC based reduced order modelling of microgrid in grid-tied mode," *Control Engineering Practice*, vol. 84, pp. 337–348, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conengprac.2018.12.004>.
- [17] I. E. Atawi and A. M. Kassem, "Optimal Control Based on Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) of an Autonomous Hybrid Photovoltaic/Storage System in Micro Grid Applications," *Energies*, vol. 10, no. 5, May 2017, Art. no. 643, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en10050643>.
- [18] M. A. Khlifi, "Study and Control of Photovoltaic Water Pumping System," *Journal of Electrical Engineering and Technology*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 117–124, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.5370/JEET.2016.11.1.117>.
- [19] K. Ghaib and F.-Z. Ben-Fares, "A design methodology of stand-alone photovoltaic power systems for rural electrification," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 148, pp. 1127–1141, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.06.052>.
- [20] S. S. Rashwan, A. M. Shaaban, and F. Al-Suliman, "A comparative study of a small-scale solar PV power plant in Saudi Arabia," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 80, pp. 313–318, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.233>.
- [21] S. Babu, A. K. Loganathan, and I. Vairavasundaram, "Optimizing electrical generators of wind energy conversion system for efficient power extraction," *Gazi University Journal of Science*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 1141–1154, Dec. 2018.
- [22] N. Singh and B. Singh, "Design and modeling of wind energy conversion system based on PMSG using MPPT technique." (IJSRET) 5.2 (2016).," *International Journal of Scientific Research Engineering & Technology*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 96–100, 2016.
- [23] E. Pathan, A. A. Bakar, S. A. Zulkifli, M. H. Khan, H. Arshad, and M. Asad, "A Robust Frequency Controller based on Linear Matrix Inequality for a Parallel Islanded Microgrid," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6264–6269, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3769>.

- [24] Q. N. U. Islam, S. M. Abdullah, and M. A. Hossain, "Optimized Controller Design for an Islanded Microgrid using Non-dominated Sorting Sine Cosine Algorithm (NSSCA)," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 6052–6056, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3468>.

Modeling and Comparison of Fuzzy-PI and Genetic Control Algorithms for Active and Reactive Power Flow between the Stator (DFIG) and the Grid

Abdelhafid Guediri

University of El Oued, VTRS Laboratory, Faculty of
Technology, El Oued, Algeria
abdelhafid-guediri@univ-eloued.dz

Abdelkarim Guediri

University of El Oued, VTRS Laboratory, Faculty of
Technology, El Oued, Algeria
karim_elect@yahoo.fr

Slimane Touil

University of El Oued, VTRS Laboratory, Faculty of Technology, El Oued, Algeria
slimanetouil@yahoo.fr

Received: 11 March 2022 | Revised: 27 March 2022 and 31 March 2022 | Accepted: 4 April 2022

Abstract-This paper performs a comparison between Fuzzy-PI regulators and Genetic Algorithm (GA) for controlling an active and reactive Doubly-Fed Induction Generator (DFIG) for providing power to the electrical grid. Theoretical analysis, modeling, and simulation studies are provided. Control strategies were developed for both active and reactive forces in order to optimize energy production. The performance of the two control strategies was examined and compared using benchmarks for durability and reference traceability. This paper studied a system consisting of a wind turbine operating at variable wind speed and a two-feed asynchronous machine (DFIG) connected to the grid by the stator and fed by a transducer at the side of the rotor. The conductors were separately controlled for active and reactive power flow between the stator (DFIG) and the grid, which was achieved in this article using conventional PI and fuzzy logic controllers. The considered controllers generated reference voltages for the rotor to ensure that the active and reactive power reached the required reference values. This was done in order to ensure effective tracking of the optimum operating point and the maximum output of electrical power. System modeling and simulation were examined in Matlab/Simulink. Dynamic analysis of the system was performed under variable wind speed.

Keywords-Genetic Algorithm (GA); fuzzy logic controller (FC); Doubly Fed Induction Generator (DFIG); variable speed wind turbine; conventional PI controller; Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT)

I. INTRODUCTION

Globally, wind power has become the fastest growing renewable energy source. Wind turbine speed control is generally used to improve energy production. DFIG-based wind power transmission systems offer various advantages, including reducing stress on mechanical structures and acoustic noise with the ability to control active and reactive energy. Another feature of the DFIG system is that the connected AC/DC/AC PWM transformers between the grid and the

rotating circuit of the induction generator are designed for only a portion of the generator power [1]. Wind power generation implementation was introduced on the basis of DFIG, a fuzzy PI gain scheduling developed for DFIG vector control units used in variable speed wind turbines [2]. Upon theoretical analysis of the wind turbine and DFIG processing, due to mathematical models of the system, a DFIG separation control was developed based on a fuzzy-PI controller in [3]. Wind power generation by DFIG can be connected directly to the grid via the stator, which is driven by a direct AC/DC inverter. The relative complexities (in size or structure) of the research space and the function to be improved lead to the use of radically different precision methods [4].

While the stochastic methods are the more efficient and effective, they use processes based on stochastic exploration of the space of possible solutions [5]. Among the latter, we find Genetic Algorithms (GAs) that represent a rich and interesting family of stochastic optimization algorithms. They are inspired by concepts of evolution and natural selection and the probabilistic research based on the mechanism of natural selection and genetics. GAs are highly effective and robust in a general set of problems. GAs maintain a set of encoded solutions and this group is geared towards the optimal solution [6]. In order to find an ideal solution to a problem in a complex space, it is necessary to find a compromise between two goals: to explore better solutions and to aggressively exploit the search space. Analytical studies have shown that GAs manage this trade-off optimally [7].

II. DFIG MODEL WITH STATOR FLUX ORIENTATION

The orientation of the voltage and the stator flux is shown in Figure 1.

The DFIG electrical state can be modeled using the Park transform, as follows [8]:

Corresponding author: Abdelhafid Guediri

$$\begin{cases} V_{sd} = R_s I_{sd} + \frac{d\varphi_{sd}}{dt} \\ V_{sq} = R_s I_{sq} + \omega_s \varphi_{sd} \\ V_{rd} = R_r I_{rd} + \frac{d\varphi_{rd}}{dt} - (\omega_s - \omega) \varphi_{rq} \\ V_{rq} = R_r I_{rq} + \frac{d\varphi_{rq}}{dt} + (\omega_s - \omega) \varphi_{rd} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{cases} \varphi_{sd} = L_s I_{sd} + M I_{rd} = \varphi_s \\ \varphi_{sq} = L_s I_{sq} + M I_{rq} = 0 \\ \varphi_{rd} = L_r I_{rd} + M I_{sd} \\ \varphi_{rq} = L_r I_{rq} + M I_{sq} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Direction of stator voltage and flux.

To obtain separate control over the stator reactive and active forces, the DFIG model is required to express all quantities. This is in accordance with the concept of stator flow direction and assumes that the stator resistance is small compared to the stator reactance of a DFIG of medium and high power volume, where the stator flux can be computed as [9]:

$$\begin{cases} V_{sd} = \frac{d\varphi_{sd}}{dt} = 0 \\ V_{sq} = \omega_s \varphi_{sd} = V_s \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\varphi_s = \frac{V_s}{\omega_s} \quad (4)$$

From the system of equations (2), we obtain:

$$\begin{cases} I_{sd} = \frac{\varphi_s}{L_s} - \frac{M}{L_s} I_{rd} \\ I_{sq} = -\frac{M}{L_s} I_{rq} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The stator reactive forces for DFIG are:

$$\begin{cases} P_s = V_{sq} I_{sq} \\ Q_s = V_{sd} I_{sd} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{cases} P_s = -V_s \frac{M}{L_s} I_{rq} \\ Q_s = \frac{V_s \varphi_s}{L_s} - \frac{V_s M}{L_s} I_{rd} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The electromagnetic torque is expressed as:

$$C_{em} = -p \frac{M}{L_s} \varphi_s I_{rq} \quad (8)$$

The relationship of rotor voltage is given as:

$$\begin{cases} V_{rd} = R_r I_{rd} - g \omega_s (L_r - \frac{M^2}{L_s}) I_{rq} \\ V_{rq} = R_r I_{rq} + g \omega_s (L_r - \frac{M^2}{L_s}) I_{rd} + g \omega_s \frac{M \varphi_s}{L_s} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

III. INDIRECT CLOSED LOOP FUZZY CONTROL

In this method, decoupling is performed at the level of the outputs of the rotor current regulators with system feedback. This allows the regulation of powers. One thus distinguishes a control by a loop in a cascade of the power and the rotor current for each axis, since this makes possible to separately control the currents I_{rd} and I_{rq} and the powers P_s and Q_s in a closed loop [10]. According to the reference torque delivered by the Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) control, the rotor side converter guarantees a decoupled active and reactive stator power control, P_s and Q_s (MPPT). By holding the DC bus at a steady voltage level and imposing the reactive power Q_L at zero, the grid side converter controls the power flow exchange with the grid through the rotor [11]. The simplified diagram of this control assembly is illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Indirect closed loop fuzzy control diagram.

IV. FUZZY INFERENCE RULES

The rules of inference can be described in several ways, either linguistically, symbolically or by inference matrix. In the latter case, a so-called inference matrix brings together all the inference rules in the form of a table. In the case of a two dimensional array, the array entries represent fuzzy sets of the input variables [12].

TABLE I. RULE TABLE OF THE FUZZY CONTROLLER

ΔU		E						
		NG	NM	NP	EZ	PP	PM	PG
Δe	NG	NG	NG	NG	NM	NP	NP	EZ
	NM	NG	NM	NM	NM	NP	EZ	PP
	NP	NG	NM	NP	NP	EZ	PP	PM
	EZ	NG	NM	NP	EZ	PP	PM	PG
	PP	NM	NP	EZ	PP	PP	PM	PG
	PM	NP	EZ	PP	PM	PM	PM	PG
	PG	EZ	PP	PP	PM	PG	PG	PG

The linguistic variables are noted as follows: NG for large negative, NP for small negative, EZ for approximately zero, PP for small positive, PG for large positive, NM for mean negative, and PM for mean positive. E is the error, Δe is the

error variation, and ΔU the controller output. The table gives forty-nine rules. For example:

R1 : IF E = NG AND Δe = NG THEN ΔU = NG.

V. DESCRIPTION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE FUZZY CONTROLLER

Our goal is to control the rotor currents of a dual-power DFIG. The developed controller uses the scheme proposed by [13]. This diagram is represented by Figure 3. The output of the regulator is given by:

$$V_{rd}^v = V_{rd}^v(k - 1) + du(k) \quad (10)$$

Fig. 3. Block diagram of the fuzzy controller.

The considered uses of the fuzzy controller include [14]:

- The triangular and trapezoidal membership functions. This choice is done due to the simplicity of implementation.
- A universe of standardized discourses.
- The universe of discourses is divided into seven fuzzy sets (fine tuning) for the input and output variables. A very fine subdivision of this universe on more than seven fuzzy sets does not generally bring any improvement in the dynamic behavior of the system to be regulated.
- Mamdani's [13] implication for inference.
- The center of gravity method for defuzzification.

For every gene that mutates, we take numbers τ and r . The first can take the values +1 for an effective alternate and -1 for a negative trade. The second is a randomly generated range within the variety (0 1). It determines the value of the trade. Under those conditions, the C'_i gene, which replaces the mutated gene, is calculated from one of the following relationships [15]:

$$\begin{cases} C'_i = C_i + (C_{\max} - C_i) \left(1 - r \left(1 - \frac{GF}{GT}\right)^5\right) & \text{if } \tau = +1 \\ C'_i = C_i - (C_i - C_{\min}) \left(1 - r \left(1 - \frac{GF}{GT}\right)^5\right) & \text{if } \tau = -1 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where C_{\max} and C_{\min} denote, respectively, the lower and higher limits of the price of the parameter C_i , and $GF \leq GT$ represents the era for which the amplitude of the mutation cancels out.

The procedure for optimizing the parameters of the regulators can be summarized by the following steps [16]:

- Randomly generate an initial population.
- Evaluate this population.
- Apply genetic operators (selection, crossing, mutation).

- Evaluate the new population created by the genetic operators.

In the following, we will apply this procedure to the two regulators, classical PI and fuzzy PI. Hybridization method: simplex. The complete control diagram is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 4. Principle of optimization by genetic gradient or simplex algorithm.

Fig. 5. Global block diagram of the command of the GA based on DFIG.

VI. COMPARISON OF THE CLASSIC GA AND FUZZY-PI REGULATOR

Fuzzy logic or fuzzy set theory has attracted the attention of a large number of researchers. Fuzzy logic control is regarded higher than the GA because it does not require precise mathematical models of the system [17]. Its strength and simplicity are the primary reasons for its use. In this work, we will develop a blur controller. The feasibility and performance of this controller have been verified in simulations of the control element that controls the exchange of active and reactive powers generated by an asynchronous machine with a dual power supply connected to a medium voltage network by acting on rotor signals via a bidirectional converter. The obtained numerical simulation results prove the growing interest in such control of electrical systems [18]. Tuning by fuzzy logic may override tuning by PI with respect to the quality of the dynamic response of the system. Indeed, the latter further reduces the response time by producing a limited overshoot accompanied by weak oscillations around the setpoint. In steady state, the precision is not as good as that of a PI regulator, where the integral action eliminates the static error; this then suggests the combination of the two types of regulators:

- A fuzzy regulator for the transient regime and
- a PI regulator for the steady state.

The major drawback of fuzzy regulators is the matching of gains, ensuring system stability. In addition, the order is calculated only from two values: the error and its variation [19].

VII. SIMULATION RESULTS

The results of the wind energy system simulation (turbine + DFIG) are controlled by fuzzy logic and GA. This paper displays the results of the different curves obtained by controlling the energetic and reactive forces generated at the stator level of the DFIG. This allows separating the expressions of the active and reactive powers of the generator or bears those of the flow and torque. The system first starts up without load. Then, an active reference force is applied:

Active power:

- Between $t = 0\text{s}$ and $t = 0.2\text{s}$ ($P_{ref} = 0 \text{ VAR}$).
- Between $t = 0.2\text{s}$ and $t = 0.6\text{s}$ negative scale ($P_{ref} = -5000\text{W}$).
- Between $t = 0.6\text{s}$ and $t = 1\text{s}$ ($P_{ref} = 0\text{W}$).

Reactive power:

- Between $t = 0\text{s}$ and $t = 0.2\text{s}$ ($Q_{ref} = 0 \text{ VAR}$).
- Between $t = 0.2\text{s}$ and $t = 0.6\text{s}$ negative scale ($Q_{ref} = -5000 \text{ VAR}$).
- Between $t = 0.6\text{s}$ and $t = 1\text{s}$ ($Q_{ref} = 0 \text{ VAR}$).

The simulation results will allow the analysis of the behavior of DFIG magnitudes for the stator flow direction with reactive force control and rotational speed adjustment in order to maximize the active energy provided by the stator windings. For this, Matlab-Simulink was used. Figures 6 and 7 show the simulation results of the active and reactive stator forces. According to these Figures, the measured stator forces follow their active references. It is noted that this difference affects the direct rotor current, I_{rd} , and does not affect the rotor current I_{rq} , which explains why there is a separation between the active power and the I_{rd} current.

Fig. 6. Stator active power (W).

Fig. 7. Stator reactive power (VAR).

Fig. 8. The direct current of the rotor (A).

Fig. 9. The quadrature current of the rotor (A).

Fig. 10. The direct current of the stator (A).

Figures 8 and 9 show the simulation results of rotating currents along the d and q axes. Figures 10 and 11 show the simulation results of the stator currents along the d and q axes.

Fig. 11. The quadrature current of the stator (A).

VIII. DISCUSSION AND COMPARISON WITH OTHER WORKS

The novelty of this work is the application of GA to DFIG and its comparison with the traditional PI regulator and fuzzy logic, where in previously published works the comparison between the traditional and fuzzy regulators was made only in addition to the improvement in the obtained results. Good results were obtained compared to previously published works .

- The base table of the mysterious console was a 7×7 table, while in previously published works it was applied to a 5×5 table.
- The number of iterations increased in order to obtain more precise and better results in terms of error compared to previously published works. For a smaller number of iterations, the results were less precise. Figure 12 shows the improvement of the objective function applied to these results.

Fig. 12. Optimization of the objective function.

IX. MATLAB SIMULATION CODE

```
KP_p=kp_pmin+(kp_pmax-kp_pmin)*kp_pde/Gmax;
KP_i=kp_imin+(kp_imax-kp_imin)*kp_ide/Gmax;
KI_p=ki_pmin+(ki_pmax-ki_pmin)*ki_pde/Gmax;
KI_i=ki_imin+(ki_imax-ki_imin)*ki_ide/Gmax;
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
SELECTION AND CROSSING
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
[fun,index]= fate (fan);
for i1=1:NC/2
    paron(i1,:)=POP(index(i1),:);
```

```
end
Lu=randsrc(1,1,[1:NB-1]);
child (1:NC/4,:)=[paron(1:NC/4,1:Lu)
paron(NC/4+1:NC/2,Lu+1:NB)];
child (NC/4+1:NC/2,:)=[paron(NC/4+1:NC/2,1:Lu)
paron(1:NC/4,Lu+1:NB)];
POP=[paron ; child];
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
MUTATION
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
Mu=rand(NC,NB);
for i=1:NC
    for j=1:NB
        if Mu(i,j)<=pm
            if POP(i,j)==1
                POP(i,j)=0;
            else
                POP(i,j)=1;
            end
        end
    end
end
end
i9=i9+1;
fanf(i9)=Val;
end
figure
stud (funf,'-o')
title(' Function optimization objective ')
xlabel ('Itération')
ylabel ('Function')
grid
```

X. CONTROL LAW

This law is a function of the error and its variation (u = f(e, Δe)). It is given by:

$$u_{k+1} = u_k + G_{\Delta u} \cdot \Delta u_{k+1} \quad (12)$$

where $G_{\Delta u}$ is the gain associated with the order u_{k+1} and Δu_{k+1} is the variation of the order. Error e and the variation of the error Δe are normalized as follows:

$$\begin{cases} x_e = G_e \cdot e \\ x_{\Delta e} = G_{\Delta e} \cdot \Delta e \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where G_e and $G_{\Delta e}$ are the scaling (normalization) factors. We vary these factors until we can have a transient phenomenon of suitable adjustment. Indeed, it is the latter, which will determine the performance of the command.

XI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a fuzzy logic controller and an active and interacting GA connected to a stator network (DFIG) are considered. The fuzzy controller's effectiveness test against GA and conventional PI control under different operating conditions showed the optimum and effective performance of fuzzy controller in terms of changing rotor resistance, insensitivity to torque disturbance, low response time, accuracy, and overtaking speed, as well as faster dynamics with little error in steady state under all dynamic operating

conditions. The simulation results showed good control behavior directed towards better performance of the fuzzy controller. Its superiority is particularly evident compared to the performance of the traditional control system and the GA. However, we can observe the appearance of a small error in the response of the system controlled by this type of control. The reason for this error is that the adaptation law is not fast enough to detect sudden changes in wind speed. This drawback can be limited by short sampling time. However, this choice can increase calculation time. In practice, good continuity of control allows saves energy (increases energy efficiency), increases component service life, and system performance, with more efficiency and stability.

APPENDIX

PARAMETERS OF 1.5 MW DFIG

Symbol	Parameter	Value
P_n	Rated power	1.5MW
V_s	Stator voltage	300V
F_s	Stator frequency	50Hz
R_s	Stator resistance	0.012 Ω
L_s	Stator leakage inductance	0.0205H
R_r	Rotor resistance	0.021 Ω
L_r	Rotor leakage inductance	0.0204H
M	Mutual inductance	0.0169H
P	Pairs of poles number	2
J	Rotor inertia	1000Kg.m ²

PARAMETERS OF THE TURBINE

Symbol	Parameters	Value
R	Blade radius	35.25m
N	Number of blades	3
G	Gearbox ratio	90
J	Moment of inertia	1000Kg.m ²
f_v	Viscous friction coefficient	0.0024N.m.s ⁻¹
V	Nominal wind speed	16m/s
V_d	Cut-in wind speed	4m/s
V_m	Cut-out wind speed	25m/s

REFERENCES

- [1] A. K. Guediri and D. Ben Attous, "Modeling and fuzzy control of a wind energy system based on double-fed asynchronous machine for supply of power to the electrical network," *International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 353–360, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13198-015-0367-1>.
- [2] P. D. Chung, "Retaining of Frequency in Micro-grid with Wind Turbine and Diesel Generator," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3646–3651, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2413>.
- [3] A. Guediri and A. Guediri, "Study and Order of a Medium Power Wind Turbine Conversion Chain Connected to Medium Voltage Grid," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7279–7282, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4169>.
- [4] Md. R. Islam, Y. Guo, and J. G. Zhu, "Steady state characteristic simulation of DFIG for wind power system," in *International Conference on Electrical Computer Engineering (ICECE 2010)*, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Sep. 2010, pp. 151–154, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICELCE.2010.5700649>.
- [5] O. P. Bharti, R. K. Saket, and S. K. Nagar, "Controller Design For DFIG Driven By Variable Speed Wind Turbine Using Static Output Feedback Technique," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 1056–1061, Aug. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.697>.
- [6] R. Saini, P. Pratim Roy, and D. Prosad Dogra, "A segmental HMM based trajectory classification using genetic algorithm," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 93, pp. 169–181, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2017.10.021>.
- [7] A. J. P. Delima, A. M. Sison, and R. P. Medina, "A modified genetic algorithm with a new crossover mating scheme," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Informatics (IJEI)*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 165–181, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.52549/ijeel.v7i2.1047>.
- [8] H. Bassi and Y. A. Mobarak, "State-Space Modeling and Performance Analysis of Variable-Speed Wind Turbine Based on a Model Predictive Control Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1436–1443, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1015>.
- [9] I. Yaichi, A. Semmah, P. Wira, and Y. Djeriri, "Super-twisting Sliding Mode Control of a Doubly-fed Induction Generator Based on the SVM Strategy," *Periodica Polytechnica Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 63, no. 3, pp. 178–190, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.3311/PPee.13726>.
- [10] Z. Kara and K. Barra, "Hybrid Controller for Variable Speed Wind Energy Conversion System with Slip Energy Recovery Using Matrix Converter Topology," *Periodica Polytechnica Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 59, no. 4, pp. 160–174, Dec. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.3311/PPee.8507>.
- [11] S. Mondal and D. Kastha, "Improved Direct Torque and Reactive Power Control of a Matrix-Converter-Fed Grid-Connected Doubly Fed Induction Generator," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 62, no. 12, pp. 7590–7598, Sep. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2015.2459056>.
- [12] W. Guo, F. Liu, D. He, J. Si, R. Harley, and S. Mei, "Reactive power control of DFIG wind farm using online supplementary learning controller based on approximate dynamic programming," in *2014 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, Beijing, China, Jul. 2014, pp. 1453–1460, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IJCNN.2014.6889871>.
- [13] S. A. E. M. Ardjoun and M. Abid, "Fuzzy sliding mode control applied to a doubly fed induction generator for wind turbines," *Turkish Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Sciences*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 1673–1686, Nov. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.3906/elk-1404-64>.
- [14] J. Yang, D. Song, H. Han, P. Tong, and L. Zhou, "The integrated control of fuzzy logic and model-based approach for variable-speed wind turbine," *Turkish Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Sciences*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 1715–1734, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.3906/elk-1403-295>.
- [15] L. Sun, Y. Chen, L. Peng, Y. Zhang, and Y. Kang, "Control winding current-oriented control for stand-alone brushless doubly fed power generation system," in *2015 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, Montreal, Canada, Sep. 2015, pp. 2776–2781, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ECCE.2015.7310049>.
- [16] K. Wiktorowicz, "Output Feedback Direct Adaptive Fuzzy Controller Based on Frequency-Domain Methods," *IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 622–634, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TFUZZ.2015.2466111>.
- [17] K. Siraj, H. Siraj, and M. Nasir, "Modeling and control of a doubly fed induction generator for grid integrated wind turbine," in *2014 16th International Power Electronics and Motion Control Conference and Exposition*, Antalya, Turkey, Sep. 2014, pp. 901–906, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EPEPEMC.2014.6980613>.
- [18] Y. Belgaid, M. Helaimi, R. Taleb, and M. B. Youcef, "Optimal tuning of PI controller using genetic algorithm for wind turbine application," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 167–178, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijeecs.v18.i1.pp167-178>.
- [19] I. Sefa, N. Altin, S. Ozdemir, and O. Kaplan, "Fuzzy PI controlled inverter for grid interactive renewable energy systems," *IET Renewable Power Generation*, vol. 9, no. 7, pp. 729–738, 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-rpg.2014.0404>.

JAYA Algorithm-Optimized Load Frequency Control of a Four-Area Interconnected Power System Tuning Using PID Controller

Sunita Pahadasingh

School of Electrical Engineering
Kalinga Institute of Industrial Technology Deemed to be
University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India
spahadasingh@gmail.com

Chitralkha Jena

School of Electrical Engineering
Kalinga Institute of Industrial Technology Deemed to be
University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India
chitralkha.jenafel@kiit.ac.in

Chinmoy Kumar Panigrahi

School of Electrical Engineering
Kalinga Institute of Industrial Technology Deemed to be
University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India
panigrahichinmoy@gmail.com

Bibhu Prasad Ganthia

Electrical Engineering Department
Indira Gandhi Institute of Technology
Sarang, Odisha, India
jb.bibhu@gmail.com

Received: 8 March 2022 | Revised: 26 March 2022 and 30 March 2022 | Accepted: 1 April 2022

Abstract-This study examined the design of a Load Frequency Control (LFC) component in a four-area interconnected power system. LFC maintains the frequency of a power system within a prescribed limit. Various controllers for the LFC of a power system have been proposed. The PID controller is a classical approach to LFC. A PID controller that uses a filter in the derivative part amplifies and smooths out the high-frequency noise. The selection of the appropriate optimization method to tune controller gains plays a vital role for LFC. In this work, the PID controller was optimized using the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and the JAYA optimization methods and was simulated in Matlab-Simulink. After studying and comparing the results, it was concluded that the PID controller using the JAYA algorithm provided better LFC in terms of system settling time, overshoot, undershoot, and performance index compared to other optimization methods.

Keywords-load frequency control; AGC; tie line; PIDN; PSO; JAYA

I. INTRODUCTION

An electric power system is a sequential arrangement of components to generate, transmit, distribute, and utilize power while continuously protecting it [1]. A power system has two important parameters that need to be constantly monitored and corrected: voltage and frequency. A generator generates power at some voltage and frequency, and these parameters should be controlled when there is a mismatch between active or reactive power generation and demand [2]. There are basically two methods to perform such control. When the active power demand is not equal to the active power generation, the frequency should be controlled, and when the reactive power demand is not equal to the reactive power generation, the

voltage should be controlled [3]. Control of voltage and frequency can be performed in two ways, which are the primary and secondary control mechanisms. The primary control mechanism examines the aspects of generation, as generation remains constant most of the time while demand varies [5]. In the primary control mechanism, the Automatic Generation Control (AGC) has to match the demand by varying the generation. But in emergency conditions, where it is not possible to control generations, the load should be controlled, which is known as the load side management [6]. AGC can control voltage as well as frequency, i.e. load frequency control plus excitation control [7]. In AGC, there is a generator that generates active power P_g and reactive power Q_g . The generator gets input power from a turbine, and the turbine gets input power from the boiler [8]. While the steam comes from the boiler, there is a governor valve placed in the boiler to control the steam. When the active power is delivered to the bus, there is a comparator that receives and senses the frequency f_g coming from the generator [9]. The comparator has a reference frequency f_{ref} , which has to be maintained, and if there is any difference between f_g and f_{ref} , there will be an error f_e which will be operated by the generator valve. This whole closed loop is the LFC [10].

II. INTERCONNECTED SYSTEM

The operation of more than one interconnected areas is known as an interconnected system or power pool or pool operation [12]. Under normal operating conditions, each control area carries its own load and each control area adopts beneficial regulating and control strategies. These are two basic operating principles of a multi-control area system [11]. Unlike a small system, where a sudden change in load causes a large

Corresponding author: Bibhu Prasad Ganthia

frequency drop and could result in a system blackout, the interconnected systems don't have these problems. In an interconnected power system, a sudden change in load causes a large frequency drop [13]. Peak demands occur at various hours of the day in various areas of an interconnected system, so the ratio of peak to average load is smaller than that of an individual load. A control area in an interconnected system is characterized by the same frequency throughout, and the frequency deviations in different areas are represented as $\Delta F1, \Delta F2, \Delta F3, \dots$. In an interconnected system, each area has a generator, a speed governing system, and a turbine. Each area has three inputs, i.e. the controller input (ΔP_{ref}), load distribution (ΔP_D), and tie-line power error (ΔP_{tie}) [14]. Each area has two outputs, which are the generator frequency (ΔF) and the Area Control Error (ACE), which is the signal fed into the integrator:

$$ACE = B\Delta F + \Delta P_{tie} \quad (1)$$

where B is the frequency bias parameter.

Fig. 1. Simulation model of four area power system.

III. PID CONTROLLER WITH DERIVATIVE FILTER

When an interconnected or micro-grid power system is subjected to a change, it is very crucial to adjust the gain parameters of the PID controller [15]. As the PID controller often ignores the noise and non-linear effects, most of the time it does not work properly in practical problems. For this reason, a first-order filter is put on the derivative term to tune it [16], as

it reduces the high-frequency noise and smoothes it out, so chattering due to noise does not occur and the derivative will not reduce the high-frequency noise [17]. The transfer function of the PID controller with derivative filter (PIDN) is given as:

$$TF_{PIDN} = K_p + K_i \left(\frac{1}{s}\right) + K_d \left(\frac{1}{N+s}\right) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2. Simulink model of PIDN controller.

IV. PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION METHOD

In PSO, a particle is each member of a population, called a swarm. Each particle has a velocity in a given direction [18], similar to the speed of a bird in the direction of food. Each particle searches for the optimal value by an updating generation (iteration). In each iteration, every particle is updated by following the two best values. The best one is the best solution (fitness), while the second best is tracked by the PSO optimizer. After finding the two best values, the velocity and position have to be updated for each particle, using:

$$x_i^{t+1} = x_i^t + v_i^t * t \quad (3)$$

$$v_{k+1}^i = wv_k^i + c_1r_1(xBest_i^t - x_i^t) + c_2r_2(gBest_i^t - x_i^t) \quad (4)$$

where $xBest$ is the best particle position and $gBest$ is the best global position. The best global position is the main strategy that all birds follow because this is the position of the bird closest to the food. The parameter w is the inertia weight. This is the main key factor, as it has the major role to change the position of each particle in the search space, from the previous position to a new one by updating velocity. c_1, c_2 are two positive constants, and r_1, r_2 are two random parameters within $[0, 1]$. The current position can be updated by adding the velocity v to the old position:

$$Present = old\ position + velocity\ (v) \quad (5)$$

The main aim of the PSO algorithm is to follow the bird which is closest to the food. Its main steps are given below:

- Step 1: Initialize the parameters and the population. At first, initialize the position x_i and velocity v_i randomly for each particle.
- Step 2: Compute the fitness value $f(x_i^t)$ of each particle, and choose the particle with the best fitness value $gBest$.

- Step 3: Update the position and velocity of each particle, by (3) and (4).
- Step 4: Check again the fitness value $f(x_i^t)$ and then find again the best global $gBest$.
- Step 5: Update $t = t + 1$.
- Step 6: the output comes as $gBest$ and x_i^t

Fig. 3. Flowchart of PSO algorithm.

V. JAYA OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUE

JAYA is a specific parameter-less algorithm. This algorithm was formulated to solve various constrained or unconstrained optimization problems. Its concept is based on the fact that the solution for a given particular problem should move towards its best solution, as its major objective is victory, meaning that it should avoid the worst solution [19, 20]. JAYA has some control parameters, such as population size and the number of generations. However, unlike other algorithms, JAYA does not have any specific parameters. For example in PSO, the inertia coefficient w and c_1, c_2, r_1 , and r_2 have to be updated. But in the case of the JAYA algorithm, such specific parameters are not required to obtain the optimal solution. The terms used in the JAYA algorithm are iteration, design variable, candidate solution, best and worst values for the

solution, modified solution, and update solution. The JAYA algorithm can be described as follows:

- Let $f(x)$ be the objective function
- Minimize/maximize $f(x)$:

$$l_i \leq x_j \leq u_j, \quad j=1,2,3 \dots m$$
- At any iteration t , assume there are m design variables and n candidate solutions.

- For n values,
 - $f(x)_{best}$ is the best value of $f(x)$
 - $f(x)_{worst}$ is the worst value of $f(x)$
- The fitness value can be computed from $n \times m$.
- $X_{j,k}$ is the value of the j^{th} variable for the k^{th} candidate.
- $X_{j,k}^t$ is the value of the variable during the t iteration.
- X_{best} is the best value of the variable.
- X_{worst} is the worst value of the variable.
- The position update equation is given by:

$$X_{new} = X_{j,k} + r_1(X_{best} - |X_{j,k}|) - r_2(X_{worst} - |X_{j,k}|)$$
- X_{new} is the updated value of the variable $X_{j,k}$.
- r_1, r_2 are two random numbers between 0 to 1.
- $r_1(X_{best} - |X_{j,k}|)$ is the tendency of the solution to move closer to the best solution.
- $-r_2(X_{worst} - |X_{j,k}|)$ is the tendency of the solution to avoid the worst solution.

- Concerning the t iteration:

$$X_{new}^t = X_{j,k}^t + r_1(X_{best}^t - |X_{j,k}^t|) - r_2(X_{best}^t - |X_{j,k}^t|)$$
- Now, a greedy selection has to be made, by comparing the obtained solution with the previous one, to check whether the obtained solution is better or not.
- For minimization, if $f_{new} < f_{old}$ update the solution, otherwise not.
- For maximization, if $f_{old} < f_{new}$ update the solution, otherwise not.
- $f_{new} = f(x_{new})$ is the fitness value at x_{new} , and f_i is the previous fitness value at x_i . For minimization, if $f_{new} < f_i$ then replace x_i with x_{new} and f_i with f_{new} . For maximization, if $f_{new} > f_i$ then replace x_i with x_{new} and f_i with f_{new} .
- The algorithm stops when the number of iterations reaches its maximum value.

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the JAYA algorithm.

VI. SIMULINK RESULTS

Figure 5 shows the four-area model with a PID controller. Figure 6 represents the Jaya optimization in PID controller gain for the frequency control in each area of the AGC. Figure 7 represents the JAYA optimization in PIDN controller gain for the frequency control in each area of the AGC. The controller block tuned the gains for the optimized data set for the JAYA algorithm and the frequency of each area of the AGC controlled concerning the demand of the grid. The deviation in frequency and the corresponding tie-line power were investigated. The value of the proportional, integral, and derivative constants, the derivative filter, and an objective function were obtained after optimizing using the PSO and then the JAYA methods. The efficacy of the JAYA-based PID controller with the derivative filter was shown by comparing it with the PSO simulation result. The changes in frequency and the corresponding tie-line deviations under load disturbance of 0.1p.u in four areas are shown in Figures 8-11, for JAYA, PSO, and GA methods. The JAYA method minimized the error

during the controller objective function operation in the system model of AGC.

Fig. 5. Four area model with PID controller.

Fig. 6. JAYA optimization with PID controller.

Fig. 7. PIDN controller block for frequency control in AGC.

Fig. 8. Frequency response of area 1 using PID controller

Fig. 9. Frequency response of area 2 using PID controller.

Fig. 10. Frequency response of area 3 using PID controller.

Fig. 11. Frequency response of area 4 using PID controller.

TABLE I. TUNED PID CONTROLLER GAINS

Controller Gains	PSO	JAYA
Kp1	0.0112	0.0218
Ki1	6.5402	2.7319
Kd1	3.7943	4.7272
ITAE1	4.7943	4.7272
Kp2	0.2176	0.2762
Ki2	3.2531	2.4062
Kd2	5.7291	5.4251
ITAE2	5.7291	5.4251
Kp3	0.0221	0.2373
Ki3	4.6011	2.1165
Kd3	4.1982	3.4231
ITAE3	4.1982	3.4231
Kp4	0.0262	0.0254
Ki4	4.7198	2.3068
Kd4	3.6846	3.3076
ITAE4	3.6846	3.3076

VII. DISCUSSION

From Figures 8-11, it is clear that the settling time for the JAYA optimization method is faster than for GA and PSO optimizations. The frequency variation is less by 18-20% when using the proposed controller method. The gains were limited by the optimization method and the errors were reduced by 8% for area 1, and 11% for area 2. The frequency deviation error was reduced by 4% in area 3 and 6% in area 4. The PID-controlled JAYA optimization method improved the transient stability of the multi-area system by 14% of rated values.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study used a PSO and a JAYA optimized PID controller in a four-area power system. The proposed method was compared to traditional control algorithms. A PID controller was used to examine the results of the proposed method. Simulations were carried out in Matlab-Simulink. It was observed that the JAYA tuned PID controller exhibited better performance than PSO and GA in terms of settling time, peak overshoot, and undershoot. Thus, the JAYA-based PID controller helped maximize the power quality of the AGC. Further analysis of this topic can be carried out using different optimization methods. Different controllers, like the fractional order proportional derivative controllers (PIDN) (FOPID), and FOPID (1+PI) can be tested for improved ALFC in a power system.

APPENDIX

$f = 50\text{Hz}$, $B_1 = B_2 = B_3 = B_4 = 0.425\text{pu MW/Hz}$, $PR = 1,000\text{MW}$ (rating), $PL=1,500\text{MW}$ (nominal loading), $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = 2.4\text{Hz/p.u. MW}$, $T_{G1} = T_{G2} = T_{G3} = T_{G4} = 0.08$, $T_{T1} = T_{T2} = T_{T3} = T_{T4} = 0.03$, $T_{P1} = T_{P2} = T_{P3} = T_{P4} = 20$, $K = -1$, $T_{12} = T_{23} = T_{34} = T_{41} = 0.545$.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Shankar, S. R. Pradhan, K. Chatterjee, and R. Mandal, "A comprehensive state of the art literature survey on LFC mechanism for power system," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 76, pp. 1185–1207, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.02.064>.
- [2] N. N. Shah, A. D. Chafekar, D. N. Mehta, and A. R. Suthar, "Automatic Load Frequency Control of two Area Power System with Conventional and Fuzzy Logic Control," *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 343–347, Mar. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.15623/ijret.2012.0103026>.
- [3] K. M. Passino and N. Quijano, "Proportional-Integral-Derivative Control with Derivative Filtering and Integral Anti-Windup for a DC Servo," Ohio State University, Columbus, OH, USA, Mar. 2002.
- [4] A. Dhamanda, A. Dutt, and A. K. Bhardwaj, "Automatic Generation Control in Four Area Interconnected Power System of Thermal Generating Unit through Evolutionary Technique," *International Journal on Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 569–583, Dec. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.15676/ijeie.2015.7.4.3>.
- [5] B. Mohanty, S. Panda, and P. K. Hota, "Controller parameters tuning of differential evolution algorithm and its application to load frequency control of multi-source power system," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 54, pp. 77–85, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2013.06.029>.
- [6] Y. del Valle, G. K. Venayagamoorthy, S. Mohagheghi, J.-C. Hernandez, and R. G. Harley, "Particle Swarm Optimization: Basic Concepts, Variants and Applications in Power Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 171–195, Apr. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2007.896686>.

- [7] B. P. Ganthia, S. K. Barik, and B. Nayak, "Shunt Connected FACTS Devices for LVRT Capability Enhancement in WECS," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5819–5823, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3560>.
- [8] W. F. Abd-El-Wahed, A. A. Mousa, and M. A. El-Shorbagy, "Integrating particle swarm optimization with genetic algorithms for solving nonlinear optimization problems," *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 235, no. 5, pp. 1446–1453, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cam.2010.08.030>.
- [9] B. Alatas, E. Akin, and A. B. Ozer, "Chaos embedded particle swarm optimization algorithms," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 1715–1734, May 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2007.09.063>.
- [10] R. Rao, "Jaya: A simple and new optimization algorithm for solving constrained and unconstrained optimization problems," *International Journal of Industrial Engineering Computations*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 19–34, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ijiec.2015.8.004>.
- [11] A. S. Alshammari, B. M. Alshammari, T. Guesmi, and R. Abbassi, "Evaluation Framework of the Deficit and Reliability Quality Measures of the Transmission System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 6930–6934, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4074>.
- [12] S. A. Dayo, S. H. Memon, M. A. Uqaili, and Z. A. Memon, "LVRT Enhancement of a Grid-tied PMSG-based Wind Farm using Static VAR Compensator," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7146–7151, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4147>.
- [13] P. D. Chung, "Smoothing the Power Output of a Wind Turbine Group with a Compensation Strategy of Power Variation," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7343–7348, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4234>.
- [14] L. B. Raju and K. S. Rao, "Evaluation of Passive Islanding Detection Methods for Line to Ground Unsymmetrical Fault in Three Phase Microgrid Systems: Microgrid Islanding Detection Method," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7591–7597, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4310>.
- [15] G. A. Alshammari, F. A. Alshammari, T. Guesmi, B. M. Alshammari, A. S. Alshammari, and N. A. Alshammari, "A New Particle Swarm Optimization Based Strategy for the Economic Emission Dispatch Problem Including Wind Energy Sources," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7585–7590, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4279>.
- [16] T. Lachumanan, R. Singh, M. I. Shapiai, and T. J. S. Anand, "Analysis of a Multilevel Voltage-Based Coordinating Controller for Solar-Wind Energy Generator: A Simulation, Development and Validation Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7793–7799, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4489>.
- [17] C. L. Wadhwa, *Electrical Power System*, 7th edition. New Delhi, India: New Age International, 2017.
- [18] H. Saarat, *Power System Analysis*. New Delhi, India: WCB McGraw-Hill, 1999.
- [19] B. P. Ganthia, A. Pritam, K. Rout, S. Singhsamant, and J. Nayak, "Study of AGC in Two-Area Hydro-thermal Power System," in *Advances in Power Systems and Energy Management: ETAEERE-2016*, A. Garg, A. K. Bhoi, P. Sanjeevikumar, and K. K. Kamani, Eds. Singapore: Springer, 2018, pp. 393–401.
- [20] A. Pritam, S. Sahu, S. D. Rout, S. Ganthia, and B. P. Ganthia, "Automatic Generation Control Study in Two Area Reheat Thermal Power System," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 225, Dec. 2017, Art. no. 012223, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/225/1/012223>.

AUTHORS PROFILE

Sunita Pahadasingh is working on her Ph.D. in the School of Electrical Engineering, Kalinga Institute of Industrial Technology, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India. Her research area is AGC smart grids.

Chitralkha Jena, is an assistant professor in the School of Electrical Engineering, Kalinga Institute of Industrial Technology, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India.

Chinmoay Kumar Panigrahi, is a professor in the School of Electrical Engineering, Kalinga Institute of Industrial Technology, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India.

Bibhu Prasad Ganthia is an assistant professor in the Department of Electrical Engineering, Indira Gandhi Institute of Technology, Sarang, Dhenkanal, Odisha, India. His research areas include renewable energy systems and power system control.

A Comparative Study on Hybrid Vibration Control of Base-isolated Buildings Equipped with ATMD

Mohamed Seghir Jaballah

Laboratory of Development in Mechanics and Materials
Civil Engineering Department
University of Ziane Achour
Djelfa, Algeria
ms.jaballah@univ-djelfa.dz

Salaheddine Harzallah

Built Environmental Research Laboratory, Civil
Engineering Faculty, Sciences and Technology Department
University of Houari Boumediene
Bab Ezzouar, Algeria
sharzallah@usthb.dz

Bachir Nail

Mechanical Engineering, Materials, and Structures Laboratory
Faculty of Science and Technology
Tissemsilt University
Tissemsilt, Algeria
bachir.nail@cuniv-tissemsilt.dz

Received: 28 March 2022 | Revised: 11 April 2022 | Accepted: 14 April 2022

Abstract-The vibration control for building structures using hybrid control (base isolators BI and Active Tuned Mass Dampers-ATMDs) has attracted the attention of researchers. This paper establishes a hybrid vibration control system of structure and compares structural response and active tuned mass damper performance among the structure using two different control algorithms (PID and LQR). Through simulation research, from the comparative analysis of performance indexes of structural response and ATMD performance, it is concluded that the LQR controller outperforms the PID controller in reducing the structural responses.

Keywords-PID control; LQR control; hybrid control; base isolation; ATMD

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the biggest challenges in structural engineering is the development of structural vibration control techniques [1]. With those techniques, structures can be better protected from the damaging effect of destructive environmental forces such as earthquakes, winds, and other external loads [2]. Structural control has been investigated and has shown great results in reducing the vibrations in different civil structures under the effect of dynamic loads [3, 4].

The structural vibration control system can be divided by its method, or the types of devices being used, into four general types: passive control, active control, semi-active control, and hybrid control. A passive system can reduce the vibration energy without the need for external power. It uses a passive mechanism to reduce the response of the structure. This type of control utilizes two methods: seismic base isolation and supplemental damping [5]. Passive control mechanisms include tuned mass (or liquid) damper (TMD/TLD), viscoelastic

damper, base isolation systems, etc. [5-7]. Although the usage of a passive control system is very simple and affordable, it has significant disadvantages, such as being less adaptable to external environmental actions such as earthquakes and winds. The active structural control system uses actuators, sensors mounted at different locations on the structure to measure external excitations and the structural response, and a computer to calculate the appropriate force control. An external power source also is needed for actuators to apply forces to control or to modify the motion of the structure. Active control devices include Active Tendon Systems (ATS), Active Mass Dampers (AMD), active brace systems, etc. [8]. Hybrid structural control systems are excellent vibration control systems, because they combine the reliability of the passive system and the adaptability of the active system [9, 10]. To get the optimal control force, many methods and algorithms have been created. An analytical model for the entire system and a dynamic model of the system are needed, including all its objects such as the structure, sensor, actuators, and controller [11, 12].

In a building structure equipped with an ATMD, a motor based device called actuator applies a force known as control force. One or more actuators apply these forces to a structure according to the control law and use an external energy source for their operation. These forces can be used to add or dissipate energy from the structure to be controlled. To build such a system, there are two radically different approaches: The first is to identify the seismic excitation which creates the vibrations to cancel it out by superimposing an "inverse" excitation on it. This active control strategy is called feedforward. It is mainly developed in acoustics [13, 14], but it is also very useful for the control of vibration of structures. The second is to identify the structure's response rather than the excitement that makes it

Corresponding author: Mohamed Seghir Jaballah

vibrate. It, therefore, requires the modeling of the structure to evaluate its dynamic behavior. The vibration control work that goes into this type of strategy is called feedback loop control. [15].

Fig. 1. Structural vibration control.

Base isolation systems are a well-known application of the passive control approach. These base isolators are placed between the foundations and the superstructure, these devices make it possible to decouple the movement from the ground to the superstructure, the aim of which is to reduce the forces transmitted from the ground. The isolators absorb the ground's shaking energy and filter high-frequency accelerations so that the isolated superstructure moves essentially in a rigid mode undergoing low accelerations and almost no deformations [16]. For this reason, the base isolation system is an effective tool to ensure the seismic protection of rigid structures. To design the appropriate base isolator and to have its optimum performance many parameters should be considered, like the different characteristics of the soil and the location of the structure [17]. LRB (Laminated Rubber Bearings) base isolators are known as one of the most used systems in isolating structures. And therefore, this type was chosen in the current study.

The main purpose of this work is to compare and evaluate two different types of control algorithms (PID and LQR), that control and drive the ATMD. The ATMD will be placed on the top floor because it has been proven that putting it there is a very effective strategy to reduce the structural responses. Our structure will be equipped with base isolators in both cases and the performance of the two systems will be evaluated under the effect of three strong earthquakes (El Centro, Kobe, and Northridge).

II. PID AND LQR CONTROLLERS

A Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) regulator is a control organ that allows carrying out the closed-loop regulation of an industrial process. The regulator compares a value measured on the process with a setpoint. The difference between these two values (the error signal) is then used to calculate a new input value of the process tending to reduce as much as possible the difference between the measurement and the setpoint (lowest possible error signal).

"PID" represents the abbreviations of the three actions it uses to make its corrections: a Proportional action, an Integral action, and a Derivative action. Adjusting this type of controller is often a matter of experience. Its independence

towards the model of the system is a guarantee of robustness when applied to known, linear, and little-variant systems[18].

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int e(t) dt + K_d \frac{de}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where K_p is the proportional gain, K_i is the integral gain, and K_d is the derivative gain.

Fig. 2. The PID controller.

Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) control belongs to the family of optimal control algorithms. In optimum control, a cost function representing a performance index is chosen and then reduced to provide the optimal input. In the quadratic optimum control problem, the cost function can be designed to be quadratically dependent on the control input and the output state or response [19]:

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_0}^{t_f} (x^T Q x + u^T R u) dt \quad (2)$$

where Q is the weighting matrix (output), and R is the control vector (input). The performance index J represents the balance between the structural response and the control energy, the purpose of which is to reduce the response of the structure. The performance index shown in (3) is chosen in such a way, as to minimize the structural response and control energy over the time interval from t_0 to t_f . When the elements of Q are large, the response of the system will be minimized to a large control force. When the elements of R are large, the control force will be small, but the structural response cannot be reduced sufficiently [20, 21].

$$u(t) = -KX(t) \quad (3)$$

K (LQR gain vector) is given by:

$$K = R^{-1} B^T P \quad (4)$$

where P is the solution matrix of Riccati's equation.

Fig. 3. The LQR controller.

The simulation was done in Matlab/Simulink. Three strong historically known earthquakes were used. El Centro (1940), Northridge (1994), and Kobe (1995) earthquakes.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The response results of the isolated, uncontrolled structure were compared to the same structure equipped with an ATMD, using PID and LQR control algorithms. Figures 5-7 show the building's top floor displacement comparison.

Fig. 5. Structural response under El Centro seismic excitation.

Fig. 6. Structural response under Kobe seismic excitation.

Fig. 7. Structural response under Northridge seismic excitation.

Fig. 8. Maximum story drift for the structure under the different earthquake excitations: (a) El Centro, (b) Kobe, and (c) Northridge.

Figure 5 shows the top floor displacement under El Centro earthquake excitation. It can be seen that the hybrid control system using the LQR controller reduces the peak displacement by almost 60% and the PID controller by 49% in comparison with the uncontrolled structure. Figure 6 shows the top floor displacement under Kobe earthquake excitation. From this Figure, it can be noted that the hybrid control system using the LQR controller outperforms the PID controller and reduces the

peak displacement by almost 57%. The top floor displacement under Northridge earthquake excitation is shown in Figure 7. Again, the hybrid control system using the LQR controller surpasses the PID controller and reduces the peak displacement by almost 62%. As these Figures show, using the LQR controller to control the displacement of the top floor of the structure always gives better results than when using a PID system. It can be seen that the hybrid system designed using an LQR controller is more efficient and effective than PID control in reducing the displacement of this building in the three cases.

VI. CONCLUSION

The objective of this study is to combine the application of base isolators and ATMDs to minimize the structural responses under the influence of seismic excitations using two different controllers, LQR and PID. According to the numerical studies for a 5-story building, and the obtained results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The comparison between LQR and PID controllers indicates that the LQR controller is more effective in reducing the displacements and the vibration of the building and surpasses the PID controller by far.
- In this study, the active control system proved to be far more efficient than the passive control systems in reducing the structural response.
- More than 50% of the top floor displacement is reduced by using the hybrid control system.
- Using a hybrid control system to control the vibration of a structure improves its performance in resisting strong earthquake excitations and makes the structure safer and more comfortable during earthquakes.

For future research, we will work in combining LQR and PID controllers in order to get the advantages of each system.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Manchalwar and S. V. Bakre, "Vibration control of structure by top base isolated storey as tuned mass damper," *International Journal of Dynamics and Control*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 963–972, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40435-020-00614-1>.
- [2] L. Xu, Y. Cui, and Z. Wang, "Active tuned mass damper based vibration control for seismic excited adjacent buildings under actuator saturation," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 135, Aug. 2020, Art. no. 106181, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2020.106181>.
- [3] S. H. Hosseini Lavassani, S. Shangapour, P. Homami, V. Gharehbaghi, E. Noroozinejad Farsangi, and T. Y. Yang, "An innovative methodology for hybrid vibration control (MR+TMD) of buildings under seismic excitations," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 155, Apr. 2022, Art. no. 107175, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2022.107175>.
- [4] M.-C. Hsieh, G.-L. Huang, H. Liu, S.-J. Chen, and B.-F. Chen, "A numerical study of hybrid tuned mass damper and tuned liquid damper system on structure motion control," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 242, Dec. 2021, Art. no. 110129, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2021.110129>.
- [5] M. Sareban, "Evaluation of Three Common Algorithms for Structure Active Control," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1638–1646, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1150>.
- [6] G. Xu and M. Yamanari, "Performance of Steel Frame with Linkage System under Earthquake Excitation," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3796–3802, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2519>.
- [7] N. Pnevmatikos and C. Gantes, "Actively and Semi-actively Controlled Structures Under Seismic Actions: Modeling and Analysis," in *Encyclopedia of Earthquake Engineering*, New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2014, pp. 1–24.
- [8] Y. Arfiadi and M. N. S. Hadi, "Passive and active control of three-dimensional buildings," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 377–396, 2000, [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-9845\(200003\)29:3<377::AID-EQE911>3.0.CO;2-C](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-9845(200003)29:3<377::AID-EQE911>3.0.CO;2-C).
- [9] B. Kavyashree, S. Patil, and V. S. Rao, "Review on vibration control in tall buildings: from the perspective of devices and applications," *International Journal of Dynamics and Control*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1316–1331, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40435-020-00728-6>.
- [10] F. Casciati, J. Rodellar, and U. Yildirim, "Active and semi-active control of structures – theory and applications: A review of recent advances," *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, vol. 23, no. 11, pp. 1181–1195, Jul. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1045389X12445029>.
- [11] M. S. H. Al-Furjan, M. Habibi, J. Ni, D. won Jung, and A. Tounsi, "Frequency simulation of viscoelastic multi-phase reinforced fully symmetric systems," *Engineering with Computers*, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00366-020-01200-x>.
- [12] M. S. H. Al-Furjan, A. hatami, M. Habibi, L. Shan, and A. Tounsi, "On the vibrations of the imperfect sandwich higher-order disk with a lactic core using generalize differential quadrature method," *Composite Structures*, vol. 257, Feb. 2021, Art. no. 113150, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.113150>.
- [13] S. Alimirzaei, M. Mohammadimehr, and A. Tounsi, "Nonlinear analysis of viscoelastic micro-composite beam with geometrical imperfection using FEM: MSGT electro-magneto-elastic bending, buckling and vibration solutions," *Structural Engineering and Mechanics*, vol. 71, no. 5, pp. 485–502, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.12989/sem.2019.71.5.485>.
- [14] T. T. Soong and B. F. Spencer, "Active, semi-active and hybrid control of structures," *Bulletin of the New Zealand Society for Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 387–402, Sep. 2000, <https://doi.org/10.5459/bnzsee.33.3.387-402>.
- [15] J. E. Hughes, Y. Kim, J. W. Chong, and C. Kim, "Particle Swarm Optimization for Active Structural Control of Highway Bridges Subjected to Impact Loading," *Shock and Vibration*, vol. 2018, Aug. 2018, Art. no. e4932870, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/4932870>.
- [16] H. Monfared, A. Shirvani, and S. O. Nwaubani, "An investigation into the seismic base isolation from practical perspective," *International Journal of Civil and Structural Engineering*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 451–463, Apr. 2013.
- [17] J. M. Kelly, "The role of damping in seismic isolation," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 3–20, 1999, [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-9845\(199901\)28:1<3::AID-EQE801>3.0.CO;2-D](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-9845(199901)28:1<3::AID-EQE801>3.0.CO;2-D).
- [18] M. Ezzraimi, R. Tiberkak, A. Melbous, and S. Rechak, "LQR and PID Algorithms for Vibration Control of Piezoelectric Composite Plates," *Mechanics*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 734–740, Nov. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.mech.24.5.20645>.
- [19] A. H. Heidari, S. Etedali, and M. R. Javaheri-Tafti, "A hybrid LQR-PID control design for seismic control of buildings equipped with ATMD," *Frontiers of Structural and Civil Engineering*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 44–57, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11709-016-0382-6>.
- [20] A. Alavinasab, H. Moharrami, and A. Khajepour, "Active Control of Structures Using Energy-Based LQR Method," *Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*, vol. 21, no. 8, pp. 605–611, 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8667.2006.00460.x>.
- [21] J. Zhang, L. He, E. Wang, and R. Gao, "A LQR Controller Design for Active Vibration Control of Flexible Structures," in *IEEE Pacific-Asia Workshop on Computational Intelligence and Industrial Application*, Wuhan, China, Dec. 2008, vol. 1, pp. 127–132, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PACIIA.2008.358>.
- [22] M. Arif Sen, M. Tinkir, and M. Kalyoncu, "Optimisation of a PID controller for a two-floor structure under earthquake excitation based on the bees algorithm," *Journal of Low Frequency Noise, Vibration and Active Control*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 107–127, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461348418757906>.

-
- [23] C. C. Chang, J. F. Wang, and C. C. Lin, "Parameter identification for active mass damper controlled systems," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 744, Jun. 2016, Art. no. 012166, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/744/1/012166>.
- [24] D. Demetriou, N. Nikitas, and K. D. Tsavdaridis, "Performance of proportional-integral-derivative controllers on structures with variable damping active tuned mass dampers," in *6th World Conference on Structural Control and Monitoring*, Barcelona, Spain, Jul. 2014.
- [25] R. Guclu, "Sliding mode and PID control of a structural system against earthquake," *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 210–217, Jul. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcm.2006.01.014>.
- [26] H. Bassi and Y. A. Mobarak, "State-Space Modeling and Performance Analysis of Variable-Speed Wind Turbine Based on a Model Predictive Control Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1436–1443, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1015>.

Drive Control of a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor Fed by a Multi-level Inverter for Electric Vehicle Application

Pham Thi Giang

Faculty of Electrical Engineering
University of Economics-Technology for Industries
Hanoi, Vietnam
ptgiang@uneti.edu.vn

Vo Thanh Ha

Faculty of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
University of Transport and Communications
Hanoi, Vietnam
vothanhha.ktd@utc.edu.vn

Vu Hoang Phuong

School of Electrical Engineering
Hanoi University Science and Technology
Hanoi, Vietnam
phuong.vuhoang@hust.edu.vn

Received: 22 March 2022 | Revised: 7 April 2022 and 14 April 2022 | Accepted: 17 April 2022

Abstract-This paper presents the drive control of a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM) fed by a multi-level inverter for electric vehicle application. In particular, the advantage of torque mobilization of the PMSM engine has been selected for the electric drive of electric cars. In addition, to improve the transmission quality of electric vehicles to ensure requirements, the T-type three-level inverter will be proposed in the control structure of electric vehicles. Moreover, the challenge of torque entails determining the appropriate physical qualities. Therefore, the design of an active damping and current controller to provide rapid and precise torque response to the induced torsional moment was also conducted. Finally, the results of Ples simulations prove the correctness of the theoretical research. The simulation results demonstrate the research theory.

Keywords-multilevel inverter; T-type inverter; PMSM; active damping; electric vehicles; FOC

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric vehicles have been around for a long time, but their use has grown enormously over the last few years. Many electric car applications that solve energy and pollution problems have been developed, put into commercial production, and used in practice [1]. Electric cars have the advantages of electric motors, such as the ability to quickly and accurately generate torque, whereas torque control is also realized [2]. However, electric cars still have limitations such as long charging time, inflexibility, and high cost. Regarding the outstanding advantages of electric cars, in terms of high performance and environmental friendliness, and considering the efforts to find solutions to reduce battery charging time, lead to the complete replacement of cars powered by internal combustion engines by electric vehicles in the future [3].

Scientists have studied technological issues inside electric cars to develop solutions to improve electric vehicles' quality of motion, energy, and performance. According to [4, 5] the structure of an electric car normally includes components such as electric motor, controller, inverter, battery, charging port, powertrain, battery, etc. as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The structure of a normal electric car.

In the longitudinal traction structure of Figure 1, we consider some problems with improving the transmission quality of electric cars to ensure requirements, so there is a need to pay attention to the following:

Firstly, electric motors have outstanding advantages in terms of controllability, allowing the use of advanced control methods to control the motor, thereby improving the kinematics of the car. Therefore, the issue of selecting the engine most suitable for electric car transmission has always been considered by many scientists and automobile companies.

Some motors have been used for electric cars, such as DC motors, which have the advantage of being easy to control. The disadvantage of this type of motors is the need for manifolds and brushes. It has a low lifespan, requires regular maintenance, and is unsuitable for hot, humid, and dusty conditions. As semiconductor valve technology, microprocessors and control techniques develop strongly and DC motors have been gradually replaced by other types of motors [6]. The Brushless DC Motor (BLDC) is a type of permanent magnet synchronous motor with trapezoidal reactance. The BLDC motor has the same mechanical characteristics, power density, high torque capacity, and high efficiency as a DC motor. The main disadvantage of the BLDC motor is the significant torque undulation [7-9]. AC motors, such as squirrel-cage rotor (IM) asynchronous motors, have the advantages of low cost, typical use, and ease of manufacture. It is possible to implement advanced vector control algorithms for IM engines with the current technology, meeting the necessary technological requirements. The disadvantage of the IM motor is its low efficiency, especially in light load mode [6]. The PMSM can be considered the most suitable motor for electric vehicle application with a high-efficiency large torque capacity, while it can be controlled with good quality. In particular, the Interior Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (IPMSM) has many advantages, suitable for electric cars [10]. The magnetic motor has benefits such as high efficiency, sizeable power-to-size ratio, high power density, long life, small moment of inertia, wide operating speed range, large amount of torque/current, and low noise stability. Therefore, magnetic motors have been promised to be widely used in transmission systems with high-quality speed regulation, such as electric vehicle robots [6, 11]. However, the cost is high and control is complicated. Based on the characteristics of electric motors used for electric cars, in this paper we will consider PMSMs.

Secondly, the inverter converts the DC voltage from the battery into the AC voltage to power the motor. The inverter is a virtual device, contributing to the improvement of the transmission quality to ensure the required specifications. Therefore, the choice of the suitable inverter for this drive system is also a problem considered by many scientists [12]. It was found that multi-level inverters have advantages over two-level inverters [13]. Based on the current scientific research, it has been discovered that in the control structure of traction power transmission systems, 2-level voltage source inverters with power circuits including six semiconductor valves and the SVM Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) technique are often used. However, a multi-level inverter has more advantages than a two-level inverter for reducing THD [14]. According to [15], the 3-phase current has a conventional sinusoidal shape with Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) equal to 7.53%, while the 2-level inverters have THD equal to 11.39%. In addition, the multi-level inverter comprises semiconductor valves and a DC voltage source, and the output voltage is in the form of wavelengths [16]. Therefore, the output voltage of a multi-level inverter may be made sinusoidal with low THD by increasing the number of voltage levels. This paper used a three-level T-type inverter fed by a PMSM motor in an electric vehicle to improve fast and accurate torque response.

Thirdly, the torque of the motor shaft T_m is the control input variable, and the angular velocity ω of the wheel is the control lever output. When the motor speed changes, the anti-slip is controlled by changing the magnitude of the torque T_m . On the other hand, the motor shaft end torque is linearly dependent on the current flowing in the motor. Therefore, to adjust the torque T_m , we control the starter motor's stator current. The set value of the stator current flowing in the primary engine is the required current proportional to the pedal angle. In addition, due to their structural characteristics, the electric vehicles are prone to small fluctuations during the entry/exit of the accelerator pedal, the resonant frequency of the controller, and during acceleration. This means that the signal to set the motor speed is affected by this oscillation. At the same time, the control object (wheel) does not consider the jerking phenomenon ($T_s \times K_{gear} = 0$), so the difference between the price-setting value and feedback will cause recoil. If not rectified and extinguished, this recoil can cause discomfort to the occupants in the vehicle [17, 18].

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL AND CONTROL OF THE ELECTRIC CAR POWER SYSTEM

A. Mathematical Model of the PMSM Synchronous Motor

According to [19], the dq coordinate system to have the system of equations of PMSM motor is :

$$\begin{cases} u_{sd} = L_{sd} \frac{di_{sd}}{dt} + R_s i_{sd} - \omega_e L_{sq} i_{sq} \\ u_{sq} = L_{sq} \frac{di_{sq}}{dt} + R_s i_{sq} + \omega_e L_{sd} i_{sd} + \omega_e \psi_f \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The equation for calculating the torque of the motor is:

$$T_m = \frac{3}{2} P_p [\psi_f i_{sq} + (L_{sd} - L_{sq}) i_{sd} i_{sq}] \quad (2)$$

The torque of the motor consists of two components: the main component $\psi_f i_{sq}$ and the reactive component due to the difference $L_{sd} - L_{sq}$. When building a control system, we need to control the stator current vector is such that the vertical current vector is perpendicular to the polar flux and there is no magnetizing current component, but only a torque generating current component or $I_{sd} = 0$. The equation describing the motor torque is:

$$T_m = \frac{3}{2} P_p \psi_f i_{sq} \quad (3)$$

B. Mathematical Model of the Electric Vehicle

1) Description of the Gearbox and the Wheel System

The gearbox model shows the angular speed and torque relationships according to the gear ratio $k_{gear} < 1$.

$$\begin{cases} T_m k_{gear} = T_{wh} \\ \omega_{wh} = \omega_m k_{gear} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where T_m is motor torque, T_{wh} the torque acting on the wheel, with $T_i = T_{wh}$, J is the moment of inertia of the motor. The equation of Newton's second law in the rotation of the motor is:

$$T_{em} - T_{wh} = J \frac{d\omega_m}{dt} \quad (5)$$

The drive wheel model is described by:

$$\begin{cases} v_{wh} = \omega_{wh} R_{wh} \\ T_{wh} = T_L = F_t R_{wh} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

When the wheel rests on the road surface with force N and is driven by a torque T_{wh} , the vehicle will act on the road surface with a force F , and, respectively, the road surface will act against the vehicle with a force of the same value in the opposite direction as F_t . In this case, F_t is the frictional force and is the useful force component that causes the vehicle to move at speed V_x .

$$F_t = m_v \cdot g \cdot \mu \quad (7)$$

where μ is the grip coefficient.

Fig. 2. Description of the gearbox and the wheel system.

Fig. 3. Drive wheel model.

2) Equation of Motion of the Vehicle and External Force Components

Applying Newton's second law to the components of the external force acting on the body of the vehicle, we have:

$$m_v \frac{dv_{ev}}{dt} = F_t - F_{aero} - F_{roll} - m_v \cdot g \cdot \sin(\alpha) \quad (8)$$

Air resistance:

$$F_{aero} = \frac{\rho C_d A_F}{2} (v_{ev} + v_{wind})^2 \quad (9)$$

In some cases, or in simulations, we can consider wind speed $v_{wind} = 0$.

Rolling resistance exists in the case of an underinflated tire:

$$F_{roll} = f_r \cdot F_{zy} \quad (10)$$

$$F_{zy} = m_v \cdot g \cdot \cos(\alpha) \quad (11)$$

Fig. 4. Transmission system, wheels, and the acting forces.

C. Mathematical Model of Electric Vehicle Powertrain

The model can be seen in Figure 5, where T_m is the driving part created by the engine and acting on the electric vehicle, J_1, J_2 are the moments of inertia of the motor and the load, and ω_m, ω_{wh} are motor speed and load.

Fig. 5. The structure of the electric vehicle model.

The response on the engine side represents the mechanical system (axle stiffness, damping) and the body model. Therefore, it is necessary to have a mathematical relationship between these two components in the electric vehicle system. The model of the system when considering shaft stiffness and damping is:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} J_1 \omega_m &= T_m - K_{gear} T_s \\ J_2 \omega_{wh} &= T_s - T_{wh} \\ u_{sd} &= L_{sd} \frac{di_{sd}}{dt} + R_s i_{sd} - \omega_e L_{sq} i_{sq} \\ u_{sq} &= L_{sq} \frac{di_{sq}}{dt} + R_s i_{sq} + \omega_e L_{sd} i_{sd} + \omega_e \psi_f \\ \begin{cases} T_s = k_s \theta_s + b_s \dot{\theta}_s \\ \theta_s = K_{gear} \omega_m - \omega_{wh} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \right. \quad (12)$$

The mathematical model of the mechanical transmission system from the engine to the wheel hub is shown in Figure 6. From Figure 6, it is found that:

- Combined with the model above, we will observe the vehicle's speed and Ft's traction force.
- This model can be used to design an active damping unit. The parameter of interest is the speed of the motor shaft.

Fig. 6. Mathematical model of the mechanical transmission system from the engine to the wheel hub.

D. Active Damping Controller Design [20]

Changing the torque will have a difference between the motor and load angles, leading to oscillation or jerking due to uncontrollable torsion angles. In addition, a sudden step-change in motor torque leads to inertial instability of the motor. This recoil effect occurs due to the excitation of the natural frequency of the powertrain. This excitation is caused by a sudden change in the amount of torque applied, given by:

$$f_0 = \frac{\sqrt{K_s}}{2\pi K_{Gear} \sqrt{J_m}} \quad (14)$$

where K_s is the stiffness coefficient of the shaft, J_m corresponds to the rotor inertia of the motor, and K_{Gear} to the gear ratio of the gearbox.

A practical solution to reduce powertrain oscillation is to actively control the torque set on the PMSM (reference torque -

T_{ref}), which needs to be increased gradually by subtracting an amount of torque T_{dp} (calculated from torsion angle and oscillation speed - active damping controller) With this method, the rotor speed is measured and fed to an external speed control loop.

Fig. 7. The control structure of the anti-shock controller.

In Figure 7, K is the active damping controller that needs to be designed. Compared with the kinematics of the electric vehicle, the motor can be considered the first-order inertia. Therefore, the parameters included in the active damping unit can be estimated through the abovementioned models. Besides, through the mechanical system, the inertial component is added to the motor shaft to change the natural frequency of vibration and the factors that cause the recoil effect. The structure of the active damping controller is shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Active damping controller structure.

The inertia of the mechanical system and the electric vehicle is converted to the motor shaft. For the mass of the car acting on the wheel, the vehicle's inertia on the wheel's axis is calculated and then divided by K_{gear} in order to be converted to the engine shaft.

$$J_{total} = J_1 + J_{ev} = J_1 + (EV_Mass) * \left(\frac{wheel_Radius}{Gear_Ratio} \right)^2 \quad (15)$$

A set signal that is the speed affected by the jerking phenomenon and the control object does not consider the cause of the jerk $T_s K_{gear} = 0$. The difference between the set value and the feedback is that the cause of the draw through the controller will calculate the torque causing the pull. Combined with the set torque, it will calculate the correct torque that the motor needs not to jerk. When the difference between the set value and the feedback is zero or $T_d = 0$, respectively, there is no longer a component causing the jerking. The inertia component of the motor is minimal compared to the inertia of the whole team, so we consider it $J_{total} = J_{ev}$. The closed

transfer function from the above model is synthesized to determine the set parameter PI. Equation (16) can express the available transfer function:

$$G_h = K_p \left(1 + \frac{1}{T_i s}\right) \cdot \frac{1}{J_{ev} s} = \frac{K_p (T_i s + 1)}{T_i J_{ev} s^2} = k \cdot \frac{(T_i s + 1)}{s^2} \quad (16)$$

with $k = \frac{K_p}{T_i J_{ev}}$.

The closed transfer function is:

$$G_k = \frac{G_h}{1 + G_h} = \frac{k \cdot \frac{(T_i s + 1)}{s^2}}{1 + k \cdot \frac{(T_i s + 1)}{s^2}} = \frac{k(1 + T_i s)}{s^2 + k(1 + T_i s)} = \frac{kT_i s + k}{s^2 + kT_i s + k} \quad (17)$$

According to the standard form of the quadratic function, it has the form:

$$G_{k\omega}(s) = \frac{2 \cdot \xi_w \cdot \omega_{nw} \cdot s + \omega_{nw}^2}{s^2 + 2 \cdot \xi_w \cdot \omega_{nw} \cdot s + \omega_{nw}^2} \quad (18)$$

where ω_{nw} is the natural frequency of oscillation of the PI controller with K_p and T_i as follows:

$$\begin{cases} K_p = 2 \cdot \xi_w \cdot \omega_{nw} \cdot J_{ev} \\ K_i = \frac{K_p}{T_i} = \omega_{nw}^2 \cdot J_{ev} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

According to the documentation, we chose $\xi_w = 0.71$ (corresponds to overshoot 5%), $t_s = 1s$.

$$\begin{cases} \xi_w = 0.71 \\ \omega_{nw} = \frac{4}{\xi_w \cdot t_s} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

E. Stator Current Controller Design [18, 21]

The design of the torque controller for PMSM motors becomes vital in high-efficiency applications. The design process for synthesizing and implementing current drivers for PMSM motors is the same as for current controllers in asynchronous motor drives. To design a torque controller for a PMSM motor, it is necessary to understand the interaction of the motor, inverter, and current controller. Consider the gain of the inverter as K_r , and the time constant of the inverter as T_r , half the PWM carrier frequency duration. If the desired performance of the current control loop is the same as that of the system, then we have a first-order hysteresis step:

$$\frac{i_d}{i_d^*} = \frac{K_i}{1 + sT_i} \quad (21)$$

The current loop circuit is:

$$\frac{i_q}{i_q^*} = \frac{K_a K_i (1 + T_m s)}{H_c K_a K_r (1 + sT_m) + (1 + sT_r) \{K_a K_b + (1 + sT_a)(1 + sT_m)\}} \quad (22)$$

where:

$$K_a = \frac{1}{R_s}; T_a = \frac{L_q}{R_s}; K_m = \frac{i}{B_r}; T_m = \frac{J}{B_i}; K_b = K_t K_m \lambda_{af}$$

The current transfer function is rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{i_q}{i_q^*} &= \frac{(K_a K_i T_m) s}{K_a K_b + (T_m + K_a K_i T_m H_c) s + (T_m T_{af}) s^2} \\ &\cong \left(\frac{K_r T_m}{K_b}\right) \frac{s}{(1 + sT_1)(1 + sT_2)} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

With $T_1 < T_2 < T_m$ and based on further estimates, $(1 + sT_2) \cong sT_2$ then the transfer function of the current loop is given by:

$$\frac{i_q}{i_q^*} \cong \frac{K_i}{(1 + sT_i)} \quad (24)$$

where:

$$K_i = \frac{T_m K_r}{T_2 K_b}; T_i = T_1 \quad (25)$$

III. SVM MODULATION OF THE 3-LEVEL T-TYPE INVERTER

The 3-phase design of a 3-level T-type inverter is shown in Figure 9 [16]. The 3-level T-type inverter works on 2 DC capacitors to divide the input voltage into two components and create a virtual neutral point. Properly adjusting and switching semiconductor valves will give a wire voltage in 5 levels: $-V_{dc}, -V_{dc}/2, +V_{dc}/2, +V_{dc}$. Thus, the output phase voltage has the form of 3 levels: $-V_{dc}/2, 0, +V_{dc}/2$.

Fig. 9. Three-phase T-type inverter structure.

A. Pulse Width Modulation SVM

According to [16], PWM SVM is performed according to the following calculation steps:

1) Step 1: Locate the Reference Vector

The number of sectors S (S = I, II, ..., VI) is determined by Table I.

TABLE I. LOCATING THE HEXAGONS

$z_{1x}, z_{1y} < 0$		$z_{1x}, z_{1y} \geq 0$	
$z_{2x}, z_{2y} < 0$	$z_{2x}, z_{2y} \geq 0$	$z_{1x} < 0$	$z_{1x} \geq 0$
$z_{3x} < 0$	$z_{3x} \geq 0$	$z_{2x} < 0$	$z_{2x} \geq 0$
Sec III	Sec VI	Sec V	Sec II
		Sec IV	Sec I

2) Step 2: Determine the Duty Cycle

In this step, the three nearest vectors are determined, based on the three vertices of the modulation triangle, by calculating the duty cycle of the three most similar defined vectors, and by choosing the switching states of the semiconductor valves. With the assumption shown in Figure 10, the sum of the output voltage vector is as follows:

The vector is represented by the vectors in (27):

$$\vec{V}_1 = (1 - m_g - m_h) \vec{p}_1 + m_g \vec{p}_2 + m_h \vec{p}_3 \quad (27)$$

$$\vec{V}_2 = (m_g + m_h - 1) \vec{p}_4 + (1 - m_g) \vec{p}_3 + (1 - m_h) \vec{p}_2 \quad (28)$$

Fig. 10. Synthesizing the output voltage vector from the 3 vectors of the sub-triangle.

The coefficients m_g and m_h are determined as:

$$\begin{cases} m_g = z_{1x} - \lfloor |z_{1x}| \rfloor = z_{1x} - k_g \\ m_h = z_{1y} - \lfloor |z_{1y}| \rfloor = z_{1y} - k_h \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

with $k_g = \lfloor |z_{1x}| \rfloor$, $k_h = \lfloor |z_{1y}| \rfloor$.

3) Step 3: Determine the Switching State

If taking coordinates $k_A = k$, the coefficient k must satisfy this condition: $-\frac{M-1}{2} \leq k \leq \frac{M-1}{2}$. The coordinates of the state vector in (a, b, c) coordinate system are given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} k_{1x} \\ k_{1y} \end{bmatrix} \approx \begin{bmatrix} k_{AN} \\ k_{BN} \\ k_{CN} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} k \\ k - k_{1x} \\ k - k_{1x} - k_{1y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

B. Algorithm to Balance Voltage on Two DC Capacitors using the SVM Modulation

DC voltage unbalance will degrade the inverter output voltage harmonic quality and this is not allowable. Therefore, dealing with this problem is necessary for multi-level inverters in general and T-type inverters in particular.

The implementation steps are:

- Step 1: Measure the voltages on the capacitor U_{dc1} , U_{dc2} .
- Step 2: Compare the voltage on the two capacitors
- Step 3: If $U_{dc1} > U_{dc2}$, discharge voltage on capacitor C_1 , and charge capacitor C_2 .
- Step 4: If $U_{dc2} > U_{dc1}$, then discharge the voltage on the capacitor C_2 and at the same time charge the capacitor C_1 .

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Based on the PMSM motor modeling, load, active damping controller, torque, and voltage SVM pulse modulation for the T-type 3-level inverter are simulated. The Plecs simulation of the structure of drive control of a PMSM motor fed by a three-level T-type inverter for electric vehicles application shown in Figure 11.

A. Simulation Results of the T-Type Inverter

Based on the above, an electric car control structure powered by a 3-level T-type inverter was built and simulations were conducted with a 3-level T-type inverter and engine parameters. A 3-level T-type inverter was simulated with a resistive load to evaluate the power circuit structure and SVM modulation of the system's 3-level T-type inverter. The results of the 3-phase voltage and stator current response, are shown in Figures 12-14.

Fig. 11. The structure of drive control of a PMSM motor fed by a 3-level T-type inverter for electric vehicle application.

Fig. 12. Three phase voltage response.

Fig. 13. Three-phase voltage response.

Fig. 14. Three-phase current response.

Through the simulation results of Figures 12-14, it is found that the output voltage response of the T-type inverter has the form of 3 levels, with amplitude of 350V. Phase voltage response is sinusoidal, and THD harmonic distortion is small (THD is 2.88, 1.52, and 2.16 for phase *a*, *b*, and *c* respectively).

Fig. 15. DC voltage response on 2 capacitors.

The simulation results in Figure15, show that the DC voltage on the two capacitors is not significantly different with the largest difference $\Delta V_{cmax} = 3V$ (0.6%), proving that the balancing algorithm works effectively.

B. Simulation Results of the Active Damping Controller

The structure in the Plescs simulation of the active damping controller is shown in Figure 16.

Fig. 16. Active damping controller structure.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the active damping control design for the permanent magnet synchronous motor drive system fed by a 3-level T-type inverter for electric cars, the following simulation scenario was considered:

- At time $t = 0s$, the torque was put equal to 100Nm, after 2s it changed to -100Nm, and at $t = 5s$ to 100Nm.
- Simulation was held in the case with not a shock absorber. The setting torque is in the form of step (step) and the setting torque is in the form of oscillation generated by the recoil controller.

Fig. 17. Torque response to shock absorber oscillation.

Through the simulation results in Figure 17, it was found that with the design of the anti-shock controller, the torque response set value for the transmission system was built in accordance with the physical properties.

C. Simulation Results of the Torque Controller

To evaluate the efficiency of the torque control design for the permanent magnet synchronous motor drive system fed by a 3-level T-type inverter for electric cars, the following simulation scenario was implemented:

- Simulation of an electric car powertrain with a physical model using 3-level T-type inverter with an active damping kit.

- At time $t = 0s$, the torque was put equal to 100Nm, after 2s it changed to -100Nm, and at $t = 5s$ to 100Nm.

The stator current response (i_{sq}), torque, wheel speed, motor, triple voltage, and THD can be seen in Figures 18-20. Through the results of Figure 19, it is found that the real stator current response i_{sq} is close to the set value, but there is still over-correction at the time of transition (speed increase and decrease).

Fig. 18. Current response i_{sq} .

Fig. 19. Torque response.

The applied torque response has the correct form for the system physics (small oscillations). This proves that the anti-shock has been promoted. Besides, the torque response has the same form as the current i_{sq} , the real torque closely follows the set torque including the oscillation. However, the torque response still has over-correction at acceleration and deceleration times, 20% torque pulsation exists, as shown in Figure 20. In addition, it can be seen that the motor speed response still has a large adjustment at the transient time and the setting time is not fast. Through the simulation results in Figure 21, it is found that the output voltage response of the T-Type inverter has a 3-level form when the powering PMSM motor drive system used for electric cars has a 3-level form, with a boundary degree 350V. Three-phase voltage response is sinusoidal, and THD is small (3.36, 1.92, and 2.88 for phase a , b , and c respectively).

Fig. 20. Motor speed response.

Fig. 21. Phase voltage response.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the SVM spatial voltage vector modulation for a three-level T-type inverter was implemented and simulated, giving 3-phase voltage and stator current response with minor harmonic distortion. In addition, active damping and torque controllers were designed. The active damping controller has been promoted with the same torque response form as the stator current. The actual torque closely follows the set torque, including the oscillation. However, these controllers use a PI controller, so the torque, stator current, and speed responses still suffer from over-throttling, and the timing set is not fast. Therefore, the future research will focus on improving the above responses according to the requirements by using nonlinear control methods and combining state variable observers such as tires and road surfaces.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Bimbraw, "Autonomous cars: Past, present and future a review of the developments in the last century, the present scenario and the expected future of autonomous vehicle technology," in *12th International Conference on Informatics in Control, Automation and Robotics*, Colmar, France, Jul. 2015, vol. 1, pp. 191–198.
- [2] S. Soylu, *Urban Transport and Hybrid Vehicles*. Rijeka, Croatia: IntechOpen, 2010.
- [3] X. Zhang, D. Gohlich, and J. Li, "Energy-Efficient Torque Allocation Design of Traction and Regenerative Braking for Distributed Drive Electric Vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 67, no. 1, pp. 285–295, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2017.2731525>.
- [4] X. Zhang, L. Zeng, and R. Pei, "Designing and Comparison of Permanent Magnet Synchronous Reluctance Motors and Conventional Motors in Electric Vehicles," in *21st International Conference on Electrical Machines and Systems*, Jeju, Korea, Oct. 2018, pp. 202–205, <https://doi.org/10.23919/ICEMS.2018.8549102>.
- [5] E. Sokolov, "Comparative study of electric car traction motors," in *15th International Conference on Electrical Machines, Drives and Power Systems*, Sofia, Bulgaria, Jun. 2017, pp. 348–353, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ELMA.2017.7955461>.
- [6] M. Yildirim, M. Polat, and H. Kurum, "A survey on comparison of electric motor types and drives used for electric vehicles," in *16th International Power Electronics and Motion Control Conference and Exposition*, Antalya, Turkey, Sep. 2014, pp. 218–223, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EPEPEMC.2014.6980715>.
- [7] H. El Hadraoui, M. Zegrari, A. Chebak, O. Laayati, and N. Guennouni, "A Multi-Criteria Analysis and Trends of Electric Motors for Electric Vehicles," *World Electric Vehicle Journal*, vol. 13, no. 4, Apr. 2022, Art. no. 65, <https://doi.org/10.3390/wevj13040065>.
- [8] D. B. Minh, V. D. Quoc, and P. N. Huy, "Efficiency Improvement of Permanent Magnet BLDC Motors for Electric Vehicles," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7615–7618, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4367>.
- [9] M. Hussain, A. Ulasyar, H. S. Zad, A. Khattak, S. Nisar, and K. Imran, "Design and Analysis of a Dual Rotor Multiphase Brushless DC Motor for its Application in Electric Vehicles," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7846–7852, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4345>.
- [10] M. Aydin and M. Gulec, "A New Coreless Axial Flux Interior Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor With Sinusoidal Rotor Segments," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 52, no. 7, pp. 1–4, Jul. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMAG.2016.2522950>.
- [11] S. Javadi and M. Mirsalim, "A Coreless Axial-Flux Permanent-Magnet Generator for Automotive Applications," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 44, no. 12, pp. 4591–4598, Sep. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMAG.2008.2004333>.
- [12] C. M. Van, T. N. Xuan, P. V. Hoang, M. T. Trong, S. P. Cong, and L. N. Van, "A Generalized Space Vector Modulation for Cascaded H-bridge Multi-level Inverter," in *International Conference on System Science and Engineering*, Dong Hoi, Vietnam, Jul. 2019, pp. 18–24, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSSE.2019.8823465>.
- [13] N. B. Mohite and Y. R. Atre, "Neutral-Point Clamped Multilevel Inverter Based Transmission Statcom for Voltage Regulation," in *Second International Conference on Emerging Trends in Engineering*, Jaysingpur, India, 2010, pp. 31–35.
- [14] S. Mohamadian and M. H. Khanzade, "A Five-Level Current-Source Inverter for Grid-Connected or High-Power Three-Phase Wound-Field Synchronous Motor Drives," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 1139–1148, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.695>.
- [15] V. T. Ha, P. T. Giang, and V. H. Phuong, "T-Type Multi-Inverter Application for Traction Motor Control," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8321–8327, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4776>.
- [16] Y. Li and Z. Quan, "Derivation of multilevel voltage source converter topologies for medium voltage drives," *Chinese Journal of Electrical Engineering*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 24–31, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.23919/CJEE.2017.8048409>.
- [17] P. Vu, D. T. Anh, and H. D. Chinh, "A Novel Modeling and Control Design of the Current-Fed Dual Active Bridge Converter under DPDS Modulation," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 7054–7059, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4067>.
- [18] Q. Huang, J. Li, and Y. Chen, "Control of Electric Vehicle," in *Urban Transport and Hybrid Vehicles*, Rijeka, Croatia: IntechOpen, 2010, pp. 163–192.
- [19] N. P. Quang and J.-A. Dittrich, *Vector Control of Three-Phase AC Machines*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2015.
- [20] F. U. Syed, M. L. Kuang, and H. Ying, "Active Damping Wheel-Torque Control System to Reduce Driveline Oscillations in a Power-Split Hybrid Electric Vehicle," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 58, no. 9, pp. 4769–4785, Aug. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2009.2025953>.
- [21] A. Zahedmanesh, K. M. Muttaqi, and D. Sutanto, "Coordinated Charging Control of Electric Vehicles While Improving Power Quality in Power Grids Using a Hierarchical Decision-Making Approach," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 69, no. 11, pp. 12585–12596, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2020.3025809>.

Performance Comparison of Ensemble Learning and Supervised Algorithms in Classifying Multi-label Network Traffic Flow

Mwita Machoke

School of Computational and Communication Science and Engineering, Department of Information Technology System Development and Management, NM-AIST, Arusha, Tanzania
machokem@nm-aist.ac.tz

Jimmy Mbelwa

University of Dar es Salaam
Dar es Salaam, Tanzania
jimmymbelwa@gmail.com

Johnson Agbinya

School of Information Technology and Engineering
Melbourne Institute of Technology
Melbourne, Victoria, Australia
jagbinya@mit.edu.au

Anael Elikana Sam

School of Computational and Communication Science and Engineering, Department of Communication Science and Engineering, NM-AIST Arusha, Tanzania
anael.sam@nm-aist.ac.tz

Received: 16 February 2022 | Revised: 21 March 2022 | Accepted: 22 March 2022

Abstract—Network traffic classification is of significant importance. It helps identify network anomalies and assists in taking measures to avoid them. However, classifying network traffic correctly is a challenging task. This study aims to compare ensemble learning methods with normal supervised classification to come up with improved classification methods. Three types of network traffic were classified (Benign, Malicious, and Outliers). The data were collected experimentally by using Paessler Router Traffic Grapher software and online and were analyzed by R software. The datasets were used to train five supervised models (k-nearest neighbors, mixture discriminant analysis, Naïve Bayes, C5.0 classification model, and regularized discriminant analysis). The models were trained by 70% of the samples and the rest 30% were used for validation. The same samples were used separately in predicting individual accuracy. The results were compared to the ensemble learning models which were built with the use of the same datasets. Among the five supervised classifiers, k-nearest neighbors and C5.0 classification scored the highest accuracy of 0.868 and 0.761. The ensemble learning classifiers Bagging (Random Forest) and Boosting (eXtreme Gradient Boosting) had accuracy of 0.904 and 0.902 respectively. The results show that the ensemble learning method has higher accuracy compared to the normal supervised classifiers. Therefore, it can be used to detect malicious activities in network traffic as well as anomalies with improved accuracy.

Keywords—ensemble; malicious; anomalies; security

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) including hardware, the Internet, data science techniques, and services such as online transactions, edge, and cloud computing has changed the way many societies communicate, work, and learn [1]. Because of the

variety of computer software available as well as the growing number of users, large-volume data processing has become more complex. The trends show that an increase in mobile data traffic will exceed zettabyte (200^{10}) by 2025 [2]. The total network traffic pattern has increased exponentially the last few years [3, 4]. Furthermore, it has also been reported that such rapid growth in data traffic is likely to cause security breaches, risks, and lowering of network performance, especially in communication network systems [5, 6]. It also provides room for potential demand for re-designing network architectures to overcome security threats [7]. Through the use of the Internet, there is a possibility of security attacks occurring at any given time in the communication network system including software, hardware, and attached accessories or communication devices.

Data flows from one point to another as unidirectional packets in Internet Protocol (IP) communication networks. The flows depend on the hardware performance and network architecture [8]. A flow is a traffic stream with a common set of identifiers that has the same source IP, destination IP, protocol, source, and destination ports [9]. Monitoring data traffic in connected devices provides useful information that would be of importance in the timely understanding of the behavior of the flows and in predicting bandwidth usage. Monitoring data flows is crucial in that, any Denial of Service attacks (DoS) and other network security threats and vulnerabilities within the network can be easily identified for timely interventions [5, 10-12]. It helps system administrators and security experts to understand and monitor all activities in the given computer network.

High online service demand is embedded in our daily life. Detecting anomalies in the network can be very difficult [13].

Corresponding author: Mwita Machoke

www.etasr.com

Machoke et al.: Performance Comparison of Ensemble Learning and Supervised Algorithms in ...

It is very difficult to detect, identify and prevent malicious activities in computer networks, especially in a distributed computing environment. Priority is given to the process of identifying the characteristics of applications that generate high traffic due to malicious activities in communicating devices. These facts reveal that network traffic management and monitoring for the smooth running of an information system is a demanding task [14]. Hence, in order to avoid the occurrence of such an unpreferred situation in a computer network, high-performing models are needed for both hardware and software solutions, therefore, the study of Machine Learning (ML) is of importance to supplement both hardware and software-based solutions [15]. ML is the ability of computer algorithms to learn from a large amount of data through experience and provide a predicted output. ML can be applied in different fields such as data science, ICT, health care, finance, etc. [16].

There are four types of ML schemes: supervised, semi-supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning. They both use classification algorithms. Examples of supervised learning classifications algorithms are Decision Tree (DT), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Naïve Bayes (NB), and logistic regression [6]. They use labeled training data as input features to generate the output [17]. Examples of unsupervised classification algorithms include k-means and hierarchical clustering [18]. They use unlabeled input features to generate the outputs.

The supervised learning classification relies on an ensemble learning technique to generate multiple models. Ensemble learning technique is a collection of classifiers used to build very sophisticated models with higher accuracy compared to single estimator classifiers [19, 50]. It is a machine learning approach in classifying datasets with high dimensions and its training process is not very complex [12]. Its output is based on the training data by aggregating them to generate a strong model. It thus fuses the results from several different models. This improves performance and prediction by stacking different models.

There are many studies related to the use of supervised and unsupervised ML in flow-based network traffic classification. For instance, in [20], the authors used ML in the classification of end users' applications. Different methods were used, such as k-NN, Random Forest (RF), and J48. The k-NN technique provided the best results followed by RF with accuracy of 93.94 % and 90.87% respectively. In [21], the authors compared Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with the Gaussian NB method. The mean accuracy of PCA was about 86% during the validation process in network intrusion detection compared to the 74% of Gaussian NB. A comparison study of DT, k-NN, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and RF was conducted in [22], resulting in higher accuracy of RF (96.87%) in comparison to the 48.56% of the SVM. This study shows that the ensemble learning method RF is very useful in network traffic data analytics compared to other ML techniques. In this study, SVM which is a supervised classifier, failed to separate network traffic based on feature classes used. Data mining approaches were applied in [18] in finding the dynamic patterns of network traffic. The study applied the clustering method by portioning the data from different

domains and characterization the traffic in the time series data set. Two feature classes (benign and malicious) were considered. The authors in [23] compared the data mining approach using ML and ensemble learning method to forecast water flow. It was shown that the use of ensemble learning provided the best performance. Some of the performance metrics were not generated, for example recall, sensitivity, and kappa. When compared to other supervised algorithms, the use of ensemble learning in evaluating intrusion detection by using different data from network traffic tracing shows an improvement in network traffic classification [19].

The development of network infrastructure hardware has resulted in the use of the Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) method in classifying network attacks and threats. However, this approach needs a lot of memory as well as resources during computation. Another weakness of the method is that it is very difficult for database maintenance, especially for zero-day attacks and protocols [24]. In the field of ICT, there are three main approaches in classifying network traffic, namely flow, payload-inspection, and port-based methods [25]. Regarding the port-based and flow-based classification, it was shown in [26] that port-based classification has higher accuracy. However, ML classification provides both higher accuracy and performance results [27] compared to port and flow-based classifications. Based on the above study, this paper aimed at comparing the accuracy and performance of ML approaches.

Since the focus of the study for this article was to develop a learning classification model that can identify and detect network anomalies with high accuracy, especially zero-day attacks, we opted for supervised learning classification algorithms. The supervised learning classification algorithms provide higher accuracy than the unsupervised ones [24]. There are two types of ensemble learning methods in supervised learning classification [28]: Boosting and Bootstrap Aggregating (Bagging), both with a potential of being used in classification and regression. Boosting is an ensemble learning method which combines several weak learners to build a strong learner by using supervised classification [29]. Bagging methods divide the training data set into small samples for training the models.

In Tanzania, only a few studies have been conducted on the evaluation of computer system network traffic by using data mining and the ML approach. Authors in [30] compared network traffic classification and packet detection, showing that both computational performance and classification accuracy can be used for the management of computer network systems. This article thus aims to compare the performance of ensemble learning techniques (Bagging and Boosting) with the normal supervised classification algorithms, particularly k-NN, NB, LDA, MDA, and C5.0. The comparison is focused on three metrics (accuracy, kappa, and logloss). The question is whether using ensemble methods improves the accuracy and value of kappa. To fulfill this objective, we computed model sensitivity and specificity, precision and recall metrics from the models, and generated both positive and negative predictions from the models. This article contributes to the development of models, hardware or software, to detect network traffic anomalies in a much more effective and efficient way. It also

contributes to the literature related to the ML approach in the computer network security field.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Data Capture and Classification Process

This section illustrates the structure of network traffic dataset classification step by step from data capture up to model evaluation as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Diagram illustrating data capture and classification.

B. Network Traffic Data Collection

We set experiments for network traffic data capture by using Paessler Router Traffic Grapher (PRTG) software and Cisco flow software in a Cisco 3900 router series hardware. The data captured at this stage were used to test the models. Online data donated by Mills [31] were downloaded in April 2021 from the Kaggle website (www.kaggle.com). These data were used for training the models with the variables shown in Table II. The experiment of the training dataset was set at Lancaster University's network address space. The data set contained robust ground truth through the correlation of malicious behavior in the network. The data were then stored in a computer and external hard disks for backup in packet capture (pcap) file format.

C. Feature Selection from Datasets

In supervised learning, after data capture, the next step is to select features from the data set collected from the network intended for testing the models. We used Joy software [32] which is a BSD-licensed libpcap-based software package for extracting features from live network traffic or pcap files. Sixteen variables with three feature class labels were generated in Comma Separated Values (CSV) and MS excel format (Table I).

D. Data Pre-processing

Data pre-processing was done in R software (Version. 4.1.2 named Bird Hippie) [33] by using RStudio editor Integrated

Development Environment (IDE) [34]. Data pre-processing was performed to transform the data to a useful format for import and manipulation by ML algorithms. A total of 191,223 datasets were extracted, followed by feature selection and were labeled as benign (86,762), malicious (74,110), and outliers (30,351). The pre-processing stage generated 133,971 labeled samples. Out of these samples, 70% ($n = 93,780$) and 30% ($n = 40,191$) were used for training and model testing respectively. The dataset was then scaled and centered by using median imputation for every variable.

TABLE I. DESCRIPTION OF VARIABLES

Complete name	Abbreviation
Average inter packet time	Avgipt
Bytes in	Bytesin
Bytes out	Bytesout
Destination IP address	Destip
Destination port number	Destport
Entropy	Entropy
Number of packets out	Numpktsout
Number of packets in	Numpktsin
Protocol	Proto
Source IP address	Srcip
Source port number	Srcport
Time end	Timeend
Time start	Timestart
Total entropy	Totalentropy
Duration	Duration
Feature class label	Label

E. Variable Multicollinearity Test

After the data pre-processing stage, we looked for variable multicollinearity by using the Spearman correlation coefficient test [35]. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) method was applied to detect and remove highly correlated variables based on VIF interpretation as shown in Table II.

TABLE II. VIF INTERPRETATION

VIF value	Conclusion
VIF = 1	Not correlated
$1 < VIF < 6$	Moderate correlated
VIF > 6	Highly correlated

To identify variables to remove or to retain in the model, R software [33] was used and RStudio IDE [34]. Model development and data analysis were conducted in a laptop with Quad Intel Core i5, 8GB of RAM, and 560 SSD running macOS Big Sur. VIF is the measure of how the variance is inflated by the correlation of the predictors which leads to the variance increase of predictors [36]. Variables with higher correlation were removed from the list while those with $VIF \ 1 \leq VIF < 6$ were kept for model development as shown in Table III.

F. Model Development

Models were developed by using the classification and regression training (Caret) packages [21] in R software with R programming language. Other packages (e.g. ggplot2, randomForest, and xgboost) were used for calculations, data manipulation, and visualization. A total of nine predictors, with three classes, namely benign, malicious, and outlier from

133,971 samples were used. Re-sampling was done by using the 10-fold cross-validation method to validate the outcome of the classifier, whereby the classification was repeated once. In this paper, different models were developed by using normal supervised classifications: C5.0, k-NN, Mixture Discriminant Analysis (MDA) algorithm, Regularized Discriminant Analysis (RDA), and NB. For comparison purposes ensemble learning classifiers, namely RF from boosting techniques and eGB from bagging techniques were used as indicated in Table IV.

TABLE III. MULTI-COLINEARITY TEST

Variables	Tolerance	VIF	Eigenvalue	Condition index
avgipt	0.998	1.002	3.421	1.000
bytesin	0.660	1.516	1.470	1.525
bytesout	0.351	2.852	1.096	1.767
entropy	0.816	1.225	0.990	1.859
numpktsout	0.300	3.338	0.691	2.224
numpktsin	0.268	3.738	0.645	2.303
totalentropy	0.198	5.051	0.372	3.031
distance	0.807	1.238	0.186	4.292

TABLE IV. CLASSIFIERS AND LEARNING METHOD

Classifier	Learning method
eGB	Ensemble (Boosting)
RF	Ensemble (Bagging)
C5.0	Normal Supervised
k-NN	Normal Supervised
RDA	Normal Supervised
MDA	Normal Supervised
NB	Normal Supervised

A serial process for RF and eGB as sequential and parallel categories of ensemble learning classifiers respectively was completed as indicated in Figure 2. RF algorithm depends on aggregating the output from several trees. Trees are modified, pruned, and an average of the results and predictions is done by using the estimation of the dependent variables on new observations. The eGB a popular ensemble learner' method which is used in ML with AdaBoost in DTs. It avoids over-fitting challenges and its accuracy is higher than AdaBoost's.

Fig. 2. Flow chart for ensemble learning classifiers.

The normal classifiers and learning methods are described below.

1) C5.0 Classification Model

This model is an extension of C4.5 which establishes a DT where every feature is considered during classification [37]. The trees constructed by C50 have high accuracy and a minimum breakdown which makes the classifier reliable and faster. The model is used to handle non-numerical features such as factor, character, etc., therefore, the model was used as a DT classifier or boosted classifier following [38]. In most studies, C5.0 performs higher than CART and C4.5 [39].

2) k-Nearest Neighbors Algorithm

In ML, k-NN is considered as a lazy learning classifier and it is used to classify objects that are closely related in training data samples based on instance learning. It uses similarity and distance between two points and categorizes the dataset based on the distance or similarities from other categories as shown in (1) and Figure 2. By calculating the Euclidean distance [40], the New Class in the figure will belong to Class C and not in Class B whereas, by using similarities, this occurs when we choose $k = 4$ as the number of neighbors. Alternatively, these can be done by using the Euclidean distance as indicated in (1) from P1 to P2.

$$\text{Euclidean Distance} = \sqrt{(P2 - P1)^2 + (K2 - K1)^2} \quad (1)$$

In this study, we used $k = 29$ because it produced the optimal results for the acquired data.

Fig. 3. Diagram illustrating the k-NN classification technique.

3) Mixture Discriminant Analysis

Discriminant analysis is used to predict the probability of belonging to a given class (or category) based on one or multiple predictor variables. It works with continuous and/or categorical predictor variables. In MDA, each class is assumed to be a Gaussian mixture of subclasses. It is the extension of Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) which can be used as supervised classification. The method is nonparametric because it minimizes within-group variability. LDA can be used in multi-class classification methods that follow the Gaussian theorem to model classes. In our dataset we had three classes denoted by "P" and our training sample was denoted by (y_1, \dots, y_n) with classes (w_1, \dots, w_n) , where $w_i \in \{1..P\}$. The prior probability j_k of each class follows the Gaussian

model $\theta(y | \mu_p, \Sigma)$. The estimation from the model (a_p) can be generated mathematically by:

$$a_p = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{I(z_i=p)}{n} \quad (2)$$

where a_p is the model estimate, p is the number of classes in the data sets, n the number of samples, and z_i a constant for normal distribution.

4) Regularized Discriminant Analysis

RDA uses multivariate means as well as a covariance matrix. The properties are generated from the data and used in the predictions. RDA data use Gaussian assumptions whereby each variable when plotted is like a bell curve. The model generates variance and means of each class from the data as illustrated in (3):

$$mean_p = \frac{1}{np} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad (3)$$

The variance of the samples was computed using (4):

$$Variance = \frac{1}{n-p} \sum_{i=1}^n [(x_i) - mean_p] \quad (4)$$

where n is the number of instances, P the number of classes, x the input values, and np is the number of classes in the instance.

For model prediction in RDA, we used the classes with the highest probability of the classes (h) with x as input through the Bayesian theorem as illustrated in (5):

$$P(Y = h | X = x) = \frac{P(h) \times P(x|h)}{\sum_{l=1}^K (P(l) \times P(x|l))} \quad (5)$$

where $P(x|k)$ is the estimated probability of x belonging to the class k , $P(Y = k|X = x)$ is the probability of the class ($Y = k$) given the input data x , and $P(k)$ is the base probability of a given class k . We are considering ($Y = k$).

5) Naïve Bayes

The use of NB classifiers in ML especially in anomaly detection has been widely applied in filtering spam emails. The accuracy of separating spam in the email is limited because its strength depends on the independence between the features [41]. The model also suffers from the heavy overhead computation which makes the mode use more resources during execution [42]. Therefore, we used this model with others for comparison due to simplicity and efficiency. NB uses the concept of the Bayesian theorem with the assumption of prior knowledge of a given hypothesis to classify features. The theorem state as:

$$P(h|d) = \frac{P(d|h) \times P(h)}{P(d)} \quad (6)$$

where $P(d)$ is the probability of the data, $P(h)$ is the probability of hypothesis h being true, $P(h|d)$ the posterior probability, $P(d|h)$ the probability of data d given that the hypothesis h was true. Likewise, the maximum posterior (MAP) hypothesis can be calculated by applying (7):

$$MAP(h) = \max(\frac{P(d|h) \times P(h)}{P(d)}) \quad (7)$$

6) Model Evaluation Metrics

The proposed classification techniques used two ensemble learning methods versus five normal supervised ML. Model Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 score metrics were used for model evaluations. Recall, F1 score, Precision, Accuracy can be mathematically computed by using the equations from Table V [11, 28]. True Positive (TP) occurs when the values of both predicted class and actual class are 1. True Negative (TN) occurs when the values of the predicted actual classes are both 0. False negatives (FN) and False Positives (FP) occur when the predicted class changes the actual class.

TABLE V. MODEL EVALUATION METRICS

Metrics	Formula
Accuracy	(TP + TN) / (TP+TN+FP+FN)
True positive rate	TP / (TP + FN)
False positive rate	FP / (FP + TN)
Precision	TP / (TP + FP)
Recall	TP / (TP + FN)
F1 score	2 Precision × Recall / (Precision + Recall)

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study's main objective was to evaluate the performance of different models in network traffic classifications. To achieve this objective, the current study used ensemble learning methods and normal supervised classifications for comparison. Multilabel data features were classified by using different models. The following evaluation metrics were applied for both ensemble and normal supervised learning: Accuracy, Under the Curve (AUC), Precision, Recall, Sensitivity, Specificity, Positive and Negative predictions.

A. Model Accuracy

1) Normal Supervised Learning Methods

Results from the five algorithms that were developed before subjecting individual models to ensemble learning techniques showed that k-NN had the highest accuracy followed by C5.0 and MDA with accuracy of 0.868, 0.761, and 0.741 respectively. NB classifier scored the lowest accuracy of 0.696 as shown in Table VI. These results are in accordance with the findings in [25, 43, 44].

TABLE VI. EVALUATION METRICS OF NORMAL SUPERVISED LEARNING METHODS

Method	Accuracy	Kappa
k-NN	0.868	0.833
C5.0	0.761	0.585
MDA	0.742	0.558
RDA	0.738	0.561
NB	0.696	0.491

2) Ensemble Models

Results from the two higher-performing ensemble models in higher dimensional dataset techniques showed that RF had higher accuracy compared to eGB as presented in Table VII. Our study is supported by [45], in which ensemble methods (xGB and RF) were used with accuracy of 89.09% and 85.49%

respectively. Another study that supports our result was [13] as indicated in the comparison in Table XIII.

TABLE VII. EVALUATION METRICS OF ENSEMBLE LEARNING METHODS

Method	Accuracy	Kappa	Logloss
RF (bagging)	0.904	0.841	2.369
eGB (boosting)	0.902	0.830	0.223

3) Comparison of Normal Supervised and Ensemble Models

The results from the comparison done after developing the models by using ensemble learning and supervised algorithms revealed that in normal supervised algorithms, k-NN had the highest accuracy as shown in Table VI. Both the ensemble learning methods had higher accuracy, with RF having the highest.

B. Evaluation of the Normal Supervised Learning Processed by Ensemble Classifier

After processing supervised algorithms by using ensemble learning methods, there was an improvement of accuracy and Kappa values as shown in Table VIII. C5.0 had the highest accuracy (0.902) as compared to the previous accuracy of 0.761 (Table V). On the other hand, k-NN also improved with a small margin from 0.868 to 0.898.

TABLE VIII. ACCURACY AND KAPPA FOR NORMAL SUPERVISED LEARNING PROCESSED BY ENSEMBLE CLASSIFIERS

Normal supervised learning	Accuracy	Kappa	Logloss
C5.0	0.902	0.839	0.229
k-NN	0.898	0.832	2.699
RDA	0.738	0.561	0.653
MDA	0.739	0.560	0.747
NB	0.698	0.470	0.471

C. Model AUC

AUC was the highest in eGB, followed by C5.0, whereas RDA had the least as shown in Table IX. The value of F1 score metrics, as the measure of the test's accuracy, was highest in C50, followed by k-NN and eGB. RDA scored the least F1-score.

TABLE IX. AUC AND F1 SCORE

Classifier	AUC	F1-scores
eGB	0.979	0.865
C5.0	0.978	0.870
RF	0.944	0.854
k-NN	0.916	0.868
NB	0.910	0.521
MDA	0.888	0.589
RDA	0.863	0.489

D. Precision and Recall

The results showed that eGB has the highest Precision followed by k-NN and RF, while RDA scored the least Precision as presented in Table X. RF exhibited the highest Recall followed by C50 and k-NN, while NB scored the lowest value.

TABLE X. PRECISION AND RECALL RESULTS

Classifier	Precision	Recall
eGB	0.906	0.843
k-NN	0.900	0.849
RF	0.900	0.867
C50	0.897	0.865
NB	0.777	0.553
MDA	0.670	0.601
RDA	0.558	0.593

E. Model Sensitivity and Specificity

RF scored the highest sensitivity, followed by C50 and k-NN, while NB had the lowest sensitivity as shown in Table XI. Furthermore, RF attained the highest specificity, followed by k-NN and eGB, while NB scored the lowest.

TABLE XI. SENSITIVITY AND SPECIFICITY RESULTS

Classifier	Sensitivity	Specificity
RF	0.867	0.946
C50	0.865	0.897
k-NN	0.849	0.942
eGB	0.843	0.943
MDA	0.601	0.859
RDA	0.593	0.859
NB	0.553	0.822

F. Prediction

Both Positive and Negative predictions generated from the models are presented in Table XII. eGB attained the highest positive prediction followed by RF and k-NN. RDA scored the lowest positive prediction. NB scored the highest negative prediction, followed by MDA.

TABLE XII. POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE PREDICTIONS

Classifier	Positive	Negative
eGB	0.906	0.954
k-NN	0.900	0.954
RF	0.900	0.955
C50	0.897	0.955
NB	0.777	0.874
MDA	0.670	0.883
RDA	0.558	0.891

G. Discussion

The result from this study has been compared with the results from [13] as shown in Table XIII and Figure 4. The acquired results show that the proposed techniques achieved better accuracy, AUC, Recall, and Precision, but not F1 score. The study which [13] shows that eGB, C5.0, and RF had an accuracy of 0.901, 0.886, and 0.885 respectively. The findings of this paper also show an accuracy of 0.902, 0.902, and 0.904 for C5.0, eGB, and RF. Therefore, our results are higher considering model accuracies. The study conducted in [46] was looking at anomaly detection by using ML techniques by using RF. One of the performance metrics was the accuracy of RF which was 99.7 which is higher compared to this paper results. Another study [47] was utilized the RF classifier and scored an accuracy of 0.893, Recall 0.890, F1 score of 0.896, and precision of 0.92. In [45], eGB obtained the following metrics scores; Accuracy of 0.926, Precision 0.927, Recall 0.926, and

F1 score 0.924 which are similar or less than the same respective scores of the current study (Table XIII).

TABLE XIII. COMPARISON WITH [13]

Classifier	Accuracy	AUC	Recall	Precision	F1 score	Kappa
[13]						
eGB	0.901	0.995	0.75	0.901	0.899	0.875
RF	0.885	0.948	0.741	0.882	0.885	0.855
C5.0	0.886	0.985	0.725	0.883	0.884	0.856
k-NN	0.85	0.966	0.675	0.846	0.847	0.811
NB	0.297	0.633	0.128	0.23	0.228	0.096
Current study						
MDA	0.739	0.888	0.601	0.67	0.56	0.56
RDA	0.742	0.86	0.593	0.558	0.561	0.738
RF	0.904	0.979	0.867	0.9	0.854	0.841
eGB	0.902	0.944	0.843	0.906	0.865	0.83
NB	0.698	0.91	0.553	0.777	0.521	0.47
k-NN	0.898	0.916	0.849	0.9	0.868	0.32
C5.0	0.902	0.978	0.865	0.897	0.87	0.839

Fig. 4. Graphs showing comparisons of this study with others.

The results of this paper are also equivalent and sometimes above the results of [48, 49]. One can conclude that the results of the current study are supported by other studies, however, with slight variations in some parameters.

IV. CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATIONS, AND FUTURE WORK

This article presented and compared the results of normal supervised algorithms and ensemble learning techniques, namely RF and eGB. The individual classifiers were compared with ensemble learners by using a real experimental dataset with little correlation. The overall accuracy of the ensemble methods was higher than the accuracy of normal classifiers. Therefore, we can conclude that the ensemble learning techniques can be used to classify the multilabel network traffic.

This study contributes to the knowledge of network traffic classification by using supervised and ensemble learning and multilabel datasets. To the best of our knowledge there are no similar studies regarding the network traffic classification in Tanzania.

The current study can be extended to new emerging technologies (edge computing, cyber security, e-commerce, fog computing, and distributed databases such as Blockchain). Also, the use of emerging ML approaches like reinforcement and deep learning could be applied with new experimental datasets. The performance comparison of ensemble learning with other learning methods in classifying network traffic in emerging technologies is very important. Application of higher processing speeds and distributed systems such as H2O, Apache Spark, etc. to facilitate the application of big data in the massive network traffic data can be also considered.

FUNDING AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The current study was funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation grant number [641918] through the AFRICANBIOSERVICES PROJECT in Tanzania under Tanzanian Wildlife Research Institute (TAWIRI). The authors extend their appreciation to Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority (TCRA), TAWIRI, and Tanzania National Parks (TANAPA) for their support during data collection, and NM-AIST for the conducive working and research environment.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Aceto, V. Persico, and A. Pescapé, "The role of Information and Communication Technologies in healthcare: taxonomies, perspectives, and challenges," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 107, pp. 125–154, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2018.02.008>.
- [2] S. Morgan, "The 2020 Data Attack Surface Report," Arcserve, 2020.
- [3] J. Shi, C. Pan, W. Zhang, and M. Chen, "Performance Analysis for User-Centric Dense Networks With mmWave," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 14537–14548, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2893403>.
- [4] TCRA, "A: TELECOM SERVICES," 2021
- [5] G. Ali, M. Ally Dida, and A. Elikana Sam, "Two-Factor Authentication Scheme for Mobile Money: A Review of Threat Models and Countermeasures," *Future Internet*, vol. 12, no. 10, Oct. 2020, Art. no. 160, <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi12100160>.
- [6] N. B. Amor, S. Benferhat, and Z. Elouedi, "Naive Bayes vs decision trees in intrusion detection systems," in *ACM Symposium on Applied Computing*, Nicosia, Cyprus, Mar. 2004, pp. 420–424, <https://doi.org/10.1145/967900.967989>.
- [7] X. Liu *et al.*, "Attention-based bidirectional GRU networks for efficient HTTPS traffic classification," *Information Sciences*, vol. 541, pp. 297–315, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2020.05.035>.
- [8] P. Barford and D. Plonka, "Characteristics of network traffic flow anomalies," in *1st ACM SIGCOMM Workshop on Internet measurement*, San Francisco, CA, USA, Nov. 2001, pp. 69–73, <https://doi.org/10.1145/505202.505211>.
- [9] L. Machlica, K. Bartos, and M. Sofka, "Learning detectors of malicious web requests for intrusion detection in network traffic," *arXiv:1702.02530 [cs, stat]*, Feb. 2017, Accessed: Apr. 20, 2022.
- [10] S. Manaseer, O. Al-Nahar, and A. Hyassat, "Network Traffic Modeling, Case Study: The University of Jordan," *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 13–16, Jan. 2019.
- [11] K. Aldriwish, "A Deep Learning Approach for Malware and Software Piracy Threat Detection," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7757–7762, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4412>.
- [12] Z. Liu, N. Su, Y. Qin, J. Lu, and X. Li, "A Deep Random Forest Model on Spark for Network Intrusion Detection," *Mobile Information Systems*, vol. 2020, Dec. 2020, Art. no. e6633252, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/6633252>.
- [13] K. Demertzis, K. Tsiknas, D. Takezis, C. Skianis, and L. Iliadis, "Darknet Traffic Big-Data Analysis and Network Management for Real-

- Time Automating of the Malicious Intent Detection Process by a Weight Agnostic Neural Networks Framework," *Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 7, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 781, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics10070781>.
- [14] A. D'Alconzo, I. Drago, A. Morichetta, M. Mellia, and P. Casas, "A Survey on Big Data for Network Traffic Monitoring and Analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 800–813, Sep. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNSM.2019.2933358>.
- [15] R. de O. Schmidt, R. Sadre, and A. Pras, "Gaussian traffic revisited," in *IFIP Networking Conference*, Brooklyn, NY, USA, Dec. 2013, pp. 1–9.
- [16] M. I. Jordan and T. M. Mitchell, "Machine learning: Trends, perspectives, and prospects," *Science*, vol. 349, no. 6245, pp. 255–260, Jul. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaa8415>.
- [17] C. Dong, C. Zhang, Z. Lu, B. Liu, and B. Jiang, "CETAnalytics: Comprehensive effective traffic information analytics for encrypted traffic classification," *Computer Networks*, vol. 176, Jul. 2020, Art. no. 107258, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2020.107258>.
- [18] W. Ruan, Y. Liu, and R. Zhao, "Pattern Discovery in DNS Query Traffic," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 17, pp. 80–87, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2013.05.012>.
- [19] H. He, X. Luo, F. Ma, C. Che, and J. Wang, "Network traffic classification based on ensemble learning and co-training," *Science in China Series F: Information Sciences*, vol. 52, no. 2, pp. 338–346, Feb. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11432-009-0050-8>.
- [20] B. Yamansavascular, M. A. Guvensan, A. G. Yavuz, and M. E. Karşligil, "Application identification via network traffic classification," in *International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications*, Silicon Valley, CA, USA, Jan. 2017, pp. 843–848, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCNC.2017.7876241>.
- [21] B. Zhang, Z. Liu, Y. Jia, J. Ren, and X. Zhao, "Network Intrusion Detection Method Based on PCA and Bayes Algorithm," *Security and Communication Networks*, vol. 2018, Nov. 2018, Art. no. e1914980, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/1914980>.
- [22] G. Harinahalli Lokesh and G. Bore Gowda, "Phishing website detection based on effective machine learning approach," *Journal of Cyber Security Technology*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–14, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1080/23742917.2020.1813396>.
- [23] A. Hussein, J. Agbinya, and I. Satti, "A Survey on Data mining Techniques for Water Flow Forecasting," *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 13–27, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.22587/ajbas.2020.14.3.2>.
- [24] S. E. Gomez, L. Hernandez-Callejo, B. C. Martinez, and A. J. Sanchez-Esguevillas, "Exploratory study on Class Imbalance and solutions for Network Traffic Classification," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 343, pp. 100–119, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2018.07.091>.
- [25] M. Soysal and E. G. Schmidt, "Machine learning algorithms for accurate flow-based network traffic classification: Evaluation and comparison," *Performance Evaluation*, vol. 67, no. 6, pp. 451–467, Jun. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.peva.2010.01.001>.
- [26] F. Dehghani, N. Movahhedinia, M. R. Khayyambashi, and S. Kianian, "Real-Time Traffic Classification Based on Statistical and Payload Content Features," in *2nd International Workshop on Intelligent Systems and Applications*, Wuhan, China, Dec. 2010, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IWISA.2010.5473467>.
- [27] R. M. AlZoman and M. J. F. Alenazi, "A Comparative Study of Traffic Classification Techniques for Smart City Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 14, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 4677, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21144677>.
- [28] D. Chopra, N. Joshi, and I. Mathur, "Improving Translation Quality By Using Ensemble Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3512–3514, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2269>.
- [29] A. J. Wyner, M. Olson, J. Bleich, and D. Mease, "Explaining the Success of AdaBoost and Random Forests as Interpolating Classifiers," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 18, no. 48, pp. 1–33, 2017.
- [30] G. S. Oreyku, F. J. Mtenzi, and C. A. Shoniregun, "Traffic classification and packet detections to facilitate networks security," *International Journal of Internet Technology and Secured Transactions*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 240–252, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJTST.2011.041294>.
- [31] R. Mills, "LUFLOW Network Intrusion Detection Data Set," <https://www.kaggle.com/mryanm/luflow-network-intrusion-detection-data-set> (accessed Apr. 20, 2022).
- [32] B. Hudson, "Understanding Encrypted Traffic Using 'Joy' for Monitoring and Forensics," presented at the Cisco Live!, Orlando, FL, USA, Jun. 10, 2018.
- [33] R Core Team, *R: a language and environment for statistical computing*. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing, 2018.
- [34] J. J. Allaire, "RStudio: Integrated Development Environment for R," presented at the The R User Conference 2011, Coventry, UK, Aug. 2011.
- [35] J. Hauke and T. Kossowski, "Comparison of Values of Pearson's and Spearman's Correlation Coefficients on the Same Sets of Data," *Quaestiones Geographicae*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 87–93, Jun. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10117-011-0021-1>.
- [36] J. I. Daoud, "Multicollinearity and Regression Analysis," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 949, Sep. 2017, Art. no. 012009, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/949/1/012009>.
- [37] J. R. Quinlan, "Book Review: C4.5: Programs for Machine Learning," *Machine Learning*, vol. 16, pp. 235–240, 1994.
- [38] M. Kuhn, "The caret Package," *Journal of Statistical Software*, vol. 28, Jan. 2012.
- [39] S. Garg, "An evaluation of investor acceptability for physical gold using classification (Decision Tree)," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 37, pp. 950–954, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.06.177>.
- [40] D. Hamilton, R. Pacheco, B. Myers, and B. Peltzer, "kNN vs. SVM: A comparison of algorithms," in *Fire Continuum-Preparing for the future of wildland fire*, Missoula, USA, Dec. 2018, vol. 78, pp. 95–109.
- [41] W. Feng, J. Sun, L. Zhang, C. Cao, and Q. Yang, "A support vector machine based naive Bayes algorithm for spam filtering," in *35th International Performance Computing and Communications Conference*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, Dec. 2016, pp. 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PCCC.2016.7820655>.
- [42] L. Jiang, Z. Cai, and D. Wang, "Improving Naive Bayes for Classification," *International Journal of Computers and Applications*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 328–332, Jan. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.2316/Journal.202.2010.3.202-2747>.
- [43] A. Callado et al., "A Survey on Internet Traffic Identification," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 37–52, 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SURV.2009.090304>.
- [44] S. Chen, G. I. Webb, L. Liu, and X. Ma, "A novel selective naïve Bayes algorithm," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 192, Mar. 2020, Art. no. 105361, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2019.105361>.
- [45] O. Aouedi, K. Piamrat, and B. Parrein, "Performance evaluation of feature selection and tree-based algorithms for traffic classification," in *International Conference on Communications Workshops*, Montreal, QC, Canada, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCWorkshops50388.2021.9473580>.
- [46] J. J. Estevez-Pereira, D. Fernandez, and F. J. Novoa, "Network Anomaly Detection Using Machine Learning Techniques," *Proceedings*, vol. 54, no. 1, 2020, Art. no. 8, <https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings2020054008>.
- [47] V. Dutta, M. Choras, M. Pawlicki, and R. Kozik, "A Deep Learning Ensemble for Network Anomaly and Cyber-Attack Detection," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 16, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 4583, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20164583>.
- [48] M. Singh, G. Srivastava, and P. Kumar, "Internet Traffic Classification Using Machine Learning," *International Journal of Database Theory and Application*, vol. 9, pp. 45–54, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.14257/ijdt.2016.9.12.05>.
- [49] T. C. Obasi, "Encrypted Network Traffic Classification using Ensemble Learning Techniques," M.S. thesis, Carleton University, Ottawa, ON, Canada, 2020.
- [50] D. K. Singh and M. Shrivastava, "Evolutionary Algorithm-based Feature Selection for an Intrusion Detection System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7130–7134, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4149>.

Household Waste Management Challenges

The Case of M'sila, Algeria

Mostepha Naghel

City, Environment, Society, and Sustainable
Development Laboratory
University of Biskra, Algeria
mostepha.naghel@univ-msila.dz

Abdallah Farhi

Design and Modeling Laboratory of Architectural
and Urban Forms and Atmospheres
University of Biskra, Algeria
a.farhi@univ-biskra.dz

Ali Redjem

City, Environment, Society and Sustainable Development Laboratory
University of M'sila, Algeria
ali.redjem@univ-msila.dz

Received: 16 March 2022 | Revised: 9 April 2022 | Accepted: 14 April 2022

Abstract—Household waste and uncontrolled urbanization management are considered major problems in African countries. In the Hodna region, the phenomenon seems to be more important in urban centers because of the huge amount of household waste generated by domestic and commercial activities. In most Algerian cities, solid waste is piled up in huge quantities in dumps and is dumped indiscriminately in waterways and public spaces. Uncontrolled urbanization, industrial development, and the evolution of lifestyle lead to increased production of waste, whereas the waste management techniques used in urban areas should be reconsidered. From this perspective, this paper studies and analyses in a spatio-temporal approach, the practices of household waste management in the city of M'sila in order to evaluate the state of such management and identify the key elements of integrated planning of waste management.

Keywords—M'sila; household waste; environment; urbanization; living environment

I. INTRODUCTION

All Algerian cities are undergoing an accelerated urbanization process [1]. The strong demographic growth and the economic, social, and political upheavals directly impact the constantly increasing volume of household waste produced daily [2]. These problems common to all the Algerian cities, are characterized by uncontrolled urbanization, i.e. poor functioning of public services following a strong urbanization (organized or informal) consuming space, and with the lack of materials and human means, this leads to difficulties of waste management (transport, collection, elimination) [1, 5]. The authorities have difficulty in containing and eliminating waste, as evidenced by the spectacle of garbage covering the roadsides and the piling up of waste in illegal dumps [4]. According to a survey conducted by the Ministry of Land Management and Environment services, more than 3000 illegal dumps have been identified. Waste management remains one of the weak stages of Algeria's urban management and urban services [5, 6]. All

urban actors must be involved, first the population, then the municipality, and finally the State to solve the waste problem. However, when it comes to the environment, specifically waste management, it is a matter of using existing management methods and responding to increasingly complex issues by constantly reinventing them. In addition, there are limitations to the national waste disposal policy. This policy remains fundamentally archaic and is characterized by the inefficiency of public intervention [6]. Indeed, the operational strategy of waste management is limited only to the collection, transport, and dumping. So far, this strategy lacks any complementary disposal and treatment structure [6]. The material and human resources of collection companies must be adapted to the rate of population growth. It is necessary to organize landfills in order to overcome the problem of saturation, and finally, it is necessary to revalorize the waste for possible reuse [7]. The research that has been done so far on household waste in M'sila remains insufficient. Generally speaking, the available literature on household waste focuses on the technical and organizational aspects of the public waste service and the threats posed by waste. However, there are themes in recovery/recycling that need to be explored in greater depth in order to understand better the multiple facets of waste in M'sila. Thus, this paper presents an inventory of waste management in M'sila. In particular, this study aims to contribute to the problem of solid waste management for better strategies to fight against insalubrity in urban areas [8].

II. WASTE DEFINITION ACCORDING TO THE ALGERIAN REGULATIONS

Waste consists of three main categories [8, 14-15]: household and similar waste, special waste (industrial, agricultural, care, services, etc.), and inert waste. The definition of the different types of waste and treatment methods may vary from one country to another [8]. According to the regulations in force, household waste is defined by Article 2 of Decree No. 84-378 of December 15, 1984, setting the conditions for

cleaning and removing household waste, which are domestic waste and assimilable by nature volume. It is in particular:

- Industrial or collective household waste.
- Products resulting from cleaning such as sweeping, sewer cleaning.
- Bulky waste, bulky objects, scrap metal, rubble, etc.
- Anatomical or infectious waste from hospitals, chemical or other care facilities.
- Slaughterhouse waste and offal.
- Commercial waste, packaging, and other residues generated by commercial activities.

Fig. 1. Location of the city of M'sila in its regional context.

III. SOURCES AND METHODS

The methodology adopted is based on literature research and field surveys. The documentary literature review allowed us to consult memoirs, books, theses, and articles in libraries and on the internet. It allowed us to have information concerning the urban dynamics and the waste management plan. The field observation allowed us to discover the garbage deposits, the state of the environment, the infrastructures, and the urban space's evolution. Simple field observation indicates a low collection rate of 152 tons/inhabitant of solid waste produced in the commune of M'sila [26]. The questionnaire was administered on 3 samples in 3 different sectors (collective housing, individual housing "allotment", and traditional housing). In addition to the residential areas, there are also predominantly commercial areas. The method of the household waste characterization was carried out in applying the sampling protocol in respect of the standards NF X30-408 and NF X30-413 relating to the characterization of waste (sampling and sorting). CARADEME is the new guide introduced by ADEME (French Environment and Energy Management Agency) for local campaigns of household waste characterization [11-13].

A. The Study Area

A medium-sized city, M'sila is located on the northern edge of the steppe of the Hodna region. It is located 250km from the capital Algiers, covering an area of 233km² having 224,991 inhabitants [27]. It is characterized by a strategic geographical position. Crossed by the RN40 (connecting M'sila to Batna, Biskra, and Setif), the RN60 (connecting M'sila to Algiers), and the RN45 (connecting M'sila to BordjBou-Argeridj and Bou-Saada), it is an ideal crossroads connecting the North of

the country to the South and the East to the West. It is limited, in the North by the commune of El Ache (Wilaya of Bordj-Bou-Argeridj), in the South by the commune of Ouled Madhi, in the East by the commune of Metarfa, and in the West by the commune of Ouled Mansour.

B. Situation of Waste Management in Algeria

In Algeria, waste management is carried out by public service, the National Program for the Integrated Management of Household Waste (Programme national pour la gestion intégrée des déchets ménagers, PROGDEM), and by the National Waste Agency (Agence Nationale des Déchets, AND) created by Executive Decree No. 02-175 of May 20, 2002 [9]. The NGOs working in Algeria on the management of DSU are grouped in an association called Coordination des entreprises de gestion des déchets (CEGED). The public administration supports the CEGED's actions, which requires inhabitants to join to get rid of DSU [6, 9]. Since the Johannesburg Summit in 2002, Algeria has intensified its environmental protection and sustainable development actions, thus giving a prominent place to social and ecological aspects in its choice of society model. The Algerian Government has implemented a National Strategy for the Environment and a National Action Plan for the Environment and Sustainable Development (Stratégie Nationale de l'Environnement et un Plan National d'actions pour l'environnement et le développement durable, PNAE-DD) which:

- Involves all the ministries and decentralized services, local authorities, and civil society, whose role is to be a force for proposals;
- Aims to integrate environmental sustainability into the country's development strategy (to induce sustainable growth and reduce poverty);
- Puts in place effective public policies to address the environmental externalities of growth connected to activities increasingly initiated by the private sector. This strategy, whose main objectives are: improving health and quality of life, conserving and improving the productivity of natural capital, reducing economic losses and improving competitiveness, and protecting the regional and global environment, has resulted in: the development of the legislative and regulatory framework, institutional capacity building, and the introduction of economic and financial instruments, and the mobilization of significant investments, through the start-up of the first environmental projects, to halt the degradation of the environment and even reverse certain negative trends observed.

The law 01-19 of December 12, 2001, relating to the management, the control, and the elimination of waste constitutes in this respect the starting point and the reference of this new strategy. Thus, two particular programs which constitute the continuation of this law are carried out and have obtained encouraging results:

- PROGDEM (National Program of Municipal Waste Management).

- PNAGDES (Plan National de Gestion des Déchets Spéciaux, National Plan for Special Waste Management).

These programs are characterized in particular by the elaboration, in collaboration with the authorities and local communities, of master plans of integrated management and treatment of waste, and the realization of concrete projects and adapted to the local specificities, like the realization of the Technical Landfill Centers (Centres d'Enfouissement Technique, CET).

C. Evaluation of the Household Waste Management Process

Waste management in all its ramifications is simply a planned system to effectively control the generation, storage, collection, transportation, treatment, and disposal of waste. Waste management is an important element of environmental protection. Its purpose is to provide a hygienic, economical, and efficient solid waste storage, collection, transportation, and treatment or disposal without polluting the atmosphere, soil, or water. The various stages of solid waste management, from generation to sanitary disposal, are considered a solid waste chain. So, the solid waste chain is the pathway through the solid waste from generation to the point of final disposal [3, 5-6].

D. Current Household Waste Management in M'sila

Municipal waste management is generally organized in 3 sectors [8]: the public sector, which has responsibility for monitoring and enforcing the provisions of certain urban services including solid waste management, the formal private sector engaged in waste management, including collection and recycling, and the informal private sector engaged in the reuse of certain types of waste [10, 21, 23].

1) Public Sector

a) At the National Level

The Ministry of Land Management and Environment (MATE) has primary the responsibility for national environmental policy. It was created at the end of the 1980s with a name that varied over time. In the 1970s, the environmental task was attached to the Ministry of Hydraulics and then to the Secretariat of State for Forestry. The Law on Waste Management, Control, and Disposal provides for the creation of three intermediate national bodies:

- AND was created by Executive Decree No. 02-175 of May 20, 2002, and placed under the supervision of the MATE. It provides an adequate instrument to assist local authorities in implementing the national waste policy.
- The National Observatory for the Environment and Sustainable Development (Observatoire national de l'environnement et du développement durable, ONEDD) was created on April 3, 2002. It is a public establishment of an industrial and commercial nature (EPIC), with legal personality and financial autonomy.
- The National Conservatory for Environmental Training (Conservatoire national des formations à l'environnement, CNFE) was created in August 2002. It has the status of EPIC and has two main missions: the training of various

public or private actors in the field of the environment, and environmental education for the public, especially schools.

b) At the Regional Level

At the regional level, the local public service of waste management is under the responsibility of:

- The Regional Environmental Inspectorates (Inspections Régionales de l'Environnement) are decentralized bodies of the State, founded by the Decree No. 88-227 of November 5, 1988 [29]. They were created on the power, organization, and functioning of the bodies of inspectors responsible for environmental protection. The mission of these inspectorates is to ensure compliance with the legislation and regulations in environmental protection to note and investigate violations in this area. At the level of the wilayas, the State has created decentralized services in charge of the environment.
- The Wilaya Environmental Departments (Directions de l'Environnement de Wilaya, DEW), were created by the Executive Decree No. 96-60 of January 27, 1996 [30], and succeeded the 15 wilaya environmental inspectorates. The wilaya directorates have 3 main areas of activity: coordination, control, and information. Coordination requires good communication and organization between the bodies of the State, the wilayas, and the communes to establish an environmental protection program for the entire territory and take measures to prevent all forms of environmental degradation (pollution, nuisances, soil erosion, etc.).

c) At the Local Level

The local level in this study refers to two structures responsible for local waste services: the communes and the groupings of communes. Article 7 of the communal code provides that the commune is responsible for preserving hygiene and public health, particularly the evacuation and treatment of wastewater and household waste.

2) Private Sector

Private sector participation in solid waste management in Algeria is very limited. The 2001 law made municipal waste management public service available to private investment and concessions to promote this participation.

3) Informal Sector

The third sector involved in waste recovery in Algeria is the informal sector, which constitutes an important economic activity. It is relatively structured in two dimensions: the first is vertical from the recovery in garbage cans and landfills to the recycling industry, and the second is horizontal and based on channels by the type of recovered waste (paper, plastic, metals). This sector allows to:

- valorize a large amount of waste,
- reduce transportation and collection costs for communities,
- provide income to many people,
- increase the capacity of landfills,

- ensure the raw material for some companies,
- situation of the pre-collection of waste.

IV. MODE OF COLLECTION, DELIMITATION, AND WASTE TREATMENT

Is provided mainly by the CET of M'sila. The management of household waste has two essential stages: removal and elimination. The removal of waste includes the pre-collection and the collection itself. The elimination refers to landfills and burials in pits.

A. Collection and Pre-collection

1) Pre-collection

The concept of pre-collection implies all operations that precede the actual collection of waste. It aims to collect, gather, and store waste by the inhabitants of a dwelling, building, housing, or company, then deposit them in places dedicated to waste. In Algeria, it takes various forms according to the type of housing and the accessibility of the equipment:

- The metal boxes: the pre-collection by the box is more used at the level of local center agglomeration (Agglomeration Centre Local, ACL) and secondary agglomerations (Agglomerations Secondaires, AS). These are metal caissons with a capacity of 2 to 2.7T installed in housing estates, districts, and in front of establishments that are major waste generators. The frequency of removal of these boxes varies between 2 to 3 times per week.
- The hard niches: are designed in the form of a construction delimited by a low masonry wall surrounding a base in hard material. The low wall has an opening allowing the deposit of waste by the users and their removal by the waste collectors. They are generally implanted in the villages without any preliminary study, with no protection against the attraction of various animals, and without any measure of treatment of leachates.
- Individual garbage cans: These are individual plastic garbage cans. This method of pre-collection is used more by the inhabitants of city centers and shopkeepers. The waste is put in these garbage cans, which the residents take back once emptied by the collection service.
- Plastic bags: This type of pre-collection is the most common in the city centers and individual housing estates. Before the collection trucks pass by, the residents deposit their waste in bags or cardboard boxes in front of their homes or on the sidewalks of the streets, in the form of piles that the APC truck collects for the public dump.

Fig. 2. Pre-collection of waste.

2) Collection

The collection operation is located at the heart of the waste management process. It is a public order operation that falls within the framework of protecting the population's health and ensuring a better quality of life. It consists of the collection and grouping of waste for transportation. At present, there are two methods of removal in Algeria: (1) door to door, in which the collection service ensures a regular passage for the waste evacuation, (2) involuntary contribution, in which the generator ensures the waste transfer towards a point of regrouping so that they are transported by the service in charge of the operation towards a place of elimination or treatment. This collection mode is very suitable for the selective sorting operation [31].

Fig. 3. Means of transporting waste to the landfill.

B. Waste Disposal

In Algeria, municipal solid waste management services have traditionally focused on "cleaning" only, with little attention paid to waste disposal resources. This had significant negative economic, environmental, and social impacts and the household waste sector was experiencing difficulties in almost all areas.

1) Dumping Sites

In Algeria, the elimination of household and similar waste by the setting in wild dumps is the most used mode, with a rate of 87%. Despite an environmental policy and regulations on waste disposal, such waste is constantly increasing. According to a survey conducted by the MATE services, more than 3000 illegal dumps have been identified in the 48 wilayas with an area of about 4552.5ha. An almost similar geographical location characterizes the majority of these dumps.

2) Technical Landfills

Since 2001, the Algerian government has chosen to eliminate urban waste by burying it in landfills and has launched an ambitious program of technical landfills throughout the country. One of the objectives of PROGDEM is to abandon the traditional method of waste disposal by landfilling [27].

Fig. 4. Burial and sorting of waste at the CET of M'sila.

V. EVOLUTION OF THE POPULATION OF M'SILA AS A FACTOR GENERATING HOUSEHOLD WASTE

Recent research has shown that the population grows by more than 30% annually in developing countries. This growth is most evident in urban areas, accompanied by increased waste generation [11, 24-25]. The waste problem is getting worse every year as the population increases. Table I shows a significant evolution of the amount of waste in the commune of M'sila. The amount of solid waste generated is equivalent to 85 t/d [26], which requires considerable efforts from the public authorities. This continuous increase in quantity can be explained by the population growth, the lack of recycling infrastructure, the failing collection system, and finally, the

TABLE I. EVOLUTION OF THE QUANTITY OF WASTE GENERATED IN M'SILA [27]

Year	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Number of inhabitants	161647	167480	175080	183803	194735	203822	214661	216788	224991
Quantity (t/year)	15621	18934	20688	33318	37280	46428	53274	55393	57902

VI. MANAGEMENT SYSTEM-THE COLLECTION OF HOUSEHOLD WASTE IN M'SILA

The management of household waste in the city is a complex problem that the municipality must face in order to better protect the environment and the public health. However, this management requires the participation of all the city actors (social, economic, administrative). The collection is one of the main operations of waste management and forms the cornerstone of the whole operation. It requires material and human means to evacuate the waste from the city.

A. Sector Delimitation

According to the various formal interviews carried out on several occasions with the services concerned and [31], we were able to know that to collect the waste of the city of M'sila, the technical service of the municipality has delimited 19 sectors of intervention based on two criteria:

- Existing material and human resources.
- Structural roads of the city.

B. Existing Material and Human Resources

1) Material Resources

The means implemented for the disposal of the city's household waste are wheeled collection vehicles and fixed collection means (caissons).

The wheeled collection vehicles are:

- 19 tipper trucks,
- 8 regular dump trucks,
- 2 dumpers,
- 3 agricultural tractors,
- 2 bulls and chargers,
- 1 amp truck.

For the rolling collection means mobilized for this operation, we noted that:

change in the socio-economic behavior of households where the standard of living has become acceptable even though the purchasing power has been decreasing in recent years. This evolution is also very remarkable according to the urban structure:

- The quantities of waste produced by collective housing are greater than those of individual housing.
- The collection systems used to receive these quantities of waste also differ according to the types of housing (for collective housing: there are boxes used for 500, 600, etc. houses).

- Some non-specialized collection vehicles directly affect the organization of the collection.
- There often temporary breakdowns.
- The number of specialized collection vehicles (tippers) represents the 15% of the total number of vehicles in the municipal fleet. The breakdowns of these means are explained by this low percentage and the age of the existing vehicles (14 and 20 years). Suppose we allocate the vehicles according to the number of inhabitants of M'sila. In that case, it can be noted that each specialized vehicle for 10,000 inhabitants is higher than the national average (1 vehicle/7500 inhabitants), while the international average is 1 vehicle/4000 inhabitants.

Therefore, the fleet of vehicles of the municipality shows a deficit of 4 to 5 vehicles to ensure a regular and average organization in terms of waste collection of the city and following financial means

There are two types of caissons:

- 3.5-ton boxes,
- 2.5-ton boxes,
- 240L and 120L wheeled bins.

The boxes are intended for collective housing and city facilities (hospitals, universities, etc.).

2) Human Resources

Currently, the commune of M'sila mobilizes for the collection of household waste of the city, a workforce of 70 workers including:

- 19 drivers,
- 44 waste collectors,
- 16 sweepers,
- the rest are agents of different categories (office, sorting, press, security),
- additional agents of private companies.

This workforce represents 1 employee for every 2500 inhabitants, which is much higher than the national average of 1 employee/1500 inhabitants, so the human resources show a deficit of 36 workers (waste collectors and sweepers). We note that the staff has no training in the field and that many waste collectors and sweepers are illiterate.

VII. QUANTITY OF WASTE GENERATED IN M'SILA

From 2011 to 2016, the amount of waste generated by the city has increased continuously. The annual production of the accumulation has increased from 33318 t/year to 57902 t/year [26, 27] (Table I), which is equivalent to an annual growth rate of 11%. If this growth rate continues, by the end of 2025, the quantity will reach 83795.97 t/year. The average waste quantity per capita ratio is 0.8kg/capita/day. This ratio is 0.41kg/capita/day in the slum areas and 1.23kg/capita/day in the residential areas. The ratio for the areas is higher than the estimated average for the major metropolitan areas of developing countries. Algeria's average annual per capita rate increased from 202kg in 1980 to 360kg in 2006. In urban areas, the ratio is 0.7kg/inhabitant/day. This correspondence of weight between M'sila and the rest of the country's cities is mainly related to the composition, which is in the majority made of fermentable but also of the low rate of humidity of the region. Indeed, the city of M'sila is under the influence of a dry semi-arid climate. It receives low rainfall, which is the case for the whole country. The latter influences the waste and makes it more or less light, especially as it is composed of 74.5% of organic matter [26].

VIII. COMPOSITION OF HOUSEHOLD WASTE IN M'SILA

The study of waste composition is an essential step for good management. Authors in [32, 33] cite several reasons for this, including the need to estimate the number of materials produced, identify the source of generation, facilitate the design of treatment equipment, define the physical, chemical, and thermal properties of waste, and ensure compliance with legislations. The waste of the city M'sila is composed of 74.5% of biodegradable materials, 33.1% of recyclable materials (paper, cardboard, plastic, glass, and metals), and 17% of inert materials in the form of construction debris. If we proceed to a finer classification, we obtain 13 categories in compliance with the NF X30-408 standards: putrescible waste (fermentable), plastic, metals, glass, paper, cardboard, textiles, sanitary textiles, combustible, composites, incombustible (inert), hazardous waste, fines (sand and ash). However, the content of waste varies according to the standard of living of the populations of the areas (Table II). A typological study allows us to classify the habitat in three categories:

- High standard of living settlements (generally in housing estates) where households have substantial financial resources enabling them to consume manufactured goods. These are populations belonging to the upper socio-professional class. A relatively high rate 76.2% of putrescible waste is composed essentially of organic matter despite the low concentration of its population.
- Medium standing habitats where households with a medium standard of living reside (these are the inhabitants of

collective housing), which partly explains the rate (75.3%) of putrescible waste composed essentially of organic matter; this is certainly due to the high concentration of population, translated by the important quantity of waste generated by the inhabitants of this sector whose collective housing is predominant.

- Low standard of living habitats of economic, evolutionary, and spontaneous type, highly populated with very little infrastructure (traditional or precarious habitat). There, the rate of putrescible waste is 75.9%, which corresponds to the lifestyles and standards of living of the inhabitants. To these habitat zones, it is necessary to add those of the commercial and business centers and the industrial zones that have a rate of 70.8%. The rate of cardboard and paper is the highest (13.7%) against 5.3% in the collective habitat, 5.2% in the individual, and 3.6% in the precarious one, because of the packaging activities of consumable products. The waste can be grouped into 2 main categories according to the composition obtained: household waste produced by households of different types on the one hand and waste from industrial and commercial areas on the other. This differentiation of the residential regions from industrial and commercial sites allows better waste management planning, especially for a possible recycling program.

TABLE II. PHYSICAL COMPOSITION OF HOUSEHOLD WASTE BY TYPE OF HABITAT AND ACTIVITY IN M'SILA IN 2016 [26]

Materials	Sector 8 (CET) Mostly collective housing (%)	Sector 2 (APC) Mostly individual housing (%)	Sector 4 (CET) Mostly precarious housing (%)	Sector 1 (APC) Mostly commercial use (%)
Putrescible waste	76.2	75.3	75.9	70.8
Papers	3.7	3.2	1.9	3.9
Cardboard	1.6	2.0	1.7	9.8
Textile	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.2
Sanitary textile	1.5	1.2	1.2	1.3
Plastics	6.6	8.5	6.6	6.4
Fuels	0.8	1.3	1.4	1.1
Glass	0.9	0.5	0.6	0.6
Composites	0.1	0.7	1.3	0.6
Metals	0.2	0.1	1.9	0.2
Fuels	1.7	0.9	1.3	1.5
Hazardous waste	0.1	0.8	0.9	0.7
Fines ≤ 20 mm	6.5	5.3	4.9	2.9
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%

A. Physical Characteristics

The physical waste composition is largely determined by the nature of the products, the packaging, and the consumption practices of the population. Knowing the waste composition is essential because it allows determining waste management methods and promoting treatment and recovery channels [13, 23]. The sampling results (Table III) allowed us to collect essential information to identify the waste. This sampling shows that the composition of household waste is very diverse. The composition of household waste during the random sampling of the 19 sectors of M'sila and the random selection of the contents of the weighing of a quantity of 10kg of each

sector allowed us to note that 74.8% of the waste is organic materials. The remaining 25.2% are distributed mainly on plastics, paper, and cardboard. Their percentages are higher than those of the metal and the glass. The share of paper and cardboard remains dominant due to collecting part of the waste from commercial activities such as packaging with household waste.

B. Chemical Characteristics

Several studies have focused on waste chemical characterization. Some aim to evaluate the polluting potential of these wastes [13] or demonstrate harmful effects on human health and the environment. Table IV gives examples of the elemental chemical composition of the waste in M'sila. Control of the nature and the volume of solid household waste produced in M'sila is necessary for better waste management. Also, the determination of the production of the different waste elements aims to facilitate the choice of the technology for the recovery of the pre-collected waste and support the development of the recovery and recycling channels. Table IV indicates the chemical composition of the household waste in M'sila.

TABLE III. COMPOSITION OF HOUSEHOLD WASTE IN M'SILA (2011-2016) [26]

Category	Subcategories	%	%
Putrescible waste	Food waste/Green waste	74.5	74.8
	Other putrescible waste	0.2	
Paper	Newspapers/Recyclable papers	1.4	3.3
	Other	1.9	
Cardboard	Flat cardboard packaging	0.1	2.9
	Corrugated packaging	2.2	
	Other	0.6	
Textiles	Textiles	0.5	0.5
Sanitary textiles	Sanitary textiles	1.3	1.6
Plastic	Flexible plastics	4.2	6.3
	Recyclable bottles/flasks	1.1	
	Other	1.0	
Fuel	Unclassified fuels	1.1	1.1
Glass	Recyclable glass	0.2	0.3
	Other	0.1	
Composites	Food cartons	0.2	0.7
	Other	0.5	
Metals	Ferrous metals	0.1	0.6
	Non-ferrous metals	0.2	
	Other metals	0.3	
Fuel	Unclassified fuels	1.8	1.8
Hazardous waste	Household hazardous waste	0.6	0.6
Fines	Fine less than 20mm	5.5	5.5
Total		100	100

TABLE IV. CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF HOUSEHOLD WASTE [34]

Features	Values
Density	0.28
Humidity level	60%
Carbon to nitrogen ratio	38
Calorific value	1000kcal/g

IX. CONCLUSION

Household waste management is a daily and very concrete problem for which local authorities and city residents have

often believed it to be simple and linear: collect and dump. Instead, it has become more complex with the demographic and spatial growth of cities, changes in nutrition habits, and new environmental challenges to the point of surprising urban actors. Seasonal results show that organic matter increases to more than 77% in summer, which is justified by the consumption of fruits and vegetables. In comparison, paper and cardboard drop to 3.5% in periods of high vacations. It can also be noted that the volumes of waste and the composition are not the same in each group of households. They depend on the standard of living, habits, and morals of the population to which we can add that the production of waste tends to increase with the standard of living. For example, residential areas differ from other areas. The current situation of household waste management in the city of M'sila highlights that the latter has difficulty in assuming the management of its waste, and this occurs due to the following reasons:

- The lack of material and human resources.
- Organizational issues.
- The lack of training of the staff in charge of these tasks is also a hindrance to good management of household waste.
- The inhabitants' involvement is deficient due to their lack of awareness and information.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Nemouchi, *Crise multidimensionnelle des villes algériennes : entre discours et réalité, la gestion du patrimoine foncier le cas de la ville de Skikda (nord-est algérien)*. Basse-Normandie, France: Université de Caen, 2012.
- [2] S. Monqid, "La gestion des déchets ménagers au Caire: les habitants en question," *Égypte/Monde Arabe*, no. 8, pp. 85–105, Sep. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.4000/ema.3003>.
- [3] *Rapport sur L'état de l'environnement en Algérie*. CNES, 1999.
- [4] M. Hafidi, *L'impact et la Gestion des Déchets Solides (Région Marrakech-SAFI)*. Morocco: Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung E.V., 2015.
- [5] A. Redjem, B. Nouibat, and B. Naghel, "Gestion des déchets solides urbains – cas de la ville de M'sila," *International Journal for Environment Global Climate Change*, vol. 3, no. 5, 2015.
- [6] *Caractérisation des déchets ménagers et assimilés dans les zones nord, semi-aride et aride d'Algérie*. Algiers, Algeria: AND, 2014.
- [7] H. I. Mohammed, Z. Majid, Y. B. Yamusa, M. F. M. Ariff, K. M. Idris, and N. Darwin, "Sanitary Landfill Siting Using GIS and AHP: A Case Study in Johor Bahru, Malaysia," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4100–4104, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2633>.
- [8] H. Maniam, S. Nagapan, A. H. Abdullah, S. Subramaniam, and S. Sohu, "A Comparative Study of Construction Waste Generation Rate Based on Different Construction Methods on Construction Project in Malaysia," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3488–3491, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2340>.
- [9] *Rapport National sur le développement humain: Algérie 2007*. Algeria: CNES, 2008.
- [10] L. Dahlén, H. Åberg, A. Lagerkvist, and P. E. O. Berg, "Inconsistent pathways of household waste," *Waste Management*, vol. 29, no. 6, pp. 1798–1806, Jun. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2008.12.004>.
- [11] S. Belguidoum, "La ville en question - analyse des dynamiques urbaines en Algérie," presented at the Penser la Ville - Approches Comparatives, Khenchela, Algeria, Oct. 2008.
- [12] *ANGED et Le réseau régional d'échange d'informations et d'expertises dans le secteur des déchets solides dans les pays du Maghreb et du*

- Machreq: Rapport sur la gestion des déchets solides en Algérie*. Algeria: GIZ, 2014.
- [13] G. Gie, L. Hauesler, and A. Kibongui Mougani, *Bilan du recyclage 1999-2008*. France: ADEME, 2010.
- [14] S. Aloueimine, G. Matejka, C. Zurbrugg, and M. Sidi Mohamed, "Caractérisation des ordures ménagères à Nouakchott," *Environnement, Ingénierie & Développement*, no. 44, pp. 4–8, Jan. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.4267/dechets-sciences-techniques.60>.
- [15] A. Redjem, A. Benyahia, M. Dougha, B. Nouibat, M. Hasbaia, and A. Ozer, "Combining the Analytic Hierarchy Process With Gis for Landfill Site Selection: the Case of the Municipality of M'sila, Algeria," *Romanian Journal of Geography*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 171–186, 2021.
- [16] P. Pichat, *La gestion des déchets*. Évreux, France: Dominos Flammarion, 1977.
- [17] M. Davis and S. Masten, *Principles of Environmental Engineering and Science*, 1st ed. New York, NY, USA: McGraw-Hill, 2003.
- [18] O. Longeon, *La gestion des déchets ménagers et autres déchets assimilés*. France, 2001.
- [19] D. Hueber, *Manuel d'information sur la gestion des déchets solides urbains*. Algiers, Algeria: Ministère de l'Aménagement du Territoire et de l'Environnement, 2001.
- [20] D. Hoornweg and P. Bhada-Tata, "What a Waste : A Global Review of Solid Waste Management," World Bank, Washington, DC, USA, Urban development series; knowledge papers 15, Mar. 2012.
- [21] B. Djemaci and M. Ahmed Zaïd - Chertouk, "La gestion intégrée des déchets solides en Algérie: Contraintes et limites de sa mise en oeuvre," CIRIEC, CIRIEC Working Paper 2011/04, Apr. 2011.
- [22] G. Danso, P. Drechsel, S. Fialor, and M. Giordano, "Estimating the demand for municipal waste compost via farmers' willingness-to-pay in Ghana," *Waste Management*, vol. 26, no. 12, pp. 1400–1409, 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2005.09.021>.
- [23] B. Djemaci, "La gestion des déchets municipaux en Algérie : Analyse prospective et éléments d'efficacité," Ph.D. dissertation, Université de Rouen, Rouen, France, 2012.
- [24] F. T. Benaïssa and B. Khalfallah, "Industrial Activity Land Suitability Assessment Using Delphi and AHP to Control Land Consumption: The Case Study of Bordj Bouarreridj, Algeria," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7738–7744, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4362>.
- [25] K. Loumi and A. Redjem, "Integration of GIS and Hierarchical Multi-Criteria Analysis for Mapping Flood Vulnerability: The Case Study of M'sila, Algeria," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7381–7385, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4266>.
- [26] *Etablissement public à caractère industriel et commercial, EPIC: Rapport annuel sur la situation du Centre d'Enfouissement Technique (CET)*. Algeria: CET, 2016.
- [27] *Direction de la planification et de l'aménagement du territoire, D.P.A.T de la wilaya de M'sila: Annuaire des statistiques*. M'sila, Algeria: Department of Planning and Territorial Development, 2016.
- [28] *Décret exécutif n°02-175 du 20 mai 2002 portant création, organisation et fonctionnement de l'Agence nationale des déchets*. Journal officiel, n°37, 2002.
- [29] *Décret n° 88-227 du 5 novembre 1988 portant attribution, organisation et fonctionnement des corps d'inspecteurs chargés de la protection de l'environnement*. Journal officiel, n°46, 1988.
- [30] *Décret exécutif n° 96-60 du 27 janvier 1996 portant création de l'inspection de l'environnement de wilaya*. Journal officiel, n°07, 1996.
- [31] *Rapport sur l'état et l'avenir de l'environnement*. Algiers, Algeria: MATE, 2003.
- [32] D. R. Reinhart and P. Mccauley Bell, *Methodology For Conducting Composition Study For Discarded Solid Waste*, vol. 0. University of Central Florida, Florida Center for Solid and Hazardous Waste Management, 1996.
- [33] A. Wicker, "Chapitre 22: Gestion des Déchets dans," in *Statistiques pour la politique de l'environnement*, 2000.
- [34] *Compendium of Regulatory Texts, on Environmental protection*. M'sila, Algeria: MATE, 2016.

Memristor, Memcapacitor, Meminductor: Models and Experimental Circuit Emulators

Youssef Kebbati

Laboratoire de Physique et Chimie de l'Environnement et de l'Espace LPC2E, Université d'Orléans, Orléans, France
youssef.kebbati@cnsr-orleans.fr

Pierre-Sylvain Allaume

Université d'Orléans
Orléans, France
pierre-sylvain.allaume@univ-orleans.fr

Yacine Bennani

Université Saad Dahlab
Blida, Algeria
bennani.yacine@gmail.com

Received: 4 March 2022 | Revised: 25 March 2022 and 31 March 2022 | Accepted: 4 April 2022

Abstract—Before 1971, the number of passive electrical components was limited to three: resistor, capacitor, and inductor. In 1971, Pr. Chua predicted the existence of a fourth element, called memristor, since it corresponds to a resistor with memory behavior. Several years later, the concept of memory circuit was extended to capacitors and inductors. This paper proposes mathematical models for mem-elements, validated by Matlab and experimental circuit emulators for memcapacitor and meminductor. The experimental results show a good fit between theory, Ltspice simulations, and emulation circuits.

Keywords—memristor; memcapacitor; meminductor; models and simulations; experimental emulator

I. INTRODUCTION

The memristor, or memory resistor, is a two-terminal passive electronic component. Memristor, as a concept, was introduced in 1971 by Leon Chua [1]. Chua defined the behavior of the memristor by a constitutive relationship between flux and charge linkage. However, the concept of memristor did not catch the attention of the scientific community until 2008. The electronic community continued to develop analog and digital circuits without considering the tremendous potential of memristors [2-4]. In fact, Hewlett Packard (HP) Labs manufactured the first memristor component with layers of TiO₂ between two layers of Pt in 2008 [5]. HP also introduced a mathematical model of component operation. The scientific community criticized this model in several points but subsequently the model was widely used [6]. Since then, thanks to the memory effect and nonlinear behavior, the memristor found use in various domains, such as neural networks [7-11], programmable analog circuits [12-15], logic gates [16], adaptive filters [17], chaotic circuits [18, 19], and non-volatile memories [20-22].

II. MATHEMATICAL MODELS

Chua, Pershin, and Di Ventra established the electrical relations for memristor, memcapacitor, meminductor as can be

seen in [23] and in Figure 1 of [24], where the charge (q), the time-integral of the voltage (ϕ), the time-integral of the charge (σ), and the time-integral of the flux (ρ) are visualized.

A. Memristor Models

Two pairs of equations define the memristor: electrical load control and the magnetic flux control [1, 25].

For electrical load control:

$$v(t) = M(q(t))i(t) \quad (1)$$

$$M(q) = d\phi(q)/dq$$

For magnetic flux control:

$$i(t) = W(\phi(t))v(t) \quad (2)$$

$$W(\phi) = dq(\phi)/d\phi$$

According to the mathematical relations, the electrical resistance of the memristor is not constant but depends on the current that was previously circulated through the device. In 1976, L. Chua introduced dynamic equations to define a memristive system with the property of "pinched hysteresis loop" between current and voltage [25, 26]. According to Biolek, this footprint of the memristor is "self-crossing" which corresponds to a cross with coordinates (0:0) [27]. The pinched hysteresis loop/self-crossing was extended to memcapacitor and meminductor.

The HP model's is based on the "modulation" of the size of the doping zone w of the memristor between the value R_{on} and R_{off} as a function of the electrical loads (current) that runs through the component.

$$M(q) = R_{off} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_v R_{on}}{D^2} q(t) \right) \quad (3)$$

$$w(t) = \mu_v \frac{R_{on}}{D} q(t)$$

Corresponding author: Y. Kebbati

where $M(q)$ is the instantaneous value of the memristor, w the size of the doped zone, D the total size of the doped zone, and μ_v the mobility of the electric charge [5, 6].

B. Memcapacitor Models

The memcapacitance is defined with the electrical relation between the time-integral of the charge (σ) and the time-integral of the voltage (ϕ). It can be either voltage-controlled or charge-controlled depending on its constitutive input variable [25, 28]. In the case of voltage control, The memcapacitance C_m is:

$$D_m(\sigma) = \frac{d\phi(\sigma)}{d\sigma} \text{ with } D_m = \frac{1}{C_m} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{d\phi}{dt} = v(t) \text{ then, } v(t) = \frac{d\phi}{d\sigma} \cdot \frac{d\sigma}{dt} = D_m(\sigma) \cdot q(t)$$

C. Meminductor Models

The meminductor represents the link between charge $q(t)$ and the time integral of the flux $\rho(t)$. The mathematical representations of meminductors have two forms: current-controlled meminductor or flux-controlled meminductor [22, 25]. Thus, the meminductance L_m is:

$$L_m(q) = \frac{d\rho(q)}{dq}, = \frac{d\phi}{dq}, \Rightarrow L_m(q).di = d\phi \quad (5)$$

Note that, the pinched hysteresis loop/self-crossing which corresponds to a cross with coordinates (0 : 0) is footprint of the mem-elements [26, 27].

Fig. 1. (a) Pinched hysteresis loop appearing between current and voltage for sinusoidal input with frequency $f=10\text{Hz}$ (green), 50Hz (red), (b) Variations of memristif values versus voltage.

III. MATLAB IMPLEMENTATION AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

A. Memristor Implementation

The model was implemented on Matlab. Figure 1 shows the pinched hysteresis loop between current and voltage and the variation of memristor versus voltage. For this simulation, the electrical load control was chosen. Note that if the frequency increases beyond 100Hz, the characteristic becomes a linear line corresponding to Ohm's law.

B. Memcapacitor Implementation

The model was implemented in Matlab and the footprint (pinched hysteresis loop) of the memcapacitor appears under sinusoidal input between voltage and electrical load. Figure 2 shows the results.

Fig. 2. (a) Voltage and electric load pinch hysteresis loop, (b) variation of current versus voltage.

C. Meminductor Implementation

The model was implemented in Matlab and the footprint (pinched hysteresis loop) of meminductor appears under sinusoidal input between flux and current. Figure 3 shows the numerical results.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL CIRCUIT EMULATORS

To the best of our knowledge, there are no physical implementations of memcapacitor or meminductor circuits. Due to this, there has been an emerging research devoted to the development of emulator circuits of these devices during the recent years. In the literature, different approaches have been proposed for the emulation of memcapacitors and

meminductors. Most of them are based on memristor component or its circuit emulator [24, 29-32]. In our case, we chose to develop memcapacitor and meminductor circuit emulators that do not require the use of a memristor or its emulator. In fact, our emulators are based on the same design and are able to emulate either a memcapacitor or a meminductor with minimal changes.

Fig. 3. (a) Flux and current pinch hysteresis loop, (b) variation of current versus voltage.

The circuit emulators are based on voltage/current converter with operational amplifier. The operating principle of the circuits is based on a second output feedback which is connected to the non-inverting input of the amplifier through the capacitor C2. Thus, in both cases, the C2 capacitor provides the memory effect. Figures 4-5 show the circuit emulators and transient simulation results from Ltspice. The pinched hysteresis appears between the voltage and the current in C2.

The circuit parameters are:

- For the memcapacitor emulator $C1=C2=50\text{nf}$, $Vf=(1\text{V},100\text{Hz})$, $Vin=(1\text{V},200\text{Hz})$.
- For the meminductor emulator $L=10\text{mH}$, $C2=50\text{nf}$, $Vf=(1\text{V},100\text{Hz})$, $Vin=(1\text{V},200\text{Hz})$.

Frequency simulations of the emulator circuits show that they act as filters. The memcapacitor emulator has a high-pass filter behavior and the meminductor emulator acts as a low-pass filter. In the Figure 6, the frequency simulation (Bode diagram) results can be seen.

Fig. 4. Memcapacitor emulator.

Fig. 5. Meminductor emulator.

Fig. 6. Frequency simulations of emulators: (a) memcapacitor, (b) meminductor.

In fact, we can show that the circuit emulators have equivalent circuit filters. These circuits can easily be built from passive elements. Figure 7 presents the equivalent circuit filters and Bode diagram results.

Fig. 7. Equivalent circuit filters and simulation results.

In order to validate the memcapacitor and meminductor emulators, circuit implementations were made. Figures 8-9 show the implementation and the experimental responses of the circuits.

Fig. 8. Experimental implementation and results: (a) (b) Memcapacitor, (c) (d) Meminductor.

The obtained results show a good fit between the simulations and the experimental tests. However, during the tests, the memcapacitor and meminductor effects were obtained at lower frequencies than those of the Ltspace simulations. We assume that the implementation of emulators on PCB will achieve better results in terms of operating frequency. Indeed, some parasitic effects will be reduced.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the concepts of memory-elements memristor, memcapacitor, and meminductor were presented. After the presentation of the mathematical models describing the behavior of these components, the circuit emulators for memcapacitor and meminductor, based-on operational amplifier voltage/current converter, were shown. The results show a good fit between the experimental tests and theory simulations.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Chua, "Memristor-The missing circuit element," *IEEE Transactions on Circuit Theory*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 507–519, Sep. 1971, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCT.1971.1083337>.
- [2] K. C. Selvam and S. Latha, "A Novel Voltage Divider Circuit," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 2, no. 5, pp. 278–280, Oct. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.239>.
- [3] S. N. Asl, M. Tarkhan, and M. S. Nia, "A Gain Programmable Analog Divider Circuit Based on a Data Converter," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2251–2255, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1436>.
- [4] B. L. Dokic, "A Review on Energy Efficient CMOS Digital Logic," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 552–561, Dec. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.389>.
- [5] D. B. Strukov, G. S. Snider, D. R. Stewart, and R. S. Williams, "The missing memristor found," *Nature*, vol. 453, no. 7191, pp. 80–83, May 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature06932>.
- [6] Y. Kebbati, "Programmable Resistors: Model and Applications," *International Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, vol. 5, no. 3, Mar. 2018, Art. no. 257266.
- [7] S. H. Jo, T. Chang, I. Ebong, B. B. Bhadviya, P. Mazumder, and W. Lu, "Nanoscale Memristor Device as Synapse in Neuromorphic Systems,"

- Nano Letters*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 1297–1301, Apr. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl904092h>.
- [8] Y. V. Pershin and M. Di Ventra, "Experimental demonstration of associative memory with memristive neural networks," *Neural Networks*, vol. 23, no. 7, pp. 881–886, Sep. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2010.05.001>.
- [9] M. R. Azghadi, B. Linares-Barranco, D. Abbott, and P. H. W. Leong, "A Hybrid CMOS-Memristor Neuromorphic Synapse," *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Circuits and Systems*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 434–445, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBCAS.2016.2618351>.
- [10] M. Prezioso, F. Merrikkh-Bayat, B. D. Hoskins, G. C. Adam, K. K. Likharev, and D. B. Strukov, "Training and operation of an integrated neuromorphic network based on metal-oxide memristors," *Nature*, vol. 521, no. 7550, pp. 61–64, May 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14441>.
- [11] R. Kozma, R. E. Pino, and G. E. Paziienza, *Advances in Neuromorphic Memristor Science and Applications*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2012.
- [12] S. Shin, K. Kim, and S.-M. Kang, "Memristor Applications for Programmable Analog ICs," *IEEE Transactions on Nanotechnology*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 266–274, Mar. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNANO.2009.2038610>.
- [13] F. Merrikkh-Bayat and S. B. Shouraki, "Memristor-based circuits for performing basic arithmetic operations," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 3, pp. 128–132, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2010.12.022>.
- [14] Y. V. Pershin and M. Di Ventra, "Practical Approach to Programmable Analog Circuits With Memristors," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 57, no. 8, pp. 1857–1864, Dec. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSI.2009.2038539>.
- [15] Y. V. Pershin, E. Sazonov, and M. Ventra, "Analogue-to-digital and digital-to-analogue conversion with memristive devices," *Electronics Letters*, vol. 2, no. 48, pp. 73–74, 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1049/el.2011.3561>.
- [16] I. Vourkas and G. Ch. Sirakoulis, "Emerging Memristor-Based Logic Circuit Design Approaches: A Review," *IEEE Circuits and Systems Magazine*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 15–30, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCAS.2016.2583673>.
- [17] T. Driscoll *et al.*, "Memristive adaptive filters," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 97, no. 9, Aug. 2010, Art. no. 093502, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3485060>.
- [18] A. Buscarino, L. Fortuna, M. Frasca, and L. Valentina Gambuzza, "A chaotic circuit based on Hewlett-Packard memristor," *Chaos: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Nonlinear Science*, vol. 22, no. 2, Jun. 2012, Art. no. 023136, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4729135>.
- [19] B. Muthuswamy and P. P. Kokate, "Memristor-Based Chaotic Circuits," *IETE Technical Review*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 417–429, Nov. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.4103/0256-4602.57827>.
- [20] C. Xu, X. Dong, N. P. Jouppi, and Y. Xie, "Design implications of memristor-based RRAM cross-point structures," in *Design, Automation & Test in Europe*, Grenoble, France, Mar. 2011, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/DATE.2011.5763125>.
- [21] J. Secco, F. Corinto, and A. Sebastian, "Flux-Charge Memristor Model for Phase Change Memory," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 111–114, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSII.2017.2701282>.
- [22] H. A. F. Almurib, T. N. Kumar, and F. Lombardi, "Design and evaluation of a memristor-based look-up table for non-volatile field programmable gate arrays," *IET Circuits, Devices & Systems*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 292–300, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-cds.2015.0217>.
- [23] L. O. Chua and S. M. Kang, "Memristive devices and systems," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 64, no. 2, pp. 209–223, Oct. 1976, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PROC.1976.10092>.
- [24] F. J. Romero, A. Ohata, A. Toral-Lopez, A. Godoy, D. P. Morales, and N. Rodriguez, "Memcapacitor and Meminductor Circuit Emulators: A Review," *Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 11, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 1225, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics10111225>.
- [25] A. G. Radwan and M. E. Fouda, *On the Mathematical Modeling of Memristor, Memcapacitor, and Meminductor*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2015.
- [26] L. Chua, "Resistance switching memories are memristors," *Applied Physics A*, vol. 102, no. 4, pp. 765–783, Mar. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-011-6264-9>.
- [27] D. Biolek, Z. Biolek, and V. Biolkova, "Pinched hysteretic loops of ideal memristors, memcapacitors and meminductors must be 'self-crossing,'" *Electronics Letters*, vol. 47, no. 25, pp. 1385–1387, Dec. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1049/el.2011.2913>.
- [28] M. Di Ventra, Y. V. Pershin, and L. O. Chua, "Circuit Elements With Memory: Memristors, Memcapacitors, and Meminductors," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 97, no. 10, pp. 1717–1724, Jul. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2009.2021077>.
- [29] Y. Babacan, "An Operational Transconductance Amplifier-based Memcapacitor and Meminductor," *Electrica*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 36–38, Feb. 2018.
- [30] M. Konal and F. Kacar, "Electronically tunable meminductor based on OTA," *AEU - International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, vol. 126, Nov. 2020, Art. no. 153391, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aecue.2020.153391>.
- [31] J. Vista and A. Ranjan, "High Frequency Meminductor Emulator Employing VDTA and its Application," *IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems*, vol. 39, no. 10, pp. 2020–2028, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCAD.2019.2950376>.
- [32] M. D. Ventra and Y. V. Pershin, "On the physical properties of memristive, memcapacitive and meminductive systems," *Nanotechnology*, vol. 24, no. 25, Feb. 2013, Art. no. 255201, <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-4484/24/25/255201>.

The Effect of Stator Inter-Turn Short-Circuit Fault on DFIG Performance Using FEM

Hacene Mellah

Department of Electrical Engineering
Akli Mohand Oulhadj University of Bouira
Bouira, Algeria
has.mel@gmail.com

Serdal Arslan

Organized Industrial Zone Vocational Higher School
Harran University
Sanliurfa, Turkey
elkserdal@gmail.com

Sahraoui Hamza

Department of Electrical Engineering
Benbouali Hassiba University of Chlef
Chlef, Algeria
hamzasahraoui@gmail.com

Kamel Eddine Hemsas

Department of Electrical Engineering
Ferhat Abbas Sétif 1 University
Sétif, Algeria
hemsas.kamel@gmail.com

Saoudi Kamel

Department of Electrical Engineering
Akli Mohand Oulhadj University of
Bouira, Bouira, Algeria
k.saoudi@univ-bouira.dz

Received: 24 March 2022 | Revised: 15 April 2022 | Accepted: 18 April 2022

Abstract-Doubly-Fed Induction Generators (DFIG) are operated for wind energy production, and as their capacity is increasing, their safety and reliability become more important. Several faults affect the performance of DFIG. The stator winding Inter-Turn Short-Circuit Fault (ITSCF) is one of the most prevalent electric machine failures. This study examined the stator ITSCF effects on DFIG performance for different cases. The DFIG was designed and engineered using the Finite Element Method (FEM) and the Maxwell software, and was examined in healthy operation and four defective cases with various Numbers of Inter-Turn Short Circuit Faults (NITSCF): 4, 9, 19, and 29. These models allowed the examination of the effects and the comparison of each case separately from the healthy state. The comparison was plotted in Matlab to show the effects of the faults. The novelty of this study was that it investigated the effects of different NITSCF on the performance of DFIG and not only on their effect on the stator current and distribution of magnetic flux density. A better understanding of the short circuit effects on the performance of the DFIG can be exploited for subsequent implementations of early fault detection systems.

Keywords-Doubly-Fed Induction Generators (DFIG); stator winding; Inter-Turn Short Circuit Fault (ITSCF); number of ITSCF; Finite Element Method (FEM); finite element analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the 1970s, modern wind power conversion technology has been developed, especially at the end of the last century. Several Wind Turbine System (WTS) concepts were explored and different wind turbines were built [1]. Since the '90s, when the renewable energy is classified based on increasing installed capacity, wind energy occupies the first place among all types of renewable energy [2]. The ten leading countries in wind power at the end of 2017 had installed more than the three-quarters of all new wind turbines in the world [2].

DFIGs, with external [3] or inner rotors [1], are used in wind power production. As their capacity increases, their safety and reliability become more important. The variation in speed is possible due to power electronics, which are required to provide a connection to the grid. Many studies dealt with DFIG grid connection issues for different purposes [4-7]. The ITSCF of the stator or rotor windings is among the most common faults of DFIGs. The effect of ITSCF on the properties of DFIG has attracted much attention during the past decade. On the other hand, many researchers investigated how to detect and localize such faults [8-12]. However, the difference in the behavior of electrical machines between normal and fault conditions must first be understood before detection and localization can be accomplished. According to [8-17], two methods exist for analyzing the ITSCF by simulation in DFIG: the analytical and the numerical. The analytical approach is based on the multi-circuit theory [18-20], and the numerical approach is usually based on FEM [21, 22]. It's critical to understand the DFIG fault simulation models and features to investigate failure mechanisms. Several studies examined a FEM simulation model of an ITSCF stator or rotor winding in DFIG [11, 23-24].

In [12], the ITSCF in the stator winding with different NITSCF was examined, but this study was limited to the stator current behavior and only took into account two stator slots: 4 and 19. In [10], the stator ITSCF was validated both by FEM simulation and experiment, however, this study was limited to the ITSCF effect on the current and only for some turns. Other studies focused only on the effect of turn-to-turn short-circuit defects on the magnetic field [25]. Authors in [23] only focused on the rotor ITSCF effect on the magnetic flux density distribution and the rotor current.

In [26], two closely related phenomena of the current spectrum of the stator and rotor were studied: ITSCF and high

Corresponding author: Hacene Mellah

www.etasr.com

Mellah et al.: The Effect of Stator Inter-Turn Short-Circuit Fault on DFIG Performance Using FEM

resistance connections, as well as their effect on the energy injected into the network in sub and super synchronous operation, and a discussion on how to tell them apart. In [24], a quantitative study was conducted on mechanical vibration, stator currents, and stator copper loss in healthy and ITSCF cases of one-third of a stator turn of DFIG using FEM. The effect of ITSCF on stator branch currents and its expression by the Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) and the vector trajectory of Park under various ITSCF cases of stator winding was studied in [27].

The current study used FEM to model and simulate the healthy and faulty state in several cases, simulating the same DFIG but with several NITSCF of one stator phase A. A comparison between healthy and faulty stator flux linkages and current of phase A and torque were examined for constant speed.

II. DFIG GEOMETRY AND THE FEM MODEL

DFIG is widely used as a principal component in a wind turbine, as shown in Figure 1, where both the stator and the rotor are connected to the power grid. Wind power (P_w) is transformed into mechanical energy by the wind turbine, and DFIG converts this mechanical energy into electric energy [1].

Fig. 1. Typical configuration of a DFIG WTS.

The first step in FEM is to create and draw the geometric outlines of the DFIG model based on the parameters of a selected device. Some of these parameters are listed in Table I.

TABLE I. DFIG RATED VALUES AND DESIGN PARAMETERS

Electrical and dimensional parameters	Value
Nominal output power	550 W
Nominal voltage	220 V
Given rated speed	1500 rpm
Number of pole pair	2
Number of stator slots	30
Number of rotor slots	24

The next step was to assign specific materials and their properties to each region, including copper to conductors and air to air gaps. The next step incorporated phenomena and parameters including current sources, rotor speed, boundary conditions, eddy currents, and magnetic circuit saturation. A finite element mesh was created for each DFIG part with a very fine mesh for the air gap to obtain the best results. Finally, the simulation parameters such as relative and absolute error, simulation step, and stop time were set. A 3D view of the designed DFIG is presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. 3D view of the designed DFIG.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section introduces the results from the simulation of normal and faulty cases in phase A of the stator winding. Various degrees of ITSCF in the DFIG were simulated to show the effect of the NITSCF on the DFIG performance. The 2D finite element mesh of the DFIG is shown in Figure 3. Afterward, these results were used to solve the electromagnetic field equation of the DFIG. Figure 4 compares the flux linkage in the stator phase A for the normal and different numbers of ITSCF. It was observed that a greater number of short-circuit inter-turn faults increased the error between the normal and fault value, with the flux magnitude for 29 short-circuit faults being the smallest of all cases. Figures 5 and 6 demonstrate the effect of the faults in phases A, B, and C in terms of the flux. As can be observed, this effect is small but not negligible.

Fig. 3. 2D Finite element mesh of the DFIG

Fig. 4. Flux linkage of the stator phase A in normal and under different NITSCF conditions.

Figure 7 shows the comparison of a faulty-healthy Root Mean Square (RMS) ratio of the flux linkage of stator phases for different NITSCF. In phase A, where the different defaults are created, the flux linkage RMS value decreased for each

NITSCF increase. This decrease in flux can be explained by the decrease in the number of turns of phase A.

Fig. 5. Flux linkage in stator phase B for normal and various NITSCF conditions in phase A.

Fig. 6. Flux linkage in a stator phase C for normal and various NITSCF conditions in phase A.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the faulty-healthy RMS ratio of stator phases for different NITSCF.

However, the opposite is noticeable for both healthy phases B and C, where the effective flux binding values increase with each NITSCF increase, especially for phase B starting from the

case of 9 NITSCF. Figure 8 shows the stator current in phase A for normal and various NITSCF in the stator winding. A short-circuit would increase the stator current and result in overheating of the winding. This can be detrimental to the machine and decrease its lifetime, and if the current exceeds the maximum short-circuit can result in its destruction. Figures 9 and 10 show the effect of NITSCF in phase A on current in phases B and C respectively. It can be observed that the effects in phases B and C are important, as the current amplitude in the condition of short-circuit results in system unbalance. Figure 11 shows a comparison of the faulty-healthy RMS ratio of the stator phases current for different NITSCF. The partial short-circuit of turns in phase A increases rapidly the current RMS value for each NITSCF rise. Moreover, at the same time, the current RMS value of the two healthy phases continues to increase with each increase in NITSCF, but in a lower order compared to the RMS value of the defective phase. Figure 12 shows the induced voltage of phase A in healthy and faulty operation. The induced voltage in phase A decreases with each NITSCF increment because the total induced voltage is a sum of the induced voltage for each turn. Figure 13 shows the induced voltage of phase B in healthy and faulty operation.

Fig. 8. Stator currents of phase A for healthy and various NITSCF conditions.

Fig. 9. Stator currents of phase B in healthy and under various NITSCF in phase A of the stator.

Fig. 10. Stator currents of phase C in healthy and various stator winding fault conditions of phase A.

Fig. 11. Comparison of the faulty-healthy RMS ratio of the stator phase currents for various NITSCF.

Fig. 12. Stator induced voltage of phase A in healthy and under various stator winding fault conditions.

Figure 14 displays the induced voltage of phase C in healthy and faulty operation, while Figure 15 shows the rotor currents. As can be noted, the rotor currents are not affected by the stator ITSCF. Figure 16 displays the torque curves of the DFIG at nominal load in healthy and under various NITSCF cases. This Figure summarizes the effect of inter-turn faults on DFIG torque. As can be observed, the inter-turn faults create an oscillation that increases with increasing NITSCF.

Fig. 13. Stator induced voltage of phase B in healthy and various NITSCF conditions in phase A of the stator.

Fig. 14. Stator currents of phase C in healthy and various NITSCF in phase A of the stator.

Fig. 15. Rotor currents.

Figure 17 shows the distribution of the magnetic flux density for normal and different stator winding fault conditions in phase A. As can be noted, the magnetic field is concentrated in both the stator and rotor regions and will increase both rotor and stator leakage reactance. The magnetic saturation will also increase in these regions. In the faulty state, asymmetric behavior will occur in the torque induced by the generator due to the change in currents passing through the stator winding. In this case, NITSCF increase causes an increase in torque ripple, as can be observed in Figure 17.

Fig. 16. Torque in healthy and various stator winding fault conditions.

Fig. 17. The magnetic field for healthy and faulty DFIG on different cases of inter-turn short-circuited numbers: (a) 29 inter-turn faults, (b) 19 inter-turn faults, (c) 9 inter-turn faults, (d) 4 inter-turn faults, (e) healthy.

IV. CONCLUSION

FEM is a numerical method that allows the analysis of complex and non-linear systems and is frequently used for modeling and simulating electrical machines. This study used a FEM model to simulate and obtain a comparative analysis between the normal and several cases of ITSCF for one stator phase of DFIG. A comparison of stator flux, currents, induced voltage, and torque between normal and fault conditions was presented at a constant speed. ITSCF in the stator winding causes a substantial increase in branch current and a small increase in currents of B and C stator phases. ITSCF in phase A of the stator winding causes a decrease in flux in this phase and a smaller decrease in the other two phases. Moreover, ITSCF creates oscillations in the torque that increase with increasing ITSCF. An increasing number of inter-turn short-circuits causes DFIG characteristics to deviate further from normal. This study provides insight into the effects of ITSCF and can be exploited to allow the development of reliable fault detection systems and improve the quality of the electrical power injected into the power grid by WTS.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors express their gratitude and acknowledge the financial support received from the University of Setif-1 in Algeria for the PRFU Research Project under Grant A01 L07 UN1901 2019 0002.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Mellah and K. E. Hemsas, "Design and Simulation Analysis of Outer Stator Inner Rotor Dfig by 2D and 3D Finite Element Analysis," *International Journal of Electrical Engineering and Technology*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 457–470, Sep. 2012.
- [2] S. Dawn, P. K. Tiwari, A. K. Goswami, A. K. Singh, and R. Panda, "Wind power: Existing status, achievements and government's initiative towards renewable power dominating India," *Energy Strategy Reviews*, vol. 23, pp. 178–199, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2019.01.002>.
- [3] H. Mellah and K. E. Hemsas, "Design and Analysis of an External-Rotor Internal-Stator Doubly Fed Induction Generator for Small Wind Turbine Application by Fem," *International Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy*, vol. 2, pp. 1–11, 2013, <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijrse.20130201.11>.
- [4] A. Guediri and A. Guediri, "Study and Order of a Medium Power Wind Turbine Conversion Chain Connected to Medium Voltage Grid," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7279–7282, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4169>.
- [5] H. Benbouhenni, A. Driss, and S. Lemdani, "Indirect active and reactive powers control of doubly fed induction generator fed by three-level adaptive-network-based fuzzy inference system – pulse width modulation converter with a robust method based on super twisting algorithms," *Electrical Engineering & Electromechanics*, no. 4, pp. 31–38, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.20998/2074-272X.2021.4.04>.
- [6] S. V. Bozhko, R. Blasco-Gimenez, R. Li, J. C. Clare, and G. M. Asher, "Control of Offshore DFIG-Based Wind Farm Grid With Line-Commutated HVDC Connection," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 71–78, Mar. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEC.2006.889544>.
- [7] X. Tian, H. Tang, Y. Li, Y. Chi, and Y. Su, "Dynamic stability of weak grid connection of large-scale DFIG based on wind turbines," *The Journal of Engineering*, vol. 2017, no. 13, pp. 1092–1097, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1049/joe.2017.0498>.
- [8] Y. Fu, Z. Ren, S. Wei, Y. Xu, and F. Li, "Using Flux Linkage Difference Vector in Early Inter-Turn Short Circuit Detection for the Windings of Offshore Wind DFIGs," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol.

- 36, no. 4, pp. 3007–3015, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEC.2021.3073007>.
- [9] O. Imoru, F. V. Nelwamondo, A. Jimoh, and T. R. Ayodele, "A neural network approach to detect winding faults in electrical machine," *International Journal of Emerging Electric Power Systems*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 31–41, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijeeps-2020-0161>.
- [10] Y. Chen *et al.*, "Numerical Modeling, Electrical Characteristics Analysis and Experimental Validation of Severe Inter-Turn Short Circuit Fault Conditions on Stator Winding in DFIG of Wind Turbines," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 13149–13158, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3050876>.
- [11] A. U. Rehman, Y. Chen, Y. Zhao, Y. Cheng, Y. Zhao, and T. Tanaka, "Detection of Rotor Inter-turn Short Circuit Fault in Doubly-fed Induction Generator using FEM Simulation," in *2018 IEEE 2nd International Conference on Dielectrics (ICD)*, Budapest, Hungary, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICD.2018.8514641>.
- [12] S. He, X. Shen, and Z. Jiang, "Detection and Location of Stator Winding Interturn Fault at Different Slots of DFIG," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 89342–89353, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2926538>.
- [13] J. Cheng, H. Ma, S. Song, and Z. Xie, "Stator Inter-turn Fault Analysis in Doubly-Fed Induction Generators using rotor current based on Finite Element Analysis," in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Progress in Informatics and Computing (PIC)*, Suzhou, China, Sep. 2018, pp. 414–419, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PIC.2018.8706293>.
- [14] H. Sabir, M. Ouassaid, and N. Ngote, "Diagnosis of Rotor Winding Inter-turn Short Circuit Fault in Wind Turbine Based on DFIG using Hybrid TSA/DWT Approach," in *2018 6th International Renewable and Sustainable Energy Conference (IRSEC)*, Rabat, Morocco, Sep. 2018, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IRSEC.2018.8703006>.
- [15] K. Ma, J. Zhu, M. Soltani, A. Hajizadeh, and Z. Chen, "Inter-Turn Short-Circuit Fault Ride-Through for DFIG Wind Turbines," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 12757–12762, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2020.12.1916>.
- [16] F. Bouaziz, O. Awedni, and L. Krichen, "Modelling and fault diagnosis of rotor inter turn short circuit fault in a doubly fed induction generator-based wind turbine," in *2020 20th International Conference on Sciences and Techniques of Automatic Control and Computer Engineering (STA)*, Monastir, Tunisia, Sep. 2020, pp. 189–194, <https://doi.org/10.1109/STA50679.2020.9329344>.
- [17] S. M. M. Moosavi, J. Faiz, M. B. Abadi, and S. M. A. Cruz, "Comparison of rotor electrical fault indices owing to inter-turn short circuit and unbalanced resistance in doubly-fed induction generator," *IET Electric Power Applications*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 235–242, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-epa.2018.5528>.
- [18] D. B. Minh, L. D. Hai, T. L. Anh, and V. D. Quoc, "Electromagnetic Torque Analysis of SRM 12/8 by Rotor/Stator Pole Angle," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7187–7190, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4168>.
- [19] Z. Xing, Y. Gao, M. Chen, and J. Xu, "Fault Diagnosis of Inter-turn Short Circuit of Permanent Magnet Synchronous Wind Turbine under the Random Wind," in *2021 IEEE 2nd China International Youth Conference on Electrical Engineering (CIYCEE)*, Sep. 2021, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CIYCEE53554.2021.9676777>.
- [20] Z. T. Mei, G. J. Li, Z. Q. Zhu, R. Clark, A. Thomas, and Z. Azar, "Scaling Effect on Inter-Turn Short-Circuit of PM Machines for Wind Power Application," in *2021 IEEE International Electric Machines Drives Conference (IEMDC)*, Hartford, CT, USA, Feb. 2021, pp. 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEMDC47953.2021.9449606>.
- [21] M. Hussain, A. Ulasyar, H. S. Zad, A. Khattak, S. Nisar, and K. Imran, "Design and Analysis of a Dual Rotor Multiphase Brushless DC Motor for its Application in Electric Vehicles," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7846–7852, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4345>.
- [22] Z. Tan, X. Song, W. Cao, Z. Liu, and Y. Tong, "DFIG Machine Design for Maximizing Power Output Based on Surrogate Optimization Algorithm," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 1154–1162, Sep. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEC.2015.2411153>.
- [23] L. Jun-qing and W. Xi-mei, "FEM analysis on interturn fault of rotor winding in DFIG," in *2013 International Conference on Electrical Machines and Systems (ICEMS)*, Busan, South Korea, Jul. 2013, pp. 797–802, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEMS.2013.6713154>.
- [24] S. He, X. Shen, Y. Wang, and W. Zheng, "Characteristic Factor Analysis on Stator Winding Inter-turn Fault in DFIG Based on FEM Simulation," in *2017 International Conference on Computer Technology, Electronics and Communication (ICCTEC)*, Dalian, China, Sep. 2017, pp. 209–213, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCTEC.2017.00052>.
- [25] L. Jun-qing, M. Li, and W. De-yan, "Influence of stator turn-to-turn short-circuit on magnetic field of DFIG," in *2011 International Conference on Electrical Machines and Systems*, Beijing, China, Dec. 2011, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEMS.2011.6073523>.
- [26] M. Afshari, S. M. M. Moosavi, M. B. Abadi, and S. M. A. Cruz, "Study on Inter-Turn Short Circuit Fault and High Resistance Connection in the Stator of Doubly-Fed Induction Generators," in *7th Iran Wind Energy Conference (IWEC2021)*, Shahrood, Iran, Feb. 2021, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IWEC52400.2021.9467018>.
- [27] Y. Chen *et al.*, "FEM simulation and analysis on stator winding inter-turn fault in DFIG," in *2015 IEEE 11th International Conference on the Properties and Applications of Dielectric Materials (ICPADM)*, Sydney, NSW, Australia, Jul. 2015, pp. 244–247, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPADM.2015.7295254>.

The Inclusion of the Environmental Dimension of Sustainability in Studying Informal Settlements Using the INDI System

The Case Study of Bousaada City, Algeria

Imane Lamdjad

Laboratory of Urban and Environmental Techniques
University of M'sila
M'sila ,Algeria
imane.lamdjad@univ-msila.dz

Boudjemaa Khalfallah

Laboratory of Urban and Environmental Techniques
University of M'sila
M'sila ,Algeria
boudjemaa.khalfallah@univ-msila.dz

Received: 28 January 2022 | Revised: 7 March 2022 | Accepted: 15 March 2022

Abstract-The phenomenon of informal settlements is considered one of the most common global issues that have negative effects on several life aspects. All Algerian cities face this problem, including the city of Bousaada and the neighborhood of Sidi Slimane, which is considered one of the largest informal settlements in the city. Although the neighborhood has benefited from the Vulnerable Housing Absorption Program funded by the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development, the latter did not achieve the set goals. Therefore, it has become necessary to think about the use of modern and effective criteria for assessing the environmental dimension of sustainability, such as the INDI system of impact indicators built into EcoQuartierGrid2011 in order to contribute to the development of these neighborhoods, to ensure a better quality of life for the residents, and achieve sustainable development in light of the environmental dimension. On this basis, the present study aims to use the INDI system to integrate the environmental dimension of sustainability in informal settlements and to investigate the environmental shortcomings that the neighborhood Sidi Slimane suffers from in order to suggest possible solutions to develop it and improve the quality of life for the residents. In pursuance of this aim, the approach of the current research is descriptive-analytical in order to design an approach that deals with the criteria of the INDI System in environmental studies. The research concludes that both INDI and EcoquartierGrid 2011 will help improve the quality of life of the population for millions of individuals and residents in Algeria and in developing countries that suffer from the problem of informal housing. A guideline based on INDI and EcoquartierGrid 2011 indicators is recommended and incorporated into environmental studies as a reference. The novelty of the current research lies in finding practical and technical solutions to the problem of squatter housing through the use of the INDI indicator system and its integration with EcoQuartierGrid2011 based on 40 topics and 318 indicators covering the economic, social, and environmental dimensions.

Keywords-environmental dimension; quality of life; indicator impact system INDI; informal settlements; Bousaada City

Corresponding author: Imane Lamjad

www.etasr.com

I. INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of informal settlement growth is considered one of the biggest issues that threaten cities in general [1] and Bousaada in particular. The latter is attributed to the high population density [2], rapid urban growth, and the inability of regulatory authorities to address this phenomenon. The number of individuals living in informal settlements reached 725 million in 2000, and 860 million in 2013 [2]. The inclusion of the environmental dimension of sustainability has become necessary in informal settlements as it directly affects the quality of human life and society [3]. This effect is manifested in inadequate housing, the absence of generally accepted building standards, the high occupancy rate of housing, the deterioration of basic infrastructure [4-5], the spread of pollution and epidemics, unsanitary living conditions [6], in addition to the deterioration of living conditions such as the lack of necessary public facilities and equipment, the deterioration of the road network and the sewage network [7], the lack of green and public spaces, and poverty and social exclusion [8].

Informal settlements are characterized by the deterioration of their physical conditions. They are usually built with reinforced concrete, which is economical [9] and the impact of associated risks [10] is neglected, along with the risks regarding the quality of housing [11] and the construction of public projects [12]. These poor conditions clearly and directly impede the achievement of sustainable development in its environmental dimension. The environmental dimension of sustainability aims to improve the management of natural resources, protect biodiversity, and provide a healthy and livable human environment [13], while consuming renewable resources [14, 15].

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND TOOLS

A. Research Tools

The current research paper follows the descriptive-analytical approach and the INDI evaluation system in order to

assess the Sidi Slimane informal settlement. The study’s aim is to help achieve the environmental dimension of sustainability and improve the quality of life of the residents. In addition to that, field investigation has been conducted.

B. Procedures of the Case Study

This study revolves around Bousaada, an Algerian city. It is located at a distance of 250km from the capital, with an estimated population density of 614 inhabitants/km² in 2014. Furthermore, it is characterized by its strategic location and its natural, cultural and historical characteristics [18-19]. The district of Sidi Slimane was chosen as a case study, as it is one of the largest informal settlements in the city. The latter has grown in the '80's due to the absence of the concerned authorities and the increase in population growth and rural migration towards the center of Bousaada. Sidi Slimane is estimated to be 115 hectares, with a population of 45,000 people. [20]. The Sidi Slimane informal settlement is evaluated by merging the evaluation program INDI with EcoQuartierGrid2011 that consists of 40 topics and 318 indicators that include economic, social and environmental dimensions [16-17], see Table I.

1) INDI and EcoQuartierGrid2011

INDI is a program that aims to evaluate and develop all existing residential neighborhoods, and is used in projects that include rehabilitation, urban renewal, and urban expansion and works to achieve sustainable development and improve participation between urban actors and residents. EcoQuartierGrid2011 has been incorporated into this system as an important part of the development of the INDI index database.

The INDI rating system helps stakeholders, architects and urban planners improve the quality of life of residents and users. It is also the only tool among the global assessment systems that aims to assess the neighborhood before and after its improvement [16], moreover, EcoQuartierGrid2011 focuses on assessing the environmental dimension more and helps old and new neighborhoods integrate the environmental dimension of sustainability [17].

2) Stepwise Methods Executed to Achieve the Objectives

Three gradual methods have been followed in order to achieve the goal of the study, which is to integrate the environmental dimension of sustainability in the Sidi Slimane neighborhood in order to improve the quality of life of the residents:

- The stage of data collection: it is represented in collecting the initial information (documents, urban plans, site visits).
- Evaluation stage: By entering data into the integrated INDI program database and evaluating it, it contributes to identifying deficiencies and how to enhance them.
- Data review stage: It is the output of the evaluation process and is represented in two parts: a section for the outputs of the INDI program and a section for the outputs of EcoQuartier 2011 Grid, both in the form of graphs and tables.

TABLE I. TOPICS OF INDI AND ECOQUARTIER 2011 INDICATORS

Dimensions of Sustainability	Topics of the INDI Indicator Impact System	Topics of EcoQuartier Grid2011
Environmental	Energy management in project design	Good location and familiarity with the project
	Energy management in buildings	Comfortable and healthy living environment
	Optical comfort	Preserving biodiversity and enhancing nature in the city
	Mobility management	Use of non-renewable resources and waste
	Field consumption	Water Saving Department
	Biodiversity	Rationalization of energy needs
	Sustainable water management	Reduced greenhouse gas emissions
	Managing sustainable and natural resources	Valuing the agricultural environment and forests
	Quality of housing, population and private spaces	
	Quality of public spaces and green spaces	Regulating transportation and reducing car use
Economic	Security and health risks and pollution reduction	Alternative and sustainable transport
	Fighting poverty and social exclusion (work and housing)	Dense neighborhood and/or context adapted
	New ways of thinking and acting	Dynamics of local development Financial and legal feasibility
Social	Access to high-quality public facilities and utilities	Maintaining continuity of approach Monitoring and consultation
	Sharing the collective effort and integrating the neighborhood into the city	Solidarity and the responsibility to live
	Solidarity and the politics of social cohesion	Coexistence promotion
	Culture, education and training	Learning management and evaluation
	Evaluation and value as a method of education	
	Participation Involvement of residents and users	Promoting heritage and identity

3) Rating Values of the INDI System

The evaluation results are classified according to the evaluation field (0,1,2,3,4,5) according to five classifications, see Table II.

TABLE II. INDI RATING EVALUATION

Values	Evaluation
0	Absence of evaluation
1	Very insufficient
2	Somewhat insufficient
3	Average
4	Somewhat satisfying
5	Very satisfying

4) The Evaluation Process

The evaluation process is carried out according to the explanatory scheme of Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The evaluation process.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sidi Slimane informal settlement was evaluated with the use of the INDI and with EcoQuartierGrid2011, see Tables III-IV and Figures 2-3. The aim of this study is to explore the shortcomings and insufficiencies in order to address the problem of substandard housing and to improve the quality of life for the population in the studied area.

TABLE III. ASSESSMENT RESULTS OF SIDI SLIMANE ACCORDING TO THE INDI SYSTEM

Assessment results of Sidi Slimane using the INDI Indicator Impact System	Initial evaluation
Energy management in project design	0.3
Energy management in buildings	0.3
Optical comfort	1
Mobility management	0.3
Field consumption	3
Biodiversity	0.5
Sustainable water management	0.5
Managing sustainable and natural resources	0.5
Fighting poverty and social exclusion (work and housing)	0.8
Access to high-quality services and facilities	1.8
Quality of residential buildings, residences, and private spaces	0.6
Quality of public spaces and green spaces	0.4
Security and health risks and noise reduction	0.3
Contribute to the collective effort and the integration of neighborhoods in the city	0.9
Solidarity and politics of social cohesion	0.2
Culture, education and training	0.2
A new way of thinking and acting	0.3
Evaluation and capitalization as a pathway to learning and improvement	0.7
Partnership	0.5
Involvement of residents and users	0.2

Fig. 2. Circuit diagram of the results of the assessment of the Sidi Slimane neighborhood according to the INDI assessment program.

Fig. 3. Circuit diagram of the results of the assessment of the Sidi Slimane neighborhood according to EcoQuartierGrid2011.

It is shown in Figure 2 that the field consumption index obtained the highest value (3), which is an average rating, explaining the increase of the informal settlement at the expense of natural areas and trees, the absence of oversight by the concerned authorities, and the weak application of laws aimed at reducing squatter housing. Most indicators of the environmental dimension of sustainability obtained a rating value around 0, which shows that the study area was randomly built without taking into account the appropriate orientation of the neighborhood to benefit as much as possible from the sunrays, and not taking into account climatic factors (such as wind direction, air currents, and shade) in addition to the lack of a network electricity and gas in the studied area, and failure to preserve natural areas, local trees, and plants when building. Furthermore, Figure 2 shows that the light comfort index obtained a value of 1, a very insufficient rating, and this explains the absence of public lighting in most of the streets of the study field. Finally, the indicator of obtaining high-quality public facilities and utilities obtained a value of 1.8, a very insufficient rating, and this explains the lack of the necessary equipment and facilities and their distance from housing, and that these facilities do not consider persons with disabilities.

It is displayed in Figure 3 that the dense and/or context-adapted living indicator has the highest value (2.3), corresponding to a somewhat insufficient rating and this explains the consumption of the urban area in the field of study. The Figure also shows that the functional blending index obtained a very insufficient rating (1.7), due to the absence of diversification in urban functions at the level of neighborhoods, residential islands, and housing units. As a conclusion, most of the indicators of the environmental dimension of sustainability got a value of 0 rating. This is explained by the absence of energy-saving buildings, the absence of a culture of preserving the environment and biodiversity, and the absence of a culture of reducing the volume and quantity of solid and household waste.

TABLE IV. ASSESSMENT RESULTS OF SIDI SLIMANE ACCORDING TO ECOQUARTIER2011

Assessment results of Sidi Slimane using Ecoquartier 2011	Initial evaluation
Good location and familiarity with the project	0.3
Monitoring and consultation	0.6
Financial and legal feasibility	0.5
Learn how to manage and evaluate	0.6
Maintain continuity of approach	0.1
Promote coexistence	0.6
Solidarity and responsibility to live	0.5
Comfortable and healthy living environment	0.7
Valuing heritage and identity	0.5
Dense neighborhood / or context adapted	2.3
Functional blending	1.7
Regulating transportation and reducing car use	0.3
Alternative and sustainable transport	0.2
Dynamism and local development	0.6
Valorization of the agricultural and forestry field	0.7
Reduce greenhouse gas emissions	0
Rationalization of energy needs	0.2
Water Saving Department	0.2
Use of non-renewable resources and waste	0.1
Preserving biodiversity and enhancing nature in the city	0.5

The research gap appears by referring to previous studies, The author in [21] believes that the absence of the principle of participation and the absence of negotiation to limit the informal settlement of the studied area (the Hanna Nassif Community Managed Settlement Upgrading pilot project) with the authorities and government agencies negatively affect the quality of life of the residents. A two-pronged approach was used: forward-looking proactive strategies to contain new urban populations and slum upgrading to address the needs of the people currently living in slums. Authors in [22] believe that improving the quality of life of their case study (slum-improvement projects in India) dwellers in India is linked to the development of a comprehensive legal framework that enables governmental and non-governmental agencies to deal quickly

with the structuring and implementation of slum improvement projects, promoting participation, transparency, and cooperation between governmental and non-governmental entities to support financial governance and facilitating land tenure. There is no method or evaluation program that was followed in this study, but direct suggestions were made. Authors in [23] argue that improving the quality of life of individuals of their case study, which includes providing basic needs such as adequate housing, sanitation, and waste management, especially with the Covid-19 pandemic, requires improving medical care for slum dwellers and working to improve the economic situation. The proposed actions are the establishment of emergency planning committees in the informal settlements, the application of the strategy of solid waste management and collection, and the provision of food aid. No method or evaluation program were followed in this study, but direct suggestions were made.

The research contribution of the current study lies in finding practical and technical solutions to the problem of informal settlement through the use of the INDI Indicator Impact System and its integration with EcoQuartierGrid 2011 with the aim of achieving the environmental dimension of sustainability and improving the quality of life in the Sidi Slimane informal settlement.

IV. CONCLUSION

This research aims to use the Indicator Impact System INDI to integrate the environmental dimension of sustainability and the environmental shortcomings that the neighborhood Sidi Slimane suffers from in order to suggest possible solutions to improve the quality of life of the residents. The results showed strong absence of the indicators of the environmental dimension of sustainability, stronger than the economic and social ones.

This study has many advantages over the previous ones since it differs in the methods and the results. While there is no method or evaluation program that was followed in previous studies, and directly suggestions and recommendations were made, the current study focuses on the process of evaluation which is based on 40 topics and 318 indicators covering the

economic, social, and environmental dimensions. This is what enables us to provide comprehensive, accurate, and practical solutions according to the study's results. In addition, the utilized techniques were used for the first time to address the problem of informal settlement. The previous studies took into account only 9 indicators at most to investigate the quality of life of the residents in informal settlements, which is insufficient and not comprehensive to address the problem, which faces several environmental, economic, and social challenges, which were studied without the utilization of programs or evaluation systems. The current study provides a starting point to understand and address the problem of informal settlement using the INDI technology integrated into EcoquartierGrid 2011 in developing countries, specifically in Algeria. These techniques are very useful in extracting deficiencies at the level of social and economic dimensions, especially environmental dimensions, and thus addressing the problem of informal settlement.

The implication of these findings is that these new technologies will be available to decision-makers and urban planners and will increase profitability, enhance the economy of the cities and improve environmental sustainability in informal settlements. The INDI and EcoquartierGrid 2011 may become a form of sustainable urban development that requires coordination, cooperation and realization of the principle of participation between the different urban actors, i.e. local and governmental authorities, the private sector, civil society, and the population.

Both the evaluation systems, INDI and EcoquartierGrid 2011 will help improve the quality of life of the population for millions of residents in Algeria and in developing countries that suffer from the problem of informal housing, and help in rationalizing energy consumption, protecting the environment, reducing pollution, and promoting development. As a conclusion, a guideline to improve the quality of life in an informal settlement in the city of Bousaada, based on INDI and EcoquartierGrid 2011 criteria and indicators should be developed, and it should be integrated into environmental studies as a reference, taking into account the recommendations shown in Table V.

TABLE V. A GUIDELINE FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LIFE IN SIDI SLIMANE BASED ON INDI AND ECOQUARTIER2011 CRITERIA AND INDICATORS

Indicators	Recommendations
Energy management in project design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -It is necessary to provide all housing in the slum of Sidi Slimane with electricity, gas, and sewage facilities. -There is a need to take into account the appropriate orientation of the building to benefit as much as possible from sunlight and climatic factors (such as wind direction, air currents, shade) when designing the building. -The establishment of housing units within the field of study that achieves self-sufficiency in energy needs so as to produce and use clean energy efficiently and effectively is proposed.
Energy management in the building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Energy efficiency can be achieved by reducing the use of electricity and gas, heating, ventilation, cooling, artificial lighting, and making use of natural lighting as much as possible. -Local and sustainable building materials that enhance heat gain must be utilized.
Optical comfort	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -All primary and secondary roads in the field of study must be equipped with public lighting.
Mobility management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The development of an integrated and sustainable transportation system that takes into account quality, pricing, security and safety, and provides common public transportation such as buses is suggested. -The use of bicycles and allocating areas for pedestrians must be encouraged. -The necessity of providing car parking, taking into account the distance of less than 300m between the dwelling and the stopping station is underlined. -The provision of public transportation at all times and at the end of the week must be taken into account. -Lanes for bicycles must be allocated. -The necessity of enabling persons with disabilities to have easy access to public transportation is underlined.

Field consumption	-There is a need to protect and preserve agricultural areas, forests, and trees. -Tightening of supervision by the concerned authorities and the application of laws that limit random housing that consumes the urban space excessively is suggested.
Biodiversity	-The preservation of natural areas when initiating the processes of preparing the neighborhood must be taken into account. -The continuity of natural areas should be preserved. -There is a need to take proactive measures aimed at preserving trees when constructing buildings. -Different types of native plants must be cultivated.
Sustainable water management	-There is a necessity of providing all housing units in the study area with potable water, rationalizing the consumption of domestic drinking water. -The quality of potable water must be ensured (taking into account sanitary, physical and chemical conditions and compliance with water quality standards). -Water leakage can be reduced by repairing and renovating old channels. -Work has to be done in order to establish separate rainwater and greywater treatment centers.
Sustainable management of natural resources and materials	-There is a necessity of using local building materials and energy-saving conservation techniques.
Fighting poverty and social exclusion (work and housing)	-There is a necessity of providing equitable employment and housing positions for all segments of society. -There is a necessity of reducing squatter housing because it negatively affects the economy.
Access to high-quality services and facilities	-There is a necessity of increasing the number of health, security, and educational equipment in the studied neighborhood, as it is insufficient. -There is a necessity of taking into account the proximity of the housing in the case of the area to public facilities (shops, school, mail, health centers, etc.) within a range of 300m. -Public facilities and facilities must provide access to persons with disabilities.
Quality of residential buildings, residences, and private spaces	-The quality of housing must be improved. -Work has to be done in order to achieve quality in public roads, common spaces between residences, private spaces, and stairs, and secure access. -The privacy of the dwellings and the interfaces between private and public spaces must be taken into account. -There is a necessity of furnishing the streets and general lighting at the level of the studied neighborhood in order to serve the residents.
Quality of public and green spaces	-There is a necessity of providing public spaces and green spaces within the field of study. Abandoned and unbuilt spaces can be exploited. -The population has to be informed and sensitized to the preservation of green spaces and natural areas. -There is a need to take into account the hierarchy of spaces and ease of reading in the design of green and public spaces.
Security and health risks and noise reduction	-There is a necessity of preparing a preventive plan for the natural disasters that the studied area suffers from (the danger of falling stones and floods). -Strict instructions must be established to reduce the risk of accidents in construction workshops. -The construction waste must be disposed of immediately after the completion of the construction process.
Contribute to the collective effort and the integration of neighborhoods in the city	-There is a necessity of diversification in urban functions at the neighborhood level, residential islands, and housing units to achieve functional blending.
Solidarity and politics of social cohesion	-The studied area contains only individual housing, so it is necessary to diversify the housing style through the establishment of social housing to enhance interaction between residents and achieve social diversity.
Culture, education, and training	-There is a necessity of valuing heritage and local identity is underlined. -Awareness-raising and media campaigns at the level of the studied neighborhood on protecting the environment and preserving green spaces and natural areas must be carried out.
A new way of thinking and acting: Approaches, methods, and tools	-Programs of training and educating workers and engineers of governmental and non-governmental agencies, private sector, associations, civil society, and the population can be carried out. -There is a necessity of calculating the project budget and the total cost of the initialization operations.
Evaluation and capitalization as a path to action and improvement	-There is a need for continuous adaptation and improvement of the project.
Partners	-The preparation of a charter for the project of environmentally sustainable residential neighborhoods that include the various actors and partners in the project, is proposed.
Involvement of residents and users	-Consultation and involving residents and users in evaluating the project's stages and planning for the establishment of public facilities, public spaces and green spaces is suggested.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. J. Maghsoodi Tilaki, R. A. Mustafā, M. Hedayati Marzbali, A. Aldrin, and J. Ariffin, "Challenges of the informal settlements in developing countries' cities: A case study of Iran," *World Applied Sciences Journal*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 160–169, Jan. 2011.
- [2] UN-Habitat, *The Challenge of Slums - Global Report on Human Settlements 2003 | UN-Habitat*. London, UK: Earthscan Publications Ltd, 2003.
- [3] J. M. Levy, *Contemporary Urban Planning*. New York, NY, USA: Taylor & Francis, 2017.
- [4] M. H. Salas-Olmedo and S. Nogués, "The Land Use and Transport Relationship in Peripheral Areas: Policy Integration based on Case Studies," in *12th World Conference on Transport Research Society*, Lisbon, Portugal, Jul. 2010.
- [5] J. L. Baker, "Climate Change, Disaster Risk, and the Urban Poor : Cities Building Resilience for a Changing World," World Bank, Washington, DC, Apr. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1596/978-0-8213-8845-7>.
- [6] B. R. K. Sinha, "Introduction: An Overview of the Concept of Quality of Life," in *Multidimensional Approach to Quality of Life Issues: A Spatial Analysis*, B. R. K. Sinha, Ed. Singapore: Springer, 2019, pp. 3–23, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-6958-2_1.
- [7] R. J. Lilford *et al.*, "Improving the health and welfare of people who live in slums," *The Lancet*, vol. 389, no. 10068, pp. 559–570, Feb. 2017, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(16\)31848-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(16)31848-7).
- [8] A. Power, "Social Exclusion and Urban Sprawl: Is the Rescue of Cities Possible?," *Regional Studies*, vol. 35, no. 8, pp. 731–742, Nov. 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343400120084713>.
- [9] S. A. A. Kareem and I. F. Ahmed, "Impact Resistance of Bendable Concrete Reinforced with Grids and Containing PVA Solution,"

- Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7709–7713, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4440>.
- [10] S. H. N. Alani and A. M. R. Mahjoob, "Corruption Risk Analysis at the Project Planning Stage in the Iraqi Construction Sector using the Bowtie Methodology," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7223–7227, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4060>.
- [11] A. Gilbert, "The Return of the Slum: Does Language Matter?," *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 697–713, 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2427.2007.00754.x>.
- [12] A. Alameri, A. S. A. M. Alhammadi, A. H. Memon, I. A. Rahman, and N. A. N. Nasaruddin, "Assessing the Risk Level of the Challenges Faced In Construction Projects," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7152–7157, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4020>.
- [13] M. Roseland, "Dimensions of the eco-city," *Cities*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 197–202, Aug. 1997, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0264-2751\(97\)00003-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0264-2751(97)00003-6).
- [14] S. E. Bibri, "The eco-city and its core environmental dimension of sustainability: green energy technologies and their integration with data-driven smart solutions," *Energy Informatics*, vol. 3, no. 1, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 4, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42162-020-00107-7>.
- [15] M. L. Banda and S. Fulton, "Litigating Climate Change in National Courts: Recent Trends and Developments in Global Climate Law," *Environmental Law Reporter*, vol. 47, no. 2, Jan. 2017.
- [16] C. Charlot -Valdieu and P. Outrequin, *Designing and evaluating an eco-district project with the INDI reference system*. Paris, France: Éditions du Moniteur, 2012.
- [17] *Call for E'coquartier Projects 2011, Explanatory Notice of the E'coquartier grid*. Paris, France: Ministry of Ecology, Sustainable Development, Transport and Housing, 2011.
- [18] *Review of the master plan for the preparation and reconstruction of the municipality of Bousaada*. Batna, Algeria: Office of Studies and Achievements in Reconstruction in Batna, 2014.
- [19] K. Loumi and A. Redjem, "Integration of GIS and Hierarchical Multi-Criteria Analysis for Mapping Flood Vulnerability: The Case Study of M'sila, Algeria," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7381–7385, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4266>.
- [20] *The statistics of the municipality of Bousaada Msila, Algeria*. Msila, Algeria, 2018.
- [21] S. A. Sheuya, "Improving the Health and Lives of People Living in Slums," *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, vol. 1136, no. 1, pp. 298–306, 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1425.003>.
- [22] B. Patel, R. Joshi, S. Ballaney, and M. Nohn, "Slum Planning Schemes: A Statutory Framework for Establishing Secure Tenure and Improving Living Conditions in Indian Slums," *Environment and Urbanization ASIA*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 45–75, Mar. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1177/097542531000200105>.
- [23] J. Corburn *et al.*, "Slum Health: Arresting COVID-19 and Improving Well-Being in Urban Informal Settlements," *Journal of Urban Health*, vol. 97, no. 3, pp. 348–357, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11524-020-00438-6>.

The Behavior of RC Beams Retrofitted with Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP)

Muhammad Fahim

Civil Engineering Department
University of Engineering and Technology, Peshawar
Peshawar, Pakistan
drmfahim@uetpeshawar.edu.pk

Fakhree Alam

Civil Engineering Department
University of Engineering and Technology, Peshawar
Peshawar, Pakistan
falam.ms20nice@student.nust.edu.pk

Hazrat Khan

Civil Engineering Department
University of Engineering and Technology, Peshawar
Peshawar, Pakistan
hazkhan.pg19mce@student.nust.edu.pk

Inziam ul Haq

Civil Engineering Department
University of Engineering and Technology, Peshawar
Peshawar, Pakistan
inziamul.haq2@students.uettaxila.edu.pk

Shahid Ullah

Civil Engineering Department
University of Engineering and Technology, Peshawar
Peshawar, Pakistan
shahid.ullah@uetpeshawar.edu.pk

Saeed Zaman

Civil Engineering Department
University of Engineering and Technology, Peshawar
Peshawar, Pakistan
saeed.zaman79@gmail.com

Received: 17 March 2022 | Revised: 5 April 2022 | Accepted: 7 April 2022

Abstract- The need for the introduction of economical and quicker retrofitting techniques is increasing due to the ever-aging infrastructure and damages produced by major catastrophic events around the world. The application of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs) for strengthening and retrofitting of reinforced concrete structures is gaining popularity due to its higher strength, lightweight, durability, corrosion resistance, and aesthetic value. This study presents the results of two strengthened and two retrofitted beams in comparison to control specimens. Two specimens were strengthened and two were retrofitted by attaching CFRP (Sika Carbo-Dur S812 or Sika-Wrap 230C) to the tension side of the beams using high strength epoxy. The results show that one CFRP strip/wrap simply attached at the tension side can help the damaged beam regain/pass the original strength. All specimens fail due to debonding of CFRP from the concrete surface emphasizing the need for efficient anchorage systems. Among the four patterns adopted, CFRP strips along with u-shaped anchorages at the ends provided the highest strength enhancement of 17.36%.

Keywords-CFRP; strengthening; retrofitting; reinforced concrete beams; debonding

I. INTRODUCTION

Collapse and cracking of structural elements of buildings, bridges, or other structures take place due to poor construction practices, use of low quality materials, inappropriate design of elements, and application of unexpected external loads that have not been considered during the design. Retrofitting is

defined as the strengthening intervention that is able to restore an acceptable level of safety against such actions [1]. The terms retrofitting and strengthening are generally used interchangeably. However, more precisely, the term rehabilitation is used when a structure is strengthened before an earthquake or other damaging phenomena whereas strengthening of damaged structures is called retrofitting [2]. Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) is made of two components, carbon fiber and resin and is used extensively for the retrofitting of reinforced concrete structures. It has the desirable properties of higher strength, light weight, durability, electrical and corrosive resistance, and good aesthetic appearance. The base material (poly acrylonitrile-PAN) of CFRP has higher molecular orientation [3]. In 1977, because of its higher stiffness and high strength-to-weight ratio, CFRPs were used in the casing of aircrafts. In 1980, CFRPs were used as a reinforcement material in reinforced concrete beams.

Ever since their first use in the construction industry, CFRP retrofitted members have been extensively investigated, both experimentally and numerically. Authors in [4] compiled a database of 127 beam specimens from the literature which were externally bonded with CFRP and GFRP sheets to increase the flexure capacity and were tested under 4-point loading. About one third of the tested specimens with external reinforcement demonstrated strength increase of 50% or more in combination with considerable deflection capacity. Authors in [5] used three different reinforcement ratios of CFRP and concluded that with

Corresponding author: Muhammad Fahim

www.etasr.com

Fahim et al.: The Behavior of RC Beams Retrofitted with Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP)

the increase in reinforcing ratios in beams, their load carrying capacity increased. Authors in [6] carried out an experimental study of RC beams to investigate the behavior of structurally damaged full-scale RC beams retrofitted with CFRP laminates. The increase in maximum load value of the specimens was between 7% and 33% for retrofitting in flexure. The main failure mode found was plate debonding which reduced the efficiency of retrofitting. Authors in [7] performed experimental and numerical studies of CFRP retrofitted beams and concluded that the strength of RC beams with single layers of CFRP was enhanced from 18 to 20% and for double layers from 40 to 45%. The deflection of RC retrofitted beams was also decreased by about 80% that of control beams. Authors in [8] studied the flexure behavior of corroded reinforced concrete beams strengthened with CFRP and found 30 to 50% increase in capacity along with improvement in stiffness. CFRP has also been used in other RC components and under different loading conditions. For example, T-beams [9], columns [10], shear walls [11], and joints [12]. Similarly, various RC components retrofitted with CFRP were investigated under various loading conditions, e.g. under torsion [13], impact loading [14], and under fire exposure [15].

In many practical situations, adopting a comprehensive retrofitting scheme is not feasible due to financial, time, or execution constraints. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of simple retrofitting schemes on the flexural behavior of reinforced beams. Two specimens were strengthened and two were retrofitted by attaching CFRP (Sika Carbo-Dur S812 or Sika-Wrap 230C) to the tension side of the beams using high strength epoxy. In addition, one strengthened and one retrofitted beam had u-shaped anchorages of the same Sika-Wrap 230C. The results are discussed and recommendations are presented in the subsequent sections.

II. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

A. Materials

Concrete with a specified compressive strength of 4,000 psi was used for casting the beam specimens. The average compressive strength of the companion cylinders tested in accordance with ASTM C-39 as shown in Figure 1 was found to be 3,940 psi.

Fig. 1. Concrete cylinder test setup.

ASTM A615 Grade 60 steel (1/2in diameter bars) was used for tension reinforcement and Grade 40 steel (3/8in diameter bars) was used for transverse reinforcement as well as compression hangers. The average yield strength was found to be 59.94ksi and 52.28ksi for Grade 60 and Grade 40 steel respectively. Sika Carbodur S812 CFRP strips and SikaWrap 230C wraps/sheets were used for strengthening and retrofitting the beam specimens. These conform to ASTM D7205/D7205M-06 [16]. The properties of CFRP strips and wraps as provided by the manufacturer are given in Table I.

TABLE I. CFRP PROPERTIES

CFRP Type	Thickness (in.)	Width (in)	Tensile strength (ksi)	Modulus of elasticity (ksi)
Sika Carbodur S812	0.047	3.15	400	23.2×10^3
SikaWrap 230C	0.0052	6	460	31.9×10^3

High strength epoxy Sikadur 30 [17] was used for attaching CFRP strips with the concrete surface. Similarly, for bonding the CFRP wraps to the concrete surface, Sikadur 330 [18] adhesive was used. Both types of epoxy are two-component thixotropic [17] epoxy including resin and filler designed for use at normal temperature. They conform to ASTM C-881 [19] and AASHTO M-235 [20] specifications.

B. Test Specimens

Five beams of 7ft length were casted and tested under 4-point (pure bending) loading. The dimensions and reinforcement details of the specimens are shown in Table I. Two beams were strengthened with CFRP before the application of any load whereas two beams were first tested to cracking moment and then retrofitted before testing again to collapse load. Two patterns were used for CFRP application, the first pattern consisted of a 3.15in wide and 0.0394in thick strip with 5in wide U-shaped anchorages at the ends as shown in Figure 3. The second pattern consisted of a 6in wide and 0.0052in thick wrap without any anchorage as shown in Figure 4. In both cases the CFRP was applied on the tension side in the middle half of the span. Each pattern was applied to one strengthened and one retrofitted beam.

Fig. 2. Cross section details of the specimens.

Fig. 3. First pattern of CFRP for beam specimens.

Fig. 4. Second pattern of CFRP for beam specimens.

C. Test Setup

The beams were tested under 4-point loading (pure bending) as shown in Figure 5. The deflection was recorded using a UCAM-70A data logger.

Fig. 5. Schematic of the test setup.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Failure Pattern

The failure patterns of the four strengthened/retrofitted specimens are shown in Figures 6-9. The predominant failure was due to the debonding of CFRP from the concrete surface. The higher flexural stresses in the middle half of the beams caused tensile cracks which were widened with the increase in the applied load. At the location of these cracks, concentrated stresses weaken the bond between CFRP and concrete and eventually lead to the complete debonding of CFRP from the surface. Failure immediately follows after the debonding. The specimens without any anchorages (specimens B4 and B6) experienced even more pronounced debonding as shown in Figures 7 and 9. The simple u-shaped anchorages (without any mechanical anchors) provided in the specimens B3 and B5 has a significant impact in reducing the crack widths and delaying debonding as shown in Figures 6 and 8.

Fig. 6. Final failure pattern of specimen B3.

B. Load vs Displacement Relationships

Figures 10 and 11 show the load vs mid-span deflection of control and strengthened beams with CFRP strips and wraps. The strengthened beams are in fact the control beams after they were tested to their ultimate capacity and were strengthened with CFRP before being tested again. It can be seen that the beams strengthened with CFRP strips regain/crossed their original strength but the beams strengthened with CFRP wraps fell slightly short of their original strength. In both cases, the strengthened specimens had larger ultimate displacement. However, reduced stiffness was observed in strengthened beams, especially the specimen with CFRP wraps. However, the final displacement recorded was much higher than that of both control specimens. It must be noted that the CFRP strip used in the specimen B3 was anchored by applying U-shaped wraps at both ends as shown in Figure 6. The effect of this anchorage can be noted by comparing Figures 10 and 11 as both ultimate load and displacement are higher for specimen B3 than for specimen B4.

Fig. 7. Final failure pattern of specimen B4.

Fig. 8. Final failure pattern of specimen B5.

Figures 12 and 13 show the load vs mid-span deflection of control and retrofitted beams with CFRP strips and wraps. The CFRP strip in beam B5 was anchored at the end using a U-shaped shear wrap as shown in Figure 8. This beam achieved the highest ultimate strength and the recorded displacement at failure was also the highest among all specimens. Retrofitted

beam B6 reached the strength level of control specimen B2 but it was less than control specimen's B1.

Fig. 9. Final failure pattern of specimen B6.

Fig. 10. Load vs displacement relationships of control specimens and a specimen strengthened with CFRP strips.

Fig. 11. Load vs displacement relationships of control specimens and a specimen strengthened with CFRP strips.

Fig. 12. Load vs displacement relationships of control specimens and a specimen retrofitted with CFRP strips.

Fig. 13. Load vs displacement relationships of control specimens and a specimen retrofitted with CFRP wraps.

Table II shows the maximum load, the corresponding displacement, and the final load and displacement values for all specimens. The highest load and displacement capacity were observed for specimen B5 which was retrofitted with CFRP strips along with u-shaped anchorages. One of the most important characteristics observed for the strengthened and retrofitted beams was their ability to withstand inelastic deformations. This manifests an increased ductility of the beams which is highly desirable in earthquake resistant structures.

TABLE II. SUMMARY OF THE TEST RESULTS OF BEAM SPECIMENS

Specimen	Maximum load and corresponding displacement		Final load displacement		Debonding load (kN)
	P_{max} (kN)	Δ_{max} (mm)	P_f (kN)	Δ_f (mm)	
B1	121.11	13.76	118.65	14.21	--
B2	105.07	11.19	100.26	14.40	--
B3	117.61	12.03	101.09	32.71	113.74
B4	99.33	14.65	89.60	20.68	96.08
B5	132.71	29.10	125.21	41.09	131.36
B6	105.54	30.86	92.18	33.69	100.97

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the effect of CFRP retrofitted on the flexural behavior of reinforced concrete beams. Six specimens were tested, two control beams, two beams strengthened with

CFRP after testing to ultimate capacity, and two beams were retrofitted with CFRP before they were exposed to any loading. The following conclusions can be drawn from the results obtained in the study:

- A simple strip/wrap of CFRP applied at the critical locations can help damaged structural components regain their original (pre-loading) strength. All four specimens in this study regained/crossed the strength of control specimens with the application of a single CFRP strip/wrap in the middle half span on the tension side.
- The study demonstrates the common failure pattern in CFRP retrofitted beams is the debonding of CFRP from the concrete surface. Effective anchorage systems can greatly enhance the capacity of retrofitted RC structures by delaying the debonding process and stressing the CFRP to higher levels.
- The highest strength achieved in this study for a retrofitted beam is 17.36% higher the average strength of control specimens. This is an encouraging sign for the use of CFRP in retrofitting and strengthening of existing old or damaged RC structures. The application is quick, simple and doesn't involve high skilled labor.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Costa, A. Arède, and H. Varum, Eds., *Strengthening and Retrofitting of Existing Structures*, 1st ed. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2017.
- [2] M. Ashraf, "Development of Low-cost and Efficient Retrofitting Technique for Unreinforced Masonry Buildings," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Engineering and Technology, Peshawar, Pakistan, 2010.
- [3] "Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) Uses and Properties," *Essaycompany*. <https://www.essaycompany.com/essays/chemistry/carbon-fiber-reinforced-polymer-cfrp-5854> (accessed Apr. 27, 2022).
- [4] J. F. Bonacci and M. Maalej, "Behavioral Trends of RC Beams Strengthened with Externally Bonded FRP," *Journal of Composites for Construction*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 102–113, May 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0268\(2001\)5:2\(102\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0268(2001)5:2(102)).
- [5] M. R. Esfahani, M. R. Kianoush, and A. R. Tajari, "Flexural behaviour of reinforced concrete beams strengthened by CFRP sheets," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 29, no. 10, pp. 2428–2444, Oct. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2006.12.008>.
- [6] Y. T. Obaidat, S. Heyden, and O. Dahlblom, "The effect of CFRP and CFRP/concrete interface models when modelling retrofitted RC beams with FEM," *Composite Structures*, vol. 92, no. 6, pp. 1391–1398, May 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2009.11.008>.
- [7] P. Alagusundaramoorthy, I. E. Harik, and C. C. Choo, "Flexural Behavior of R/C Beams Strengthened with Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer Sheets or Fabric," *Journal of Composites for Construction*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 292–301, Nov. 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0268\(2003\)7:4\(292\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0268(2003)7:4(292)).
- [8] S. Linwang, C. Jian, C. Qingjun, L. Guobao, and Z. Juan, "Investigation on the Flexural Behavior of Corroded Concrete Beams Repaired by CFRP Sheet Under Different Corrosion Levels," *The Open Civil Engineering Journal*, vol. 10, no. 1, Sep. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.2174/1874149501610010598>.
- [9] A. Bennitz, J. W. Schmidt, J. Nilimaa, B. Taljsten, P. Goltermann, and D. L. Ravn, "Reinforced Concrete T-Beams Externally Prestressed with Unbonded Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Tendons," *Structural Journal*, vol. 109, no. 4, pp. 521–530, Jul. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.14359/51683871>.
- [10] J. A. O. Barros, R. K. Varma, J. M. Sena-Cruz, and A. F. M. Azevedo, "Near surface mounted CFRP strips for the flexural strengthening of RC columns: Experimental and numerical research," *Engineering Structures*,

- vol. 30, no. 12, pp. 3412–3425, Dec. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2008.05.019>.
- [11] N. Askarizadeh and M. R. Mohammadzadeh, "Numerical Analysis of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) Shear Walls and Steel Strips under Cyclic Loads Using Finite Element Method," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2147–2155, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1279>.
- [12] W. T. Lee, Y. J. Chiou, and M. H. Shih, "Reinforced concrete beam-column joint strengthened with carbon fiber reinforced polymer," *Composite Structures*, vol. 92, no. 1, pp. 48–60, Jan. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2009.06.011>.
- [13] G. Al-Bayati, R. Al-Mahaidi, and R. Kalfat, "Experimental investigation into the use of NSM FRP to increase the torsional resistance of RC beams using epoxy resins and cement-based adhesives," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 124, pp. 1153–1164, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2016.08.095>.
- [14] J. Abd and I. K. Ahmed, "The Effect of Low Velocity Impact Loading on Self-Compacting Concrete Reinforced with Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7689–7694, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4419>.
- [15] H. A. Al-Baghdadi and A. Sabah, "Behavior of RC Beams Strengthened with NSM-CFRP Strips Subjected to Fire Exposure: A Numerical Study," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7782–7787, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4493>.
- [16] D. P. Abrams and N. Shah, "Cyclic Load Testing of Unreinforced Masonry Walls," Illinois University At Urbana Advanced Construction Technology Center, Urbana, IL, USA, 92-26-10, Dec. 1992.
- [17] "Sikadur®-30," *Sika*. <https://gbr.sika.com/en/construction/structural-strengthening/adhesives-and-bonding/structural-adhesives/sikadur-30.html> (accessed Apr. 27, 2022).
- [18] "Sikadur®-330," *Sika*. <https://gbr.sika.com/en/construction/structural-strengthening/adhesives-and-bonding/structural-adhesives/sikadur-330.html> (accessed Apr. 27, 2022).
- [19] G. Magenes and G. M. Calvi, "Cyclic behavior of brick masonry walls," in *Earthquake Engineering, Tenth World Conference*, Rotterdam, Netherlands, 1992.
- [20] *AASHTO M 235M/M 235-13 (2018): Standard Specification for Epoxy Resin Adhesives (ASTM Designation: C 881-10)*. American Association of State and Highway Transportation Officials, 2013.

Performance Investigation of an Inflatable Solar Dryer with Steel-Can Solar Air Heater for Drying Coffee and Corn

Charity L. Oria

School of Engineering, Ateneo de Davao University
Davao City, Philippines and
College of Engineering, Sultan Kudarat State University
Sultan Kudarat, Philippines
charityoria@sksu.edu.ph

Eleonor V. Palconit

School of Engineering
Ateneo de Davao University
Davao City, Philippines
evpalconit@addu.edu.ph

Received: 5 April 2022 | Revised: 14 April 2022 | Accepted: 18 April 2022

Abstract-Coffee and corn are the two most important crops in the Philippines. One of the most critical stages, where crop management can be improved, is drying. In coffee, a moisture level of 12% is optimum for minimizing quality degradation throughout lengthy storage periods, whereas, corn requires a moisture content of 13%. With the demand for simple and cost-effective drying technologies, an Inflatable Solar Dryer (ISD) was created and adapted using a Hohenheim-type solar tunnel and Salvatierra-Rojas' study. A mesh wire served as a drying space and was placed inside the ISD to avoid moisture condensation. A clear polyethylene (PE) film is attached to a reinforced black Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) film by a zipper to produce a drying tunnel. The tunnel does not require a foundation because the pressure generated by a solar-powered fan sufficiently stabilizes it. The ISD also incorporated steel cans as solar air heaters to boost the temperature of entering air into the chamber and gradually provide heated air temperature to the bottom parts of the crops. Crops were scattered on the mesh wire and blended with a rake. Drying in the open sun was also done in parallel for comparison purposes. After protracted drying, both crops reached the required moisture content. The trial found that the weight of both crops was affected by the drying duration. The difference in weight for coffee is 1.1kg, while for corn is 0.5kg exhibiting a significant advantage in ISD.

Keywords-postharvest management; corn; coffee; inflatable solar dryer; solar air heater; solar-powered fan

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is vital to the economies of developing countries as it is the primary source of food, currency, and employment for rural populations. On the other hand, agriculture and land-use reforms are critical for achieving food security, poverty alleviation, and overall sustainable development. According [1], farming employs 28.4% of the workforce in the Philippines and contributes an average of 10.18% of the country's GDP. Given this percentage, the Philippines continues to import agricultural products. Corn and coffee are two essential crops imported in the Philippines. According to the Department of Agriculture (DA), the

Philippines imports 75,000 MT to 100,000 MT of dry coffee beans from Vietnam and Indonesia each year at P7 billion to P10 billion [2]. At the same time, corn imports averaged 604,000 tons from 2017 to 2019. Based on the data from the United State Department of Agriculture (USDA), corn imports are predicted to remain steady from 2021 to 2022 as a result of improved local production and ample feed grain inventories [3], while the country's coffee production would increase to 214,626 MT by 2022, based on the Philippine Coffee Roadmap [2]. By undertaking pest and disease management activities and providing seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides, many government agencies along with the private sector are working to boost the country's corn and coffee production. Postharvest management, such as the provision of dryers, was, on the other hand, negligible, even though it is equally vital in the entire production of crops. According to [4], post-production losses in the country occur mainly in handling and drying, resulting in delayed, incomplete, or inefficient drying.

Open Sun Drying (OSD) was introduced for agricultural product preservation and storage. This method of drying is still widely used even today. However, OSD faces many inherent limitations like overexposure, which causes food damage, high losses in yield production due to insects, rodents, and birds, longer drying time, and unpredictable climate conditions [5]. In the Philippines, OSD is the main practice of the farmers. In fact, with the absence of drying facilities, many crops, including coffee beans and corn, are dried on highways or road pathways where vehicles may run over and ruin the products. Other corn and coffee producers, on the other hand, choose to trade their crops immediately after harvesting to prevent farm losses and additional expenses. It can be noted that freshly picked coffee beans and corn when sold will have a low farm gate price as compared to dried crops. Locally, newly gathered, or wet corn is priced at Php.12.00 at the farm gate, whereas dry corn with an optimal moisture content of 13% is priced at Php.17.00. The farm gate price for newly picked coffee beans is Php.30.00, while the farm gate price for dry coffee with an optimal moisture content of 12% is Php.110.00. With such

disadvantages and differences between the price of wet and dry crops, the need for solar dryers and their implementation has drawn the attention of researchers.

Many types and models of solar dryers have been studied and developed worldwide. However, in the Philippines, there are limited published articles about the implementation of solar dryers. The latest solar dryer study done in the country was the ISD by Salvatierra-Rojas in 2017, using rice as the commodity [6]. The dryer gives a promising result in drying rice in humid climates like in Philippines. Furthermore, the study demonstrates that the ISD is an ideal dryer for small-scale farmers due to its low-cost materials and simple operation. Therefore, the goal of this study is to employ such an ISD to dry corn and coffee beans. The results were compared to the performance of OSD in terms of drying time and final weight when reaching the desired moisture content of 13% for corn [7] and 12% for coffee beans [8]. Recycled steel-can Solar Air Heater (SAH) was integrated into the ISD to increase air inlet temperature and determine its contribution to the ISD by closely monitoring the inlet, mid, and inside humidity and temperature. Mesh wire was also placed inside the ISD to prevent condensation.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Design of the Inflatable Solar Dryer

The ISD was based on [6], which was constructed from the Hohenheim-type solar tunnel [9] that has been developed and commercialized to dry different agricultural products in different climatic conditions. Unlike the Hohenheim-type dryer and the Salvatierra-Rojas study, which laid the grains barely in black PVC films inside the chamber, this study incorporated an elevated mesh wire inside the ISD chamber to allow double pass of hot air into the lower and upper part of the dried products and to allow better circulation of the moist inside the chamber. The dryer is still collapsible, just like in [6].

The ISD drying chamber comprises 150 μ m UV-transparent polyethylene (PE) film and is joined to a 0.52mm reinforced black PVC film by a heavy-duty zipper. A heavy-duty zipper is positioned and sewn along the margins of both plastic layers. The entire unit is placed directly on the ground. The tunnel does not require structural support and is effectively stabilized by air pressure from inflation. One 220V solar-powered fan blows air into the tunnel, which is then expelled through the opposite side's vents. The inclusion of renewable energy was based on the findings of [6], which recommended that more research should focus on incorporating photovoltaic power supply for the ventilators to enable off-grid operation [6]. The chamber's tested drying space is 2.5m long and 1.5m wide. To prevent moisture condensation inside the ISD chamber, this study used a 15 \times 15cm mesh wire supported by four pieces of 2 \times 2ft. wood. The crops were then spread at the height of 20mm on top of the mesh wire and were mixed with a rake to minimize overheating of the top layer exposed to the sun.

B. Design of the Solar Air Heater (SAH)

The SAH was used in the study to raise the temperature of the air entering the ISD. The SAH was made out of 390ml steel cans. For the first layer, 49 pieces of steel cans were arranged

vertically in 7 groups and for the second layer, 30 pieces of the same cans were laid in 5 groups. There was a gap between the cans for the second layer to allow air circulation inside the SAH. The SAH's frame was made of a 5mm plyboard and was measured to be 0.905m in length, 0.6m in width, and 0.2m in height. The SAH has round perforations on one end to allow the incoming air to pass through. On the opposite end of the SAH, a single rectangular hole connects to the fan and ISD through a 10mm foam insulator. The SAH was painted black as a coating material to increase its thermal operation [10]. The SAH's top cover and glazing system were made of 5mm transparent glass to restrict the steel cans' radiant and convective heat absorbance. Four heavy-duty caster wheels were installed at the bottom of the SAH to make it portable and easy to transport.

A two-layer design composed of insulator foam and black PVC film was stitched together, and magic tape was attached to link the sides and form a tunnel to connect the SAH, fan, and ISD, as shown in Figure 1. Table I shows the design parameters, such as the overall size of the SAH, ventilator size, and the overall size of the ISD.

Fig. 1. Design of ISD and integrated SAH with a solar powered fan.

TABLE I. DESIGN PARAMETERS OF THE EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Design parameters	Details
Solar Air Heater (SAH)	
Type	Steel can solar energy heat absorber
Overall size of the SAH	0.905m length × 0.6m width × 0.2m height
Overall size of the steel can heat absorber	0.755m length × 0.6m width × 0.15m height
Ventilator	
Type of ventilator	Solar-powered fan
Diameter of ventilator	16 inches
Ventilator	220 V AC/DC
Airflow rate	1.7 m/s
Inflatable solar dryer (ISD)	
Overall size of the ISD	2.5m length x 1.5m width
Height of the inflated tunnel	0.75m
Mesh wire drying space	
Overall size of the drying space	2.1m length x 1.1m width
Height from the ground	0.15m
Capacity (fresh)	100 kg

C. Drying Experiment

The dryer was used in the Philippines' Sultan Kudarat province (6.5069° N, 124.4198° E). The dryer was set up in the middle of a paddy field that was completely unoccupied. The crops used in the trials were Robusta coffee and yellow corn. Each experiment trial was conducted a day after the crops were harvested. The initial moisture content of both crops and their initial weight were measured at the start of the drying experiment. Similarly, before the crops were set aside throughout the night or during heavy rains, the weight and the moisture content were tested again to see how much had changed over the drying period within the day. The trial began at 7 a.m. and ended at 5 p.m. every day, i.e. for a daily duration

of 10 hours. The coffee had a moisture content of 40.5% on a wet basis, whereas the corn had 38.9%. During each experiment trial, the solar-powered fan was permitted to run continuously within the drying duration. At 1-hour intervals, the crops were dried and scattered with a rake. Each dryer had three batches of crops to dry. The OSD was used as a control method, with each batch containing 16.3kg of coffee beans and 16.9kg of corn. The sample crops were spread out on a black PVC film next to the ISD with a bulk height of 20mm. The crops in the OSD were mixed with a rake at the same time as the ISD. The crops were kept aside throughout the night or when there was severe rain but were dried the next day until the ideal moisture content for each crop was reached.

D. Instrumentation of Drying Experiments

To evaluate the study's goal, four essential tools were used. A 25kg capacity digital weighing scale was used to determine the initial and final weight of the crops, whereas a digital moisture content meter (AR991 KERRO Smart Sensor Digital Grain Moisture Meter) was used to determine the moisture content. A self-logging humidity and temperature sensor (BSIDE Mini USB Humidity Temperature Data Recording Logger) was mounted on the inlet, in the middle (in the fan, where the wind is blown), and on the ISD chamber to determine the temperature and relative humidity as shown in Figure 2. When linked to a computer, data were logged every 10s and were automatically generated and exported.

E. Statistical Analysis

T-test experimental design was conducted using the Excel statistical software, with p values less than 0.05 considered significant.

Fig. 2. Position of humidity and temperature sensor top view

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Temperature and Relative Humidity (SAH, Fan, ISD)

The humidity and temperature loggers were positioned in three different locations in the dryer. The first location was in the SAH, where there was incoming air, the second was next to the solar-powered fan to see if the steel can SAH could boost

the incoming air temperature, and the third was on the top of the crops inside the ISD. The dryer's ambient temperature varied from 31 to 46°C, 31 to 51°C, and 31 to 70°C respectively from the SAH air inlet, alongside the fan, and within the ISD. Figure 3 shows the air temperature and humidity profile within the dryer over 10h, using the chosen intervention phase data. In general, there was a progressive temperature rise between the

SAH input and the fan, but the most increase was between the fan and the ISD. The highest temperature of the day was between 11 a.m. and 2 p.m. However, the temperature in the three places gradually declined after sundown, eventually approaching ambient temperature. The temperature rises in the dryer continued to be minimal due to evaporative cooling provided by the crops and more significant convective losses due to a higher difference in temperature out from ambient air.

Fig. 3. The dryer's temperature and humidity at (a) SAH air inlet, (b) the fan in the middle, (c) ISD at the top of the crops.

B. Moisture Content and Drying Behavior

The moisture content of the crops during ISD and OSD drying is shown in Table II. Under ISD, coffee with an initial moisture content of 40.5% reached the ideal moisture content of 12% in 3 days (27h), while in OSD, coffee with the same initial moisture content dried to 12% moisture content within 5 days (47h). For the corn, the crops placed in the ISD with an initial moisture content of 38.9% dried to the target of 13% within a day, while when drying under OSD, the crops with the

same initial moisture content dried in 2 days (14h). The target moisture content of 12% for coffee and 13% for corn may be easily obtained by continuously drying. However, when the crops were retrieved from the dryer at night, remoistening occurred, resulting in an increase in moisture content overnight. On the other hand, remoistening becomes minimal to none once the target moisture content is obtained.

TABLE II. MOISTURE CONTENT IN ISD AND OSD

Products	The moisture content of the products		
	Fresh product	ISD	OSD
Coffee	40.5%	12.00%	12.1%
Corn	38.9%	12.25%	12.76%

C. Weight

The results of coffee weight shown in Table III and Figure 4 revealed a significant difference with a p-value of 0.018 under ISD and OSD, with a difference of 1.1kg in the final weight of coffee after reaching the desired 12% moisture content. However, corn weight results in Table IV show no significant difference. The difference in the final weight of corn after reaching the 13% moisture content is 0.5kg with a p-value of 0.09. This means that the product's drying time impacts the final weight when it reaches the target moisture content.

TABLE III. T-TEST OF WEIGHT OF COFFEE

Dryer	Mean	SD	Diff.	t	P-value	Interpretation
ISD	7.7	0.17	0.35	3.89	0.018	Sig.
OSD	7.35	0.1				

Fig. 4. Coffee weight with respect to time.

TABLE IV. T-TEST OF WEIGHT OF THE CORN

Dryer	Mean	SD	Diff.	t	P-value	Interpretation
ISD	11.40	0.1	0.23	2.21	0.09	No sig.
OSD	11.17	0.14				

D. Drying Duration and Condensation Phenomena

The drying time is determined by the time it took for the ideal moisture content to be achieved. Table V and Figures 4-5 show the drying duration of coffee and corn under ISD and OSD. The difference in drying time between coffee and corn, 20h for coffee and 6h for corn, is significant for farmers looking to save revenue on labor and other expenses. Condensation in the ISD's floor was eliminated due to the mesh that acts as a drying surface inside the ISD. Condensation

happens when the temperature of the crops or the dryer's surfaces falls below the drying air's moisture content. Without the mesh wire, the temperature of the crops will be higher at the top than at the bottom because the top layer of the crops is subjected to solar radiation and the temperature is enhanced by heat absorption. Incoming air from the SAH, on the other hand, reaches the bottom portion of the crops through the mesh wire and progressively dries the crops at the bottom. Another strategy to avoid condensation from forming is to increase the mixing rate after sunrise to transport the warm top layer of the crops to the bottom layer.

Fig. 5. Corn weight with respect to time.

TABLE V. DRYING DURATION OF COFFEE BEANS AND CORN

Products	Moisture content	Drying duration (hours)	
	Dried product	ISD	OSD
Coffee	12.0%	27	47
Corn	13.0%	8	14

IV. CONCLUSION

Due to the erratic rainfall, drying crops, particularly corn and coffee, is difficult in the Philippines, even during the dry season. To prevent such a situation, some farmers trade their products as soon as they are harvested (wet crops). However, because the market for freshly picked corn and coffee beans has poor farm gate prices, most farmers are drying their crops on roads and walkways to increase their income, even though this results in unclean and hazardous quality. The proposed ISD can help with these issues since it preserves the crops from damage, high yield losses due to pests, prolonged drying times, and uncertain weather changes. The dryer is easy to transfer, fix, and set up in a new area. Since it is made out of plastic and only has a few mechanical components, its simple design is easy to maneuver and maintain. The results of the trials reveal that 3 batches of 16.3kg coffee may be dried to an ideal moisture content of 12% on the third day or an exact period of 27h of drying. However, drying the same amount of coffee in the open sun takes 5 days or 47 hours. In the case of corn, the results demonstrate that 13% moisture content can be achieved in less than a day, or 8h, whereas it must be dried for a second day, or an equivalent of 14h, in the open sun. Based on the data acquired throughout the testing, the drying time will considerably impact the weight of the crops in a way. The ventilators are turned off after 5 p.m., and the crops are

retrieved from the dryers since this experiment should be based on farmers' actual practice of OSD. Further study should concentrate on integrating solar energy storage [11, 12] on the solar air heater to continuously heat the air entering the drying chamber, even during the night or when there is no sunlight. Additionally, automatic control and notification of the condition of the dryer and dried products are necessary to avoid over-drying, which results in excessive moisture loss.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This publication, and specifically the coffee commodity, was prepared under the Grant funded by WCR under the PhilCAFE Cooperative Agreement/Grant No. 22107CS01609 funded by USDA and led by ACIDI/VOCA. The authors would also like to thank the helpful research assistants, Carissa Oria and the rest of the group, Ms. Velessa Jane Dulin for assessing the results, and Ms. Rosela Sazon for proofreading the article.

REFERENCES

- [1] Statista Research Department, *Share of people employed in the agriculture industry in the Philippines between 2019 and 2020*. Statista, 2021.
- [2] L. C. Domingo, "Philippine coffee industry gets boost," *The Manila Times*, Manila, Philippines, Mar. 23, 2018.
- [3] P. Corpuz, *Philippines: Grain and Feed Annual*. USDA, 2020.
- [4] P. Udomkun *et al.*, "Review of solar dryers for agricultural products in Asia and Africa: An innovation landscape approach," *Journal of Environmental Management*, vol. 268, Aug. 2020, Art. no. 110730, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.110730>.
- [5] J. B. Hussein, M. A. Hassan, S. A. Kareem, and K. B. Filli, "Design, Construction and Testing of a Hybrid Photovoltaic (PV) Solar Dryer," *International Journal of Engineering Research and Science*, vol. 3, no. 5, pp. 1–14, May 2017, <https://doi.org/10.25125/engineering-journal-IJOER-MAY-2017-4>.
- [6] A. Salvatierra-Rojas, M. Nagle, M. Gummert, T. de Bruin, and J. Müller, "Development of an inflatable solar dryer for improved postharvest handling of paddy rice in humid climates," *International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 269–282, May 2017, <https://doi.org/10.25165/ijabe.v10i3.2444>.
- [7] M. Angelović, K. Krištof, J. Jobbágy, P. Findura, and M. Krizan, "The effect of conditions and storage time on course of moisture and temperature of maize grains," *BIO Web of Conferences*, vol. 10, 2018, Art. no. 02001, <https://doi.org/10.1051/bioconf/20181002001>.
- [8] E. M. Kyaw, I. W. Budiastira, Sutrisno, and Samsudin, "Estimation of moisture content in Liberica coffee by using near infrared spectroscopy," *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 542, no. 1, Apr. 2020, Art. no. 012013, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/542/1/012013>.
- [9] K. Lutz, W. Mühlbauer, J. Müller, and G. Reisinger, "Development of a multi-purpose solar crop dryer for arid zones," *Solar & Wind Technology*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 417–424, Jan. 1987, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0741-983X\(87\)90016-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0741-983X(87)90016-6).
- [10] N. B. Khedher, "Experimental Evaluation of a Flat Plate Solar Collector Under Hail City Climate," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2750–2754, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1957>.
- [11] M. A. Aichouni, N. F. Alshammari, N. B. Khedher, and M. Aichouni, "Experimental Evaluation of Nano-Enhanced Phase Change Materials in a Finned Storage Unit," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5814–5818, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3616>.
- [12] N. B. Khedher, "Numerical Study of the Thermal Behavior of a Composite Phase Change Material (PCM) Room," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2663–2667, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1824>.

A Second Order Arnoldi Method with Stopping Criterion and Reduced Order Selection for Reducing Second Order Systems

Abdesselam Tamri

Laboratoire de Recherche Modélisation, Simulation et
Optimisation des Systèmes Complexes Réels
University Ziane Achour
Djelfa, Algeria
atamri@mail.univ-djelfa.dz

Lahcène Mitiche

Laboratoire de Recherche Modélisation, Simulation et
Optimisation des Systèmes Complexes Réels
University Ziane Achour
Djelfa, Algeria
l_mitiche@yahoo.fr

Amel Baha Houda Adamou-Mitiche

Laboratoire de Recherche Modélisation, Simulation et
Optimisation des Systèmes Complexes Réels
University Ziane Achour
Djelfa, Algeria
amelmitiche@yahoo.fr

Received: 10 April 2022 | Revised: 21 April 2022 | Accepted: 26 April 2022

Abstract-This paper introduces a new algorithm for reducing large dimensional second-order dynamic systems through the Second Order Arnold Reduction (SOAR) procedure, with a stopping criterion to select an acceptable good order for the reduced model based on a new coefficient called the Numerical-Rank Performance Coefficient (NRPC), for efficient early termination and automatic optimal order selection of the reduced model. The key idea of this method is to calculate the NRPC coefficient for each iteration of the SOAR algorithm and measure the dynamic evolution information of the original system, which is added to each vector of the Krylov subspace generated by the SOAR algorithm. When the dynamical tolerance condition is verified, the iterative procedure of the algorithm stops. Three benchmark models were used as numerical examples to check the effectiveness and simplicity of the proposed algorithm.

Keywords-model order reduction; second-order systems; second-order Krylov sub-spaces; second-order Arnoldi procedure (SOAR); structure preserving; stability; projection; state space

I. INTRODUCTION

The large-scale second-order model is considered a well-known representation for the modeling of the dynamic behavior of multivariable complex systems in various fields of science and engineering, such as electrical, mechanical, structural, electromagnetic, and micro-electromechanical systems (MEMS). Some of these systems encounter computational problems in simulation due to the huge model order to treat this problem. Therefore, a reliable approximate model with reduced order is intended, which could replace the original in simulation or control and preserve the second-order

structure of the original system and the same key properties, such as stability [1, 2].

This study examined the following large-scale system given in the second-order form:

$$\Sigma_N : \begin{cases} M\ddot{q}(t) + D\dot{q}(t) + Kq(t) = bu(t) \\ y(t) = l^T q(t) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $M \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ is an invertible matrix, $q(0)=q_0$ and $\dot{q}(0)=\dot{q}_0$ are initial conditions, M , D , and $K \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ are respectively the mass, damping, and stiffness matrices as known for mechanical models, $q(t) \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is the state variables vector, and b , $l \in \mathbb{R}^N$ represent the input and the output measurement matrices, respectively [1]. A Model Order Reduction (MOR) of the second-order system Σ_N using the Second-Order Arnoldi (SOAR) algorithm was investigated. The SOAR approach has attracted many researchers in recent years and has been used to solve the following problems: a quadratic Eigen-value [3, 4], the MOR of second-order dynamical systems [1, 6], and in the analysis of structural acoustics [5, 6]. From a mathematical point of view, the SOAR design is based on a projection-based MOR technique that uses a second-order Krylov subspace and the SOAR procedure to generate the projection matrix as follows: in the first step a recurrence formula is defined for the two matrices coefficient A and B and one or two initial vectors, and then, in the second step, an orthonormal basis of projection subspaces from the famous second-order Krylov subspace defined in the recurrence formula is generated. The SOAR method is used in MOR, which constructs another reduced second-order state-space system Σ_n with reduced order, where the input-output behavior dynamics are completely recovered,

Corresponding author: Abdesselam Tamri

i.e., preserving the basic characteristics of the full order system [1, 2].

This study proposes an automated method to generate the best reduced-order model for a large second-order system using the SOAR procedure, by defining a new criterion to auto-stop the iteration process in the SOAR procedure and auto-select an acceptable reduced order of the projection matrix. The efficiency and robustness of the proposed algorithm were validated by various well-chosen numerical examples of second-order models.

II. MODEL ORDER REDUCTION AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Problem Formulation

The analysis of the second-order system Σ_N leads to building a very large complex model. Thus, mathematical tools are needed to reduce the computational complexity and accelerate the modeling task by constructing a reduced-order system Σ_n . The proposed tools preserve the characteristic properties of the original system, such as the second-order form and stability [2,10]. The reduced second-order system Σ_n is defined by:

$$\Sigma_n : \begin{cases} M_n \ddot{z}(t) + D_n \dot{z}(t) + K_n z(t) = b_n u(t) \\ \hat{y}(t) = l_n^T z(t) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $z(t)$ represents the state vector with dimension $n \ll N$, and the matrices M_n, D_n , and $K_n \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are the mass, damping, and stiffness matrices respectively, as known in structural dynamics. The vectors b_n and $l_n \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are the input distribution and output measurement respectively. Applying the Laplace transform, the transfer function of the original second-order model is given as:

$$h(s) = l^T (Ms^2 + Ds + K)^{-1} b \quad (3)$$

The power series of the Laplace transformation $Q(s)=L(q(t))$ can be expressed as:

$$Q(s) = R_0 + R_1 s + \dots = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} R_l s^l \quad (4)$$

with R_l being the l^{th} order system moments. The above second-order system Σ_N can be rewritten in first-order form by taking

the following state vector $x(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}(t) \\ q(t) \end{bmatrix}$:

$$\begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} M & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{q}(t) \\ \dot{q}(t) \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} -D & -K \\ I & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}(t) \\ q(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} u(t) \\ y(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & l^T \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}(t) \\ q(t) \end{bmatrix} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) can be expressed in matrix form as:

$$C\dot{x}(t) - Gx(t) = Bu(t), \quad y(t) = L^T x(t) \quad (6)$$

where:

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} M & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix}, \quad G = \begin{bmatrix} -D & -K \\ I & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\ B = \begin{bmatrix} b \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad L^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & l^T \end{bmatrix}$$

are respectively the input and the output of the first-order system representation. The transfer function $h(s)$ can be rewritten as:

$$h(s) = L^T (Cs - G)^{-1} B \quad (7)$$

and the power series of the transfer function $h(s)$ as:

$$h(s) = m_0 + m_1 s + \dots = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} m_l s^l \quad (8)$$

The design of MOR Krylov subspace techniques is based on moment matching methods. Its principle is to replicate the moments of the original system Σ_N on the moments of the reduced system Σ_n [11-13].

B. SOAR Algorithm for Second-Order Systems

This section describes the definition of a second-order Krylov subspace using the SOAR algorithm. The second-order Krylov subspace is defined as:

$$G_n(A, Z, w) = \text{colspan}\{r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{n-1}\} \quad (9)$$

where:

$$\begin{cases} r_0 = w, \quad r_1 = Ar_0 \\ r_i = Ar_{i-1} + Zr_{i-2}, \quad i = 2, 3, \dots \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $A, Z \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are square matrices called constant matrices and $w \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$ is a column vector called the starting vector. The sequence r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{n-1} is known as Krylov second-order basic blocks [1].

The $G_n(A, Z; w)$ subspace defined in (9) is called an n^{th} second-order Krylov subspace [2, 10, 11]. There is a connection between the subspace $G_n(A, Z; w)$ and the standard Krylov subspace $K_n(A, w)$ defined in (11), while $G_n(A, Z; w)$ can be considered as a generalization of $K_n(A, w)$.

$$K_n(A, w) = \text{span}(w, Aw, A^2w, \dots, A^{n-1}w) \quad (11)$$

In the case of the matrix $Z = 0$, the second-order Krylov subspace $G_n(A, Z; w)$ is equal to the general Krylov subspace $K_n(A, w)$. The application of the vector sequence $\{r_j\}$ of the second-order Krylov sub-space to obtain an orthonormal basis $\{r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{n-1}\}$ is called SOAR (Second Order ARnoldi) algorithm [2]. The following Lemma 1 can be used in the proof of Theorem 1 [10]:

- Lemma 1: Let $T_n \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ be an upper Hessenberg matrix. The k entry $T_n^j e_1$ is zero for $k = j+2, \dots, n$ and $j = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$. In particular, $e_n^T T_n^j e_1 = 0$ for $j=0, 1, \dots, n-2$ [1].
- Theorem 1: Let Q_n be the orthonormal matrix defined by the sequence vectors $Q_n = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n\}$, where the vectors q_i with $i = 1, \dots, n$ are generated by the SOAR procedure after the execution of n iterations. Then the analysis of the relationship between the j^{th} system's moment r_j and the output of the SOAR procedure can be expressed as [1]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} r_j \\ r_{j-1} \end{bmatrix} = H^j v = \begin{bmatrix} Q_n \\ P_n \end{bmatrix} T_n^j e_1, \quad \text{for } j = 0, 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (12)$$

In particular:

$$r_j = Q_n T_n^j e_1, \quad \text{and } r_{j-1} = P_n T_n^j e_1, \quad \text{for } j = 0, 1, \dots, N-1 \quad [10].$$

Theorem 2 provides a sufficient condition for the n first output vectors moment of the reduced and the original systems to match.

- Theorem 2: Let Q_n be the projection matrix generated by the SOAR algorithm to reduce the order of the second-order model. If $r_i \in \text{colspan}(Q_n)$ for $j = 0, \dots, n$ then $r_j = Q_n \hat{r}_j$ [1]. This theorem helps to verify that the condition of the output moment matching can be maintained.
- Theorem 3: The first unmatched moment is obtained after the execution of the n^{th} iteration of the SOAR procedure, and the error Δm_{n+1} between the two moments Δm_{n+1} of the original and \hat{m}_{n+1} of the reduced system can be given by an analytical expression [1]:

$$\Delta m_{n+1} = m_{n+1} - \hat{m}_{n+1} = C^T \left(\prod_{j=1}^n t_{j+1,j} \right) q_{n+1} \quad (13)$$

C. SOAR Procedure with Deflation and Memory Saving

In the SOAR algorithm, the p_n set vector is closely related to q_n , and the bi-product vector p_n is utilized. To avoid explicit references and updates of p vectors, a new version of SOAR, shown in Figure 1, was presented in [10] to reduce the memory requirements by almost half [15]. Since $p_l = 0$:

$$Q_n = P_{n+1} \hat{T}_n = P_{n+1} (:, 2:n+1) \hat{T}_n (2:n+1, 1:n) \quad (14)$$

```

Input Matrices :A, Z, r0, q
Output Matrices: Qn
1. /* Initialization */
2. q1 := r0 / ||r0||2
3. f := 0
4. for j := 1, 2, ..., q
5.   r := Aqj + Zf
6.   for i := 1, 2, ..., j
7.     tij := qiT r
8.     r := r - qi tij
9.   Next i
10.  tj+1,j := ||r||2
11.  if tj+1,j = 0
12.    qj+1 := r / tj+1,j /*Normalization*/
13.    f := Qj  $\hat{T}(2:j+1, 1:j)^{-1} e_j$ 
14.  else
15.    reset tj+1,j := 1
16.    qj+1 := 0
17.    f := Qj  $\hat{T}(2:j+1, 1:j)^{-1} e_j$ 
18.  save f and check deflation and breakdown
19.  End-if
20.  Next j
    
```

Fig. 1. SOAR with deflation and saving memory algorithm – Algorithm 1.

III. PROPOSED STOPPING CRITERION FOR SOAR

Finding a suitable order q for the reduced model that leads to a better approximation is an important component of order reduction. The question is when to pause an iterative order reduction [16]. The two traditional techniques to stop an iterative MOR approach based on the Krylov subspace are:

A. Finding the Zero Vector

Although it has an automatic implementation, the conventional approach consisting of finding the zero vector ($t_{j+1} = 0$ in the SOAR procedure) to interrupt the process is extremely ineffective. The major drawback of this method is that it adds a lot of redundancy to the transformation matrix

and duplicates the same information about the dynamic behavior of the original model once and again.

B. Time Response Comparison and Manual Termination

In this method, a reduced-order model is generated in each iteration of the SOAR procedure, a time response comparison is made for both models, the reduced and the original one, and the process is terminated if the errors are acceptable. Some fundamental definitions of matrix factorization should be presented before the implementation and application of the new criterion for stopping and selecting the reduced order in the SOAR procedure.

- Definition 1: Let $A \in C^{n \times m}$, and suppose $\text{rank}(A) = r$, and $n \leq m$. Then, there exist matrices $U \in C^{n \times n}$, $V \in C^{m \times m}$, and $\Sigma \in R^{n \times n}$ such that:

$$A = U \Sigma V^* \quad (15)$$

$$U \text{ and } V \text{ are unitary, and } \Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\Sigma} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

where $\hat{\Sigma}$ is a diagonal matrix with $\hat{\Sigma} = \text{diag}\{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_r\}$ and $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_r > 0$. Positive numbers σ_i for $i = 1, \dots, r$ are determined uniquely by A and called singular values of A . Equation (15) is called the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of matrix A . Columns U and V are called the left and right singular vectors respectively. The index r of the smallest singular value is called the theoretical rank of matrix A .

- Definition 2: Let σ_r be the calculated singular values of the matrix $A \in C^{n \times m}$, and let δ be a positive real number, $\delta > 0$. The numerical δ -rank is defined as the number of singular values greater than δ . The numerical δ -rank is written as k , if:

$$\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \sigma_k \geq \delta \geq \sigma_{k+1} \geq \dots \geq \sigma_r, r = \min(n, m) \quad (16)$$

For each iteration of the SOAR algorithm, the contribution of the second-order Krylov vectors, taking into consideration the knowledge about the model dynamics stored in them, decreases monotonously. It is therefore expected that each generated vector r_i will be less effective to the numerical rank of the transformation matrix Q_n .

The suggested stopping criteria rely on the estimation of a signal of progress in the numerical rank of the generated transformation matrix with each iteration in the SOAR procedure, exactly before adding the new normalized vector. To measure this signal, an indicator is assigned for each vector generated by the iterative process before being fed to the normalization routine (line 12 in Algorithm 1). This indicator is called *NRPC* and has a value range of [0,1]. The greater value of the *NRPC* for the nominee vector harmonizes an important contribution of that vector to the improvement of the numerical rank and the dynamic progression of the original system and must hence be included in Q_n . The *NRPC* for the candidate vector r_i is given as the inverse of the sum of singular values of the current transformation matrix Q_i , obtained by appending the new non-normalized vector r to the transformation matrix Q_n of the previous iteration.

$$NRPC = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^i \sigma_j} \quad (17)$$

Therefore, it is possible to approximate the stopping criteria as:

- In each iteration calculate the *NRPC* indicator using (17).
- The iteration can be halted as soon as $NRPC < \varepsilon$, where $\varepsilon > 0$ some specified value.

Algorithm 2 demonstrates how to integrate this stopping criterion into Algorithm 1 of SOAR.

```

Input Matrices : A, Z, r0; q
Output Matrices: Qn
1. /* Initialization */
2. Execute Algorithm 1 from line 2 to line 10
3. Qi := [Qi, r]
4. Sigma := svd(Qi)
5. NRPC := 1/sum(sigma)
6. If NRPC < epsilon then Stop
7. end if
8. Execute Algorithm 1 from line 11 to line 20
    
```

Fig. 2. SOAR with stopping criterion algorithm – Algorithm 2.

IV. NUMERICAL APPLICATIONS

Numerical applications were conducted to demonstrate the efficiency and accuracy of the SOAR method with the proposed stopping criterion and the robustness of the terminating mechanism for the Krylov-based reduction method. Three practical engineering examples were studied: (i) a shaft on bearing supports with a damper originating from a Finite Element (FE) [7], (ii) the butterfly gyroscope problem [8], and (iii) the FE model of the 3D Cantilever Timoshenko beam [20]. Table I displays the size of these and their corresponding reduced models and some parameter settings used in the simulation, such as the expansion point s_0 and the frequency range. The output of the relative errors between the original and the reduced systems and the related frequency responses [7, 8] were considered for comparison.

TABLE I. MODEL EXAMPLES WITH PARAMETER SETTINGS

Model	Full size	Reduced sizes	Parameters	
			S_0	Frequency range
FE model of a shaft on bearing supports	400	10,20,40	$150 \times 2\pi$	[0,3000] Hz
butterfly gyroscope	17361	10,19,39	1.05×10^5	$[10^3, 10^6]$ Hz
FE model of 3D Cantilever Timoshenko beam	600	10,19,39	0	[0,1200] Hz

Figure 3 shows the pattern of the stopping criterion and the *NRPC* coefficient, which is the inverse of the sum of the singular values of the current transformation matrix Q_i , obtained by appending the new non-normalized vector r to the transformation matrix Q_n of the previous iteration. After the 20th iteration, *NRPC* decreases slowly and it can be assumed that a good reduced-order model can be selected at around 20 and above. In other terms, an acceptable good approximation model can be obtained for *NRPC* values in [0, 0.5]. A fixed tolerance value ε in [0, 0.5] was defined to implement a condition to select a good reduced order and stop the SOAR procedure.

Fig. 3. Pattern of variation of *NRPC* vs number of iterations.

Fig. 4. Example 1 - Frequency responses of the exact and reduced transfer functions $h(s)$ and $h_n(s)$.

Fig. 5. Example 1 - The relative errors $\|h(s) - h_n(s)\| / \|h(s)\|$.

Fig. 6. Example 1 - Poles distribution for three reduced models.

Fig. 7. Example 2 - Frequency responses of the exact and reduced transfer functions $h(s)$ and $h_n(s)$.

Fig. 8. Example 2 - The relative errors $\|h(s) - h_n(s)\| / \|h(s)\|$.

Fig. 9. Example 2 - Poles distribution for three reduced models.

Fig. 10. Example 3 - Frequency responses of the exact and reduced transfer functions $h(s)$ and $h_n(s)$.

Fig. 11. Example 3 - The relative errors $\|h(s) - h_n(s)\| / \|h(s)\|$.

Fig. 12. Example 3 - Poles distribution for three reduced models.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a new MOR approach with an efficient stopping criterion to find the suitable order of a reduced model, by using a modified SOAR algorithm as a Krylov MOR approach with auto-selection of the reduced order. Based on the obtained results, the proposed algorithm showed high efficiency and accuracy in terms of relative error against the original systems, while the key properties of the second-order form in the reduced model were still preserved. Furthermore, its superiority was proven compared to conventional SOAR in terms of robustness, where a suitable and optimal reduced-order was chosen systematically. The proposed approach worked very well for the three examples used in numerical tests (FE Model of a shaft on bearing supports with a damper, a butterfly gyroscope model, and the FE Model of a 3D Cantilever Timoshenko Beam). The key properties, such as the preservation of the second-order structure and stability were guaranteed with an automatic selection of a significantly reduced order as a size of the reduced model in the numerical simulation results.

REFERENCES

- [1] C.-C. Chu, H.-C. Tsai, and M.-H. Lai, "Structure preserving model-order reductions of MIMO second-order systems using Arnoldi methods," *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, vol. 51, no. 7, pp. 956–973, Apr. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcm.2009.08.028>.
- [2] Z. Bai and Y. Su, "Dimension Reduction of Large-Scale Second-Order Dynamical Systems via a Second-Order Arnoldi Method," *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 1692–1709, Jan. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1137/040605552>.
- [3] Y. Su, J. Wang, X. Zeng, Z. Bai, C. Chiang, and D. Zhou, "SAPOR: second-order Arnoldi method for passive order reduction of RCS circuits," in *IEEE/ACM International Conference on Computer Aided Design, 2004. ICCAD-2004.*, San Jose, CA, USA, Aug. 2004, pp. 74–79, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCAD.2004.1382546>.
- [4] Z. R. Labidi, H. Schulte, and A. Mami, "A Model-Based Approach of DC-DC Converters Dedicated to Controller Design Applications for Photovoltaic Generators," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4371–4376, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2829>.
- [5] R. Srinivasan Puri, "Krylov Subspace Based Direct Projection Techniques for Low Frequency, Fully Coupled, Structural Acoustic Analysis and Optimization," Ph.D. dissertation, Oxford Brookes University, 2009.
- [6] R. S. Puri and D. Morrey, "A comparison of one- and two-sided krylov-arnoldi projection methods for fully coupled, damped structural-acoustic analysis," *Journal of Computational Acoustics*, vol. 21, no. 02, Jun. 2013, Art. no. 1350004, <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218396X13500045>.
- [7] H. Bassi and Y. A. Mobarak, "State-Space Modeling and Performance Analysis of Variable-Speed Wind Turbine Based on a Model Predictive Control Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1436–1443, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1015>.
- [8] J. G. Korvink and E. B. Rudnyi, "Oberwolfach Benchmark Collection," in *Dimension Reduction of Large-Scale Systems*, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2005, pp. 311–315, https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-27909-1_11.
- [9] T.-J. Su and R. R. Craig, "Model reduction and control of flexible structures using Krylov vectors," *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 260–267, 1991, <https://doi.org/10.2514/3.20636>.
- [10] Z. Bai and Y. Su, "SOAR: A Second-order Arnoldi Method for the Solution of the Quadratic Eigenvalue Problem," *SIAM Journal on Matrix Analysis and Applications*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 640–659, Jan. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1137/S0895479803438523>.

- [11] B. Salimbahrami and B. Lohmann, "Order reduction of large scale second-order systems using Krylov subspace methods," *Linear Algebra and its Applications*, vol. 415, no. 2, pp. 385–405, Jun. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.laa.2004.12.013>.
- [12] C. A. Beattie and S. Gugercin, "Krylov-based model reduction of second-order systems with proportional damping," in *Proceedings of the 44th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, Seville, Spain, Sep. 2005, pp. 2278–2283, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CDC.2005.1582501>.
- [13] L. Zhou, L. Bao, Y. Lin, Y. Wei, and Q. Wu, "Restarted Generalized Second-Order Krylov Subspace Methods for Solving Quadratic Eigenvalue Problems," *International Journal of Mathematical and Computational Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 7, pp. 997–1004, Jul. 2010.
- [14] C.-C. Chu, H.-J. Lee, and W.-S. Feng, "Error Estimations of Arnoldi-Based Interconnect Model-Order Reductions," *IEICE TRANSACTIONS on Fundamentals of Electronics, Communications and Computer Sciences*, vol. E88-A, no. 2, pp. 533–537, Feb. 2005.
- [15] G. W. Stewart, *Matrix Algorithms: Volume 2, Eigensystems*, 1st edition. Philadelphia, PA, USA: SIAM: Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, 2001.
- [16] B. Salimbahrami, B. Lohmann, T. Bechtold, and J. Korvink, "A two-sided Arnoldi algorithm with stopping criterion and MIMO selection procedure," *Mathematical and Computer Modelling of Dynamical Systems*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 79–93, Mar. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13873950500052595>.
- [17] M. A. Bazaz, M. Nabi, and S. Janardhanan, "Automated and efficient order selection in Krylov-based model order reduction," *International Journal of Modelling, Identification and Control*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 332–340, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMIC.2013.053538>.
- [18] S. Ubaru and Y. Saad, "Fast methods for estimating the Numerical rank of large matrices," in *Proceedings of The 33rd International Conference on Machine Learning*, New York, NY, USA, Jun. 2016, pp. 468–477.
- [19] Y.-T. Li, Z. Bai, W.-W. Lin, and Y. Su, "A Structured Quasi-Arnoldi procedure for model order reduction of second-order systems," *Linear Algebra and its Applications*, vol. 436, no. 8, pp. 2780–2794, Apr. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.laa.2011.07.023>.
- [20] H. Panzer, J. Hubele, R. Eid, and B. Lohmann, "Generating a Parametric Finite Element Model of a 3D Cantilever Timoshenko Beam Using Matlab," 2009.
- [21] S. S. Desouky, A. Z. El-Dein, R. A. A. El-Aal, and N. a. A. El-Rahman, "A New Contribution in Reducing Electric Field Distribution Within/Around Medium Voltage Underground Cable Terminations," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 1962–1966, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1357>.

Prioritization of Occupational Accident Causes in the Automotive Manufacturing

Muhammad Zain Syed

Department of Industrial Engineering and Management, Dawood University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
syedmzain1@gmail.com

Aaraiz Khalique

Department of Industrial Engineering and Management, Dawood University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
aaraizkhalique@gmail.com

Muhammad Dawood Idrees

Department of Industrial Engineering and Management, Dawood University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
muhammad.dawood@duet.edu.pk

Atif Jamil

Department of Computer Systems Engineering, Dawood University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
atif.jamil@duet.edu.pk

Abdul Sami

Department of Electronic Engineering, Dawood University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan.
dr.abdulsami@duet.edu.pk

Arif Abdullah

Department of Electronic Engineering, Dawood University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
arif.abdullah@duet.edu.pk

Nawal Sajid

Department of Industrial Engineering and Management, Dawood University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
nawal_3211@hotmail.com

Kanzal Khan

Department of Industrial Engineering and Management, Dawood University of Engineering and Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
kanzalkhan96@gmail.com

Safdar Rizvi

Department of Computer Sciences Bahria University
Karachi Campus
Karachi, Pakistan
safdar.bukc@bahria.edu.pk

Received: 23 January 2022 | Revised: 19 March 2022 and 5 April 2022 | Accepted: 18 April 2022

Abstract-The automotive industry is a significant contributor to the economy. Additionally, it is prone to occupational accidents. The current study focuses on organizational accidents in high-risk activities, particularly occupational accidents in the automobile and manufacturing industries. This investigation aims to rank and quantify the causes of occupational accidents. These reasons are identified through a literature review and are investigated utilizing the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). An AHP model is built based on a literature review. This model created a questionnaire and its evaluation via a survey of experts' opinions. This study shows that the most significant and dominant elements in accidents are human and organizational factors since they receive roughly equal weighting, whereas environmental factors weigh less.

Keywords-Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP); automotive; occupational accidents; high-risk operations

I. INTRODUCTION

Management commitment to safety culture varies from organization to organization. Organizational and psychological factors increasingly influence the accident rate [1]. According to a quantitative survey of 225 complaints, dangerous activities constitute the top cause of occupational accidents. Additionally, hazardous circumstances and elements associated

with machines and equipment significantly impact occupational accidents. Additionally, it is essential to develop new plans and programs for assessing workers' occupational health to take preventative measures against health risks [2-4]. In Turkey's metal production industry revealed that the majority of workplace fatalities are caused by risky activities and lack of training [5, 6]. Additionally, at an Italian steel manufacturing company, it was shown that working in a hypercritical atmosphere results in occupational accidents and disease. The study noted that working at a high temperature and being exposed to environmental conditions such as noise, vibration, poor air quality, and a demanding workload may result in severe injuries and burns [6]. Similarly, factors that contribute to occupational stress, lack of a reward system, and worker health may also contribute to occupational sickness and job stress results in an increase of dangerous behaviors [7].

Numerous factors have been identified as contributing to occupational mortality. These ambiguous situations occur due to a variety of personal characteristics, behaviors, and organizational circumstances [8, 9]. This partiality and bias in safety management contribute to the development of flawed policies. While doing a safety review, operators' psychological behavior, religious and cultural beliefs must be considered when examining fatality reports [10-12]. This aids in

Corresponding author: Muhammad Dawood Idrees

understanding their risk perception along with the cause of death [13]. Numerous manufacturing companies employ the Six Sigma methodology to enhance their product quality and operational efficiency, and to increase security. It is an organization's responsibility to safeguard the operator's safety. Workplace accidents occur mostly due to unsafe working conditions and behaviors, low visibility, and a hazardous atmosphere. These variables can result in life-threatening illness, accidents, lifelong disability, or death [14].

The conclusion of [15] indicates that these accidents have certain characteristics. There is a greater probability of limited exposure, and most injuries are caused by power machinery. These judgments would predate programs on accident prevention in the automotive industry. Human factor engineering is concerned with ensuring that the design of the man-machine system does not exceed the human capacity for information processing. Emotional stress affects one's ability to digest information, as defined by reception and feedback time. These indicators focus on employee safety, particularly pre-employment screening and stress management practices. It is the company's responsibility to give stress management training. Additionally, monitoring, interpreting, and interfering in employees' risky activities prevents accidents [16].

The evaluation of circumstances is a systematic tool used in occupational safety to ascertain the reasons of accidents. Conducting this type of study can assist a company in forecasting future occurrences. The analytical report is deficient in detail due to the absence of examining the variables associated with the workplace conditions. Also, a systematic model for evaluating workplace accident causes is required and a database containing accident statistics. Numerous studies have been conducted to improve the quality of accident analysis models and procedures to reduce the number of accidents. However, the increasing number of accidents motivates analysts to conduct additional research in this field. Numerous sectors have implemented continuous improvement systems to increase worker safety, productivity, and quality. However, just a few occupational publications examine using the research's standardized recommended criteria. This chasm will have been closed by addressing the training and skills of the professionals responsible for compiling an accident investigation report. Similarly, to ensure the validity of accident cause reports, the firm must implement monitoring mechanisms to ensure the methodology is being followed [17].

II. METHODOLOGY

This research conducts a thorough analysis of the occupational accident causes in the automobile industry. It has been discovered that occupational deaths are caused by three distinct cause categories: environmental, human, and organizational factors. These factors have sub factors as shown in Figure 1. These factors and sub factors have been identified through an extensive literature review [8-12]. This process results in the development of a model based on these criteria and sub-criteria under the supervision of safety specialists and academic experts. The AHP approach determined the relative importance of many causes in an occupational accident or sickness.

Fig. 1. Criteria and sub-criteria of occupational accidents cause in the automotive industry.

Decisions are usually quick and even have to be made at the instant. However, these decisions require time, tools, and techniques to resolve many situations. Sometimes it is challenging to quantify many alternatives to make a judgment. In such circumstances, executing these judgments requires logical, systematic, and mathematical tools through which decisions would be obtained. Numerous decision-making approaches and procedures have been proposed and AHP [18] is one of these methods. There are many reasons to use AHP in decision-making, and one of them is to prioritize factors. This method necessitates the establishment of an objective or goal, classifying various criteria, selecting a scale, evaluating preferences, conducting a consistency test, and aggregating the resultant weights of sub-criteria about the primary criterion. Figure 2 summarizes the entire study hierarchy. The pairwise comparison questionnaire requires an assortment of a scale. The pairwise comparison of different alternatives was assessed by employing the Saaty scale [18, 19] to conduct the examination. Before evaluation, the design of the questionnaire was validated by academic professionals. The standardized procedure of AHP requires a pairwise comparison of one criterion to another through a questionnaire and results in a ranking of the factors. The geometric mean was applied to the whole sample size and was further evaluated for consistency in order to prioritize the causes leading to the objective.

III. RESULTS

This analysis included 5 automobile manufacturers in Pakistan and 220 participants. To ensure the reliability of the results, the primary focus during sample collection was on

safety management specialists. As a result, safety management specialists and automobile industry experts discussed and responded to the questionnaire. The comprehensive literature assessment on occupational accident causes follows a logical structure and focuses on diverse developed and developing countries. The complete analysis, conducted using Microsoft Excel, is summarized in Table I, including pairwise comparisons of the major risk factors for occupational accidents.

Fig. 2. Research flow diagram.

TABLE I. PAIR-WISE COMPARISON OF OAC

OAC	E	H	O
E	0.250569035	0.315352748	0.199831687
H	0.300700026	0.378444924	0.442300229
O	0.448730939	0.306202328	0.357868084

Similarly, as shown in Table I, the study obtained results for the sub-criteria of environmental, human, and organizational aspects. Finally, the results, as shown in Table II of occupational accidents indicated that ecological variables (E) had a 26% weighting, human factors (H) had a 37% weighting, and organizational factors also had a 37% weighting on the accident rate, as illustrated in Figure 3. The complete results in Table II also contain the weights of sub-criteria at the local and global levels. According to Table II, the leading environmental factor that causes an occupational accident or illness is excessive occupational noise (E1) with 8% weightage. The human factors that cause occupational accidents are unsafe acts (H2) with 13% weightage, job stress (H4) with 9%

weightage, and personal physique (H3) with 8% weightage. Finally, the most significant organizational elements that contribute to the accident occurrence are the lack of safety training and education (O2), which account for 10% of the weight, and the physical conditions of the workplace which account for 8%.

Fig. 3. Weightage of OAC.

TABLE II. LOCAL AND OVERALL WEIGHTS OF OAC

Main criteria	Local weights	Sub-criteria	Local weights	Global weights	Overall weights
E	0.255	E1	0.303	0.08	26%
		E4	0.211	0.07	
		E3	0.228	0.06	
		E2	0.258	0.05	
H	0.374	H2	0.194	0.13	37%
		H4	0.349	0.09	
		H3	0.212	0.08	
		H1	0.245	0.07	
O	0.371	O2	0.157	0.10	37%
		O5	0.274	0.08	
		O4	0.159	0.07	
		O1	0.193	0.06	
Total			1.00	1.00	1.00

IV. CONCLUSION

This study discusses important occupational accident causes in car production, including environmental, human, and organizational factors. The AHP approach categorizes and prioritizes the primary causes of occupational accidents. Identifying these factors encourages the prevention of the leading causes. Based on past research, a logical assessment of the literature on various ergonomic and managerial variables was conducted, and a new model was built. Human and organizational variables are the most significant and dominant components in accidents, since they receive approximately equal weighting, while environmental factors receive less weighting.

APPENDIX

RESEARCH SURVEY

Name:
Organization/Industry:
Email:
Do you have experience with the Health & Safety department in the Automotive Sector?

Instructions

- If you think criterion 1 is more important than criterion 2, you must pick a number from the left side. Let's suppose you think criterion 1 is five times more important than criterion 2, so you can circle 5 from your left.
- Similarly, if you think criterion 2 is more important, you can mark 5 from the right.
- Circle only one number in each comparison.

Criterion 1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Criterion 2
-------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	-------------

Questionnaire - Pair-wise Comparison of Occupational Accident Causes

Q1) PAIR-WISE COMPARISON OF OCCUPATIONAL ACCIDENT CAUSES

E	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	H
E	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	O
H	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	O

Q2) PAIR-WISE COMPARISON OF ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

E1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	E2
E1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	E3
E1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	E4
E2	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	E3
E2	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	E3
E3	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	E4

Q3) PAIR-WISE COMPARISON OF HUMAN FACTORS

H1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	H2
H1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	H3
H1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	H4
H2	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	H3
H2	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	H3
H3	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	H4

Q4) PAIR-WISE COMPARISON OF ORGANIZATIONAL FACTORS

O1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	O2
O1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	O3
O1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	O4
O1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	O5
O2	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	O3
O2	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	O4
O2	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	O5
O3	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	O4
O3	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	O5
O4	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	O5

REFERENCES

[1] S. Clarke, "Safety culture: under-specified and overrated?," *International Journal of Management Reviews*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 65–90, 2000, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2370.00031>.

[2] S. Clarke, "Safety culture: under-specified and overrated?," *International Journal of Management Reviews*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 65–90, 2000, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2370.00031>.

[3] K. Koklonis, M. Sarafidis, M. Vastardi, and D. Koutsouris, "Utilization of Machine Learning in Supporting Occupational Safety and Health Decisions in Hospital Workplace," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7262–7272, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4205>.

[4] F. Siddiqui, M. A. Akhund, A. H. Memon, A. R. Khoso, and H. U. Imad, "Health and Safety Issues of Industry Workmen," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3184–3188, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2138>.

[5] B. Gulhan, M. N. Ilhan, and E. F. Civil, "Occupational accidents and affecting factors of metal industry in a factory in Ankara," *Turkish Journal of Public Health*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 76–85, Aug. 2012.

[6] I. A. Memon, A. Ali, M. A. Memon, U. A. Rajput, S. a. K. Abro, and A. A. Memon, "Controlling the Defects of Paint Shop using Seven Quality Control Tools in an Automotive Factory," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 5062–5065, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3160>.

[7] S. Murè, L. Combetti, and M. Demichela, "How harsh work environments affect the occupational accident phenomenology? Risk assessment and decision making optimisation," *Safety Science*, vol. 95, pp. 159–170, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2017.01.004>.

[8] T. K. Courtney, G. S. Sorock, D. P. Manning, J. W. Collins, and M. A. Holbein-Jenny, "Occupational slip, trip, and fall-related injuries--can the contribution of slipperiness be isolated?," *Ergonomics*, vol. 44, no. 13, pp. 1118–1137, Oct. 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140130110085538>.

[9] N. Meshkati, "Human factors in large-scale technological systems' accidents: Three Mile Island, Bhopal, Chernobyl," *Industrial Crisis Quarterly*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 133–154, 1991.

[10] D. B. Goldston, S. D. Molock, L. B. Whitbeck, J. L. Murakami, L. H. Zayas, and G. C. Nagayama Hall, "Cultural Considerations in Adolescent Suicide Prevention and Psychosocial Treatment," *The*

- American psychologist*, vol. 63, no. 1, pp. 14–31, Jan. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.63.1.14>.
- [11] A. Moreira-Almeida, F. L. Neto, and H. G. Koenig, "Religiousness and mental health: a review," *Revista Brasileira De Psiquiatria (Sao Paulo, Brazil: 1999)*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 242–250, Sep. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1590/s1516-44462006000300018>.
- [12] R. H. Lehto and K. F. Stein, "Death anxiety: an analysis of an evolving concept," *Research and Theory for Nursing Practice*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 23–41, 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1891/1541-6577.23.1.23>.
- [13] A. Barkhordari, B. Malmir, and M. Malakoutikhah, "An Analysis of Individual and Social Factors Affecting Occupational Accidents," *Safety and Health at Work*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 205–212, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2019.01.002>.
- [14] S. A. Gyekye, "Occupational safety management: the role of causal attribution," *International Journal of Psychology: Journal International De Psychologie*, vol. 45, no. 6, pp. 405–416, Dec. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207594.2010.501337>.
- [15] M.-V. Sánchez-Rebull, A. Niñerola, R. Ferrer-Rullan, and A.-B. Hernández-Lara, "Six Sigma for workplace safety improvement: improving hazards and unsafe conditions in a metallic packaging manufacturing company," *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 766–778, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10803548.2020.1829318>.
- [16] B. Y. Jeong and D. S. Shin, "Characteristics of Occupational Accidents in Korean, Chinese, Japanese and Western Cuisine Restaurants," *Human Factors and Ergonomics in Manufacturing & Service Industries*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 316–322, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1002/hfm.20647>.
- [17] M. Kolich and D. Wong-Reiger, "Emotional stress and information processing ability in the context of accident causation," *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 591–602, Oct. 1999, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-8141\(98\)00065-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-8141(98)00065-1).
- [18] F. Salguero-Caparros, M. Suarez-Cebador, and J. C. Rubio-Romero, "Analysis of investigation reports on occupational accidents," *Safety Science*, vol. 72, pp. 329–336, Feb. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2014.10.005>.
- [19] H. Bain, N. Howard, and T. L. Saaty, "Using the Analysis of Options Technique to Analyze a Community Conflict," *The Journal of Conflict Resolution*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 133–144, 1971.

The Effectiveness of Retrofitting RC Frames with a Combination of Different Techniques

Mohamed Saadi

LGC-ROI, Department of Civil Engineering
Faculty of Technology, University of Batna 2
Batna, Algeria
m.saadi@univ-batna2.dz

Djarir Yahiaoui

LGC-ROI, Department of Civil Engineering
Faculty of Technology, University of Batna 2
Batna, Algeria
d.yahiaoui@univ-batna2.dz

Received: 12 April 2022 | Revised: 28 April 2022 | Accepted: 28 April 2022

Abstract-During the last two decades, the attention of researchers has been focused on repairing and retrofitting concrete frames to make them more earthquake-resistant. Two methods have been developed to increase the seismic resistance of previously undamaged structures before they are subjected to an earthquake. The first is through the addition of new structural members, such as steel braces and the second is by selectively strengthening structural elements, for instance through steel caging. Seismic response analysis results have been utilized in multi-story RC frames that were designed without seismic design criteria. This study aims to determine whether the retrofitting technique is effective based on comparisons between steel braces, steel cages, and their combinations. The seismic performance is defined by the seismic code for Algeria RPA 2003 according to the latest recommendations. Static nonlinear analysis was used to compare seismic responses of existing non-ductile reinforced concrete RC frames under a variety of retrofit schemes. The results show that retrofitting with steel caging gives excellent performance in terms of ductility and low shear capacity. The retrofitting with steel bracing increased the shear capacity but led to a severe ductility deficiency. The retrofitting structure combined with steel bracing and steel caging shows good performance in shear capacity and ductility. Using the Zipper system (steel bracing) and V system in combination with steel caging gives similar results to the RPA model.

Keywords-RC frame; retrofit; steel bracing; steel-cage technique

I. INTRODUCTION

Most structures before the '70s were designed to be able to resist gravity loads, and while these structures performed well under such loads, their performance under seismic loads was questionable. Several recent earthquakes, such as those in Taiwan (1999) and Algeria (2003), have caused significant damages to buildings and many reinforced concrete structures collapsed because they did not comply with the current seismic codes and had deficiencies such as poor detailing, discontinuous load paths, and a lack of capacity design provisions.

Two main retrofitting approaches have been identified to improve the seismic performance of existing undamaged structures before they are exposed to an earthquake. One is the

insertion of new structural elements such as structural walls or steel braces and the other is selective strengthening of deficient structural elements, for example by using concrete or steel caging and fiber reinforced polymers. For the first approach, steel bracing is typically used in the retrofitting of RC frames. This type of structure is efficient and economical for resisting lateral loads. Among the first studies on retrofitting using this technique were [1, 2]. Model tests have also been reported in [3]. Their study indicated the effectiveness of this method in increasing the shear resistance capacity of the structure. Two of the flaws of this method are architectural details and difficulties making connections between the steel bracing and the RC frames. Authors in [4] performed experimental studies on the pushover response of scaled RC frames braced with both diagonal and knee bracing systems. Authors in [5] investigated the seismic behavior of RC frames reinforced with various steel bracing systems, including X, inverted V, ZX, and Zipper systems. By adding bracing, they were able to improve deformation, strength, and ductility. It was found that X and Zipper bracing systems perform better than others. Authors in [6] examined the use of hysteretic dampers and column strengthening to develop the desired behavior of buildings with an open first floor. Authors in [7] studied the impact of retrofitting RC frames with steel X-bracing on the global behavior of the frame, including its global displacement, performance level, and inter-story drifts. Similarly, the authors in [8] analyzed the seismic response of steel X-bracing numerically and concluded that it greatly reduces the shear loads on the beam-column joint. The maximum lateral displacement in RC frames is also reduced by retrofitting them with X-braces. In the tests conducted in [9], the joint displayed excellent self-centering properties without deteriorating in strength. The application of friction dampers to a self-centering PC frame was also studied for seismic retrofitting of reinforced concrete structures. A recent study [10] found that disk springs could provide self-centering capabilities without the drawbacks associated with post-tensioned tendons.

The steel caging method is generally favored because of its high retrofitting effectiveness and economic efficiency [11-12]. Authors in [13-16] first applied the steel-cage retrofitting method for bridge columns in California. Authors in [17] studied the efficiency of rectangular solid steel caging and

partial steel caging. Authors in [18-19] described the effect of a partially stiffened steel caging and composite prefabricated jacket on improving the strength and ductility of RC columns. Recently, authors in [20] suggested an extension of the previous works, introducing a new genetic algorithm that minimizes the cost of seismic upgrading.

In the current study, a structure that was designed without seismic design criteria was retrofitted with three techniques: steel caging technique, steel bracing system, and their combination were studied and examined. The seismic performance of these frames was determined by nonlinear static pushover analysis.

II. DESCRIPTION OF DIFFERENT RETROFITTING PROCEDURES

A. Steel Caging Technique

The application of metallic jackets in RC columns aims to increase shear strength and strengthen the lap-splicing region and the ductility capacity. The steel caging option involves the total encasement of the column with thin steel plates placed at a small distance from the column surface, with the ensuing gap filled with non-shrink grout. Steel caging is now a common practice in many countries [21]. When the yield stress of the steel is increased, the ultimate load on the strengthened column increases [22, 23].

B. Steel Bracing Technique

Steel bracing can be a very effective method for the global strengthening of buildings [24]. Some of its advantages are the ability to accommodate openings, the minimal weight added to the structure, and, in the case of external steel systems, the minimum disruption to the function of the building and its occupants [25]. Alternative configurations of bracing systems may be used in selected bays of a reinforced concrete frame to provide a significant increase in the horizontal capacity of the structure [26]. To improve the seismic performance of an existing reinforced concrete building, authors in [27] used steel bracing. Three methods of seismic evaluation were employed in this study: the nonlinear static pushover as described in FEMA 356 [28] and FEMA 440 [29] and dynamic time history analysis. The retrofitting of an RC frame with the steel X-bracing method can be seen in [30].

III. DESCRIPTION OF THE FRAME MODELS

A five-story RC building has been considered in this study (Figure 1). The slabs were represented in the structural model of the building using their weight in the gravity load case and as centered masses at all joints, with bay length of 4m and height of 3m. The building was designed without seismic design criteria, while it is located in a high seismicity region with a peak ground acceleration of 0.32g. Table I shows the details of the design sections, where the characteristics of the original frame and the reinforcement of the beams and columns were determined according to the Algerian seismic code (RPA 2003) [31]. To retrofit the structures with the bracing system, it is necessary to have studied the influence of variation in the section of the bracing element and different bracing systems (X, V, and Zipper). Figure 2 shows the RC frames retrofitted with different steel bracing systems.

Fig. 1. Structural model.

TABLE I. REINFORCEMENT DETAILS

	Columns	Beams
Original frame	30×30 3T12	30×30 3T12
RPA frame	40×40 8T14	30×50 3T16

Fig. 2. Bracing models.

To retrofit the structures with steel caging, it is important to investigate the impact of retrofitting vertical and horizontal bays with steel caging. Figures 3-4 show the retrofitting details and the models of retrofitting vertical and horizontal bays with steel caging respectively. In order to conclude the comparison between the bracing systems and to properly propose a reinforcement model close to the RPA model, a final comparison was made. A combination of the bracing systems with the steel caging was applied.

Fig. 3. Retrofitting details with steel caging.

Fig. 4. Retrofitting with steel caging.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Pushover Results of the Original and RPA Frame

The aim of the reinforcement of the structure is to increase the capacity of resistance to shearing, the ductility of the original frame, and to reach the capacity of new structures calculated by the RPA Code. This starts with nonlinear static analysis in order to know the difference between the capacities of the two structures (original and RPA), and then the type of reinforcement is chosen. Figure 5 presents a comparison between the capacity curves of the original frame and the RPA, showing that the base shear of the new structure is larger by 137.5%, and the ductility by 58%.

Fig. 5. Curve of capacity for old and RPA structures.

B. Pushover Results of Different Retrofitting Systems

Figure 6 shows the results of the nonlinear analysis of the structure frame strengthened with different bracing systems (X, V, and Zipper) and the variation in the cross-section of the bracing element. The results show that when the bracing section is increased, ductility is decreased and strength is increased, in accordance with the findings in [5]. The behavior of the different systems is much stiffer. The results show that the section of D76.1×3.2 for all the bracing systems except the X system gives a behavior close to the RPA frame with reference to the lateral load. Compared to the original frame, for the retrofitting with the 76.1 Tube section, the capacity of Zipper, X, and V systems is increased by 2.3, 3.4, and 2.02 respectively. The highest ductility reduction factor is given by the Zipper system with the 76.1 Tube section which equals to almost 4.08. For the X and V systems, the ductility reduction factor is equal to 2.7 and 3.1 respectively.

C. Pushover Results for Steel Caging Technique

Figure 7 shows the lateral response of the structure frame with retrofitting with steel caging of the horizontal and vertical bays. The results show that whatever the reinforcement of the structures, whether horizontal or vertical, the ductility is almost identical to the RPA frame, but the lateral capacity is increased by 27.3% in comparison with the original frame. Meanwhile, the results indicate that the lateral capacity with vertical reinforcement gives a smaller increase than the horizontal reinforcement.

Fig. 6. Lateral load-displacement response retrofitting with different steel bracing systems.

Fig. 7. Lateral load-displacement response retrofitting with steel caging technique.

D. Pushover Results for Retrofitting with Steel Bracing and Steel Caging

Figure 8 represents the lateral response of the structure frame with retrofitting of the vertical bays with steel caging and the different bracing systems (X, V, and Zipper) at the same time.

Fig. 8. Lateral load-displacement response retrofitting with steel bracing system and steel caging.

It is clear from Figure 8 that the base shear was increased by 100% compared to the reinforcement with the steel bracing system only. The V and Zipper system with the steel caging technique give almost the same curves as the RPA frame. The results show that the section of D76.1 \times 3.2 for all the bracing

systems gives a behavior close to the RPA frame with reference to the lateral load. Compared to the original frame, for the retrofitting with the 76.1 Tube section, the capacity of Zipper, X, and V systems is increased by a factor 2.5, 3.02, and 2.4 respectively. The highest ductility reduction factor is given by the V system with the 76.1 Tube section which equals almost to 8.25. For the Zipper and the X systems, the ductility reduction factor is equal to 6.03 and 4.1 respectively.

V. CONCLUSION

The main purpose of this research is the retrofitting of an RC frame that has been designed without seismic design criteria, and is located in a region of high seismicity. In the present work, the retrofitting of this structure was done by three techniques, namely the steel bracing system, the steel caging technique, and the combination of these two methods. The main results of the present work can be summarized as follows:

- The results show that all systems have a given ductility for a small section and when there is an increase in the section of the bracing the ductility is decreased and the strength is increased. The behavior of different systems is much stiffer.
- Whatever the reinforcement of the structures, whether horizontal or vertical, the ductility is almost identical to the RPA frame.
- Retrofitting with Zipper and V systems in combination with steel caging gives similar results to the RPA model.
- The models with steel bracing and steel caging are good for predicting damage in the nonlinear analysis of RC structures.

Therefore, retrofitting for RC frames with a combination technique should take into account the two demand measures, MIDR and MID, particularly under NFD-HR and NFFS earthquakes.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Sekiguchi, T. Okada, M. Murakami, F. Kumazawa, F. Horie, and M. Seki, "Seismic Strengthening of An Existing Steel Reinforced Concrete City Office Building," in *9th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, Tokyo, Japan, Aug. 1988, vol. VII, pp. 439–444.
- [2] M. Badoux and J. O. Jirsa, "Steel Bracing of RC Frames for Seismic Retrofitting," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 116, no. 1, pp. 55–74, Jan. 1990, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(1990\)116:1\(55\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(1990)116:1(55)).
- [3] T. D. Bush, E. A. Jones, and J. O. Jirsa, "Behavior of RC Frame Strengthened Using Structural Steel Bracing," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 117, no. 4, pp. 1115–1126, Apr. 1991, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(1991\)117:4\(1115\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(1991)117:4(1115)).
- [4] M. R. Maheri, R. Kousari, and M. Razazan, "Pushover tests on steel X-braced and knee-braced RC frames," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 25, no. 13, pp. 1697–1705, Nov. 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296\(03\)00150-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296(03)00150-0).
- [5] A. Kadid and D. Yahiaoui, "Seismic Assessment of Braced RC Frames," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 14, pp. 2899–2905, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2011.07.365>.
- [6] A. Benavent-Climent and S. Mota-Paez, "Earthquake retrofitting of R/C frames with soft first story using hysteretic dampers: Energy-based design method and evaluation," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 137, pp. 19–32, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2017.01.053>.
- [7] A. Rahimi and M. R. Maheri, "The effects of retrofitting RC frames by X-bracing on the seismic performance of columns," *Engineering*

- Structures, vol. 173, pp. 813–830, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2018.07.003>.
- [8] A. Rahimi and M. R. Maheri, "The effects of steel X-brace retrofitting of RC frames on the seismic performance of frames and their elements," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 206, Mar. 2020, Art. no. 110149, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2019.110149>.
- [9] M. N. Eldin, A. J. Dereje, and J. Kim, "Seismic retrofit of RC buildings using self-centering PC frames with friction-dampers," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 208, Apr. 2020, Art. no. 109925, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2019.109925>.
- [10] M. Noureldin, S. A. Memon, M. Gharagoz, and J. Kim, "Performance-based seismic retrofit of RC structures using concentric braced frames equipped with friction dampers and disc springs," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 243, Sep. 2021, Art. no. 112555, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2021.112555>.
- [11] H. Sezen and E. A. Miller, "Experimental Evaluation of Axial Behavior of Strengthened Circular Reinforced-Concrete Columns," *Journal of Bridge Engineering*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 238–247, Mar. 2011, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)BE.1943-5592.0000143](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)BE.1943-5592.0000143).
- [12] M. Saadi, D. Yahiaoui, N. Lahbari, and B. Tayeb, "Seismic Fragility Curves for Performance of Semi-rigid Connections of Steel Frames," *Civil Engineering Journal*, vol. 7, no. 7, pp. 1112–1124, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-2021-03091714>.
- [13] Y. H. Chai, M. J. N. Priestley, and F. Seible, "Seismic Retrofit of Circular Bridge Columns for Enhanced Flexural Performance," *Structural Journal*, vol. 88, no. 5, pp. 572–584, Sep. 1991, <https://doi.org/10.14359/2759>.
- [14] Y. H. Chai, "An Analysis of the Seismic Characteristics of Steel-Jacketed Circular Bridge Columns," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 149–161, 1996, [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-9845\(199602\)25:2<149::AID-EQE543>3.0.CO;2-W](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-9845(199602)25:2<149::AID-EQE543>3.0.CO;2-W).
- [15] M. J. N. Priestley, F. Seible, Y. Xiao, and R. Verma, "Steel Jacket Retrofitting of Reinforced Concrete Bridge Columns for Enhanced Shear Strength-Part 1: Theoretical Considerations and Test Design," *Structural Journal*, vol. 91, no. 4, pp. 394–405, Jul. 1994, <https://doi.org/10.14359/9885>.
- [16] M. J. N. Priestley, F. Seible, Y. Xiao, and an dRavindra Verma, "Steel Jacket Retrofitting of Reinforced Concrete Bridge Columns for Enhanced Shear Strength--Part 2: Test Results and Comparison With Theory," *Structural Journal*, vol. 91, no. 5, pp. 537–551, Sep. 1994, <https://doi.org/10.14359/4168>.
- [17] R. S. Aboutaha, M. D. Engelhardt, J. O. Jirsa, and M. E. Kreger, "Rehabilitation of shear critical concrete columns by use of rectangular steel jackets," *ACI Structural Journal*, vol. 96, no. 1, pp. 68–78, Jan. 1999.
- [18] Y. Xiao and R. Ma, "Seismic Retrofit of RC Circular Columns Using Prefabricated Composite Jacketing," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 123, no. 10, pp. 1357–1364, Oct. 1997, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(1997\)123:10\(1357\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(1997)123:10(1357)).
- [19] Y. Xiao and H. Wu, "Retrofit of Reinforced Concrete Columns Using Partially Stiffened Steel Jackets," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 129, no. 6, pp. 725–732, Jun. 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(2003\)129:6\(725\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(2003)129:6(725)).
- [20] F. Di Trapani, A. P. Sberna, and G. C. Marano, "A new genetic algorithm-based framework for optimized design of steel-jacketing retrofitting in shear-critical and ductility-critical RC frame structures," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 243, Sep. 2021, Art. no. 112684, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2021.112684>.
- [21] J. M. Adam, S. Ivorra, F. J. Pallares, E. Gimenez, and P. A. Calderon, "Axially loaded RC columns strengthened by steel caging. Finite element modelling," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 2265–2276, Jun. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2008.11.014>.
- [22] M. F. Belal, H. M. Mohamed, and S. A. Morad, "Behavior of reinforced concrete columns strengthened by steel jacket," *HBRC Journal*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 201–212, Aug. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hbrj.2014.05.002>.
- [23] F. Di Trapani, M. Malavisi, G. C. Marano, A. P. Sberna, and R. Greco, "Optimal seismic retrofitting of reinforced concrete buildings by steel-jacketing using a genetic algorithm-based framework," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 219, Sep. 2020, Art. no. 110864, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2020.110864>.
- [24] P. H. Sarjou and N. Shabakhty, "Effect of the Improved Pall Friction Damper on the Seismic Response of Steel Frames," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1833–1837, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1176>.
- [25] H. Veladi and H. Najafi, "Effect of Standard No. 2800 Rules for Moment Resisting Frames on the Elastic and Inelastic Behavior of Dual Steel Systems," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2139–2146, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1040>.
- [26] Y. Almoosi and N. Oukaili, "The Response of a Highly Skewed Steel I-Girder Bridge with Different Cross-Frame Connections," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7349–7357, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4137>.
- [27] H. A. Safarizki, S. A. Kristiawan, and A. Basuki, "Evaluation of the Use of Steel Bracing to Improve Seismic Performance of Reinforced Concrete Building," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 54, pp. 447–456, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2013.03.040>.
- [28] ASCE, *Prestandard and commentary for the seismic rehabilitation of buildings*. Washington DC, USA: FEMA, 2000.
- [29] Applied Technology Council, *FEMA P-695, Quantification of Building Seismic Performance Factors - Applied Technology Council Online Store*. Washington DC, USA: FEMA, 2008.
- [30] A. Kheyroddin, R. Sepahrad, M. Saljoughian, and M. A. Kafi, "Experimental evaluation of RC frames retrofitted by steel jacket, X-brace and X-brace having ductile ring as a structural fuse," *Journal of Building Pathology and Rehabilitation*, vol. 4, no. 1, Apr. 2019, Art. no. 11, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41024-019-0050-z>.
- [31] "09 DTR B C 2 48 RPA 2003," *calameo.com*. <https://www.calameo.com/books/000899869ad355520b3ae> (accessed Apr. 30, 2022).

Flash Flood Risk Assessment for Girne Region, Northern Cyprus

Youssef Kassem

Department of Mechanical Engineering
Engineering Faculty
Near East University
Nicosia, Cyprus
yousseuf.kassem@neu.edu.tr

Hüseyin Gökçekuş

Department of Civil Engineering
Civil and Environmental Engineering Faculty
Near East University
Nicosia, Cyprus
huseyin.gokcekus@neu.edu.tr

Nour Alijl

Department of Civil Engineering
Civil and Environmental Engineering Faculty
Near East University
Nicosia, Cyprus
nourshan2002@outlook.com

Received: 23 March 2022 | Revised: 12 April 2022 | Accepted: 30 April 2022

Abstract—Girne region is in the northern part of Northern Cyprus which is environmentally fragile and susceptible to natural disasters. Flash floods are a major problem in the region due to the heavy and torrential rainfalls in its urban environment. Therefore, this study aims to assess the flash flood risk for the Girne region, using the Geographic Information System (GIS). A mitigation flood risk plan is proposed and applied to the case study of the Girne region. The flood risk matrix is proposed based on the occurrence probability of the flood and the associated inundation depth. The risk matrix criterion was classified according to the degree of risks as high, moderate, and low. Five thematic maps affecting flood occurrences, including slope, elevation, land use, peak discharge, and flow accumulation, were classified to generate flood hazard maps. The results of the estimation of the magnitude of the inundation areas that can assess the degree of damage and its economic aspects are presented graphically. The developed flood risk matrix tool is a quantitative tool to assess damage and is essential for decision-makers.

Keywords- Flash flood, Girne, Northern Cyprus, GIS, flood risk matrix

I. INTRODUCTION

Floods may occur suddenly and be accompanied by other hazards such as landslides, mudflows, and damages to infrastructure [1, 2]. They occur due to the high intensity of rainfall within a shorter period [3]. The high-velocity runoff in small basins and the rapid rise of water and sediment transport have made flash floods extremely dangerous to infrastructure and human life. Flashfloods and used landslides have become major disasters worldwide [4]. In general, flash floods are the combined result of weather and geomorphological conditions [5-7]. Urban flooding is an essential issue globally due to its

frequent occurrence that leads to damage to infrastructure and loss of lives. Flash floods in an urban area are recognized by the relatively short period of ephemeral water flow, which rarely lasts more than a day [8]. Thus, understanding the nature and the characteristics of flooding is one of the main goals of flood risk management. At present, flood maps are a potentially valuable tool for improving this understanding, but some drawbacks regarding the use of flood maps to mitigate flood risk and identify prone areas have been highlighted in the literature [9]. Anyhow, flood maps help to identify the most sensitive zones for civil protective actions, assess damages and make valid urban planning [8].

In Northern Cyprus, the coastal regions Girne (Kyrenia), Gazimağusa (Famagusta), and Güzelyurt (Morphou) are highly susceptible to urban flooding. During the recent years, heavy rain and thunderstorms affected over 3000 people, inflicting damages to the road network and the partial closure of a freeway in the Girne region [10-13]. This study aims to present a flood risk mitigation plan and a flood risk matrix technique for assessing risks in the urban Girne region of Northern Cyprus. The study focuses on the evaluation of the magnitude of the inundation areas and can assess the degree of damage from flash floods in the region for different frequencies of HEC-HMS hydrologic and 2D HEC-RAS hydraulic modeling techniques in order to delineate the inundation area at different degrees of flood hazards. To the best of our knowledge, there are no detailed studies in the Girne region regarding flash flood risk assessment.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The proposed methodology aims to present a framework developed for flood modeling on regional scale combining GIS with a rainfall-runoff model (HEC-HMS) and a hydrologic

model (HEC-RAS). Figure 1 illustrates the methodology used in this study.

Fig. 1. The flowchart of the proposed methodology.

A. Study Area

Girne region is located in the northwest of Northern Cyprus at 35.2992° N latitude and 33.2363° E longitude as shown in Figure 2(a).

Fig. 2. The geographical location of Girne, Northern Cyprus: (a) Location, (b) elevation, (c) slopes.

It is surrounded by the Five Fingers mountain (Beşparmak), where elevations range from -2 to 1026m above sea level (Figure 2(b)), which has a major impact on defining the weather on the island. Slopes range from 0 % to 20% as shown in Figure 2(c). Rainfall distribution over the country varies considerably among regions. The minimum and maximum average values of rainfall in Mesaoria are 300 and 400mm whereas they are 400 and 450mm in the Karpas Peninsula area. Snow is rarely occurring on the upper hills of the Beşparmak Mountains in the North and is usually present at the peaks of the Troodos Mountains in South Cyprus throughout the year. The maximum snowfall over the Northern part of Cyprus in the last ten years (1992-2002) was measured to be 15cm on Beşparmak, Selvili Tepe, and Katara hills. Additionally, temperatures ranged from 21°C along the coast to 15°C on the top of the Girne. Maximum temperature can reach 45°C in the Mesaoria Plain. Moreover, there is no perennial stream in the Northern part of Cyprus. Twenty-eight streams located in the Northern part of Cyprus discharge about 27MCM of water annually [14]. Additionally, 10 ephemeral streams originating from the Troodos Mountain in the Southern part of Cyprus, discharge about 43MCM of water yearly [14]. Figure 3 shows the extracted channel networks and the flow connections from QGIS including dam locations.

Fig. 3. Channel network and sub-basins-QGIS.

B. Extracted Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and Hydrologic Analysis using QGIS and SAGA PLUG

Digital Elevation Model (DEM) data can be downloaded directly and are free for use from USGS earth explorer (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov>). The extracted 3D models of the earth's surface have cells that are represented as raster images in a pixel grid format. Each cell indicates the covered area's average elevation value. The model was improved by filling sinks and depressions locations with the Wang Liu algorithm. Catchments, Sub-Basins (SBs), flow accumulation, drainage sites, and flow directions will be used as input for runoff simulation after implementing spatial and hydrological analysis tools such as Quantum GIS (QGIS) and saga plug.

C. The Wang Liu Method

Virtually, all DEMs contain flat areas or depression pixels that may be actual landscape representations of artifacts. These features must be handled before any further hydrological analysis can be conducted [15]. Various algorithms have been developed for correcting these aspects, differing in how they handle the nature of the depressions. The Wang Liu method was utilized to fill sinks and depression areas in the extracted

DEM, and preserve the downward slope along the flow path, in addition, to enhancing hydrological analysis for surface elevations [15].

D. Rainfall Data and Return Period Analysis

The data have been collected from the Meteorological Department located in Lefkoşa, Northern Cyprus for a period from 1995 to 2015. Figure 4 shows the total amount of rainfall each year. The maximum and minimum values of total rainfall were recorded in 2012 and 2013 with a value of 593.86mm and 182.79mm respectively.

Fig. 4. Total amount of rainfall for the selected region.

Moreover, the estimation of the return period of high intensity of rainfall is particularly significant for many engineering elements including the construction of contour drains, dams, road culverts, airfield drainage, storm sewers in metropolitan areas, and flood or sediment control dams in water catchments. The measurement of the likely time interval between the occurrence of one event and the occurrence of a subsequent event of equal or larger magnitude is the return period. When a variable (X) equal to or higher than x occurs once every T years on average, then the probability of occurrence P is shown in (1) [16].

$$P = \frac{1}{T}(X \geq x) \text{ or } T = \frac{1}{P}(X \geq x) \quad (1)$$

Several approaches have been presented to establish the plotting position, which refers to the probability value assigned to each piece of data to be plotted. Equation (2) is the most plotted position formula [16]:

$$P = \frac{1}{T} = \frac{m-b}{n+1-2b} \quad (2)$$

where m is the rank value in a list ordered by descending magnitude, n is the total number of values to be plotted, and b is a parameter that varies by formula ($b=0.5$ for Hazen, $b=0.3$ for Chegodayev, $b=0$ for Weibull, $b=3/88$ for Blom, $b=1/3$ for Tukey, and $b = 0.44$ for Gringoten) [16].

E. Assessment of Land Use, Soil Characteristics, and Curve Number (CN)

Surface runoff is the excessive rainfall after evaporation and infiltration have been excluded. Based on exhaustive rainfall/runoff data variety of land cover conditions and soil characteristics (moistures, structures, textures, and

compactions), the method results in the establishment of a set of curves called Curve Number (CN). This empirical parameter is used in hydrology for predicting direct runoff or infiltration from rainfall excess. In general, soil groups are classified into four classes according to the Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS), which helps to identify land use classes and CN [17]. In this study, a virtual map (Figure 5) was prepared by utilizing spatial analysis tools in QGIS using Landsat-8 images, which were uploaded from USGS earth explorer dated on 20th of February 2020.

Fig. 5. Landsat-8 image -Girne/QGIS.

F. Rainfall-Runoff Simulation Model

Runoff simulation was done using HEC_HMS based on previous studies [18, 19] that utilized the software to assess flood impact and predict flows. The main elements to run simulation are: sub-basins, time-series data, control specifications, and metrological data. SCS CN was utilized to calculate the hydraulic loss rate. The 56 sub-basins were extracted using QGIS as shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Channel network and sub-basins-HEC-HMS.

G. Loss Method

Many methods have been utilized to simulate infiltration losses such as exponential, deficit and constant, initial and constant, Green and Ampt, Smith Parlange, and Soil Moisture Accounting- SMA SCS CN. The nominated method in this study is SCS CN which is used to determine the hydrologic loss rate. Equation (3) is used to calculate the runoff of the hydrographic basin:

$$Q = \frac{(P-0.2S)^2}{P+0.8S} \quad (3)$$

where Q is the surface runoff amount, P is the rainfall amount, and S is the potential maximum retention amount, which can be calculated by using the below function:

$$S = \left(\frac{25400}{CN} \right) - 254 \quad (4)$$

where *CN* is the curve number.

H. Transform Method

In previous studies, 7 methods have been employed to calculate the excess of precipitation to runoff: Mod-Clark, SCS unit hydrograph, user-specified graph, user-specified unit hydrograph), Snyder unit hydrograph, Clark unit hydrograph, and kinematic wave. The nominated method in this study was SCS unit hydrograph-based lag time calculated for each sub-basin. Lag time (*Tlag*) represents the length of time between the peak discharges of the centroid of precipitation mass and the peak discharges of the resulting hydrograph it depends on the time of concentration (*TC*) as explained in (5) and the time of concentration (*TC*) calculated by (6) [20]:

$$Tlag = 0.6 TC \quad (5)$$

$$TC = \frac{4 + \sqrt{H} + 1.5L}{0.8\sqrt{H}} \quad (6)$$

where *L* represents the length of the main channel in km, *H* represents the difference between the mean basin elevation and the outlet elevation in m.

I. Weighting of Parameters Which Influence Flood Events

Based on the literature review and the Delphi approach [21, 22], 5 parameters were considered and rated to assess flood risk: Flow accumulation (F), Peak discharge (P), Elevation (E), Land use (L), and Slope (using ArcGIS). Spatial tool analysis was utilized to develop numerical thematic maps for flood hazard maps that were georeferenced to EPSG Projection 6312 Cyprus coordinate system. Parameter rating was done by applying Jenk’s Natural Breaks method. The selected method classified Risk Levels (RLs) to 5 categories and assigned numerical values from 1 to 5: catastrophic RL = 5, severe RL = 4, major RL = 3, minor RL = 2, low RL = 1. Considering that the nominated parameters have different influences on flood generation. Correlation analysis was applied taking into consideration the influence of each factor on the other factors. Thus, two kinds of influence were utilized: major influence was assigned 1 point for the parameter bearing a direct influence on the remaining parameters, minor influence was assigned 1/2 point for first parameter bearing an indirect influence on the other parameters. The calculated rate is summarized in Table I.

TABLE I. INTERACTION BETWEEN FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE FLOOD RISK (FACTOR RATES)

Factor changing	Major effect	Minor effect	Factor rate
Flow accumulation (F)	(L)	(S)	1.5 points (1major + 1minor)
Slope (S)	(F), (L)		2.0 points (2major + 0minor)
Land use (L)	(F), (P)	(S)	2.5 points (2major + 1minor)
Peak discharge (P)	(F), (E)	(L)	2.5 points (2major + 1minor)
Elevation (E)	(R), (L), (F)	(S)	3.5 points (3major + 1minor)

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the extracted factors, hazard and inundation prone areas with a high risk of flooding can be identified and to be used for risk matrix identification and quantitative analysis. Five thematic maps were developed and classified based on the selected method.

A. Catchment Area and Flow Delineation

The catchment consists of 56 sub-catchments with a total area of about 640km². The geometric and morphological parameters of the sub-catchment were used as main inputs to simulate runoff by utilizing the HEC-HMS model to calculate an excess of precipitation and peak discharge. Also, by utilizing the SCS method, *TC* and *Tlag* were calculated. As shown in Figure 7, the highest values for *TC*, and *Tlag* were found to be 229.39min and 137.64min respectively for sub-basin 10 and the minimum values were recorded for sub-basin 25 with a value of 48.25min and 28.90min respectively. This variation occurred due to the variance of elevation difference, stream length, and other morphological parameters influencing the estimation of the time of concentration.

Fig. 7. Calculated values for time lag and time of concentrations.

B. Land Use - Land Cover and Curve Number Estimation

Remote sensing techniques were employed to classify Land Use and Land Cover (LULC). Girne LULC was extracted from the high-resolution Landsat-8 rasters, by utilizing spatial tool analysis in ArcGIS and maximum likelihood classifications based on NVDI. Five categories (road, woods, urban areas, vegetation, and pasture) were employed to calculate the *CN* in Figure 8. The maximum value of *CN* was 86.64 for sub-basin 1 which consists of 85% pasture area and the minimum value

was 82.52 for sub-basin 35 which consists of 65% wood area and 30% building area.

Fig. 8. Computed composite SCS-CN for the sub-basins.

C. Return Period Analysis

Six different methods were employed to calculate the design period for the annual maximum rainfall for the Girne region. As a result, the return design period of infrastructure hydraulic design is less than or equal to the recorded period data. The estimation of quintiles using empirical distribution functions or plotting point methods was followed. The return period of the 40.14mm event was 23 and 44 years, based on plotting points applied by the Hazen and Weibull methods respectively. The rainfall depth is estimated and summarized in Table II.

TABLE II. DESIGN RAINFALL FOR THE STUDY AREA

Design period	5 Years	10 Years	25 Years	50 Years	100 Years	200 Years
Rainfall	32.46	39.03	47.71	54.28	60.85	67.41

D. Rainfall-Runoff Simulation

In this study, the selected region is within ungagged catchments, and no runoff records were available. A Synthetic Unit Hydrograph (SUH) was utilized to calculate direct runoff and excess rainfall by using HEC-HMS. The main parameters in the utilized model are hydrological data and sub-catchment physical features. Computed runoff characteristics in terms of Peak Discharge (PD) value and Runoff Volume (RV) are summarized in Table III for various design periods. For example, it is found that the maximum value of PD was 15.3cu.m/s for sub-basin 23 with a total area of 41.40km², while the maximum RV was recorded for sub-basin 1 with a value of 381.68mm³ for the selected design period with 2001 as the base year. It should be noted that the output from the model would be used as input for the hydraulic model.

E. Parameter Weighting and Map Classifications

Table IV lists the classification of the nominated factors into hazard levels. The calculated percentage of each parameter was found by multiplying the proposed weight of effect with the rate. In general, the hazardous area cannot be estimated by considering the effect of each factor independently. The integration of all factors is necessary to obtain the overall map of flood-hazard areas. Since not all factors have the same

degree of influence on the hazardous areas, the weighting approach was applied. The selected parameters have the most substantial impact on flood risk based on their rate and weight, taking into consideration the cross-pollination between parameters. In this study, the ratings for the hazard levels (expert judgment), in points, which are illustrated in Table IV are: Catastrophic = 5, Major = 4, Moderate = 3, Minor = 2, Low = 1. It should be noted these observations are supported by previous works [23, 24]. Moreover, the thematic maps were generated by utilizing GIS tools as shown in Figures 9 and 10. In this study, the high-risk areas are shown in blue colors such as Akdeniz, Grine, karakum, Geçitköy, Cape Kormakitis, and Karaođlanođlu with slopes less than 3.6% and elevations less than 129m. While the slope and higher elevation had minimal impact on the flood risk, the low-risk areas were shown in red color for the Five Fingers mountain (Beşparmak).

Fig. 9. Slope thematic map classification.

Fig. 10. Elevation thematic map classification.

Fig. 11. Land use thematic map classification.

Additionally, a land-use/land cover map was extracted from the land sat-8 image. Land-use/land cover factor which influences the flood risk impact where the vegetation cover exists will reduce flood risk impact by controlling surface runoff when reaching the soil, while without vegetation cover in an urban area it will increase the flood risk as shown in Figure 11. This outcome is in accordance with the results of [23].

Peak discharge values were determined by utilizing runoff simulations and a thematic map (Figure 11) was generated by utilizing IDW (Inverse Distance Weighting) tool in GIS. Finally, the flow accumulation thematic map was extracted as

shown in Figure 12. It is observed that sub-basins 4 and 2 have higher risk levels (i.e. blue color represents the high value of flow accumulation).

TABLE III. PEAK DISCHARGE AND RUNOFF VOLUME

SB number	Area [km]	Base year 2001		5 years		10 years		25 years		50 years		100 years		200 years	
		PD [cu.m/s]	RV [mm]	PD [cu.m/s]	RV [mm]	PD [cu.m/s]	RV [mm]	PD [cu.m/s]	RV [mm]	PD [cu.m/s]	RV [mm]	PD [cu.m/s]	RV [mm]	PD [cu.m/s]	RV [mm]
Sb1	4.89	1.80	381.68	1.50	374.07	1.80	380.58	2.10	389.20	2.40	395.72	2.70	402.24	3.00	408.77
Sb2	4.84	1.80	372.67	1.50	365.08	1.70	371.58	2.10	380.17	2.40	386.67	2.60	393.17	2.90	399.67
Sb3	15.85	5.90	371.15	4.80	363.57	5.70	370.06	6.90	378.65	7.70	385.14	8.60	391.64	9.50	398.14
Sb4	27.87	10.30	371.95	8.50	364.36	10.00	370.86	12.10	379.44	13.60	385.94	15.20	392.44	16.70	398.94
Sb5	20.74	7.70	370.57	6.30	363.00	7.50	369.49	9.00	378.07	10.10	384.56	11.30	391.06	12.40	397.55
Sb6	12.72	4.70	368.69	3.90	361.11	4.60	367.60	5.50	376.17	6.20	382.66	6.90	389.15	7.60	395.65
Sb7	7.90	2.90	368.69	2.40	361.11	2.80	367.60	3.40	376.17	3.80	382.66	4.30	389.15	4.70	395.65
Sb8	12.36	4.60	374.10	3.80	366.51	4.50	373.01	5.40	381.61	6.10	388.11	6.70	394.61	7.40	401.12
Sb9	19.27	7.10	375.17	5.90	367.58	7.00	374.08	8.40	382.68	9.40	389.19	10.50	395.69	11.60	402.20
Sb10	19.65	7.30	376.24	6.00	368.65	7.10	375.15	8.60	383.75	9.60	390.26	10.70	396.77	11.80	403.28
Sb11	5.78	2.10	373.03	1.80	365.44	2.10	371.94	2.50	380.53	2.80	387.03	3.10	393.53	3.50	400.03
Sb12	13.63	5.00	370.50	4.20	362.92	4.90	369.41	5.90	377.99	6.70	384.49	7.40	390.98	8.20	397.48
Sb13	10.42	3.90	371.30	3.20	363.72	3.80	370.21	4.50	378.79	5.10	385.29	5.70	391.79	6.20	398.29
Sb14	24.55	9.10	371.87	7.50	364.29	8.90	370.78	10.60	379.37	12.00	385.87	13.40	392.37	14.70	398.87
Sb15	12.60	4.70	374.10	3.90	366.51	4.60	373.01	5.50	381.61	6.20	388.11	6.90	394.61	7.60	401.12
Sb16	29.69	11.00	371.51	9.10	363.93	10.70	370.42	12.90	379.01	14.50	385.51	16.20	392.00	17.80	398.50
Sb17	22.76	8.40	372.31	7.00	364.72	8.20	371.22	9.90	379.80	11.10	386.30	12.40	392.80	13.70	399.31
Sb18	15.88	5.90	371.51	4.80	363.93	5.70	370.42	6.90	379.01	7.80	385.51	8.60	392.00	9.50	398.50
Sb19	13.95	5.20	371.87	4.30	364.29	5.00	370.78	6.00	379.37	6.80	385.87	7.60	392.37	8.40	398.87
Sb20	9.20	3.40	370.57	2.80	363.00	3.30	369.49	4.00	378.07	4.50	384.56	5.00	391.06	5.50	397.55
Sb21	7.55	2.80	371.22	2.30	363.64	2.70	370.14	3.30	378.72	3.70	385.22	4.10	391.71	4.50	398.21
Sb22	7.01	2.60	373.74	2.10	366.16	2.50	372.65	3.00	381.25	3.40	387.75	3.80	394.25	4.20	400.76
Sb23	41.41	15.30	371.51	12.60	363.93	14.90	370.42	17.90	379.01	20.20	385.51	22.50	392.00	24.80	398.50
Sb24	7.62	2.80	368.32	2.30	360.75	2.70	367.23	3.30	375.81	3.70	382.30	4.10	388.79	4.60	395.28
Sb25	6.14	2.30	367.96	1.90	360.39	2.20	366.87	2.70	375.44	3.00	381.93	3.30	388.42	3.70	394.91
Sb26	7.27	2.70	368.32	2.20	360.75	2.60	367.23	3.10	375.81	3.50	382.30	3.90	388.79	4.30	395.28
Sb27	8.14	3.00	368.69	2.50	361.11	2.90	367.60	3.50	376.17	4.00	382.66	4.40	389.15	4.90	395.65
Sb28	9.19	3.40	368.18	2.80	360.61	3.30	367.09	4.00	375.66	4.50	382.15	5.00	388.64	5.50	395.13
Sb29	8.67	3.20	370.07	2.60	362.49	3.10	368.98	3.80	377.56	4.20	384.05	4.70	390.55	5.20	397.04
Sb30	11.29	4.20	371.22	3.40	363.64	4.10	370.14	4.90	378.72	5.50	385.22	6.10	391.71	6.80	398.21
Sb31	8.44	3.10	368.32	2.60	360.75	3.00	367.23	3.60	375.81	4.10	382.30	4.60	388.79	5.00	395.28
Sb32	7.12	2.60	368.69	2.20	361.11	2.60	367.60	3.10	376.17	3.50	382.66	3.90	389.15	4.30	395.65
Sb33	6.10	2.20	368.69	1.90	361.11	2.20	367.60	2.60	376.17	3.00	382.66	3.30	389.15	3.60	395.65
Sb34	12.27	4.50	369.05	3.70	361.48	4.40	367.96	5.30	376.54	6.00	383.03	6.70	389.52	7.30	396.01
Sb35	11.60	4.30	366.94	3.50	359.37	4.20	365.85	5.00	374.42	5.60	380.90	6.30	387.39	6.90	393.87
Sb36	3.73	1.40	369.27	1.10	361.69	1.30	368.18	1.60	376.76	1.80	383.25	2.00	389.74	2.20	396.23
Sb37	3.30	1.20	371.59	1.00	364.00	1.20	370.50	1.40	379.08	1.60	385.58	1.80	392.08	2.00	398.58
Sb38	8.73	3.20	368.69	2.70	361.11	3.10	367.60	3.80	376.17	4.30	382.66	4.70	389.15	5.20	395.65
Sb39	17.28	6.40	368.32	5.30	360.75	6.20	367.23	7.50	375.81	8.40	382.30	9.40	388.79	10.30	395.28
Sb40	14.51	5.30	367.96	4.40	360.39	5.20	366.87	6.30	375.44	7.10	381.93	7.90	388.42	8.70	394.91
Sb41	2.83	1.00	367.96	0.90	360.39	1.00	366.87	1.20	375.44	1.40	381.93	1.50	388.42	1.70	394.91
Sb42	6.28	2.30	369.41	1.90	361.84	2.30	368.33	2.70	376.90	3.10	383.39	3.40	389.89	3.80	396.38
Sb43	7.48	2.80	367.30	2.30	359.73	2.70	366.21	3.20	374.78	3.60	381.27	4.10	387.75	4.50	394.24
Sb44	7.93	2.90	368.32	2.40	360.75	2.80	367.23	3.40	375.81	3.90	382.30	4.30	388.79	4.30	388.79
Sb45	7.66	2.80	368.32	2.30	360.75	2.80	367.23	3.30	375.81	3.70	382.30	4.20	388.79	4.60	395.28
Sb46	3.76	1.40	367.96	1.10	360.39	1.40	366.87	1.60	375.44	1.80	381.93	2.00	388.42	2.20	394.91
Sb47	3.53	1.30	368.32	1.10	360.75	1.30	367.23	1.50	375.81	1.70	382.30	1.90	388.79	2.10	395.28
Sb49	4.22	1.60	368.69	1.30	361.11	1.50	367.60	1.80	376.17	2.10	382.66	2.30	389.15	2.50	395.65
Sb50	1.91	0.70	370.50	0.60	362.92	0.70	369.41	0.80	377.99	0.90	384.49	1.00	390.98	1.10	397.48
Sb51	3.61	1.30	369.05	1.10	361.48	1.30	367.96	1.60	376.54	1.80	383.03	2.00	389.52	2.20	396.01
Sb52	4.71	1.70	371.22	1.40	363.64	1.70	370.14	2.00	378.72	2.30	385.22	2.60	391.71	2.80	398.21
Sb53	16.22	6.00	368.32	4.90	360.75	5.80	367.23	7.00	375.81	7.90	382.30	8.80	388.79	9.70	395.28
Sb54	7.11	2.60	368.32	2.20	360.75	2.60	367.23	3.10	375.81	3.50	382.30	3.90	388.79	4.20	395.28
Sb55	11.59	4.30	368.69	3.50	361.11	4.20	367.60	5.00	376.17	5.60	382.66	6.30	389.15	6.90	395.65
Sb56	7.35	2.70	368.32	2.20	360.75	2.60	367.23	3.20	375.81	3.60	382.30	4.00	388.79	4.40	395.28

TABLE IV. CATEGORIZATION—CALIBRATION AND WEIGHT EVALUATION OF THE FACTORS AFFECTING FLOOD RISK AREAS IN GIRNE

Factors	Domain of effect	Descriptive level (flood risk level)	Proposed weight of effect (RL)	Rate (FR)	Weighted rating (FR*RL)	Total weight	Percentage
Slope	0-7.5	Catastrophic	5	2.0	10	30.0	17%
	7.5-15.0	Sever	4		8		
	15.0-25.0	Major	3		6		
	25.0-93.0	Minor	2		4		
	93.0 and above	Low	1		2		
Elevation	-5.0 - 129	Catastrophic	5	3.5	17.5	52.5	29%
	129.0 - 251.0	Sever	4		14		
	251 - 398	Major	3		10.5		
	398 - 603	Minor	2		7		
	603 - 1020	Low	1		3.5		
Land use (L)	Urban & bare area	Catastrophic	5	2.5	12.5	37.5	20%
	Scrub, annual crops	Sever	4		10		
	Permanent crops	Major	3		7.5		
	Pastures	Minor	2		5		
	Forest-woods	Low	1		2.5		
Flow accumulation (F)	27875 - 52789	Catastrophic	5	1.5	7.5	22.5	13%
	14087 - 27875	Sever	4		6		
	5798 - 14087	Major	3		4.5		
	1525 - 5798	Minor	2		3		
	0 - 1525	Low	1		1.5		
Peak discharge (P)	8.8 - 15.30	Catastrophic	5	1.5	12.5	37.5	21%
	6.4 - 8.8	Sever	4		10		
	4.5 - 6.4	Major	3		7.5		
	3.0 - 4.5	Minor	2		5		
	0.7 - 3.0	Low	1		2.5		

Fig. 12. Land use thematic map classification.

F. 2D Flood Mapping and Hydraulic Model using HEC-RAS

HEC-RAS was utilized to generate the hydraulic 2D flood mapping based on excessive precipitation and inflow hydrographs in unsteady flow conditions. The selected design periods were used to calculate Water Surface Elevation (WSE) and flow depth. For the next 5 years, the flood map predicts a maximum depth of 10.25m downstream and a minimum depth of 0.002m at high elevations, classifying the risk as catastrophic (the 25-year map is shown in Figure 13). A bit of water spreading over the mainstream and channel networks is shown while in the 50-year map more stream spreading were seen. For the 100- (Figure 14) and 200-year maps, the flood was significant and dominant. Other researchers who analyzed the inundation depth can support these observations. For instance, authors in [25] found that the flow depth for the low-risk area is less than 0.1m at the high elevation while 3m and above for high-risk areas mainly in major down streams.

Flood hazard maps, which were generated from the combined 5 thematics for different design periods were utilized to identify prone areas in the Girne region. In the context, lowlands, such as the Geçitköy located in the sub-basin 23 and

Akdeniz in the sub-basin 4, are most vulnerable to flood occurrence, and meanwhile, at the highest land areas, minor risk occurs at Five Fingers mountain, while catastrophic risk areas in blue color are spreading in major downstream areas in Geçitköy. As illustrated in Figures 15 and 16, the low-risk area decreased from 30.42km² to 13.45km² while the catastrophic event area increased from 0.006km² to 4.344km². The differences are due to changes in land use, urban and human activities, and climate change.

Fig. 13. 25 year design period flood inundation map.

Fig. 14. 100 year design period flood inundation map.

Fig. 15. Flash flood hazard map for the 25-year design period.

Fig. 16. Flash flood hazard map for the 100-year design period.

G. Risk Flood Matrix

The risk matrix (Figure 17) was established based on the likelihood of flow depth occurrence and its impact. A classified consequence (low, minor, major, severe, and catastrophic) is represented in a horizontal row, and the probability of occurrence of the return period in a vertical row. The degree of risk was determined by multiplying probability and impact, and the results were classified as low, medium, and high which are represented in green, yellow, and red, respectively.

		Potential Consequences of flow depth				
		<0.10 m	0.10-0.50	0.50-1.00	1.00-2.00	>2
		1	2	3	4	5
Likelihood of Occurrence	Almost certain (every time)	Low	Minor	Major	Sever	Catastrophic
	Likely (1-5 years)	Low	Minor	Major	Sever	Catastrophic
	Possible (5-50 years)	Low	Minor	Major	Sever	Catastrophic
	Unlikely (100 years)	Low	Minor	Major	Sever	Catastrophic
	Rare (100-200 year)	Low	Minor	Major	Sever	Catastrophic

Legend	
Red	High
Yellow	Medium
Green	Low

Fig. 17. Flood risk matrix.

Fig. 18. Proposed strategies.

H. Defining Strategies

The strategies are classified into two categories, namely vulnerable local community and structural strategies [26-28]. The vulnerable local community strategy aims to eliminate and

mitigate risk [27] due to the lack of response at an emergency. The structural strategy aims to control risk by reducing the impact of the flood. Figure 18 summarizes the classified straggles and examples for each category.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The current paper intends to propose an established framework for a flood risk mitigation plan (Figure 19), which comprises data collected from weather forecasting in partnership with the water development department and crisis services. Hydrological analysis and risk analysis were conducted and measures were recommended. Flood parameters were illustrated in thematic maps in GIS using the IDW method. Peak discharge for various design periods was estimated using runoff simulation HEC-HMS. Flow depth was estimated using the hydrologic model HEC-RAS. Land uses were extracted from Landsat images-08. Elevation and slopes were extracted from a DEM. Flood hazard and inundation thematic maps revealed that lowlands are the most vulnerable to flooding, whereas higher land areas are less vulnerable to flood risk. The obtained results will assist planners and decision-makers in identifying prone areas to take appropriate and timely steps during the pre-disaster period.

Fig. 19. Flood risk mitigation plan.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank the Faculty of Engineering, especially the Mechanical Engineering Department at Near East University for their support and encouragement.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. G. Collier, "Flash flood forecasting: What are the limits of predictability?," *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, vol. 133, no. 622, pp. 3–23, 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.29>.
- [2] A. A. Mahessar *et al.*, "Flash Flood Climatology in the Lower Region of Southern Sindh," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4474–4479, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2726>.
- [3] A. A. Sarker and A. K. M. M. Rashid, "Landslide and Flashflood in Bangladesh," in *Disaster Risk Reduction Approaches in Bangladesh*, R. Shaw, F. Mallick, and A. Islam, Eds. Tokyo, Japan: Springer Japan, 2013, pp. 165–189.
- [4] M. Špitalar, J. J. Gourley, C. Lutoff, P.-E. Kirstetter, M. Brilly, and N. Carr, "Analysis of flash flood parameters and human impacts in the US from 2006 to 2012," *Journal of Hydrology*, vol. 519, pp. 863–870, Nov. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2014.07.004>.
- [5] M. Abdel-Fattah, M. Saber, S. A. Kantouch, M. F. Khalil, T. Sumi, and A. M. Sefelnasr, "A Hydrological and Geomorphometric Approach to Understanding the Generation of Wadi Flash Floods," *Water*, vol. 9, no. 7, Jul. 2017, Art. no. 553, <https://doi.org/10.3390/w9070553>.
- [6] S. Bisht, S. Chaudhry, S. Sharma, and S. Soni, "Assessment of flash flood vulnerability zonation through Geospatial technique in high altitude Himalayan watershed, Himachal Pradesh India," *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, vol. 12, pp. 35–47, Nov. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsase.2018.09.001>.
- [7] P. K. Rai, R. S. Chandel, V. N. Mishra, and P. Singh, "Hydrological inferences through morphometric analysis of lower Kosi river basin of India for water resource management based on remote sensing data," *Applied Water Science*, vol. 8, no. 1, Jan. 2018, Art. no. 15, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-018-0660-7>.
- [8] T. L. Dammalage and N. T. Jayasinghe, "Land-Use Change and Its Impact on Urban Flooding: A Case Study on Colombo District Flood on May 2016," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 3887–3891, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2578>.
- [9] P. Costabile, C. Costanzo, G. De Lorenzo, R. De Santis, N. Penna, and F. Macchione, "Terrestrial and airborne laser scanning and 2-D modelling for 3-D flood hazard maps in urban areas: new opportunities and perspectives," *Environmental Modelling & Software*, vol. 135, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 104889, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2020.104889>.
- [10] "Flood in Cyprus," *UN-SPIDER Knowledge Portal*. <https://www.un-spider.org/advisory-support/emergency-support/3288/flood-cyprus>.
- [11] "Flooding Hits Kyrenia - Dam Overflows," *North Cyprus News*, Jan. 08, 2020. <https://lgnnews.com/flooding-hits-kyrenia-dam-overflows/>.
- [12] "Heavy Rain Floods Kyrenia," *North Cyprus News*, Nov. 03, 2017. <https://lgnnews.com/heavy-rain-floods-kyrenia/>.
- [13] "Cyprus – Flash Floods Leave 4 Dead," *FloodList*. <https://floodlist.com/europe/cyprus-flash-floods-december-2018>.
- [14] Y. Kassem, H. Gökçekuş, and T. Rizza, "Groundwater Quality Assessment Based on Water Quality Index in Northern Cyprus," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8435–8443, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4790>.
- [15] Y. Liu, H. Liu, L. Wang, M. Xu, S. Cohen, and K. Liu, "Derivation of spatially detailed lentic habitat map and inventory at a basin scale by integrating multispectral Sentinel-2 satellite imagery and USGS Digital Elevation Models," *Journal of Hydrology*, vol. 603, Dec. 2021, Art. no. 126876, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2021.126876>.
- [16] Y.-J. Wang, C.-Z. Qin, and A.-X. Zhu, "Review on algorithms of dealing with depressions in grid DEM," *Annals of GIS*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 83–97, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19475683.2019.1604571>.
- [17] J. Yuan, K. Emura, C. Farnham, and M. A. Alam, "Frequency analysis of annual maximum hourly precipitation and determination of best fit probability distribution for regions in Japan," *Urban Climate*, vol. 24, pp. 276–286, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2017.07.008>.
- [18] Natural Resources Conservation Service, *National Engineering Handbook Hydrology*. Washington DC, USA: United States Department of Agriculture, 2007.
- [19] W. Gumindoga, D. T. Rwasoka, I. Nhapi, and T. Dube, "Un gauged runoff simulation in Upper Manyame Catchment, Zimbabwe: Application of the HEC-HMS model," *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C*, vol. 100, pp. 371–382, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2016.05.002>.
- [20] W. A. Scharffenberg, "HEC-HMS User's Manual," US Army Corps of Engineers, HEC, Washington DC, USA, Dec. 2013.
- [21] M. Giandotti, "Previsione delle piene e delle magre dei corsi d'acqua," 1933.
- [22] J. Liu, Z. Xu, F. Chen, F. Chen, and L. Zhang, "Flood Hazard Mapping and Assessment on the Angkor World Heritage Site, Cambodia," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 11, no. 1, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 98, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11010098>.
- [23] N. Kazakis, I. Kougiass, and T. Patsialis, "Assessment of flood hazard areas at a regional scale using an index-based approach and Analytical Hierarchy Process: Application in Rhodope-Evros region, Greece," *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 538, pp. 555–563, Dec. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.08.055>.
- [24] N. N. Kourgialas and G. P. Karatzas, "Flood management and a GIS modelling method to assess flood-hazard areas—a case study," *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 212–225, Mar. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02626667.2011.555836>.

-
- [25] G. D. Bathrellos, H. D. Skilodimou, K. Soukis, and E. Koskeridou, "Temporal and Spatial Analysis of Flood Occurrences in the Drainage Basin of Pinos River (Thessaly, Central Greece)," *Land*, vol. 7, no. 3, Sep. 2018, Art. no. 106, <https://doi.org/10.3390/land7030106>.
- [26] Y. Zhang, Y. Wang, Y. Chen, F. Liang, and H. Liu, "Assessment of future flash flood inundations in coastal regions under climate change scenarios—A case study of Hadahe River basin in northeastern China," *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 693, Nov. 2019, Art. no. 133550, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.07.356>.
- [27] C. Samela, R. Albano, A. Sole, and S. Manfreda, "A GIS tool for cost-effective delineation of flood-prone areas," *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, vol. 70, pp. 43–52, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2018.01.013>.
- [28] "Guidance on Flash Flood Management Recent Experiences from Central and Eastern Europe," *CORE*, 2007. <https://core.ac.uk/display/22563624>.

An Improved Denoising Algorithm for Removing Noise in Color Images

Shaveta Rani

Department of Computer Science and Applications
CT University
Ludhiana, Punjab, India
shavetabawa@pau.edu

Yogesh Chhabra

Department of Electronics and Communications
CT University
Ludhiana, Punjab, India
yogeshfzr@gmail.com

Kamal Malik

Department of Computer Science and Engineering
CT University
Ludhiana, Punjab, India
kamal.malik91@gmail.com

Received: 27 March 2022 | Revised: 16 April 2022 and 22 April 2022 | Accepted: 30 April 2022

Abstract-Noise has a significant impact on image quality in a variety of applications, including machine vision and object recognition. Denoising is crucial for successful image processing since noisy pictures lead to erroneous findings and segmentation and enhancement mistakes. Existing methods were primarily developed for grayscale image denoising and are unable to detect all damaged pixels in an image effectively. This paper proposes a sequential ROAD-TGM-HT method to suppress impulsive noise in color image denoising. The noisy pixel location is detected using the consecutive method in the first step, and the distorted value of the damaged pixel is reconstructed in the second stage, followed by the Hough transform for the remaining undetected pixels. Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) were used to analyze the qualitative and quantitative performance. ROAD-TGM-HT excels on color images with noise levels ranging from 0.10 to 0.70, as per PSNR and SSIM qualitative data.

Keywords-salt and pepper noise; ROAD-TGM; PSNR; SSIM; de-noising; impulse noise; high-density noise

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital images are frequently influenced by many types of noise caused by a variety of factors. Data transfer of images via a noisy channel, defective storage positions in hardware, and defective pixels in camera sensors during capturing images are some of the most typical causes [1-3]. Image denoising is the act of eliminating noise from an image. The main goal of image denoising is to keep image structures such as features, borders, and textures intact. It is critical to eliminate all types of noise before analyzing an image, or else there is a risk of misunderstanding [4-5]. The efficiency of an image denoising procedure is determined by the amount of noise removed from the faulty image and the recovered pixel value's similarity to the source pixel. Important information, such as edge details, will not be maintained if the image denoising approach is

ineffective. During the last decades, experts have attempted to develop an effective and precise denoising technology that preserves crucial visual characteristics while reducing noise [6-8]. Various quantitative measures, such as the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Mean Square Error (MSE), and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), can be used to analyze the efficacy of a denoising algorithm [9-11]. Although other forms of noise alter visuals, impulse noise has the most impact. As a result, researchers concentrated on removing impulsive noise while preserving crucial information in the image [12]. In the field of image processing, the term "Salt and Pepper Noise" (SPN) is used to describe impulsive noise [13-14]. SPN occurs mostly during capture and transmission procedures. In this type of noise, certain pixels in a digital image have a maximum or minimum value. Image quality falls dramatically due to SPN.

Image denoising techniques are important to remove noise from an image. However, these approaches are often intended for grayscale images. To make these approaches functional on color images, an iterative process that can stream the components (Red, Green, and Blue) of a color image must be developed. Therefore, by dividing a color image into three components, a grayscale algorithm may be designed to work with them. Many different ways to eliminate the SPN noise from images have been presented but they don't work efficiently on color images. Considering the grayscale image, which has a single matrix with pixel intensity values ranging between 0-255, if a color image is split down into its three fundamental color components, each may be processed independently and then they can be merged to generate a colored image. Existing algorithms designed primarily for grayscale picture de-noising are unable to efficiently detect all damaged pixels in the image.

This paper proposes a composite ROAD-TGM-HT approach to remove noise from color images effectively. The

Corresponding author: Shaveta Rani

novelty of this method is that Rank-Ordered Absolute Differences with Trimmed Global Mean Filter (ROAD-TGM) has never been employed with Hough transform before. The MF [15-38], NAFSMF, DBUTMF, and ROAD-TGM were also used and their performance was compared. The performance of these approaches was evaluated using a dataset of color images with varying amounts of noise, varying from 10% to 70%.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A spatial filtering approach is typically employed to eliminate noise from damaged images. For denoising the image, spatial domain filters perform neighboring operations on the input image data. The numerous kinds of spatial domain filtering techniques [16-17] are Median Filter (MF) [18-36], Progressive Switching Median Filter (PSMF) [19], Center-Weighted Median Filter (CWMF) [20], Decision-Based Median Filter (DBMF) [21], Adaptive Median Filter (AMF) [22], Decision-Based Algorithm (DBA) [23], Noise Adaptive Fuzzy Switching Median Filter (NAFSMF) [24], Adaptive Weighted Mean Filter (AWMF) [25], Different Applied Median Filter (DAMF) [26], Decision Based Unsymmetric Trimmed Variant Filter (DBUTVF) [39], Modified Decision Based Unsymmetrical Trimmed Median Filter (MDBUTMF) [27], and Rank-Ordered Absolute Differences with Trimmed Global Mean Filter (ROAD-TGM) [28-29]. The Median Filter [38] performs noise filtering by replacing the median of the neighboring pixels with the value of the contaminated pixels. MF's main shortcoming is that it is only effective at very low noise levels, ranging between 10-40% noise density [30]. MF [37] typically requires a bigger window size at high noise levels and may not retain critical image information. PSMF [19] is a better version of the median filter. An impulse detector is first used to create a series of binary flag images. The position of noise is predicted by the binary flag image. An iterative approach is used to reduce image noise. The performance of this filter is low on random-valued noise, but it performs admirably for fixed-valued noise [31]. CWMF assigns a higher weight to the center values of each window, allowing key information to be preserved while noise is removed from the images [31-32]. CWMF outperforms simple MF and keeps its performance throughout a wide range of noise densities. Its execution depends on the median weight [33]. DBMF detects the existence of impulse noise among the pixels and processes the damaged image [34]. A pixel is deemed uncorrupted if its value is between 1 and 254. If the value does not fall within this range, the pixel is considered corrupted, and its value is set to the median of the neighboring pixels in the provided window. The biggest drawback of DBMF is the possibility of streaking, which happens when the image is damaged by high-density noise. In this scenario, the noisy pixel is changed by a similarly disruptive neighboring pixel value. As a result, this approach is unable to retrieve edge details adequately in large noise densities.

AMF [22] was created to address the flows of MF. Its goal is to use a dynamic adaptable window, by gradually expanding its size until the adaptive requirements are fulfilled. The window size must be sufficient to tolerate high-density noise. As a result of this, the filter's reliability and response time are

both harmed. DBA was proposed in [23] as a speedy selective median filter to reduce noise at higher densities. The median of the uncorrupted pixels was used to restore the corrupted pixels in a 3×3 selective window. DBA substitutes corrupted pixels with the earlier processed uncorrupted pixel when no uncorrupted pixel is detected in the filter window. However, DBA has the disadvantage of generating stripes in the restored images. MDBUTMF [27] was introduced as a further refinement of the previous approaches by employing the mean of the 3×3 filter to substitute corrupted pixels when no uncorrupted pixels can be detected. Although MDBUTMF eliminates the striped effect, it does not demonstrate a substantial increase in image restoration at higher noise levels. AWMF [25] employs an approach to determine if a pixel is uncorrupted by comparing its intensity with the range between the filtering window with minimum and maximum noise intensities. The mean of the uncorrupted pixels in the filtering window is used as a substitute for the identified corrupted pixels. If no uncorrupted pixels are detected in the filtering window, the filtering window is enlarged in size. AWMF takes longer to process due to its adaptive nature. NAFSMF [24] uses a dynamic adaptive window. A fuzzy decision-making approach determines a new value for NAFSMF. NAFSMF is also effective in suppressing high-density noise. DAMF [26] is capable of handling all impulse noise densities. The ROAD-TGM method employs a trimmed global mean filter with rank-ordered absolute differences [35] and is processed in two phases. In the first stage, ROAD is used to determine noisy pixels. The noisy pixels are transformed to the median of the non-noisy pixels inside a chosen window in the second stage. When the chosen window only includes corrupted pixels, the TGM filter is employed. This method employs a fixed-size window in both the filtering and detection stages. When recovering images impacted by random-valued impulse noise, its denoising performance outperforms other known methods. When images are distorted by high amounts of impulse noise, the ROAD-TGM algorithm delivers effective noise filtering.

These methods work in two stages: (i) detecting noisy pixels and (ii) restoring them. However, it has been observed that certainly damaged pixels aren't picked during the identification stage and remain corrupted. This study employed the Hough transform to find the remaining pixels. The proposed method uses ROAD and TGM to identify damaged pixels and the Hough transform which forms lines on a denoised image and fills those pixels by calculating the mean of the uncorrupted pixels.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

A 5×5 detection window (W) centered on $I(i, j)$ was implemented on the damaged image. In [40], a 3×3 window with $m = 4$ is recommended for less than 25% noise density, otherwise, a 5×5 window with $m = 12$ is recommended. Increasing the filter size causes blurring. The following equation is used to calculate the absolute difference (D) of all pixel values with the center pixel:

$$D = |W(i + k, j + l) - W(i, j)|, -LD \leq k, l \leq LD \quad (1)$$

The sum of the twelve lowest absolute differences is computed after sorting the array D . This produces the ROAD value for the current pixel as:

$$ROAD_m(x) = \sum_{i=1}^m ri(x) \quad (2)$$

The current pixel's ROAD value is compared to a specified threshold value. The current pixel is considered damaged or uncontaminated based on the threshold value. Threshold values affect the performance of noise detection. As the threshold value raises, an increasing number of noise-free pixels are left unfiltered. The filtering is conducted solely on noisy pixels at a specific threshold value, which is referred to as ideal. The noise-removing effectiveness of filtering is reduced when the threshold is increased further because the filtering is not applied to certain noisy pixels. When set to the ideal threshold setting, the filter successfully maintains tiny lines and other fine details. For the best results, the threshold value for all images was set at 40, but this value can change depending on the dataset. The foregoing processes are repeated for the complete image, resulting in a binary image (I) of size $M \times N$.

$$A = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{For } ROAD(i,j) < T1 \\ 0 & \text{For } ROAD(i,j) > T1 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The noiseless pixels in the specified window are used to replace the deteriorated pixels. A trimmed global mean filter is used if the chosen window contains only noise-impacted pixels. The TGM is then computed once the noise has been removed. The pixels from the window and the mean of the uncorrupted pixels are acquired to replace the value of a noisy pixel. The proposed method used ROAD and TGM to identify damaged pixels at first and then uses the Hough Transform to fill the remaining pixels not captured by ROAD-TGM. The Hough transform creates lines between the corrupted pixels on a denoised image, calculates the mean of the denoised image after creating lines, and fills those pixels with the mean of the uncorrupted pixels. Figure 2 represents the flow diagram of the restoration process. Various images from the USC dataset [41] of standard color images were used for simulation, as shown in Figure 1. All images were 512×512 in tiff format, with intentionally added noise ranging from 0.10 to 0.70.

Fig. 1. Original images: (a) Hut, (b) Female, (c) Zelda, (d) Baboon.

Fig. 2. Flowchart representing the proposed method for restoration.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tests were performed using MATLAB R2007b. Image Quality Assessment Metrics, such as MSE and PSNR, were used to evaluate the performance of the image denoising algorithms by measuring the quality of the processed image in contrast to the original. PSNR, which is expressed in decibels (dB) and is calculated as the ratio of a signal's maximum achievable power to the disruptive noise power. Higher PSNR indicates a greater performance, and the lower the PSNR value, the worse the performance of a denoising method. Equations (4) and (5) were used to calculate PSNR and MSE:

$$PSNR \text{ (dB)} = 10 * \log_{10} ((255 \times 255)/MSE) \quad (4)$$

$$MSE = \frac{1}{P \times Q} \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^q (I_d(i, j) - I_o(i, j))^2 \quad (5)$$

where $I_o(i, j)$ with size $P \times Q$, $I_d(i, j)$ represents the denoised image created by the denoising algorithm.

SSIM measures the loss of image quality due to activities such as data transfer and compression. SSIM [45] is used to assess the perceived quality of digital movies and images. It is a complete reference measure that is calculated using two images: the reference image is the original and the resultant image is the second. SSIM calculates the brightness (b), contrast (c), and structure (s) of x and y images, as:

$$SSIM(x; y) = [b(x; y)]^\alpha [c(x; y)]^\beta [s(x; y)]^\gamma \quad (6)$$

This section compares the proposed method to current algorithms for assessment. As previously stated, multiple noise densities were progressively applied to each image, ranging from 20% to 70% noise level, resulting in sequences of the increasingly distorted image with impulsive noise. The PSNR graph is shown in Figure 3 for the Baboon, Female, Hut, and Zelda images. Figures 4-7 illustrate the denoised images generated using the various methods.

Fig. 3. PSNR Graphs: (a) Baboon, (b) Female, (c) Hut, and (d) Zelda.

Fig. 4. (aa–af) Hut images corrupted by 20-70%, restored images using: (ba–bf) MF, (ca–cf) NAFSM, (da–df) DBUTVF, (ea–ef) proposed method.

Fig. 5. (aa–af) Female images corrupted 20-70%, restored images using: (ba–bf) MF, (ca–cf) NAFSM, (da–df) DBUTVF, (ea–ef) proposed method.

Table I compares the proposed method with the state-of-the-art denoising algorithms on images with noise levels ranging in 10-70%. Different simulation tests were carried out on the test images, which were corrupted with impulsive noise. All methods were evaluated using PSNR and SSIM values. The proposed ROAD-TGM-HT method was compared with MF, NAFSM, and DBUTVF to remove impulsive noise from the image, and the results showed that it outperformed them, consistently providing higher PSNR and SSIM values.

Fig. 6. (aa–af) Zelda images corrupted by 20-70%, restored images using: (ba–bf) MF, (ca–cf) NAFSM, (da–df) DBUTVF, (ea–ef) proposed method.

Fig. 7. (aa–af) Baboon image corrupted 20% -70%, restored images using: (ba – bf) MF, (ca–cf) NAFSM, (da–df) DBUTVF, (ea–ef) proposed method.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF DENOISING FILTERS WITH PSNR AND SSIM VALUES.

Image	Noise Density		0.10	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.70
Hut	MF [17-18]	PSNR	29.81	28.29	24.72	20.18	16.36	13.23	10.67
		SSIM	0.9926	0.9694	0.8988	0.7390	0.5349	0.3314	0.1925
	NAFSM [24]	PSNR	30.23	29.48	28.85	28.16	27.43	26.65	25.81
		SSIM	0.9843	0.9772	0.9700	0.9605	0.9500	0.9383	0.9221
	DBUTVF [39]	PSNR	30.48	29.67	28.79	27.68	26.51	25.06	22.92
		SSIM	0.9857	0.9788	0.9698	0.9554	0.9359	0.9088	0.8661
	PROPOSED	PSNR	30.63	30.11	29.45	28.82	28.04	27.34	26.49
		SSIM	0.9870	0.9825	0.9763	0.9687	0.9600	0.9494	0.9350
Baboon	MF [17-18]	PSNR	30.80	26.53	22.86	19.15	15.73	12.89	10.50
		SSIM	0.9761	0.9375	0.8636	0.7326	0.5607	0.3892	0.2499
	NAFSM [24]	PSNR	31.96	28.98	27.00	25.73	24.65	23.66	22.74
		SSIM	0.9758	0.9503	0.9223	0.8944	0.8594	0.8243	0.7826
	DBUTV [39]	PSNR	28.77	26.48	24.80	23.26	21.95	20.70	19.40
		SSIM	0.9706	0.9436	0.9112	0.8711	0.8241	0.7658	0.6964
	PROPOSED	PSNR	33.80	30.52	28.37	26.83	25.53	24.32	23.13
		SSIM	0.9830	0.9637	0.9416	0.9172	0.8872	0.8528	0.8180
Zelda	MF [17-18]	PSNR	38.59	31.06	25.32	20.02	15.93	12.60	10.08
		SSIM	0.9872	0.9466	0.8155	0.5824	0.3471	0.1943	0.1067
	NAFSM [24]	PSNR	37.64	34.66	32.60	31.07	30.04	29.12	28.01
		SSIM	0.9874	0.9750	0.9614	0.9487	0.9325	0.9173	0.8915
	DBUTVF [39]	PSNR	39.11	35.44	33.51	31.17	29.46	27.27	25.52
		SSIM	0.9880	0.9760	0.9611	0.9390	0.9155	0.8836	0.8353
	PROPOSED	PSNR	40.72	37.63	35.24	33.41	32.08	30.69	29.19
		SSIM	0.9917	0.9828	0.9716	0.9591	0.9446	0.9271	0.9052
Female	MF [17-18]	PSNR	35.73	29.94	24.36	20.00	16.10	13.15	10.64
		SSIM	0.9921	0.9596	0.8652	0.6694	0.4480	0.2739	0.1637
	NAFSM [24]	PSNR	36.13	34.51	32.87	31.06	29.88	28.50	27.23
		SSIM	0.9934	0.9882	0.9800	0.9724	0.9632	0.9518	0.9328
	DBUTVF [39]	PSNR	31.05	29.90	29.01	27.57	26.35	25.03	23.17
		SSIM	0.9813	0.9788	0.9698	0.9554	0.9359	0.9088	0.8661
	PROPOSED	PSNR	36.75	35.16	33.28	31.84	30.31	29.28	28.02
		SSIM	0.9946	0.9903	0.9844	0.9770	0.9671	0.9562	0.9421

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an improved sequential ROAD-TGM-HT filter to reduce high-density noise from color images while preserving precise image features. To test the efficiency of the proposed method, varying degrees of noise from 10% to 70% were applied to a large dataset of color images, and then their PSNR and SSIM values were measured after denoising. The proposed de-noising method outperformed other known algorithms in terms of PSNR and SSIM. The suggested approach can be improved by improving the initial value estimation stage.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Singh, G. Sethi, and G. S. Kalra, "Spatially Adaptive Image Denoising via Enhanced Noise Detection Method for Grayscale and Color Images," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 112985–113002, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3003874>.
- [2] D. Aspandi, O. Martinez, F. Sukno, and X. Binefa, "Composite recurrent network with internal denoising for facial alignment in still and video images in the wild," *Image and Vision Computing*, vol. 111, Jul. 2021, Art. no. 104189, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imavis.2021.104189>.
- [3] D. G. Kim, M. Hussain, M. Adnan, M. A. Farooq, Z. H. Shamsi, and A. Mushtaq, "Mixed Noise Removal Using Adaptive Median Based Non-Local Rank Minimization," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 6438–6452, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3048181>.
- [4] A. Mukherjee, S. Sarkar, and S. K. Saha, "Segmentation of natural images based on super pixel and graph merging," *IET Computer Vision*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 1–11, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1049/cvi2.12008>.
- [5] A. Jindal, N. Aggarwal, and S. Gupta, "An Obstacle Detection Method for Visually Impaired Persons by Ground Plane Removal Using Speeded-Up Robust Features and Gray Level Co-Occurrence Matrix," *Pattern Recognition and Image Analysis*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 288–300, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1054661818020086>.
- [6] I. Aizenberg, C. Butakoff, and D. Paliy, "Impulsive noise removal using threshold Boolean filtering based on the impulse detecting functions," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 63–66, Jan. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LSP.2004.838198>.
- [7] F. Jing, H. Shaohai, and M. Xiaole, "SAR image de-noising via grouping-based PCA and guided filter," *Journal of Systems Engineering and Electronics*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 81–91, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.23919/JSEE.2021.000009>.
- [8] L. Zhang, J. Liu, F. Shang, G. Li, J. Zhao, and Y. Zhang, "Robust segmentation method for noisy images based on an unsupervised denoising filter," *Tsinghua Science and Technology*, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 736–748, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.26599/TST.2021.9010021>.
- [9] S. Kaisar, S. Rijwan, J. A. Mahmud, and M. M. Rahman, "Salt and Pepper Noise Detection and removal by Tolerance based Selective Arithmetic Mean Filtering Technique for image restoration," *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 271–278, Jun. 2008.
- [10] X. Fei, L. Xiao, Y. Sun, and Z. Wei, "Perceptual image quality assessment based on structural similarity and visual masking," *Signal Processing: Image Communication*, vol. 27, no. 7, pp. 772–783, Aug. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.image.2012.04.005>.
- [11] G. M. Daiyan and M. A. Mottalib, "Removal of high density salt and pepper noise through a modified decision based median filter," in *2012 International Conference on Informatics, Electronics Vision (ICIEV)*, Feb. 2012, pp. 565–570, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIEV.2012.6317448>.
- [12] P. S. Windyga, "Fast impulsive noise removal," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 173–179, Jan. 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1109/83.892455>.
- [13] T. Chen and H. R. Wu, "Application of partition-based median type filters for suppressing noise in images," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 829–836, Jun. 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1109/83.923279>.
- [14] A. Noor, Y. Zhao, R. Khan, L. Wu, and F. Y. O. Abdalla, "Median filters combined with denoising convolutional neural network for Gaussian and impulse noises," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 79, no. 25, pp. 18553–18568, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-020-08657-4>.
- [15] H. Zeng, Y. Z. Liu, Y. M. Fan, and X. Tang, "An Improved Algorithm for Impulse Noise by Median Filter," *AASRI Procedia*, vol. 1, pp. 68–73, Jan. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aasri.2012.06.014>.
- [16] W. Fan, H. Yu, T. Chen, and S. Ji, "OCT Image Restoration Using Non-Local Deep Image Prior," *Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 5, May 2020, Art. no. 784, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics9050784>.
- [17] T. Chen, K. K. Ma, and L. H. Chen, "Tri-state median filter for image denoising," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 1834–1838, Sep. 1999, <https://doi.org/10.1109/83.806630>.
- [18] C. C. Chang, J. Y. Hsiao, and C. P. Hsieh, "An Adaptive Median Filter for Image Denoising," in *Proceedings of the 2008 Second International Symposium on Intelligent Information Technology Application - Volume 02*, Sep. 2008, pp. 346–350, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IITA.2008.259>.
- [19] S. T. Boo, H. Ibrahim, and K. K. V. Toh, "An Improved Progressive Switching Median Filter," in *2009 International Conference on Future Computer and Communication*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Apr. 2009, pp. 136–139, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICFCC.2009.87>.
- [20] S. J. Ko and Y. H. Lee, "Center weighted median filters and their applications to image enhancement," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems*, vol. 38, no. 9, pp. 984–993, Sep. 1991, <https://doi.org/10.1109/31.83870>.
- [21] R. Kunsath and M. Biswas, "Modified decision based median filter for impulse noise removal," in *2016 International Conference on Wireless Communications, Signal Processing and Networking (WiSPNET)*, Chennai, India, Mar. 2016, pp. 1316–1319, <https://doi.org/10.1109/WiSPNET.2016.7566350>.
- [22] H. Hwang and R. A. Haddad, "Adaptive median filters: new algorithms and results," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 499–502, Apr. 1995, <https://doi.org/10.1109/83.370679>.
- [23] K. S. Srinivasan and D. Ebenezer, "A New Fast and Efficient Decision-Based Algorithm for Removal of High-Density Impulse Noises," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 189–192, Mar. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LSP.2006.884018>.
- [24] K. K. V. Toh and N. A. Mat Isa, "Noise Adaptive Fuzzy Switching Median Filter for Salt-and-Pepper Noise Reduction," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 281–284, Mar. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LSP.2009.2038769>.
- [25] P. Zhang and F. Li, "A New Adaptive Weighted Mean Filter for Removing Salt-and-Pepper Noise," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 21, no. 10, pp. 1280–1283, Jul. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LSP.2014.2333012>.
- [26] U. Erkan, L. Gökrem, and S. Enginoğlu, "Different applied median filter in salt and pepper noise," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 70, pp. 789–798, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2018.01.019>.
- [27] S. Esakkirajan, T. Veerakumar, A. N. Subramanyam, and C. H. PremChand, "Removal of High Density Salt and Pepper Noise Through Modified Decision Based Unsymmetric Trimmed Median Filter," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 287–290, Feb. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LSP.2011.2122333>.
- [28] G. S. Kalra and S. Singh, "Efficient digital image denoising for gray scale images," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 75, no. 8, pp. 4467–4484, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-015-2484-x>.
- [29] A. Singh, G. Sethi, and G. S. Kalra, "Amalgamation of ROAD-TGM and progressive PCA using performance booster method for detail persevering image denoising," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 81, no. 2, pp. 1719–1742, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-021-11426-6>.
- [30] U. Erkan, D. N. H. Thanh, L. M. Hieu, and S. Enginoğlu, "An Iterative Mean Filter for Image Denoising," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 167847–167859, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2953924>.
- [31] S. J. Ko and Y. H. Lee, "Center weighted median filters and their applications to image enhancement," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems*, vol. 38, no. 9, pp. 984–993, Sep. 1991, <https://doi.org/10.1109/31.83870>.

- Systems, vol. 38, no. 9, pp. 984–993, Sep. 1991, <https://doi.org/10.1109/31.83870>.
- [32] R. H. Chan, C. Hu, and M. Nikolova, "An iterative procedure for removing random-valued impulse noise," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 11, no. 12, pp. 921–924, Sep. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LSP.2004.838190>.
- [33] K. Aiswarya, V. Jayaraj, and D. Ebenezer, "A New and Efficient Algorithm for the Removal of High Density Salt and Pepper Noise in Images and Videos," in *2010 Second International Conference on Computer Modeling and Simulation*, Jan. 2010, vol. 4, pp. 409–413, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCMS.2010.310>.
- [34] G. M. Daiyan and M. A. Mottalib, "Removal of high density salt and pepper noise through a modified decision based median filter," in *2012 International Conference on Informatics, Electronics Vision (ICIEV)*, Feb. 2012, pp. 565–570, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIEV.2012.6317448>.
- [35] A. Singh, G. Sethi, and G. S. Kalra, "Amalgamation of ROAD-TGM and progressive PCA using performance booster method for detail persevering image denoising," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 81, no. 2, pp. 1719–1742, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-021-11426-6>.
- [36] S. Banerjee, A. Bandyopadhyay, A. Mukherjee, A. Das, and R. Bag, "Random Valued Impulse Noise Removal Using Region Based Detection Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2288–2292, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1609>.
- [37] V. Yatnalli, B. G. Shivaleelavathi, and K. L. Sudha, "Review of Inpainting Algorithms for Wireless Communication Application," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5790–5795, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3547>.
- [38] K. H. Hii, V. Narayanamurthy, and F. Samsuri, "ECG Noise Reduction with the Use of the Ant Lion Optimizer Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4525–4529, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2766>.
- [39] K. Vasanth, V. Jawahar Senthilkumar, and V. Rajesh, "A Decision based Unsymmetrical Trimmed Variants for the Removal of High Density Salt and Pepper Noise," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 42, no. 15, pp. 38–43, Mar. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.5120/5772-8166>.
- [40] R. Garnett, T. Huegerich, C. Chui, and W. He, "A universal noise removal algorithm with an impulse detector," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 14, no. 11, pp. 1747–1754, Aug. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIP.2005.857261>.
- [41] USC - University of Southern California, "SIPI Image Database - Misc." <https://sipi.usc.edu/database/database.php?volume=misc> (accessed May 02, 2022).

An Enhanced Visual Object Tracking Approach based on Combined Features of Neural Networks, Wavelet Transforms, and Histogram of Oriented Gradients

Mohammed Bourennane

Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Biskra,
Biskra, Algeria
bourennane@gmail.com

Madina Hamiane

College of Engineering, Royal University for Women,
Bahrain
mhamiane@ruw.edu.bh

Nadjiba Terki

LESIA Laboratory of Research, Department of Electrical
Engineering, University of Biskra, Biskra, Algeria
n.terki@univ-biskra.dz

Abdallah Kouzou

LAADI Laboratory, Faculty of Science and Technology,
University of Djelfa, Djelfa, Algeria and
Electrical and Electronics Engineering Department,
Nisantasi University, Istanbul, Turkey
a.kouzou@uni-djelfa.dz

Received: 28 April 2022 | Revised: 7 May 2022 | Accepted: 12 May 2022

Abstract- In this paper, a new Visual Object Tracking (VOT) approach is proposed to overcome the main problem the existing approaches encounter, i.e. the significant appearance changes which are mainly caused by heavy occlusion and illumination variation. The proposed approach is based on a combination of Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNNs), Histogram of Oriented Gradient (HOG) features, and discrete wavelet packet transforms. The problem of illumination variation is solved by incorporating the coefficients of the image discrete wavelet packet transform instead of the image template to handle the case of images with high saturation in the input of the used CNN, whereas the inverse discrete wavelet packet transforms are used at the output for extracting the CNN features. By combining four learned correlation filters with the convolutional features, the target location is deduced using multichannel correlation maps at the CNN output. On the other side, the maximum value of the resulting maps from the correlation filters with convolutional features produced by the previously obtained HOG feature of the image template are calculated and are used as an updating parameter of the correlation filters extracted from CNN and from HOG. The major aim is to ensure long-term memory of the target appearance so that the target item may be recovered if tracking fails. In order to increase the performance of HOG, the coefficients of the discrete packet wavelet transform are employed instead of the image template. The obtained results demonstrate the superiority of the proposed approach.

Keywords-visual tracking; deep convolution neural networks; wavelet transform; HOG features

I. INTRODUCTION

Visual Object Tracking (VOT) is becoming a very active area of research, attracting much attention due to its importance

Corresponding author: Mohammed Bourennane

within numerous applications such as unmanned control systems, motion analysis, and video processing [1-5]. VOT is basically used to estimate an unknown visual target trajectory based on a known initial starting state of the considered target. However, the visual tracking remains a difficult problem to be solved accurately despite the efforts in this area during the last decade, due to the new challenges that have been induced by new technology evolution and which make the target objects often experience important changes in their appearance, such as the scale variation, fast motion, in-plane rotation, deformation, motion blur, occlusion, illumination variation, out-of-plane rotation, background clutter, etc.

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) features have been recently put to use in a variety of computer vision applications [6-8], e.g. object identification, image segmentation, and image classification [9]. The effective use of the rich hierarchical features of CNNs in visual tracking, has brought significant improvement. It has been proved that the convolutional layers have the ability of ensuring the presentation of the invariant features against the variation of the target appearance which can be very useful in visual object tracking applications. Unfortunately, it has been found that the CNNs have a major limitation resulting from the fact that they are built based on the principles of other visual classification tasks [10]. Authors in [11] proposed the exploitation of the rich hierarchical features of the Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNNs) to ensure enhanced accuracy and robustness of visual object tracking. It has been proposed that, in order to ensure invariant feature representation with respect to significant variations in the target appearance, the outputs of the last convolutional layers should be used to encode the semantic information of the target. This technique faced the problem of losing the precise

localization of the target due to large spatial resolution, it has even been resistant to target significant appearance changes. In the same time, it has been observed that the features of the earlier convolutional layers can ensure precise localization of targets but in the same time they are less sensitive to target appearance changes. Based on the concept that various layers in a CNN model give varying levels of information in describing an object [2-4], some authors have attempted to address this issue by combining feature representations provided by different CNN layers with correlation filters to realize efficient tracking performance [2-5]. Despite the achieved advantages of these techniques, compared to those based on CNN, this proposal presented some limitations. It has been based essentially on the learning and updating of the correlation filters in the frequency to overcome the problem of appearance variations. This led to unwanted boundary effects and important degradation of the tracking model quality. Furthermore, it has been found that it cannot be effective for long time tracking and it cannot ensure the detection of the target position failures. In the same time, it has faced a major problem against changes of illumination within specific color sequences [13]. Authors in [14] proposed an efficient hybrid image fusion method based on the Integer Lifting Wavelet Transform (ILWT) and the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) to generate fused images with high visual quality which can be used to reduce some visual tracking problems.

Traditional signal processing methodologies, such as multi-resolution analysis utilizing wavelets, have been thoroughly investigated, allowing them to be more interpretable than CNNs. In fact, there have been several prior works, which have incorporated wavelet representations into CNNs [15]. Authors in [16] proposed Wavelet CNNs (WCNNs) and demonstrated how to generalize filtering and downsampling by reformulating convolution and pooling layers. Authors in [17] presented a CNN that is similar to the dense convolutional network (DenseNet). Haar wavelets were employed as convolution and pooling layers, which are often used in multi-resolution analysis. In this approach, the feature maps generated by the subsequent convolutional blocks have been concatenated with these wavelet layers. Authors in [18] used the Dual-Tree Complex Wavelet Transformation (DTCWT) in addition to WCNNs to solve the organ tissue image segmentation problem, whereas, by moving activation layers into wavelet space, authors in [19] employed a new concept of learning filters based on activations in the domain of wavelet. Authors in [15] describe the Deep Adaptive Wavelet Network (DAWN) architecture, which employs a combination of the lifting technique and CNNs to learn features via multi-resolution analysis. The DAWN algorithm is designed to obtain a wavelet representation of the input at each decomposition level. This contrasts with the black-box nature of CNNs. The DAWN architecture, unlike standard wavelets, is data-driven and adapts to the input pictures. Additionally, it is trainable from start to finish and achieves cutting-edge texture classification with a small set of trainable parameters.

During the recent years, many detection and classification problems have been solved with the Histogram of Oriented Gradient (HOG) features [20-22]. Local forms of the

designated object are captured exactly by the HOG. Two sets of feature descriptors are commonly used [20]. This combination enhances detection efficiency but increases feature dimensions and computational complexity. Authors in [23] proposed a Haar-HOG-based approach which has shown better performance in terms of speed and efficiency than the algorithms based only on separate use of the Haar-like feature or the HOG descriptor. The proposed Haar-HOG algorithm has been found to be more accurate than the Haar-like features-based algorithm. On the other side, compared with algorithms using HOG descriptor only, this algorithm has a higher detection rate and a reduced false positive rate. The main contributions of this article can be summarized as:

- The wavelet decomposition based on different frequency sub-bands such as Low-Low (LL), Low-High (LH), High-Low (HL), and High-High (HH), have been used instead of RGB (Red-Green-Blue) image to resolve the problem of illumination variation in such cases when the saturation exceeds $\frac{2}{3} \times 100\%$.
- Based on the importance of combining feature representations from different CNN layers [3, 4, 24], a model of Hierarchical Convolutional Filters (HCF) is proposed. The proposed model is composed of different convolutional layers (conv1-4, conv3-4, conv4-4, and conv5-4).
- Wavelet decomposition, made up of four layers [LL, LH, HL, HH] instead of using the original image, has been used to improve the performance of the extracted HOG features.
- In addition, an update control approach has been designed to allow the appearance changes identification while preventing model drift. This has been carried out by calculating the maximum value of the resulting maps from correlation filters with convolutional feature products of HOG features for the image template that has been previously obtained, and which has been used as a parameter to the updating of the correlation filters.
- For the evaluation of the proposed approach, the large-scale benchmark datasets OTB50 with 50 challenging image sequences and OTB100 with 100 challenging image sequences have been used.

II. THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

The main aim of the algorithm proposed in this paper is to present a new contribution that can overcome the main difficulties encountered in visual tracking most of the previous proposed approaches face under target appearance changes such as severe occlusion and illumination variation. In this section, the proposed algorithm is described in detail. The different stages of the proposed tracking algorithm are shown in Figure 1. Firstly, based on [3, 4], the target location is estimated by learning 4 two-dimensional correlation filters with CNN features. Secondly, according to the properties of the input image, the selection of the use of RGB or GRAY with the wavelet decomposition is carried out.

Fig. 1. Main stages of the proposed algorithm.

Thirdly, the maximum value of the resulting maps is calculated from the correlation filters with convolutional feature products of HOG features based on the previously obtained image template. This calculated value is used as a parameter to update the correlation filters.

A. Convolution Features

Due to the very interesting properties of CNNs in ensuring accurate separation between the object and its background, they have been used largely to improve many aspects of computer vision. We present the translation estimation with the creation of a translation model by form extraction using a CNN model. VGGNet-19 [25] feature extractor trained on the ImageNet dataset [26] is used to encode the target appearance. While the characteristics propagate to deeper layers, the spatial resolution progressively decreases, but semantic discrimination between objects belonging to various categories is enhanced. The determination of the exact target item position in visual object tracking is more relevant than semantic category. Bilinear interpolation [3] is used to resize each input frame to 224×224 size.

Firstly, the fully connected layers are removed and the outputs of the convolution layers conv1-4, conv3-4, conv4-4, and conv5-4 are used as deep features. In addition, a cosine window to weight each feature channel is used to eliminate the boundary discontinuities [16, 27]. When the CNN depth increases, the spatial resolution of a target object decreases progressively because of the pooling processes. By using the bilinear interpolation given in (1), each feature map is also rescaled to size $\frac{M}{4} \times \frac{N}{4}$, where M and N are the dimensions of the feature vector x , to correct the spatial resolution across the pooling layers.

$$x_i = \sum_k a_{ik} h_k \quad (1)$$

B. Correlation Filters

Usually a correlation tracker search for the maximum value on the response in a discriminative classifier to locate target

objects is used [28-30]. In this research, all convolutional layer outputs are used as multi-channel features [31, 32]. We assume that x is the l^{th} layer of a feature vector of size $M \times N \times D$, where M , N , and D are the image width, image height, and the number of channels respectively. We ignore the dependence of M , N , and D on the layer index l and note $x^{(l)}$ directly as x . All the circular shifts of x along the M and N dimensions are taken as training samples. A Gaussian function label: $y(m, n) = e^{-\frac{(m-M/2)^2 + (n-N/2)^2}{2\sigma^2}}$, where σ is the kernel width, is attributed to each shifted sample $x_{(m,n)}(m, n) \in \{0, 1, \dots, M-1\} \times \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\}$. By solving the minimization problem (2), a correlation filter W with the same size of x is trained.

$$W^* = \text{argmin}_W \sum_{m,n} \|W \cdot x_{m,n} - y(m, n)\|^2 + \lambda \|W\|^2 \quad (2)$$

where λ is a regularization parameter ($\lambda \geq 0$).

Linear kernel in a Hilbert space is used to induce the inner product in (2), i.e. $W \cdot x_{m,n} = \sum_{d=1}^D W_{m,n,d}^T x_{m,n,d}$. As the label $y(m, n)$ is soft (not binary), so no hard-threshold sample is required. The minimization problem in (2) could be solved in each individual feature channel using Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT), since it's similar to training the vector correlation filters [33]. The capital letters denote the Fourier transformed signals. In the frequency domain, the learned filter on the d^{th} ($d \in \{1, \dots, D\}$) channel is given in (3):

$$W^d = \frac{Y \odot \bar{X}^d}{\sum_{i=1}^D X^i \odot \bar{X}^i + \lambda} \quad (3)$$

where Y is the Fourier transformation form of $y = \{y(m, n) | (m, n) \in \{0, 1, \dots, M-1\} \times \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\}\}$ and the bar refers to the complex conjugation. The operator \odot is the Hadamard product. For each image patch in the next frame the l^{th} layer feature vector is noted as z with size $M \times N \times D$. The l^{th} correlation response map is given by:

$$f_l = \mathcal{F}^{-1}(\sum_{d=1}^D W^d \odot \bar{Z}^d) \quad (4)$$

The operator \mathcal{F}^{-1} refers to the inverse FFT transform, the position of maximum value of the correlation response map f_l of size $M \times N$ refers to the target location on the l^{th} convolution layer.

C. Estimation of Coarse-to-Fine Translation

For each set of correlation response maps $\{f_l\}$, we can deduce the target translation of each layer, i.e. to search for the maximum value of the earlier $(l-1)^{\text{th}}$ layer, the location of maximum value in the last, l , layer is taken as regularization. If $(\hat{m}, \hat{n}) = \underset{m,n}{\operatorname{argmax}} f_l(m, n)$ refers to the location of the maximum values on the l^{th} layer, then the optimal location of the target in the $(l-1)^{\text{th}}$ layer is given by:

$$\underset{m,n}{\operatorname{argmax}} f_{l-1}(m, n) + \gamma f_l(m, n) \quad (5)$$

where $|m - \hat{m}| + |n - \hat{n}| \leq r$.

The constraints imposed on m and n limit the searched area in the $(l-1)^{\text{th}}$ correlation response map to the $r \times r$ neighboring regions of (\hat{m}, \hat{n}) . From the last to the inner layers, each response value is weighted by a regularization term γ and propagated back to the response maps of the earlier layers [3, 4]. Finally, by maximizing the result of (5) on the layer with the best spatial resolution, the target location is estimated. On the other hand, using (2), (3), and (5), we can calculate the maximum response of the correlation filter of HOG considering $l=1$, and $\gamma=1$.

D. Model Update

In this work, the correlations filters are updated as proposed in [33]. Initially, we update the numerator A^d and denominator B^d of the correlation filter W^d in (3), separately using a moving average:

$$A_t^d = (1 - \eta)A_{t-1}^d + \eta Y \odot \bar{X}_t^d \quad (6a)$$

$$B_t^d = (1 - \eta)B_{t-1}^d + \eta \sum_{i=1}^p X_t^i \odot \bar{X}_t^i \quad (6b)$$

$$W_t^d = \frac{A_t^d}{B_t^d + \lambda} \quad (6c)$$

We update the correlation filters extracted from CNN and HOG features conservatively, because the conservatively learned filter is robust to noisy updates and succeeds in estimating the confidence of every tracked result. To see if tracking failures occur, we establish a T_0 threshold. If the maximum filter response of the correlation filter of HOG is greater than T_0 , the tracked result z has a very high degree of confidence. In that case, we update the correlation filters.

III. DISCRET WAVELET PACKET TRANSFORMS

Two-Dimensional Discrete Wavelet Transform (2D-DWT) can be used to decompose an image into sub-signals, which present the original image components (I) under different frequency ranges. 2D-DWT is used in the input side to ensure the process of splitting the original image (I) into 4 sub images (ILL, IHL, ILH, and IHH). At first, two down-sampling filters (noted as $\downarrow 2$) of low (L) and high (H) bands are used yielding to two rows (IL and IH). Then each obtained images in both rows passes through two filters of low (L) and high (H) down-

sampling bands which means 4 filters are used in this phase to obtain 4 sub-images as 2 columns: the first column is (ILL, IHL) and the second column is (ILH, IHH). ILL presents the approximation coefficient matrix which is obtained from the passage through 2 simultaneous low-pass filters and the other 3 present the detail coefficients matrices IHL (horizontal features), ILH (vertical features), and IHH (diagonal features), as shown in Figure 2. Moreover, the 2-D DWT has a separable characteristic with the scaling function $\Phi_{LL}(x, y)$ and three 2D-wavelets, $\Psi_{HL}(x, y)$, $\Psi_{LH}(x, y)$, and $\Psi_{HH}(x, y)$, which can be expressed as follows [34]:

$$\Phi_{LL}(x, y) = \Phi(x)\Phi(y) \quad (7)$$

$$\Psi_{HL}(x, y) = \Psi(x)\Phi(y) \quad (8)$$

$$\Psi_{LH}(x, y) = \Phi(x)\Psi(y) \quad (9)$$

$$\Psi_{HH}(x, y) = \Psi(x)\Psi(y) \quad (10)$$

where $\Phi(x)$ and $\Phi(y)$ are the wavelet functions following the x-axis (horizontal) and the y-axis (vertical), $\Psi(x)$ and $\Psi(y)$ are the horizontal and vertical 1D scaling functions.

Fig. 2. Downsample and upsample comparison of DWT and IDWT.

In contrast, the inverse DWT (IDWT) is used in the output for adding 4 sub-images to the original one using up-sampling filters (noted as $\uparrow 2$) with the same concept as the DWT but with the inverse operation as shown in Figure 2. It is clear that the inputs are the 4 sub-images (ILL, IHL, ILH and IHH) and the output is the filtered original image (I).

IV. SATURATION CONDITION

In the proposed approach, the illumination variation has been handled in a reliable way based on a new proposed concept. The main idea of the proposed concept is based on integrating the wavelet decomposition obtained from the DWT [ILL, ILH, IHL, IHH] when the saturation of the image is very high instead of using the image components (RGB) directly in the network. The saturation power state can be computed for each input frame according to the following steps:

- First step: the conversion of the red, green, and blue values of an RGB image to hue (H), saturation (S), and value (V) values of an HSV image.
- Second step: the calculation of the saturation energy according to [13]:

$$E_s = 100 \times \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (S_{ij})^2}{E_T} \quad (11)$$

$$E_T = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (H_{ij})^2 + \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (S_{ij})^2 + \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (V_{ij})^2 \quad (12)$$

where E_s refers the saturation energy and E_T refers to the total energy of the input frame.

- Third step: if $E_s > \frac{2}{3} \times 100$, then the illumination is very weak. In this case, the wavelet decomposition [LL, LH, HL, HH] is used in the input of CNN. In the opposite case, the

TABLE I. THE PERCENTAGE OF ENERGY SATURATION IN THE SINGER2 SEQUENCE

Frame	6	8	10	12	14	16	18
Energy saturation (%)	76.58	76.30	76.82	25.16	71.62	73.39	72.03

It is clear from Table I that the energy saturation varies from a frame to another between the minimum value of 25.16% corresponding to frame 12 and the maximum value of 76.82% corresponding to frame 10. Based on the condition mentioned in the third step, it can be observed that energy saturation is low only in the case of frame 12 and the required condition is not satisfied. In this case the RGB approach is used. It is obvious that for the other frames this required condition is satisfied, hence the wavelet decomposition [LL, LH, HL, HH] is used in the input of CNNs in these frames. It can be concluded that under the application of the proposed approach, the case of illumination variation can be handled more accurately based on the beneficial features of 2D-DWD. Figure 3 illustrates the accurate placement of the target within the 6 chosen frames of the Singer2 sequence. The blue frame corresponds to the initial position of the tracked object and the red frame to the used tracker based on the proposed approach combining the wavelet and the CNNs. It is obvious that the proposed approach allows robust tracking of the moving object under illumination variations and in the same time it maintains the long-term memory of target appearance which ensures a high degree of accuracy in locating the target in the majority of the frames of the sequence. On the other hand, for the validation of the proposed approach based on the proposed saturation condition, two tests have been carried out based on the calculation of the error tracking in both cases, with (red) and without (blue) the saturation condition. It is clearly observed in Figure 3 that the tracking error obtained under the proposed approach is minimized to a very low value compared to the standard case in which the saturation condition variation is not taken into account.

Fig. 3. A frame-by-frame display of the results of the Singer2 sequence tracking, with and without the saturation condition (in pixels).

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The proposed algorithm has been validated and evaluated on two benchmark datasets, OTB50 [35], which includes 50

RGB decomposition of the input image is used. This step is carried out following the proposed approach.

The combined DWT and CNN method is found to be robust and therefore it is capable of alleviating the problem of illumination variation. As an example, Table I presents the percentage of energy saturation of the Singer2 sequence calculated along 6 frames following (11).

videos and OTB100 [35], which includes 100 videos. The tracking algorithm has been implemented in MATLAB on an Intel I7-8750H 2.20GHz CPU with 16GB RAM and the MatConvNet toolbox [36], while the feature extraction using CNN forward propagation has been carried out on a GeForce GTX1060 GPU. The CNN-based VGG-Net-19, consisting of 19 layers (16 convolution layers, 3 fully connected layers, 5 MaxPool layers, and 1 SoftMax layer) [25], has been trained on the free large-scale hierarchical image database ImageNet [26] and was adopted for feature extraction. The features are used only from the outputs of pool 1, pool 3, pool 4, and pool 5. The size of the search window is fixed to 1.8 times the target size. The regularization parameter of (2) is set to $\lambda = 10^{-4}$, the kernel width is taken as 0.1 for the generation of the Gaussian function labels, the learning rate η in (6) is set to 0.01, and T_0 is taken as 0.3. The value of γ is set as 1, 0.5, 0.25, and 0.15 for the conv5-4, conv4-4, conv3-4, conv1-4 layers respectively.

The performance of the proposed tracker has been evaluated based on two performance metrics, the Area-Under-the-Curve (AUC) and the Distance Precision (DP). For the validation of the proposed tracker's performance, a comparison has been carried out based on trackers presented in previous works: ASLA [37], CSK [38], DSST [30], MEEM [39], MUSTER [40], SAMF [41], SRDCF [27], Struck [42], siamfc3s [43], HCFTs [4], HDT [11], Staple [44], CNN-SVM [45], CF2 [3], LCT [46], KCF [32], TLD [47], KCF_GaussHog [32], KCF_LinearHog [32], BACF [48], DeepSRDCF [49], DRVT [50], MemDTC [51], MemTrack [51], SRDCFdecon [52]. The obtained results, corresponding to the two considered performance metrics, have been shown by two curves for One-Pass Evaluation (OPE), such as the DP rate vs. the location error threshold which measures the proportion of frames with distance between the tracking results and the ground truth less than a certain number of pixels, and the success rate vs. the overlap threshold which describes the percentage of successful frames as shown in Figures 4 and 5 for the OBT50 and OBT100 datasets respectively. The location error threshold variation is taken within the interval of [0, 50] and the overlap threshold variation within the interval of [0, 1]. The legend of the precision plots of OPE shows the ranking of the different trackers compared to the proposed tracker based on the DP score sat a threshold of 20 pixels, whereas the legend of success plots of OPE shows the ranking of the same trackers as in the previous Figure based on the AUC score. The obtained results for both datasets prove that the proposed tracker outperforms the other state-of-the-art trackers.

Fig. 4. OPE curves on the OTB50 dataset. Left: Overlap Precision (OP), right: Center Localization Error (CLE).

Fig. 5. OPE curves on the OTB100 dataset. Left: OP, right: CLE.

Fig. 6. Overlap success plots and distance precision plots in 10 tracking challenge situations.

For the clarity of result presentation, only the top 10 ranked trackers are taken into account as shown in Figures 5-6. It is clear that the proposed tracker performs favorably with an AUC of 64.5% and 60.5% and a DP of 90.1% and 87.8% on OTB-100 and OTB-50 respectively.

The obtained results prove clearly that the proposed tracker outperforms the second best tracker (HCFT), with a gain of 3.1% in the average DP, and with by 0.8% in the average overlap precision the second best tracker (MemDTC) in the case of OTB-100. For the OTB-50, the proposed tracker has an

improved gain of 4.7% and 2.1% for the average DP and average overlap precision compared to the second best tracker which is the same as the case of OTB-100. Figure 6 illustrates the overlap success rate plots and the DP plots obtained on OTB100 dataset for 10 challenging instances such as scale variation, fast motion, in-plane rotation, deformation, motion blur, occlusion, illumination variation, out-of-plane rotation, background clutter, and out-of-view. It can be clearly noted within all the sub-figures of Figure 6 that the proposed tracker outperforms the aforementioned state-of-the-art counterparts.

Fig. 7. Qualitative results of the proposed method, along with trackers from [3, 4, 32, 33, 45] challenge sequences.

Figure 7 shows the tracking performance of several representative trackers such as HCFTs [4], CNN-SVM [45], CF2 [3], DSST [30], KCF [32], and the proposed tracker on 6 challenging sequences. From top to bottom, the sequences are Human3, Girl2, Human5, Box, Car1, and Lemming respectively. Human3 has the challenge of scale variation occlusion, deformation, background clutters, and out-of-plane rotation. Girl2 contains scale variation, occlusion, deformation, out-of-plane rotation, and motion blur. Human5 includes scale variation, occlusion, and deformation. Car1 compromises illumination variation, motion blur, scale variation, fast motion and background clutters. Box holds illumination variation, motion blur, occlusion, out-of-plane rotation, in-plane rotation, background clutters, scale variation, and out-of-view. Lemming gathers illumination variation, fast motion, occlusion, scale variation, out-of-view, and out-of-plane rotation. It is obvious that the proposed tracker handles all these complicated scenarios better than the other trackers.

CNN-SVM with deep features performs well when scale variation, out-of-plane rotation, and occlusion are present (Human3, and Girl2), but it is less effective in handling drastic variations (Human5, Box, Lemming). CF, DSST and KCF are less effective in dealing with occlusion and deformation (Human3, Girl2, Human5, Box, and Lemming). HCFTs performs well in presence of scale variation, occlusion, motion blur and background clutter (Box, Lemming) but it is less effective in dealing with deformation (Human3, Girl2 and Human5). Overall, the proposed tracker operates adaptively and robustly when confronted with a variety of challenging factors. It is worth noting a minor drawback which has been faced during the application of the proposed tracker. The significant change in the aspect ratio in the case of Jump sequence has caused the missing of the target, which implies that a more robust design is required for scale variation, and aspect ratio adjustment strategy for the proposed tracker to overcome completely these kinds of deficiencies.

Fig. 8. The proposed tracker failed on the sequence Jump from OTB-100. The red and blue bounding boxes indicate the ground truth and the proposed tracker results respectively.

To check the effectiveness of the proposed tracker, it has been implemented based on two different proposed methods such as the HOG with wavelet (HOG-DWT) and HOG without wavelet, which have been combined with Hierarchical Convolutional Features (HCFs), with and without wavelets and it has been evaluated with the OTB-100. The obtained results of the tracker based on the two proposed methods, are shown in Figure 9, taking into account different combinations such as:

- Proposed: the tracker is based on HOG with DWT and HCFs with DWT.
- Proposed, No DWT in CNN: the tracker is based on HOG with DWT and HCFs without DWT.
- Proposed, No DWT in HOG: the tracker is based on HOG without DWT and HCFs with DWT.
- Proposed, No DWT in HOG and CNN: the tracker is based on HOG without DWT and HCFs without DWT.
- Proposed, No HOG: the tracker is based only on HCFs with DWT.
- Proposed, No HOG, No DWT in CNN: the tracker is based on HCFs without DWT.

It is clear that combining HCF, HOG, and wavelets ensured optimal results, although HOG affects the proposed method in object tracking under the occurrence of out-of-view, occlusion, out-of-plane rotation, motion blur, scale variation, deformation, and illumination variation. From the obtained results, it can be said that the exploitation of wavelets in HOG has improved the proposed tracker in handling occlusion, scale variation, and out-of-plane rotation. Furthermore, the use of wavelet in HCFs

improves the proposed tracker's behavior in handling only the illumination variation occurrence. Through the above analysis, it can be concluded that the combination of HCFs, HOG, and DWT can greatly improve the robustness and accuracy of the proposed tracker.

Fig. 9. Performance evaluation of the proposed tracker at each stage using the OTB-100 dataset.

In the present analysis, the use of different types of wavelets has been investigated on the tracker's performance. Figure 10 shows the calculated precision for a series of distance thresholds (percentage of frames where the distance to the ground truth is within the threshold) of Singer2 sequence. It can be clearly noticed that the wavelet type 'bior2.4' leads to obtaining the best result of 98.4%, which further justifies the validity of the proposed approach.

Fig. 10. Precision of sequence Singer2 with different types of wavelets.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an effective combination among CNN layer features, HOG features, and DWT image wavelet transforms, based on the exploitation of the hierarchical CNN features which have been trained on a large scale data base, has been proposed for the improvement of the visual object tracking algorithm. The output layers of the CNNs are used to preserve the semantics of the target objects, which are robust to significant appearance changes. The input layers of the CNNs are exploited for encoding more precise spatial details, which are useful for precise localization. Both features with the precise details are used at the same time for visual object tracking, while a linear correlation filter has been trained on each CNN layer for the deduction of the targeted location based on hierarchical correlation maps in a coarse-to-fine manner. In the same time, to enhance the accuracy of the proposed tracker

and to overcome the problem of drifting encountered during the update process of the correlation filter, an approach for ensuring such process in real time along each step has been proposed. This approach is based on training of the correlation filter on HOG features in order to make it a tool to update the filters produced by CNN and HOG features. Furthermore, to improve the performance of the proposed tracker, the DWT has been utilized to achieve two main goals: the calculation of the HOG features instead of using RGB and the calculation of CNN features in the case of images with high saturation. The obtained results from the extensive carried out simulations, show that the proposed tracker outperforms the state of the art trackers. However, despite the proven effectiveness of the proposed tracker, there is a need to further improve its robustness in the future.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. A. Dharejo *et al.*, "A deep hybrid neural network for single image dehazing via wavelet transform," *Optik*, vol. 231, Apr. 2021, Art. no. 166462, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijleo.2021.166462>.
- [2] M. Y. Abbass, K.-C. Kwon, N. Kim, S. A. Abdelwahab, F. E. A. El-Samie, and A. A. M. Khalaf, "Efficient object tracking using hierarchical convolutional features model and correlation filters," *The Visual Computer*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 831–842, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00371-020-01833-5>.
- [3] C. Ma, J.-B. Huang, X. Yang, and M.-H. Yang, "Hierarchical Convolutional Features for Visual Tracking," in *IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*, Santiago, Chile, Dec. 2015, pp. 3074–3082, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCV.2015.352>.
- [4] C. Ma, J.-B. Huang, X. Yang, and M.-H. Yang, "Robust Visual Tracking via Hierarchical Convolutional Features," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 41, no. 11, pp. 2709–2723, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2018.2865311>.
- [5] A. Zgaren, W. Bouachir, and R. Ksantini, "Coarse-to-Fine Object Tracking Using Deep Features and Correlation Filters," in *15th International Symposium on Visual Computing*, San Diego, CA, USA, Nov. 2020, pp. 517–529, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64556-4_40.
- [6] Y. Said, M. Barr, and H. E. Ahmed, "Design of a Face Recognition System based on Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5608–5612, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3490>.
- [7] P. Chakraborty and C. Tharini, "Pneumonia and Eye Disease Detection using Convolutional Neural Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5769–5774, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3503>.
- [8] S. Alqethami, B. Almtanni, W. Alzhrani, and M. Alghamdi, "Disease Detection in Apple Leaves Using Image Processing Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8335–8341, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4721>.
- [9] J. Zhang, J. Sun, J. Wang, and X.-G. Yue, "Visual object tracking based on residual network and cascaded correlation filters," *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, vol. 12, no. 8, pp. 8427–8440, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-020-02572-0>.
- [10] Y. Bai, T. Xu, B. Huang, and R. Yang, "Deep Deblurring Correlation Filter for Object Tracking," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 68623–68637, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2986311>.
- [11] Y. Qi *et al.*, "Hedged Deep Tracking," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, Jun. 2016, pp. 4303–4311, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2016.466>.
- [12] C. Ma, Y. Xu, B. Ni, and X. Yang, "When Correlation Filters Meet Convolutional Neural Networks for Visual Tracking," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 1454–1458, Jul. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LSP.2016.2601691>.
- [13] D. E. Touil, N. Terki, and S. Medouakh, "Hierarchical convolutional features for visual tracking via two combined color spaces with SVM

- classifier," *Signal, Image and Video Processing*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 359–368, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11760-018-1364-z>.
- [14] B. Latreche, S. Saadi, M. Kious, and A. Benziane, "A novel hybrid image fusion method based on integer lifting wavelet and discrete cosine transformer for visual sensor networks," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 78, no. 8, pp. 10865–10887, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-018-6676-z>.
- [15] M. X. Bastidas Rodriguez *et al.*, "Deep Adaptive Wavelet Network," in *IEEE Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*, Snowmass, CO, USA, Mar. 2020, pp. 3100–3108, <https://doi.org/10.1109/WACV45572.2020.9093580>.
- [16] S. Fujieda, K. Takayama, and T. Hachisuka, "Wavelet Convolutional Neural Networks," arXiv, arXiv:1805.08620, May 2018. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1805.08620>.
- [17] G. Huang, Z. Liu, L. Van Der Maaten, and K. Q. Weinberger, "Densely Connected Convolutional Networks," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Honolulu, HI, USA, Jul. 2017, pp. 2261–2269, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2017.243>.
- [18] H. Lu, H. Wang, Q. Zhang, D. Won, and S. W. Yoon, "A Dual-Tree Complex Wavelet Transform Based Convolutional Neural Network for Human Thyroid Medical Image Segmentation," in *IEEE International Conference on Healthcare Informatics*, New York, NY, USA, Jun. 2018, pp. 191–198, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICHI.2018.00029>.
- [19] F. Cotter and N. Kingsbury, "Deep Learning in the Wavelet Domain," arXiv, arXiv:1811.06115, Nov. 2018. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1811.06115>.
- [20] W. Yun, D. Kim, B. Song, and H. Yoon, "Block comparison based face identification using HOG feature," in *18th IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication*, Toyama, Japan, Oct. 2009, pp. 484–487, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ROMAN.2009.5326203>.
- [21] W. Zhang, G. Zelinsky, and D. Samaras, "Real-time Accurate Object Detection using Multiple Resolutions," in *IEEE 11th International Conference on Computer Vision*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, Oct. 2007, pp. 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCV.2007.4409057>.
- [22] M. Villamizar, F. Moreno-Noguer, J. Andrade-Cetto, and A. Sanfeliu, "Efficient rotation invariant object detection using boosted Random Ferns," in *IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, San Francisco, CA, USA, Jun. 2010, pp. 1038–1045, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2010.5540104>.
- [23] Y. Wei, Q. Tian, and T. Guo, "An Improved Pedestrian Detection Algorithm Integrating Haar-Like Features and HOG Descriptors," *Advances in Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 5, Jan. 2013, Art. no. 546206, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/546206>.
- [24] D. E. Touil, N. Terki, and S. Medouakh, "Learning spatially correlation filters based on convolutional features via PSO algorithm and two combined color spaces for visual tracking," *Applied Intelligence*, vol. 48, no. 9, pp. 2837–2846, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10489-017-1120-z>.
- [25] K. Simonyan and A. Zisserman, "Very Deep Convolutional Networks for Large-Scale Image Recognition," arXiv, arXiv:1409.1556, Apr. 2015. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1409.1556>.
- [26] J. Deng, W. Dong, R. Socher, L.-J. Li, K. Li, and L. Fei-Fei, "ImageNet: A large-scale hierarchical image database," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Miami, FL, USA, Jun. 2009, pp. 248–255, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2009.5206848>.
- [27] M. Danelljan, G. Häger, F. S. Khan, and M. Felsberg, "Learning Spatially Regularized Correlation Filters for Visual Tracking," in *IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*, Santiago, Chile, Dec. 2015, pp. 4310–4318, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCV.2015.490>.
- [28] D. S. Bolme, J. R. Beveridge, B. A. Draper, and Y. M. Lui, "Visual object tracking using adaptive correlation filters," in *IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, San Francisco, CA, USA, Jun. 2010, pp. 2544–2550, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2010.5539960>.
- [29] K. Zhang, L. Zhang, and M.-H. Yang, "Real-Time Compressive Tracking," in *12th European Conference on Computer Vision*, Florence, Italy, Oct. 2012, pp. 864–877, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-33712-3_62.
- [30] M. Danelljan, G. Hager, F. Khan, and M. Felsberg, "Accurate Scale Estimation for Robust Visual Tracking," in *British Machine Vision Conference*, Nottingham, UK, Sep. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.5244/C.28.65>.
- [31] H. K. Galoogahi, T. Sim, and S. Lucey, "Multi-channel Correlation Filters," in *IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*, Sydney, NSW, Australia, Dec. 2013, pp. 3072–3079, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCV.2013.381>.
- [32] J. F. Henriques, R. Caseiro, P. Martins, and J. Batista, "High-Speed Tracking with Kernelized Correlation Filters," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 583–596, Mar. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2014.2345390>.
- [33] V. N. Boddeti, T. Kanade, and B. V. K. V. Kumar, "Correlation Filters for Object Alignment," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Portland, OR, USA, Jun. 2013, pp. 2291–2298, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2013.297>.
- [34] F. A. Dharejo *et al.*, "A deep hybrid neural network for single image dehazing via wavelet transform," *Optik*, vol. 231, Apr. 2021, Art. no. 166462, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijleo.2021.166462>.
- [35] Y. Wu, J. Lim, and M.-H. Yang, "Object Tracking Benchmark," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 37, no. 9, pp. 1834–1848, Sep. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2014.2388226>.
- [36] A. Vedaldi and K. Lenc, "MatConvNet: Convolutional Neural Networks for MATLAB," in *23rd ACM international conference on Multimedia*, Brisbane, Australia, Oct. 2015, pp. 689–692, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2733373.2807412>.
- [37] X. Jia, H. Lu, and M.-H. Yang, "Visual tracking via adaptive structural local sparse appearance model," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Providence, RI, USA, Jun. 2012, pp. 1822–1829, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2012.6247880>.
- [38] J. F. Henriques, R. Caseiro, P. Martins, and J. Batista, "Exploiting the Circulant Structure of Tracking-by-Detection with Kernels," in *12th European Conference on Computer Vision*, Florence, Italy, Oct. 2012, pp. 702–715, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-33765-9_50.
- [39] J. Zhang, S. Ma, and S. Sclaroff, "MEEM: Robust Tracking via Multiple Experts Using Entropy Minimization," in *13th European Conference*, Zurich, Switzerland, Sep. 2014, pp. 188–203, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10599-4_13.
- [40] Z. Hong, Z. Chen, C. Wang, X. Mei, D. Prokhorov, and D. Tao, "Multi-Store Tracker (MUSTER): A cognitive psychology inspired approach to object tracking," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Boston, MA, USA, Jun. 2015, pp. 749–758, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2015.7298675>.
- [41] Y. Li and J. Zhu, "A Scale Adaptive Kernel Correlation Filter Tracker with Feature Integration," in *Computer Vision - ECCV 2014 Workshops*, Zurich, Switzerland, Sep. 2014, pp. 254–265, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-16181-5_18.
- [42] S. Hare *et al.*, "Struck: Structured Output Tracking with Kernels," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 38, no. 10, pp. 2096–2109, Jul. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2015.2509974>.
- [43] L. Bertinetto, J. Valmadre, J. F. Henriques, A. Vedaldi, and P. H. S. Torr, "Fully-Convolutional Siamese Networks for Object Tracking," in *Computer Vision - ECCV 2016 Workshops*, Amsterdam, Netherlands, Oct. 2016, pp. 850–865, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-48881-3_56.
- [44] L. Bertinetto, J. Valmadre, S. Golodetz, O. Miksik, and P. H. S. Torr, "Staple: Complementary Learners for Real-Time Tracking," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, Jun. 2016, pp. 1401–1409, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2016.156>.
- [45] S. Hong, T. You, S. Kwak, and B. Han, "Online Tracking by Learning Discriminative Saliency Map with Convolutional Neural Network," in *32nd International Conference on Machine Learning*, Lille, France, Jul. 2015, pp. 597–606, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1502.06796>.

- [46] C. Ma, X. Yang, C. Zhang, and M.-H. Yang, "Long-term correlation tracking," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Boston, MA, USA, Jun. 2015, pp. 5388–5396, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2015.7299177>.
- [47] Z. Kalal, K. Mikolajczyk, and J. Matas, "Tracking-Learning-Detection," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 34, no. 7, pp. 1409–1422, Jul. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2011.239>.
- [48] H. K. Galoogahi, A. Fagg, and S. Lucey, "Learning Background-Aware Correlation Filters for Visual Tracking," in *IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*, Venice, Italy, Oct. 2017, pp. 1144–1152, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCV.2017.129>.
- [49] M. Danelljan, G. Hager, F. S. Khan, and M. Felsberg, "Convolutional Features for Correlation Filter Based Visual Tracking," in *IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision Workshop*, Santiago, Chile, Dec. 2015, pp. 621–629, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCVW.2015.84>.
- [50] X. Li, Q. Liu, N. Fan, Z. Zhou, Z. He, and X. Jing, "Dual-regression model for visual tracking," *Neural Networks*, vol. 132, pp. 364–374, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2020.09.01>.
- [51] T. Yang and A. B. Chan, "Visual Tracking via Dynamic Memory Networks," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 360–374, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2019.2929034>.
- [52] M. Danelljan, G. Hager, F. S. Khan, and M. Felsberg, "Adaptive Decontamination of the Training Set: A Unified Formulation for Discriminative Visual Tracking," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, Jun. 2016, pp. 1430–1438, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2016.159>.

Utilizing Numerical Simulations to Analyze the Efficiency of a Porous Reactor

Wilson Ribeiro do Prado Júnior

Department of Basic Science and Environmental
Engineering School at Lorena, University of São Paulo
Lorena, São Paulo, Brasil
wrpjunior@usp.br

Jairo Aparecido Martins

Research & Development
DESCH North America
Cambridge, Ontario, Canada
Jairo.martins@desch.com

Estaner Claro Romão

Department of Basic Science and Environmental
Engineering School at Lorena, University of São Paulo
Lorena, São Paulo, Brasil
estaner23@usp.br

Received: 28 March 2022 | Revised: 16 April 2022 and 30 April 2022 | Accepted: 7 May 2022

Abstract-This paper presents a series of numerical simulations of a porous reactor, where a generic reaction between reagents is carried out, generating a product. All numerical simulations were performed by using the software COMSOL Multiphysics, which made use of the Navier-Stokes and Brinkman equations. These equations were utilized to govern the fluid flow in the numerical simulation. Throughout the simulations, several initial parameters were altered to evaluate their impact on the reactor efficiency based on the concentration of component C. Furthermore, other parameters such as the distribution of speed and geometry in the equipment were taken into consideration, and an optimal configuration for the case is demonstrated.

Keywords-numerical simulation; porous reactor; Navier-Stokes equations; brinkman equations

I. INTRODUCTION

This work aims to study the effects of some process parameters in a reactor of porous media, to provide industrial improvements, and to maximize the obtained product for the same reactor or similar equipment. Although the type of reactor studied in this work has several applications for expelling gas into the atmosphere, it is treated in a generic manner in order to reach a conclusion and extend it to any similar reactor. As an example, this type of reactor has several applications in industries, including internal combustion engines [1-3] where the post-treatment of exhausted gases can be numerically simulated [4-7]. In this paper, a generic case is assumed with a simple chemical equation to analyze this type of reactor, and the way its properties influence its performance, when the species A and B react to form the species C:

Since this reaction only occurs in a porous catalyst and the intention is to treat generic cases, the initial porosity is assumed

as 0.3 and fixed with a low permeability established as 10^{-9} , comparable with the permeability of brick or leather, which are in the range of 10^{-9} to 10^{-10} . This paper uses a modeled reactor with porous media as provided by COMSOL™, with the adaptation shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Model of the reactor of porous media showing the inlet and outlet.

This paper's main idea is to numerically simulate the process of heterogeneous catalyzing between two species of reagents. It happens when the species A is injected into a reactor through a perpendicular tube while the species B gets into the tube by the tube's main entrance (Figure 1). Both are partially mixed into the reactor before they pass through the porous media, where a reaction occurs and the third species C is obtained. This reaction happens with the transport of ideally inert gas in the reaction. So, it is expected with the simulations and improvements implemented to decrease the concentration of the species B being expelled out of the equipment. As described previously, this type of reactor can be utilized in combustion engines to reduce gas emissions to the atmosphere. Further, several equations that govern the phenomenon are presented, also the main parameters utilized (chemical reaction, system geometry, mesh, etc.), and lastly, the obtained output is

shown. In addition, this work shows the way the sequence of analysis of the parameters is involved in the problem and the consequent optimization can bring benefits to the process and the economy by reducing operating costs.

II. FLOW IN POROUS MEDIA

A. Transport of Diluted Species

A diluted species has a very small concentration when compared with a solvent fluid. Consequently, mixture properties such as density and dynamical viscosity may be considered equal to the solvent's. The equation of mass conservation used to calculate the transport of diluted species by diffusion and convection is given by [9]:

$$\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot J_i + u \cdot \nabla C_i = R_i \quad (2)$$

where C_i is the species concentration (mol/m³), R_i is the reaction rate of species i (mol/(m³·s)), u is the fluid median velocity (m/s) and J_i is the diffusive flow vector (mol/(m²·s)).

B. Brinkman's Equations

Brinkman's equations are an extension of Darcy's equation that describes the movement of a slow flow in porous media. It describes the dissipation of kinetic energy by the viscous shearing from Navier-Stokes equations, which describes the fast-flow movements throughout free channels. So, these equations calculate the fast movements of fluids in porous media with kinetic potential by velocity, pressure, and gravity into the flow. The flow in porous media is governed by the equation of continuity and momentum, converging to Brinkman's equation [9]:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\varepsilon_p \rho) + \nabla \cdot (\rho u) = Q_m \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\rho}{\varepsilon_p} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + (u \cdot \nabla) \frac{u}{\varepsilon_p} \right) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \left[\frac{1}{\varepsilon_p} \left\{ \mu \nabla u + (\nabla u)^T - \frac{2}{3} \mu (\nabla \cdot u) I \right\} \right] - \left(\kappa^{-1} \mu + \frac{Q_m}{\varepsilon_p^2} \right) u + F \quad (4)$$

where μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid (kg/(m·s)), u is the velocity vector, ρ is the density of the fluid (kg/m³), p is the pressure (Pa), ε_p is the porosity, κ is the permeability of the porous medium (m²), and Q_m is a mass source or sink (kg/(m³·s)).

III. MODELING THE PHENOMENA

The model for the phenomena of transport to diluted species utilized here is composed of the Navier-Stokes and Brinkman equations (as mentioned above). Here, an isothermal situation is adopted and the used gas transported is Nitrogen. In terms of geometry, it complies with Figure 2, where: $H = 0.01$, $R = 0.01$, $H_p = 0.003$, $R_a = 0.0004$, $H_a = 0.002$, $R_{ai} = 0.0002$, $D = 0.005$, $d = 0.003$ (all in meters), that will be used in Case 1. In terms of mesh building, the physical type of the element was considered, therefore, the "normal" mesh type was used, which has 166,645 domain elements, 16,556 boundary elements, and 758 edge elements. It is important to highlight that this work does not aim at a particular reaction, but rather a generic case is demonstrated. Although in this simulation the kinetics of the reaction is governed by a generic equation, it is important to

understand that a specific and real case requires a particular kinetics analysis. The expression that follows is the one utilized in this paper for the generic analysis:

$$R_C = A_f \cdot e^{\left(\frac{-E}{RgT_{iso}} \right)} \cdot C_A \cdot C_B \quad (5)$$

where R_C is the formation rate of species C (mol/(m³·s)), A_f is the frequency factor (m³/(s·mol)), E is the activation energy (J/mol), Rg is the universal constant of gases (J/(mol·K)), T_{iso} is the isothermal temperature of reaction (K), C_A and C_B are the concentrations (mol/(m³·s)).

Fig. 2. Geometric parameters of the reactor.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Even though the presented simulations came from innumerable combinations of the concentrations as inlets for each species, the velocity of each species, the adopted isothermal conditions, and the area of the region where the mixture occurs (H_p), only the main results are presented in the paper.

A. Case 1

For this case, the following parameters are considered: $\varepsilon = 0.3$, $\kappa = 10^{-9}$ m², $v_A = 0.025$ m/s (velocity of input A), $v_B = 0.025$ (velocity of input B), $Df_a = Df_b = Df_c = 10^{-6}$ m²/s (diffusion coefficient of the species), $C_A = 7$ mol/m³ (initial concentration of species A) and $C_B = 1$ mol/m³ (initial concentration of species B). The concentration of species B (Figure 3) is homogeneously distributed in the reactor, except in the entrance duct of species A, where the concentration is zero. We notice that in the upper part of the reactor inside and just after the porous media where the concentration of B drops approximately to 0.7 mol/m³. Albeit this happens due to the system reaction, the lower part of the reactor remains practically the same as the initial concentration.

Fig. 3. Case 1: Distribution of the concentration of species B (mol/m³).

Fig. 4. Case 1: Distribution of the concentration of species C (mol/m³).

The way the reaction happens is shown in Figure 4. In the upper part of the reactor, almost there isn't any formation of species C in the lower region. This matches with the result presented in Figure 2, where species B has its concentration reduced in the upper region of the reactor. Note that, soon after the porous media, species C starts to become homogeneous in the solution. By the dimension of the high of the duct (Figure 5), it is possible to observe with more precision the concentration of the species B in the outlet of the reactor, which is between 0.78 mol/m³ and 0.94 mol/m³. Taking into consideration that the main objective of the process is to have the reduced concentration of the species B expelled from the reactor, it is not so efficient, since the substance entered the reactor where the initial concentration was 1 mol/m³ and had a maximum reduction of 20%.

Fig. 5. Case 1: Concentration of species B in the reactor outlet.

B. Case 2

Compared with Case 1, a change in velocity of $v_A = 0.075$ m/s is adopted. The increase of the entrance velocity of species A in the reactor resulted in the consumption of species B being much more pronounced than verified in Figure 6. Nevertheless, since the duct entrance radius was kept the same, it resulted in a raise of the velocity and consequently a proportional increase of the flow of species A, which means that 3 times more reagent A would be required to produce a change in concentration. This condition is not satisfactory since it would end up elevating the cost of the process.

Fig. 6. Case 2: Distribution of the concentration of species B (mol/m³).

C. Case 3

Compared with Case 1, here the C_A is assumed to be 10 mol/m³. In this case, changing only the C_A , resulted in a highly reduced variation of the limits presented in Figures 5 and 7. This means that the superior limit of approximately 0.94 changed to 0.92 mol/m³, and the inferior limit from 0.78 to 0.74. Both generate a very small "gain" when compared with an increase in the concentration of the species A.

Fig. 7. Case 3: Concentration of species B in the reactor outlet.

D. Case 4

In this simulation a change of $T_{iso} = 400$ K is adopted.

Fig. 8. Case 4: Distribution of the concentration of species C (mol/m³).

An increase of the temperature (isothermal) in the system favors the reaction (Figure 8), raising substantially the

generation of a species C , which reaches close to triple its value at its maximum point, 0.59 mol/m^3 versus 0.22 mol/m^3 in the parameter of Case 1. However, high heating, with an increase of 100°C might be costly and even making unfeasible to build a reactor due to the needed material thermal properties requirements.

E. Case 5

In this simulation a change of $H_p = 4 \text{ mm}$ is adopted. Likewise Case 3, this case (Figure 9) does not result in an expressive benefit in the decreasing of the species B in the reactor outlet, but still ends up with an increase of 33% in the size of the porous region.

Fig. 9. Case 5: Concentration of species B in the reactor outlet.

F. Case 6

In this simulation, a change of $d = 1 \text{ mm}$ is adopted. An increase in the distance of entrance of species A (Figure 10) towards the porous media in the reactor almost does not bring change to the process, even though it helps in the homogeneity of the solution, which can be seen by the concentration of the species C . The formation happens in a more distributed shape in the porous media.

Fig. 10. Case 6: Distribution of the concentration of species C (mol/m^3).

G. Optimization

Although most of the considered changes brought positive advantages, those resulted in a cost increase on the project coming from more expensive materials needed to build the reactor. This happens because the reactor had to withstand either extreme conditions or a considerable jump in the energy

consumption or the reagents. A possible solution tested was to add these changes on a reduced scale, indeed, increasing the velocity of entrance of the species A by 0.05 m/s rather than tripling its value. Making use of the following parameters: $v_A = 0.030 \text{ m/s}$, $C_A = 8 \text{ mol/m}^3$, $Ra = 0.45 \text{ mm}$, $Rai = 0.25 \text{ mm}$, $T_{iso} = 350 \text{ K}$, $H_p = 3.5 \text{ mm}$, $d = 1 \text{ mm}$, the results are presented in Figure 11.

Fig. 11. Optimization: Concentration of species B in the reactor outlet.

The results are satisfactory since a reduction of the concentration of B of approximately 50% can be obtained when compared with the inlet concentration.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper made use of many numerical simulations to analyze the way the geometrical and physical-chemical properties of a reactor of porous media could influence its efficiency, analyzing them separately or in a group. It was concluded that many of the changes suggested resulted in good results or at least some impact on the reactor operation manner. However, many of them bring problems with applications like a need for more specific and expensive materials to build the reactor, something that ends up as economically unfeasible. By applying minor changes in the parameters that could result in a decrease in the residual concentration of species B , the process was optimized rather than opting for a change in only one parameter.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge the financial support by CAPES (process number 23038.000263/2022-19).

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Weclas, "Potential of Porous-Media Combustion Technology as Applied to Internal Combustion Engines," *Journal of Thermodynamics*, vol. 2010, Feb. 2011, Art. no. e789262, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2010/789262>.
- [2] Z. G. Deng, R. Xiao, B. S. Jin, Q. L. Song, and H. Huang, "Multiphase CFD Modeling for a Chemical Looping Combustion Process (Fuel Reactor)," *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 31, no. 12, pp. 1754–1766, 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ceat.200800341>.
- [3] A. Abad, J. Adánez, L. F. de Diego, P. Gayán, F. García-Labiano, and A. Lyngfelt, "Fuel reactor model validation: Assessment of the key parameters affecting the chemical-looping combustion of coal," *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, vol. 19, pp. 541–551, Nov. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2013.10.020>.

-
- [4] W. A. Cutler, "Overview of Ceramic Materials for Diesel Particulate Filter Applications," in *28th International Conference on Advanced Ceramics and Composites A: Ceramic Engineering and Science Proceedings*, 2004, pp. 421–430, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470291184.ch61>.
- [5] J. P. Muhirwa, S. I. Mbalawata, and V. G. Masanja, "Markov Chain Monte Carlo Analysis of the Variable-Volume Exothermic Model for a Continuously Stirred Tank Reactor," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 6919–6929, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3962>.
- [6] H. A. Maddah, "Numerical Analysis for the Oxidation of Phenol with TiO₂ in Wastewater Photocatalytic Reactors," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3463–3469, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2304>.
- [7] S. Bekkouche and M. Kadja, "Numerical Analysis of Density-Driven Reactive Flows in Hele-Shaw Cell Geometry," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5434–5440, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3349>.
- [8] D. A. Nield and A. Bejan, *Convection in Porous Media*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2013.
- [9] *Subsurface Flow Module User's Guide v. 5.5*. Stockholm, Sweden: COMSOL, 2020.

Design of Protection Strategies and Performance Analysis of an HVDC Link During Multiple Disturbances

Abdelhadi Hameurlaine
Department of Electrical Engineering
University of Djelfa
Djelfa, Algeria
elhadi06@gmail.com

Haouari Sayah
Intelligent Control and Electrical Power System Laboratory
University of Sidi Bel-Abbes
Sidi Bel-Abbes, Algeria
housayah@yahoo.fr

Larbi Boukezzi
Materials Science and Informatics Laboratory (MSIL)
University of Djelfa
Djelfa, Algeria
larbiboukezzi@gmail.com

Received: 20 April 2022 | Revised: 9 May 2022 | Accepted: 13 May 2022

Abstract- In High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) transmission system applications, the control and protection system plays an essential role in the overall performance. This paper aims to give solutions to some performance problems that can occur in the HVDC link. In this paper, ways to mitigate this serious malfunction of the commutation failure process in the operation of HVDC converters are studied and protection functions like the Commutation Failure Prevention (CFPREV) have been used. Furthermore, HVDC transmission systems are vulnerable to DC faults and its protection becomes ever more important with the fast growth in the number of installations. In this context, the DC fault protection function is one of the most important challenges to the development of HVDC transmission systems. The dynamics of the studied power system including the HVDC link are thoroughly investigated in this paper through various simulation scenarios.

Keywords- commutation failure; control strategies; protection functions; HVDC; faults; performance

I. INTRODUCTION

High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) transmission systems are an excellent asset in modern power systems, mainly for their ability to overcome problems of AC transmission, such as the interconnection of asynchronous grids, stability of long transmission lines, and use of long cables for power transmission [1-4]. Due to environmental, technical, and economical reasons [2-6], the HVDC system is a mature technology but it has certain constraints such as the risk of commutation failures [3]. Commutation failures following AC system disturbances may occur in HVDC systems, especially in the inverter station. This fault is the result of the failure to complete commutation before the commutation voltage

reverses its polarity [5]. Furthermore, faults in the DC transmission system, which are generally pole-to-ground faults, block power transfer and are not likely to be of much significance unless voltage reduction occurs [7].

The objective of the current paper is to demonstrate ways to improve HVDC system performance, especially during large disturbances, such as three-phase faults on the AC side of the inverter and DC line faults at the rectifier side. Therefore, in this paper, the DC fault protection (DCPROT) is inserted to detect faults on the line and take the necessary actions to clear them [8]. The protective function Commutation Failure Prevention (CFPREV) is used in the inverter [9]. The control subsystem mitigates commutation failures due to AC voltage dips. Finally, in order to improve the dynamic performance of the proposed controller and protection devices, various simulation scenarios are tested. The main conclusion is that the reliability of an HVDC link depends on control and on the protection system.

II. SYSTEM MODELING AND CONTROL

In order to define the needs in terms of control and protection, the first step is to develop a model for the HVDC transmission system. HVDC systems traditionally use the fixed-parameter PI controller to control the DC line current and excitation angle [10], where the rectifier station controls the DC current through the firing angle (α) and the inverter controls voltage through the extinction angle (γ). In general, a typical basic monopolar HVDC system can be configured as shown in Figure 1 [11], where the schematic diagram and the equivalent circuit are shown in (a) and (b) respectively [12].

Fig. 1. HVDC transmission link: (a) schematic diagram, (b) equivalent circuit.

The direct current can be expressed using the equivalent circuits as [13]:

$$I_d = \frac{V_{d0r} \cos \alpha - V_{d0i} \cos \gamma}{R_{cr} + R_L - R_{ci}} \quad (1)$$

where R_{cr} and R_{ci} are the equivalent commutating resistances for rectifier and inverter respectively, and R_L is the line resistance. Both impedances are nonlinear and are not pure resistive, referred from converter side AC systems.

$$R_{cr} = \frac{3}{\pi} \omega L_c \text{ and } L_{cr} = L_{co} = L_c \quad (2)$$

where V_{d0r} and V_{d0i} are the ideal no-load rectifier and inverter voltages respectively, referred from converter side AC systems.

Therefore, the direct voltage V_d at any point on the line and the direct current I_d can be controlled by controlling the internal terminal voltages: $V_{d0r} \cos \alpha$ and $V_{d0i} \cos \gamma$. These two voltages can be controlled by controlling the firing instant of the thyristor or through the tap changing of the converter transformer. Another important control function is implemented to change the reference current according to the value of the DC voltage. This control, named Voltage Dependent Current Order Limiter (VDCOL) [9], automatically reduces the reference current set point when DC voltage decreases during a DC line fault or a severe AC fault. Reducing the reference currents also reduces the reactive power demand on the AC system, helping to recover from fault.

III. CONCEPTS OF THE PROPOSED PROTECTION

In this section, we insert two different protection devices associated with the proposed control strategy to improve the dynamic performance of an HVDC system. The first one, at the rectifier, is the DC fault protection (DCPROT) to detect and remove faults in the DC line. The second protection function is the commutation failure prevention (CFPREV) at the inverter, which controls subsystem commutation failures due to AC voltage dips. In this context, the expected behavior in steady state and stability problems are discussed in order to define the

needs in terms of control and protection. Moreover, the reliability of the HVDC control system depends on the regulators, but also on the protection sub-functions [14]. The actions that are taken by device protection systems when faults or dysfunctions occur are shown. To evaluate the performance of the proposed protection, simulation results are presented.

A. DC Protection Function

The protection is active in the rectifier. It will detect a fault on the DC side and will force the delay angle into the inverter region in order to extinguish the fault current [15]. The fault detection on the DC line is based on the drop in the line to ground voltage. The normal voltage polarity of the line is a parameter as well as the reference level of the fault detection. Delay time is used in the detection to discriminate between a line fault and other disturbances resulting in low DC voltage. A delay time of 200ms is allowed, after the DC system start-up, before activating the detection logic to make sure that the normal operating DC voltage is established. Also, an external signal generated by another protective detection will trigger a forced alpha during an adjustable interval sufficient to allow the deionization of the fault path prior to the re-application of voltage.

B. Commutation Failure Prevention Function

The objective of this device is to develop a control and protection strategy to accommodate large disturbances when an HVDC system is connected to a weak AC system [16]. This phenomenon is the result of the failure to complete commutation before the commutation voltage reverses its polarity, taking into account the need for sufficient extinction time for de-ionization and to re-establish the blocking ability. The protective function, used in the inverter, mitigates commutation failures due to AC voltage dips. After fault detection (three-phase or one-phase) an angle value is sent to the converter delay control in order to be deducted from the maximum delay angle limit. Commutation failure is the most common disoperation of an inverter due to the minimum limit on extinction angle gamma [17]. This puts a limit to the maximum firing angle for a successful inverter operation, as shown by the following equation:

$$\alpha = 180^\circ - (\beta + \gamma) \quad (3)$$

A signal transmitted to the VDCOL indicates the detection of a commutation failure, as this VDCOL function prevents the detection of commutation failure by the CFPREV module, the VDCOL transiently reduces the current in order to prevent the converter from excessive current [18]. To detect three-phase faults abc- $\alpha\beta$ transformation is used where, U_α and U_β may be expressed by:

$$\begin{cases} U_\alpha = \frac{1}{3}(2U_a - U_b - U_c) \\ U_\beta = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}(U_b - U_c) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The CLARK transformation [19] is used for three-phase fault detection and zero-sequence voltage evaluation. The

detection is based on instantaneous values, which ensure fast reaction of the control system when an AC fault occurs.

IV. SYSTEM STUDY

The HVDC system simulated in this study, is modeled based on the CIGRE HVDC benchmark system [20], as shown in Figure 2. The system is monopolar with a 12-pulse converter. The rectifier is connected to the strong AC system with a Short Circuit Ratio (SCR) of 5. The inverter is connected to the weak AC system with a SCR of 2.5.

Fig. 2. Basic configuration of the HVDC transmission system.

The model description follows [20].

The AC side of the HVDC system consists of a supply network, filters, and converter transformers. The AC supply network is modeled by a Thevenin equivalent with equivalent source impedance [22]. The filters are added to absorb the harmonics generated by the converter and to supply the reactive power needed by the converter. The DC side of each converter consists of a smoothing reactor. The DC transmission line connected to each converter station is represented by a T network. The 12-pulse converter station is configured by two universal bridge blocks in series. The universal bridge block implements a universal three-phase power converter that consists of up to six power switches connected in a bridge configuration[23]. The system parameters of the HVDC system are given in Table I.

TABLE I. HVDC SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value		
	AC side 1	AC side 2	DC side
AC voltage	500 kV	345 kV	-----
Reactive Power	5000 MVA	10000 MVA	-----
Frequency	60Hz	50Hz	-----
DC voltage	-----	-----	500 kV
DC current	-----	-----	2 kA
Active power	-----	-----	1000 MW
DC cable length	-----	-----	300 km
Smoothing reactors	-----	-----	0.5 H

V. SIMULATION RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In this section the behavior of the HVDC transmission system is analyzed. In order to test the controllers and the proposed protection functions, two different scenarios will be simulated in order to analyze the dynamic performance. During

the first scenario, a DC line fault on the rectifier side is applied to observe the DC fault protection action. In the second one, a three-phase-to-ground fault on the AC side of the inverter is studied to evaluate CFPREV control. In both scenarios, the waveforms for electrical quantities like DC voltage, DC current, and firing delay angle α are presented and analyzed during the application of faults, at rectifier and inverter side, and finally, the corresponding inverter side AC voltage and AC current waveforms are shown.

A. First Scenario: DC System Faults

The scenario is shown in Figure 3. This fault is applied at $t = 0.7s$ for a duration of 50ms. The DC current increases quickly until 2.22p.u., and it is cancelled at the inverter side.

Fig. 3. DC fault on the rectifier side.

The DC voltage falls to zero at the rectifier. This DC voltage drop is seen by the VDCOL through DC fault protection. The VDCOL reduces the reference current to

0.28p.u. at the rectifier. A DC current still continues circulating in the fault. At $t=0.78s$, the rectifier firing angle α is forced to be 166° by the DC protection function after detecting a low DC voltage. In this situation the rectifier operates in inverter mode. The DC line voltage becomes negative and the energy stored in the line is returned to the AC system. Then α is released at $t=0.83s$ and the DC voltage and the current recover in approximately 0.5s.

B. Second Scenario: AC System Faults

Three-phase-to-ground fault is applied at the AC side of the inverter at $t=0.7s$ and is cleared at $t=0.75s$. Figure 4 shows the inverter side, the DC voltage, DC current and firing delay angle during the fault. The oscillation of the DC voltage and current waveform are primarily caused by the controller action.

Fig. 4. Three-phase-to-ground AC fault on the inverter side.

The DC voltage at the inverter drops and the DC current increases rapidly to 2.22p.u. on the inverter side. When the

fault is cleared at $t=0.8s$, the control function (VDCOL) operates and reduces the reference current to 0.3p.u.. The system recovers in approximately 0.35s after fault clearing. During the fault period, the DC voltage oscillates around zero due to the commutation failure on the inverter side. The control scheme provides smoother operation of the converter firing angles, which is shown in waveform firing angle.

Furthermore, Figure 5(a)-(b) shows the phase AC voltage and AC current waveforms at the inverter side, for a three-phase-to-ground fault. The AC fault does not affect the rectifier side AC system because the rectifier is connected to a strong AC system. The AC voltage becomes nearly zero, after the fault is cleared, the inverter side AC voltage increased to 1.53p.u.. The AC currents at the inverter shows minor disturbance and high amplitude fault current flows with oscillations.

Fig. 5. Voltage and current responses under three phase to ground fault at the inverter.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper focuses mainly on the HVDC performance assessment dynamic state under various scenarios. First, the dynamic response of the HVDC system is analyzed under unbalanced grid conditions. In a typical HVDC link, the rectifier station controls the DC current through the firing angle and the inverter station controls voltage through the extinction angle. The faults associated with an HVDC system are cleared through the action of protection devices. The protection devices thus play a vital role in the satisfactory operation of the HVDC systems. Simulation results show clearly that the reliability of an HVDC control system does not depend only on the

controller, but also on protection functions. In this paper, the actions that are taken by some HVDC link protection systems when faults or dysfunctions occur are presented. The obtained results demonstrate that the DC fault line is eliminated by the rectifier operation in inverter mode through the increase of its firing angle to ensure the extinction of the residual current. This necessary action, is ensured by the DC protection device. For three-phase faults, the commutation failure prevention greatly reduces the risk of repeated commutation failures. Finally, from the simulation results, it can be seen that the system works stably with the purposed protection devices and the fixed parameter PI controller applied to an HVDC system. The protection devices implemented in this paper showed good performance under various scenarios. However, more extensive studies can be conducted in the future. Future work should explore other possibilities and routes in which this paper could lead to. The main perspectives should include:

- The development of a Voltage Source Converter (VSC), with the insertion of these protection devices applied to the conventional HVDC link.
- Protection and implementation of nonlinear control algorithms for VSC-HVDC systems.

APPENDIX

ABBREVIATIONS

AC	Alternating Current
DC	Direct Current
DCPROT	Direct Current Fault Protection
CFPREV	Commutation Failure Prevention
HVDC	High Voltage Direct Current
VDCOL	Voltage Dependent Current Order Limiter

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Arrillaga, N. R. Watson, and Y. H. Liu, *Flexible Power Transmission: The HVDC Options*, 1st ed. Chichester, UK; Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2007.
- [2] V. K. Sood, *HVDC and FACTS Controllers: Applications of Static Converters in Power Systems*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2006.
- [3] H. Abdelhadi and Z. Sid-Ahmed, *Amélioration des performances et protection des liaisons CCHT*. Éditions Universitaires Européennes, 2015.
- [4] H. Huang, Z. Xu, and X. Lin, "Improving performance of multi-infeed HVDC systems using grid dynamic segmentation technique based on fault current limiters," in *2013 IEEE Power Energy Society General Meeting*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, Jul. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PESMG.2013.6672672>.
- [5] H. Abdelhadi, H. Sayah, and M. Boudiaf, "Improvement of the VSC-HVDC System Performances Based on the Intelligent Controller," *Majlesi Journal of Electrical Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 51–59, Dec. 2019.
- [6] R. S. Narayan, S. Mohan, and K. Sunitha, "Simulative Study into the Development of a Hybrid HVDC System Through a Comparative Research with HVAC: a Futuristic Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1600–1604, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1192>.
- [7] Y. A. Mobarak, A. M. Hemeida, A. El-Bahnasawy, and M. M. Hamada, "Reactive Power Compensation on Egypt Electricity Network for Optimal Energy Saving," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3699–3704, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2451>.
- [8] H. Yin, L. Fan, and Z. Miao, "Fast power routing through HVDC," in *2013 IEEE Power Energy Society General Meeting*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, Jul. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PESMG.2013.6672586>.
- [9] R. Pierre, "Dynamic Modeling and Control of Multi-Terminal HVDC Grids," Ph.D. dissertation, Ecole Centrale Lille, Lille, France, 2014.
- [10] H. Bassi and Y. A. Mobarak, "State-Space Modeling and Performance Analysis of Variable-Speed Wind Turbine Based on a Model Predictive Control Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1436–1443, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1015>.
- [11] J. Yang, J. E. Fletcher, and J. O'Reilly, "Short-Circuit and Ground Fault Analyses and Location in VSC-Based DC Network Cables," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 59, no. 10, pp. 3827–3837, Jul. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2011.2162712>.
- [12] A. Hameurlaine, S.-A. Zidi, A. Kouzou, and M. A. Djehaf, "Improvement of the HVDC link performances based on the protection functions," in *2015 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Technology (ICIT)*, Seville, Spain, Mar. 2015, pp. 2714–2720, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIT.2015.7125498>.
- [13] J. Sau-Bassols, E. Prieto-Araujo, O. Gomis-Bellmunt, and F. Hassan, "Selective Operation of Distributed Current Flow Controller Devices for Meshed HVDC Grids," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 107–118, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRD.2018.2848547>.
- [14] M. Monadi, C. Gavriluta, A. Luna, J. I. Candela, and P. Rodriguez, "Centralized Protection Strategy for Medium Voltage DC Microgrids," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 430–440, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRD.2016.2600278>.
- [15] A. Swetapadma, S. Chakrabarti, and A. Y. Abdelaziz, "Feasibility study of intelligent fault location estimation methods for double-circuit transmission lines," *International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems*, vol. 31, no. 12, 2021, Art. no. e13198, <https://doi.org/10.1002/2050-7038.13198>.
- [16] N. Dhaliwal, L. Crowe, R. Kolt, and M. Rashwan, "Replacement of Control and Protection in Line Commutated Converter (LCC) HVDC Systems," in *2021 AEIT HVDC International Conference (AEIT HVDC)*, Genoa, Italy, 2021.
- [17] C. Li, X. Bie, W. Ma, X. Liu, and X. Guo, "Study on Control and Protection Strategy of Neutral Bus Switch in HVDC Flexible Transmission System," in *2019 4th IEEE Workshop on the Electronic Grid (eGRID)*, Xiamen, China, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/eGRID48402.2019.9092679>.
- [18] C. Wu, D. Zhang, and J. He, "A Novel Protection Scheme for MMC-HVdc Transmission Lines Based on Cross-Entropy of Charge," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 222800–222812, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3043854>.
- [19] W. Leterme, P. Tielens, S. De Boeck, and D. Van Hertem, "Overview of Grounding and Configuration Options for Meshed HVDC Grids," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 29, no. 6, pp. 2467–2475, Sep. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRD.2014.2331106>.
- [20] H. R. Wickramasinghe, G. Konstantinou, Z. Li, and J. Pou, "Alternate Arm Converters-Based HVDC Model Compatible With the CIGRE B4 DC Grid Test System," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 149–159, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRD.2018.2850933>.
- [21] X. Chen, H. Li, G. Wang, C. Xu, and Y. Liang, "A Convolution Power-Based Protection Scheme for Hybrid Multiterminal HVDC Transmission Systems," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 1655–1667, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JESTPE.2020.2978262>.
- [22] X. Li *et al.*, "HVdc Reactor Reduction Method Based on Virtual Reactor Fault Current Limiting Control of MMC," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 67, no. 12, pp. 9991–10000, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2019.2960735>.
- [23] S. Dey and T. Bhattacharya, "A Transformerless DC–DC Modular Multilevel Converter for Hybrid Interconnections in HVDC," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 68, no. 7, pp. 5527–5536, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2020.2994889>.

Hybrid Grey Wolf and Finite Element Method (GWO-FEM) Algorithm for Enhancing High Voltage Insulator String Performance in Wet Pollution Conditions

Dyhia Doufene

Department of Electrical Engineering
Electrical and Industrial System Laboratory (LSEI)
University of Science and Technology Houari Boumediene
Bab Ezzouar, Algeria
doufenedyhia@yahoo.fr

Samira Benharat

Department of Electrical Engineering
Electrical and Industrial System Laboratory (LSEI)
University of Science and Technology Houari Boumediene
Bab Ezzouar, Algeria
sbenharat@hotmail.fr

Slimane Bouazabia

Department of Electrical Engineering
Electrical and Industrial System Laboratory (LSEI)
University of Science and Technology Houari Boumediene
Bab Ezzouar, Algeria
sbouazabia@yahoo.fr

Sid Ahmed Bessedik

Department of Electrical Engineering
Université Amar Telidji de Laghouat
Laghouat, Algeria
s.bessedik@lagh-univ.dz

Received: 12 April 2022 | Revised: 29 April 2022, 3 May 2022, and 7 May 2022 | Accepted: 12 May 2022

Abstract- The presence of wet pollution on the upper surface of a string insulator increases the electric field on the insulator surface, especially at the triple junction (pin-cement, cement-porcelain) as well as at the surrounding air of the insulator. The rise of the electric field leads to the ionization of the air surrounding the insulator. This phenomenon, called corona discharge, is accompanied by several consequences that are harmful to the electricity transmission network, such as electromagnetic interferences, energy losses, visible light, audible noise, and the destruction of materials by erosion. If favorable conditions are gathered, it may even cause the flashover of the insulator. Designing an optimal insulator shape that reduces this electric field value at the triple junction will be an important achievement in enhancing the performance of electrical grids. The objective of this paper is to evolve a hybrid algorithm based on the GWO-FEM for optimizing the shape and the electrical performance of a string insulator. To achieve this purpose, this work is structured in four parts. First, modeling of the insulator string geometry is conducted in Comsol-multiphysics, then FEM computation of the electric field on the polluted surface of the string insulator is completed, and the maximum electric field value at the triple junction is saved as the fitness function that will be sent to the GWO algorithm to be optimized (minimized). The third part of the work is devoted to the coding of the constrained (electrical and geometrical constraints) GWO algorithm in a Matlab interface, and finally, coupling the GWO code with the FEM code. This study is achieved in wet polluted conditions. The results are given in both 2D and 3D representations. From the obtained results we can confirm that

the developed GWO-FEM hybrid algorithm for optimizing insulator strings is a very promising tool for designing and enhancing the shape and the electrical performance of insulators.

Keywords- insulator design; grey wolf optimisation; finite element method; 3D electric field

I. INTRODUCTION

Transmission and distribution lines constitute the link between production and consumers. These lines are held by insulating strings [1]. Their performance is crucial for the good functioning of the electrical network. It is well established by experimental studies and confirmed by simulations [2-8], that the highest electric field value around an insulating string is found on the last pin in contact with the high voltage conductor, more exactly at the triple junction (pin-cement, cement-porcelain), which also corresponds to the highest thermal point [9], therefore, these areas are very critical in high voltage lines. The presence of high electric field leads to corona discharges by ionizing the surrounding air of the insulator, resulting in energy losses, electromagnetic interferences, visible light, audible noise, and the destruction of materials by erosion [10-12]. When the electric field stress exceeds a threshold value, especially in the presence of pollution conditions [13], flashover of the insulator string may occur. Thus, finding the insulating string design that can reduce the critical value of the electric field at the triple junction region, and at the same time reduce the weight of the insulator

constitutes, a considerable advantage for improving the performance of electrical networks. It is here where the contribution of the present paper is registered.

Designing an improved shape of the insulator string involves taking into account many constraints, such as electrical, mechanical, environmental and economic, so using simulations prior to real testing and manufacturing is money and time saving. Recent works carried out concerning the improvement of the high voltage insulators performance based on optimization methods, are divided into two main categories: (i) optimizing the shape of the chain elements [14-23] and (ii) grading ring optimization [24-25]. This research aims to study a hybrid algorithm based on the Grey Wolf Optimization and the Finite Element Method (GWO-FEM) for designing an insulator sting and enhancing its electrical and geometrical performance. The current paper brings a complementarity to fill some existing gaps in the field of designing high voltage insulators. Its main contributions are:

- The proposal of the new hybrid GWO-FEM algorithm for insulator optimization.
- Corona ring optimization and one-element insulator optimization have been already done in previous studies, but, to the best of our knowledge, total string optimization is achieved for the first time in this paper.
- By using optimization constraints, two goals are achieved, namely reduction of the electric field value at the triple junction and of the weight of the insulator string.
- 3D geometry representation and electric field distribution were conducted.
- The most significant contribution of this work is the pollution case study which is conducted for the first time in this paper.

To accomplish the above contributions, this work is divided into four main parts:

- Modeling of the insulator string geometry in Comsol-multiphysics.
- FEM computation of the electric field on the insulation surface of the insulator and saving the maximum electric field value at the triple junction as the fitness function that will be sent to the GWO algorithm to be optimized.
- Coding of the constrained GWO algorithm in Matlab [26-27].
- Coupling of the GWO code with the FEM code.

II. INSULATOR GEOMETRY MODELING

Figure 1 shows one element of the studied 6-element string insulator. The parameters of the insulators are given in Table I. The model is a string insulator of 6 elements of an U400B glass insulator commonly used in the Algerian power grid. The modeling of the insulator geometry in Comsol-multiphysics is represented in 2D and 3D in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. U400B model.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF THE INSULATOR STRING

Dimensions [cm]			Applied voltage [kV]	
Shed diameter (D)	Unit spacing (H)	Creepage distance (L)	Pin	Cap
32.0	20.5	435	100	0

Fig. 2. The reference 6-element string insulator. (a) 2D, (b) 3D.

A wet pollution layer (Figure 3) is put on the upper surface of each element of the string. The thickness of the pollution layer is 0.5mm. The pollution layer is in contact with the earthed cap. The material parameters used for the simulation are given in Table II.

Fig. 3. Zoom in the pollution layer.

TABLE II. MATERIAL PARAMETERS OF THE SIMULATION MODEL

Material	Permittivity	Conductivity [S/m]
Air	1	0
Glass	5.59	10-14
Iron	106	5,998.107
Cement	5.9	10-12
Pollution	80	10-4

III. FEM COMPUTATION OF POTENTIAL AND ELECTRIC FIELD

After the meshing process, potential and electric field distributions are computed by solving (1) and (2) by using FEM.

$$\Delta V=0 \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{E} = -\vec{\nabla} V \quad (2)$$

where E represents the electric field and V is the electric potential.

The electric potential varies from 100kV from the pin to 0V on the cap as shown in Figure 4 giving the potential repartition along the creepage distance of the insulator string.

Fig. 4. Electric potential repartition on the creepage path of the insulator string.

From the electric field repartition (Figure 5), starting from the pin towards the cap, we record a maximum value of 190kV/cm at the last pin. This obtained result is in adequacy with the results from the literature review [2-9], which attest that the highest electric field value is located at the last pin of the string connected to the high voltage and exactly at the triple junction. So, for the optimization purpose, the maximum electric field E_{max} recorded at this triple junction is saved as the

fitness function and is sent to the GWO cod to be optimized (minimized). The potential and electric field distribution in 2D and 3D are given in Figures 6 and 7 respectively. A zoom in the last pin shows clearly the triple junction with the highest electric field value.

Fig. 5. Electric field repartition on the creepage path of the insulator string.

Fig. 6. Electric potential distribution for the insulator sting. a) 2D, (b) 3D.

Fig. 7. Electric field distribution for the insulator sting. a) 2D, (b) 3D.

IV. OPTIMIZATION PROCESS USING GWO

The principle of the GWO algorithm [28] is based on reproducing the hunting technique of grey wolves and modeling mathematically their social hierarchy. Four categories can be noticed in wolf population. The α (alpha), β (beta), and δ (delta) wolves represent the optimal solutions for the optimization problem. The last category is the ω (omega) wolves, which are the followers [28, 30]. The mathematical modeling of the steps of the hunting process is given below.

- Encircling: (surrounding the prey while hunting), is modeled by (3) and (4):

$$\vec{D} = |\vec{C} \cdot \vec{X}_p(t) - \vec{X}(t)| \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{X}(t+1) = \vec{X}_p(t) - \vec{A} \cdot \vec{D} \quad (4)$$

where t is the current iteration, X_p and X are the positions of the prey and the grey wolf respectively, C and A are the coefficient vectors calculated by (5) and (6):

$$\vec{A} = 2 \cdot \vec{a}(t) \cdot \vec{r}_1 - \vec{a}(t) \quad (5)$$

$$\vec{C} = 2 \cdot \vec{r}_2 \quad (6)$$

The elements of the vector a linearly decrease from 2 to 0, and r_1, r_2 are random vectors in $[0,1]$.

- Hunting: Equations (7)-(9) reproduce the hunting model:

$$\begin{cases} \vec{D}_\alpha = |\vec{C}_1 \cdot \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{X}(t)| \\ \vec{D}_\beta = |\vec{C}_2 \cdot \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{X}(t)| \\ \vec{D}_\delta = |\vec{C}_3 \cdot \vec{X}_\delta - \vec{X}(t)| \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where $C_1, C_2,$ and C_3 are obtained by (6).

$$\begin{cases} \vec{X}_1(t) = \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{A}_1 \cdot (\vec{D}_\alpha(t)) \\ \vec{X}_2(t) = \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{A}_2 \cdot (\vec{D}_\beta(t)) \\ \vec{X}_3(t) = \vec{X}_\delta - \vec{A}_3 \cdot (\vec{D}_\delta(t)) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $X_\alpha, X_\beta,$ and X_δ are the first three best solutions at iteration $t, A_1, A_2,$ and A_3 are obtained from (5), and $D_\alpha, D_\beta,$ and D_δ are obtained from (7).

$$\vec{X}(t+1) = \frac{\vec{X}_1(t) + \vec{X}_2(t) + \vec{X}_3(t)}{3} \quad (9)$$

- Attacking: when the prey representing the optimal solution, can no longer move, the wolves launch the attack, which marks the end of the hunt. This process is mathematically reproduced by decreasing the value of a linearly from 2 to 0.

V. GWO AND FEM COUPLING

The hybrid GWO-FEM algorithm is obtained by following the different steps given in the flowchart of Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Flowchart of the GWO-FEM algorithm process.

VI. OPTIMIZATION RESULTS

The different lengths (L_1 to L_4), shown in Figure 9 are taken as the optimization variables. A constraint is imposed to the total creepage length to not exceed the reference length of the

industrial model in order to obtain a shape with a reduced creepage distance and as a consequence reduced weight of the insulator. The stopping criterion of the hybrid algorithm is 150 iterations [15]. The obtained shape of the optimized insulator string is given in Figure 10. A comparative analysis of the results before and after optimization is established in Table III.

Fig. 9. The optimization variables.

Fig. 10. Optimized shape of the string insulator.

TABLE III. OPTIMIZATION RESULTS

	Reference string	Optimized string
l_1 [cm]	3.30	0.50
l_{11} [cm]	3.40	0.60
l_2 [cm]	3.85	0.14
l_{22} [cm]	4.03	0.32
l_3 [cm]	3.50	0.130
l_4 [cm]	1.16	5
Creepage distance [cm]	435	324
Creepage length reduction (%)	25	
Electric field at the triple junction [kV/cm]	190	177
Electric field reduction at the triple junction region (%)	8	
The diametrical surface of the insulating glass surface [cm ²]	435.7	369.7
Reduction of the surface value of the insulating glass surface [%]	15.14	

The potential and the electric field distributions after optimization are given in Figures 11 and 12 respectively. The potential and electric field repartition along the creepage distance (from the pin to the cap) on the optimized insulator string are registered in Figures 13 and 14 respectively.

Fig. 11. Electric potential distribution for the optimized insulator sting. (a) 2D, (b) 3D.

Fig. 12. Electric field distribution for the optimized insulator sting. (a) 2D, (b) 3D.

Fig. 13. Electric potential repartition on the creepage path of the optimized string insulator.

Fig. 14. Electric field repartition on the creepage path of the optimized string insulator. (a) On the creepage path (from the pin to the cap), (b) zoom at the triple junction point (the last pin connected to the high voltage).

VII. DISCUSSION

From the comparative analysis between the cases before and after optimization (Table III), we can clearly notice the efficiency of the proposed optimization method since the two objectives set in this work, namely the reduction of the electric field and the creepage distance, have been correctly achieved. The developed GWO-FEM hybrid algorithm for optimizing insulator strings is a promising technique for designing and

enhancing the shape and the electrical performance of insulators. The comparative analysis carried out between the reference string and the optimized one in the presence of a wet pollution shows the following findings :

- A decrease of 8% in the electric field at the triple junction of the last insulator connected to the high voltage was recorded. This reduction constitutes a major advantage with regard to the reduction of corona discharges at the surface of the insulator, and consequently a decline of the noise, the light, and the electromagnetic interferences issued from the ionization phenomenon of the air particles surrounding the insulator string. Other positive consequences are the elongation of the insulator lifetime following the reduction of the corrosive effect of the corona discharges and the reduced risk of insulator flashover.
- Creepage length decreased by 25% and the diametral surface of the string insulator by 15.14%, which represent a huge advantage resulting in an important weight decrease and thus improving the economic aspect of the manufacturing of the insulators.
- The 3D study gives a more realistic aspect to the achieved results.

Comparing the obtained results with [23, 24], where the objective function (the electric field at the pin region) is predicted using Artificial Neural Networks, big similarity in the obtained shape after optimization is noticed.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The developed GWO-FEM hybrid algorithm provides very satisfactory results, therefore it can be used as a powerful tool for designing high voltage insulators in general. With this hybrid algorithm, optimal design of the insulator string is reached, satisfying two constraints: an electrical constraint (minimizing the maximum electric field value) and a geometrical constraint (minimizing the weight of the insulator string). The main advantage of the proposed hybrid algorithm is the possibility of combining other constraints that are involved in the flashover of high voltage insulators, such as the dry band formation, NSDD encapsulation, water draining, and also mechanical and thermal stresses can be taken into account, which is possible with the use of the computation interface of Comsol-multiphysics that allows multiphysics studies at the same time and thus permitting the obtainment of an optimal design encompassing all the stresses undergone by the insulator string.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research and the Directorate General for Scientific Research and Technological Development who provided the scholarship for visiting the high voltage laboratory at the School of Engineering at Cardiff University.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Pylarinos and I. Pellas, "Investigation of an Insulator Flashover in an 150 kV OTL of the Power System of Crete," *Engineering, Technology &*

- Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4851–4858, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3198>.
- [2] E. Akbari, M. Mirzaie, M. B. Asadpoor, and A. Rahimnejad, "Effects of Disc Insulator Type and Corona Ring on Electric Field and Voltage Distribution over 230-kV Insulator String by Numerical Method," *Iranian Journal of Electrical and Electronic Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 44–57, Mar. 2013.
- [3] V. T. Kontargyri, I. F. Gonos, and I. A. Stathopoulos, "Measurement and simulation of the electric field of high voltage suspension insulators," *European Transactions on Electrical Power*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 509–517, 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1002/etep.238>.
- [4] A. J. Phillips *et al.*, "Electric Fields on AC Composite Transmission Line Insulators," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 823–830, Apr. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRD.2007.911127>.
- [5] T. Doshi, R. S. Gorur, and J. Hunt, "Electric field computation of composite line insulators up to 1200 kV AC," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 861–867, Jun. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2011.5931075>.
- [6] Y. Qing, W. Sima, D. Jiazhao, Y. Tao, and C. Lin, "New optimization method on electric field distribution of composite insulator," in *Annual Report Conference on Electrical Insulation and Dielectric Phenomena*, West Lafayette, IN, Oct. 2010, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CEIDP.2010.5724046>.
- [7] Y. Zhang *et al.*, "Flashover Performance Test with Lightning Impulse and Simulation Analysis of Different Insulators in a 110 kV Double-Circuit Transmission Tower," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 3, Mar. 2018, Art. no. 659, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11030659>.
- [8] C. A. Christodoulou, V. Vita, V. Mladenov, and L. Ekonomou, "On the Computation of the Voltage Distribution along the Non-Linear Resistor of Gapless Metal Oxide Surge Arresters," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 11, Nov. 2018, Art. no. 3046, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11113046>.
- [9] D. Doufene, S. Bouazabia, and R. Bouhaddiche, "Heating Dissipation Study of a Pollution Layer on a Cap and Pin Insulator," in *International Conference on Communications and Electrical Engineering*, El Oued, Algeria, Dec. 2018, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCEE.2018.8634549>.
- [10] O. G. Gryb, I. T. Karpaliuk, A. O. Zaporozhets, S. V. Shvets, and N. V. Rudevich, "Acoustic Diagnostics for Determining the Appearance of Corona Discharge," in *Control of Overhead Power Lines with Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs)*, Y. I. Sokol and A. O. Zaporozhets, Eds. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2021, pp. 127–157.
- [11] I. O. Zaitsev and V. V. Kuchanskyy, "Corona Discharge Problem in Extra High Voltage Transmission Line," in *Systems, Decision and Control in Energy II*, A. Zaporozhets and V. Artemchuk, Eds. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2021, pp. 3–30.
- [12] A. V. Golenishchev-Kutuzov, V. A. Golenishchev-Kutuzov, D. A. Ivanov, G. D. Mardanov, A. V. Semennikov, and Yu. V. Van'kov, "Complex Diagnostics of Defects in High-Voltage Insulators," *Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Sciences: Physics*, vol. 83, no. 12, pp. 1490–1493, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.3103/S1062873819120062>.
- [13] M. Dimitropoulou, D. Pylarinos, K. Siderakis, E. Thalassinakis, and M. Danikas, "Comparative Investigation of Pollution Accumulation and Natural Cleaning for Different HV Insulators," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 764–774, Apr. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.545>.
- [14] S. F. Stefenon, C. S. Furtado Neto, T. S. Coelho, A. Nied, C. K. Yamaguchi, and K.-C. Yow, "Particle swarm optimization for design of insulators of distribution power system based on finite element method," *Electrical Engineering*, vol. 104, no. 2, pp. 615–622, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00202-021-01332-3>.
- [15] D. Doufene, S. Bouazabia, S. A. Bessedik, and K. Ouzzir, "Grey Wolf Optimizer Algorithm for Suspension Insulator Designing," in *Sixth International Congress on Information and Communication Technology*, London, UK, Feb. 2021, pp. 763–771, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-2380-6_67.
- [16] K. Bhattacharya, S. Chakravorti, and P. K. Mukherjee, "Insulator contour optimization by a neural network," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 157–161, Apr. 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1109/94.919908>.
- [17] W. Chen, H. Yang, and H. Huang, "Optimal Design of Support Insulators Using Hashing Integrated Genetic Algorithm and Optimized Charge Simulation Method," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 426–433, Apr. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2008.4483461>.
- [18] W.-S. Chen, H.-T. Yang, and H.-Y. Huang, "Contour Optimization of Suspension Insulators Using Dynamically Adjustable Genetic Algorithms," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 1220–1228, Jul. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRD.2010.2046187>.
- [19] D. Doufene, S. Bouazabia, and A. Haddad, "Optimised performance of cap and pin insulator under wet pollution conditions using a mono-objective genetic algorithm," *Australian Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 149–162, Jul. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1448837X.2019.1627740>.
- [20] S. Banerjee, A. Lahiri, and K. Bhattacharya, "Optimization of support insulators used in HV systems using support vector machine," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 360–367, Apr. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2007.344616>.
- [21] D. Doufene, S. Bouazabia, and A. Haddad, "Shape and electric performance improvement of an insulator string using particles swarm algorithm," *IET Science, Measurement & Technology*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 198–205, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-smt.2019.0405>.
- [22] D. Doufene, S. Bouazabia, A. A. Ladjici, and A. Haddad, "Polluted insulator optimization using neural network combined with genetic algorithms," in *18th International Symposium on Electromagnetic Fields in Mechatronics, Electrical and Electronic Engineering*, Lodz, Poland, Sep. 2017, pp. 1–2, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISEF.2017.8090689>.
- [23] D. Doufene, S. Bouazabia, and A. A. Ladjici, "Shape optimization of a cap and pin insulator in pollution condition using particle swarm and neural network," in *5th International Conference on Electrical Engineering - Boumerdes*, Boumerdes, Algeria, Oct. 2017, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEE-B.2017.8192094>.
- [24] B. M'hamdi, M. Tegar, and A. Mekhaldi, "Optimal design of corona ring on HV composite insulator using PSO approach with dynamic population size," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 1048–1057, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2015.005383>.
- [25] D. Nie, H. Zhang, Z. Chen, X. Shen, and Z. Du, "Optimization design of grading ring and electrical field analysis of 800 kV UHVDC Wall wall bushing," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 1361–1368, Aug. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDEI.2013.6571457>.
- [26] D. Pylarinos, "A Custom-made MATLAB Based Software to Manage Leakage Current Waveforms," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 36–42, Apr. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.31>.
- [27] G. Satheesh, B. Basavaraja, and P. M. Nirgude, "Electric Field Simulation Around Contaminated SIR Insulators Using MATLAB," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2542–2545, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1742>.
- [28] S. Mirjalili, S. M. Mirjalili, and A. Lewis, "Grey Wolf Optimizer," *Advances in Engineering Software*, vol. 69, pp. 46–61, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advengsoft.2013.12.007>.
- [29] M. H. Nadimi-Shahraki, S. Taghian, and S. Mirjalili, "An improved grey wolf optimizer for solving engineering problems," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 166, Mar. 2021, Art. no. 113917, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2020.113917>.
- [30] S. Arora, H. Singh, M. Sharma, S. Sharma, and P. Anand, "A New Hybrid Algorithm Based on Grey Wolf Optimization and Crow Search Algorithm for Unconstrained Function Optimization and Feature Selection," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 26343–26361, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2897325>.

Implementation of a Hybrid Technique for the Predictive Control of the Residential Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning Systems

Mitali Ray

School of Electrical Engineering
KIIT Deemed to be University
Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India
mitaliray87@gmail.com

Padarbinda Samal

School of Electrical Engineering
KIIT Deemed to be University
Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India
padarbindasamal87@gmail.com

Chinmoy Kumar Panigrahi

School of Electrical Engineering
KIIT Deemed to be University
Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India
panigrahichinmoy@gmail.com

Received: 29 April 2022 | Accepted: 15 May 2022

Abstract—Since daily energy needs are increasing, it is imperative to find ways to save energy, such as improving the energy consumption of buildings. Heating Ventilating and Air-Conditioning (HVAC) loads account for the majority of a building's energy use. The accurate estimation of energy consumption and the examination of various ways to improve the energy efficiency of buildings are very important. This paper presents an analysis of HVAC loads in a residential building by examining three Neural Networks (NNs): Feed-Forward (FF), Cascaded Forward Backpropagation (CFBP), and Elman Backpropagation (EBP) networks, based on Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Square Error (MSE), and Mean Relative Error (MRE). Furthermore, these networks were combined in hybrid NNs to obtain more optimized results. These results were also compared with other approaches and showed better prediction performance.

Keywords—HVAC loads; neural networks; energy management; hybrid networks

I. INTRODUCTION

The building sector, which includes both residential and commercial structures, is responsible for up to 36% of global energy use, according to the Energy Information Administration (EIA) [1]. Since 2015, worldwide energy consumption in the residential sector and transportation has climbed at a pace of 1.1% per year according to the International Energy Agency. According to EIA, global energy consumption in the commercial sector is predicted to grow at a pace of 1.2% per year from 2015 to 2040. The rise in energy consumption due to buildings is predicted to be bigger in developing than in developed countries. To reduce energy consumption in buildings, a nation's main objective in terms of

the policy is to make them more energy-efficient. Factors that influence energy efficiency management in a building include occupancy levels, heating and cooling loads, the climatic zone, and the exterior envelope of the building.

The prediction and study of energy consumption in buildings are carried out using energy simulation tools, which are frequently used in the construction industry and assist in the design of buildings and efficient management of their energy use [2]. These tools have limitations such as long computational times and the requirement of programming expertise [3]. There are also applications using machine learning tools that are comparatively faster and more convenient [3]. Once a model is properly trained, obtaining answers by modifying a few parameters of the building's design becomes quite simple. The use of Support Vector Machine (SVM) to predict the energy consumption of buildings in a tropical environment was examined in [4]. An SVM was used to forecast the cooling demand of a building on an hourly basis in [5]. Several regression models were created and validated to anticipate the heating demand of residential buildings in [3]. The use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) has been explored in different diversified areas [6-8].

In residential buildings, ANNs are used to forecast Heating Load (HL) and Cooling Load (CL) based on various characteristics of the buildings [6, 10-12]. Although it is a substantial characteristic, the glazing area does not appear to be connected to HL or CL, which is an important limitation of [6]. This paper presents a comparative analysis and hybridization of NNs for forecasting the heating and cooling loads of an HVAC system. MAE, MSE, and MRE were taken as performance indicators, considering eight input variables.

II. NEURAL NETWORKS

An ANN is a series of algorithms that aspires to establish a correlation among a set of data through a certain procedure that replicates the human brain operation. An ANN refers to a system of neurons, either organic or artificial. ANNs are used as problem-solving methods, with the capability of developing solutions to extremely difficult problems and uncovering hidden patterns in large datasets. This results in a collection of approaches that can be employed to provide a fast and cost-effective solution to a complex real-world challenge. Moreover, ANNs have self-learning abilities to produce the output, which is not limited to the inputs provided to them. ANNs were used in [8, 9] to predict thermal loads and in [10] to analyze the energy consumption of a building. In this work, the implementation of hybrid ANNs was performed by considering the sequential combination of any two ANNs among FeedForward (FF), Cascaded Forward Back-Propagation (CFBP), and Elman Back-Propagation (EBP) to estimate the thermal loads of a residential building. Furthermore, a comparative analysis was conducted with other approaches to validate the results.

A. Feedforward Network

FF ANNs are used to learn the mapping between the independent (inputs) and dependent (outputs) variables and predict the outputs. FF networks consist of a series of connected layers. The first layer is connected to the network input. Each subsequent layer is connected to the layer above it via the previous layer's connection. The output of the network is produced by the final layer, as shown in Figure 1. The network is simpler than other recurrent networks and can be used efficiently in pattern recognition. The network does not have feedback, so the output of each layer does not affect the same layer. In this study, a 3-hidden layer network with 20–20–20 neurons was considered with tansig as the transfer function and purelin as the output layer activation function.

Fig. 1. Feedforward network.

B. Cascaded Forward Backpropagation Network

The CFBP network model includes a connection from the input and every previous layer to the following layers, as shown in Figure 2. This network can accommodate the nonlinear relationship between input and output without eliminating their linear relationship. A 3-hidden layer network with 20–20–20 neurons was considered, where tansig was considered as the transfer and the output layer activation function, as it provided better results than other combinations.

C. Elman Backpropagation Network

The EBP network is a two-layer backpropagation network where a recurrent connection exists from the output of the hidden layer to its input with a tap delay. The recurrent connection allows the network to both detect and generate

time-varying patterns, as shown in Figure 3. In this study, a 3-hidden layer network with 20–20–20 neurons per layer was considered, where tansig is considered as both the transfer and the output layer activation function, as it provided better results than other combinations.

Fig. 2. Cascaded Forward Backpropagation Network.

Fig. 3. Elman backpropagation network.

III. PROPOSED MODEL AND INPUT-OUTPUT DATASET

A. The Proposed Model

Performance analysis was based on the prediction of heating and cooling loads in a residential building using hybrid neural networks. Initially, three different ANNs were trained, tested, and validated by considering 10-fold cross-validation. Then, a sequential combination of ANNs was performed to model hybrid networks. The output generated by an input from the input training pattern was then compared with the targeted output, aiming to minimize the error function, as shown in (1):

$$\min(E) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^u \|b_i - t_i\|^2 \quad (1)$$

where u is the number of sets of the training ordered pairs, which depends on the number of samples being taken, b_i is the network output, t_i is the target output, and E is the error function.

B. Input-Output Database

The proposed method was experimentally validated using a dataset collected from the UCI machine learning repository [6, 11]. The Ecotect software was used to simulate 12 distinct building shapes and generate 768 possible building shapes. Relative compactness, surface area, wall area, roof area, overall height, orientation, glazing area, and glazing area distribution ($X1, \dots, X8$) were the input variables of the dataset, and heating and cooling loads ($Y1$ and $Y2$) were the output variables. More information on the simulation experiments can be found in [6]. The output variables have a substantial correlation with the first five input variables in the examined dataset. As the volumes of the buildings are assumed to be constant, the values of $X1$ (relative compactness) and $X2$ (surface area) are inversely proportional. The input variables $X4$ (roof area) and $X5$ (height) are highly correlated. The correlation coefficient (-0.937) shows that these two variables are roughly inversely proportional.

IV. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF THE ANN MODEL

The trainlm algorithm was used for training. Tansig was considered as the output layer activation function for the CFBP and the EBP networks, as it provided smaller errors for these two networks. Similarly, purelin was considered as the output layer activation function for the FF network. The comparative analysis was obtained by changing the performance goal and learning rate in a step-by-step manner. The weight initialization with arbitrary values and bias updates was performed. The accuracy of these models was measured by the MAE, MSE, and MRE performance indicators:

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - x_i|}{n} \quad (2)$$

$$MSE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - x_i|^2}{n} \quad (3)$$

$$MRE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - x_i|}{nx_i} \quad (4)$$

where y_i is the predicted value, x_i is the true value, and n is the number of samples.

Performance analysis was conducted on these three networks. Three hidden layers were used in all networks, with 20 neurons in each layer. The trainlm function updates weights and biases as per Levenberg-Marquardt optimization and is the fastest backpropagation algorithm. Therefore, the trainlm was used as a common training algorithm for all networks. The performance goal was set to 10e-5, and the learning rate was taken as 0.01 for all three networks. Analysis was conducted based on MAE, MSE, and MRE performance evaluators. As purelin is a linear transfer function that gave an accurate result in the FF network, it was used as an output layer activation function in FF. Similarly, as tansig is a hyperbolic tangent sigmoid transfer function, and is preferable to be used where speed is important, it was used as the output layer activation function for both CFBP and EBP. The behaviors of all three networks are shown in Table I. Then among all CFBP networks with 20-20-20-2 neurons, the tansig-tansig-tansig-tansig transfer function was chosen as the optimal network with fewer errors.

TABLE I. PERFORMANCE BY VARYING NEURAL NETWORKS

ANN	Heating load			Cooling load		
	MAE	MSE	MRE	MAE	MSE	MRE
FF	0.1248	0.033	0.0075	0.1686	0.0611	0.0087
CFBP	0.1023	0.0326	0.0058	0.1406	0.0473	0.0072
EBP	0.2023	0.0819	0.0106	0.2471	0.1193	0.0117

V. HYBRID MODEL PERFORMANCE CALCULATION

A hybrid ANN is a valuable learning tool where numerous ANNs are collaboratively used to solve a problem and improve the predicted output of a sequential data set. MAE, MSE, and MRE were used as the performance indicators for each model in order to calculate the best hybrid configuration. Performance indicators were used to select the best algorithm. In this study, a hybrid intelligent model was designed by combining two of the proposed models, which were efficient for network analysis. Two of the mentioned algorithms were considered for

each combination. As in the performance analysis of the ANNs, the best results were obtained with 20-20-20-2 neurons, tansig-tansig-tansig-purelin transfer function, trainlm training algorithm, 10e-7 performance goal, and learning rate of 0.01 for the FF network. The best result for the CFBP network was achieved by using 20-20-20-2 neurons, tansig-tansig-tansig-tansig transfer function, trainlm training algorithm, 10e-7 performance goal, and learning rate of 0.01. Similarly, the best result for the EBP network was achieved using 20-20-20-2 neurons, tansig-tansig-tansig-tansig transfer function, trainlm training algorithm, 10e-7 performance goal, and learning rate of 0.01. The block diagram of the hybrid network is shown in Figure 4, and the flow chart of the hybridization is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the hybrid network.

Fig. 5. Flowchart of the hybridization of the neural network.

Six different combinations were considered as hybrid networks: FF and CFBP, FF and EBP, EBP and FF, EBP and CFBP, CFBP and FF, and CFBP and EBP.

VI. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The performance analysis of these hybrid networks is shown in Table II. It can be observed that the best results were achieved in the FF and CFBP hybrid network, with 0.0466 and 0.0797 for MAE in HL and CL, 0.0071 and 0.0166 for MSE in HL and CL, and 0.0031 and 0.0039 MRE in HL and CL respectively. In this network, the computational time was also very smaller (28s). Its error plot is shown in Figure 6 and the variation between target and actual values is shown in Figure 7. The variation between the target and the actual output of the FF and CFBP hybrid network for 768 sample numbers was very low. This signifies achievements of least error by this hybrid network compared to the others.

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF HYBRID MODELS

Hybrid neural network	Heating load			Cooling load			Time (s)
	MAE	MSE	MRE	MAE	MSE	MRE	
FF and CFBP	0.0466	0.0071	0.0031	0.0797	0.0166	0.0039	28
FF and EBP	0.1097	0.0281	0.0067	0.0775	0.0153	0.0040	100
EBP and FF	0.1002	0.0287	0.0051	0.0932	0.0229	0.0038	172
EBP and CFBP	0.0834	0.0227	0.0046	0.0757	0.0184	0.0035	186
CFBP and FF	0.0202	0.0009	0.0010	0.1368	0.0277	0.0048	146
CFBP and EBP	0.1052	0.0244	0.0076	0.0663	0.0102	0.0032	196

Fig. 6. Error plots for: (a) heating load, (b) cooling load.

Fig. 7. Target vs actual outputs: (a) heating load, (b) cooling load.

VII. COMPARISON WITH OTHER METHODS

The proposed method was also compared with other methods. Different performance evaluators like MAE, MSE, and MRE were considered for error analysis. In [6], Iteratively Reweighted Least Squares (IRLS) and Random Forests (RF) were used for the prediction of heating and cooling loads. It was found that MAE, MSE, and MRE for the HL using IRLS were 2.14, 9.87, 10.09, and using RF were 0.51, 1.03, and 9.41 respectively, while the MAE, MSE, and MRE for CL using IRLS were 2.21, 11.46, 2.18, and using RF were 1.42, 6.59, 4.62. SVR and MLP were implemented with the same data in [14] to predict the heating and cooling loads, using MAE and MSE as performance evaluators. The results were found to be 0.778, 0.7838 in SVR and 0.4118, 0.2335 in MLP for HL, and 1.4762, 3.024 in SVR and 2.0973, 6.896 in MLP for CL. In [15], the backpropagation method achieved MAE, MSE, and MRE of 0.1000, 0.0335, and 0.0053 for HL, and 0.1254, 0.763, and 0.0062 for CL. The error analysis is shown in Table III. It can be observed that the proposed hybrid FF and CFBP method improved MAE, MSE, and MRE for both heating and cooling loads, compared to the above-mentioned methods.

TABLE III. COMPARISON WITH OTHER METHODS

Proposed methods	MAE		MSE		MRE	
	HL	CL	HL	CL	HL	CL
IRLS [6]	2.14	2.21	9.87	11.46	10.09	2.18
RF [6]	0.51	1.42	1.03	6.59	9.41	4.62
SVR [14]	0.778	1.4762	0.7838	3.024	-	-
MLP [14]	0.4118	2.0973	0.2335	6.896	-	-
Back-propagation [15]	0.1000	0.1254	0.0335	0.763	0.0053	0.0062
FF and CFBP	0.0466	0.0797	0.0071	0.0166	0.0031	0.0039

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this study, a hybrid ANN was proposed to estimate the consumption of HVAC loads in a residential building for an eight-input dataset with 768 building samples. The hybrid model of Feed-Forward and Cascaded Forward Back Propagation (FF and CFBP) gave mean absolute errors of 0.0466 and 0.0797, mean square errors of 0.0071 and 0.0166, mean relative errors of 0.0031 and 0.0039 for heating and cooling loads respectively. The results showed that the suggested hybrid neural network had the lowest statistical errors and the best prediction performance. The difficulty of collecting actual building energy datasets is a drawback in this field of building efficiency enhancement. The use of real-world data by considering weather parameters like temperature, global solar radiation, etc, can give better results in future studies.

REFERENCES

- [1] "IEA – International Energy Agency," *IEA*. <https://www.iea.org>.
- [2] A. Yezioro, B. Dong, and F. Leite, "An applied artificial intelligence approach towards assessing building performance simulation tools," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 612–620, Jan. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2007.04.014>.
- [3] T. Catalina, J. Virgone, and E. Blanco, "Development and validation of regression models to predict monthly heating demand for residential buildings," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 40, no. 10, pp. 1825–1832, Jan. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2008.04.001>.
- [4] B. Dong, C. Cao, and S. E. Lee, "Applying support vector machines to predict building energy consumption in tropical region," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 37, no. 5, pp. 545–553, May 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2004.09.009>.
- [5] Q. Li, Q. Meng, J. Cai, H. Yoshino, and A. Mochida, "Applying support vector machine to predict hourly cooling load in the building," *Applied Energy*, vol. 86, no. 10, pp. 2249–2256, Oct. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2008.11.035>.
- [6] A. Tsanas and A. Xifara, "Accurate quantitative estimation of energy performance of residential buildings using statistical machine learning tools," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 49, pp. 560–567, Jun. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2012.03.003>.
- [7] E. A. Al-Ammar, N. H. Malik, and M. Usman, "Application of using Hybrid Renewable Energy in Saudi Arabia," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 84–89, Aug. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.33>.
- [8] B. Zahran, "Using Neural Networks to Predict the Hardness of Aluminum Alloys," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 757–759, Feb. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.529>.
- [9] S. N. Truong, "A Low-cost Artificial Neural Network Model for Raspberry Pi," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5466–5469, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3357>.
- [10] R. Yao, B. Li, and K. Steemers, "Energy policy and standard for built environment in China," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 30, no. 13, pp. 1973–1988, Oct. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2005.01.013>.
- [11] J.-S. Chou and D.-K. Bui, "Modeling heating and cooling loads by artificial intelligence for energy-efficient building design," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 82, pp. 437–446, Oct. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2014.07.036>.
- [12] Y. Sonmez, U. Guvenc, H. T. Kahraman, and C. Yilmaz, "A comparative study on novel machine learning algorithms for estimation of energy performance of residential buildings," in *2015 3rd International Istanbul Smart Grid Congress and Fair (ICSG)*, Istanbul, Turkey, Apr. 2015, pp. 1–7, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SGCF.2015.7354915>.
- [13] W. Qiao and Z. Yang, "Modified Dolphin Swarm Algorithm Based on Chaotic Maps for Solving High-Dimensional Function Optimization Problems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 110472–110486, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2931910>.
- [14] A. Moradzadeh, A. Mansour-Saatloo, B. Mohammadi-Ivatloo, and A. Anvari-Moghaddam, "Performance Evaluation of Two Machine Learning Techniques in Heating and Cooling Loads Forecasting of Residential Buildings," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 11, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 3829, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10113829>.
- [15] S. Das, A. Swetapadma, C. Panigrahi, and A. Y. Abdelaziz, "Improved Method for Approximation of Heating and Cooling Load in Urban Buildings for Energy Performance Enhancement," *Electric Power Components and Systems*, vol. 48, no. 4–5, pp. 436–446, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15325008.2020.1793838>.